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YERITH-ERP-9.0 Software System Product Sheet

YERITH-ERP-9.0 is an **ERP software system** with 6 user roles, and types:

1. « Administrator »
2. « Business manager »
3. « Cashier »
4. « Seller »
5. « ASSET – stock manager »
6. « Storekeeper ».

YERITH-ERP-9.0 **features:**

1. Runtime monitoring verification with "yerith_qvge (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>)";
2. alerts over stock quantity, and, time period;
3. BA-Business Analytics (business dashboard);
4. HR (human resources) — ALSO with automated and / or manual payment handling for employees; customer relationship management (CRM), budget line management;
5. sale management (e.g. point of sale);
6. ASSET – stock management (e.g. check in);
7. user, and role administration;
8. wild-char searches with character %.

YERITH-ERP-9.0 **is:**

1. easier, and, intuitive, in its use
2. lighter, and, faster, in memory usage
3. multi sites.

YERITH-ERP-9.0's runtime memory usage test is realized using run-time software analysis tool **valgrind**.

GENERAL SOURCE CODE QUALITY CONTROL is realized with compile-time code analysis tool **Cppcheck**.

Business manager's main window

BUSINESS workflow of YERITH-ERP-9.0

OPERATIONS

Point of Sale Hardware

- ✓ Barcode scanner
- ✓ Thermal printer, etc.

Database Management Systems

- ✓ mariadb 10.5.

Operating Systems

- ✓ Debian-Linux 11; 12.

Advantages of YERITH–ERP–9.0 Compared to Other Top ERP systems

YERITH–ERP–9.0 is a very easy to use ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) system because of its characteristics:

1. separate views for each user role
2. complete and fundamental training in 8 days
3. easy to use graphical user interface (GUI)
4. no college or university training needed
5. no formal business training needed
6. *no internet connection needed.*
7. *EASIER business management overseeing over web–browser based solutions (e.g. : "Contr–ALL" (<https://www.contrall.online>), etc.)*

Table 1 pictures the 'fully–featured–ness', 'effectiveness', & 'simplicity' of YERITH–ERP–9.0, compared to other top ERP systems like for instance "Contr–ALL", "Sage Gescom i7", and "SAP Business One".

Figure 1: Asset / Stock Listing Window

Table 1: Comparison between YERITH–ERP–9.0 and 3 top tier–1 ERP systems

FEATURES	YERITH–ERP–9.0 (≈ 10 years old)	Contr–ALL (≈ 7 years old)	Sage Gescom i7 (≈ 40 years old)	SAP Business One (≈ 40 years old)
★ HR & Accounting full featured ERP	YES	NO	YES	YES
★ runtime monitoring checks enabled	YES (Yri–Db–Runtime–Verif)	NO	YES	YES
★ Documentation online available fully	YES (Here For Instance) (https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724)	NO	NO	NO
separate views per user role	YES	YES	YES	YES
complete training (or solution)	at least 4 weeks	at least 3 weeks	at least 2 months	at least 3 months
★ difficulty in navigation	easy	easy	very difficult	very difficult
usage language in software	easy everyday English	simple	simple	technical
advanced marketing knowledge	no	no	useful	useful
★ Availability on platforms (Hardware)	PC, Tablet	PC, Tablet, Smartphone	PC, Tablet	PC, Tablet
★ web–online interface	not yet	yes, fully web available interface	not yet	not yet
★ internet connection	optional	useful (not at all internet means no access to any of your business resources.)	optional	optional

OPERATIONS

Runtime MONITORING Verification

✓ YERITH_QVGE

Point of Sale Hardware

- ✓ Barcode scanner
- ✓ Thermal printer, etc.

Operating Systems

- ✓ Debian–Linux 11; 13.

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YERITH-ERP-9.0 Point Of Sale Recommended Hardware

1 Barcode Scanner

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of barcode scanner: "Xfox FJ-5 USB Plug and Play Automatic Barcode Scanner" (approx. 17€).

Bar-code Scanner

2 Thermal Printer

ALL EPSON THERMAL PRINTERS !

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of thermal printer: "Epson TM T20ii Point of Sale Thermal Printer" (approx. 100€).

Thermal Printer

3 Cash Drawer

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of cash drawer: "HP QT457AT" (approx. 90€).

Cash Drawer

4 Touch Screen Monitor

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of touch screen monitor: "ASUS 15.6" LCD Monitor (VT168H)" (approx. 155€).

Touchscreen Monitor

5 Computer

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of desktop computer: "Lenovo Thinkcentre M720 Small Form Factor (SFF)" (approx. 450€).

Computer

6 Multi User Terminal Computer

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of multi user terminal computer: "NC-300 Multi User Terminal Computer" (approx. 112€).

Multi User Terminal Computer

✓ **PECULIARITIES IN CERTAIN COUNTRIES AND/OR REGIONS** USAGE OF POINT-OF-SALE (THERMAL) PRINTERS REQUIRES ALSO ACQUISITION OF A GOVERNMENT-SOLD DEVICE FOR RECORDING AND CERTIFYING ALL FINANCIAL TRANSACTIONS BETWEEN THE THERMAL PRINTERS AND/OR YERITH-ERP-9.0 (e.g.: GERMANY, CANADA, etc.).

Table 2.1: Devices and hardware useful for YERITH-ERP-3.0.

Figure 2.1: Computer (MANDATORY)

Figure 2.2: Touchscreen Monitor (MANDATORY)

Figure 2.3: Cash Drawer (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.4: "Point of Sale Thermal Printer" (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.5: Bar-code Scanner (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.6: 1 Network Router (MANDATORY)

Figure 2.7: Numeric Tablet (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.8: "2 in 1 Computer" (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.9: Multi User Terminal Computer (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.10: Hardware components of Multi-User Terminal Computer NC-300 (at <https://www.savingology.com>): images are taken from SavingOlogy.com.

Figure 2.11: NC-300 PCI card

Figure 2.12: NC-300 terminals

Information Brochure of the ERP software system YERITH-ERP-9.0

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]"

Table 1: YERITH-ERP-9.0 functions-tasks, and associated users-roles.

Tasks	« Business manager »	« Seller »	« ASSET – stock manager »	« Storekeeper »	« Cashier »
create a department	✓				
insert 1 ASSET, stock, or service	✓	✓ (SERVICE)	✓ (ASSET / STOCK)		
delete ASSET, stock	✓				
view ASSET, stock	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
modify ASSET, stock	✓		✓		
transfer ASSET, stock	✓		✓	✓	
check-out ASSET, stock	✓		✓	✓	
modify ASSET, stock management strategy (e.g.: « FIFO », etc.)	✓	✓ (NO PERMANENT)	✓ (NO PERMANENT)		
point of sale	✓	✓			✓
view ASSET, stock transfers	✓		✓	✓	
purchase management	✓	✓	✓ (PARTIAL)		
supplier management	✓				
customer relationship management (CRM)	✓	✓ (PARTIAL)			
business dashboard	✓				
sale return	✓				
view sales information	✓	✓ (SELF)			

1 Developer Biography

Figure 1: Portrait of YERITH-nissi.

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]" is a CHRISTIAN BY FAITH, Cameroonian, born on September 16 1983 in DOUALA (LITTORAL region, CAMEROON).

Xavier has a "Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)" qualification from the **University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY** (May 25, 2007).

XAVIER NOUNDOU IS "A D.ENG. (DOCTOR OF ENGINEERING) / PHILOSOPHIAE DOCTOR (PH.D.)" from **THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO (ON, CANADA); DECEMBER 20, 2011!**

Xavier has following academic research and professional engineering contributions:

1. 'Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis For C using LLVM'
 1. source code in C++:
<https://github.com/sazzad114/saint>
<https://archive.org/download/yerith-saint-2021-MARCH-01/YERITH-SAINT-2021-MARCH-01.pdf>
 2. full text: [yerith-saint-2021-MARCH-01/YERITH-SAINT-2021-MARCH-01.pdf](https://archive.org/download/yerith-saint-2021-MARCH-01/YERITH-SAINT-2021-MARCH-01.pdf)
2. 'YERITH-ERP-3.0':
 1. source code in C++:
 - a. YERITH-ERP-9.0:
<https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0>
 - b. YERITH-ERP-9.0 SYSTEM DAEMON:
<https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon>
 - c. YR-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF:
<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>
 - d. YR_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF:
https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif
 2. full text (ongoing publication):
https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-pgi-compendium_202206/JH_NISSI_ERP_PGI_COMPENDIUM.pdf

2 Introduction

YERITH-ERP-9.0 is an **Enterprise Resource Planing** (ERP) software system.

Users of YERITH–ERP–9.0 could have the following roles:

1. « Administrator »
2. « Business manager »
3. « Cashier »
4. « Seller »
5. « ASSET – stock manager »
6. « Storekeeper ».

YERITH–ERP–9.0 allows for business management tasks (listed in Table 1), depending on user role, as follows:

1. create a department (e.g.: finance, asset, stock, etc.)
2. manage clients, and human resources, and suppliers
3. manage enterprise asset (e.g.: cars, etc.)
4. manage financial expenses WITH BUDGET LINES
5. manage inventory stock
6. manage sales
7. view business dashboards (across sites).

3 Potential Usages of YERITH–ERP–9.0

YERITH–ERP–9.0 potential usages are:

1. STOCK AND TRADE EXCHANGES MARKET PLACE
2. ENTERPRISE RESOURCE AND PLANING SOFTWARE for supermarkets and commercial stores
3. i.e. ANY NON GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATION, or GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATION.

4 Advantages of YERITH–ERP–9.0

1. YERITH–ERP–9.0 is 100% stable
2. YERITH–ERP–9.0 has an alert system with two types of alerts: alerts based on stock–quantity, and time–period alerts
3. users have the choice between small size receipts, and bigger size receipts ("A4")
4. YERITH–ERP–9.0 runs on the Linux operating system, because Linux is stable, performant, and less vulnerable to security breaches in comparison to other operating systems ('Windows 10')
5. YERITH–ERP–9.0 has an user interface "Sales" to view sale information (Figure 4), and thus enables users to make managerial decisions
6. YERITH–ERP–9.0 has an interface "Business dashboard" that generates financial accounting reports, from sale and payment information, to help managers to make "business decisions".

Yerith R&D

Yerith-erp-pgi-platiNum business Workflow

Figure 2: BUSINESS workflow of YERITH–ERP–9.0.

Figure 3: Runtime MONITORING DAEMON service.

5 RUNTIME MONITORING daemon service as a parallel unharmful sub-process

Figure 3 illustrates an emptied log error event screen of YRI_QVGE (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033>).

STARTING year 2024, I have introduced a free runtime monitoring daemon service for tracking SQL transaction errors at runtime and recovering automatically from these errors via execution of pre-defined SQL-queries.

- 1.) A scientific document published openly at ZENODO.ORG (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033>);
- 2.) THE OPEN-SOURCE FOSS (Free And OPEN SOURCE CODE SOFTWARE) location on the web–internet world-wide currently located at: Github.com (<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri-db-runtime-verif>).

6 Alert System

Users with roles « Administrator » or « Business manager » are the ones able to create alerts.

YERITH-ERP-9.0 allows its users to create two types of alerts:

1. alerts over stocks-quantities
2. alerts over time intervals (this helps for perissable articles and for sales discounts over a period of time).

6.1 Alerts over Stock-Quantity

An alert over a stock-quantity is a message that is sent to a pre-determined user whenever "pre-determined" stock-quantity (X) of a specific article-stock is reached.

For instance, Xavier (« Business manager ») could create an alert for stock "mango" that will be triggered whenever stock "mango" quantity reaches 100; An alert-message is sent to user John (« Storekeeper »).

6.2 Alerts over Time-Period

A time-period is defined by a starting-date and an ending-date (dates are from the "gregorian" calendar).

An alert over a time-period (T) is a message that is generated, sent to a pre-determined user, and kept within YERITH-ERP-9.0 from T's starting-date up to T's ending-date.

For example, an alert with a message has to be sent to Paul (« Cashier ») when the date of May 05th is reached. The alert message specifies that a rebate of 20% has to be applied on every sale of yoghurt 'trèsbon' during a time interval of 2 weeks.

7 Database Management System

YERITH-ERP-9.0 uses 'MariaDB' as the standard DBMS. 'MariaDB' is very stable, very performant, and free-software.

8 Conclusion

Figure 4: Sale-information window.

Figure 5: Point-of-sale window.

Figure 5 illustrates the window for selling articles.

Installation Guide for ERP Software System YERITH-ERP-9.0

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]"

VERSION: November 29, 2024

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Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Typography

Within this guide, all commands written in the following type setting:

`command`

are to be executed as "super user" ("root user").

1.2 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

1.2.1 SCREEN (computer Desktop)

YERITH-ERP-9.0 is best screen sized on a screen of 22 inch and higher !

1.2.2 RANDOM ACCESS MEMORY (RAM)

YERITH-ERP-9.0 could be used with a computer with a Random Access Memory (RAM) of about 512 Mb.

HOWEVER, FOR MAXIMUM PERFORMANCE, I RECOMMEND AT LEAST 2 GB OF RAM MEMORY !

1.3 Prerequisite Software

Table 1.1: Prerequisite software for installation of YERITH-ERP-9.0.

Software	Versions
Debian	11.1 (bullseye)
gdebi	0.9.5.7 + nmu5
mariadb-server	10.5.12-0 + deb11u1
mariadb-client	10.5.12-0 + deb11u1
Qt	5.15.2
Texlive	2020.20210202-3

1.4 Files Required for Installation Procedure

Table 1.2: Files required for installation of YERITH-ERP-9.0.

FILES
"yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-ENGLISH.deb"
"yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data-ENGLISH.deb"
"yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon.deb"

Table 1.2 illustrates files required for installing YERITH-ERP-9.0.

Chapter 2

AUTOMATED INSTALLATION with gdebi-gtk OR gdebi

Figure 2.1: Gdebi-gtk user graphical interface.

2.1 Installation of gdebi-gtk and gdebi

1. Open a "bash-terminal"
2. type following command:

```
apt -y install gdebi-gtk gdebi
```

2.2 Installation with gdebi-gtk

1. Open a "bash-terminal"
2. type following command:

```
gdebi-gtk yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-ENGLISH.deb
```

3. press button "Install Package"
4. repeat the previous command with files "**yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data-ENGLISH.deb**" and "**yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon.deb**" respectively.

2.3 Installation with gdebi

1. Open a "bash-terminal"
2. type following command:

```
gdebi -n yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-ENGLISH.deb
```

3. repeat the previous command with files "**yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data-ENGLISH.deb**" and "**yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon.deb**" respectively.

Chapter 3

MANUAL Installation Procedure Of YERITH-ERP-9.0 – DBMS

3.1 INSTALLATION STEPS OF mariadb-server (ON REMOTE COMPUTER-SERVER)

Following steps have to be followed in order to have a well functioning installation of YERITH-ERP-9.0 – DBMS:

1. install database software mariadb-server (ON REMOTE COMPUTER-SERVER)
2. modify IF REQUIRED MYSQL CONFIGURATION FILE '/etc/mysql/mariadb.conf.d/50-server.cnf' (ON REMOTE COMPUTER-SERVER).

3.2 Installation of mariadb-server (ON REMOTE COMPUTER-SERVER)

1. Open a "bash-terminal"
2. type following command:

```
apt -y install mariadb-server mariadb-client
```

3.3 Modify MYSQL CONFIGURATION FILE '/etc/mysql/mariadb.conf.d/50-server.cnf'

APPLY THE FOLLOWING INSTRUCTIONS ONLY IF YOU REQUIRE YOUR YERITH-ERP-9.0 – DBMS to be on a REMOTE COMPUTER-SERVER DIFFERENT FROM 'localhost'!

1. MODIFY INLINE 'bind-address = 127.0.0.1' TO 'bind-address =YE.YF.YG.YH' WHERE 'YE.YF.YG.YH' REPRESENTS PUBLIC IP ADDRESS OF LOCAL DBMS-COMPUTER
2. this step requires a reboot of DBMS-mariadb-server:

```
service mariadb restart
```


Chapter 4

MANUAL Installation Procedure Of YERITH-ERP-9.0

4.1 INSTALLATION STEPS OF YERITH-ERP-9.0

Following steps have to be followed in order to have a well functioning installation of YERITH-ERP-9.0:

1. install gdebi and expect software
2. install YERITH-ERP-9.0 (Qt and Texlive are automatically installed)
3. modify configuration file 'yerith-erp-3-0.properties' to access YERITH-ERP-9.0 – DBMS.

4.2 Installation of gdebi and expect

1. Open a "bash-terminal"
2. type following command:

```
apt -y install gdebi expect
```

4.3 Installation of Qt, Texlive, and of YERITH-ERP-9.0

1. Open a "bash-terminal"

2. type command:

```
gdebi -n yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data-ENGLISH.deb
```

3. then type command (INSTALLS ALERT AND SAVE-BACKUP SYSTEM daemon):

```
gdebi -n yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon.deb
```

4. then finally type command:

```
gdebi -n yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-ENGLISH.deb
```

This command automatically installs Qt, and Texlive.

4.4 Sample 2 computers store

Figure 4.1: Sample 2 computers store.

4.5 Sample decentralized multi sites supermarket

Figure 4.2: Sample decentralized multi sites supermarket.

4.6 **Modify (IF REQUIRED) CONFIGURATION FILE 'yerith-erp-3-0.properties' to access YERITH-ERP-9.0 – DBMS**

APPLY THE FOLLOWING INSTRUCTIONS ONLY IF YOU REQUIRE YOUR YERITH-ERP-9.0 – DBMS to be on a REMOTE COMPUTER-SERVER DIFFERENT FROM 'localhost'!

1. FILE 'YERITH-ERP-3-0.PROPERTIES' IS LOCATED AT LOCAL DRIVE:
'/opt/yerith-erp-3-0-standalone-configurations-data'
2. MODIFY INLINE 'db_ip_address=localhost' TO 'db_ip_address=YE.YF.YG.YH' WHERE 'YE.YF.YG.YH' REPRESENTS REMOTE COMPUTER-SERVER-DBMS IP ADDRESS.

Appendix A

Standard Administrative User Account 'admin'

After [YERITH–ERP–9.0](#) successful installation, the application is accessible using a standard administrative user account with the following credentials:

1. user name: **admin**
2. user password: **admin1**

This administrative user account could be modified at your wish.

Appendix B

HOW TO CONFIGURE A POINT-OF-SALE THERMAL PRINTER

Appendix C

PREFERENCE FILES FOR A USER OF YERITH-ERP-9.0

Appendix D

YERITH-ERP-9.0 CONFIGURATION FILES

Appendix E

how to uninstall 'YERITH-ERP-9.0'

1. Open a "bash-terminal"
2. type command:

```
apt -y --purge remove yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-english
```

3. FINALLY, type command:

```
apt -y --purge remove yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data-english
```


Appendix F

how to uninstall 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON'

1. Open a "bash-terminal"
2. type command:

```
apt -y --purge remove yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon
```

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Information Brochure of the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE)

Xavier Noubbissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]
CONTACT: YERITH.XAVIER@gmail.com

Table 1: EQUIVALENCES

scientific literature	engineering acronym
PRE	BEFORE
POST	AFTER
A TRACE	AN EVENT LOG
A FINAL STATE	AN ERROR STATE

Figure 1: A motivating example, as previous bug found in YERITH-ERP-9.0.

$Q0 := NOT_IN_BEFORE(YRI_ASSET, department.department_name).$
 $Q1 := IN_AFTER(YRI_ASSET, stocks.department_name).$

Figure 2: A SAMPLE state diagram mealy machine file. KEYWORDS belonging both to 'engineering (ERROR_STATE)', and 'science (START_STATE)' can be intermingled in the same SDMM specification file.

1. yr_sd_mealy_automaton_spec yr_missing_department_NO_DELETE
2. {
3. START_STATE(d):NOT_IN_BEFORE(YRI_ASSET, department.department_name)
4. -> [in_sql_event_log('DELETE.department.YRI_ASSET', STATE(d))] / 'SELECT.department' ->
5. ERROR_STATE(e): IN_AFTER(YRI_ASSET, stocks.department_name).
6. }

Figure 3: A SCREENSHOT OF YERITH_QVGE.

Figure 4: A SCREENSHOT OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL EVENT LOG.

1 Developer Biography

Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.] is a CHRISTIAN BY FAITH, Cameroonian, born on September 16 1983 in DOUALA (LITTORAL region, CAMEROON). Xavier has a "Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)" qualification from the **University of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY** (May 25, 2007). XAVIER NOUNDOU IS A "Dr.-Ing. : Doctor of Engineering (PhD equivalent – Computer Software Verification & Analysis)" from **THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO (ON, CANADA)**; DECEMBER 20, 2011!

Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.] has worked together with **Pr. Prof. Dr. habil. Jan Peleska**, at AGBS–University of Bremen, GERMANY; and 2 years later at WatForm–University of Waterloo, ON, Canada, with **Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick Lam**.

Xavier could successfully work with **Dr. Frank Tip** at The University of Waterloo (Waterloo, ON, Canada) on his first JAVA dynamic program analysis.

Xavier also had the great opportunity through **Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Marcel Mitran** and **Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick Lam**; to work as a graduate intern in Markham (Toronto, ON, CANADA) at IBM TORONTO SOFTWARE LABORATORY; in the JAVA–J9 Just–In–Time Compiler Optimization Team, together with **Vijay Sundaresan, M.Sc. (McGill University, QC, Canada)**.

Xavier has following academic and professional engineering research contributions:

1. 'Statistical test case generation for reactive systems' at RTT-MBT at VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH (<https://www.verified.de>).

2. 'Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis For C using LLVM':

1. source code in C++:
<https://www.github.com/sazzad114/saint>
2. full text:
<https://zenodo.org/record/8051293>

3. 'YERITH-ERP-3.0':

1. source code in C++:
 - a. YERITH-ERP-9.0:
<https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0>
 - b. YERITH-ERP-9.0 SYSTEM DAEMON:
<https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon>

2. full text (ongoing publication):
<https://zenodo.org/record/8052724>

¹https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang

²<https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>

2 Introduction

Figure 5: SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

YERITH_QVGE is a CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) design tool to generate "domain-specific language (DSL) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG"¹ files, to be inputted into the "compiler YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP", so to generate C++ files for the runtime verifier tester "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"² that allows for manual verification of SQL correctness properties of Graphical User Interface (GUI) software.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF inputs SQL correctness properties expressed using the formalism state diagram mealy machine (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG). Figure 5 illustrates a software system architecture of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, together with the monitored program under analysis. The Free Open Source Code Software (FOSS) tool-chain of development testing is located as follows for free, EXCEPT for "YERITH_QVGE" that is a Closed Source Code Software (CSCS):

- COMPILER (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP):
https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang
- RUNTIME VERIFIER TESTER (i.e.: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF):
<https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>
- state diagram mealy machine UNIT TESTS CODE (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS):
https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS
- state diagram mealy machine (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG):
https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif

3 YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) Project Dependency

Table 2: YERITH_QVGE Design and Testing System Dependencies

PROJECT	Required Library
1) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG	
2) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP	1)
3) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS	1)
4) YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	2)

Table 2 illustrates for each library project, which others it depends on.

3. Software design properties with SQL
4. Software design properties including event sequences over different layers of software system architecture
5. Class diagram with sequence diagram.

5 Advantages of YERITH_QVGE

Figure 6: YERITH_QVGE software library dependencies.

Figure 6 show a diagram overview of the presentation in Table 2. The step of the unit tests is colored in gray because it is only for developers of YERITH_QVGE intended.

4 Potential Uses of YERITH_QVGE

YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) could be used for the following automatic generation, analysis, verification, and validation tasks:

1. Automatic generation of runtime monitoring module program to prove whether a test procedure, automated, or not, is correct with regards to a test and / or design STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE.

In effect, let the test execution be runtime monitored to watch whether accepting error states would be found.

For instance, Junit testing environment could automatically integrate an automatically generated runtime monitor infrastructure for unit testing.

2. Automatic generation of runtime monitoring module program for any software that can emit Dbus messages.

Such runtime monitoring modules are for interest for special LTL model checking properties that cannot get a definite answer through use of a conventional model checker.

Figure 7: Workflow.

A sample state diagram mealy machine is shown in Figure 2.

WITH manual drawing of SQL CORRECTNESS PROPERTY MODEL, you are freed from manually writing "state diagram mealy machine text files" that could be tedious and lengthy. Also, editing state diagram mealy machine files manually could be more error-prone than letting a compiler (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP) do it for you.

6 Conclusion

YERITH_QVGE costs only 2,500 EUROS. WE ONLY SUPPORT DEBIAN-LINUX (<https://www.debian.org>).

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state diagram mealy machine, 2

CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering), 2

domain-specific language (DSL), 2

runtime verifier tester, 2

SQL correctness properties, 2

User's Cheat Sheet for YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF : A C++ Functional Library for Specifying "SDMM" (State Diagram Mealy Machine)

AUTHOR: Xavier Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]
Contact: YERITH.xavier@gmail.com

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Table 1: STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE SPECIFICATION KEYWORDS IN YERITH_QVGE. 'AUTO' KEYWORDS SPECIFIES ALSO SQL QUERY FOR GOING OUT AUTOMATICALLY FROM A FAIL (FORBIDDEN) STATE. ("SEE SECTION ??.")

N°	scientific keywords	engineering keywords
1.	in_set_trace	in_sql_event_log
2.	not_in_set_trace	not_in_sql_event_log
3.	recovery_sql_query	recovery_sql_query
4.	STATE	STATE
5.	START_STATE	BEGIN_STATE
6.	FINAL_STATE ("FINAL_STATE_AUTO")	END_STATE ("END_STATE_AUTO") / ERROR_STATE ("ERROR_STATE_AUTO")
7.	IN_PRE	IN_BEFORE
8.	IN_POST	IN_AFTER
9.	IN_POST_NOP	N/A
10.	NOT_IN_PRE	NOT_IN_BEFORE
11.	NOT_IN_POST	NOT_IN_BEFORE
12.	NOT_IN_POST_NOP	N/A

Figure 1: A motivating example, as previous bug found in YERITH-ERP-9.0.

$Q_0 := \text{NOT_IN_BEFORE}(\text{YRI_ASSET}, \text{department.department_name})$; $Q_1 := \text{IN_AFTER}(\text{YRI_ASSET}, \text{stocks.department_name})$.

Figure 2: YERITH-ERP-9.0 administration section displaying departments ($\neg Q_0$).

Figure 3: YERITH-ERP-9.0 stock asset window listing some assets (Q_1).

Figure 4: A SAMPLE state diagram mealy machine file. KEYWORDS belonging both to 'engineering ("ERROR_STATE_AUTO")', and 'science (START_STATE)' can be intermingled in the same SDMM specification file.

```

1. yr_sd_mealy_automaton_spec yr_missing_department_NO_DELETE
2. {
3.   START_STATE (d) : NOT_IN_BEFORE (YRI_ASSET, department.department_name)
4.   -> [in_sql_event_log ('DELETE.department.YRI_ASSET', STATE (d)) ] / 'SELECT.department' ->
5.     ERROR_STATE (e) : IN_AFTER (YRI_ASSET, stocks.department_name) .
6. }
  
```

Figure 5: SAMPLE INTERNET-RELATED USE CASE SCENARIO OF "SDMM".

Listing 1: Sample real world "C++" code as opposed to PSEUDO-CODE "C++" code; as modified by a developer after automatic generation of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

```

1  bool YERITH_QVGE_sample_PAPER_extended_version_PROPERTY::DO_VERIFY_AND_or_CHECK_tL_PROPERTY(
2  QString sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number,
3  uint sql_record_qty_MODIFIED,
4  YRI_CPP_UTILS::SQL_CONSTANT_IDENTIFIER cur_SQL_command)
5  {
6  QStringList sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number_LIST = sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number.split(";", Qt::KeepEmptyParts);
7  QString sql_table_name = sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number_LIST.at(0);
8  QString CPP_FILE_NAME = sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number_LIST.at(1);
9  QString cpp_line_number = sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number_LIST.at(2);
10
11  switch(cur_SQL_command)
12  {
13  case YRI_CPP_UTILS::INSERT:
14      break;
15
16  case YRI_CPP_UTILS::SELECT:
17      if (YRI_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF_Utils::isEqualsCaseInsensitive(sql_table_name, "departements_produits")) {
18          return YRI_SQL_SELECT_departements_produits();
19      }
20      break;
21
22  case YRI_CPP_UTILS::UPDATE:
23      break;
24
25  case YRI_CPP_UTILS::DELETE:
26      break;
27
28  default:
29      break;
30  }
31
32  return false;
33  }
    
```

Figure 7: A SCREENSHOT OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL EVENT LOG.

Figure 6: A SCREENSHOT OF YERITH_QVGE.

1 Motivation for SDMM's Runtime Monitoring Verification Library "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF"

1.1 A Sample Use-Case Scenario of "SDMM"

1.2 WHY DO I NEED FORMAL METHODS

I HAVE interest in developing mathematical definitions and demonstrations for formal methods for following reasons :

1. any developer and / or BSC student can write code that compiles, run, and has JUnit classes testing code that passes.

In effect, JUnit tests only stipulates that a running program does what a programmer had in intent; BUT not by any means exactly what a stakeholder needed.

2. BUT what demonstrates that the written and running program does what the primordial first intent of the developer and of his stakeholders was !?
3. THIS is exactly what formal methods (mathematics for computer science oriented towards testing and verifying; making sure, that a software program does what its intent is) does.

1.2.1 "C++ library YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" : Expressing of sequencing of actions in time (temporal usage rules for system safety)

Specifying temporal usage rules for system safety is primordial for ensuring a proper quality assurance of a system that is aimed to be more productive and safer in its usage by users, and / or maintainers.

THIS is why we created the C++ library YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF. "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" is an acronym for **YERITH_State_Diagram_Runtime_Verification**.

1.3 Comparison with Unit Testing

1.3.1 Unit Testing

UNIT TESTING [Zel20]; [Nou09] (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052444>) consists in creating System Under Test program execution sequences with certain data & certain test criteria so to assert following statements over a program under test :

1. a specific input data in a unit test module method generates a pre-defined certain output data; Thus developers must provide test input data for each test case runtime execution.

UNIT TESTING is a kind of what is called :

- o **White-box testing** [Zel20, MYE20]; meaning a developer knows intrinsics (inside details) of the system-software under test;
 - ⇒ Another kind of testing is called **BLACK-box testing** [Zel20, MYE20]; meaning a developer doesn't need any inside source code details knowledge of the system-software under test.

Sample unit testing frameworks are for instance :

- a) **JUnit testing framework** (<https://www.junit.org>) for JAVA programs;

- b) **Qt Test testing framework** (<https://doc.qt.io/qt-5>) for Qt Graphical User Interface programs;

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF [NN25] (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) is a simpler and more offering alternative; especially for software integrating testing (See Subsubsection 1.3.3)!

However, it is more appropriate for people with a strong mathematical background (set algebra & formal methods);

- c) **CppUnit testing framework** (<https://freedesktop.org/wiki/Software/cppunit>) for C++ software.

1.3.2 Automated Unit Testing

Automated Unit Testing consists in automatically generating a System Under Test program execution sequences with certain data & certain test criteria so to assert following statements over a program under test :

1. a specific input data in a unit test module method generates a pre-defined certain output data; Thus developers receive automatically test data & test cases for each test case runtime execution.

Such generator systems like for example **RT-Tester MBT** (<https://www.verified.de/products/model-based-testing>) from "Verified System International GmbH" (<https://www.verified.de>), generally require a specification of the software and / or program under test; So to be able to perform the automatic code source generation for the Embedded Unit Tester "RT-Tester MBT (Model Based Testing)".

RT-Tester MBT, for example, inputs a "David Harel Statechart" (See Subsubsection 1.6.1) specification as for instance generated by a plug-in for "Borland Together 6", delivered as a by-product by "Verified System International GmbH".

A detailed algorithm and function description of **RT-Tester MBT** could be found in Subsection 1.6 !

1.3.3 Runtime Monitoring Verification

RUNTIME MONITORING Verification with state diagram mealy machine on the other side consists in :

1. specifying a wrong system under test program logical sequence using a mealy automaton as defined for instance in Subsection 1.5;
2. it is possible to specify conditions that trigger event between SDMM states : **guarded condition**; A guarded condition is placed between squared brackets ("**guarded_condition**").

Example :

```
->[in_sql_event_log('guardedevent', STATE(d))] / 'event1' ->
```

The previous example guarded condition (**in_sql_event_log('guardedevent', STATE(d))**) transition means that : 'event1' occurs only if event 'guardedevent' has previously occurred and is an element all events that lead to mealy machine state STATE (d) .

The arrows signs ('->') around depicts this is a transition.

3. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** observes monitors the SUT and emits all events as described and specified by developers; Thus developers don't provide test cases and / or test data!

Developers execute normally the System Under Test, by providing a normal system execution time run.

1.4 State Diagram Mealy Machine : Usages & Advantages

1.4.1 Usages

- Software code program testing & verifying requires means of expressing requiring in a form that can be used and executed by a computer program.

"SDMM " is a textual (See Figure 4) and graphical (See Figure 1) representation of software system requirements; HOWEVER, requirements expressed using "SDMM " are fail (forbidden) requirements : I.E., software system execution run that shall never happen !

- During software development, developers need to characterize effects of program statements onto software program behavior.

For instance, what causes the deletion of a database table column department value at the level of the software user-scale (Example in Figure 2). Figure 2 could also be represented by a *state diagram mealy machine* as illustrated in Figure 1.

1.4.2 Advantages

- WHITE-box** as Well As **Black-box testing** is possible and / or available at once for any developer in testing; Depending on how YOU specify your runtime monitoring diagram & code (See Section 4.1).
- Software developers could implement code source checking of **LTL-model checking formulas** (<https://www.wikipedia.org/>) for their fail (forbidden) program requirements;

I hope to also have sample **LTL-model checking formulas** implemented in future releases of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, which is a runtime monitoring verification container provided to work with the **"YRI_QVGE Design & Verification System"**.

- Software developers that create & maintain fail (forbidden) program requirements mustn't have a perfect knowledge of code sources of the System Under Test.

1.4.3 Cases of Practical Usages of "SDMM"

- Automobile industry "car-automobile-breaking safety & security usage rules" on-the-fly to avoid thousands of car-recall because of a bug (E.g.: **Toyota Camry 2009** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2009%E2%80%93Toyota_vehicle_recalls));

A car defect could only just be fixed at any Toyota registered auto-car-dealer by inputting a "SDMM" fix specification into an in-car placed YRI-QVGE-PC-Tablet device; Instead of sending it back to a Toyota car factory!

1.5 State Diagram Mealy Machine : Brief Summary Explanation

"YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" has following usages and advantages:

- Formalism STATE DIAGRAM mealy machine** for system specification: Mealy Machines are kind of state machines where output states depend only on input on a source state.

STATE DIAGRAM mealy machine as defined by myself is a finite state automaton that only has following characteristics:

- Each automaton / machine only has 1 start state S_0 , and 1 final state S_f that is an accepting / error state.

A final, accepting, or error state is a state that shows a defect status of the system under analysis (SUA / PUA / SUT).

- Each state S_i only has 1 outgoing state transition to an output state S_0 .
- Each transition T , except a start transition "start", could have a **pre-condition, and post-condition**; That both are called or named state-edge-condition (**pre-condition on T_1 : " $\underline{T_1}$ "; post-condition on T_1 : " $\overline{T_1}$ "**).

A state S_i has a state-condition either as pre-condition " $\underline{T_1}$ " on a state transition Or as a post-condition " $\overline{T_1}$ " of a state transition T_1 .

In Figure 1, state-conditions are for instance " $\underline{Q_0}$ ", and " $\overline{Q_1}$ ".

Each state-condition " S_i ", and / or pre-condition; And / or post-condition is an algebra set specification that uses set inclusion operations : \in, \notin .

- A set inclusion operation as state-condition for a state S_i could for instance be :
 - $\underline{Q_0} := \text{IN_BEFORE}(y, D)$ **is to read "BEFORE next event, variable y is IN set D ($y \in D$)"**. THIS boolean first-order preposition is assigned into variable $\underline{Q_0}$; the "underlining" illustrates that this is a pre-condition : "**meaning a condition That shall hold before (PRE) next event to occur in software system.**"
 - $\overline{Q_0} := \text{IN_AFTER}(y, D)$ **is to read "AFTER next event, variable y is IN set D ($y \in D$)"**. THIS boolean first-order preposition is assigned into variable $\overline{Q_0}$; the "over-lining" illustrates that this is a post-condition : "**meaning a condition That shall hold after (POST) next event to occur in software system.**"
 - $\text{IN_BEFORE_NOP}()$: THIS boolean first-order preposition means that this pre-condition ("True") holds before (BEFORE) next event to occur in software system."
 - $\text{IN_AFTER_NOP}()$: THIS boolean first-order preposition means that this post-condition ("True") holds before next event to occur in software system, after (POST) previously occurred event."
 - $\text{NOT_IN_BEFORE}(y, D)$
 - $\text{NOT_IN_BEFORE_NOP}()$
 - $\text{NOT_IN_AFTER}(y, D)$
 - $\text{NOT_IN_AFTER_NOP}()$

II.) A C++ library that implements runtime monitoring and fail-state recovery as a static library : (https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif).

III.) A Free and OPEN SOURCE CODE SOFTWARE (Foss) implementation of a runtime monitor for using *state diagram mealy machine* specifications; BY means of a QT-dbus software communication stack with your own software : **"YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"** (<https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>).

YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF's formal description of the state diagram formalism follows **Mealy machine** [Wik22] added with **accepting states (final or erroneous states), and state diagram transition pre- and post-conditions** : "*state diagram mealy machine*" ("SDMM").

Another excellent, detailed with proofs and theory presentation of mealy automata [PLH21] is available. In comparison to statechart [HarXX], which is a **visual formalism** for states diagrams, YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF doesn't support at time for instance the following features: *hierarchical states (composite state, submachine state), timing conditions.*

A sample state diagram mealy machine is pictured in Figure 1. *D* is the start state,

1.6 Related State Diagram Formalisms

We here cite sample state diagram formalisms and the theory behind them for checking and / or verifying **software design & programming properties.**

- Statechart by David HAREL : A statechart is here a visual formalism–description to enable a description of a complex software system that can also have states with substates; And / or timing conditions on states entries, and / or transition triggering conditions.
- "Kripke structure" with THEORY & formalism called "MODEL Checking"; mainly by DAVID–Emerson & CLARKE–Edmund [CGK+18] (<https://mitpress.mit.edu/books/model-checking-second-edition>)

Software tools to perform model checking are called **model checkers**. Sample model checkers are NuSMV (<https://nusmv.fbk.eu/downloads.html>); SMV (<https://mcmil.net/smv.html>); Spin-model checker (<https://spinroot.com/spin/whatispin.html>).

1.6.1 David Harel Statechart : A Visual Formalism for State Diagram

Figure 9: A Sample David HAREL–Statechart model of the temporal property expressed in fig. 4 : —"Whenever department YRI_ASSET was deleted (event 'DELETE.department.YRI_ASSET'); querying stock table shall not find again an inventory stock in any department named YRI_ASSET"—.

Statechart [HarXX], as defined and proposed by David HAREL; Represent diagrams, sometimes composite with internal states that are used to describe reactive systems, meaning systems that react and act based on environmental input and interaction.

QT development library professional supports statechart as defined by David-Harel. SCXML is used to specify a state machine. (<https://www...>)

Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System (TDIOHS) as defined by Peleska et al. [BFPT06] implements David-HAREL statechart full compatibility incorporating the following elements for software system specification & elicitation :

- 1.) A software system behavior and actions can be represented as finite set of configurations; A configuration is an assignment

of variables to values that situates a software system evolution over time;

- 2.) A set of configurations of a software system as a finite states graph representation where nodes represent software system states, And edges represent transition between software system states;
- 3.) Start– & End– (Final–, Accepting–, Erroneous–) state to represent INITIAL & FINAL software system state.

A reactive system has a particularity that it doesn't define a final-accepting state as it continuously reacts with its environment : it loops around its start state;
- 4.) Software system states transition defined as graph–edge between software system configuration–states;
- 5.) Software system state transition "Event" as label between graph–nodes;
- 6.) Guarded condition as behavioral condition that must hold in order for a state transition event to trigger & thus send the software system into a new configuration;
- 7.) Timing condition
- 8.) hierarchical states (composite states, submachine state)

1.6.2 Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System (TDIOHS)

Figure 10: A STCT–symbolic test case tree randomly generated by manual drawing for explanation purposes.

TDIOHS–Timed-Discrete-Input-Output-Hybrid-System [BFPT06] is a statechart compatible state diagram formalism defined by "Peleska et al." at the University of Bremen in Germany.

"Peleska et al." define a test mechanism to generate test cases from TDIOHS statechart visual description; The generated test cases abide to "Marie–Claude Gaudelle" algorithm defined in [Gau06] to statistically and uniformly-distribute test cases around a tree that describe all potential program code execution paths : STCT (Symbolic Test Case Tree).

A System Under Test (SUT) tree execution paths could then be traversed based on the real test data generated by a symbolic test data generator component as illustrated for instance in [nf10].

A sample STCT is illustrated in Figure 10; "N₀" is a start node of the program tree.

1.6.3 TDIOHS in Action within "Borland Together 6" with RT–Tester of 'verified.de'

Xavier NOUNDOU, myself, wrote together with Verified Systems International GmbH a plugin that enables developers to automatically create C++ testing code for design drawings created in the CASE-Computer Aided Software Engineering Design tool

"Borland Together 6" (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Micro_Focus_Together).

I performed this task under supervision and advising of "Jan Peleska", as a student in Computer Science at the University of Bremen in Bremen–Germany in years "2004 / 2005".

Based on the automatically generated C++ module code, a developer could then use the UNIT Testing Framework for embedded systems RT-Tester of Verified.de (<https://www.verified.de/products/model-based-testing>) to create software module unit testing code with following criteria :

- 1.) **MCDC (Modified Condition Decision Coverage) : test cases & data for checking any outcome of any boolean assignment of variables involved & used in a conditional IF-Then-Else branching statement;**
- 2.) **Uniformly statistically distributed test cases [NN07] & test data [nf10] from all possible test runtime execution of the Program Under Analysis (PUA) [NN07, BFPT06];**
- 3.) **Myself I only received "2,000 Euros" as fund collected as money-rewards-intellectual property out of this work since "May 2007" when I delivered program code software as part-deliverable to acquire my "Diplom-INFORMATIKER" qualification from the department of Mathematics & Computer Science ("Fachbereich3") of the "UNiversity-racist of Bremen–Germany".**

1.6.4 TDIOHS in Action by "Automatic Test Cases / Data Generation"

Master Thesis [NN07] in Computer Science of "Xavier N. NOUNDOU", at the University of Bremen in Bremen–Germany; demonstrates an implementation of uniform distributed statistically algorithm for selecting paths for creating test cases from a Statechart designed in "Borland-Together 6".

The statechart is first of all transformed into a Symbolic Test Case Tree (STCT) before "MARIE-Claude Gaudelle" [Gau06] modified algorithm by [NN07] is applied.

In [CHKS12], Tatiana Mangels & Jan Peleska present "CTGEN", a Unit Under Test (UUT) test cases and test data generator for embedded system written in the C programming language.

More information and contacts for buying and / or trying this software product can be found at following URL : <https://www.verified.de/products/model-based-testing>, from the German society "Verified Systems International GmbH".

2 Mathematical Formal Definition of SDMM

THIS section gives a mathematical theoretical definition of state diagram mealy machine (abbreviated "SDMM"), as conceived originally by us for our project YERITH-ERP-9.0 [Nou22] runtime monitoring verification started in year 2015 in Yaounde Cameroon.

YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF's formal description of the state diagram formalism follows **Mealy machine** [Wik22] added with **accepting states (final or erroneous states), and state diagram transition pre- and post-conditions**: "state diagram mealy machine". Another excellent, detailed with proofs and theory presentation of mealy automata [PLH21] is available. In comparison to statechart [HarXX], which is a **visual formalism** for states diagrams, YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF doesn't support at time for instance the following features: *hierarchical states (composite state, submachine state), timing conditions*.

2.1 Definition 1 : A state diagram (for mealy machine).

A state diagram is an 8-tuple $(S, S_0, C, \Sigma, \Lambda, \delta, T, \Gamma)$ where:

- S : a finite set of states
- $S_0 \in S$: a start state (or initial state)
- C : a set of predicate conditions; pre-conditions are underlined (e.g.: $\underline{Q0}$), and post-conditions are overlined (e.g.: $\overline{Q1}$). A pre-condition is comparable to a Harel-statechart *guarded condition*.
- Σ : an input alphabet, $\Sigma := \{False, True\}$.
'False' means no input from SUT into YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
'True' means any input could come from SUT.
- Λ : an output alphabet (of program events $e_n (n \in \mathbb{N})$), ϕ the no program event. A program event generally corresponds to a function or method call at a SUT source code statement (or program point).
- $\delta : S \times C$: a 2-ary relation that maps a state s to a state-condition c as either a state diagram transition pre-condition (\underline{c}), or as a state diagram transition post-condition (\overline{c}).
- $T : S \times \Sigma \rightarrow S \times \Lambda$: a transition function that maps an input symbol to an output symbol and the next state.
- $:$: a 2-ary relation that maps a state diagram transition to a guarded condition expression.
- Γ : a set of accepting states; $\Gamma \in S$.

For instance, for the motivating example described in Figure 1 we have:

- $S = \{D, E\}$;
- $S_0 = D$;
- $C = \{\underline{Q0}, \overline{Q1}\}$;
- $\Sigma = \{False, True\}$;
- $\Lambda = \{\phi, 'SELECT.department'\}$;
- $\delta = \{(D, \underline{Q0}), (E, \overline{Q1})\}$;
- $T = \{((D, False), (D, \phi)), ((D, True), (E, 'SELECT.department'))\}$;
- $\Gamma = \{E\}$

2.2 Definition 2 : A pre-condition.

A pre-condition of a state diagram transition is a predicate that must be true before the transition can be triggered. A pre-condition $\underline{Q0}$ could have 2 forms:

- $\underline{Q0} := \text{IN_PRE}(X, Y)$ that means value "X" is in (\in) database column value set "Y".
- $\underline{Q0} := \text{NOT_IN_PRE}(X, Y)$ that means value "X" is not in (\notin) database column value set "Y".

2.3 Definition 3 : A post-condition.

A post-condition of a state diagram transition is a predicate that must be true after the transition was triggered. A post-condition $\overline{Q1}$ could have 2 forms:

- $\overline{Q1} := \text{IN_POST}(A, B)$ that means value "A" is in (\in) database column value set "B".
- $\overline{Q1} := \text{NOT_IN_POST}(A, B)$ that means value "A" is not in (\notin) database column value set "B".

For state diagram mealy machines with more than 2 states, only the first transition has a pre-condition specification (IN_PRE , or NOT_IN_PRE). Each other transition only has a post-condition specification (IN_POST , or NOT_IN_POST). Since each state only has 1 outgoing (edge) state transition, the post-condition of the

previous (incoming) state transition acts as the pre-condition of the next transition.

IT is also for user interest to have following NO-Operation post-conditions when working with state diagram mealy machines with more than 2 states :

- IN_POST_NOP
- NOT_IN_POST_NOP

OUR experience, not reported at time anywhere, shows that *state diagram mealy machine* with more than 2 states are really more for parallel system modeling; I.E. systems that work in GUI with timers and several threads of work at anytime.

"In such cases, subsequent linearly placed states may not belong to same thread of execution: this is kind of what is called in CSP (Communicating Sequential Processes) []; Parallel Composition."

Subsection 2.7 details better and well this correlation between "CSP" [Ra01] & "SDMM".

2.4 Definition 4: A trace.

A trace $T_n = \langle e^0, e^1, \dots, e^n \rangle$ is a sequence of SUT events (or SUT program points) $e^{i, i \in \{0, \dots, n\}}$ of length n . $trace(D)$ is the trace of SUT events up to state D . For instance, for the motivating example described in Figure 1 we have: $trace(E) = trace(D), \langle 'SELECT.department' \rangle$.

2.5 SUT Event Processing Method YRI_trigger_an_edge_event

Listing 2 illustrates the pseudo-code of YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF SUT event processing method `YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)`. `'YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)'` is responsible for interpreting a monitor at runtime, based on its current state, and on the current event received from SUT. Each state in YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF states diagrams shall have only 1 outgoing edge (transition), by specification and construction, as explained in Proposition 2.5.1 in Section 2.

The algorithm in Listing 2 demonstrates that, given correct trace and event information from SUT, YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF always exactly matches the user specification. Thus never giving false warnings.

2.5.1 Proposition 1: NO FALSE WARNINGS.

YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF only allows 1 outgoing edge or transition for a state in its specifications, and for *not desirable (forbidden) behavior*, as illustrated in Figure 1. These 2 properties, together with algorithm `'YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)'` (Listing 2) of YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF, ensures that there are no false warnings during YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF analyses.

For example, the opponents runtime monitoring and / or verification tools-systems [BH12, BRBY00, AAC+05, Bod05, CR07] may give false warnings.

We need to also report that if a developer doesn't well specify to the runtime verifier tester where to emit event, as for instance in "Listing 1", false warnings (false positives) may occur.

2.5.2 Explanation on HOW to avoid code that creates False Warnings (False Positives)

2.6 Guarded Condition Expression Specification in YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF

Guarded conditions expressions can be specified using one of the `yr_create_monitor_edge` method and a boolean

expression of type `YR_CPP_BOOLEAN_expression`. An edge without an explicit guarded condition has an *implicit* `'[True]'` guarded condition on it. The implicit guarded condition `'[True]'` mustn't be identified as an implicit input event `'True'`, as specified in Definition 1.

Guarded conditions are meant to be trace set specification on program events. For instance in Figure 1 (motivating example): `"[in_set_trace ('DELETE.department.YRI_ASSET', STATE(D))]"` means that a SQL 'DELETE' event removing a department named 'YRI_ASSET' from MariaDB SQL table 'department' must have occurred in the trace leading to state 'D', before event `'SELECT.department'` can be triggered. A guarded condition could have two practical forms:

- `"[in_set_trace ('event', STATE(D))]"` is equivalent to: `'event' ∈ trace(D)`.
- `"[not_in_set_trace ('event', STATE(D))]"` is equivalent to: `'event' ∉ trace(D)`.

where 'event' is an input event ($event \in \Sigma$) and 'D' a state diagram state ($D \in S$).

2.7 SDMM for modeling parallel-concurrent software system

A state in a *state diagram mealy machine* specification acts as a parallel concurrent process state.

IT means each state transition represents a parallel-concurrent process synchronization event as for example defined in a formalism named CSP (Concurrent Sequential Processes) as a parallel composition operator (`"||"`).

For instance, in Fig. 1, Processes D & E could be specified in communication in CSP like : " $(D || B)$ over event `SELECT.department`"!

TODO : improve syntax description of CSP.

2.8 SDMM in Action within YRI_QVGE by 'Yerith R&D'

A screenshot of a fail (forbidden) *state diagram mealy machine* is illustrated in Figure 6.

This fail fail (forbidden) *state diagram mealy machine* is the same described in Figure 4 with "YRI_QVGE Design & Verification System" domain specific language (DSL) "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG".

The program-DSL code source illustrated in Figure 4 was automatically generated by myself by "**Saving a design as a DOT/GraphVIZ**" document.

"Saving a design drawing as a DOT/GraphVIZ" creates source code in domain specific language `"YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG"` within a file ending with `'.sd_mealy'`.

2.9 SDMM in Action by automatic "Runtime Monitors Automatic Generation"

I created YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF so to allow automatic generation of runtime execution time monitoring modules for *state diagram mealy machine* defined using a Domain Specific Language (DSL) called YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG.

YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF enables expression and description of state diagram mealy machine specification.

THE Domain-Specific Language (DSL) definition in **Backus-Naur-Form (BNF)** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Backus%E2%80%93Naur_form) of this DSL called YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG is printed in the USER'S guide of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>).

Listing 2: C++ Pseudo-code for `YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)`: `YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF` method for triggering state diagram events (edges or transitions).

```

1  bool MONITOR::YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)
2  {
3      MONITOR_EDGE cur_OUTGOING_EDGE = _cur_STATE.outgoing_edge();
4
5      if (cur_OUTGOING_EDGE.evaluate_GUARDED_CONDITION_expression() &&
6          (an_edge_event == cur_OUTGOING_EDGE.edge_event_token()))
7      {
8          bool precondition_IS_TRUE = cur_OUTGOING_EDGE
9              .CHECK_SOURCE_STATE_PRE_CONDITION(_cur_STATE);
10
11         if (precondition_IS_TRUE)
12         {
13             set_current_triggered_EDGE(cur_OUTGOING_EDGE);
14
15             MONITOR_STATE a_potential_accepting_state =
16                 cur_OUTGOING_EDGE.get_TARGET_STATE();
17
18             if (CHECK_whether__STATE__is_Final(a_potential_accepting_state))
19             {
20                 CALL_BACK_final_state_FUNCTION(a_potential_accepting_state);
21             }
22             return true;
23         }
24     }
25     return false;
26 }

```

3 HOW TO Setup C++ Library "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" for Usage in A C++ PROGRAM SOURCE CODE

When you build runtime monitoring verification library "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF", a static binary library is newly generated.

YOU then need to copy this newly created static binary library into your C++ project. YOU then need for instance using QT, to put a line as follows so to be able to use "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF":

```
LIBS += -L$$PWD/lib_SD -lyri_sd_runtime_verif
```

in your project file ending with following string '.pro' (e.g.:qt-project.pro");

Whereas string "-L\$\$PWD/lib_SD" represents a path that leads to where "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" is stored.

String "-lyri_sd_runtime_verif" mentions to link ("-l") runtime monitoring library "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" during your build process !

3.1 Development Toolchain

Table 2 illustrates for each library project, which others it depends on.

1.) The runtime monitoring interface static library "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" enables users to express software

program states, that are incorrect, USING mealy machines since mealy machine transitions depends only on the current state and its current input;

- 2.) "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS" is only required in case you modified the FOSS library "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" and would like to apply some unit tests to check your modifications.
- 3.) The LIBRARY and / or language that enables to specify "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" state diagram mealy machines is called "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG";
- 4.) The LIBRARY that creates for you the incorrect mealy machine as a C++ code, by describing it using either a text file, and / or a state machine described using `YRI_QVGE` ("YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG") as a design drawings; IS coined the name "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP";
- 5.) NORMALLY you wouldn't need to directly invoke the compiler / translator "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP". This is best done by the runtime monitor generator "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF".

The user's guide for "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF" (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) explains how to do so.

Table 2: YERITH_QVGE Toolchain

PROJECT	Required Program / Library
1) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF	"Qt-trolltech" (https://doc.qt.io/qt-5)
4) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS	1)
2) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG	1)
3) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP	2)
5) YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	3)

4 METHODS of C++ Library "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF"

Table 3: Sample important Classes (prefix YRI_CPP_ to class name) & Methods of C++ Library "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF".

N°	CLASSES	METHODS	UTILITY
1.	MONITOR	CREATE_MONITOR	Creates a new runtime monitor
2.	MONITOR	YRI_register_set_final_state_CALLBACK_FUNCTION	register a C++ method a the callback function in case an error state was found.
3.	MONITOR	RESET_RUNTIME_MONITOR	Sets the current state TO the start state.
4.	MONITOR	YRI_trigger_an_edge_event	"TRUE" is returned in case an edge event "an_edge_event" was triggered.
5.	MONITOR	create_yri_monitor_state	Creates a runtime monitor state.
6.	MONITOR	create_yri_monitor_edge	Creates a runtime monitor edge.
7.	MONITOR	find_yri_monitor_state	Search for a runtime monitor state within a runtime monitor.
8.	MONITOR	set_RUNTIME_MONITOR_NAME	Sets an identity name to a runtime monitor.
9.	MONITOR	IS_in_TRACE_LOG	
10.	MONITOR	TRACE_LOG_current_RECEIVED_EVENT_TOKEN	
11.	MONITOR	GET_root_edge	
12.	MONITOR	DELETE_yri_monitor_edge	
13.	notinset_inset_TRACE_expression	YRI_CPP_notinset_inset_TRACE_expression	
14.	notinset_inset_TRACE_expression	set_USE_SQL_SYNTAX_event_logging_FOR_PRINTING	

We place and explain sample methods of C++ Library "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" that WE deem of major interest for developers :

1.)

4.1 Generated Method YOU need to code

5 A Hardware Dedicated Device : YRI-QVGE-PC-Tablet

A hardware dedicated device running a runtime monitoring verification device called `YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF` is in creation by myself.

6 Detailed Scientific and Engineering Presentation Document on 'zenodo.org'

Detailed formal scientific and engineering contributions of design and testing system YERITH_QVGE can be found in **JOURNAL ARTICLE "Runtime Verification Of SQL Correctness Properties with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"** [nN23].

7 Conclusion

The graphical drawing tool YERITH_QVGE (Figure 6) costs only 2,500 EUROS. WE ONLY SUPPORT DEBIAN-LINUX (<https://www.debian.org>).

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User's Guide for the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE)

AUTHOR: Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]
Contact: YERITH.XAVIER@gmail.com

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Table 1: STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE SPECIFICATION KEYWORDS IN YERITH_QVGE. 'AUTO' KEYWORDS SPECIFIES ALSO SQL QUERY FOR GOING OUT AUTOMATICALLY FROM A FAIL (FORBIDDEN) STATE. ("SEE SECTION 9.")

N°	scientific keywords	engineering keywords
1.	in_set_trace	in_sql_event_log
2.	not_in_set_trace	not_in_sql_event_log
3.	recovery_sql_query	recovery_sql_query
4.	STATE	STATE
5.	START_STATE	BEGIN_STATE
6.	FINAL_STATE ("FINAL_STATE_AUTO")	END_STATE ("END_STATE_AUTO") / ERROR_STATE ("ERROR_STATE_AUTO")
7.	IN_PRE	IN_BEFORE
8.	IN_POST	IN_AFTER
9.	IN_POST_NOP	N/A
10.	NOT_IN_PRE	NOT_IN_BEFORE
11.	NOT_IN_POST	NOT_IN_BEFORE
12.	NOT_IN_POST_NOP	N/A

Figure 1: A motivating example, as previous bug found in YERITH-ERP-9.0.

$Q_0 := \text{NOT_IN_BEFORE}(\text{YRI_ASSET}, \text{department.department_name})$; $Q_1 := \text{IN_AFTER}(\text{YRI_ASSET}, \text{stocks.department_name})$.

Figure 2: YERITH-ERP-9.0 administration section displaying departments ($\neg Q_0$).

Figure 3: YERITH-ERP-9.0 stock asset window listing some assets (Q_1).

Figure 4: A SAMPLE state diagram mealy machine file. KEYWORDS belonging both to 'engineering ("ERROR_STATE_AUTO")', and 'science (START_STATE)' can be intermingled in the same SDMM specification file.

```

1. yr_sd_mealy_automaton_spec yr_missing_department_NO_DELETE
2. {
3.   START_STATE (d) :NOT_IN_BEFORE (YRI_ASSET, department.department_name)
4.   -> [in_sql_event_log ('DELETE.departement.YRI_ASSET', STATE (d) )] / 'SELECT.department' ->
5.     ERROR_STATE (e) :IN_AFTER (YRI_ASSET, stocks.department_name) .
6. }
  
```

Figure 5: SAMPLE INTERNET-RELATED USE CASE SCENARIO OF "SDMM ".

Listing 1: Sample real world "C++" code as opposed to PSEUDO-CODE "C++" code; as modified by a developer after automatic generation of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

```

1  bool YERITH_QVGE_sample_PAPER_extended_version_PROPERTY::DO_VERIFY_AND_or_CHECK_lt_PROPERTY(
2  QString sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number,
3  uint sql_record_qty_MODIFIED,
4  YRI_CPP_UTILS::SQL_CONSTANT_IDENTIFIER cur_SQL_command)
5  {
6  QStringList sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number_LIST = sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number.split(";", Qt::KeepEmptyParts);
7  QString sql_table_name = sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number_LIST.at(0);
8  QString CPP_FILE_NAME = sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number_LIST.at(1);
9  QString cpp_line_number = sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number_LIST.at(2);
10
11  switch(cur_SQL_command)
12  {
13  case YRI_CPP_UTILS::INSERT:
14      break;
15
16  case YRI_CPP_UTILS::SELECT:
17      if (YRI_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF_Utils::isEqualCaseInsensitive(sql_table_name, "departements_products")) {
18          return YRI_SQL_SELECT_departements_products();
19      }
20      break;
21
22  case YRI_CPP_UTILS::UPDATE:
23      break;
24
25  case YRI_CPP_UTILS::DELETE:
26      break;
27
28  default:
29      break;
30  }
31
32  return false;
33  }

```

Figure 6: A SCREENSHOT OF YERITH_QVGE.

Figure 7: A SCREENSHOT OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL EVENT LOG.

1 Introduction

4. Software design properties including event sequences over different layers of software system architecture

Figure 8: SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

This user's guide helps briefly and concisely how to create a binary executable of the runtime monitoring testing tool **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** having user defined runtime monitors. The guide also specifies keywords allowed within runtime monitor specifications as State Diagram Mealy Machines.

YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) could be used for the following automatic generation, analysis, verification, and validation tasks:

1. Automatic generation of runtime monitoring module program to prove whether a test procedure, automated, or not, is correct with regards to a test and / or design STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (formally described in [Nou23]).

In effect, let the test execution be runtime monitored to watch whether accepting error states would be found.

For instance, Junit testing environment could automatically integrate an automatically generated runtime monitor infrastructure for unit testing.

2. Automatic generation of runtime monitoring module program for any software that can emit Dbus messages.

"Such runtime monitoring modules are for interest for special LTL model checking properties that cannot get a definite answer through use of a conventional model checker".

3. Software design properties with SQL

5. Class diagram with sequence diagram.

¹https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif
²<https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>

2 YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) Short Overview

Figure 9: YERITH_QVGE software library dependencies.

YERITH_QVGE is a CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) design tool to generate "domain-specific language (DSL) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG ¹" files, to be inputted into the "compiler YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP", so to generate C++ files for the "runtime verifier tester YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF ²" that allows for manual verification of SQL correctness properties of Graphical User Interface (GUI) software.

Figure 10 illustrates a workflow diagrammatically of the afore described process.

Figure 9 show a diagram of the afore described process; The step of the unit tests is colored in gray because it is only for developers of YERITH_QVGE intended.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF inputs SQL correctness properties expressed using the formalism "state diagram mealy machine (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG)". Figure 8 illustrates a software system architecture of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, together with the monitored program under analysis. The Free Open Source Code Software (FOSS) tool-chain of development testing is located as follows for free, EXCEPT for "YERITH_QVGE " that is a Closed Source Code Software (CSCS):

- COMPILER (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP): https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang
- RUNTIME VERIFIER TESTER (i.e.: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF): <https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>
- state diagram mealy machine UNIT TESTS CODE (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS): https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS
- state diagram mealy machine (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG): https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif

³Scientific: fail (forbidden) trace.

⁴Structure Query Language.

3 YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) Project Dependency

Table 2: YERITH_QVGE Design and Testing System Dependencies

PROJECT	Required Program / Library
1) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG	
2) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP	1)
3) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS	1)
4) YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	2)

Table 2 illustrates for each library project, which others it depends on.

4 Advantages of YERITH_QVGE

A sample state diagram mealy machine is shown in Figure 4.

WITH manual drawing of SQL CORRECTNESS PROPERTY MODEL, you are freed from manually writing "state diagram mealy machine text files" that could be tedious and lengthy. Also, editing state diagram mealy machine files manually could be more error-prone than letting a compiler (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG) do it for you.

5 State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM)

TABLE 1 depicts scientific keywords and their engineering counterpart that can be used in describing NOT DESIRABLE ³ SQL ⁴ call sequence state diagram mealy machine in YERITH_QVGE Design and Testing System.

A STATE DIAGRAM mealy machine specification is compiled into C++ code that describes a runtime monitor to be executed in the runtime monitoring tester YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. Figure 4 depicts a sample State Diagram Mealy Machine specification on a NOT DESIRABLE SQL call sequence.

5.1 HOW TO READ A "SDMM"

Figure 1 shows a finite automaton representation of the mealy machine description in Figure 4. It shall be read as follows:

- The program is in a start state D ; state D is a start state since there is incoming "START" arrow into it.
- (Pre-) Condition Q_0 : "department name ' YRI_ASSET' is not in table column ' department_name' of database table ' department' "; applies in state D .
- Whenever GUARD CONDITION : ***in_sql_event_log(' DELETE . department . YRI_ASSET', STATE (d))***: "event ' DELETE . department . YRI_ASSET' appears in SQL event log (trace) leading to state D "; applies in state D , system under test (SUT) event ' SELECT . department' could occur.
- When SUT event ' SELECT . department' occurs, SUT is now in state E ; state E is an error state because the node that represents it in Figure 1 has 2 circles on it.
- (Post-) Condition Q_1 : "department name ' YRI_ASSET' is in table column ' department_name' of database table ' stocks' "; applies in state E .

This shall not be the case since department ' YRI_ASSET' is no more defined in SUT database table ' department' .

5.2 "SDMM" WITH MORE THAN 2 STATES

State Diagram Mealy Machines (SDMM) with more than 2 states have following characteristics, as detailed in scientific and engineering journal paper [Nou23] in preparation:

- Only the first transition has a pre-condition specification
- Each other transition only has a post-condition specification
- Since each state only has 1 outgoing state transition, the post-condition of the previous (incoming) state transition acts as the pre-condition of the next transition.

6 YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) Workflow

Figure 10: Workflow explanation.

The "Design and Testing System" YERITH_QVGE works with following workflow, as illustrated graphically in Figure 10, and in Figure 5:

1. Draw Structure Query Language (SQL) temporal safety property using drawing tool YERITH_QVGE;
2. copy the generated ".spec_sd_mealy" files into a user project directory in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF home development folder: "\$YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF";
3. follow the steps described in Section 7 so to gather a single executable that defines all specified runtime monitors.

7 Custom User Project (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)

Table 3: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF Directories

Variable for illustration purposes	Meaning
\$YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	root directory of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF
\$YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF/\$USER_PROJECT	root directory of user project

Table 3 illustrates directories that will be used to describe a process to generate a single binary executable for a user's custom project with several runtime monitor specifications.

Figure 7 illustrates a screenshot of the Graphical User Interface (GUI) of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. You can get a copy of

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF using the following command:

```
git clone https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif
```

Creating a binary executable for State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM) specifications consists of the following elements:

1. 'MariaDB' database connection configuration file: this file defines settings to connect to the system under test (SUT) application database; it is located in path: "\$YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF/YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF-GUI-ELEMENTS-SETUP/yri-db-runtime-verif-database-connection.properties".

A database connection to the SUT application database is required in order to check LTL property through the SDMM application library YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG.

2. Property configuration file: this file defines environment variables necessary for building a binary executable for the user; it is located in path: "\$YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF/\$USER_PROJECT/bin/configuration-properties.sh".
3. "\$YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF/\$USER_PROJECT/sd-mealy-machine-specs": this directory contains user defined State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM) specifications to generate Corresponding runtime monitors within a single binary executable.

4. Generate an executable for a user defined runtime monitor:

- a) A following command MUST be renewed each time you are new in a bash-shell environment; execute following command in directory "\$YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF":

```
.. /YRI-create-executable-for-user-SDMM.sh -d $USER_PROJECT
```

- b) modify the LTL verification code part within the generated source code files.

Then execute following command in directory "\$YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF":

```
./yr_db_runtime_verif_BUILD_DEBIAN_PACKAGE.sh
```

- c) uninstall YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF with following command in directory "\$YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF":

```
./yr_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF_uninstall.sh
```

- d) re-install YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF with following command in directory "\$YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF":

```
./yr_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF_INSTALL.SH
```

- e) **Redo [1st-step] in case you add or modify a '.spec_sd_mealy' specification file in folder "\$YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF/\$USER_PROJECT/sd-mealy-machine-specs"!**

8 HOW TO START YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF

- The "ELF-x64" binary executable, in the source development directory is located in full path: "\$YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF/bin".

- The DEBIAN-LINUX icon () of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF is located in "Applications" menu under section "Programming", and section "Accessories".

- The "ELF-x64" binary executable, after installation of the DEBIAN-LINUX package 'yri-db-runtime-verif.deb' is located in full path: "/opt/yri-db-runtime-verif/bin".

Figure 11: SAMPLE sql recovery state diagram model in YERITH_QVGE

9 SQL QUERY Recovery execution on demand

A user can specify which SQL command query to execute whenever a System Under Test (SUT) lands in an accepting error state. This is done using keywords ending with "AUTO", used for meaning "AUTO RECOVERY FROM FAIL STATE":

1. recovery_sql_query
2. END_STATE_AUTO
3. FINAL_STATE_AUTO
4. ERROR_STATE_AUTO.

The use of an "AUTO" keyword shall be accompanied with a use of keyword `recovery_sql_query`, that specifies a SQL command query to run when landing in this fail error accepting state.

9.1 Automatic SQL Command Query Generation

YERITH_QVGE implements an automatic SQL query generation strategy in case a user don't specify a SQL command query, since it could be leaved empty: Subsections 9.1.1, 9.1.2, 9.1.3, and 9.1.4 describe the strategy implemented.

9.1.1 ERROR ACCEPTING STATE for sdmm 1.

not in_before (YX, YY) ACTION (V)
in_after (DD, YR)

9.1.2 RECOVERY 1.

in_after (DD, YR) ACTION (RECOVERY_ND)
not in_after (DD, YR)

9.1.3 RECOVERY 2

in_after (DD, YR) ACTION (RECOVERY_D)
in_after (YX, YY)

9.1.4 Concrete RECOVERY 2 action (Practical solution to be implemented in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

in_after (YX, YY) insert_RECOVERY (YX, YY) •
in_before (YX, YY)

10 HOW TO USE a user interface

Figure 12: YERITH_QVGE user interface screenshot.

11 YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF SPECIFICATION LANGUAGE

Figure 13 illustrates a "Backus-NAUR form (BNF)" of our specification language for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF tool.

12 Formal Scientific and Engineering Project Description

Detailed formal scientific and engineering contributions of design and testing system YERITH_QVGE can be found in **JOURNAL ARTICLE "Runtime Verification Of SQL Correctness Properties with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"** [Nou23].

13 Conclusion

The graphical drawing tool YERITH_QVGE (Figure 6) costs only 2,500 EUROS. WE ONLY SUPPORT DEBIAN-LINUX (<https://www.debian.org>).

References

- [Nou23] Xavier Noundou. A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime. <https://zenodo.org/records/13232567>, October 2023.

Figure 13: **Grammar in Backus–Naur Form (BNF) of YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG Mealy Machine STATE DIAGRAM Specification Language.**

```

<specification> ::= yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec '{' (mealy-automaton-spec) '.' '}'
<mealy-automaton-spec> ::= <sut-state-spec>
    | <sut-state-spec> '→' <sut-edge-state-spec>
<sut-edge-state-spec> ::= <sut-edge-mealy-automaton-spec> '→' <mealy-automaton-spec>
<sut-edge-mealy-automaton-spec> ::= <edge-mealy-automaton-guard-cond> <event-call>
<edge-mealy-automaton-guard-cond> ::= /* empty */ '/' | '[' <trace-specification> ']' '/'
<trace-specification> ::= <in-sql-event-log> | <not-in-sql-event-log> | <in-set-trace> | <not-in-set-trace>
<sut-state-spec> ::= <start-state-property-spec>
    | <start-state-property-spec> ':' <algebra-set-specification>
    | <state-property-spec> ':' <algebra-set-specification>
    | <final-state-property-spec> ':' <algebra-set-specification>
    | <final-state-auto-property-spec> ':' <algebra-set-specification> ':' <recovery-sql-query-spec>
<algebra-set-specification> ::= <in-algebra-set-spec> | <not-in-algebra-set-spec>
<in-algebra-set-spec> ::= <in-spec> '(' <prog-variable> ',' <db-table> '.' <db-column> ')'
    | <in-spec-nop> '(' ')'
<not-in-algebra-set-spec> ::= <not-in-spec> '(' <prog-variable> ',' <db-table> '.' <db-column> ')'
    | <not-in-spec-nop> '(' ')'
<in-sql-event-log> ::= in_sql_event_log '(' <event-call> ',' <state-property-specification> ')'
<not-in-sql-event-log> ::= not_in_sql_event_log '(' <event-call> ',' <state-property-specification> ')'
<in-set-trace> ::= in_set_trace '(' <event-call> ',' <state-property-specification> ')'
<not-in-set-trace> ::= not_in_set_trace '(' <event-call> ',' <state-property-specification> ')'
<in-spec> ::= IN_BEFORE | IN_AFTER | IN_PRE | IN_POST
<in-spec-nop> ::= IN_POST_NOP
<not-in-spec> ::= NOT_IN_BEFORE | NOT_IN_AFTER | NOT_IN_PRE | NOT_IN_POST
<not-in-spec-nop> ::= NOT_IN_POST_NOP
<start-state-property-spec> ::= start_state '(' AlphaNum ')'
<state-property-spec> ::= state '(' AlphaNum ')'
<final-state-property-spec> ::= end_state '(' AlphaNum ')' | final_state '(' AlphaNum ')' | error_state '(' AlphaNum ')'
<final-state-auto-property-spec> ::= end_state_auto '(' AlphaNum ')' | final_state_auto '(' AlphaNum ')'
    | error_state_auto '(' AlphaNum ')'
<recovery-sql-query-spec> ::= recovery_sql_query '(' <db-table> ',' <sql-recovery-query> ')'
<sql-recovery-query> ::= String
<event-call> ::= String
<prog-variable> ::= AlphaNum
<db-table> ::= AlphaNum
<db-column> ::= AlphaNum

```

Yerith-Erp-9.0 SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [D.ENG. PR. PROF.]"

This document describes the thick client software system architecture of Yerith-Erp-9.0. This document also explains the reasons for which we chose to design and implement Yerith-Erp-9.0 as a thick client software system, as opposed to currently more popular webbrowser based software system.

This document further demonstrates the superiority, in terms of simplicity, speed, maintenance, and low costs of development of thick client software system architectures over webbrowser based software system architectures !

1. YERITH-ERP-9.0, source code (no executable binary):

◆git <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0>

2. YERITH-ERP-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON, source code (no executable binary):

◆git <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon>

3. YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF:

◆git <https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>

4. YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF:

◆git https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif

- a.) *This year 2015 we have added This ERP-Enterprise Resource Planing Software for Customers and / or Clients that mainly live in francophone Africa; Because mainstream ERP software kind of SAP-Walldorf, Odoo, Sage, are very demanding in terms of business formal education !*

This part of the world currently is mainly crowded of under educated people-folk; Meaning people that currently don't have attended at least 5 years of formal education since they were born on planet earth.

- b.) *[This year 2025 we have added text about our automatic generation for free for users of Yerith-Erp-9.0; of web-HTML5-PHP webshops.]*

Version: October 12, 2025.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

This introduction motivates why I created Yerith-Erp-9.0, and why it uses the best software programming language AND METHODOLOGY (OOP: OBJECT-ORIENTED PROGRAMMING) of its time !

1.1 Motivation

Yerith-Erp-9.0 [NOU22, NOU21a, NOU21b] is an **Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP)** software system that aims 'effectiveness' and 'simplicity', compared to other high ranked ERP software systems (e.g.: 'Sage Gescom i7', 'SAP Business One', 'Odoo', etc.).

Yerith-Erp-9.0 is implemented by me with THE USER INTERFACE LIBRARY QT [Ltd22]. Our goal when designing and implementing this ERP software system is morefolds:

- 1) RENDER ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING (ERP) SOFTWARE SYSTEM USAGE AND MANIPULATION AS EASY AS READING A LEISURE OR RECREATIONAL BOOK SO TO REDUCE USER STRAIN SIZE !
- 2) CONTRIBUTE TO REDUCE POVERTY BY IMPROVING SOFTWARE SYSTEM TECHNOLOGY FOR ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING (ERP).

1.1.1 Application Domain

Yerith-Erp-9.0 can be used by any managerial organization, WHETHER governmental, OR NON GOVERNMENTAL (N.G.O)!

Yerith-Erp-9.0 is aimed at being simpler in usage and manipulation than older top ranked ERP software systems (e.g.: 'Sage Gescom i7', 'SAP Business One', 'Odoo', etc.)!

A DETAILED COMPARISON OF OCCURS IN PAPER [NOU21a]!

Applications domains of Yerith-Erp-9.0 are for instance:

1. engineering offices;
2. insurance companies;
3. attorney offices;
4. etc.

1.1.2 Implementation Technology

Table 1.1: COMPARISON TABLE BETWEEN C++ [Ste90], Javascript [Fla20], AND JAVA [AGH00]. Javascript and JAVA only have virtual machines that are in FACT REACTIVE SYSTEMS!

FEATURES	C++	Javascript	Java
1. PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE PHILOSOPHY	object-oriented	object-oriented	object-oriented
2. MACROS	✓	✓	
3. MULTIPLE INHERITANCE	✓		
4. support INTERFACES	✓	✓	✓
5. STATIC COMPILATION	✓		
6. RUNTIME MONITORING & VERIFICATION	✓ (YRI_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF)	✓	✓
7. UNIT TESTING FRAMEWORK	✓	✓	✓
8. NETWORK CAPABLE	✓	✓	✓
9. CROSS PLATFORM PORTABLE	✓	✓	✓
10. include FILE LIBRARY CAPABILITY	✓		
11. MULTI THREADING	✓		✓
12. WYSIWYG GUI DESIGN TOOL	✓		✓
13. VIRTUAL MACHINE IS A REACTIVE SYSTEM		✓	✓

We found following reasons for introduction of virtual machines in the programming languages **Javascript**, and **JAVA**:

- **JAVA** and **Javascript** overcome runtime monitoring requirements by introducing language interpretation via virtual machine implementation and execution of programs.
- C++ doesn't have a mainstream equivalent to date; due to its compiled nature.
I advocate **YRI_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF** as the component through which any programming language may have for free by runtime execution, runtime monitoring capability.

We chose to design and implement Yerith-Erp-9.0 as a thick client software system because of the following reasons:

1. The implementation language C++ offers much flexibility:

1. MULTIPLE INHERITANCE:

It allows developers to abstract as much as possible business code upwards, away from downwards implementation classes. For instance, in Yerith-Erp-9.0, GUI Qt windows inherits for instance *search filtering feature*, and *print capability* from 2 different classes.

Print capability couldn't be inherited from the same class where *search filtering* is abstracted and partially implemented (interface in JAVA for instance doesn't allow any method body code), because it works in its pure abstract class (C++ class with at least 1 empty method body), together with feature **database column filtering for viewing and printing**.

The drawback of the multiple inheritance in C++ is: it sometimes can be very difficult to build it using "gcc (g++) [GCC]"!

2. MACROS:

They enable developers to create TEXT TEMPLATE in their code.

For instance, I use macros in some parts of my code to reduce execution time and stack activation records size for method or function calls in Yerith-Erp-9.0!

2. The availability of 'WHAT YOU SEE IS WHAT YOU GET' (WYSIWYG) tools for fast and useful user interface design (e.g.: Qt designer [Com20], miniStudio (vxWorks) [WEI20], etc.)
3. The low number of logical software system architecture layer (i.e.: 2.) involved with the use of a thick client software system architecture, as opposed to a webbrowser based software system (i.e.: 4, *client user interface*, *presentation layer*, *business logic*, and *data (DBMS)*).

FURTHERMORE, TABLE 1.1 ILLUSTRATES A FEATURE COMPARISON TABLE BETWEEN object oriented languages C++, Javascript, and JAVA!

1.1.3 Software System Current Metrics

Table 1.2: Yerith-Erp-9.0 RELEVANT SOFTWARE SYSTEM METRICS

Software System Metric	Value
User Interface (windows, dialog) number	60
MariaDB SQL table number	40
MariaDB SQL table column number	320
Latex template for PDF printing	75
Source lines of code (SLOC)	390,000

1.2 Overview

This pamphlet is structured as follows:

- Chapter 1 motivates why I created Yerith-Erp-9.0, and why it uses the best software programming language AND METHODOLOGY (OOP: OBJECT-ORIENTED PROGRAMMING) of its time !
- Chapter 2 tabular evaluates why thick client are BETTER THAN webbrowser based software system architectures !
- Chapter 3 explains why Yerith-Erp-9.0 is modular in its uses, and fits any industrial setting.
- Chapter 5 introduces Yerith-Erp-Pgi-9.0-Web-System** ([git https://github.com/yerithrd/yeritherppgiwebsystem](https://github.com/yerithrd/yeritherppgiwebsystem)) **that encompasses 2 projects to deliver for free, Without much computer programming webshops for Yerith-Erp-9.0 clients and / or customers :**
 - Yerith-Web-Pages-Generator-9.0** : this project delivers webshop programming using a new simple Domain-Specific Language (DSL) with a compiler / translator that generates automatically PHP source code for its users.
[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9)
 - Yerith-Web-Design-Tool** : This QT-trolltech additional tool that enables webshop automatic source code generation based on user drawn widgets using Qt designer.
[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)
 - ALL functionalities will be available only on USB-dongle key on shopping stores as commercial priced product.**
- Chapter 6 explains why Yerith-Erp-9.0 uses the BEST SOFTWARE TECHNOLOGY IN TERMS OF SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE !

Chapter 2

Thick Client VS. Webbrowser based Software System Architecture

This comparison chapter tabular evaluates why thick client are BETTER THAN webbrowser based software system architectures !

2.1 Thick client: 2 layers logical software architecture

Figure 2.1: 2 layers logical architecture of thick client software system (Image copied from [sec20]).

A thick client software architecture may also have more than only 2 layers.

2.1.1 Security Leak

We advocate to create a runtime verification monitoring tool that protect de-compilation and / or reverse engineering of code source and / or binaries within a productive environment !!!

Program Code-binary obfuscation could also be an alternative solution to avoid de-compilation and / or reverse engineering in order to destroy !!!

1. *A copy of a commercial software on your local hard drive is an enormous amount of money that was invested into your local computer, With a risk for a company that you crack-dishonest their cryptographic protection design to secure their source / binaries code on your hard drive !!!*

IN EFFECT, de-compiling your binary software code is not possible at all !!!

IN EFFECT, a commercial onerous software binaries shall be sold only installed into a USB-dongle key, Since only its user can have access to it.

2. *With a web-browser based software architecture, not anyone could know which software you are using because none is installed on your hard drive; THIS could be for instance advantageous for banking software for instance as no one except its user could know how to access it from a local computer web-browser !!!*

2.2 Webbrowser based: at least 4 layers logical software architecture

Figure 2.2: Webbrowser-based software architecture : at least 4 layers logical software architecture (Image modified from online pdf paper "FlashCache: A NAND Flash Memory File Cache for Low Power Web Servers" [<https://doi.org/10.1145/1176760.1176774>] by Trevor et al.). YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF runtime monitors communication layers.

2.2.1 Software Vulnerability

1. *intrusion of a malware-software into an application server; Example like "IBM-Websphere"; "Apache Tomcat"; etc.; Causes a malfunction of a store-organization network completely.*

★ *Such software vulnerabilities don't exist with thick client software system !*

2.2.2 NETWORK connection related issues & problems

1. *The probability to have malfunction of your software system is high because of the network probable deficiency due to at least 3 layers of inter-connection between your local tier-view (Tiers -1 as depicted in Figure 2.2); and your remote Application And / Or Database server !!!*

2.2.3 BUSINESS related data & INFORMATION Issues with Web-Browser based Architecture Software Systems

A.) *Since all or part of your business data critical are only located on a hard-drive outside of your local area network (LAN), There might be issues with following legal & documentary aspects :*

1. Disruption of WAN (Wide Area Network) and / or Internet might prevent you indefinitely to access your business data.
2. LAWS of the country-place where you locate your data might endanger your business; Partly because it is different from your local laws where you officially have registered your business venture !

ON the other hand side of it; Remote location of your business data in a better country-place might favor your business compared to where it is locally registered !

It might be allowed in that remote country-place to perform certain digital ideas and things that are forbidden where your original business is located : for instance PORNOGRAPHY, etc. !

You may expose yourself to legal prosecutions in the latter case; Either in the remote country-place of your remote digital activities-server, Or locally where this digital activity is Prohibited-by-laws !!!

2.3 Webbrowser based: *now* 2 layers with QT-trolltech-WebAssembly & YERITH_{r&d}-Yerith-Web-Dsl-9.0 (year "2025")

2.4 Tabular Comparison Between Thick-Client And Webbrowser based Architecture

Table 2.1: Thick client application VS Webbrowser based application (with solutions of YERITH_{r&d} now (2025)).

	Thick client application ✓	Webbrowser based application
business code	user interface	application server
co-related software systems	1 (DBMS)	at least 3 (DBMS, web / application server)
number of logical layers	2 (client and data)	4 (client, presentation, logic, and data)
rapid prototyping (WYSIWYG tools)	yes	very limited / [Yerith-Web-Dsl-9.0]
software security vulnerability	low (1 programming language)	VERY high (several programming languages) / [SDMM & YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF]
user interface	all computers (GUI with BUSINESS CODE)	all computers (web-browser)

Table 2.1 compares thick client software systems against webbrowser based software systems.

Table 2.1 ALSO ILLUSTRATES ADVANTAGES of thick client software system architecture over webbrowser based software system architecture !

The common argument for webbrowser based software system architecture is you update the business code just at 1 place: *the application server* !

I argue that thick client architecture IS JUST AS WELL BEST UPDATED AT 1 PLACE: *the user's computer*.

FOR INSTANCE, UPDATE OR UPGRADE OF ENTERPRISE SOFTWARE SYSTEM WEBBROWSER BASED REQUIRES ALMOST AT LEAST 1 24 HOURS SHUTDOWN OF ALL INVOLVED WEB (apache tomcat, etc.) APPLICATIONS SERVERS.

The issue of automatic software upgrade in a computer network is best solved by the 'apt upgrade software system of Debian-Linux', as an example !

Chapter 3

The Thick Client Software System Architecture of Yerith-Erp-9.0

This chapter explains why Yerith-Erp-9.0 is modular in its uses, and fits any industrial setting !

Table 3.1: Thick client application VS Webbrowser based application.

	Thick client application ✓	Webbrowser based application
business code	user interface	application server
co-related software systems	1 (DBMS)	at least 3 (DBMS, web / application server)
number of logical layers	2 (client and data)	4 (client, presentation, logic, and data)
rapid prototyping (WYSIWYG tools)	yes	very limited
software security vulnerability	low (1 programming language)	high (several programming languages)
user interface	all computers (GUI with BUSINESS CODE)	all computers (web-browser)

3.1 Business and user interface code deployment

Table 3.1 depicts the issue of business and user interface code deployment on all computers participating in the functioning of Yerith-Erp-9.0, as a software system for a user.

We tackle the problem of automatic deployment of business and user interface code on all user computers by using the 'apt upgrade' software system on 'Debian-Linux [DEB22]'.

3.2 Databases

DBMS MySQL [Mar22] is used for storing and managing huge data across globe.

3.3 NUMBER OF LOGICAL SOFTWARE SYSTEM LAYERS: E.G. Sample technical configurations

This section illustrates 2 different possible computer network configurations that could prevail in industry.

3.3.1 Sample 2 computers store

Figure 3.1: Sample 2 computers store.

3.3.2 Sample decentralized multi sites supermarket

Figure 3.2: Sample decentralized multi sites supermarket.

Chapter 4

Runtime MONITORING for Safety & Security; With SDMM

THIS chapter introduces runtime monitoring for safety & security of software system using "SDMM" (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033>)! Runtime monitoring enables at runtime in a productive environment to correct a behavior defect of a software code program binary effectively !!!

Figure 4.1: Runtime Monitoring ILLUSTRATION with state diagram mealy machine (sdmm)!

Chapter 5

Yerith-Web-Pages-Generator-9.0 : Website Application FOR free

THIS chapter introduces a software-system that we started invention and / or creation this current year 2024, As an alternative solution for our clients. Users of Yerith-Erp-9.0 could then with Yerith-Web-Dsl-9.0 automatically generate website applications for their goods and services to share with clients and / or other people abroad !

5.1 What You See Is What You Get (WYSIWYG-Tool) : Yerith-Web-Design-Tool

Figure 5.1: A SOFTWARE architecture overview of Yerith-Web-Pages-Generator-9.0 ("An SDMM usage scenario by IBM-websphere".)

Figure 5.2: Yerith-Web-Pages-Generator-9.0 generates legacy web files from Qt 5 interface files (".ui" files).

Figure 5.3: A Stack Stapled Architecture Overview of Yerith-Web-Pages-Generator-9.0.

Common non-technical users of Yerith-Erp-9.0 cannot program a website.

To encourage such users to create their webshops using Yerith-Erp-9.0; We introduce "Yerith-Web-Dsl-9.0", And "Yerith-Web-Design-Tool" :

- 1.) Any stock inventory and stock service introduced within Yerith-Erp-9.0 could then be converted into a web presentation shop using both technologies;
 - "Yerith-Web-Dsl-9.0" is a high-level view programming language to create web HTML5-PHP pages by describing them more simply than using raw conventional, since year 1990, HTML5 (and PHP) programming web languages.

Listing 5.1: *A sample very limited for explanation & illustration purpose yerith-web-dsl-9.0 Source code!*

```
1 yerith-web-pages-generator-MAIN YECEFOIQ-WEB-PAGES
2 {
3
4 web-html-page yri_test
5 {
6 # 'C'omments. #
7 yri_html_page_title: 'Bienvenue!';
8 yri_html_page_MENU_BAR_link_string: 'yri_test!';
9 yri_html_page_input_header_menu_bar[web-html-page-menu-bar-headers];
10 };
11
12
13 web-html-page index
14 {
15 yri_html_page_title: 'Bienvenue au centre de formation qualifiante Yecefoiq!';
16
17 yri_html_page_MENU_BAR_link_string: 'yri_index!';
18
19 yri_html_page_input_header_menu_bar[web-html-page-menu-bar-headers];
20
21 yri_html_page_text_SECTION (HTML_HEADER_H/3; 'Description du Centre de Formation')
22 {
23 VARIABLE_YRI_PARAGRAPH variable_paragraph_1
24 {text-yri-font-size = 11}:
25 {text-yri-width-box = 5 cm} ===
26 "Ce centre de formation en Informatique est la proprit de
27 la start--up entrepreneuriale de Gnie des Systmes de
28 Gestion Informatiss YERITH RD.
29 Les cours du centre de formation ont pour cibles les
30 personnes suivantes:"
31
32 li_begin: 'Travailleurs qualifis en Informatique.'
33 li: 'Travailleurs qualifis en Sciences et en Gnie.'
34 li: 'lves et coliers des tablissements confessionnelles vangliques.'
35 li: 'tudiants dans les universits publiques confessionnelles vangliques.'
36 li_end: 'tudiants dans les universits du monde moderne
37 (incluant des catholiques orthodoxes).'
38 };
39 };
40
41 web-html-page-menu-bar-headers
42 {
43 # vertical-left vertical-right horizontal-top #
44 web-html-page-menu-bar-headers_Position = 'vertical-left';
45
46 yri_html_page_section[index,
47 yri_test,
48 a_propos,
49 programme_des_cours,
50 contenu_des_cours,
51 impressum];
52 };
53 }
```

Chapter 6

Conclusion

This conclusion explains why Yerith-Erp-9.0 uses the BEST SOFTWARE TECHNOLOGY IN TERMS OF SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE !

Table 6.1: Yerith-Erp-9.0-PLATINUM (Yerith-Erp-Pgi-9.0-Web-System) VS. Odoo.

Artifacts	Yerith-Erp-9.0-PLATINUM	Odoo
libraries & programs	YERITH_QVGE, etc.	python-lxml, etc.
user interface code TOOLS WYSIWYG	QT-DESIGNER	(CUSTOM BUILD) FRAMEWORKS
business code	PHP (partly generated), C++	Python, JavaScript
Database Management Server (DBMS)	MySQL	PostgreSQL
web server	Quercus	Werkzeug

Yerith-Erp-9.0 has a thick client software system architecture because we found thick client software system architectures simpler than webbrowser based software system architectures.

Thick client software system architectures is simpler because it requires less layers in its logical (or physical) software system architecture, and is easier to develop and maintain as a software system application.

Table 2.1 illustrates a thick client software system is SUPERIOR IN TERMS OF TOOLS FOR MAINTENANCE AND DEVELOPMENT than a webbrowser based software system !

A webbrowser based software system architecture has more drawbacks as follows:

- 1.) it requires at least 2 other software systems, *apart from the ones normally required by developed software system itself, for instance libraries (e.g.: Log4j), to fully operate (e.g.: web server, application server, etc.).*

Table 6.1 depicts this situation in the light of the open source ERP software system Odoo.

Accordingly, a thick client software system doesn't require any running and managing infrastructure such as for example an application server !

- 2.) A webbrowser based software system requires at least 4 layers in its logical system architecture (e.g.: client, presentation, logic, and data layers).

Accordingly, a thick client software system only requires at least 2 layers !

- 3.) A webbrowser based software system potentially entails more software security vulnerabilities because its implementation requires the use of at least 2 different programming languages, and frameworks in combination.

Accordingly, a thick client software system needs only the use of 1 homogeneous software programming language !

Chapter 7

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Appendix A

Presentation Documents of open source software system YERITH-ERP-9.0

YERITH-ERP-9.0 Software System Product Sheet

YERITH-ERP-9.0 is an **ERP software system** with **6 user roles, and types:**

1. « Administrator »
2. « Business manager »
3. « Cashier »
4. « Seller »
5. « ASSET – stock manager »
6. « Storekeeper ».

YERITH-ERP-9.0 **features:**

1. Runtime monitoring verification with "yerith_qvge (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>)";
2. alerts over stock quantity, and, time period;
3. BA-Business Analytics (business dashboard);
4. HR (human resources) — ALSO with automated and / or manual payment handling for employees; customer relationship management (CRM), budget line management;
5. sale management (e.g. point of sale);
6. ASSET – stock management (e.g. check in);
7. user, and role administration;
8. wild-char searches with character %.

YERITH-ERP-9.0 **is:**

1. easier, and, intuitive, in its use
2. lighter, and, faster, in memory usage
3. multi sites.

YERITH-ERP-9.0's runtime memory usage test is realized using run-time software analysis tool **valgrind**.
 GENERAL SOURCE CODE QUALITY CONTROL is realized with compile-time code analysis tool **Cppcheck**.

Business manager's main window

BUSINESS workflow of YERITH-ERP-9.0

OPERATIONS

Point of Sale Hardware

- ✓ Barcode scanner
- ✓ Thermal printer, etc.

Database Management Systems

- ✓ mariadb 10.5.

Operating Systems

- ✓ Debian-Linux 11; 12.

Author: "Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]"

Version of – October 12, 2025 –

Advantages of YERITH-ERP-9.0 Compared to Other Top ERP systems

YERITH-ERP-9.0 is a very easy to use ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) software system because of its characteristics:

1. separate views for each user role
2. complete and fundamental training in 8 days
3. easy to use graphical user interface (GUI)
4. no college or university training needed
5. no formal business training needed
6. *no internet connection needed.*
7. *EASIER business management overseeing over web-browser based solutions (e.g.: "Contr-ALL" (<https://www.contrall.online>), etc.)*

Table 1 pictures the 'fully-featured-ness', 'effectiveness', & 'simplicity' of YERITH-ERP-9.0, compared to other top ERP systems like for instance "Contr-ALL", "Sage Gescom i7", and "SAP Business One".

Figure 1: Asset / Stock Listing Window

Table 1: Comparison between YERITH-ERP-9.0 and 3 top tier-1 ERP systems

FEATURES	YERITH-ERP-9.0 (≈ 10 years old)	Contr-ALL (≈ 7 years old)	Sage Gescom i7 (≈ 40 years old)	SAP Business One (≈ 40 years old)
★ HR & Accounting full featured ERP	YES	NO	YES	YES
★ runtime monitoring checks enabled	YES (Yri-Db- Runtime-Verif)	NO	YES	YES
★ Documentation online available fully	YES (Here For Instance) (https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724)	NO	NO	NO
separate views per user role	YES	YES	YES	YES
complete training (or solution)	at least 4 weeks	at least 3 weeks	at least 2 months	at least 3 months
★ difficulty in navigation	easy	easy	very difficult	very difficult
usage language in software	easy everyday English	simple	simple	technical
advanced marketing knowledge	no	no	useful	useful
★ Availability on platforms (Hardware)	PC, Tablet	PC, Tablet, Smartphone	PC, Tablet	PC, Tablet
★ web-online interface	not yet	yes, fully web available interface	not yet	not yet
★ internet connection	optional	useful (not at all internet means no access to any of your business resources.)	optional	optional

OPERATIONS

Runtime MONITORING Verification

✓ YERITH_QVGE

Point of Sale Hardware

- ✓ Barcode scanner
- ✓ Thermal printer, etc.

Operating Systems

- ✓ Debian-Linux 11; 13.

Version of – October 8, 2025 –

YERITH-ERP-9.0 Point Of Sale Recommended Hardware

1 Barcode Scanner

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of barcode scanner: "Xfox FJ-5 USB Plug and Play Automatic Barcode Scanner" (approx. 17€).

Bar-code Scanner

2 Thermal Printer

ALL EPSON THERMAL PRINTERS!

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of thermal printer: "Epson TM T20ii Point of Sale Thermal Printer" (approx. 100€).

Thermal Printer

3 Cash Drawer

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of cash drawer: "HP QT457AT" (approx. 90€).

Cash Drawer

4 Touch Screen Monitor

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of touch screen monitor: "ASUS 15.6" LCD Monitor (VT168H)" (approx. 155€).

Touchscreen Monitor

5 Computer

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of desktop computer: "Lenovo Thinkcentre M720 Small Form Factor (SFF)" (approx. 450€).

Computer

6 Multi User Terminal Computer

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of multi user terminal computer: "NC-300 Multi User Terminal Computer" (approx. 112€).

Multi User Terminal Computer

✓ **PECULIARITIES IN CERTAIN COUNTRIES AND/OR REGIONS** USAGE OF POINT-OF-SALE (THERMAL) PRINTERS REQUIRES ALSO ACQUISITION OF A GOVERNMENT-SOLD DEVICE FOR RECORDING AND CERTIFYING ALL FINANCIAL TRANSACTIONS BETWEEN THE THERMAL PRINTERS AND/OR YERITH-ERP-9.0 (e.g.: GERMANY, CANADA, etc.).

Information Brochure of the ERP software system YEROTH-ERP-3.0

Dr.-Ing. Xavier Noubissi Noundou

Tasks	« Business manager »	« Seller »	« ASSET – stock manager »	« Storekeeper »	« Cashier »
create a department	✓				
insert 1 ASSET, stock, or service	✓	✓ (SERVICE)	✓ (ASSET / STOCK)		
delete ASSET, stock	✓				
view ASSET, stock	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
modify ASSET, stock	✓		✓		
transfer ASSET, stock	✓		✓	✓	
check-out ASSET, stock	✓		✓	✓	
modify ASSET, stock management strategy (e.g.: « FIFO », etc.)	✓	✓ (NO PERMANENT)	✓ (NO PERMANENT)		
point of sale	✓	✓			✓
view ASSET, stock transfers	✓		✓	✓	
purchase management	✓	✓	✓ (PARTIAL)		
supplier management	✓	✓			
customer relationship management (CRM)	✓	✓ (PARTIAL)			
business dashboard	✓				
sale return	✓				
view sales information	✓	✓ (SELF)			

Table 1: YEROTH-ERP-3.0 functions-tasks, and associated users-roles.

1 Developer Biography

Figure 1: Portrait of Dr.-Ing. XAVIER.

Dr.-Ing. Xavier Noubissi Noundou is a CHRISTIAN BY FAITH, Cameroonian, born on September 16 1983 in DOUALA (LITTORAL region, CAMEROON).

Xavier has a "Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)" qualification from the **University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY** (May 25, 2007).

XAVIER NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU IS A PHILOSOPHIAE DOCTOR ABD (PH.D. ABD) from **THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO (ON, CANADA); DECEMBER 20, 2011 !**

Xavier has following academic research and professional engineering contributions:

1. 'Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis For C using LLVM'

1. source code in C++:

<http://github.com/sazzad114/saint>
<http://archive.org/download/>

2. full text: [yeroth-saint-2021-MARCH-01/YEROTH-SAINT-2021-MARCH-01.pdf](http://archive.org/download/yeroth-saint-2021-MARCH-01/YEROTH-SAINT-2021-MARCH-01.pdf)

2. 'YEROTH-ERP-3.0':

1. source code in C++:

a. YEROTH-ERP-3.0:

http://drive.google.com/file/d/1-JJke20aa_fuIj3twWsBkj3-KRxgZL4q/view?usp=share_link

b. YEROTH-ERP-3.0 SYSTEM DAEMON:

http://drive.google.com/file/d/1kn5_1KvWPkFD0VxA8eGvk-kuI08L-_T/view?usp=share_link

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http://archive.org/download/yeroth-erp-pgi-compendium_202206/YEROTH_ERP_PGI_COMPENDIUM.pdf

2 Introduction

YEROTH-ERP-3.0 is an **Enterprise Resource Planing** (ERP) software system.

Users of YEROTH-ERP-3.0 could have the following roles:

1

Version of – January 12, 2023 –

Information Brochure of the ERP software system YEROTH-ERP-3.0

YEROTH_{r&d}

1. « Administrator »
2. « Business manager »
3. « Cashier »
4. « Seller »
5. « ASSET – stock manager »
6. « Storekeeper ».

YEROTH-ERP-3.0 allows for business management tasks (listed in Table 1), depending on user role, as follows:

1. create a department (e.g.: finance, asset, stock, etc.)
2. manage clients, and human resources, and suppliers
3. manage enterprise asset (e.g.: cars, etc.)
4. manage financial expenses
5. manage inventory stock
6. manage sales
7. view business dashboards (across sites).

3 Potential Usages of YEROTH-ERP-3.0

YEROTH-ERP-3.0 potential usages are:

1. STOCK AND TRADE EXCHANGES MARKET PLACE
2. ENTERPRISE RESOURCE AND PLANING SOFTWARE for supermarkets and commercial stores
3. i.e. ANY NON GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATION, or GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATION.

4 Advantages of YEROTH-ERP-3.0

1. YEROTH-ERP-3.0 is 100% stable
2. YEROTH-ERP-3.0 has an alert system with two types of alerts: alerts based on stock-quantity, and time-period alerts
3. users have the choice between small size receipts, and, bigger size receipts ("A4")
4. YEROTH-ERP-3.0 runs on the Linux operating system, because Linux is stable, performant, and less vulnerable to security breaches in comparison to other operating systems ('Windows 10')
5. YEROTH-ERP-3.0 has an user interface "Sales" to view sale information (Figure 2), and thus enables users to make managerial decisions
6. YEROTH-ERP-3.0 has an interface "Business dashboard" that generates financial accounting reports, from sale and payment information, to help managers to make "business decisions".

Sale date	Client name	Client location	Product name	Qty	Tax	Total sale
03.04.2022	DR.-ING. YEROTH YEROTH	YEROTH	test_yeroth_1	8.00	0.00	1,600.00
03.04.2022	DR.-ING. YEROTH YEROTH	YEROTH	test_yeroth_1	9.00	0.00	18,000.00
03.04.2022	PROF. DR.-ING. YEROTH	ANCIEN	test_yeroth_1	3.00	0.00	6,000.00
03.04.2022	DIVERS		test_yeroth_1	1.00	0.00	201.00
03.04.2022	DIVERS		test_yeroth_1	1.00	0.00	201.00
03.04.2022	DIVERS		test_yeroth_1	26.00	0.00	5,226.00
12.04.2022	DR.-ING. YEROTH YEROTH		MT_3334_CT_1	1.00	0.00	750,000.00
03.05.2022	DR.-ING. YEROTH YEROTH	YEROTH	YEROTH_TEST_CHAUSURE	2.00	37,700.00	557,700.00

Figure 2: Sale-information window.

5 Alert System

Users with roles « Administrator » or « Business manager » are the ones able to create alerts.

YEROTH-ERP-3.0 allows its users to create two types of alerts:

1. alerts over stocks-quantities
2. alerts over time intervals (this helps for perissable articles and for sales discounts over a period of time).

5.1 Alerts over Stock-Quantity

An alert over a stock-quantity is a message that is sent to a pre-determined user whenever "pre-determined" stock-quantity (X) of a specific article-stock is reached.

For instance, Xavier (« Business manager ») could create an alert for stock "mango" that will be triggered whenever stock "mango" quantity reaches 100; An alert-message is sent to user John (« Storekeeper »).

5.2 Alerts over Time-Period

A time-period is defined by a starting-date and an ending-date (dates are from the "gregorian" calendar).

An alert over a time-period (T) is a message that is generated, sent to a pre-determined user, and kept within YEROTH-ERP-3.0 from T's starting-date up to T's ending-date.

For example, an alert with a message has to be sent to Paul (« Cashier ») when the date of May 05th is reached. The alert message specifies that a rebate of 20% has to be applied on every sale of yoghourt 'trèsbon' during a time interval of 2 weeks.

6 Database Management System

YEROTH-ERP-3.0 uses 'MariaDB' as the standard DBMS. 'MariaDB' is very stable, very performant, and free-software.

Author: Dr.-Ing. Xavier Noubissi Noundou

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7 Conclusion

Figure 3: Point-of-sale window.

Figure 3 illustrates the window for selling articles.

Figure 4: Administrative window for business manager.

Figure 4 illustrates the administrative window for business managers.

YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 : Configuration MULTI-SITES (SUCCURSALES)

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou (Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.)"

CE LIVRET EXPLIQUE COMMENT RÉ-UTILISER YERITH-PGI-ERP-9.0
AVEC DES SITES (SUCCURSALES).

Figure 1 – WORKFLOW de travail générique de YERITH-PGI-9.0.

VERSION : 31 mars 2025

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Chapitre 1

INTRODUCTION

LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-9.0 [uNu22, uNu23a, uNu23b] permet à ses utilisateurs la réutilisation de la fonctionnalité "multi-sites (succursales)" ! La fonctionnalité "multi-sites (succursales)" permet à 1 organisation de contrôler ses activités décentralisées de façon centralisée à l'aide de YERITH-PGI-9.0. Les opérations des succursales (ou encore d'1 filiale) sont répertoriées dans la base de données (MySQL) à l'aide de la colonne 'localisation'. 'La colonne localisation' de la base de données "yerith_erp_9" **CORRESPOND À** :

1. Localisation (INSTALLATION EN FRANÇAIS)
2. Site (EN ANGLAIS)

dans les interfaces graphiques (GUI) de YERITH-PGI-ERP-9.0.

1.1 Définitions

1.1.1 Filiale (DICTIONNAIRE ROBERT)

Société jouissant d'une personnalité juridique (à la différence de la succursale) mais dirigée ou contrôlée par une société mère.

1.1.2 Succursale (DICTIONNAIRE ROBERT)

Établissement qui dépend d'un siège central, tout en jouissant d'une certaine autonomie. Exemple : Les succursales d'une banque.

Chapitre 2

Configuration D'1 ORDINATEUR D'1 SUCCURSALE

Figure 2.1 – FIGURE ILLUSTRATIVE de la marque succursale

CHAQUE ORDINATEUR INSTALLÉ DANS 1 SUCCURSALE possède 1 identification égale à 1 **CHAÎNE DE CARACTÈRE** unique.

CETTE CHAÎNE de caractère est la même pour chaque ordinateur de la succursale observée. LA FIGURE 2.1 illustre **L'IDENTIFIANT "YERITH_RD_TEST"** d'1 succursale de test. Il s'agit de L'ONGLET "Connecter une localisation" dans la fenêtre 'FENÊTRE DE L'ADMINISTRATEUR'!

2.1 INSTALLATIONS DE yerith-erp-pgi-9.0 PAR SUCCURSALE

1. Chaque copie de YERITH-PGI-ERP-9.0 installée sur 1 ordinateur a été compilée avec l'identifiant de sa succursale.

L'IDENTIFIANT de la succursale se fait grâce à 1 chaîne de caractère dans le fichier nommé

`YERITH_ERP_9_0_CURRENT_LOCALISATION_FOR_RELEASE_BUILD`

CE FICHIER EST À CE MOMENT DANS LE RÉPERTOIRE de développement :

`yerith-erp-9-0/yerith-erp-9-0-development-scripts`

2. AINSI COMPILÉE, 1 copie exécutable de YERITH-PGI-ERP-9.0 IDENTIFIE chacune de ses transactions dans la colonne "**localisation**" de la base de donnée MySQL d'1 IDENTIFIANT ÉGAL À TOUS LES IDENTIFIANTS de sa succursale.

Chapitre 3

CAS D'1 Filiale

3.1 TPE et PME

Figure 3.1 – BASE DE DONNÉES CENTRALISÉE d'1 filiale POUR TPE / PME

La figure 3.1 correspond à l'accès à la base de données de **LA Filiale (TPE ou PME)**.

DES TPE (Très Petite Entreprise) et des PME (Petite et Moyenne Entreprise) devraient suivre ce modèle avec 1 seul identifiant (pour colonne localisation) pour tous leurs ordinateurs (OD1 = OD2 = ... = ODn = OD).

3.2 Très Grandes Entreprises (TGE)

Figure 3.2 – BASE DE DONNÉES CENTRALISÉE d'1 filiale pour TGE

La figure 3.2 correspond à l'accès à la base de données de **LA Filiale TGE**.

DANS DE TRÈS GRANDES ENTREPRISES (Ex. : santa lucia AHALA, CAMWATER BONANJO, etc.), chaque département de L'ENTREPRISE A SON identifiant (pour colonne localisation) pour tous les ordinateurs du département ($OD1 \neq OD2 \neq \dots \neq ODn$).

Chapitre 4

CAS D'1 Succursale

Figure 4.1 – BASE DE DONNÉES décentralisée du SIÈGE CENTRAL

La figure ?? correspond à l'accès temps réel et temps différé aux bases de données RESPECTIVEMENT locale et centrale de LA SUCCURSALE et de la MAISON MÈRE (synchronisés à temps d'intervalles réguliers avec l'outil "RSYNC" DE [Debian Linux](#)).

4.1 Coupure de connexion Internet

L'ARCHITECTURE RÉSEAU PRÉSENTÉE dans la FIGURE ?? permet à 1 succursale de travailler localement, même en cas de coupure de connexion internet vers le Siège central.

La synchronisation ultérieure permettrait ainsi de synchroniser des données avec le siège central via l'application **RSYNC-DEBIAN-LINUX**.

Chapitre 5

LOGIN et connexion à 1 succursale

Seul 1 utilisateur de type (ayant 1 rôle de) "Manager" ("business manager" en Anglais) a la possibilité de se connecter à 1 succursale différente de celle où son ordinateur est situé.

Figure 5.1 – Connexion à 1 succursale (SOCIÉTÉ – SITE)

La figure 5.1 illustre la fenêtre dialogue de connexion de YERITH-PGI-ERP-9.0 pour 1 utilisateur. Cette fenêtre contient 1 champs de texte duquel 1 utilisateur ayant 1 rôle de *Manager* peut choisir 1 succursale vers laquelle il peut se connecter.

Lorsqu'un utilisateur est connecté à 1 autre succursale, toutes des informations et données affichées à l'écran proviennent de la base de données de la succursale concernée.

Chapitre 6

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YERITH_QVGE : A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime

Xavier noumbissi Noundou¹

¹Yaounde, Center region, Cameroon.

Contributing authors: yerith.xavier@gmail.com;

Abstract

Software correctness properties are essential to maintain quality by continuous and regressive integration testing, as well as runtime monitoring the program after customer deployment. This paper presents an effective and lightweight C++ program verification framework: **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**, to check SQL (Structure Query Language) [1] software correctness properties specified as temporal safety properties [2]. A temporal safety property specifies what behavior shall not occur, in a software, as sequence of program events. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** allows specification of a SQL temporal safety property by means of a state diagram mealy machine [3]. In **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**, a specification characterizes effects of program events (via SQL statements) on database table columns by means of set interface operations (\in , \notin), and, enable to check these characteristics hold or not at runtime. Integration testing is achieved for instance by expressing a state diagram that encompasses both Graphical User Interface (GUI) states and MySQL [4] databases queries that glue them. For example, a simple specification would encompass states between 'Department administration' and 'Stock listing' GUI interfaces, and transitions between them by means of MySQL databases operations. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** doesn't generate false warnings; **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** specifications are *not desirable (forbidden) specifications (fail traces)*. This paper focuses its examples on MySQL database specifications, labeled as states diagrams events, for the newly developed and FOSS (Free and Open Source Software) Enterprise Resource Planing Software YERITH-ERP-3.0 [5].

Keywords: model-based testing, reactive system analysis, computer software program analysis, computer software dynamic program analysis, software integration testing with SQL and GUI, runtime monitoring

Fig. 1: **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** WORKFLOW (diagram inspired from operation diagram in [6]).

1 Introduction

Table 1: YERITH-ERP-3.0 RELEVANT SOFTWARE SYSTEM METRICS

Software System Metric	Value
User Interface (windows, dialog) number	60
MariaDB SQL table number	38
MariaDB SQL table column number	320
Source lines of code (SLOC)	300,000

1.1 Motivations

This paper describes an effective dynamic analysis framework, based on runtime monitors specified in C++ programs (implemented in the software library `yri_sd_runtime_verif`), to perform software temporal safety property checking of GUI (Graphical User Interface) based software.

GUI based software are very comfortable and handy to use. However, tools to perform temporal safety property verification of GUI software are almost not available as FOSS. The testing of

combinations between GUI windows and database queries that glue them to make sense to the user, is almost unavailable as FOSS, or at all to the best of the knowledge of the author of this paper. The FOSS C++ library `libfsmtest` [7] provides test suite generation support for source code behavior specifications as mealy automata. However, `libfsmtest` only allows for *desirable* correctness properties, and doesn't provide GUI (interaction) support or as plugin-based.

Unit or integration testing for GUI widgets is available by use of "NUnit" testing frameworks like e.g. `Qt-Test` [8], `CppUnit` [9], etc.. Software testing across GUI widgets (and MySQL queries) is however limited in support by these "NUnit" framework. To the best of the knowledge of the author of this paper, `DejaVu` [10] provides some support for Java 'record and replay' testing while `FROGLOGIC` [11] provides support for C++ GUI software 'record and replay' testing technology. 'Record and replay' testing means a user performs a sequence of events that are recorded by testing infrastructure and automatically replay later on to see if expected events thereof occur. However, none of this 'record and replay' technology tool enable temporal safety property specification as FOSS, with SQL as plugin.

As we will see in the related work, section 7, of this paper, most of software correctness property checking frameworks don't put an emphasis on checking temporal safety property of GUI software. Characterizing the effects of program statements (via SQL statements) on database table columns, and to check that these characteristics hold or not, is of predominant importance for large software systems with an impressive number of database tables. Table 1 illustrates for instance FOSS YERITH-ERP-3.0 relevant software system metrics.

It means it can be very difficult for developers to keep application related logical requirements between the tables without appropriate software testing or analysis tools.

A large amount of former work on runtime monitoring assumes for a sequential program, or an abstraction of the program as one single source code, on which program analysis is performed [12–16].

The program analysis technique the author of this paper presents here abstract SQL events, GUI events, or sequences of them, as a state diagram, and enables developers to run them sequentially against a runtime monitor specified as a C++ program. In particular, the example presented in Section 3 specifies results of GUI windows events as SQL database pre-conditions on state diagram transitions; SQL events are specified as state diagram transition events. Figure 1 shows a high level overview of **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** workflow.

1.2 Main Contributions

This paper presents 3 original main contributions:

- an industrial level quality framework (**YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**: <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>), that solves temporal property verification by dynamic program analysis. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** makes use of the C++ Qt-DBus library, to input a *runtime monitor specification* (`yri_sd_runtime_verif`) as C++ program code, that also enables software-library-plugin checks;
- a C++ library: `yri_sd_runtime_verif` (https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif); modeling a state diagram runtime monitoring interface using only set

algebra inclusion operations (\in , \notin) for state diagram program state specification as pre- and post-conditions.

`yri_sd_runtime_verif` only enables the specification of states diagrams specifications as *not desirable (forbidden) behavior specifications (fail traces)*. Thus, **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** doesn't generate any false warning. A violation of a safety rule has been found whenever a final state could be reached. On the other hand, not reaching a final state doesn't mean that there is not a test case (or test input) that cannot reach this final state.

- An application of **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** to check 1 temporal safety property error, found in the ERP FOSS YERITH-ERP-3.0.

Previous version of this paper

This paper extends a previous version [17], currently in conference proceedings **SPLASH-ICTSS 2023** submission, with state diagram with more than 2 states, guarded conditions specifications, 2 new keywords for state diagram transition trace specification ("`in_sql_event_log`", "`not_in_sql_event_log`"), 2 new keywords ("`IN_POST_NOP`", "`NOT_IN_POST_NOP`") for no-operations state post-conditions; And **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** binaries with more than 1 runtime monitor.

1.3 Overview

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents formal definitions of the principal concepts used in this paper. Section 3 presents a motivating example that will be used throughout this paper to explain the presented concepts of this paper. Section 4 presents the software architecture of **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**, our GUI dynamic analysis framework. Section 5 introduces the C++ software library `yri_sd_runtime_verif` to model states diagrams, and reused by **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**. We evaluate our dynamic runtime analysis in Section 6. Section 7 compares this paper with other papers that achieve similar work or endeavors. Section 8 concludes this paper.

2 Formal Definitions

`yri_sd_runtime_verif`'s formal description of the state diagram formalism follows *Mealy machine* [3] added with *accepting states (final or erroneous states), and state diagram transition pre- and post-conditions*: "state diagram mealy machine". Another excellent, detailed with proofs and theory presentation of mealy automata [18] is available. In comparison to statechart [19], which is a *visual formalism* for states diagrams, `yri_sd_runtime_verif` doesn't support at time for instance the following features: *hierarchical states (composite state, submachine state), timing conditions (timing conditions on states entries, and / or transition triggering conditions)*.

Definition 1 : A state diagram.

A state diagram is an 8-tuple $(S, S_0, C, \Sigma, \Lambda, \delta, T, \Gamma)$ where:

- S : a finite set of states
- $S_0 \in S$: a start state (or initial state)
- C : a set of predicate conditions; pre-conditions are underlined (e.g.: $\underline{Q0}$), and post-conditions are overlined (e.g.: $\overline{Q1}$). A pre-condition is comparable to a Harel-statechart *guarded condition*.
- Σ : an input alphabet, $\Sigma := \{False, True\}$.
'False' means no input from SUT into **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**.
'True' means any input could come from SUT.
- Λ : an output alphabet (of program events $e_n (n \in \mathbb{N})$), ϕ the no program event. A program event generally corresponds to a function or method call at a SUT source code statement (or program point).
- $\delta : S \times C$: a 2-ary relation that maps a state s to a state-condition c as either a state diagram transition pre-condition (\underline{c}), or as a state diagram transition post-condition (\overline{c}).
- $T : S \times \Sigma \rightarrow S \times \Lambda$: a transition function that maps an input symbol to an output symbol and the next state.
- $:$ a 2-ary relation that maps a state diagram transition to a guarded condition expression.
- Γ : a set of accepting states; $\Gamma \in S$.

For instance, for the motivating example described in Figure 2 we have:

- $S = \{D, E\}$;
- $S_0 = D$;
- $C = \{\underline{Q0}, \overline{Q1}\}$;
- $\Sigma = \{False, True\}$;
- $\Lambda = \{\phi, 'SELECT.department'\}$;
- $\delta = \{(D, \underline{Q0}), (E, \overline{Q1})\}$;
- $T = \{((D, False), (D, \phi)), ((D, True), (E, 'SELECT.department'))\}$;
- $\Gamma = \{E\}$

Definition 2 : A pre-condition.

A pre-condition of a state diagram transition is a predicate that must be true before the transition can be triggered. A pre-condition $\underline{Q0}$ could have 2 forms:

- $\underline{Q0} := \text{IN_PRE}(X, Y)$ that means value "X" is in (\in) database column value set "Y".
- $\underline{Q0} := \text{NOT_IN_PRE}(X, Y)$ that means value "X" is not in (\notin) database column value set "Y".

Definition 3 : A post-condition.

A post-condition of a state diagram transition is a predicate that must be true after the transition was triggered. A post-condition $\overline{Q1}$ could have 2 forms:

- $\overline{Q1} := \text{IN_POST}(A, B)$ that means value "A" is in (\in) database column value set "B".
- $\overline{Q1} := \text{NOT_IN_POST}(A, B)$ that means value "A" is not in (\notin) database column value set "B".

For state diagram mealy machines with more than 2 states, only the first transition has a pre-condition specification (**IN_PRE**, or **NOT_IN_PRE**). Each other transition only has a post-condition specification (**IN_POST**, or **NOT_IN_POST**). Since each state only has 1 outgoing (edge) state transition, the post-condition of the previous (incoming) state transition acts as the pre-condition of the next transition.

IT is also for user interest to have following **NO-Operation** post-conditions when working with state diagram mealy machines with more than 2 states :

- **IN_POST_NOP**

◦ **NOT_IN_POST_NOP**

OUR experience, not reported at time anywhere, shows that *state diagram mealy machine* with more than 2 states are really more for parallel system modeling; I.E. systems that work in GUI with timers and several threads of work at anytime.

“In such cases, subsequent linearly placed states may not belong to same thread of execution: this is kind of what is called in CSP (Communicating Sequential Processes) [1]; Parallel Composition.”

Definition 4 : A trace.

A trace $T_n = \langle e^0, e^1, \dots, e^n \rangle$ is a sequence of SUT events (or SUT program points) $e^i, i \in \{0, \dots, n\}$ of length n . *trace(D)* is the trace of SUT events up to state D. For instance, for the motivating example described in Figure 2 we have: $trace(E) = trace(D), \langle 'SELECT.department' \rangle$.

Proposition 1: NO FALSE WARNINGS.

`yri_sd_runtime_verif` only allows 1 outgoing edge or transition for a state in its specifications, and for *not desirable (forbidden) behavior*, as illustrated in Figure 2. There is no need to specify the red colored edge in Figure 2 because it represents runtime cases where no input events arrive from SUT into **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**. These 2 properties, together with algorithm `'YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)'` (Listing 3) of `yri_sd_runtime_verif`, ensures that there are no false warnings during **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** analyses. For example, the runtime monitoring or verification systems [12–16] may give false warnings.

2.1 Guarded Condition Expression Specification in `yri_sd_runtime_verif`

Guarded conditions expressions can be specified using one of the `yr_create_monitor_edge` method and a boolean expression of type `YR_CPP_BOOLEAN_expression`. An edge without an explicit guarded condition has an *implicit* `'[True]'` guarded condition on it. The implicit guarded condition `'[True]'` mustn't be identified

as an implicit input event `'True'`, as specified in Definition 1.

Guarded conditions are meant to be trace set specification on program events. For instance in Figure 2 (motivating example): `"[in_set_trace ('DELETE.department.YRI_ASSET', STATE(D))]"` means that a SQL `'DELETE'` event removing a department named `'YRI_ASSET'` from MariaDB SQL table `'department'` must have occurred in the trace leading to state `'D'`, before event `'SELECT.department'` can be triggered. A guarded condition could have two practical forms:

- `"[in_set_trace ('event', STATE(D))]"` is equivalent to: `'event' ∈ trace(D)`.
- `"[not_in_set_trace ('event', STATE(D))]"` is equivalent to: `'event' ∉ trace(D)`.

where `'event'` is an input event (`event ∈ Σ`) and `'D'` a state diagram state (`D ∈ S`).

Fig. 2: A motivating example, as current bug in YERITH-ERP-3.0.

$\overline{Q0} := \text{NOT_IN_PRE}(\text{YRI_ASSET}, \text{department.department_name}).$
 $\overline{Q1} := \text{IN_POST}(\text{YRI_ASSET}, \text{stocks.department_name}).$

Fig. 3: YERITH-ERP-3.0 administration section displaying departments ($\neg Q0$).

Fig. 4: YERITH-ERP-3.0 stock asset window listing some assets ($\overline{Q1}$).

3 Motivating Example: missing department definition

3.1 The Enterprise Resource Planing Software YERITH-ERP-3.0

YERITH-ERP-3.0 is a fast, yet very simple in terms of usage, installation, and configuration Enterprise Resource Planing Software developed by Noundou et al. [5] for very small, small, medium, and large enterprises. YERITH-ERP-3.0 is developed using C++ by means of the Qt development library. YERITH-ERP-3.0 is a large software with around 300 000 (three hundred thousands) of physical source lines of

code. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** could be used for integration testing of YERITH-ERP-3.0, among different software modules.

3.2 Example Temporal Safety Property

The motivating example of this paper consists of the temporal safety property stipulating that *"A DEPARTMENT SHALL NOT BE DELETED WHENEVER STOCKS ASSET STILL EXISTS UNDER THIS DEPARTMENT"*. This statement means that a user shall be denied the removal of department 'YRI_ASSET' in Figure 3 because there are still a stock asset listed within department 'YRI_ASSET', as illustrated in Figure 4. Figure 2

Fig. 5: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF graphical EDITOR viewing interface demonstrating that a final state has been reached (Section 6 analyzes these results).

illustrates the above temporal safety property as a simple state diagram.

3.2.1 State Diagram Explanation

'D' is a *start* state as illustrated by an arrow ending on its state shape. 'E' is a *final* (error, or accepting) state as illustrated by a double circle as state shape.

The pre-condition Q_0 (as a predicate) in state 'D':

"NOT_IN_PRE(YRI_ASSET, department.department_name)" means:

- a department named 'YRI_ASSET' is not in column 'department_name' of MariaDB SQL database table 'department'. This might happen whenever

button 'Delete' in Figure 3 is pressed when item 'YRI_ASSET' is selected.

Similarly, the post-condition $\overline{Q_1}$ (as a predicate) "IN_POST(YRI_ASSET, stocks.department_name)", in accepting state 'E', means:

- a department named 'YRI_ASSET' is in column "department_name" of MariaDB SQL database table 'stocks'.

The state diagram event transition in Figure 2: 'SELECT.department' denotes that when in 'D', a SQL 'select' on database table "department" has occurred; 'E' is then reached as an *accepting state*.

Guarded Condition Expression

The guarded condition expression "[`in_set_trace ('DELETE.department.YRI_ASSET', STATE(D))`]" means a SQL 'DELETE' event removing a department named 'YRI_ASSET' from MariaDB SQL table 'department' must have occurred in the trace leading to state 'D'.

Yri_sd_runtime_verif Specification Code

The source code specified in Listing 2 also illustrates a specification in C++ using software library `yri_sd_runtime_verif` of the state diagram specification above.

3.3 YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF Analysis Report

The motivating example automaton in Figure 2 is analyzed by **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** as follows:

- whenever department 'YRI_ASSET' is deleted in YERITH-ERP-3.0, as done in Figure 3, the runtime monitor state 'D' with a state condition Q_0 is entered
- when MySQL library (plugin) event 'SELECT.department' occurs, in Figure 3 because of YERITH-ERP-3.0 displaying the remaining product departments, the guarded condition for edge event 'SELECT.department' is automatically evaluated to 'True' by C++ library `yri_sd_runtime_verif`, because no other guarded condition was specified by the developer
- `yri_sd_runtime_verif` enters the runtime monitor state to 'E' and state condition Q_1 via method `YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)` because there are still assets (`yerith_asset_3`) left within product department 'YRI_ASSET', as illustrated in Figure 4. 'E' is then an accepting (or final or error) state.

Figure 5 illustrates an analysis result of the afore described process, which gets evaluated and described in Evaluation Section 6.

Fig. 6: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: simplified software system architecture.

4 The Software Architecture of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF

4.1 Dynamic Analysis

4.1.1 SUT Source Code Instrumentation.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF runs as a separate Debian Linux process from the application to dynamically analyze (YERITH-ERP-3.0 in this case). Figure 6 illustrates a software system architecture layer of a software system that uses **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**. Figure 6 and Figure 7 illustrate how YERITH-ERP-3.0 is instrumented to send MySQL database events, as they occur on due to the GUI of YERITH-ERP-3.0, to process **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**, so it can perform runtime analysis of the monitor implemented within it.

4.1.2 Debugging Information.

Each GUI manipulation of YERITH-ERP-3.0 in its instrumented source code part could generate a state transition within the analyzed runtime monitor state diagram in **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**. Visualize "line 35" of Figure 5 to observe that a specific analysis message is sent to the console of **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** in cases where a final state has been reached; the message at "line 33" is for an

Fig. 7: YERITH_QVGE software library dependencies.

accepting (final) state of the state diagram specification of the motivating example presented in Figure 2.

4.2 SQL Events

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF currently only processes the 4 SQL events in Table 2.

4.3 A Runtime Monitor (An Analysis Client)

Listing 1: "XML file adaptor for YERITH-ERP-3.0 test cases (reduced from 4 to only 1 SQL event for paper)."

```
<!DOCTYPE node PUBLIC "-//freedesktop//DTD D-BUS Object
Introspection 1.0//EN"
"http://www.freedesktop.org/standards/dbus/1.0/introspect.
dtd">
<node name="/YRruntimeverification">
  <interface name="com.yerith.rd.IYRruntimeverification">
    <method name="YRI_slot_refresh_SELECT_DB_MYSQL">
      <annotation name="org.qtproject.QtDBus.QtTypeName.In0"
        value="QString"/>
      <annotation name="org.qtproject.QtDBus.QtTypeName.In1"
        value="uint"/>
      <annotation name="org.qtproject.QtDBus.QtTypeName.In2"
        value="bool"/>
      <arg type="QString" direction="in"/>
      <arg type="uint" direction="in"/>
      <arg type="bool" direction="out"/>
    </method>
  </interface>
</node>
```

An user (an analysis client) of **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** needs to subclass class **YR_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF_Monitor**. The UML class diagram in Figure 8 displays the class structure of **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**. Qt-Dbus communication adaptor **IYRruntimeverificationAdaptor**

Table 2: SQL Event Dbus Method Interface

SQL Event	Dbus Method Interface
DELETE	YRI_slot_refresh_DELETE_DB_MYSQL(QString, uint)
INSERT	YRI_slot_refresh_INSERT_DB_MYSQL(QString, uint)
UPDATE	YRI_slot_refresh_UPDATE_DB_MYSQL(QString, uint)
SELECT	YRI_slot_refresh_SELECT_DB_MYSQL(QString, uint)

Fig. 8: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: simplified class diagram in UML [20].

shall be generated by the user of this library (on **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** side) using Qt-Dbus command `qdbusxml2cpp` and an XML file, similar to the one displayed in Listing 1:

An analysis client must first override method **'DO_VERIFY_AND_or_CHECK_ItI_PROPERTY'** of class **'YR_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF_Monitor'** so to implement a checking algorithm for each event received from SUT, as for instance the events illustrated in Figure 2 of the motivating example. The analysis client then calls method **'YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)'** (Listing 3) of class **'YR_CPP_RUNTIME_MONITOR'** of C++ library `yri_sd_runtime_verif` for each corresponding state diagram transition event.

Fig. 9: Class diagram in UML [20] to model a State Transition Diagram.

Fig. 10: Class diagram in UML [20] to model state diagram transition trace conditions in yri_sd_runtime_verif code.

Listing 2: yri_sd_runtime_verif C++ code modeling a current bug in YERITH-ERP-3.0 (Figure 2).

```

1 YRI_CPP_MONITOR_EDGE *a_last_edge_0 = create_yri_monitor_edge("D",
2 "E",
3 "select.departements_products");
4
5 a_last_edge_0->get_SOURCE_STATE()->set_START_STATE(true);
6
7 a_last_edge_0->get_TARGET_STATE()->set_FINAL_STATE(true);
8
9 a_last_edge_0->set_PRE_CONDITION_notIN("YRI_ASSET",
10 "departements_products.nom_departement_produit");
11
12 a_last_edge_0->set_POST_CONDITION_IN("YRI_ASSET",
13 "stocks.nom_departement_produit");
14
15 YRI_register_set_final_state_CALLBACK_FUNCTION(&YRI_CALL_BACK_final_state);

```

5 yri_sd_runtime_verif: A C++ Library to Model States Diagrams

5.1 Structure Of yri_sd_runtime_verif

yri_sd_runtime_verif is a state diagram C++ library the author of this paper created to work with the dynamic analysis program YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. Figure 9 and Figure 10 represent the class structure, in UML, of yri_sd_runtime_verif. Listing 2 shows the C++ code that models the motivating example in

Figure 2, and that uses runtime monitoring C++ state diagram library yri_sd_runtime_verif.

There is no need to write C++ code for the red specified edge of Figure 2; this represents runtime cases where no input event arrives from SUT into YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

Table 3 specifies which class is in yri_sd_runtime_verif code for each runtime monitor/state diagram element.

5.2 Methods for Pre- and Post-Condition Specifications

Table 4 illustrates methods for specifying pre- and post-conditions of a runtime monitor

Table 3: Runtime Monitor Specification Classes

State Diagram Feature	Class
State	YR_CPP_MONITOR_STATE
Transition	YR_CPP_MONITOR_EDGE
Event	YR_CPP_MONITOR_EVENT
Trace at state level	YR_CPP_MONITOR_TRACE_EVENT
Guard Condition	YR_CPP_BOOLEAN_expression
Set Trace Inclusion at edges	YR_CPP_in_SET_TRACE_expression
Set Trace non Inclusion at edges	YR_CPP_not_in_SET_TRACE_expression
Runtime Monitor	YR_CPP_MONITOR

Table 4: `yri_sd_runtime_verif` Methods for Pre-/Post-Condition Specification

Class <code>YR_CPP_MONITOR_EDGE</code> Methods	Utility
<code>set_PRE_CONDITION_notIN(QString, QString)</code>	sets a NOT IN DATABASE pre-condition
<code>set_PRE_CONDITION_IN(QString, QString)</code>	sets an IN DATABASE pre-condition
<code>set_POST_CONDITION_notIN(QString, QString)</code>	sets a NOT IN DATABASE post-condition
<code>set_POST_CONDITION_IN(QString, QString)</code>	sets an IN DATABASE pre-condition

state diagram transition. Each method takes in 2 arguments of string ('QString') type: 'DB_VARIABLE', 'db_TABLE_db_COLUMN'.

The first method argument: 'DB_VARIABLE', specifies which variable is to be expected as value for the specification of the second variable argument 'db_TABLE_db_COLUMN'. The second variable gives in a string to be specified in format "DB_table_name.DB_table_column"; and its supposed value is the returned value of the first variable argument 'DB_VARIABLE'.

These 4 pre- and post-conditions methods make assumptions that a **program variable value** 'DB_VARIABLE' is in set "DB_table_name.DB_table_column" or not; if the value of 'DB_VARIABLE' is in the database table column, it means it is **in the set** (\in) of values "DB_table_name.DB_table_column"; and not being in the table column means it is **not in the set** (\notin).

Example from the motivating example in Section 3

Listing 2 of the runtime monitoring specification stipulates for instance in its "line 12", as post-condition:

```
a_last_edge_0->
  set_POST_CONDITION_IN("YRI_ASSET",
    "stocks.nom_departement_produit");
that 'YRI_ASSET' shall be a value in the value set ( $\in$ ) of SQL table 'stocks' column 'nom_departement_produit'.
```

5.3 SUT Event Processing Method `YRI_trigger_an_edge_event`

Listing 3 illustrates the pseudo-code of `yri_sd_runtime_verif` SUT event processing method `YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)`. 'YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)' is responsible for interpreting a monitor at runtime, based on its current state, and on the current event received from SUT. Each state in `yri_sd_runtime_verif` states diagrams

Listing 3: C++ Pseudo-code for `YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event): yri_sd_runtime_verif` method for triggering state diagram events (edges or transitions).

```

1  bool MONITOR::YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)
2  {
3      MONITOR_EDGE cur_OUTGOING_EDGE = _cur_STATE.outgoing_edge();
4
5      if (cur_OUTGOING_EDGE.evaluate_GUARDED_CONDITION_expression() &&
6          (an_edge_event == cur_OUTGOING_EDGE.edge_event_token()))
7      {
8          bool precondition_IS_TRUE = cur_OUTGOING_EDGE
9              .CHECK_SOURCE_STATE_PRE_CONDITION(_cur_STATE);
10
11         if (precondition_IS_TRUE)
12         {
13             set_current_triggered_EDGE(cur_OUTGOING_EDGE);
14
15             MONITOR_STATE a_potential_accepting_state =
16                 cur_OUTGOING_EDGE.get_TARGET_STATE();
17
18             if (CHECK_whether__STATE__is__Final(a_potential_accepting_state))
19             {
20                 CALL_BACK_final_state_FUNCTION(a_potential_accepting_state);
21             }
22             return true;
23         }
24     }
25     return false;
26 }

```

shall have only 1 outgoing edge (transition), by specification and construction, as explained in Proposition 2 in Section 2.

The algorithm in Listing 3 demonstrates that, given correct trace and event information from SUT, `yri_sd_runtime_verif` always exactly matches the user specification. Thus never giving false warnings.

Table 5: SUT (YERITH-ERP-3.0) "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF graphical EDITOR" error states (Figure 5).

SQL EVENT	SUT PROGRAM POINT (TRACE)
"SELECT.department"	"src/yerith-erp-windows.cpp:992"

6 Evaluation

The main experimental results in this paper demonstrate the efficacy of our tool to find errors in the SUT (YERITH-ERP-3.0), presented in Subsection 3.2.

Qualitative Results.

SUT (YERITH-ERP-3.0) TRACING.

Table 5 illustrates SUT source code trace information as presented in **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** console output in Figure 5. We have translated from French to English the MariaDB SQL table names.

SQL EVENT CALL SEQUENCE.

A careful observation of the output in Figure 5 illustrates the following sequence:

- **line 23:** at state D , execution of the state diagram event "'SELECT.department' " (SUT button 'Delete' has been pressed at **line 21**)
:
select * from departements_produits WHERE nom_departement_produit = 'YRI_ASSET';
- **line 28, line 29:** evaluation of the precondition Q_0 of state D stating that product department 'YRI_ASSET' is not existent evaluates to 'TRUE' (triggering of event "DELETE.department.YRI_ASSET' " by pressing of SUT button 'Delete' at **line 21** has removed any asset department name 'YRI_ASSET').
*[YRI_CPP_MONITOR::CHECK_PRE_CONDITION_notIN:] precondition_IS_TRUE: True **
- **line 31, line 32:** checking post-condition Q_1 in state E (there are still stocks in stock department 'YRI_ASSET') evaluates to 'TRUE', thus state E is reached as an accepting state, because department name 'YRI_ASSET' still exists in SUT SQL table "stocks", as illustrated in Figure 4 of the motivating example:
"execQuery: select * from stocks WHERE nom_departement_produit = 'YRI_ASSET';"
*[YRI_CPP_MONITOR::CHECK_post_condition_IN:] postcondition_IS_TRUE: True **

Runtime Performance.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF and **yri_sd_runtime_verif** don't incur a runtime supplemental overhead to the SUT, apart from emitting SQL events from SUT to **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** as they occur, since no hand-shaking mechanism is used between **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** and the SUT. The emission of an SQL event from SUT to **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** doesn't cost more than 2 statements execution time (getting a pointer to the DBUS server, and calling a method 'YR_slot_refresh_SELECT_DB_MYSQL' or other similar 3 methods (for INSERT, UPDATE, and, DELETE) on it).

7 Related Work

- **SUT source code instrumentation with runtime monitor specification.** "Clara" [12] enables to express software correctness properties using **AspectJ** and *dependency state machines (related to trace-matches [21])*, both as instances of the *typestate* formalism, a formalism that is merely used for checking correctness of programs by a static compilation (analysis) technique called *typestate checking*. The Clara framework weaves (instruments), and annotates a program with runtime monitors using **AspectJ**, then tries to optimize the weaved program by static analysis. The "residual program", meaning the weaved statically optimized program is then executed and runtime monitored by developers to detect runtime errors. Runtime monitoring tools [13–16] work as similar as the Clara framework does.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF doesn't instrument the System Under Test (SUT) with any specification. It runs the runtime monitor concurrently from the analyzed SUT, but not with hand-shaking mechanism, thus not increasing runtime execution of the SUT. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** specifies the runtime monitor as a *state diagram mealy machine*, a subset of *typestate*, specified as a C++ program, and extended with accepting states and state transition pre- and post-condition.
- **SUT binary code instrumentation with a runtime monitor.** With **tracerory** [6, 22]", **Jon Eyolfson and Patrick Lam** use runtime program binary code instrumentation technique in **INTEL-pin** [23] to instrument running programs for purposes of detecting unread memory. I.e., **tracerory** doesn't generate itself a runtime monitor, it uses **INTEL-pin** [23] to generate a runtime monitor for its verification purposes. "Purify" [24] doesn't allow for SUT user correctness property specification. It has built-in memory access safety properties to check *offline* on program execution, after instrumentation of the SUT, its third-party, and vendor object-code libraries.

In contrast, with **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**, the user instruments the source code of the analyzed C++ program at compile time with SQL events emitting code. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** could also be used to perform memory write integrity check like **tracerory**. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** monitors program trace events at database level (also source code statement level by mapping to SQL query statements), and not at program counter level as **tracerory** does. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** inputs a SUT correctness property specification as a *state diagram mealy machine* (as a subset of LTL [2]); **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** is a runtime monitor container; **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** also generates itself a runtime monitor whereas **tracerory** doesn't.

- **Source code automated test case generation for C++ with TDIOHS [25], or FOSS library libfsmtest [7].** "Peleska et al." created a Framework for generating Harel-statecharts fully compatible state diagrams as Test programs as C++ object-oriented program code; Based on "Peleska et al." formalism of Time Discrete Input/Output Hybrid System (TDIOHS). TDIOHS models state systems that handle real and discrete real number data as input to the system under test; TDIOHS models SUT execution by a so called SYMBOLIC TEST CASES TREE (STCT) that represents all possible runtime execution paths of the SUT by means of symbolic test cases data. Symbolic test cases data are data that cannot be used in a runtime execution, BUT that are generated outside from STCT tree by a symbolic test data generator algorithm. The SUT sample tree execution paths are then traversed based on the real test data generated by a symbolic test data generator component [26].

In contrast, the framework **YERITH_QVGE** runtime monitors a program under analysis only for specified fail (forbidden) trace behaviors as given by users.

- **Specification as set interface operations.** "Hob" [27, 28] is a program verification framework that enables to: characterize effects of program statement on data

structures by means of all (\forall , \exists , etc.) algebra abstract set interface operations; and to check that these characteristics hold or not, using static analyses.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF is a program verification framework that enables to: characterize effects of program statements via SQL [4] (Structure Query Language) on database table columns by means of set interface operations (\in , \notin); and to check that these characteristics hold or not, using dynamic runtime analysis.

- **Concurrent Event Stream Analysis.**

"DejaVu" [29] enables to check safety temporal property expressed in **first-order past linear-time temporal logic (FO-PLTL)** for events that carry data. **DejaVu** inputs a trace log (*offline*) and a FO-PLTL formula, and outputs a boolean value for each position in the inputted trace. "LOGSCOPE" [30] checks, *offline*, software systems correctness properties expressed using a rule-based specification language over state machines. It is not very precise what type of state machine is created and processed. "LOGSCOPE" translates specifications into C++ monitors (that could carry data). "EventRaceCommander" [31] repairs in web applications (*online*), event race errors, a kind of safety error.

States diagrams specifications are implemented as C++ program monitors using C++ library `yri_sd_runtime_verif`. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** outputs a developer given (by means of a callback function, as seen in 'line 15' in Listing 2) string message ¹ in case an accepting state was entered, and a trace event of YERITH-ERP-3.0 leading to it. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**'s monitors need not store data, as **DejaVu** monitors must. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** events also carry data (database table and column name, records quantity modified by current SUT event). Runtime monitors could be checked against programs written in any programming language or framework, as

long as they emit necessary SQL events to **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**.

¹'YRI_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF_Monitor_notify_SUCCESS_VERIFICATION'
in this paper motivating example in Figure 5.

Fig. 11: A Mealy Machine State Diagram Specified Using `yri_sd_runtime_verif` Specification Language.

```

1. yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec yri_missing_department
2. {
3.   START_STATE(d):NOT_IN_PRE(YRI_ASSET,department.department_name)
4.   ->[in_sql_event_log('DELETE.department.YRI_ASSET',STATE(d))]/'SELECT.department'->
5.     ERROR_STATE(e):IN_POST(YRI_ASSET,stocks.department_name).
6. }

```

Fig. 12: 'YERITH_QVGE' model for the example specification in Figure 11.

8 Conclusion And Future Work

This paper has presented a lightweight C++ Qt-DBus [32] tool to check a program against a runtime monitor using set interface operations (\in , \notin) on program statement: **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** doesn't generate false warnings; **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** specifications are *not desirable (forbidden) specifications (fail traces)*. Since the concurrent communication between **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** and a program occurs over the RPC (Remote Procedure Call) instance `DBus`, a runtime monitor could be checked against programs written in any programming language or framework, as long as they emit the necessary SQL events to **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**.

Future work would be a tool-chain to validate `yri_sd_runtime_verif` models as represented in this paper.

Also, the author of this paper has developed a graphical drawing tool (`YERITH_QVGE`) for in Section 2 defined state diagrams. A model of `YERITH_QVGE` is shown in Figure 12. It is an extension of the FOSS (Free and Open Source Software) Qt `Graphviz` [33] drawing tool `QVGE` [34]. `YERITH_QVGE` generates, from a model, an input file for the compiler `yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang_comp`.

Listing 4: 'DO_VERIFY_AND_or_CHECK_ltl_PROPERTY': YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF's overridden method for processing SUT event stream C++ pseudo-code.

```

1  bool DO_VERIFY_AND_or_CHECK_ltl_PROPERTY(
2      QString sql_table_NAME,
3      SQL_CONSTANT_IDENTIFIER cur_SQL_command)
4  {
5      switch (cur_SQL_command)
6      {
7          case SELECT:
8
9              if ("department" == sql_table_NAME)
10             {
11                 return YRI_trigger_an_edge_event("select.department");
12             }
13             break;
14
15             default:
16                 break;
17         }
18     }
19     return false;
20 }

```

A Processing of SUT Event Stream By An Analysis Client

B YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF SPECIFICATION LANGUAGE

Listing 4 illustrates the pseudo-code of **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** SUT event processing method 'DO_VERIFY_AND_or_CHECK_ltl_PROPERTY'. An analysis client must first override method 'DO_VERIFY_AND_or_CHECK_ltl_PROPERTY' of class 'YRI_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF_Monitor' so to implement a checking algorithm for each event received from SUT, as for instance the events illustrated in Figure 2 of the motivating example.

The analysis client then calls method 'YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)' of class 'YRI_CPP_RUNTIME_MONITOR' of C++ library yri_sd_runtime_verif for each corresponding state diagram transition event.

Fig. 13: Grammar in Backus–Naur Form (BNF) of `yri_sd_runtime_verif` Mealy Machine State Diagram Specification Language.

```

<specification> ::= yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec '{' <mealy-automaton-spec> '}'
<mealy-automaton-spec> ::= <sut-state-spec>
                        | <sut-state-spec> '→' <sut-edge-state-spec>
<sut-edge-state-spec> ::= <sut-edge-mealy-automaton-spec> '→' <mealy-automaton-spec>
<sut-edge-mealy-automaton-spec> ::= <edge-mealy-automaton-guard-cond> <event-call>
<edge-mealy-automaton-guard-cond> ::= /* empty */ '/' | '[' <trace-specification> ']' '/'
<trace-specification> ::= <in-sql-event-log> | <not-in-sql-event-log> | <in-set-trace> | <not-in-set-trace>
<sut-state-spec> ::= <start-state-property-spec>
                  | <start-state-property-spec> ':' <algebra-set-specification>
                  | <state-property-spec> ':' <algebra-set-specification>
                  | <final-state-property-spec> ':' <algebra-set-specification>
                  | <final-state-auto-property-spec> ':' <algebra-set-specification> ':'
                  <recovery-sql-query-spec>
<algebra-set-specification> ::= <in-algebra-set-spec> | <not-in-algebra-set-spec>
<in-algebra-set-spec> ::= <in-spec> '(' <prog-variable> ',' <db-table> '.' <db-column> ')'
                       | <in-spec-nop> '(' ')'
<not-in-algebra-set-spec> ::= <not-in-spec> '(' <prog-variable> ',' <db-table> '.' <db-column> ')'
                          | <not-in-spec-nop> '(' ')'
<in-sql-event-log> ::= in_sql_event_log '(' <event-call> ',' <state-property-specification> ')'
<not-in-sql-event-log> ::= not_in_sql_event_log '(' <event-call> ',' <state-property-specification> ')'
<in-set-trace> ::= in_set_trace '(' <event-call> ',' <state-property-specification> ')'
<not-in-set-trace> ::= not_in_set_trace '(' <event-call> ',' <state-property-specification> ')'
<in-spec> ::= IN_BEFORE | IN_AFTER
           | IN_PRE | IN_POST
<in-spec-nop> ::= IN_POST_NOP
<not-in-spec> ::= NOT_IN_BEFORE | NOT_IN_AFTER
              | NOT_IN_PRE | NOT_IN_POST
<not-in-spec-nop> ::= NOT_IN_POST_NOP
<start-state-property-spec> ::= START_STATE '(' AlphaNum ')'
<state-property-spec> ::= STATE '(' AlphaNum ')'
<final-state-property-spec> ::= END_STATE '(' AlphaNum ')'
                             | FINAL_STATE '(' AlphaNum ')'
                             | ERROR_STATE '(' AlphaNum ')'
<final-state-auto-property-spec> ::= END_STATE_AUTO '(' AlphaNum ')'
                                   | FINAL_STATE_AUTO '(' AlphaNum ')'
                                   | ERROR_STATE_AUTO '(' AlphaNum ')'
<recovery-sql-query-spec> ::= recovery_sql_query '(' <db-table> ',' <sql-recovery-query> ')'
<sql-recovery-query> ::= String
<event-call> ::= String
<prog-variable> ::= AlphaNum
<db-table> ::= AlphaNum
<db-column> ::= AlphaNum

```

Fig. 14: YERITH-ERP-3.0 Maintenance Verification Interface.

C YERITH-ERP-3.0 MAINTENANCE VERIFICATION INTERFACE

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University of Waterloo
 200 University Ave. West
 Waterloo Ontario
 Canada
 N2L3G1

Graduate Official Transcript

Jeffrey M. Caelli
 Associate Vice-President
 Graduate Studies
 and Postdoctoral Affairs

Name: **Noumbissi Noundou, Xavier**
 Student ID: **20284586**
 Ontario Education Nbr: **445938806**

Beginning of Graduate Record

Fall 2009

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 1.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
ECE 725	Computer-Aided Verification	0.50	0.50	90

Winter 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 2.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 3.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 4.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 5.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2011

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 6.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
CS 744	Advanced Compiler Design	0.50	0.50	86

Fall 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 7.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2012

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 8.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

University of Waterloo
 200 University Ave. West
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Graduate Official Transcript

Duffin M. Caell
 Associate Vice-President
 Graduate Studies
 and Postdoctoral Affairs

Name: **Noumbissi Noundou, Xavier**
 Student ID: **20284586**
 Ontario Education Nbr: **445938806**

Winter 2013

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 9.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
CS 846	Advanced Topics in Software Engineering	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Program Analysis of Web Apps			

Spring 2013

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 10.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
ECE 750	Special Topics in Computer Software	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Static Analysis for Softwr Eng			

Fall 2013

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 11.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2014

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 12.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2014

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 13.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2014

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 14.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2015

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 15.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	WD
Withdrawal Date: 04/30/2015				

Milestones

Program: **Engineering Doctoral**
PhD Comprehensive Examination
 Status: **Completed**
 Date Completed: **12/20/2011**
 Grade: **CR**

End of Graduate Official Transcript

University of Waterloo
 200 University Ave. West
 Waterloo Ontario
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 N2L3G1

Graduate Official Transcript

Duffin M. Caell
 Associate Vice-President
 Graduate Studies
 and Postdoctoral Affairs

Name: Noubissi Noundou, Xavier
Student ID: 20284586
Ontario Education Nbr: 445938806

Beginning of Graduate Record

Fall 2009

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 1.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
ECE 725	Computer-Aided Verification	0.50	0.50	90

Winter 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 2.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 3.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 4.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 5.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 6.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
CS 744	Advanced Compiler Design	0.50	0.50	86

Fall 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 7.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2012

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 8.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

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Name: Noubissi Noundou, Xavier
Student ID: 20284586
Ontario Education Nbr: 445938806

Winter 2013

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 9.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
CS 846	Advanced Topics in Software Engineering	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Program Analysis of Web Apps			

Spring 2013

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 10.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
ECE 750	Special Topics in Computer Software	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Static Analysis for Softwr Eng			

Fall 2013

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 11.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 12.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 13.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 14.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2015

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 15.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	WD

Withdrawal Date: 04/30/2015

Milestones

Program: Engineering Doctoral
 PhD Comprehensive Examination
 Status: Completed
 Date Completed: 12/20/2011
 Grade: CR

End of Graduate Official Transcript

CONTRAT DE BAIL PROFESSIONNEL

Entre les soussignés :

Monsieur NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU Xavier, Ingénieur-informaticien demeurant à Douala, Tél : 697 19 49 06 / 652 39 69 50. E-mail : yerith.xavier@gmail.com, titulaire de la CNI n° 20190212230510554, délivré le 15/04/2019 à LT 09 ;

Ci-après désigné le « Bailleur » d'une part ;

Et

La Société **GLOBAL EXPERT SOLUTION Sarl**, dont le siège social est fixé à Douala Cité des Palmiers, BP : 236 Douala, pris en la personne de son représentant légal en la personne de **MELEU NOSSI BELVIANNE**, née le ... 18/12/1989 ... à ... DOUALA ... fille de ... NOSSI JEAN ... et de ... MATLANG BIE titulaire de la CNI n° ... 10/14/64/255 ... délivrée le ... 17/12/2019 à ... DLA BONABER Tél : 694 913 365 / 682 766 081 ;

Ci-après désigné le « Preneur » d'autre part ;

IL A ETE CONVENU ET ARRETE ENTRE LES PARTIES CE QUI SUIT :

Le Bailleur loue par les présentes, au Preneur qui accepte, un immeuble bâti dont la désignation suit, aux clauses et conditions ci-dessous :

Article 1 : Désignation

Un appartement composé de plusieurs pièces sis à la cité de Palmiers lieu-dit Haute tension. Il n'est pas fait plus amples descriptions, le preneur déclarant l'avoir visité et connu parfaitement les lieux.

Article 2 : Durée

La durée du bail est d'une année (01) ans qui prend effet à compter du 02 Novembre 2024 et prend fin au 1^{er} Novembre 2025 et non renouvelable ;

Article 3 : Usage

Les lieux, objets du présent contrat sont destinés exclusivement au commerce. (nature du commerce) Toute destination autre donnée à cet immeuble sans l'accord écrit du bailleur est interdite.

Article 4 : Etat Des Lieux

Le preneur prend l'immeuble en l'état et fera l'objet d'un constat contradictoire pas un Huissier de Justice. Les parties constatent contradictoirement l'état des lieux et le

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preneur l'accepte sans réserve. Il s'engage en outre à le garder en bon père de famille jusqu'au terme du bail.

Le preneur n'est pas autorisé à faire des transformations ou changer la forme ou la structure de l'immeuble sauf sur accord écrit du bailleur. A la fin du bail, il pourra avec l'accord du bailleur remettre l'immeuble à son état initial ou laisser ces transformations sans aucune compensation du bailleur.

Article 5 : Cession Et Sous- Location

Le Preneur ne peut ni sous - louer ni céder le présent bail à un tiers à titre gratuit ou onéreux sans l'avis écrit du bailleur.

En cas de sous - location, il est précisé de toutes façons que le Preneur restera directement responsable du paiement des loyers, ainsi que des impôts divers pouvant notamment provenir des réparations locatives ou de remise en état.

Article 6 : Assurances

Le Preneur s'engage à assurer les lieux loués contre les risques locatifs, notamment l'incendie et l'explosion, les dégâts des eaux, le recours des voisins et des tiers. Cette assurance qui se fera auprès d'une compagnie acceptée par le preneur devra être maintenue pendant toute la durée du bail.

Article 7 : Visite Des Lieux

Le Preneur devra laisser le bailleur, ses représentants ou préposés visiter les lieux loués chaque fois qu'ils le jugeront nécessaire, à charge pour le Bailleur d'en prévenir le Preneur par tout moyen à sa convenance vingt-quatre heures (24) à l'avance de cette visite. Le preneur s'engage à donner libre accès au bailleur à cette occasion et sans aucune forme d'entrave.

Article 8 : Réparation et travaux dans L'immeuble

Le Bailleur a la charge des grosses réparations notamment de construction, et de surélévation. Il peut les effectuer en cours de bail si ceux - ci deviennent nécessaires. Le preneur accepte de souffrir (sans aucune contrepartie ou indemnité) des incommodités ou inconfort causés sur tout ou partie de l'immeuble pendant l'exécution des grosses réparations qui incombent au bailleur.

Le Preneur devra aviser immédiatement le Bailleur de toutes grosses réparations à la charge de ce dernier dont il sera à même de constater la nécessité, sous peine d'être tenu pour responsable de toute aggravation résultant de son silence ou de son retard.

Le Preneur est tenu des réparations locatives, d'entretien et de maintenance. En dehors des réparations occasionnées par un cas de force majeur ou de la vétusté de l'immeuble, il est tenu des dégradations et des pertes qui arrivent par le fait des personnes de sa maison, ses agents et préposés.

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Article 9 : Eau – Electricité

Le Preneur fera son affaire personnelle, ses abonnements auprès des concessionnaires d'eau et d'électricité ainsi que du paiement de ses factures de consommation sans que le bailleur en soit inquieté.

S'il advenait que les concessionnaires viennent à enlever leurs compteurs à raison du non-paiement de leurs fournitures par le Preneur, celui-ci supportera dans leur intégralité les frais de coupure, de repose du compteur, et autres frais liés directement ou indirectement à cette situation.

Article 10 : Loyer

Le bail est consenti et accepté pour un loyer mensuel de FCFA 90 000 (Quatre-vingt-dix mille francs) net de toute charge et prestation. Ce loyer est payable annuellement et d'avance. Il est payable en espèces entre les mains du bailleur ou de ses agents, préposés dûment désignés par lui.

A la signature du présent contrat, une somme de F CFA 720 000 (SEPT CENT VINGT MILLE) est versée au bailleur et dont quittance est donnée par les présentes, représentant 8 mois de loyer.

Lorsque le paiement se fait par chèque, il n'est effectif qu'à la date à laquelle le compte du bailleur est effectivement crédité.

Article 11 : Dépôt De Garantie/Caution

Le preneur dépose à la signature des présentes, une caution de FCFA 90 000 (Quatre-vingt mille francs) FCFA. Cette caution constitue la garantie pour couvrir toute destruction ou charge non couverte par le preneur, de ses agents ou de ses préposés au moment de la libération de l'immeuble.

La caution ne sera restituée au preneur à la fin du bail, si n'a pu être utilisée comme il est dit au paragraphe précédent, qu'en cas de justificatifs de règlements des dernières factures d'eau et d'électricité.

Bien entendu, les derniers loyers et autres frais locatifs accessoires ne pourront en aucun cas s'imputer sur le dépôt de garantie.

Article 12 : révision du loyer

Les parties conviennent que le bailleur réserve le droit de réviser le montant du loyer à au renouvellement du bail. Cette révision sera en fonction des usages à Douala, ou en fonction de la formule indiciaire applicable. La révision pourra en outre, tenir compte de la conjoncture économique, eu égard au renchérissement du prix des matériaux de construction sur le marché et de l'offre de bail en cours.

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Le bailleur devra toutefois faire connaître son intention de réviser le bail soit au moins (1) mois avant la fin de la période de bail en cours ou en cours de l'exécution du bail renouvelé avec un différé d'un mois au moins pour la prise d'effet dans ce dernier cas.

Article 13 : Restitution Des Locaux - Remise Des Clés

A l'expiration du bail, le Preneur restituera les locaux à l'état initial d'occupation. Le sort des transformations éventuelles y effectuées avec l'accord du bailleur seront déterminés ainsi qu'il est dit à l'article 4.

Le preneur remettra promptement les clés au bailleur. Tout retard occasionné à cet effet et du fait du preneur entrainera une indemnité d'au moins égale à un mois du dernier loyer. En outre, toute réclamation du solde de la caution ne sera exigible qu'après remise effective des clés au bailleur et production des justificatifs de règlements des dernières factures d'eau et d'électricité, si celui-ci n'a pu être utilisé pour la réfection de l'immeuble dégradé par le preneur ou ses préposés.

Article 14 : Règlement Urbains Et De L'immeuble

Le preneur est tenu de satisfaire à toutes prescriptions de la police, de voirie municipale, d'hygiène et de salubrité pendant le cours du bail.

Article 16 : Impôts - Droit D'enregistrement

Le Preneur est tenu de s'acquitter exactement des impôts et droits d'enregistrement existant à raison de son occupation des lieux loués. En particulier, il sera tenu pour responsable du paiement dans les délais des droits d'enregistrement dus à l'établissement du présent bail ainsi qu'à chaque renouvellement.

Les parties conviennent que la remise des clés au preneur pour son occupation effective de l'immeuble n'interviendra qu'après l'enregistrement du présent bail ou la remise des frais d'enregistrement au bailleur.

Article 17 : Tolérances

Toutes les tolérances de la part du bailleur, qu'elles qu'en aient pu être la fréquence et la durée au sujet des clauses et conditions du présent contrat ne pourront jamais être considérées comme y apportant modifications ou suppression, ni génératrices d'un droit quelconque. Le bailleur pourra toujours y mettre fin à tout moment.

Article 18 : Clauses Résolutoires- Compétence

Le présent bail sera résilié de plein droit si bon semble au bailleur dans les cas suivants :

En cas de non-respect d'une seule clause ou de non-paiement d'un seul mois/terme de loyer, le présent contrat de bail sera résilié de plein droit, après une mise en demeure

jh-nissi

d'un mois rester sans effet. d'avoir à respecter la ou les clauses du bail violées, notifiées au preneur par acte extrajudiciaire ou par tout moyen laissant trace écrite.

En cas de résiliation, le bailleur pourra en cas de refus par le Preneur de libérer les lieux, obtenir l'expulsion de ce dernier et de tous ceux qui tiennent de son chef par simple Ordonnance du juge statuant à bref délai (juge des référés), sans préjudice des dommages - intérêts.

Les parties attribuent à cet effet compétence de juridiction aux tribunaux de première instance de Douala Ndokoti du lieu de situation de l'immeuble loué pour tout a litige qui surviendrait de l'exécution du présent contrat de bail.

La possibilité d'un règlement à l'amiable de tout différend né de l'exécution du présent contrat est toujours ouverte à la partie la plus diligente.

Articles 17 : Election De Domicile

Pour l'exécution des présentes et de leurs suites y compris la signification de tous actes, les parties élisent respectivement leur domicile, pour le bailleur à son siège social, et pour le preneur dans les lieux loués.

Fait à Douala en quatre exemplaires originaux, le 26 Novembre 2024

P/LE BAILLEUR

Dr. -Ing. Nounou

P/ LE PRENEUR

- "**DATEUR, KEMAJOU**" Cameroon's gendarmerie colonel indic PAULETTE AZEFA tried to ASSASSINATE myself, openly, in front of at least 7 people, on Yaounde street, on January 09th, 2024.
- Kemajou spouses talk to people walking across roads that they shalln't perform christian cross-signs since these interrupts sorcery they are doing on people walking on roads (June 3rd, 2024).
- Secret (hidden) orders of any type SHALL be out of civilian society.
- Cameroon SHALL DEACTIVATE any kind of army soldiers estate, as SWITZERLAND has done in the past.
- Its not a good idea to judge people based on suspicious behavior, and not, real proven or not lived really facts.
- ROSE sangnou, a BIRTH GIVER of mine, SHALLN'T ANYMORE be causing so much trouble into my life because she entertains a rostricrucian affair with Prof. Dr. rer. pol. JEAN-CLAUDE SHANDA-TONME; AND with 'DORIS beteubang Gweh', 'tchitchui-teuntchou-noumeni-ingrède-ingrid-Chandriand', 'Hugues Ntomani Tiako'; 'Dr. Henriette Pola', and her spouse 'Dr. Laurent tchandeu'.
- People such as KEMAJOU, who acts as a colonel gendarmerie of Cameroon army ARE ALWAYS TRYING to overcome criminal laws of Geneva.
- I don't want to be living with people who has as profession the killing of other people.
- Rose sangnou sister, (Justice) DOROTHEE SHANDA NDJATIE, HAS TRIED to kill me by police force illegally in February 2021, as I have a file on judge HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA at DOUALA-ndokoti JUSTICE Palace ! • LAQUINTINE'S Psychiatrist EYOUN CHRISTIAN, MD, was involved together with 8 other persons at night around 11 : 30PM so to hijack my privately owned property in Douala-CITÉ-DES-PALMIERS. • JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMAI from same tribal tribe as ACCUSED psychiatrist main offender (sawa-douala) ! • IT SEEMS "Dr christian eyoum, MD" the corrupted CPDM psychiatrist wanted myself to be sodomized by "BERTRAND" who broke the seal of my gate in steel.
- CIA (Central Intelligence Agency) shalln't hire anymore incompetent persons like "Peter Alan Burth" 'Emmanuel-dobaleba-faux-pasteur' 'Brigitte-ekindi' 'magne-narcisse-qc-satan' 'robert-billy-joe-bob-tabet-depse-pd' 'NDZIE' 'PRC-présidence de la république du Cameroun' 'CHAPELLE DE LA GLOIRE DE CHRIST - marc denis djeng djeng - alias pasteur marc' 'jp-kamgain' 'psy-acteur-Eboungue (ing. pétrolier)' 'EMMANUEL-idoit; hors-mis agent-immobilier-soumbil (6 90 60 75 63)' 'santaire;SAPEUR-POMPIER-de-malheur-anti-gang;civil;indic-gendarme-policier-uniforme-medic' 'NORBERT ichatar' 'Bitoungi (douanes)' 'David Moniaux' 'Aurélie Yagno Kamdoun' 'DR. FOSSO-séd' 'Soot-canadian' 'sarah-landy-canadian-citizen' 'tchangoue-labforge.ca' 'carine-alias-edith - LELÉ - NJOUGEP - TCHANA' 'Julien-mboutou; santé publique' 'Dan Wasula doua' so called pastor baptist church 'KAMGA adamo - demon' 'Cameroon-chief-of-state; CAMEROUN:' 'SANDRINE yimbu' 'CHENGWA' 'DJOMO-Sawa-gilles-ézéchiel' 'didi-ruben' 'mama-fouda' 'INES ngakou' 'Serge Achille Popoussi NONO - sed - cmr' '[ingrède-tchitchui-noumbissi;ingrid-tchitchui-noumbissi;ingrède-teuntchou-noumeni;ingrid-teuntchou-noumeni]; [NROUBANG] (djomo) [TCHUDDJANG-séd-pré] [NGONGANG] Hôpital Jamró' 'assassins;dégingués.' 'LAURENT-tchandeu-henriette-pola' 'VOUFFO manuela-psy-malade-mentale' 'alain-elame' 'francis magloire come nkoulou' 'ZOUMPÉ-jacky-diane' 'Pélagie METOUMO, epse tchouoto; hors-mis maître Pélagie METOUMO, epse tchouoto' 'BIYA (Paul et Chantal en particulier)' 'DAMIERCHRYSLER AG' 'Belvianne meleu nossi' 'Jean LOÏC sieve' 'GLOBAL EXPERT SOLUTION Sarl' 'maman THÉRESE de OMEGA-kom-sipa-eric-joël.' 'rigobert; géomètre; JEAN-bernard de OMEGA-kom-sipa-eric-joël.' 'Synclair NJEUTCHA TCHANA; hors-mis maître Synclair NJEUTCHA TCHANA' 'BRYAN-tchamaha-ntaata-italie' 'SALIOU MOUSSA-pd' 'Afana' 'Taurecia GmbH-bavaria' 'magne-bakam-bir-dgré-séd-cameroun' 'BIR - emanèl-nkoa-marcelin-pierre - capitaine-mbida-dsp - mado-sœur emane-ETOGA' 'Brice sime (afirland-first-bank)' 'GUTTFEMBERG' 'tchamaha ntaata' 'Sylvanie MFEUKEN' 'ANICET Mfeukem' 'WANDJI ngongang Théodore' 'COLONEL eloundou-séd' 'Colonel EMILE bankou (semil-séd)' 'Christopher NGOSONG (University of Buea)' 'Rainer and Gabrielle SCHULZE-SMIDT' 'Franck biya' 'M. ongoué (S2TBED-biya-franck)' 'David (GATE SOLUTION CENTER)' 'KREYENHOP (BLG logistics, CDU politicians)' 'Achilles Kouam (PAUL fokam kammgone)' 'Thierry Nyamen (Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.)' 'catholic-church' 'Criminal-DST.' 'MOISE-yamkam-tebiwo' 'REZA kopae (riskview inc.)' 'Thomas NDIE DJOTIO' 'Christelle-akamba-ét-autres-noms-de-akamba' 'VALERIE' 'ALT LE PLUS' 'Nestor KENPACK (N.K. quincallierie)' 'atanga-nji-paul' 'Daniela-siemens-OCS-erlangen' 'Menguéné Mvindi' 'TCHIEUFFA' 'Audrey NGUETTE tchanga' 'MBA-Claude bisseg' 'samaneh navabpour; amirhossein vakili' 'JHANE-ayachi' 'ZABER-algérien-bremen' 'DZUKOU-tate-foiso-oliviane' 'ROSTAND-moungam' 'KOM-marcel-rostand-mepo' 'Irene-ines-ngakou-temou-FAINEANTE' 'suisse-bordellerie' 'VANELLE-JUNIOR-laure AZEFA-gang' 'GODRICK chekete H.' 'pateur Landry' 'Eric Joël KOM SIPA' 'Grégoire Owona (CPDM general secretary)' 'SANGO (Spouse Bernadette NOUOUNDOU(CMR-dgré)' 'gendarme essono en civil (iloga-iloga-aurelien)' 'GÉNÉRAL DE CORPS D'ARMÉE boubba.' 'consortium-conrad-black-ROTHSCHILD' 'GALAX-YVES-LANBRY-ETOGA-chien' 'jean-yang-CMU' 'HOGA-HOGA-AURELIEN' 'BORIS tossou; mbuembe-kevina-laure.' 'mezang-atome INGRID.' 'TOM ball-mrs' 'maître-docteurs-professeurs.' 'JEAN-pierre moubé' 'Chef-supérieur-douala.deido.-3ème degré' 'CHRISTIAN eyoum; laquintine; psy' 'SHANDA NDJATIE' 'MAXIME napoa eteme' 'sandy-séd-beidu; jo-ate' 'joanne atvé' 'chauffeurs-soudours-souffleurs-gardiens-jaune-SARL-société' (so called baptist church pastor) 'Dr. PAUL simon nomo, Psy.D.' 'Majeed Mike (quantstamp.com)' 'LEO passos (quantstamp.com)' 'Iuc; masc. hypolithe tekeu.' 'Eunice GAPEI Yemé' 'Yves Francis DANTEU' 'TEUNTCHOU-chandriand-noumen' 'Winnie-shanda-joël.' 'Alexis TCHIEUYAP' 'Gervais Nana' 'JEAN CLAUDE SHANDA TONME' 'JACKSON-séd-njeutcha (Conqute.)' 'Jean-Paul YAMTICHE (Afirland first bank; Intelligensia)' 'BISSCKE; nkondo-sodomiseur' 'JEAN-PIERRE kamgain' 'Bernadette NOUOUNDOU, Epse SANGO (cmr-dgré)' 'agent-santé.' 'Gailie-idoite-dodo.' 'RAOUL Prince njonkep (SED)' 'ERIC BODEN' 'Prof. Dr. Xavier Sieve Noundou (CMR-dgré)' 'Me. André Édoucké' 'Michelle mvondo-psy;biya-regime' 'JULES neta noundou - (cmr-dgré)' 'temp FABRICE-WILFRIED-siemens-canadian-armed-forces; Prof. Dr. med. Norbert SIEMEN (CMR-séd)' 'Pharmacy fiango-ngoe-peter-ARUME' 'Ondréj Lhoták' 'Dr. Chantal NOUOUNDOU, Epse ... (cmr DGRE)' 'ANNIE METIAM' 'terreur - ;HONORÉ WOUCHÉ' 'POKAM-KWAM' 'Serge, jérusalem apostolat' 'NOUMBISSI' 'Guimezap' 'GEORGETTE' 'Victor Noundou Koliou cmr-séd' 'CHRISTIAN rikong ngyeung' 'Hilaire-yimidoj-bertrand-nguere; ancien-séd-gras-savoys' 'igic-clovis-telecom-assassin; 'CLOVIS-kemmegne' 'Jeanne M'VONDO' 'CHETA' 'rodrigue-alain-siemens-ngongang' 'angela WOLFGANG fermannd JR owona' 'fanfan (GAUTHIER) SHANDA tonme' 'DR. GADJEU francis aimé tchana' 'lute' 'Patrick lam, Ph.D., P.Eng.' 'JON eyolffson' 'Prof. Dr. rer. nat. Jan Peleska' 'Patrick'; ALL-others to try to kill humble black engineers and scientists.
- People like PAUL BIYA shalln't be called president of all Cameroon anymore because as CPDM ruling party, they harass people that don't call themselves from RDPC!

CONTACT

- Address: YECEFOIQ - "Immeuble YERITH"- barrière - Simbock, Mfoundi 6, Yaounde, Cameroon
- located opposite side of Biya's S2TBED forestry society (since 2015 officially) !
- Email: Yerith.Xavier@gmail.com

CITIZENSHIP ; PLACE OF BIRTH

Cameronian 🇨🇲, no other citizenship ; Douala (Littoral, Cameroon)

UPLOADED a copy of national id (N.20190242230510554) onto "https://www.facebook.com" this year 2024.

TEACHING STATEMENT

- [Teaching] and [Advising] is my priority at time since in Cameroon Software inception is very long and tedious because Cameroon authorities, Especially SED.
- My 1st professor and best educator is [prof. dr. rer. nat. habil. JAN-peleska], at the University of Bremen, Bremen, Germany; The 1st best teacher as of now was "prof. dr. ULRICH KRAUSE-dépse, at the University of Bremen; as well"; THE 1st best leader & 2nd best teacher as of now was "Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick] Lam, at the [University of Waterloo, ONTARIO, CANADA]".
- I endeavor to teach what makes my research vivid ["RM: Program Software Runtime Monitoring"] and useful for young and adult people around the world; I can teach almost everything in Computer Sciences; I haven't practiced Computer Graphics, and Computer Imaging programming at all.

RESEARCHING GOALS IN COMPUTER SOFTWARE ENGINEERING - [CONTINUED]

- Create a very cheap and pragmatic Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) software: (e.g. [YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM\(?\)](#)).
- CREATE a market place where stock exchanges occur real-time; [YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME] is used as platform for valuation of stocks; And for stock exchanges. THE market place is a physical place in "YERITH-R&D building"; THE physical stock exchanges occur outside of "YERITH-R&D building"; just a plot of land '5 meters' away on the opposite side of road leading to "YERITH R&D" !
- CREATE a computing device for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF that will be a certified product with at least ISO, and CE stamps : [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET]; See also Fig. 22.

PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING ASSOCIATIONS MEMBERSHIPS

- Current: "acm: The Association for Computing Machinery"; "FME: Formal Methods Europe"; "ASQ: American Society for Quality".

PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING LITERATURE REVIEWS

- OOPSLA 2010

PROFESSIONAL INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOPS AND CONFERENCES

- IMRT radiation therapy at SIEMENS OCS Erlangen-BAVARIA-Germany 2008; [FSE-soqua 2006]; PLDI 2009; IBM CASCON 2010; MITACS ONTARIO 2012; PLDI 2012

PROFESSIONAL RESEARCH CONTRIBUTIONS / INTERESTS

- [JUDICIAL information] | [PUBLICATIONS] | [Figures] | [Tables] | [Trang] | [TALKS] | [Latest] | [Resume / CV - Overview] | [Engineering Methodologies & Tools Expertise] | Publications list on "www.zenodo.org" | Publications list on "www.archive.org"
- Operating System Debian Linux Distribution Contribution for customers of ["YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0"](#); "YERITH-NISSI". Bash; DEBIAN LINUX; Jan. 2017 -
- ERP-trading Stock Exchange Software: [YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0\(?\)](#); [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](#) C++; Qt 5; Mar. 2015 -
- Software Engineering-Formal Methods [?] | [Ic] / Software Validation / Software Verification CASE tools [YRI_QVGE\[24.24\]](#), [RT-Tester](#), [MBT\[1b\]](#)]
- Software Testing [22.22] (also with "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH") [YRI_QVGE\[1b\]](#), [MASTER THESIS(?), [RT-Tester](#), [MBT\[1b\]](#)], [JUNIT 4 Tutorial\[1\]](#)]
- A. Web [JAVA Dynamic Taint Analysis\[3\]](#) | Qt 5-Designer as WYSIWYG Tool | Development (YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0) | Cyber-Safety | Security
 - JudoDB, with "Dr. Patrick Lam (doctor-Ph.D. advisor of mine)"; [git https://github.com/patricklam/judodb](#) GWT, PHP; JAVA; June 2014 - Nov. 2014
 - [WEB Cyber-Security\[2\]](#) [?] [3] [?] (PLG SEMINAR AT DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)
- C. Information Flow Policy Control; Typstate-API usage rule checking; [Dynamic Program Analysis Monitoring](#)
 - [A Runtime Monitoring Mealy Machine C++ library](#); [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](#) C++; Qt 5; June 2022 -
 - [Algorithmic trading \[13.13.7\]](#) | [YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of \[GUI\] Software at Runtime](#)
FOSS Code location, EXCEPT for commercial CASE drawing tool : [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](#) C++; Qt-Dbus; June 2022 -
 - [A Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus](#); [git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis](#) JAVA; Firebug; Jan. 2013 - Apr. 2013
- D. [Static Program Code Analysis Verification; Compilers; Verifiable DSL \(Verifiable Domain-Specific Languages\)](#)
 - 20.20 Open Source (FOSS) Contribution to "Valkyrie: Valgrind-GUI"; [git https://github.com/yerothd/valkyrie_NON_OFFICIAL](#) C++; Qt 5; July 2023 -
 - 1d [Vordiplom-B.Sc. Independent Study: A Semantic Comparison between Timed Automata and Büchi Automata](#) Set-Algebra; Sep. 2004 - Dec. 2004
 - 34 [Ph.D. disser: A Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM](#); [git https://github.com/AmesianX/saint](#) LLVM; C++; JAVA
 - 1d [A State Diagram Mealy Machine Description Language](#); [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang](#) flex, bison; Apr. 2023 -
 - 32 [JAVA static code analysis \[34\]](#) | [Ph.D. thesis: Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software](#) LLVM; SOOT; JAVA

SUMMER SCHOOL PARTICIPATION — HIGHLIGHTS — [CONTINUED]

- "Management Psy Human Resource Course" - Collège Integ, Douala, Littoral, Cameroun — Taught by "Dr. Jean Moubé, Psy.D." Jan. 2020 - June 2020

CHEIFTAENCY / MISCELLANEOUS

- KING YERITH-NISSI. (Prophet of Jeovah-nissi, "Isaiah 45" (SINCE nov. 14; 2014) in HOLY BIBLE, PAROLE DE VIE-(Amis pour toujours) - French language)
- I also act as a Prophet described in "Apocalypse 12".
- I also act as a Prophet described in "Apocalypse 1", named "Fidèle, et Véritable".
- Creator and Professor at YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE), a subsidiary of YERITH R&D
- "High Qualified Person-migrant in CANADA (Québec, then Ontario) for 9 years until August 2014".
- Driving license class B - Cameroon & Canada

PROFESSIONAL TOOLS AND PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES

- **Operating Systems:** MS Windows (XP, 98, 2000, 7, 10, 11), DEBIAN LINUX (8, 9, 10, 11, 12)
- **SCM (Source Code Version Management Tools):** Git, Mercurial (hg), SVN, Rational ClearCase
- **Web Technologies:** YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0, MariaDB, HTML5, CSS, PHP, Quercus, Apache Tomcat, GWT (Google Web Toolkit), JSP
- **Scripting Languages:** Cygwin, Python, sed, AWK, Bash
- **Programming languages, Debugging, and Testing Analysis tools:** YRI_QVGE[13.13], UML 2.0, SCALA, JAVA, C/C++, JUnit-5, DDD, Gcov, VALKYRIE YERITH[20.20], LTSA
- **Programming & Compiler Frameworks:** DIFF, Patch, Tx1, apache ANT, MAKE, Qt 5, SOOT, LLVM, flex, bison, Eclipse IDE, Codeblocks, CharmNT

UNIVERSITY LEVEL TEACHING (AS A TEACHING ASSISTANT PH.D. CANDIDATE; THEN A "DOCTOR-PHD")

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA (OCTOBER 2009 – APRIL 2015)

- **Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465) | Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650) | Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651) | Programming for Performance (ECE 459) | Computer Networks (ECE 428) | Compilers (ECE 351) | [C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)].**

ACADEMY WORK RESEARCH EXPERIENCE – 1

- **Start-up YERITH R&D, Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON** March 2025 – Currently
PROFESSOR PROFESSOR DOCTOR-ENGINEER (PR. PROF. DR-ING.) for Computer Engineering ([RESEARCH] & [TEACHING]), at YECEFOIQ, CEO
- **IUC (Institut Universitaire de la Côte), Douala, Littoral region, CAMEROON** 2019
Web Software Developer Consultant (NUMERHIS-ERP Web Application Development); advised by Hypolithe Tekeu, MASC
- **IAI (Institut Africain d'Informatique) Cameroon, Yaounde, Center, CAMEROON** 2016
Professor (Prof.) – Consulting Lecturer (Computer Architecture for Software Engineers in anglophone section); advised by: Ing. (B.Sc.) Salabessi (and Mr. Nanga)
- **Professional and Academic Degree [Ph.D. in Computer Science (Specialization : Programming Languages)]** March 10, 2015 !
University of Waterloo, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA
PhD Comprehensive Examination (DR-ING. (PhD)) – ECE-University of Waterloo December 20, 2011 !
PhD Research Seminar [TALK] – ECE-University of Waterloo April 16, 2014
PhD Dissertation Defence (Ph.D.) – CS-University of Waterloo January 2015
doctoral "Ph.D. degree" dissertation (Excerpt of Full not required text, by Patrick LAM, Ph.D.): *Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM*
(October 14, 2025) Addendum of co-related research in Program Analysis: *Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software by Program Analysis FOR Safety & Security* (https://www.archive.org/details/yerith-program-analysis-2023/YERITH-PROGRAM_ANALYSIS_2024_With_CURRICULUM_vitae_2024.pdf)
- **The University of Waterloo (ECE at WatForm), Ontario, CANADA** September 01, 2012 – March 10, 2015
Professor (PostDoctoral Fellow; Prof. – Expert in a domain of science) for Computer Engineering ([RESEARCH] & [TEACHING]) at ECE (program analysis & software testing research, and teaching (also related courses) | around \$2, 500 Canadian dollars for a term payment; 8 terms in total ≈ 2 – years.
"Graduate-student 1: Divam Jain (CS-MMATH, JAVA-SOOT) | Graduate-student 2: Zheng (Felix) Fang (ECE-MASc, Divam's research continuation) | [ALL STUDENTS]"
"Advisor 1: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Igor Ivkovic | Advisor 2: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Vijay Ganesh | Advisor 3: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Patrick Lam | Advisor 4: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Sivoththaman Siva"
"Colleague 1: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták | Colleague 2: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Nomair Naem | Colleague 3: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Fabrice Wilfried Siemeni | Colleague 4: Pr. Prof. Dr. Godrick H. Chékété | Colleague 5: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. mahesh tripunitara | Colleague 6: Pr. Prof. Dr. Derek Rayside | Colleague 7: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. LEO passos | | "Colleagues in christianity (Prof. Dr. Yaw Boakye-Agyeman, Nana Yaw, Eric Brefo-Mensah, Chiwanza Kasanga, Mushota Kasanga and spouse Timi) – -ATTENDED "koinonia church in bloomingdale, ON"; "apostle continuation church in brampton, ON"."
- **IBM CANADA Ltd., Markham, Ontario, CANADA (SABBATICAL-year from The-University-of-Waterloo-Ontario-Canada.)** January 01, 2012 – August 31, 2012
Thorough security check screening done for employment by employer IBM Canada LTD before starting employment.
Graduate Intern (JAVA-J9 Just-In-Time Compilation Optimization for IBM Websphere); advised by Prof. Vijay Sundaresan; and Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam
- **PROFESSIONAL (AND ACADEMIC) DEGREE. Doctor of Engineering (academic equivalent to a "doctoral PhD in Electrical and Computer Engineering") [D.ENG. (DR-ING. in "French")]** | around \$2, 500 Canadian dollars for a term payment; 7 terms in total ≈ 2 – years.
Engineering Doctoral Ph.D. degree Program (Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD) at The University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA September 01, 2009 – December 20, 2011 !
► **"DOCTOR-ENGINEER [DR-ING. (D.ENG. in "English")]" degree Program (Specialization : Software Engineering & Testing & Verification & Analysis)**
► **Successfully Passed PhD Comprehensive Examination on "December 20, 2011" – Overall Grade 88% [A+] Department of Electrical & Computer Engineering (ECE)**
Research Proposal (doctoral Ph.D. Thesis in Electrical and Computer Engineering): **Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software**
Mathematics Subject Classification: 68—Computer Science
Computer Science Subject Classification: Software Engineering, Program Verification, Program Analysis (static code analysis, dynamic program analysis)
Advisor 1: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Nomair Naem | Advisor 2: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták | Advisor 3: Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam | Advisor 4: Prof. Dr. Sivoththaman Siva
- **The University of Waterloo (ECE at WatForm), Ontario, CANADA** September 01, 2009 – December 20, 2011
Teaching Assistant & Research Assistant for Computer Software Engineering (program analysis (static code and dynamic analysis) research, and teaching assistantship in computer software engineering); Advised by Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, and Prof. Dr. Sivoththaman Siva
- **Post-Master Work with SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), Erlangen, Bayern, GERMANY** November 01 2007 – July 31 2009
Thorough security check screening done for employment by employer "SIEMENS AG" before starting employment.
Software-Engineer (Junior Software Developer) (CE-FDA certified software code development; Radiation Therapy DMIP communication control protocol C++ development); advised by: Ing. (M.Sc.) DARIO MERAVALIA, and Dipl.-Inf. (FH) GERHARD SENG.
- **PROFESSIONAL (AND ACADEMIC) DEGREE. Diplom-Informatiker (academic equivalent to a "Master 2 in Computer Science"; 270-ECTS points) | around \$400 Euros for a semester payment; 11 semesters including GERMAN language courses time included.**
I HAVE SACRED this diploma certificate (Duplicate by Prof. Dr-Ing. UTE bormann and Prof. Dr. Kerstin Schill; from November 01, 2017)" in front of BISHOP at St-Patrick Church in Toronto-downtown, ONTARIO, CANADA; just 3 weeks after resigning my shit-CANADIAN CITIZENSHIP at KITCHENER-WATERLOO criminal justice court [Living in Salvation Army Shelter near Justice Court.].
Integrated Bachelor's & Master's degree in Computer Science Program at The Elite-University of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY October 01, 2002 – May 25, 2007
► **"DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER" degree Program (Specialization : Software Engineering & Testing) – Grade 1.6/4 [A+] Department of Mathematics and Computer Science**
Diplomarbeit (Master Thesis): *Statistical test case generation for reactive systems* | Advisor: Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska
- **AGBS at The University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY** September 01, 2006 – February 28 2007
(Part-Time) Software System Developer (A 'UML 2.0 profile statecharts' plugin for 'Borland-Together'); advised by: Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska
- **"IMMIGRATION CANADA delivers myself a High Qualified Person-migrant permanent residency for CANADA"** 2005
FORMER-family member in Canada : "Théodore Wandji Ngongang (5850 Rue Souart Apt 7, H3S 2E8, Montreal, QC, Canada)"
I already passed my Bachelor's degree in CS ("Vordiplom in Informatik Certificate") before gaining High Qualified Person Permanent Resident Card
- **Bergmann Automaten GmbH (now Gewete GmbH), Rellingen, Hamburg, GERMANY** March 01, 2005 – April 31, 2007
(Part-Time) Software System Developer (WERKSTUDENT) (JAVA servlet and C++ communication protocol development); advised by: Dipl.-Ing. (FH) SVEN KAMRATH (and Dipl.-Ing. JENS MÖLLER)
- **ZMML at The University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY** February 01, 2003 – February 28, 2005
(Part-Time) WEB AND "RAD" APPLICATION DEVELOPER (Creating websites, and RAD-server self tests evaluation programs); advised by Prof. Dr. rer. pol. Klaus Jürgen Bönkost

CONVICTIONS ABOUT CIVIL SOCIETY – CONTINUED – 2

- CIA (Central Intelligence Agency) shalln't hire anymore incompetent persons like 'Jeanne-chantal andela;vendeuse-sauvette.' 'nguema;huissier-de-justice;tchopba' 'churches; in USA-abroad; or whatsoever similar; so-called humanitarianism.' 'road-seller; seller anywhere else' 'relatives' 'agent' 'SOLITA-voisine-sed' 'IRIS Mbieukop; pof;' 'agent-ministère-défense-cameroun.' 'YAGER MABOMA'; to try to kill humble black engineers and scientists.

FREE TIME HOBBIES

- Aikido, Swimming, and "Gospel Choir 'GEORGIA MASS CHOIR'" listening.

ACADEMY WORK RESEARCH EXPERIENCE – 2

- ~~HABILITATION, equivalent~~ • Topic: "Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime" June 01, 2022 – Currently
Start-up YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, CAMEROON
Proposal: YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime (Details at link 1)
- Start-up YEROTH R&D, Yaounde, CENTER region, CAMEROON October 2018 – November 2023
Software Verification & Validation Fellow, CEO
- Start-up Yeren Labs, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA September 2017 – September 2018
CTO (Chief Technology Officer), CEO
- Start-up Yeren, Yaounde, CENTER region, CAMEROON April 2015 – August 2017
CTO (Chief Technology Officer), CEO
- × [PKFokam Research Institute, Yaounde, Center, CAMEROON]
Professor (Prof.) Ph.D. seeker (Static Code Analysis Research from WATERLOO); advised by: [Dr. PAUL fokam kammogne], & [Dr. Ing. JUSTIN bomda]; [and M. Samuel DIMITE]
~~"JAN peleska" & "University of Waterloo" try to hijack myself through this 2-days-job-contract~~
[All people pro-eminent persons I have seen at his banks, "including Deceased gay-pd GERVAIS mendoze", are in prison !!! (419-scam)]
- Judo-Québec, Montreal, Quebec, CANADA JUNE 2014 – NOVEMBER 2014
(Part-Time) Web Development Consultant (JAVA SE 7, GWT, PHP) for JUDODB; advised by: Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam
- RiskView Inc., Toronto, Ontario, CANADA January 2013
Software Consultant for Finance Software Security (SCALA servlet development for Finance); advised by: Reza Kopae, M.Sc.
- WeAIT GmbH, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY June 2005 – July 2005
Software Development Internship (J2EE, MySQL web application for medical personal training management); advised by Dipl.-Inf. Stephan Sucker
- SGS Cameroon, Douala, littoral REGION, CAMEROON September 2004
System administration internship (Computer networked installation; employee desktop technical support; (MS Windows NT, MS Windows 2000, etc.); advised by CHENGWA, & ...)
- bremen4u GmbH, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY March 2004
Web development internship, System Administration (MySQL, RedHat Linux, JSP, PHP, HTML5, CSS); advised by Martin, B.Sc.
- IWT at The University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY October 2002 – January 2003
(Part-Time) Student Metal Processing & Measurement Helping Scientist; advised by: Dipl.-Ing. Sven Bengelsdorf.
- DaimlerChrysler AG, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY June 2002 – August 2002
Industrial Chain Worker (Kfz-Schlosser Helper); setting of Mercedes personal cars seat belts
- Brüel & Kjær, Technology Park – University of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY July 2002 – September 2002
(Part-Time) Student Helper (event management); advised by: Dipl.-Pol. Torben (and Dr. Woehring)
- Cyberix, Douala, Littoral region, CAMEROON October 2001 – November 2001
Web Development Internship (HTML, CSS); advised by: Ing. Fogueum (and Théodore Wandji Ngongang)
- GCE A Level in Exact Sciences; BACCALAURÉAT C (Mathematics, etc.) 2000
Grade of "11.59 / 20"
Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON
- GCE O Level in Exact Sciences; PROBATOIRE C (Mathematics, etc.) 1999
Grade of "12.09 / 20"
Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON
- B.E.P.C (Brevet d'Études DU PREMIER CYCLE) 1997
Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON
- C.E.P.E (CERTIFICAT D'ÉTUDES PRIMAIRES ÉLÉMENTAIRES) 1993
Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON

PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION LANGUAGES

- FRENCH, and ENGLISH CAMEROON; NATIVE
- "GERMAN DSH LANGUAGE CERTIFICATE", Sehr Gut (Very Good) April 2002 (UNIVERSITY OF DORTMUND, DORTMUND, NRW, Germany)
- "ENGLISH USA TOEFL-IBT", Grade 86 June 2018 (Hamilton, Ontario, Canada)

[SUMMER SCHOOL PARTICIPATION] – ADDENDUM

- "Online Software Security Course" – Stanford University, California, USA June 2013 – August 2013
- "CUT 1 – Certificate in University Teaching1" – University of Waterloo, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA 2010
- "First Summer School on Formal Techniques" – NSF, SRI International, Menlo College, Atherton, California, USA May 22, 2011 – May 27, 2011
- "Graduate Student English Training Course" – Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM), Montreal, Quebec, Canada Aug. 2009
- "Graduate Management Admission Test (GMAT) Preparation Course" – Concordia University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada June 2007
- "C Programming Language Preparation Course" – UY 1, ENSPY, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon — Taught by "Master-1 Mr. Donfack (ENSPY)" Aug. 2001 – Sep. 2001

5. **CREATE** a software component full-featured that enables ERP-stock data import using a technology Kind-of VOICE-to-text !
6. Create a framework that allows for formal method specification of static dataflow analyzes as temporal property verification formulas;
Such a framework generate code software as static staged dataflow analyzes for its users.
More importantly, I will try to reuse previous work done for [YRI_QVGE\[13.13\]](#) research work, as part deliverable.
7. **TRY** to integrate research results on software security in "YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum "; from Vijay GANESH research (<https://research.gatech.edu/people/vijay-ganesh>); MOST possibly using "SDMM".
8. Automatic generation of web HTML pages from a Domain Specific Language (DSL) that is more approachable for a high level programming language perspective (i.e: similar to C++ / JAVA): YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0[27.27].
9. Create and render software analysis, debugging, and testing tools as easy as possible to use, with only finite automata theory background; and / or Typestate-API usage rule checking typestate-API knowledge (e.g.: [YERITH-SAINT\[34\]](#), [SDMM\[1d\]](#), [YRI_QVGE\[13.13\]](#), VALKYRIE-VALGRIND[20.20]).
10. **Prepare** a course on "Software System Security Vulnerability Detection and Analysis". I prepare this course material so to implement a software system for protecting other software from malware.
11. Create a stand-alone software product that enables medical physician to augment their efficiency in terms of patient work flow throughput : 'yerith-sante-organigramme'
Even Dr. Christian EYOUM find this utility-tool very impressive in terms of effectiveness & simplicity if this could be really in his world (PSY) implemented !
12. Create a stand-alone tool that generates code for creating statechart C++ code for mealy machine state diagram ([SDMM\[1d\]](#)).
This tool is specifically created and programmed for generating code that uses checkboxes to select options for Graphical User Interface [GUI] code.
13. Position "static dataflow analysis research and techniques" as similar as runtime verification (i.e.: circle 4 in Figure 18; e.g.:PH.D. THESIS[32], [YERITH-SAINT\[34\]](#)).
14. Create and produce a computer device that could be embedded into other computer devices and that will communicate with them through serial ports and / or USB interfaces SO to provide YRI_QVGE program verification to USER FINISHED products on-the-fly, AS an add-on ENGINEERED industrial product: ALSO this product could qualify for an CE—ISO—related certification for avionics, railways, automotive, and CE—ISO certifications for Healthcare : [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET].

1.1 CAMEROON new country name based on CHRISTIANITY-jesus-of-nazareth-NAME-and-TRIBES-number

Changing CMR onto YERITH as country name since JESUS-OF-Nazareth utilizes 12 237 as number of tribes for its ISRAEL tribe.

2.2 National Currency BILLS and / or COINS

- CMR YERITH NATIONAL Money currency as 'YERITH-dollar ("JESUS-OF-Nazareth"-dollar)'.

THIS money currency bill and / or coin system will be backed by computing systems from YERITH R&D; AS open-sourced products :

- 1.) YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME; A software-system product created out of Enterprise Resource Planing Software YRI_QVGE[13.13.7] that is also usable as an algorithmic trading system !

3.3 National Identification

1. A system allowing any of the 3 documents cited below as valid official identification for any official or unofficial activity shall be implemented in Central CEMAC:

1. Valid NATIONAL IDENTITY CARD
2. Valid PASSPORT CEMAC—CEDEAO
3. Valid bank account id.
4. ALL PERSONS working with weapons or force by law have to be identified with names on badge wherever they are outside of their working places.

A bank account id IS in effect linked to a Valid national identity card.

""MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO (Mtn-network: 6 75 66 24 87)" for instance, a cousin paternal "French—germain" of mine, Could afford for a law school with a bank account that wasn't really linked with his by birth official IDENTITY documents !"

MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO (Mtn-network: 6 75 66 24 87) also possesses a diplomatic passport at least or equivalent because he also works for MINREX.

IN effect, "MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO (Mtn-network: 6 75 66 24 87)" was a diplomat before joining the LAW-school in LAGOS—corrupt.

I could notify this since the law school of lagos he attended didn't issue for a certificate with exact same official birth identity names as written thereof.

THIS COUSIN OF MINE IS A CRIMINAL in all systems of justice worldwide.

2. 1 system, computerized, and / or, a text registry book shall be created to register any Cameroon citizen with no need for any citizen to walk around with a national identity card.
3. There are some drawbacks as for instance mentioned on the website of FREE SOFTWARE FOUNDATION, in the United States of America (USA), to have a centralized registration system for citizen or People living inside a country !
4. *"A gervais nana (gersatelgmail.com)" I know somewhere in YDE, seems to be connected as a free-mason to ""MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO"" .*
"GERVAIS NANA" must be investigated since I know "TEBIWO-YAMKAM-MOÏSE" Is a murderer in all systems.
5. I remember having an issue with a screen of a laptop I bought to a place (GERSATEL) owned by *"Gervais NANA"* ; after 1 day, A blur appeared on the screen and I wasn't reimbursed.
6. *It seems "WELADJI" a burglar that I went with at Gendarmerie D'AKWA-SUD in 2023 because he apparently tried to steal 20, 000 FRANCS as a non used money for a purchase item that I ordered from his shop at DLA-douala-bar;*

"WELADJI" WAS NOW in position in another shop where I started buying stuff for my customers. "Moubeb-Jean" is working just at opposite side of this computer hardware shop in Douala: "COLLEGE INTEG".

7. *"ISAAC TEUNTCHOU-poltron-peggist" , a father in law of 1 uterine sister of my person; "Ingride-NOUMBISSI-TCHITCHUI (heiratet-(SPOUSE)-Dipl.-Ing.-(FH)-CHANDRIAND-Teuntchou-Noumeni, MSc.)" is trying to hijack from my propriety all my real-estate.*
8. *shanda-tonne-jean-claude; bob-tabet-peggist-Deido-plage-poisson-braisé, the idiot that sleeps with rose-sangnou my genitor; AND with her sister Dorotheé shanda owona " (LEVITICUS 20 : 12 – 14)."*
"OLAMCAM (tel.:6 52 12 65 57 --georges-kamdem) (peggist working in Douala shipment-haven) owner Tabet-bob (OWNING a house in "bonaberi"; money from bribery in ONTARIO according to JP-kamgain sayings) & friends GEORGES-kamdem; & JP-kamgain; they have tried to sodomize myself with Christian-eyoum-c.p.d.m [by trying to say to JP-kamgain-to act as a friend-of-myself]. "
"BOB-tabet is an ancient jail-black-attendee of ONTARIO justice system that escaped Canada by talks I heard [of KAMGAIN]."
"[Culprit-JP-kamgain] told me once [TABEL-ROBERT]-wanted-HR-module payment services for his employees in DOUALA."
9. *ISAAC-teuntchou, the idiot that sleeps with his daughter-in-law; TEUNTCHOU-noumeni-chandriand is currently trying to hijack my property of DLA-cité-des-palmiers-beedi, BY Sending INGRID to my attorney of law so to try to say that SHE wants some money from my current ongoing rental agreement with a so called MELEU-belvianne, AND her fiancée called SEWE-idiot-toie.*
10. *"Audrey-NGUETIE-tehamga" shalln't anymore go and seek people from my former places of work to try to tell them I abandon her after 1-night.*
THIS disgusting megere wasn't capable of understand I cannot be fornicating with someone that Cannot imagine herself as a wife in a non-gay homosexual matrimonial house AS i could observe from her gay-white-salsa friends & sister "YOLLANDE-nguetie married at that other senegalese in Montreal
"TCHAMAHAMA ntaata-GUTTEMBERG" & "Remi-POUASSI-taata" who are my blood-family (father-theo-chien-noumbissi-batchieu—babouantou) cousins & 'also blood-village people of MAURIGE-nguetie' & 'Audrey-nguetie-tehamga;' SHALL know that Homosexuality is a disease from a BORN-again christian point of view: ITS cure is living without any sexual encountering as proclaimed in " 1 Corinthians 7 : 1 " & " 1 Corinthians 7 : 38-40 " !
11. *VICTOR-koliou-serpent—Tehandeu-gay thinks he is linked to myself by my late father; I HAVE already told this culprit & wretched canadian-traveler as a assassin that could be even arrested just at airport; Like I was faultily arrested by canadian-faked police so to destroy my luxurious image !*

THIS criminal worldwide, since he even called before I attended 3 days & nights at his junior-est brother DEMO-noundou house in Hamburg—Germany; to say that Demo could even not even respond to any call of myself because I did not notify him—demo when I was living Cameroon.

There is a fake idolatry-people like "bamileke" demo & tehandeu-family-noundou; That if you want to attend a living at someone place, you must call onto him before you arrive. THIS kind of guja-assassin-diplomat schizophrenic-idea is in fact to listen to calls & organize fake routes with spies everywhere so to dictate how your daily life shall look like !.—MVONDO.

Following items from previous page; JUSTICE and PAST-MEMORIES to heal in Cameroon

9. Multiple or DOUBLE citizenship **SHALL NOT be allowed** since Africans are not well behaved to use and observe strict rules that are due to protect civilians with only 1 citizenship appurtenance.
10. Double citizenship with following countries that harasses honest Cameroonian like myself shalln't be allowed:
- Canada
 - United States of America (USA)
 - Germany
 - Any country where a gay-homosexual-marriage is pronounced in a so-called **"JESUS-OF-NAZARETH"** congregation: I.E: such a country shall be considered a scam **"(LEVITICUS 20:12-13, and Romans 1:26-28)!"**

SIMPLICE-kameni and alike people must be imprisoned.

HJACKING properties and down-casting businesses of elite-intellectualist from abroad like myself and others I may not even know about is what make them have a life luxurious around C.P.D.M and SED-yves-landry-galax-etoga-idiot; so called secret-services.

" THERE is also another "negger" working on behalf of simplice-kameni as LEAD of the so-called-cocaine-reseller wood-factory S2T-BED, called IDIOT-repeating-christian-signs; that behave like so-called "TONTON-makout' in HAITI-movies; (<https://wwwurl>) YOU see this kind of people that kills under behalf of a politician like BIYA; AND that you cannot even prosecute because there is no whereabouts of his origins or identities here in Cameroon-official-Communaute-URBAINE-de-YAOUNDE. "

" !! ALSO this biya-cpdm-gang against a proper african descendant on AFRIKA-soil Has a motto: ABSURDITY !!! "

FACTS:

1. kill where life is supposed to be saved;
Example: USE your own blood-giver to hijack your life and properties [REFERENCE.]

HOSPITAL is used to destroy lives.

2. destroy where it is supposed to be killed;

POLICE and ARMY kill people that go to them for seeking help after being robbed or whatsoever here in AFRIKA;

so called **UNITED-nations** (<https://www.un.org>) are only a replacement for colonies by white-supremacists.

- IT seems it is cameroon-cpdm-people who are UNITED nations workers here in CMR; HERE.

4.4 JUSTICE and PAST-MEMORIES to heal in Cameroon

1. [~~Dr. PAUL Siméon nomo, from MONATÉLÉ came to my private house in YDE-AAHALA, to arrest illegally without any notification or whatsoever, using a firefighter truck and 3 firefighter to molest myself in front of several neighbors so to discredit my life as a peaceful citizen of Cameroon.~~]
~~HE seems this criminal assassin from BIYA private places is now living in Maryland, USA; since I went back to Canada to resign from CANADIAN shit citizenship.~~
 Another cousin of mine so called "~~Rodrigue Alain Sienchie~~", told me that 1 day armed soldiers with uniforms came to arrest him in the house of his parents, sent by "~~Dorothée SHANDA-NDJATIE OWONA~~"; THEN went to sodomized him at LAQUINTINIE HOSPITAL.
 "SO I SUSPECT this criminal ~~LAURENT TCHANDEU-DJATIE DOROTHÉE OWONA~~ to have sent to my private house in Yaounde in 2017 this 'so called baptist church pastor Dr. SIMEON NOMO, PSY.D.'."
2. "~~Eyoum Christian~~" idiot's immunity of justice because he is a psychiatrist Must be investigated !
3. '~~S2TBED~~', finally repairs our main common road: They destroyed a previous road with LATERITE so much that IT must be fixed with concrete !
4. '~~S2TBED~~', biya's illegal industrial forestry enterprise society, an illegal neighbor of "Immeuble YERITH" of mine, IS constantly disrupting electrical energy current supply.
5. ALL my real estate in Douala (3 3-bedrooms apartments) need to be released by a genitor of mine THAT is not anymore wanted in my life because of all atrocities SHE CONSTANTLY commits with SHANDA GREGROIRE OWONA Wolfgang TCHAMOU angela ndjatie. !!!
 SISTER'S of Rose Sangnou my genitor, Dorothée Shanda Ndjatie, IS CONSTANTLY harassing her to take me to any psychiatric institute by force, Even though there is already a criminal investigation against her and Rose Sangnou at DLA-ndokoti justice palace; DOROTHÉE is a criminal PERSON !
6. 'MADO's brother CAPTAIN pierre marcellin emana nkoa' must reimburse back my 210 000 FRANCS since SEMIL (Sécurité Militaire) told me in 2016 THAT THEY CANNOT convoke them SINCE receipts were signed by his cousin "JEAN-DE-DIEU onana".
 "MY NEIGHBOR CARINE LELE NJOUGEPE TCHANA", seems to be here because of them, so to deteriorate the quality of life of legal people living here, and promote their own-beings through propaganda LIKE 'it seems THE colonel living THERE above of the hill IS the one that FIXED the road leading to your compound !
7. JUSTICE FOR BREAKING AND torturing myself (Xavier noumbissi Noundou [DR-ING. PR. PROF.]) in front of at least 17 people in front of my inherited personal domicile in Douala-Béedi-Cite-des-Palmiers MUST be finalized before Cameroon election 2025.
8. 'JUSTICE president and certain types of judges must be apolitical: I.e.: THEY CANNOT BELONG TO A POLITICAL PARTY !
9. MARTINEZ ZOGO assassin AMOUGOU BELINGA justice criminal court must be finished before Cameroon election 2025.
10. PEOPLE responsible for the drama of Edea Railway Failure in .. MUST be judged in a civil criminal court before Cameroon election 2025.
11. MILITARY SOLDIERS that killed about "7 women and their teddies in north Cameroon must be judged."
12. "EDGARD ALAIN MEBE NGO'O" criminal procedure in military justice courts must be achieved before Cameroon election 2025.
13. Military Soldier must have their own facilities and amenities in cities, and not mixed intermingle anymore with civilians, AS THIS IS CURRENTLY THE CASE when they DON'T wear military attire uniform !
 In fact, MILITARY SOLDIERS or Alike don't have a same behavior justice as civilians; Not talking about habits and gesture.
14. Bepanda drama because of 'general MPAY' must be re-recovered in a justice palace court of civilians and / or military justice !

5.5 ACADEMY and Technology Research Institutions

1. Promote creation of research centers for solving problems located specifically in central west Africa:
 1. Another source of revenue for CMR
 2. Improving life conditions for CMR and neighboring friend countries.
2. Enable a financing WITH non reimbursement option for doctors in science and / or engineering.

6.6 Employments and JOBS creation for adult people

1. THERE must be a minimum amount of jobs offer for each society that was funded by the government for researching and improving life quality in CMR and neighboring countries.
2. *WOMEN that are selling goods outside of their home like "CAROLE mangue" (la fille de "MA-bernadette" au secrétariat-d'état-yves-idiot.) shalln't be part of SED or any governmental secret or not agencies !!!*
THIS culprit shall also try to not resell goods that were illegally imported into CMR.
3. ALL PEOPLE that were trained by the BIYA-regime as illegal para-military personal, MUST go into peace-keeper corps organization of the UNITED NATIONS or somewhere else so to keep cities and villages free of fire and all other destructive people.

FOR instance people like "PASCAL dayang", working at "S2TBED" of the culprit franck-biya has insinuated to myself that HE will disrupt any business activities that I-doctor-of-engineering Xavier NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU will perform in my compound !!!

["S2TBED"- "PASCAL dayang mercenary SED soldier" as threat in CMR !!!]

4. Transform all wood factories within city of YAOUNDE in computer desktop and / or laptop assembly production units

7.7 JUSTICE and DIVINITIES

1. *Destruction of all secret services units in Cameroon !!*
 1. "OUATARA people shall not anymore be opponent to christian people here in Cameroon as it is the case with Shanda-TONME jean claude" presently.
 2. People like SHANDA OWONA harass other people because they feel as safest as possible because of some kind of impunity based on their appurtenance to DGRE special unit forces ("JEAN CLAUDE shanda tonme and spouse" weren't for instance infringed in DLA-NDOKOTI palace for breaking into my compound, closed at night, with around 9 burglars; So called Technicians of "PSY-laquintinie"; around 23 : 30 at night while I was sleeping IN february 2021 in DOUALA).
 3. Politicians shall be reduced to be people applying criminal and civil laws instead of people trying to make their own ideas come through via ENTERING private life of people like "Shanda TONME jean claude" has done in the past 30 alike years with my personal family and life ('Family NOUNDOU michel', and 'Family JEAN NGONGANG') !
 4. 'SEMIL' and special alike units of Cameroonian army shall be dismantled because of reported proved or not really ATROCITY facts.
 5. 'SEMIL', 'DGRE', 'SED', etc.; all former people wearing weapons shall be displaced into military caserns so to avoid mixing MILITARY alike people with civilians !
 6. IMPUNITY of all people wearing weapon must cease with tribunal applications of criminal laws.
2. *Create an electoral public and common website for all information, and / or official application documents for all elections in Cameroon !!*
3. *Create a website for publication of all laws in Cameroon; including presidential decrees, acts, and / or acts, and so on ...!*
4. *Reforming judicial system with computer software digitization so to PROMOTE equity and justice by laws !*
5. *EACH CITIZEN or person living in Cameroon SHALL officially declare its lifestyle philosophy and / or religion at a 'Chefferie De Block' when moving inside that area of the city !*
 - a. This enables to solve issues based on this declaration in a fairly manner, according to a new reformed judicial criminal law system !
6. *PROHIBIT any type of religious or associations that don't have well openly presented and written codes of laws, Abiding to CAMEROON criminal laws !*

8.8 TRANSPORTATION and CITIES transportation

1. *Reduce airplane travel costs between cities in Cameroon.*
INSTANCES:
 - a. {DLA → YDE} with one way at 12 000 FRANCS.
 - b. {YDE → BAFOUSSAM} with one way at 18 000 FRANCS.
 - c. Etc..

9.9 Technology And Development

1. *Schooling shall be created and managed to be in harmony with Religious, and / or Philosophy lifestyle of parents that intend to have children in a school; BOTH primary and secondary.*
UNIVERSITIES could mix students of all horizons: so the student and leaders of next Coming Cameroon could learn how to live harmoniously.
2. *State schools for civil servants shall be banned in favor of UNIVERSITY education and of an additional training on the job when hired !*
3. *Universities shall be autonomous and not depend anymore of the PRESIDENCY OF THE REPUBLIC*
4. *Create an industry for solar electrical energy with cars and buses as consumers in a lapse of time of 12 years starting 2026.*
5. *Assemble DIGITAL computers in Cameroon in less than 12 years of presidency.*

10.10 MARRIAGE and INTER-PERSONAL sexual corporal Relationship

1. *PROHIBIT sexual actions IN OUTDOOR by laws.*
2. *REMOVE TRADITIONAL SYSTEM of justice because of its unfairness; Based on WOMAN precedence in power:*
 - a. *SINCE Christians don't need to marry to a woman or any gender, as described in 1 CORINTHIANS 7 : 38 – 39 !*
 - b. *SINCE people could stay without marriage, In Christianity, marriage is THE EXCEPTION, But not a sin;*
 - c. *Any person that is not married and that is a born-again Christian cannot be managed by a married person ! THIS is because A MARRIED person couldn't qualify to understand a life at a certain level as He is living constantly with another gender !*
 - d. *People that have marriage in traditional system normally cannot undergo a civil marriage in a christian church (I.E: TRADITIONAL system allows for Impudicity, Which is prohibited in Christianity !).*
 - e. *Born-Again Christians don't marry at all in any type of marriage !*
 - f. *"SHANDA-TONME jean claude's first and last son": Late (justice of attorney) "Me. Shanda Sanou Cabral Patrice" was apparently killed brutally since his body was missing from people assisting SHANDA's family for obituaries.*
 - g. *"HIS (jean-claude shanda-tonme) OBITUARIES in next coming years must not be public since He hasn't been a good citizen for at least hundreds of young cameroonian" that I have hear about for the last 12 years since I started by immigration process back to my homeland country Cameroon of C.P.D.M-R.D.P.C !*
3. *Automatic Splitting OF INHERITANCE after parental death between children:* Because there are a lot of troubles to leave this task to a family with not enough money for paper and bureaucracy work at notary justice palaces !
4. *LEGALIZE homosexual UNION.*
 - a. *People in this union cannot have children adopted from another non-homosexual union at ALL; AND VICE-VERSA for couple married in non-homosexual life style !*

11.11 MUNICIPALITY Reform (AND WASTE and DISPOSAL of garbage)

1. *chefferie de block: This administrative territorial unit is based on traditional tribal lineage ! THIS SHALL BE ENDED AS EACH CITIZEN is subject to the same civil law:*
 1. *currently, a 'chefferie de block' is based on common and traditional law. Since common law has precedence over tribal traditional law, A CITIZEN living must be subject only to COMMON CIVIL LAW where he is living, OR NOT.*
2. *There shall be created AN INDUSTRY for recycling and displacement of waste-garbage USING ecologic burning container:* Each "chefferie de block" shall have its own burning destroying waste-garbage ecologic container.
3. *There shall be at least 1 municipal playing and recreational area of at least 400 m² in each city quarter ("quartier").*
4. *There shall be at least 1 municipal library in each city quarter ("quartier").*

- UNITED STATES OF AMERICA (U.S.A)

- 1.) SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), CONCORD, CALIFORNIA, U.S.A (JANUARY 2008)
- 2.) SRI International, MENLO COLLEGE, MENLO PARK, ATHERTON, CALIFORNIA, U.S.A (May 2011)

- CANADA

- 3.) UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ON, canada 2009 – 2015
- 4.) MITACS ONTARIO, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, CANADA (October 2012)
- 5.) IBM CASCON 2010 (IBM CENTRE FOR ADVANCED STUDIES CONFERENCE), Hilton Suites Toronto/Markham, Conference Centre, Markham, ON, CANADA (November 2010)
 I attended this conference to present "my doctoral thesis in a simple manner that could be defended in front of several researchers worldwide" (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>); With different backgrounds; As well as practitioners from IBM toronto software laboratory in MARKHAM (<https://www.ibm.ca>) .
- 6.) PLDI conference (Programming Languages Design And Implementation), Toronto, ON, CANADA (November 2009)
- 7.) Graduate Management Admission Test (GMAT) PREPARATION COURSE, CONCORDIA UNIVERSITY, MONTREAL, QUEBEC, CANADA (June 2007)
- 8.) Graduate English Training Course, UNIVERSITÉ DU QUÉBEC à MONTRAL (UQAM), MONTREAL, QUEBEC, CANADA (AUGUST 2009)

- GERMANY

- 9.) UNIVERSITÄT BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY 2001 – 2007
- 10.) SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), ERLANGEN, BAYERN, GERMANY 2007 – 2009
- 11.) SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), HEIDELBERG, BADEN-WÜRTTEMBERG, GERMANY 2007 – 2009

This section reports and summarizes our current and actualized knowledge on the subject of software licensing.

20.20 SOFTWARE LICENSes

- o "Summary of MOSTLY used software-licenses":

[Software ~~Hardware~~ Certification authorities; "O.H.A.D.A"; CENELEC; CE; ISO; "A.R.I.N.C"]

Table 1: Software LICENSes summary table.

SOFTWARE license type	Peculiarities	Uses	URL for legal writing specification
1. "CSCS : Close Source Code Software"	Software / Programs AUTHOR exclusive copyright & ownership	YOU use only a binary.	Each retailer provides this on a case by case request.
2.			
3.			
4.			
5.			
6.			

- **CSCS : Close Source Code Software** (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- **Open source code software (OSS** (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)) :

- OTHER forms of free software license (FOSS** (<https://www.wikipedia.org>))

- APACHE-BSD license** (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- **APACHE**
- ["**BSD**"]

- GNU licenses** : (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- **GPL**
ANY software that uses this piece of whole source code and / or binaries have to also be licensed GPL.
- "**Lesser GPL - LGPL**" ✓
Program binaries could be used in a commercial project without any request and / or payments to the owner of the source code. Modifications of the source code follows certain rules specified as follows :
 - 1.) *Mention of the authors have to be explicitly written in headers of code sources as directed by rules explicitly sampled at following URL : (<https://>).*
 - 2.) *YOUR own using software source code must also abide to the LGPL GNU software license according to what is written at following URL : (<https://>).*

- BERKELEY-style license** (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- **BSD**

- MIT-license; "also called AS-IS-no-warranty-AT-ALL"** (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- **MIT** ✓
THIS kind of Open-Source Software (OSS) programs is provided in a state that no reclamation could be done because it could be very tedious to determine liabilities between parties such as a provider, and a customer and / or client.
The so-called MIT License are part of the AS-IS no-warranty code; ALSO all GPL typed licenses in general.
Programs using AS-IS no-Warranty code software licenses generally stipulates either following text, OR similar surrounding text around following :

- o ["The program is provided AS IS with NO WARRANTY OF ANY KIND, INCLUDING THE WARRANTY OF DESIGN, MERCHANTABILITY AND FITNESS FOR A PARTICULAR PURPOSE."]

This section reports and summarizes all information required at least for certification of our runtime verification monitoring tester tool; BOTH software and/or HARDWARE products.

21.21 Documents for certification for "YERITH R&D" software – hardware PRODUCTS engineered in AFRICA-main—land

Table 2: *Design Documents* for the CASE (Computer-AIDED SOFTWARE Engineering) tool YERITH_QVGE.

Design Document	VERSION	LOCATION
1. <i>USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification)</i>		
2. <i>Module Description (Module Functional Specification)</i>		
3. <i>Module / Unit Testing</i>		

Table 3: *Design Documents* for the Runtime Monitoring Verifier Tester [YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF].

Design Document	VERSION	LOCATION
1. <i>USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification)</i>		
2. <i>Module Description (Module Functional Specification)</i>		
3. <i>Module / Unit Testing</i>		

Table 4: *Design Documents* for the Monitoring Verifier Tester [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET]

Design Document	VERSION	LOCATION
1. <i>USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification)</i>		
2. <i>Module Description (Module Functional Specification)</i>		
3. <i>Module / Unit Testing</i>		

A personal computer tablet for SIMPLIFYING runtime monitoring on-the-fly

Figure 20, Figure 21, and Figure 22 illustrates a sample product usage of the toolkit YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF that permits and allows for its users following actions and tasks to be solved fluently :

1. Send tracing logging for a developer and / or engineer trough 1 of the following communication interfaces :
 - 1.)

- 1.) *Design Documents Unit TESTING, and Static Code Analysis Verification;*
- 2.) *USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification);*
- 3.) *Module Description (Module Functional Specification).*

This section reports and summarizes all information required at least for certification of our runtime verification monitoring tester tool; BOTH software and/or HARDWARE products.

22.22 TOOLS used for Qualification AND / OR Certification of Software-hardware PRODUCTS at "YERITH R&D"

Table 5: Tools used for Qualification and / Or Certification at YERITH R&D.

TOOL	VERSION	Uses	LOCATION
1. "BUGZILLA (https://www.bugzilla.org)"	"N.A"	Bugs and Defects registration & following-up.	
2. "GNU Privacy Guard-GPG (https://www.gnupg.org)"	2.2.27-2	Digital signing check-in source code & documents.	
3. "Git (https://www.git.org)"	1 : 2.30.2-1 + deb11u2	COMMIT, and following-up source code for certification authorities.	

Table 5 illustrates some programming and / or debugging tools I use at YERITH R&D for developing certified products with "ISO - INTERNATIONAL STANDARD ORGANISATION (<https://www.iso.org>)", etc.; Certification organizations :

- o Bugs and Defects Management Software : "BUGZILLA (<https://www.bugzilla.org>)";
 1. "VERSION of current BUGZILLA software installations" : "N.A".
 2. "Location of BUG report-free database website URL" : "www.digital.ocean.com/YERITH_QVGE_HTTPS_url (<https://www.digitalocean.com>)".
 3. "Location of BUGZILLA software installation" : "Intern to YERITH R&D".
- o Software for electronically signing (e.g.: Source code, Design Documents, etc.) : "GNU Privacy Guard-GPG (<https://www.gnupg.org>)";
 1. "VERSION of current GNU Privacy Guard-GPG software installations" : "2.2.27-2".
- o SCM (Source code Management) software : Version Control Management Software : "Git (<https://www.git.org>)";
 1. "VERSION of current Git software installations" : "1 : 2.30.2-1 + deb11u2".

This section reports and summarizes all information required at least for certification of our runtime verification monitoring tester tool; BOTH software and/or HARDWARE products.

23.23 Yerith_QVGE Legal Software and/or Hardware CERTIFICATION Artifacts

- o "Yerith_QVGE Legal Software CERTIFICATION Artifacts":

- YERITH_QVGE DESIGN AND TESTING SYSTEM[13.13] : A product for qualification; CE.

23.23.1 "CERTIFICATION Tools used at YERITH R&D"

[Certification TOOLS.]

23.23.2 "PRODUCTS for Engineering And/ OR Finance Engineered Computing"

- 1.) YERITH_QVGE software design CASE (Computer-AIDED SOFTWARE Engineering) tool; [RELated Design & User Documentation Artifacts.]

[“June 2022” – Currently]

Figure 1: A SCREENSHOT OF YERITH_QVGE FOR GRAPHICAL DESIGN OF STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM) SPECIFICATIONS; THAT COULD SPECIFY TRADE OPERATIONS BASED ON TRADE-TIME.

- 2.) YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET ; [RELated Design & User Documentation Artifacts.]

[“Nov. 2024” – Currently]

Figure 2: A screenshot of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL error event log running on YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET.

Figure 3: A sample YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET in action.

THIS hardware computing device, WITH software that uses "INTEL-Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) could be used for "on-the-fly" runtime verification monitoring & Recovering manifold :

- One connects YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET to either an Ethernet network connection, or serial interface communication port RS-232, and / or Universal Serial BUS-USB interface port ;

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (a screenshot is found in Figure 2) is started on "YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET", and connects to specified processes, on the attached connected other computing device (E.g.: in Fig. 3, a control console for "Siemens-LINAC"); In a configuration panel. THE open source version of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) is a bit different of the non-free upgraded version installed on "YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET".

This section reports and summarizes all efforts needed as far AS I could learn and experienced as seasoned software developer at "IBM-toronto-software-laboratory"; And at "Siemens-medical-solutions".

24.24 Years of experience as Software Developer for Legally APPROVED products

o "Legal Requirements for a correct con-formant Software Artifact":

- **YERITH_QVGE LEGAL documents for Qualified Products from AFRICA—main—land.**
- **[SOFTWARE licensing.]**
- **"Communauté Économique et MONÉTAIRE de l'Afrique Centrale – (C.E.M.A.C)" (<https://www.cemac.int>)** : THIS central Africa certification applies for Accounting and Finance.
 - I.) **"O.H.A.D.A (<https://www.cemac.int>)"** ; for **"FINANCIAL ACCOUNTING SOFTWARE"**
- **TüV-Nord ([https://www](https://www.tuv-nord.com)) in North-West GERMANY** : This german authority in Science and Engineering reflects better our initial commitment as a **"DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?]**, even before a **[MASTER-OF-SCIENCE]** degree was created at the **UNIVERSITY-racist of Bremen (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)**.
 - A.) **"CE - EUROPEAN COMMUNITY (https://www.single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/ce-marking_en)"** ; **"ISO - INTERNATIONAL STANDARD ORGANISATION (<https://www.iso.org>)"** ; **"FDA - FEDERAL DRUG ADMINISTRATION (U.S.A) (<https://www.fda.gov>)"** for **"MEDICAL SOFTWARE"**
 1. **Bugs and Defects** are to be managed by a software such as **"IBM-CharmNT (<https://www.ibm.com/us>)"** ;
 2. **Design Documents** are to be updated annually at maximum time based on regulatory deadlines of **AUTHORITIES That Delivers Certificates "; I think at least ONCE-ANNUALLY"**;
 3. **Design Documents** are electronically signed by an author and reviewers;
 4. **Design Documents** are saved in an ERP software such as **"SAP-EDM (<https://www.sap.de>)"**, etc.;
 5. **Design Documents** have a table to indicate changes within the document for each modification of it;
 6. **Design Documents** USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification);
 7. **Design Documents** Module Description (Module Functional Specification) with Diagrams; E.g.: **"Finite State Machine Diagrams"**, etc.;
 8. **Design Documents** Unit TESTING, and Static Code Analysis Verification; Runtime Memory Error Detection TOOLS.
 9. **Source code** is to be stored in a control version management system such as **"Rational-ClearCase"**, etc.;
 10. **Source code** changes are to be reviewed and electronically signed using a key-card like the ones used by **["SIEMENS-healthineers-OCS"]**;
 - B.) **CENELEC (<https://www.iso.org/fr/standard/68383.html>)** for **"RAILWAY"**

A sample railway software related product regulation is : **"CENELEC EN50128" (<https://www.iso.org/fr/standard/68383.html>)**.
 - C.) **A.R.I.N.C (<https://www.aviation-ia.sae-itc.com>)** for **"AVIONICS SOFTWARE"**

Sample A.R.I.N.C specifications : **"RTCA D0178-B"**; **"RTCA D0178-C"**.

 - **Static Code Analysis Verification conforming to "MISRA-C" (<https://www.misra.org>)** ;

["MISRA-C"]

This section reports and summarizes all efforts I have made throughout my Time at The University Of Waterloo as a 'Ph.D. candidate'. THIS page links and connects 5 years of academic and professional research I HAVE been spending at the white-asian-white racist extremist university of waterloo in ontario, CANADA.

25.25 Years of PRE-Doctoral & years of Doctoral Research at University-racist OF waterloo, ONTARIO, CANADA

ML; C++; Java; OSI; Eclipse; Intel-Pin; Open-MP Haskell, GWT, Python, IBM, Quercus, Bash-scripting	<i>Program Analysis (Static, Dynamic).</i> a-la-KILDALL-Gary;LFDS-Reps; datalog; Soot; LLVM	Courses taught: 1. Software Testing, Quality Assurance & Maintenance 2. Programming for Performance 3. Tools & Methods for Software Engineering 4. Foundations of Software Engineering 5. C++ Programming Laboratory 6. Compilers 7. Computer Networks
<i>(ADVANCED) Compiler Technology</i> Yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang; Alias Analysis, Comp. Opt.	<i>Program Verification (Isa.-HOL, etc.); Model Checking</i> SDMM; CAV - Computer-Aided Verification; NuSMV; Alloy	
Programing Languages OOP; Functional	Software; Programming; Testing Alg.; Rel. Eng.; Security; Par.-Comp.	} Foundations of My Doctoral Ph.D. / Post-Doctoral Works in Computer Science (Software Engineering)
	Formal Methods; Kripke Structures Automata theory (NFA, DFA, etc.)	

- o [PublicaTIONS.]
- o "Software LICENSING".
- o "Legal Requirements for a correct con-formant Software Artifact".
- o Contacts with NORTH-AMERICAN scientists
- o Contacts with other Scientists
- o Issues & MISUNDERSTANDINGS at the University of Waterloo, Ontario, Canada
- o TIME at the University-racist-of-BREMEN, BREMEN, BREMEN, Germany:
 1. "2 years" STudent Software Developer PART-TIME job – Bergmann Automaten GmbH (now Gewete GmbH), Germany.
 2. "2 years" WERKSTUDENT at ZMML-university-sexist-racist of bremen, BREMEN, GERMANY.: February 2003 – February 2005.
 3. "4.5 years PRE-time" in GERMAN-racist program : "'DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?]"
- o Doctoral years of research at the university-racist of waterloo, ontario, CANADA-idiot:
 1. "2 years PRE-time" at SIEMENS-idiot medical solutions.: November 2007 – JULY 2009.
 2. "Summary of teaching training certificates
 3. PAPER conference peer reviewed : OOPSLA 2010.
 4. GIVEN PREsentation : IBM CDp Cascon 2010.
 5. Visited courses.
 6. Independent assisted research summary as a "Master of Science (M.Sc.)"
 7. VISITed SUMMER-school /workshops / conferences summary
["1st SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques"-2011] | [PLDI 2009] | [IBM CDp Cascon 2010]
 8. PSYCHOLOGICAL-Care with PRACTICE of SWIMMING at THE university-racist of waterloo every other day during almost 4 years – "Degree-Swimmer-5 / degree-MASTER-Swimmer-6" successfully attended.
 9. "Year 1" : 09/2009 – 08/2010;
 10. "Year 2" : 09/2010 – 12/2011 – [with PhD Comprehensive Examination.];
 11. Doctoral THESIS Presentation / PhD Comprehensive Examination on "December 20, 2011"

- o QUALification as a "Professional Engineer in Ontario, CANADA":

THE requirements to qualify myself as Professional Engineer in ONTARIO are all met after 1 year supervision under PATRICK LAM "(2011)"; because I have already 48 months of professional engineering work experience before entering the professional academic doctor of engineering program in ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER Engineering at university-racist-white of waterloo.

"AS a "doctor PhD in electrical & computer engineering" graduate [abbreviated "Dr./PhD" in French; In french, "Dr./PhD" only nowadays means doctor in engineering; and no fellowship at all; I AM A FRANCOPHONE.]; THERE shouldn't be any need to again acquired a professional designation "Professional Engineer", since "doctor PhD in electrical & computer engineering" is already an Engineering titled degree. So as a francophone from dark-afrika-heimat, I am not interested anymore in any Engineering, or whatsoever designated vocational position in whiteist-world !"

"ALSO as a born-again christian, I CANNOT BE member-ed in any fellowship of iron-rings, female-peggist; etc. ."

"JON eyolfson for instance has a "Bachelor-of-Engineering"; so he doesn't need to apply for a "Professional Engineer"; BUT [Wenzhu-man has a "Master of Applied Science (MAsc)"]; AND no "Engineering titled degree from CANADA and /or USA"; SO for her needs she must apply for P.Eng.; so to get government oriented positions !"

This section reports and summarizes all efforts I have made throughout my Time at The University Of Waterloo as a 'Ph.D. candidate'. THIS page links and connects 5 years of academic and professional research I HAVE been spending at the white-asian-white racist extremist university of waterloo in ontario, CANADA.

26.26 Years of POST-doctoral Research; a Summary Report – 2nd page

- o *POst-Doctoral (Ph.D.; Prof.) years of research at the university–racist of waterloo, ontario, CANADA–idiot:*
 1. "Year 1": 01/2012 – 08/2012 – [*PROfessional Internship at IBM Toronto–idiot Software Lab..*]
 2. "Year 2": 09/2012 – 08/2013
 3. "Year 3": 09/2013 – 08/2014
 4. "Year 4": 09/2014 – 04/2015
 5. STUDENT advising summary
 6. TEACHing assistantship summary
 7. "Summary of teaching training certificates"
 8. *Independent & Collegiate Research Summary as "D.ENG. [DR.–ING. in 'French language'] (PH.D.)"*
 9. Visited courses as post–doctoral (POST-DOCTORAL STUDIES) fellow.
 10. VISited ONLINE courses /workshops / conferences summary
[Software-Security–online–"stanford.edu" 2013] | [MITACS ONTARIO 2012] | [ICse 2012]
 11. RESEARCH outcome hindrance
 12. RESEARCH outcome plagiarism
 13. RESEARCH outcome plagiarism-continUED
 14. GIVEN–co–taught courses at the University–racist of Waterloo in ONTARIO, Canada
 15. ACADEMIC HELP from other people aside from DEAR-idiot PATRICK-lam
 16. *!!! PhD Research Seminar TALK. as an ECE graduate talk. !!!*
 17. *!!! PhD Dissertation Defense at DAVID R. Cheriton School OF Computer Science in "January 2015" !!!*
 18. *IAI–cameroon–bande–d'idiots au service d'1 B.E.P.C–chantoux*
- o [*TRAINING on the job of young engineers*]:
 - Runtime monitoring for Web Apps
 - API usage rule checking for 'C' programs (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>)
- o *STARTUP entrepreneurship research & development project YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM:*

After I left the university–racist–of–waterloo in ontario, IN MARCH 2015; I went to live in Cameroon–yaounde for almost 2 years, working on a free and open source software for Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP).

POST-Doctoral Research at YERITH R&D since MARCH 2015:

 - I) *Engineering Methodologies & Tools Expertise;*
 - II) *YERITH_QVGE legal artifacts for QUALIFICATION certified products Engineered in AFRICA;*
 - III) *A web-site Domain-Specific Language (DSL) Processor for generation of HTML5, PHP, CSS, etc. combined web–applications named YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 (Accompanied with a WYSIWYG-Tool : YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL !)*
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9>
 - IV) *A realtime component (for operating system DEBIAN LINUX) is in preparation for trading stock exchange erp system "YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME": YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RT-SYSTEM;*
 - V) *A RUNTIME monitoring verification "state diagram mealy machines (SDMM)" C++ Library :*
 https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf [*I*]
 https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif
 - VI) *A State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM) translator–compiler :*
[YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP](https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) [*1*]
 https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang
 - VII) *A RUNTIME monitoring verification runtime container for "SDMM" :*
 [YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF](https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [*1*]
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>
 - VIII) *Simple to use and pragmatic Enterprise–Resource–Planing (ERP) software :*
 [YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/) (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>) [*?*]
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0>

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES 6 (Cyber-Security & Web Deployment Development)

27.27 WEB PAGES HTML and others Generation with YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0

27.27.1 Motivation

Table 6: A SOFTWARE architecture overview of YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 (["An SDMM usage scenario by IBM-websphere"].)

Figure 4: YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 generates legacy web files from Qt 5 interface files (".ui" files).

Figure 5: A Stack Stapled Architecture Overview of YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0.

YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 is a novel project that constitutes the base for YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM ([git https://github.com/yerithrd/yeritherppgiwebsystem](https://github.com/yerithrd/yeritherppgiwebsystem)) that endeavors to create web sites solutions for entrepreneurial organizations that use YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM without much additional programming of web interfaces and / or interactions; AT such, web sites solutions for entrepreneurial organizations will emerge as easy as pressing a button.

YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 is a Domain Specific Language to [describe WEB SITES programmatically]; SUCH as a C++ program imperatively, AND well structured; So to automatically generate STATIC DYNAMIC WEB SITES BASED ON HTML (HYPERTEXT MARKUP LANGUAGE) AND CSS (Cascading Style Sheets) language constructs : "WWW - World Wide Web (WWW) Design & Programming using YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/YRITENTERlaterOn>).

Numerous companies in Cameroon might evaluate this new research software system product to simplify and speed up their software development process :

1. "Dr.-Ing. PAUL dayang (2013, University of Bremen)"; currently employed at the University of Ngaoundere in Far North of Cameroon.
 - This researcher and lecturer, employed by the University of Ngaoundere, has never replied to my long time email as an alumni of the prestigious University of Bremen in Germany where I graduated with a "Diplom-Informatiker degree 2 years before him !"
 - I could see he started a web graphical system (also with "ANDROID-google platform" (https://)) html-based to promote online afore-provisional shopping of food provisions in Africa for his dissertation as a "Doctor of Engineering". I was sad not to see this project emerge as a commercial start-up here in Cameroon where there is only "www.cm.coinafrique.com" (<https://www.cm.coinafrique.com>) that I deem as a serious competitor in this era of work.
 - I believe the programming abstraction I will provide for "DAYANG and RÖDIGER (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/~roediger>) work" would help them both in "Ngaoundere" and in "Bremen" to promote Free and Open Source web shopping for Africa where even a clean market is not existing in Main city Yaounde !
 - AT the university of bremen-white-racist, I Visited a course titled "E-business technologies 2"; I don't remember the name of the professor but I DID SO while I WAS in my 3rd year as part of so called "ANGEWANDTE INFORMATIK" ("Applied Computer Science"). IN graduate level course "E-business technologies 2", I learned about n-tiers web architectures, SOAP-Service Oriented Architecture Protocol, etc.

ALSO, in my 2nd year, there was a small "practicum" where I learned on PHP, and MariaDB; "ERIC-cuon-pd STREIBL" was the organizer.

2. "DUT-Diplôme Universitaire de Technologie" CHRISTIAN ngueyong rikong" (Start-Up)

CHRISTIAN ngueyong rikong is a seasoned software developer that creates large to medium-sized websites; AND Google-android mobile applications for his clients around world.

"CHRISTIAN rikong ngueyong, that I schooled with in Douala secondary school — "ALFRED SAKER HIGH SCHOOL" — would also not be against such a tool-framework that could reduce his development time and effort, since BLACK-USA entrepreneurs cannot afford tremendous amount of money for tools sold by MICROSOFT CORP., FACEBOOK INC., etc. !" (<https://www.christianrikong.com>)

3. "Dr. (B.Sc.) Claudel Noumbissi" (Start-Up)
4. "Ing. (B.Sc.) Arthur Zang" (Start-Up)
5. "Dr.-Ing. (Ph.D.) Ibrahim Nguena Moukouop" (Start-Up)
6. "Dr.-Ing. (Ph.D.) Thomas Djotio Ndié" (Start-Up)
7. "Institut Universitaire de la Cote", Douala (Start-Up)
8. "Santa Lucia – AHALA", Yaounde (Currently using Odoo ERP web & thick-client) !
9. "DR. (M.Sc.) Fabrice Wilfried Siemni" (Start-Up)

Fabrice WILFRIED siemni could generate sample website pages with no programming knowledge at all.

10. etc.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES 6 – CONTINUED –

Table 7: YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL keywords and meaning (An excerpt).

YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 keyword	(level) Nested in keyword	Programming related meaning
1. yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN		Contains web site all pages description
2. web_html_page_menu_bar_headers	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	Contains web site each page menubar pages names
3. web_html_page	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	A HTML page description
4. yri_html_page_title	(3) web_html_page	A HTML page title
5. yri_html_page_input_header_menu_bar	(3) web_html_page	Inputs a menubar onto this HTML page
6. yri_html_page_text_SECTION	(3) web_html_page	Describes a text section on a HTML page
7. VARIABLE_YRI_PARAGRAPH	(6) yri_html_page_text_SECTION	Defines text paragraph within a HTML page
8. text_yri_font_size	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	Defines a font size
9. text_yri_width_box	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	Defines a width for a text paragraph

Figure 6: Webbrowser-based software architecture : at least 4 layers logical software architecture (Image modified from online pdf paper "FlashCache: A NAND Flash Memory File Cache for Low Power Web Servers" [<https://doi.org/10.1145/1176760.1176774>] by Trevor et al.). YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF runtime monitors communication layers.

27.27.2 RELATED WORK at YERITH R&D; Software System Architecture of ERP Systems

- "Our paper not for publication in a conference paper, [SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH-ERP-3.0\[?\]](https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf) : (https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf); reveals common web system architecture patterns and structure, INCLUDING ([CYBER-SECURITY\[34\]](#)) software system security vulnerability analysis; As observed these last 10 years at least from "October 14, 2025".
- ["WE have visited, in year 2013, an online software security vulnerability detection and protection course with the STANFORD-university-racist while attending our degree [DOCTORAL PH.D.-program at the University of Waterloo;] THIS required acquired knowledge helps us creating safe and secure software systems by Construction."]
- "WE previously, in our "3rd semester", at the University-racist of Bremen, Bremen, GERmany-idiot; Have visited a course for undergraduates named "Information Security 1" given by "TZI.DE (Technology Center for Computer Science) (<https://www.tzi.de/en>)" founding member "Prof. Dr-Ing. Carsten-cuon-obèse Bormann-nazi" (<https://www.tzi.de/BORMAN-nazi>)."
- ★ ★ "I could also achieved a running taint analysis ([git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis)) for the Quercus PHP JAVA web application server during my post-doctoral studies & work at the university-racist of waterloo in ontarian Canada-idiot. IT was a graduate course taught by "Frank-idiot-nazi TIP-gay-cuon"."] ★ ★

27.27.3 WHAT YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 Would Service & Provide

- "Qt 5 software development platform" enables auto-deployment for Android-google platform." (<https://>)
 YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yeritherppgiwebsystem>) will reuse this functionality to generate legacy web source code files (HTML5, PHP, CSS, Javascript (GWT (Google Web Toolkit))); VIA a translation program-technology from "Qt 5-ui (user-interface)" files onto YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 input file coin as DSL-specific YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 files ("spec_html"); Figure 4.;
- We at YERITH R&D could then use any "Qt 5-Designer tool as a WYSIWYG Tool for generating Web-HTML-PHP pages : YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL" !
- "We plan at mid-term to be able to generate "Software architecture proof testing-programs", both for GUI-interfaces (thick-client), and Web-interfaces (thin-client); automatically just by specifying certain behavioral interactions using state diagram mealy machines ([SDMM\[1d\]](#)).";
- "The so-called "Software architecture proof testing-programs" will have certain warranties about [cyber-security], about [cyber-safety], [runtime-memory usage] and [user-defined usage rules].".

27.27.4 Implementation Technologies

I use "flex and bison compiler / translator generation technology" for creating YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL. I plan to automatically generate code for enabling runtime monitoring of the generated web sites. A first version of this FOSS (Free And Open Source Software) is available at URL: [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9) .

27.27.5 YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL Keyword Table

Table 7 depicts and explains commands and directives for creating web-based HTML pages sites.

We plan also the generation of web sites based on an "n-tiers architecture pattern", illustrated for instance in Figure 6; that demonstrated solid resistance in practice for more than 10 years now as demonstrated by applications server existence and usage such as :

1. Apache tomcat application server
2. Glassfish application server: mainly used in combination with JAVA OSI component-based software development architecture.
3. Quercus PHP server interpreter application server
4. IBM websphere

All this work has to solve the issue of generating certain portion of web sites for customers and users of ["YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM"\[?\]](#) Enterprise Resource Planing software in a time period in-between of 3 years from this year 2024 !

"ALL THIS UNDER THE PROTECTION OF OUR LORD AND SAVIOR JEOVAH-NISSI IN HEAVEN."

28.28 Securing Websites

Figure 7: A Sample Taint-analysis State Diagram MEALY-georges machine file.

```

1. yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec YERITH_QVGE_sample_TaintAnalysis
2. {
3.   START_STATE(T0):NOT_IN_BEFORE(in,yri_tainted_analysis.sanitizers_methods)
4.   ->[not_in_sql_event_log('SELECT.i0#sanitize',STATE(T0))]/'INSERT.i0#in'->
5.     FINAL_STATE(TF):IN_POST(i0,yri_tainted_analysis.tainted_values).
6. }

```

Figure 8: A Sample Taint-analysis State Diagram MEALY-georges machine.

$\underline{Q_0} := \text{NOT_IN_BEFORE}(op, yri_tainted_analysis.sanitizers) ; \quad \overline{Q_F} := \text{IN_POST}(i0, yri_tainted_analysis.tainted).$

28.28.1 Motivation

Numerous security vulnerabilities towards and against web applications exist :

- **“SQL injection”** : “A user tries to make a software execute a SQL query on a software-connected database by passing for instance; **THROUGH user credential input SQL-code to destroy part or all your database.**

user-name: 'Insert into users ('user_name', 'user_password') values ('drop table users', 'drop database');

- **“Format Strings”** : A software has part of it receiving directly input from an outside-world interface and using it without checking it is proper formed. Any malformed input can cause a mal-interpretation of data & could then caused for instance; **A CRASH of the software under analysis !**

int variable_x = 0; scanf(%, variable_x); // Wrong format is expected by scanf !.

// scanf currently expects a string instead of an integer.

- **“Cross-site scripting attacks”**; **“Buffer-overflow”**; **“Man-in-the-Middle”**; etc.
- **ALL cyber-security types** We previously wrote about in this listing items could be detected by removing all tainted values of an application; I.E.; provide a validation function and / or method, for each tainted value.

THIS is best done during testing of the software product before delivery of an end-product to clients and / or customers.

A recovery from a fail state accepting error program location can be done by adding a generic recovery validating function and / or method that Could identify; and provide; best sanitizing / validating method for each tainted input.

SINCE YERITH_QVGE provide only forbidden trace specification, a recovery and detection is generally only possible after at least 1 violation of the SDMM specification property automaton has been achieved !

A usage scenario with in future coming dedicated PC-Tablet computer YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF; could be found in Figure 1.

Our approach to add more security & safety to open-source webshops generated by our technology YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL is manifold :

- 1.) **USE of runtime verification & monitoring platform YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) :
 - **USE of standard security vulnerability breaches detection mechanisms** as for Instance illustrated for Taint Analysis in this Subsection 28.28.3 !
 - **USE of developer-otherly specified security vulnerabilities patterns** expressed as SDMM, & similarly described as for instance in Figure 8 !

28.28.2 Event Race Parallel-Concurrent Processes

- 1.)

28.28.3 Dynamic Taint Analysis for Web Security

- 1.) *IN a previous work at the university–racist of waterloo, in Canadian–whitte ontario [3], we've implemented in web–server Quercus; A dynamic taint analysis using JAVA as programming language.*

We plan to re–use Quercus as web–application server for generated webshops from YERITH–WEB–DESIGN–TOOL.

- 2.) *Currently, we have created YRI–DB–RUNTIME–VERIF, 1 runtime monitoring container generator that enables creation of taint analysis engine with no coding for a developer; IT only requires to deliver a state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) specification expressed using a textual description DSL–language called **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG** [1c] : Figure 7;*

This textual description (Domain-Specific Language) offers also, when a state diagram mealy machine has more than 2 states, a reference communicating processes parallel specification for the problem under analysis since processes are synchronized on each event after a 1st event because each state of the state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) represents a potential other parallel running process state; Illustration follows for instance in Figure 8.

28.28.4 Warranties on Web Pages–Security

- 1.) *[Warranties on Cyber–Safety].*

29.29 WEB-QT Assembly : A comparison with [YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL](#)

- WebAssembly-technology of QT-trolltech uses a platform independent binary format (called emscripten) to deliver website functionality for QT-application out-of-the-box;

Technology emscripten is not open-sourced and it is not as simple as "use of [YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL](#)".

30.30 WYSIWYG-Tool for generating websites

Figure 9: YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL : A SCREENSHOT of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 generator within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum.

Figure 9 illustrates a design engineering modeling window frame originating from ERP-software YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum for automatically generating webshop for its users.

30.30.1 Motivation

Numerous users of ERP-YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum would be also interested in having a WWW-online presentation for interacting with their clients and / or customers.

In our white-black paper SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH-ERP-3.0[?]? : (https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf); we motivate why we prefer fat-client software-system architecture over thin-client (also called website-architecture).

However we also want to enable our users to be online on the web easily by just pressing a button since costs to develop another system might be very impressing. THAT is why YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum offers now for its users and / or developers an interface for automatically generating and deploying website-webshops solutions that reuse any information already present in the database created & running as a fat-thick-client (QT) architecture.

30.30.2 Steps & Technology

- Selecting QT-trolltech ui files to transform into web-HTML5 and / or PHP files;
- Pressing a button that generates PHP-HTML5 files via a step-by generation of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 files.

Our use of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 has advantages of preventing us of drastic changes in either HTML5 standards or platforms since YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 represents a website architecture as a high-level programming language (e.g.: C++, JAVA, etc.).

Listing 1: A sample very limited for explanation & illustration purpose YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 Source code !

```

1  yerith-web-pages-generator-MAIN YECEFOIQ-WEB-PAGES
2  {
3
4  web-html-page index
5  {
6  yri_html_page_title: 'Bienvenue au centre de formation qualifiante Yecefoiq !';
7  yri_html_page_input_header_menu_bar[web-html-page-menu-bar-headers];
8  yri_html_page_MENU_BAR_link_string: 'yri_index !';
9
10 yri_html_page_text_SECTION (HTML_HEADER_H/3; 'Description du Centre de Formation')
11 {
12 VARIABLE_YRI_PARAGRAPH variable_paragraph_1
13 {text-yri-font-size = 5} :
14 {text-yri-width-box = 5cm} ==
15 "PLEASE read following list items ordered !:"
16
17 li_begin: '1st list item'
18 li: '2nd list item.'
19 li_end: 'Last list item.'
20 };
21 };
22
23 web-html-page-menu-bar-headers {
24 web-html-page-menu-bar-headers_Position = 'vertical-left';
25
26 yri_html_page_section[index,
27 programme_des_cours,
28 contenu_des_cours,
29 impressum];
30 };
31 }

```


31.31 Software Validation with YERITH_QVGE (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)

Figure 10: A parallel system example ping-pong with David-harel statechart; Example created and / or inspired from QT-trolltech sample; in Documentation present; Statechart found in some place I don't remember yet..

Figure 11: A sample ping-pong parallel process depicted in Figure 10.

```

1. yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec YERITH_QVGE_sample_PingPong
2. {
3.   START_STATE(pinger)
4.   ->[in_sql_event_log('ping',STATE(pinger))]/'pong'->
5.     STATE(ponger):IN_POST_NOP
6.     ->[in_sql_event_log('pong',STATE(ponger))]/'pong'->
7.       FINAL_STATE(pinger_two):IN_POST_NOP.
8. }

```

Software System Validation checks whether certain software system properties are **IMPLEMENTED CORRECTLY** according to its specifications.

1. Software **VALIDATION** as an automatic test case generation runtime monitoring instance from **YERITH_QVGE** !

- a.) A test case is generated without checking for test data using a constraint solver engine because it can be acquired only by manual interaction with the software under analysis.

31.31.1 Cyber-Safety Warranties & Others

1.) **Warranties on Cyber-Security**.

12.12 Software Verification Engineering Modeling with SDMM

Figure 12: A SAMPLE state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) file.

```

1. yr_sd_mealy_automaton_spec yr_missing_department_NO_DELETE
2. {
3.   START_STATE(dept_exists):NOT_IN_BEFORE(YRI_ASSET, dept.dept_name)
4.   ->[in_sql_event_log('DELETE.dept.YRI_ASSET', STATE(dept_exists))]/'SELECT.dept'->
5.     ERROR_STATE(dept_exists):IN_AFTER(YRI_ASSET,stocks.dept_name).
6. }

```

Figure 13: A motivating example, as previous bug found in YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum; A SQL-database based only in a disk-file with not much roundabout code could also be used instead of a full-featured database management system such as MariaDB (<https://www.mariadb.com>).

$Q_0 := NOT_IN_BEFORE(YRI_ASSET, dept.dept_name)$; $Q_1 := IN_AFTER(YRI_ASSET, stocks.dept_name)$.

"SDMM state diagram formalism is more powerful and expressive than David-harel statechart formalism. I.E. As depicted in fig. 15, a drawing-design is not well capable of scaling for a software-system with for instance 9 sub-systems events and / or states."

Figure 14: A David-harel statechart modeling of a temporal property expressed as a finite state diagram machine of mealy-GEORGES in fig. 13.

Figure 15: A parallel system example ping-pong with David-harel statechart.

1. Software Engineering Design & Verification using state diagram mealy machine (SDMM), runtime monitoring & static code analysis :

- WE are working & researching on translating automatically viable statechart specification onto state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) runtime monitoring verification specifications;
- USER requirement elicitation & specification is easily transcribed into a formal SDMM automaton-formula; Even by a mathematician with not much knowledge in Computer Technical Programming; As THIS is required when developers use David-Harel Statechart visual formalism as you can observe in Figure 14 !

A temporal property specification using state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) only requires use of the following mathematic elements :

- Logic formulas to describe propositional formulas as conditions to trigger software system state-transitions; AND also to describe "GUARD-condition" to be checked 'VALID' before a software-system state-transition is triggered & executed by YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, a runtime monitoring verification container.
- Variables : to describe states & state-conditions (pre- & post-conditions).
- Formulas mustn't be drawn because there exists also a textual description language coined as a Domain-Specific Language called YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG [1c] : Figure 12 illustrates for instance a textual description for the mealy machine state diagram drawn in Figure 13 !
- "Statecharts by David-Harel, BECAUSE it is a visual formalism; Requires knowledge of code of drawing squares & other signs and keywords." !

- Modeling a temporal property specification added with state-transitions pre- & post-conditions is very tedious and complicated to realize using David-harel Statechart.

THIS kind of modeling is impressively more easy to realize using finite automata formalisms such as depicted in Figure 13; This figure depicts a temporal software system safety property designed with Mealy-machine, "And formalized as a state diagram mealy machine (SDMM (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) [1d]) by myself" !

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF is extremely efficient in usage and / or specification because state-conditions ("pre-condition underlined" & "post-conditions over-lined" are executed by a runtime execution "expansion algorithm" called "Method YRI_trigger_an_edge_event" that checks at no costs for users.)

- With statecharts, specification of software system with parallel subsystem doesn't scale well starting for instance with 8 subsystems, because all 8 subsystems must be drawn 1 inside others !

ON the contrary side, state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) only requires specifying an finite state automaton with more than 2 states, and linear in space & traversal algorithm complexity; Which is done automatically for a developer by the runtime monitoring verification generator-container YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF !.

- "OPEN-source version of the software system programming library QT-trolltech offers since version (at minimum number) 5.15 (around year 2020) a package called SCXML that implements David-harel statechart programming capabilities" !

13.13 Software Verification with YERITH_QVGE

A library or plugin at any layer (OR a combination mixture of layers) of a software system architecture could be verified and validated using YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF by applying a receipt: IT would be sufficient to map each system call wanted for call sequence verification and / or validation to a MySQL query: So one doesn't need to re-create new QT-DBus interfaces for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: E.g.: "SYSTEM V libc". [A sample use case for IBM-Websphere server web !]

Figure 16: Software system architecture of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: it is also a runtime monitor container for software verification.

Figure 17: YRI_QVGE software stack dependencies.

1. Create A FRAMEWORK FOR DYNAMIC runtime analysis and monitoring of Temporal Safety Property in Plugin-based software (Figure 17 illustrates graphically interdependency between these under described sub-projects.).

- a. **YRI_QVGE (an extension of Qt-QVGE):** A "CASE (computer-aided software engineering)", CLOSED SOURCE CODE SOFTWARE (CSCS), for creating and generating MEALY MACHINE STATE DIAGRAMS as GUI (GRAPHICAL USER INTERFACE) TOOL. [model-based testing, DSL – domain-specific languages] [06/2022 – CURRENT]

"[THE GUI TOOL YERITH_QVGE] (See Figure 23) GENERATES A FILE CONTAINING A MEALY MACHINE STATE DIAGRAM SPECIFICATION using YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG; this file could be used as input for the compiler YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP, so to gather a C++ package to run as runtime monitor within YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. THIS TOOL COSTS 2,500 EUROS."

- b. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF:** A Dynamic Program Monitoring Recovering Analyzer Generator for any software emitting QtDBus messages per sockets (See subsection 13.13.3 (Runtime Verification), and / or Figure 21; and / or Figure 24).

"THIS IS at time (October 14, 2025); State-of-art technology; comparable technology are for instance RT-Tester with TDIOHS (Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System); State Diagram formalism From "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH, SPIN-OFF THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN" (RT-Tester; MBT[?]). TDIOHS complies fully with all semantic elements of HAREL-statecharts !

"AND technologies "IBM Purify Plus"; "LOGSCOPE" ("Specification-Based Monitoring in C++") and "DejaVu" ("DejaVu: A Monitoring Tool for First-Order Temporal Logic") by [Dr. Klaus Havelund] at N.A.S.A (<https://www.nasa.gov>)".

- YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>

- c. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP:** a compiler using flex and bison, for YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF specification language (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG), so to automatically generate C++ code for runtime monitors implemented in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. [compilers, model-based testing, reactive system analysis, domain-specific languages] [04/2023 – CURRENT]

"COMPETITORS from LOGSCOPE and DejaVu; AND RT-Tester; MBT[?]; have similar description state diagram language; but work all of them as SPECIFICATION OF WISHED PROGRAM BEHAVIOR; whereas SDMM[1d] works at SPECIFICATION OF FORBIDDEN (fail) PROGRAM BEHAVIOR."

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang

- d. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG:** A SPECIFICATION LANGUAGE FOR STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM) extended with pre-/post-conditions on STATE DIAGRAM TRANSITIONS and with a final state. (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) [statecharts, model-based testing, reactive system analysis, domain-specific languages] [04/2023 – CURRENT]

"YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG complies fully to David-harel statecharts ["Statecharts: a visual formalism for complex systems" (<https://www.wisdom.weizmann.ac.il/~dharel/SCANNED.PAPERS/Statecharts.pdf>)] which is a visual formalism for states diagrams."

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang

- e. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS:** UNIT TESTING PROJECT for YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF. [06/2022 – CURRENT]
"THIS test unit suite is there to check peculiarities of project YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF; As a Free And OPEN SOURCE CODE SOFTWARE (foss), I strongly recommend using it before committing changes to the main git-branch project."

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS

- f. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF / YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF:** a framework for verifying SQL software correctness properties of gui software at runtime [06/2022 – CURRENT]

[model-based testing, reactive system analysis, computer software program analysis, computer software dynamic program analysis, software integration testing with SQL and GUI, runtime monitoring]

"YOU SPECIFY USING A STATE DIAGRAM AN ERRONEOUS SUT (System Under Test) TYPE STATE STYLE BEHAVIOR with YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF. USING YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, YOU CHECK AT RUNTIME WHETHER SUCH AN ERRONEOUS SUT SEQUENCE BEHAVIOR OCCURS."

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif

13.13.1 TAXONOMY : Software Verification vs. Program Code Verification

Figure 18: "Program verification (including model checking)" is a subset (C) of "SOFTWARE VERIFICATION". (See also research goal 13.)

Software System verification is a discipline to verify whether a software, meaning a product use at customer level and full-featured, conforms to certain software system user related usage properties.

In contrast, **program code verification** checks only program at the level of their source code or binary code product against code programming related properties, And not necessarily at level of a full featured user level product. Thus all code programming related properties could be cast down to certain software system related properties. **It follows PROGRAM VERIFICATION is a Subset Of Software (System) Verification: illustrated in Figure 18 !**

Program Analysis by Xavier-*yerith* (https://www.archive.org/details/yerith-program-analysis-2023/YERITH-PROGRAM_ANALYSIS_2024_With_CURRICULUM_vitae_2024.pdf) !

13.13.2 How to use YERITH_QVGE

A software component or a whole running software binary could be verified against SQL correctness temporal properties by USING *YRI_QVGE*, as illustrated in Figure 16:

- The 1st layer illustrates the runtime verifier tester monitor engine: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, that entails several custom runtime monitor specifications, provided by user.
- The 2nd layer shows the SUT (System Under Test); or PUA (Program Under Analysis); layer that communicates with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF through QT socket calls (via Dbus messages). Each event message is sent to all runtime monitors. The SUT source code has been instrumented first, so to specify which program statements actions are to be packaged as messages to YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. "INTEL-Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) could also be used to instrument program binaries at runtime directly, Avoiding recompilation and even usable where source code of SUT (PUA) is unavailable.
- The 3rd layer illustrates a library or plugin (i.e.: MySQL) that is being monitored via instrumentation of the SUT; in this case, the SUT is YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum. Other providers could modify An Open Source Code Version (FOSS) of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF to verify and monitor another library-plugin other than MySQL.
- The 4th and last layer shows the Operating System (OS) layer and its communication via systems calls with the 3rd layer of the library-plugin.

13.13.3 How to use YERITH_QVGE in relation to verification cyber-security detection remediation methods.

1. Model Checking (<https://wikipedia.org>):

Temporal logic formalisms, such as LTL (Linear Temporal Logic) (<https://>); Could be used to create State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM) (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf) [1d] and generate a binary executable of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b] to perform runtime monitoring, and runtime SQL recovery of Graphical User Interface (GUI) supported software (And also not supported GUI software). Users must only note that "SDMM" specifications are fail (forbidden) trace behavior specifications of a program under analysis (SUT).

Structures could be created on how to translate simple LTL constructs into simple "SDMM"; So to ease usage of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF;

2. Runtime Verification (Monitoring; including Software Cyber-Security Exploit Detection Remediation):

A whole class of problems involving sequencing of actions and / or method calls ranging from:

- Application Programming Interface (API) checking protocol usage;
- WEB-APPLICATION RUNTIME MONITORING[?]; Software Security Vulnerability Analysis: I.E. Taint Analysis;
- Firewall security rules enforcement filtering;
- Information Flow Policy Control and Enforcement : (E.g. : Figure 20);
- Checking of automated and / or manual (unit) test procedure conformance with regards to TESTED PROGRAM (SOFTWARE) temporal properties;
- etc.

Could be solved by usage of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF; YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF GIT-REPOSITORY[1b]: <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>. "Pr. Prof. Dr. Jean Yang, Ph.D." from CMU-"Carnegie Mellon University" (<https://www.cs.cmu.edu/~jyang2>)" could be a potential competitor in this area of research.":

A. "Jeeves Programming Language" – last updated "October 2015" (<https://projects.csail.mit.edu/jeeves>)

- API usage rule check at 'AKITA Software' (<https://www.akita.com>)' in USA; California (CA).
- "Jeeves Programming Language" enables static typing;
- Dynamic code source rewriting to achieve Semantics; implemented as an embedded Domain Specific Language (DSL) in Python programming language (IT is unclear in which document [PROFESSOR JEAN yang checks] that this code is correct).

Figure 19: Embedded program verifier notifier within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum; YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF runs as a background process service.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES IV – CONTINUED — 2 VS. Jeeves Programming Language

Table 8: Jeeves Programming Language Versus (Vs.) The Runtime Monitoring Verifier Tester YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF

"Information Flow and Policy Control"	YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	Jeeves Programming Language
1. Specification as a Domain Specific Language (DSL)	Yes (stand-alone SDMM (HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567) [1d] DSL specification; Based on MEALY MACHINE AUTOMATON; "HAREL-statechart (https://www.wisdom.weizmann.ac.il/~dharel/SCANNED.PAPERS/Statecharts.pdf) compatibility") ✓	yes (DSL embedded into Python)
2. False (Positives) Warnings	No (1 formal proof exists in journal paper (HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567) [1d]) ✓	* yes (CHECK A REFERENCE)
3. DSL Specification CARRIES DATA too	Yes (as Qt-DBus NETWORK data parameters) ✓	yes (as local stack function/method parameter)
4. As program annotations	Yes (FOSS Library Qt-DBus instructions) ✓	yes ('Jeeves' instructions)
5. USABLE in a any programming language	Yes (FOSS Library Qt-DBus instructions) ✓	no (Only Python)
6. ONLY usage with Python	No (any programming language that could emit Qt-DBus instructions) ✓	yes
7. Embedded in a programming language	NO ✓	yes (Python DSL library)
8. CRASH could occur during analysis and / or policy enforcing	NEVER	YES
9. Execution runtime overhead	No (concurrent event stream analysis monitoring verification) ✓	Yes (Embedded Python runtime dynamic source code rewriting)
10. Persistent storage technology	Yes; "MariaDB (https://www.mariadb.org)" ✓	Yes; "PostgreSQL (https://www.postgresql.org)" ✓

Table 8 compares tabularly the "Jeeves Programming Language" and "The Runtime Monitoring Verifier Tester YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF". In contrast to the "Jeeves Programming Language" that specifies information flow policy and control enforcement for Python, YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF is not implemented as programming language feature, and thus could be used for any software system that could emit Qt-DBus signals ; Thus, information flow control and enforcement is run as a separate process, concurrently to the system under analysis (verification or monitoring) as pictured in Figure 16.

Figure 33 illustrates a sample SDMM ([HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567](https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567)) [1d] specifying that a "FILE SHALL NOT be written-updated after it HAS BEEN CLOSED-DELETED".

13.13.4 Runtime Dynamic Program Interpretation Rewriting with "Jeeves"

The information flow policy control and enforcement solution provided by the "Jeeves Programming Language" is as follows :

1. A domain-specific language (DSL) is defined and embedded in a modification of the dynamic interpreted programming language Python. The drawback of an embedded DSL is a non re-usability in using other programming languages and framework other than those related closely to Python;

2. Only certain cases are flow policy control and enforcement are solved statically by "Python-Jeeves" type system;

It means that 'false positives warnings' cases still exist in programmer code and couldn't be removed by static compilation and / or dynamic code interpretation.

In contrast, "the mixed formal methods – runtime dynamic analysis monitoring" I used in "YRI_QVGE", don't allow by construction for 'false positives warnings': A 'false positive warning' is a message from the analyzing system that indicates an error accepting state while THERE IS IN EFFECT NO ERROR found yet.

3. Flow policy enforcement is solved dynamically at runtime by dynamic code rewriting; WE HOPE that this feature could be proved sound for all program statements because it might create uncertainty of valid flow policy enforcement at all.

Differently, "YRI_QVGE" uses SQL database statement query for performing error accepting state recovery (~~or also called "Information Flow Policy Control and Enforcement"~~).

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES IV – CONTINUED — 2 VS. Jeeves Programming Language

13.13.5 Sample Comparison BETWEEN Object-ORIENTED programming languages”

Table 9: COMPARISON TABLE BETWEEN C++, Python, AND JAVA. JAVA has an (interpretative and / or JIT-compiled) virtual machines that are in FACT reactive systems (E.g. : A "GUI software" is as well a reactive system) ! (WYSIWYG: What You See Is What You Get; VM: Virtual Machine)

FEATURES	C++	PYTHON	Java
1. PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE PHILOSOPHY	object-oriented	object-oriented	object-oriented
2. MACROS	✓	”	
3. MULTIPLE INHERITANCE	✓		
4. support INTERFACES	✓	✓	✓
5. STATIC COMPILATION	✓	✓	
6. RUNTIME MONITORING & VERIFICATION	✓ (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)	✓ (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)	✓ (VM INTERPRETATION AND MANAGEMENT)
7. UNIT TESTING FRAMEWORK	✓	✓	✓
8. NETWORK CAPABLE	✓	✓	✓
9. CROSS PLATFORM PORTABLE	✓	✓	✓
10. include FILE LIBRARY CAPABILITY	✓	✓	
11. MULTI THREADING	✓	✓	✓
12. WYSIWYG GUI DESIGN TOOL	✓	”	✓
13. VIRTUAL MACHINE IS A REACTIVE SYSTEM			✓

13.13.6 "Formal Methods – Runtime Dynamic Analysis" Vs. "Compiler Static Analysis Technology"

Figure 20: Runtime Verification Monitoring with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

Figure 21: YERITH SDMM based runtime monitoring verification analysis.

Figure 22: A sample [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET] in action.

I advocate :

1. Solving problems using compiler static analysis technology; that is based on lattice-theory is more safe than formal methods algorithms at first because MANUAL model checking has to be used to prove formal methods solutions correct, which could be very tedious and lengthy; "OR EVEN INTRACTABLE". SEE the state explosion problem (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Model_checking).

On the other hand static dataflow analysis algorithms based on lattice-theory are safe by construction and don't need no more proofs of consistency and validity as long as they only follow the base-pattern algorithm as for instance defined by "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)".

THE previous statement also applies when using an instance of a static dataflow analysis based on the IFDS (Interprocedural, Finite, Distributive, Subset) (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Inter-procedural-data-flow-analysis-with-IFDS-IDE-Bodden/a3f7557fe673ff0711e9049cf5ece8b02a51f7f1>) algorithm from "THOMAS reps" (<https://www.grammatech.com>) at "The University of Winsconsin-MADISON-mad". (<https://www.wisc.edu>)

2. The formal method approach I use in solving problems listed in "Subsection 13.13.3"; a combination of formal methods with runtime dynamic analysis is as perfect as the "static dataflow analysis" standard algorithm by "Gary A. kildall", because **YRI_QVGE** uses only "fail (forbidden) traces" specifications and only exactly 1 outgoing edge for each transition in a state diagram mealy machine specification (<https://www.zenodo.org/RECORDS/13232567>) [1d]:

A whole class of problems involving sequencing of actions and / or method calls ranging from :

- Application Programming Interface (API) checking protocol usage;
- Software Security Vulnerability Analysis: I.E. Taint Analysis;
- Information Flow Policy Control and Enforcement: I.E. ...
- Checking of automated and / or manual (unit) test procedure conformance with regards to TESTED PROGRAM (SOFTWARE) temporal properties;
- etc.

3. Runtime Verification Analysis Results Combined With Static Dataflow Analysis Algorithms à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)" as ; for instance implemented in "Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) :

- o One could combine runtime verification analysis facts with static dataflow analysis so to reduce fail state accepting code source location paths.

For instance, applying **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b] to find an API violation rule such as a "FILE-Write-AFTER-FILE-close" as specified in Figure 33; that specifies a "SDMM DSL code (<https://www.zenodo.org/RECORDS/13232567>) [1d]" for finding a write after close program execution :

- a.) WHENEVER such a "file Close-WRITE API rule violation usage" is found by a runtime monitoring verifying analysis program binary, this information could later on be used by a static analyzer on code sources to eliminate manually from the program code sources code the found API violation RULE.
- b.) Our work : "Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) on detecting tainted path with an application for finding API usage rule violation in C++ code as ILLUSTRATED in Figure 35, COULD be used for instance !
- c.) Symbolic Execution / test-cases-test-data generation :

WHENEVER a fail-state accepting state is found by a run execution of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF;

- 1.) Such a run could only be executed with some test data stored somewhere in the SUT; a test case is also available for free since of the trace event log.

Such acquired test cases & test data could then be used later on to create some "testing suites" to exhibit this fail-state accepting error sequence run !

Symbolic execution run with finding of test data using a constraint solver like "Microsoft-Z3" (<https://www.microsoft.com/research--idiot--z3>) for instance, is only needed in case more test data and / or test cases are required for this fail-state accepting run.

13.13.7 CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) TOOL for Software System Verification AND / OR algorithmic trading trade-time

Figure 23: A SCREENSHOT OF YERITH_QVGE FOR GRAPHICAL DESIGN OF STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM) SPECIFICATIONS; THAT COULD SPECIFY TRADE OPERATIONS BASED ON TRADE-TIME.

Figure 24: A SCREENSHOT OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL ERROR EVENT LOG.

1. [YERITH_QVGE] has also applications in specifying real-time trading operations based on trade-time; YERITH_{r&d} is going in the next years, to develop an algorithmic trading platform for free, Especially for exchanging inventory physical stock products (goods) for AFRICA; this is an ongoing project as an extension of the Enterprise Resource Planing SOFTWARE [YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM?]; [YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME].

HAVING as physical good a currency bill and / or coin is Not impossible: THIS is what we daily practice when we buy items at a cashier and / or in street rural market; So people possessing a bill and / or coin may have advantages over people having only inventory physical consumer goods for their exchanges; SO it must be that parts of markets might Not ACCEPT currency bills AND / OR coins "for equity and fairness" since not everyone can afford buying currencies and / or bills-coins at a bank and / or financial institution. !

Having to buy currencies to European UNION, for instance for CMR, is very expensive. PART of exchanges within AFRICA borders could be done just by physical product (good) exchange between people and / or governments; Especially since getting currencies bills and / or coins is very expensive.

■ RELATED work at "QUANTstamp.com"; Venture funded initially by Y-COMbinator from STANFORD.EDU (<https://www.stanford.edu>) :

QuantStamp.com (<https://www.quantstamp.com>) is a firm that works mainly on solving the main problem on 'How to verify, check, a correct con-formant "bitcoin" contract on an Ethereum-platform trading (<https://>) : a so called SmartContract (<https://www.iq.wiki/wiki/quantstamp>)'.

"Figure 31 shows in French language a similar "stock-physical exchange" architecture based on an Ethernet-network "RJ45, and / or Giga-USB;" for YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum users."

2. Create and produce a computer device that could be embedded into other computer devices and that will communicate with them through serial ports and / or USB interfaces SO to provide YRI_QVGE program verification to USER FINISHED products on-the-fly, AS an add-on ENGINEERED industrial product: ALSO this product could qualify for an ISO-related certification for avionics, railways, automotive, and CE-ISO certifications for Healthcare: [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET].

Figure 25: A sample [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET] in action.

POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS:

- a.) "ON-the-fly (Add-hoc)" online / offline RUNTIME Verification MONITORING of all financial transaction operations at a financial institution; ATTACH a device at each computer and / or server using YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum; A comparable instance figure is illustrated for a control console device at Figure 25; WHEREAS one replaces a "control console LINAC" device with SERVER / Computer.
- b.) A linear accelerator control console communication protocol runtime monitoring (E.g.: Figure 25). A more detailed explanation graphical occurs in "Figure 20, Section 13.13.6";
- c.) A railway track controller program runtime monitoring console at site;
- d.) An aero-plane Maneuvering Characteristics Augmentation System (MCAS) runtime monitoring device
- e.) etc.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III – Distributed & Operating Computing Systems (ERP; Software & Hardware)

Figure 26: BUSINESS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Figure 27: Software System COMPONENTS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

1. **CREATE A VERY CHEAP AND PRAGMATIC enterprise resource planing (ERP) software system** [Mar. 2015 – CURRENT]
 [STOCK EXCHANGE network for Francophone AFRICA; agile development method, [enterprise resource planing software], software engineering, computer software programming, computer software testing, computer program analysis]
 - a. RENDER ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING (ERP) SOFTWARE SYSTEM USAGE AND MANIPULATION AS EASY AS READING A LEISURE OR RECREATIONAL BOOK SO TO REDUCE USER STRAIN SIZE ! (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>)
 - b. CONTRIBUTE TO REDUCE POVERTY BY IMPROVING SOFTWARE SYSTEM TECHNOLOGY FOR ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING (ERP). (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>)
 1. All following advantages of using YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum contributes to reduce waiting files; THUS increase the number of customers and clients of an entrepreneurial organization !
 2. Best and accurate technology SHALL REDUCE management effort and produce more reliable and cost-minimized business financial accounting information that enables to anticipate and reduce time of decision making.
 - 1.) Gathering an overview over all financial and commercial; And customers / clients transaction information comes in JUST 1 button pressing from business dashboard window.
 - 2.) Exporting data onto Tabulator software such as 'LibreOffice-Calc, etc.' as Comma-Separated-Values (CSV), is as easy as selecting requested database table columns and Export them by pressing a button;
 - 3.) Calculating beneficial and interests costs is just as easy as reading it from business financial dashboard report generated automatically real-time and real-data from sales and customers, and / or Acquisitions databases tables.
 3. Best and accurate technology reduces time execution of commercial business transactions, and thus, associated costs.
 - 1.) Business Analytics : Ranking about sold and transferred goods and / or item stocks is best and just as easy done by reading it from a business commercial window dashboard; Ranking data decides what to order next for a better business turnover for your commercial financial entrepreneurial organization;
 - 2.) Ordering new item stocks is as easy as reading item stocks quantities from stocks window stock's inventory value.
 4. So entrepreneurial commercial organizations could reduce a selling price without reducing its profit.

14.14 R&D Hardware & Software System Components

- o YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET [docs] — for Security / Safety.
 - o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 [algo] [docs] 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)
 - o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-CONFIGURATIONS-DATA [algo] [docs] 📄 <https://zenodo.org/records/14868175>
 - o YERITH-ERP-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM [algo] [docs] YERITH-ERP-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM[?] (🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9))
 - o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RM-SYSTEM [algo] [docs] 📄 [YRI_QVGE\[1\] \(git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif\)](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)
 - o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-HR-SERVICE-DAEMON [algo] [docs] 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon)
 - o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON [algo] [docs] 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)
 - o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RT-SYSTEM [algo] [docs] 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)
- TODO for YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME !!!**

14.14.1 Detailed Presentation View

1. **HARDWARE device for on-the-fly runtime verification monitoring:** ★ YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET.
 FOSS documents location to..come.on..github.com/yerithrd (<https://github.com/yerithrd>)
2. **ERP software itself:** ★ YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
 FOSS code location; **WARNING : we migrate 'varchar(256)' into 'varchar(50) mostly' !** 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)
3. **Component 1:** ★ "yerith-erp-9-0-configurations-data": Configuration data for YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
 This software component entails:
 - A configuration property file "yerith-erp-9-0.properties" that contains MariaDB database connection parameters data.
 - A configuration property file "yerith-erp-9-0-system-local-configuration-ENGLISH.properties" that contains local computer device and storage configuration parameters data.
 - A folder "yerith-erp-9-0-sql-backup-restore" where YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM database backups will be stored.
4. **Component 2:** ★ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM[?]: Web Sites Generator Software Component.
 FOSS code location 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9)
5. **Component 3:** ★ YRI_QVGE[1]: Runtime Monitoring Analysis Verification System.
 FOSS code location 1 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)
 FOSS code location 2 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)
 FOSS code location 3 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)
 FOSS code location 4 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS)
6. **Component 4:** ★ "yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon": Service daemon for human resources related payments.
 FOSS code location 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon)
7. **Component 5:** ★ "yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon": Service daemon for alerts over inventory stocks, assets, and financial expenses.
 FOSS code location 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III – Distributed & Operating Computing Systems ("Adversaries systems")

Figure 28: BUSINESS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Figure 29: Software System COMPONENTS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Table 10: Comparison between 'YERITH-ERP-9.0' and 3 top tier-1 ERP systems

Features	'YERITH-ERP-9.0' (≈ 10 years old)	'Contr-ALL' (≈ 7 years old)	'Sage Gescom i7' (≈ 40 years old)	'SAP Business One' (≈ 40 years old)
★ HR & Accounting full featured ERP	YES	NO	YES	YES
★ runtime monitoring checks enabled	YES (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)	NO	YES	YES
★ Documentation online available fully	YES (Here For Instance) (https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724)	NO	NO	NO
separate views per user role	YES	YES	YES	YES
complete training (or solution)	at least 4 weeks	at least 3 weeks	at least 2 months	at least 3 months
★ difficulty in navigation	easy	easy	very difficult	very difficult
usage language in software	easy everyday English	simple	simple	technical
financial accounting knowledge	no	no	no	useful
advanced marketing knowledge	no	no	useful	useful
★ internet connection	optional	useful (not at all internet means no access to any of your business resources.)	optional	optional

Table 10 illustrates 3 other top-ERP Systems that I deem to be serious competitors of YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum for now and in future time because of the quality of their design and / or features; As Implemented for now As I could find out.

Some Observations

1.) 'Contr-ALL' is a youngest one with only at time of initial investigation after an interview Questions & Answers with its creator "Rostand-MOUNGAM", 7 years old !

"Rostand MOUNGAM" rents 1 of my apartment for his legal living & business consulting services, Together with "NAOMIE" his wife !

2.) 'Contr-ALL' seems very close to a good ERP System like 'Sage Gescom i7' !

'Sage Gescom i7' is at time of writing (June 2025) around 40 years old !

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III (Software Systems) – CONTINUED — 3 – "ALGORITHMS CREATED / INVENTED"

1. CREATE A VERY CHEAP AND PRAGMATIC *enterprise resource planing software (ERP)* [Mar. 2015 – CURRENT]
 ["YERITH R&D" Publications, STOCK EXCHANGE network for Francophone AFRICA, agile development method, enterprise resource planing software, software engineering, computer software programming, computer software testing, computer program analysis]

15.15 Summary of Created And / Or Invented ALGORITHMS in this ERP Project

Figure 30: Manager Main Window in YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum

- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 — Algorithms Excerpt [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)
 1. Non intermingling of QT-timer & User-button-pressing events for Cancellation Confirmation. ["class YerithERPCancelModificationTimingObject"]C++; YRI_QVGE.
 - a.) Dynamic selection of Cancellation withing each window frame based on user interaction. ["class YerithWindowsCommons"] C++; Qt 5.
 2. Concurrent algorithms using semaphores so to allow disk configuration data usage between multiple users. ["class YerithPOSUser; class YerithWindowsCommons"]C++; Qt 5.
 3. Manual Selection & Viewing of user QTableView columns. ["class YerithWindowsCommons"] C++; Qt 5; mathematics-geometry.
 4. Checking of daemon service running processes & emitting signals onto user viewing buttons. ["class YerithAdminWindow"]C++; Qt 5; Bash; lxqt-sudo.
 5. Automatic online English / French translation algorithm. ["class YerithWindowsCommons"] C++; Qt 5.
 6. Password detection & MD5-hash-Coding / Decoding for QT-widgets automatically. ["class YerithPushButtonPASSWORD"] C++; Qt 5.
 7. Selection of each ERP sale-service function within only 1 window frame. ["class YerithEntrerWindow"] C++; Qt 5.
 - a.) Graph coloring algorithm to find paths. FSA; Graph-based algorithms.
 8. Pagination of QT-table data structure view-layout("QTableView") ["class YerithWindowsCommons"] C++; Qt 5.
 9. Printing & Creation of PDF documents based on LaTeX documentation system ["class YerithTableViewPRINT_UTILITIES_TEX_TABLE"]C++; Qt 5; LaTeX.
 - a.) Progress bar automatic Delivery for PDF-printing. ["class YerithProgressBar"] C++; Qt 5.
 10. Online textual search & display of database query for window table frame items. ["class YerithAbstractClassYerithSearchWindow"] C++; Qt 5.
 11. Automatic upgrade of SQL database between versions of YERITH-ERP-9.0. [folder "yerith-erp-9-0-upgrade-sql/"] Git, Bash; SQL.
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-CONFIGURATIONS-DATA — Algorithms Excerpt <https://zenodo.org/records/14868175>
 1. BASH-scripts to automatically generate a ".deb" file that entails configuration data for ERP-system software YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum ! DEBIAN LINUX 11; Bash.
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM — Algorithms Excerpt [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9)
 1. Translation algorithm from QT XML interface design-drawings onto YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 ! ["class YERITH_WEB_SYSTEMS_MAIN_GENERATOR"]Qt 5-QXmlStreamReader.
 2. Translator to generate PHP; HTML5; CSS code sources from YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0. ["yerith-web-pages-generator/src"]YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0; flex; bison.
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RM-SYSTEM — Algorithms Excerpt [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)
 1. FSM based communication RPC algorithms to monitor and verify temporal properties scheme of [GUI] software. ["Library YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"]DBus; C++; Qt 5.
 2. BNF grammar YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG Translator into a State Diagram Mealy Machine FSM. ["Library YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"] flex; bison.
 3. State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM) library that enables runtime monitoring on-the-fly. ["Library YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"] C++; Qt 5.
 - a.) Fully compliant to David-harel statechart visual formalism. David-harel statechart.
 - b.) O(n) graph traversal algorithm (Method "YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(string)"). finite state automaton; forbidden (fail) trace specification.
 - c.) Grammar in Backus-Naur Form (BNF) for specifying State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM). BNF (Backus-Naur Form).
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-HR-SERVICE-DAEMON — Algorithms Excerpt [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON — Algorithms Excerpt [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)
 1. THREAD conform compliant algorithm to process stocks, & stocks-based alert messages triggered on time and / or quantities. C++; Qt 5.
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RT-SYSTEM — Algorithms Excerpt **TODO for YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME !!!**

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III (Software Systems) – CONTINUED — 2 – "DOCUMENTATION"

1. CREATE A VERY CHEAP AND PRAGMATIC *enterprise resource planing software (ERP)*

[Mar. 2015 – CURRENT]

[STOCK EXCHANGE network for Francophone AFRICA, agile development method, enterprise resource planing software, software engineering, computer software programming, computer software testing, computer program analysis]

16.16 Summary Documentation of YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Figure 31: *Generic Schema of Trading Realtime with YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum (French language)*

■ YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET (HARDWARE device for on-the-fly runtime verification monitoring)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)a. *Database network connectivity – FRENCH*

Configuration MULTI-SITES (SUCCURSALES)

https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-multi-sites-base-de-donnees/YERITH-ERP_multi_sites_base_de_donnees.pdfb. *Installation GUIDE – FRENCH*

Installation GUIDE – FRENCH

<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8060217>

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-CONFIGURATIONS-DATA

📄 <https://zenodo.org/records/14868175>

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RM-SYSTEM

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-HR-SERVICE-DAEMON

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RT-SYSTEM

TODO for YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME !!!

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES II – Dissertation Thesis Doctor–PH.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering

Figure 32: YERITH–SAINT (LGPL license) : Accessing JAVA code with "Polyglot LLVM frontend"

A Mealy Machine State Diagram (SDMM) Specified Using Figure 33: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF Specification Language for NO–WRITE–AFTER–CLOSE memory check API file usage rule.

```

1. yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec YERITH_QVGE_sample_Write_after_close_file
2. {
3.   START_STATE(closed):IN_PRE(g, is_alias(g, f))
4.   -> [in_set_trace('DELETE.file.f', STATE(closed))] / 'UPDATE.file.g' ->
5.     FINAL_STATE(WRITE_AFTER_CLOSE):IN_POST(g, is_alias(g, f)).
6. }

```

1. Create A FRAMEWORK FOR STATIC verification of Temporal Safety Property in Plugin–based software by static dataflow analysis mainly for the JVM–Java Virtual Machine; by late **Gary A. KILDALL** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall).

a. **Research Proposal (Doctoral Ph.D. Thesis) in Electrical & Computer Engineering :**

🔗 **"Temporal Property Verification in Plugin–based Software;"** (Advised by **Nomair Naem** | **Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.** | **Patrick Lam, Ph.D.**) |

[UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

YERITH_{R&D}, CENTER REGION, CAMEROON — (ADDENDUM WITH STATE DIAGRAM MEALY

[June 2024 – June 2024]

MACHINE (🔗 SDMM (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf)[1d]))

[YERITH R&D — [Software Safety], API (application programming interfaces) typestate checking;, tracematches, computer software static program analysis, computer software dynamic program analysis, software testing, software integration testing, YERITH R&D — [computer software cyber–security, GERMAN STYLE HABILITATION]

17.17 RESEARCH WORK OVERVIEW

THIS IS A PRELIMINARY WORK ON CHECKING TEMPORAL SAFETY PROPERTIES USING A TRACEMATCH–LIKE SPECIFICATION LANGUAGE; SOOT (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) AND DATAFLOW ANALYSIS IS USED TO PRESENT A STATIC WHOLE PROGRAM ANALYSIS.

TRACEMATCHES alike specifications enable developers to specify API usage rule drawing, as a deterministic finite automaton (<https://www.wikipedia.org>). Patrick LAM and Xavier noumbissi NOUNDOU have at this effect presented short overview slides of 30 minutes at IBM workshop CASCON 2010 ! (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>). PDFSAM (<https://www.pdfsam.org>), and sample other Open Source Code Software (FOSS) ARE USED as benchmark for project evaluation.

18.18 SOLUTIONS WITH LLVM BY CHRIS LATTNER AT "APPLE LTD."

Instead of the 1st proposed Java–Soot approach as a whole program static dataflow analysis, a whole program context–sensitive dataflow static taint analysis for C using LLVM could successfully be implemented and described in 🔗 YERITH–SAINT (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) [34].

The 1st YERITH–SAINT algorithm was implemented for programs written in C programming language, and used a pre–processing step for analyzing points–to set using "poolalloc" (<https://github.com/poolalloc>) from Chris Lattner (<https://www.llvm.org>).

BECAUSE our static dataflow taint analysis algorithm works on three–address–code, LLVM compiler framework could also apply YERITH–SAINT to JAVA code as input programming language to LLVM frontend–compiler–framework (Example : <https://github.com/polyglot-compiler/JLang>); See for instance Figure 32 !

20.20 RELATED WORK: DYNAMIC PROGRAM ANALYSIS API–RULE CHECKER "TRACERORY"

"Unread memory verification" is an instance of API (Application Programming Interface) usage rule checking.

"TRACERORY" runtime unread memory verification tool of Jon Eyolfson" (<https://www.hdl.handle.net/10012/6206>) ; "Detecting Unread Memory Using Dynamic Binary Translation at RV 2013 in Turkey" (<https://www.YRITOLOOKFOR.org>) , Of my former office roommate at "ECE–Waterloo–formal–method Davis Center Room" (<https://www.watform.uwaterloo.ca>), 1st floor, and colleague in static dynamic program analysis, could be outperformed with use of 🔗 YRI–DB–RUNTIME–VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b]: "a runtime monitor container for state diagram mealy machines (SDMM)".

"TRACERORY" uses runtime program binary code instrumentation in "INTEL–Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) to instrument running programs for purposes of detecting unread memory; I ignore whether "INTEL–Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) has an open–source FOSS competitor at time yet; — Jan. 15, 2025 —.

Figure 33 illustrates a sample "SDMM" specification with instrumentation of source code with statements 'DELETE.file.f' and 'UPDATE.file.g' for runtime verification monitoring of API usage rule for checking memory write integrity: Runtime function "is_alias(g, f)" tells whether heap variable "g", and "f" refers to the same memory address. Such a "SDMM" specification is synchronized against a running program within a runtime monitor container: YRI–DB–RUNTIME–VERIF (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) .

21.21 CONCLUSION

"Due to incompatibilities with Patrick LAM; after March 10, 2015, I abandoned this research idea because I couldn't afford being laid–off without any letter or any other formal mean of communication other than telling a lie about a supposed ["Ph.D. Research Seminar"] at EIT building in Waterloo main (200 University Ave West) Campus! " (Ph.D. Dissertation Defence at DAVID R. Cheriton School OF Computer Science in "January 2015")

It is easier to specify forbidden–fail–traces instead of saying how traces shall be like. Required 2 courses from overall 4 courses to pass where completed in year 2013–(CS846 & ECE750); in addition to before Examination completed courses (ECE725 & CS744). 4 experts in software systems were committee members of my doctoral PhD comprehensive examination AT UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA :

1. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.

Email: olhotak@cs.uwaterloo.ca

2. Derek Rayside, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

Email: drayside@uwaterloo.ca

3. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

Email: p23lam@uwaterloo.ca

4. Lin Tan, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

Email: lintan@purdue.edu

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (COURSES VISITED – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. Courses I VISITED while at the University–racist of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[ECE 725 / CS 745 – "Fall 2009",
CS 744 – "SPRING 2011",
First SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques – "SPRING 2011",
Computer Science related subjects courses,
program analysis,
YERITH R&D — [program verification],
model checking,
compiler design]

Summary–PAGES

Table 11: Visited Courses at THE university-racist of waterloo, ontario, canada-idiot

"Course Reference CODE" / "GRADE"	Period of YEAR	Course TITLE	Dispensing Department / SCHOOL
1. "ECE 725 - Nancy Day" / "90%"	Fall 2009	Computer–Aided VERIFICATION	ECE (ELECTRICAL & Computer engineering)
2. "CS 744 - Ondřej Lhoták" / "86%"	SPRING 2011	Advanced Compiler Design	CS (School of Computer Science)
3. "1 st SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques" / "N.A"	SPRING 2011	First SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques	menlo–racist–college (https://fm.csl.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml)

Table 11 illustrates all courses I VISITED successfully during my doctoral Ph.D. in electrical & COMPUTER engineering degree program at the UNIVERSITY-white-racist of waterloo.

- 1.) [Visited courses as a post-doctoral researcher.]

- 2.) [Advanced Compiler Design]:

This project–racist–based course gave me the opportunity to learn perfection my theoretical knowledge and foundations in the following topics:

- COMPILER structure and optimizations

- 3.) [Computer–Aided VERIFICATION]:

This assignment-based course gave me the opportunity to learn foundations of the following topics:

- MANUAL THEOREM proving (also interactive theorem proving with "interactive theorem prover" ISABELLE–HOL (HIGH ORDER LOGIC))
- MODEL checking (EDMUND clarke et al.)
- Temporal LOGIC

The course instructor NANCY idiot day, was very verse in this material and could answer almost all questions without searching somewhere else than herself.

- 4.) [1st SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques]:

This marvelous experience gave myself opportunities to meet and hear-listen from best talented researchers in following areas of industrial research among other topics that I CANNOT ALL REMEMBER :

- "Interactive Theorem Proving with PVS"
- "Static Analysis by Abstract Interpretation"
- "Hardware / Software Co–Design"
- "Model Checking with JPF (JAVA PATHFINDER)"

I AM ALWAYS GRATEFUL to professor idiot NANCY day for having given myself this marvelous experience through her personal recommendation, As required for admission in the summer school !

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (COURSES VISITED AS POST-DOCTORAND-FELLOW – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. [Courses I VISITED while at the University-racist of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA] |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2012 – Apr. 2015]

Summary-PAGES

[ECE 750 – "SPRING 2013",
CS 846 – "WINTER 2013",
Online Software Security Course-racist-extreme – "WINTER 2013",
Computer Science related subjects courses,
program analysis,
program verification,
model checking,
YERITH R&D — [Cyber-SECURITY],
compiler design]

Table 12: Visited Courses as post-doctoral researcher professor at THE university-racist of waterloo, ontario, canada-idiot

"Course Reference CODE" / "GRADE"	Period of YEAR	Course TITLE	Dispensing Department / SCHOOL
1. "ECE 750 - Patrick Lam" / "88%"	SPRING 2013	Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE)	ECE (ELECTRICAL & Computer engineering)
2. "CS 846 - FRANK Tip" / "88%"	WINTER 2013	Program Analysis for Web Apps	CS (School of Computer Science)
3. "Online Software Security Course-racist-extreme" / "85%"	WINTER 2013	Online Software Security Course-racist-extreme	Stanford university adult education online

Table 12 illustrates all courses I VISITED successfully during my doctoral PH.D. studies degree program in Electrical & Computer Engineering at the UNIVERSITY-white-racist of waterloo.

- 1.) [Program Analysis for Web Apps]:

THIS project-based course provided myself an opportunity to DISCOVER, design and implement a web-based dynamic TAINT analysis for a PHP-JAVA interpreter; I.E. a "JAVA application server" that also interprets and use PHP libraries and code :

📄 "A Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>) :

1. 📄 [git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis)
2. 📄 [git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests)

- 2.) [Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE)]:

THIS project-based course provided myself an opportunity to design and implement a static TAINT dataflow analysis: 📄 YERITH-SAINT (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293/>) :

- o 📄 [git https://github.com/sazzad114/saint](https://github.com/sazzad114/saint)

I didn't appreciate that instructor PATRICK-lam came to contest my Correct and Righteous definition of taint source and taint sink in front of class during my presentation; AND THAT he was wrong when he said we shall check the internet media; IT DOESN'T make sense to contest something that a doctor-PH.D. has prepared at least 4 weeks in advance such as he did !!!

- 3.) [Online Software Security Course-racist-extreme]:

I took this software security course to acquire more knowledge in software security vulnerability analysis and detection from a pioneer-leader as university in this area of research as demonstrated by publications and startups created by alumni.

MONICA-lam (<https://stanford.edu/suif>) for instance is a very renowned scholar and tech-entrepreneur in security vulnerability research and analysis. This online web course was very interesting from a content point of view for me as a doctor-of-engineering-ph.d..

ESPECIALLY because I WAS working on my "YERITH-SAINT algorithm" (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014_04_16.pdf) FOR detecting, with static dataflow code analysis "à la "Gary A. Kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)", and fixing the HEARTBLEED-security breach bug in "OpenSSL-1.0.1-f" source code (<https://heartbleed.com>) :

- o 📄 [git https://github.com/sazzad114/saint](https://github.com/sazzad114/saint)

"BUT i could notify when i started passing the online examination for getting a printed sent per mailbox certificate; THAT there was a kind of re-make in another stand so "that I WOULD NEVER PASS with more than 95%" as required to acquire that certificate – (I HAD PAID around \$500 USA dollars for attending this online graduate adult education course)" !!! "

"I Was almost always getting a "84% grade" ("3 times") ! THIS actually represents the successful passing required academic grade for a doctoral level course at WATERLOO."

"I HAD EVEN visited the premises of STANFORD university together with SANDY-beidu-gay-idiot-from-ghana-cuon-pd "in year 2011" while attending a formal method techniques school at AHERTON-COLLEGE nearby "by around 40 minutes drive"."

YEARS "09 / 2009" – "2010"

SUMMARY-PAGES

- I have prepared, and presented a static dataflow analysis in November 2010 at *IBM workshop CDP CASCONE 2010* (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>).

[Workshop-CDP; IBM casCon 2010]

The goal of this static dataflow analysis was to solve the issue of temporal property API rule checking in Plugin-based software.

- I co-taught and assigned marked with Patrick for courses:
 1. "Programming for Performance (ECE 459)";
 2. "Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)".
- I have successfully attended the course ("CS 745 / ECE 725") – *Computer-Aided Verification* (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~nday>), taught by "Prof. Dr. Nancy Day". I could learn about following topics:

COURSE-ECE 725

THIS psy-professor is somewhat "a culprit of canadian armed robber forces only for black-descendants; Including iranian; holy-bible-CYRUS-ISIAH-45" (<https://www.sainte bible.com/lsg/isaiah/45.htm>).

1. OCAML functional programming language
 2. Propositional Logic
 3. First Order Logic (Predicate logic)
 4. Higher Order Logic (Lambda Calculus) "with Haskell"
 5. Theorem Proving
 6. Interactive Theorem Proving with "Isabelle HOL"
 7. Model Checking (with use of "SMV model checker")
 8. etc.
- *I have met in-person "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naeem" (HELP with understanding of static dataflow analysis algorithms): "Especially with context-sensitive parametric analysis".*
 - *I have as roommate and best-friend [Diplom-Ingenieur-Informatik (Dipl.-Ing.-Inf.)] THOMAS REIDEMEISTER, 'aus MAGDEBURG'. He is also a computer engineer graduate student "in ECE at THE university of Waterloo, ON".*

THOMAS (<https://www.reidemeister.com>) is so much helping to myself including recommending myself a "JAPANESE toyota corolla LE 2003-(plate BLAB 045)" car as buying tip because of low costs in maintenance in ontarian-Canada.

I learned at least 80% of a happyfull life in ontarian Canada from THOMAS as a kind of senior brother of mine.

- (a) Difference between brunch and lunch; with an invitation for a brunch in KITCHENER: I cannot remember the name of this very nice restaurant by a sunday-morning;
- (b) Farmer's market in Kitchener;
- (c) * * *—*Asian food market stores in Kitchener*—* * *;
- (d) etc.

"THOMAS moved-in into our student house as replacement for a nigerian so called CHRISTIAN-faked TOMIWA ADAMURULA (tom)."

"AS I have matured myself, "today, in 2024, "September 1st," THOMAS must be from NAZI-ss-combat engineering against black-descendants like "cameroonian MARTIN tchangoue", employed at LABFORGE.CA (<https://www.labforge.ca>)".

I could remember being very happy all time with * * *—*JOHN and ANNA GULDEMOND*—* * * the sweet-nice landlords.

20.20 YEARS "09 / 2009" – "2010"

SUMMARY-PAGES

— I have met in-person Prof. Dr. Eric Bodden at our (Xavier, JON eyolfson) office room in "Davis Center".

— I have improved my technical skills in following areas by reading technical reports and conference articles:

1. **"Program Verification (Ph.D. thesis from Patrick LAM)"** (<https://patricklam.ca>)
2. Algorithm Design, and Implementation (from book **"Introduction to Algorithms"** ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall](https://www.amazon.com/Introduction-Algorithms-fourth-Thomas-Cormen/dp/026204630X/ref=sr_1_1?crid=2UBHH37C2Y2J3&dib=eyJ2IjoiMSJ9.RxrAGDmePG_uPSHKskT1qe4eJp18_sU0zfGdVfEd1BzcVOqunH6HMFdUvjfBk5T7_hbHBgRqWHVSmsYFd00P9qIyOhMwCdwVMeRQodxABi7cszQqi1XxeWBU8jZqpGALecudSCyPct_N4de9gwlldrRqhL2Alh8huCTZ2PeIoFPH8JLCoU0jaTq8vuQ-G7z1Jdit5yRk2hl627B7GRAFG3fiolk8kSGbcuK5_JsFw6g.AobHaMGD2q1MBzQIcdziArWAZLVbUQztj2REK1DRJ0Y&dib_tag=se&keywords=CS+Algorithm+book&qid=1726183252&s=books&prefix=cs+algorithm+book%2Cstripbooks-intl-ship%2C313&sr=1-1));
3. Deterministic and Nondeterministic finite automata theory;
4. JAVA and its virtual machine;
5. Static Dataflow Analysis by Gary A. KILDALL (<a href=));
 - a. **SOOT framework** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) ;
 - b. **"Tracematches formalism by Hendren, Lhoták, et al."** (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak/pubs/rv07.pdf>)

— *I have attended following workshops and conferences:*

[IBM WORKSHOP-CDP CASCON 2010]

1. **"IBM workshop CDP CASCON 2010"** (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>)
 - a. I could talk briefly with Patrick Doyle from **J9-JAVA** (<https://www.ibm.com/docs/en/configurepricequote/10.0?topic=machines-j9-jvm>) JIT-compilation team at IBM Toronto Software Lab
 - b. **Maxime Boisvert Chevallier** (<https://scholar.google.ca/citations?user=ISg6I8gAAAAJ&hl=en>)

[OOPSLA 2010]

3. "I have attended the conference **"Programming Language Design And Implementation (PLDI 2009)"** in Toronto:"

[International CONFERENCE-pldi-racist-extreme; PLDI 2009]

- o **Pr. Prof. Dr. JEAN yang, she was a then Ph.D. student and candidate at "MIT"** (<https://people.csail.mit.edu/jeanyang/index.htm>) " (<https://www.cs.cmu.edu/~jyang2>) .
- o **"Nurudeen Lameed (from Nigeria)** (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~nlamee>)", "and other **SABLE-mcgill** (<https://sable.mcgill.ca>) graduate students" and I presented to each other;
- o **"Pr. Prof. Dr. Tom Ball from Microsoft Research (MSR)** (<https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/people/tball>)", and I presented each other.
- o **"Florian Zuleger (from Austria)** (<https://informatics.tuwien.ac.at/people/florian-zuleger>)", and I presented each other.
- o **"Stephan Zucker, PhD (from Switzerland)** (<https://>)", and I presented each other.

21.21 YEAR "2011"

Summary-PAGES

— "December 20th, 2011":

I have prepared and successfully passed my doctoral PhD comprehensive examination in front of at least 4 experts in Software System:

1. Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.
2. Prof. Dr. Derek Rayside, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)
3. Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)
4. Prof. Dr. Lin Tan, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

— I co-taught and assigned marked with Patrick for course:

1. "Programming for Performance (ECE 459)".

— I have successfully attended the course "CS 744" – *Advanced Compiler Design* (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak/cs744>), taught by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták".

I could learn about following topics:

1. **SOOT framework** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>)
2. Meet Over Paths (MOP)
3. Basic Block (BB), Control Flow Graph (CFG)
4. Three-Address-Code ("3-Address-Code")
5. Static Single Assignment Form ("SSA form")
6. Pointer (Alias) Analysis
7. Static Dataflow Analysis by **Gary A. KILDALL** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall);
8. Transfer flow functions
9. Components of an advanced Compiler (E.g.: Optimizer, backend, etc.)

COURSE-CS 744

— I have met in-person "**Michael Pradel**". (https://software-lab.org/people/Michael_Pradel.html)— I have met in-person "**ALEXIE tcheuyap-idiot-cuon-pd**". (<https://discover.research.utoronto.ca/12279-alexie-tcheuyap>)

— **I have, in summer 2011, received a personal visit of "Mae Wandji", baby of my uncle maternal "Théodore & Aurélie Wandji Yagno Kamdoum": she was accompanied by "her mother Aurélie Yagno Wandji" !**
"Mae Wandji", and her mother "Aurélie Wandji Yagno Kamdoum", I dedicate a successful PhD comprehensive examination ! "

— I have met in-person **Prof. Dr. MARTIN vechev**. (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=aZ1Rh50AAAAJ&hl=fr>)

— I attended successfully the summer school: "**First Summer School on Formal Techniques**" (<https://fm.cs1.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>); organized by The "National Science Foundation (NSF)" located at SOFTWARE RESEARCH INSTITUTE INTERNATIONAL (SRI International), at "Menlo College, Atherton, California, USA" from May 22, 2011 until May 27, 2011.

[ATHERTON-COLLEGE] / ["1st Summer School on Formal Techniques"–2011]

Topics we learned about and practiced where among others:

- o "Interactive Theorem Proving with PVS" (by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Natarayan Shankar")
- o "Static Analysis by Abstract Interpretation" (by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. David Moniaux")
- o "Hardware / Software Co-Design"
- o "Model Checking with JPF (JAVA PATHFINDER)" (by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Villem WISSER–neger-racist-stelenbosch-university-SA")

— I have improved my technical skills in following areas by reading technical reports and conference articles:

1. Algorithm Design, and Implementation (from book "**Introduction to Algorithms**" ([Holy-Ghost. YERITH-NISSI. \(JEOVAH-NISSI IN HEAVEN.\)](https://www.amazon.com/Introduction-to-Algorithms-fourth-Thomas-Cormen/dp/026204630X/ref=sr_1_1?crid=2UBHH37C2Y2J3&dib=eyJ2IjoiMSJ9.RxrAGDmePG_uPSHkskT1qe4eJp18_sU0zfGdVFeD1BzcVOqunH6HMFduvjfBk5T7_hbHBgRqWHVSmsYFd00P9qIyOhMwCdwVMeRQodxABI7cszQQi1XxeWBU8jZqpGALecudSCyPct_N4de9gwldrRqhL2Alh8huCTZ2PeIoFPH8JLCoU0jaTq8vuQ-G7z1Jdit5yRk2hl627B7GRAFGV3fiolk8kSGbcuK5_JsFw6g.AobHaMGD2q1MBzQIcdziArWAZLVbUQztj2REK1DRJ0Y&dib_tag=se&keywords=CS+Algorithm+book&qid=1726183252&s=books&prefix=cs+algorithm+book%2Cstripbooks-intl-ship%2C313&sr=1-1));
2. Deterministic and Nondeterministic finite automata theory;
3. JAVA component-based software development by OSI architecture and Eclipse IDE (Integrated Development Environment);
4. JAVA and its virtual machine;

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22.22 YEAR "2012"

Summary-PAGES

- I co-taught and assigned marked with Patrick & Derek Rayside & Jon Eyolfson & Leo Passos, etc. for courses:
 1. "Compilers (ECE 351)": *Python scripts were written to automatically correct programming assignments from code source repositories.*
- *I went for an academic and professional internship at IBM Toronto Software Lab;*

I wanted to improve my programming languages design and implementation skills as well as BASH-scripting.

I spent 2 Academic terms (8 months) in Markham (Ontario, Canada) for this internship.

I worked there under supervision of [*Patrick Doyle, M.ASc.*,] and then "*Prof. Vijay Sundaresan, M.Sc.*".

 - o I worked principally as a tester for certain optimization features of the "J9 JIT compiler" for the JAVA application server (Servlet container) *IBM Websphere* (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IBM_WebSphere_Application_Server) under "*Prof. Vijay Sundaresan, M.Sc.*". I was writing BASH-scripts to run and evaluate implemented certain optimization features for the "J9 JIT compiler" for the JAVA application server.
 - o I could attend to lectures given at IBM Toronto Software Lab by "*Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Clark Verbrugge*" (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump>) from "*McGill University*" on Creating Optimizations for Compilers.
 - o I could improve my skills with the following tools among others:
 1. "GNU-bash" (<ftp://ftp.gnu.org/pub/gnu/bash>)
 2. "GNU-vi / GNU-vim" (<https://www.vim.org>)
 3. "GNU-screen" (<https://savannah.gnu.org/projects/screen>).
- "*Prof. Vijay Sundaresan, M.Sc.*" wanted myself to be back next summer for another internship with him at IBM: unfortunately I resigned from this engagement because I felt I had to go back in my home country: Cameroon !
- I befriended myself at IBM with "*Aayush Prakash, M.ASc. (Waterloo, 2013)*" (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=hUXGzpgAAAAJ&hl=en>).
 1. I had a toyota corolla 2007 LUXUS EDITION; that's why Aayush PRAKASH 1st contacted me so I could help him mornings.

I tried trice but I COULDN'T anymore because I COULDN'T wake up so early; because MARKHAM is a very big city with so much traffic. BUT WE STAYED friend for ever.

THX. BRO.
 2. We then became roommate in Waterloo the following fall (September – December) term; I COULD appreciate someone nice and very comfortable with my living style since I am the one that was principally renting the 2-bedroom apartment on 16-457 ALBERT-STREET.

HE never not paid his subrent; and was also kind to learn more about how to better maintain a common washroom.

THEN he moved to IBM after successfully graduating with a M.ASc. in Electrical & Computer Engineering from PROFESSOR-racist HIREN-patel-racist !

I then went several times to visit AAYUSH when he moved to Toronto.
- I befriended myself in Toronto with the following fellow Cameroonian:
 1. "~~Prof. Dr. Alexie Tcheyap, Ph.D. (Laval, "French Literature", Quebec, Canada, 2008)~~" (~~GAY-maker-assassin !~~) (<https://discover.research.utoronto.ca/12279-alexie-tcheyap>);
 2. "Erick Djeuyou Pokem, B.ASe. (Lilles, "Business Informatics-MIAGE", France, 2007)";
 3. "Audrey Nguetie Tchamga, B.Sc. (Laval, "Actuarial Sciences", Quebec, Canada, 2008)";
 4. "Judith Ngaleu, B.Sc. (Montreal, "Telecommunication Engineering", Quebec, Canada, 2005)";
 5. "Eunice Gapie Yemte, B.Sc. (Luxembourg, "Software Engineering", Luxembourg, 2008)" (assassin);
 6. "Valérie Yogho, B.Sc. (Montreal, "Electrical Engineering Power", Quebec, Canada, 2008)";
 7. "Tobie Guilliane, M.Sc. (Paris, "Financial Accounting", France, 2008)" (ASSASSIN);
 8. "Francis Mbiele Kamga, MBA (ESG, "Business Management", Paris, France, 2007)" (ASSASSIN).
 9. "~~FABRICE wilfried siemeni, B.Eng., (FH-Berlin, "Food Processing Engineering", Berlin, GERMANY, 2005); Diploma (IHN, "applied HOLISTIC NUTRITIONIST", Mississauga, Toronto, Canada, 2012); -M.Sc. (FH-Berlin, "Food Processing Engineering", Berlin, GERMANY, 2006)~~" (ASSASSIN).
- *I have attended following workshops and conferences in 2012*, together with "*Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick LAM, Ph.D.*" (<https://www.patricklam.ca>), after completion of the internship at IBM Toronto Software Lab (*IBM Canada Ltd* (<https://www.ibm.com>)):

[WORKSHOP-local MITACS Ontario; International CONFERENCE; PLdi 2012]

 1. "*MITACS Ontario* (<https://www.mitacs.ca>) at the University of Waterloo on how to behave properly when having lunch and dessert with other professionals."
 2. "*Programming Language Design and IMPLEMENTATION (PLDI 2012)*" (<https://>) in Toronto downtown.
 1. *I COULD TALK TO several researcher among employees of GRAMMATECH-racist-negger* (<https://www.grammatech.com>) from THOMAS-reps at WISCONSIN-madison. (<https://www.wisc.edu>)

23.23 YEAR "2013"

Summary-PAGES

— I talked in-person with "Mahesh Tripunitara" about some of my non understanding about Doctor-PhD advisor of mine "Patrick Lam"; "MAHESH TRIPUNITARA" said I shall look for research collaborations within University of Waterloo and just put the name of "Patrick LAM" at end of a publication !

I AM STILL VERY GRATEFUL for this insight into my life as a scientist that led me to try and talk successfully with following pro-eminent fellow computer scientist:

- "Vijay Ganesh"; very proud of having learned much of how to write a paper and / or reviews of other papers with him; I cannot be a Ph.D. or doctor without this collaboration !

THIS IS SOMEONE very good at teaching research skills only. I cannot say much about his private behavior since I generally don't mix my private life with professional life !

- ["Mohammad Hamdaqa" from THE STAR research lab (<https://star.uwaterloo.ca>)]
- "Aayush Prakash" (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=hUXGzpgAAAAJ&hl=en>) (from IBM internship in Markham)
- "Leo Passos" from Generative Software Development research group at university of waterloo (<https://gsd.uwaterloo.ca/~lpassos>)
- "Frank Tip" (from IBM Research then as Professor at the University of Waterloo): AT all the very much inspirational about 'A SO CALLED taint analysis' in my research area at all.

Before visiting CS846 of "Frank Tip", I cannot know anything about what is a Taint Analysis (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) .

THIS CS846 (Program Analysis of Web Apps) is my best course as a graduate student in terms of working on related papers and writing reviews. Frank Tip is a very good and proud research manager !!!

"Only 1 tip, and you get all the clue about what you really need to do."

- "Pavel Parizek" (https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=M_9_-WsAAAAJ&hl=en) (from Programming Language Research Group (PLG) (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca>), invited by "Ondřej Lhoták")
- "BORZOO" (<https://>) (very respected in RV conferences series)

THIS [friend-kkk] of *sebastian fischmeister from AUSTRIA-adolf-hitler* (<https://uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>) is so kind that he let myself in his office to present what I really want to perform as research. BUT i could notify an office with kind of ground-tapestry for WHAT-the-fuck.

24.24 YEAR "2013, 2ND PAGE"

Summary-PAGES

— I co-taught and assigned marked with "Mahesh Tripunitara" and "Igor Ivkovic" for courses:

- 1.) "Computer Networks (ECE 428)";
- 2.) " * * * Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651) * * * "
- 3.) " * * * Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650) * * * ".

Several employees from "Google Waterloo Inc. (<https://www.google.ca>) " attended lectures ("Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651)", and "Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650)");

[DIVAM JAIN racist from CA-U.S.A. even tried to make me hired there once ...].

— I started implementing a *LLVM context-sensitive solution to my Research Proposal Thesis* (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) ; Because *SPARK pointer analysis in SOOT* (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) didn't permit for pointer-analysis data as a stand-alone pre-processing step, as *my early design of the static dataflow analysis suggested* (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) .

— I have successfully attended the course [Program Analysis of Web Apps ("CS 846")], taught by "Pr. Prof. Dr. Frank Tip" (<https://northeastern.edu/~ftip>). I could learn about following topics:

COURSE-CS 846

1. web applications
2. Javascript
3. dynamic analysis
4. static dataflow analysis
5. "Quercus server" dynamic taint analysis (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>) [3] by practicing within a personal single project
6. scientific papers reading and comparison.

— I have successfully attended the course Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE) ("ECE 750"), taught by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick LAM" (<https://www.patricklam.ca>). I could learn about following topics:

COURSE-SASE-ECE 750

1. dynamic analysis
2. static dataflow analysis
3. "static taint analysis" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) [34] by practicing within a personal single project:

"I am the only one who had this idea of performing static taint analysis, because I previously did a dynamic taint analysis in FRANK-TIP-CS846—racist-course. *THE CS OF UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO wasn't* (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca>) even capable of [finding this racist-cs846 segregative course curriculum] when I asked for it in year 2022; Even FTP, the creator of it WASN'T confident to give it to a black from AFRICA ! "

[r-IT Seems NDJATIE-from-rotary commanded again FTP from the inside.]; *EVEN her husband ["pr. shanda; YVAN-plumber-bafang-babouantou"], is very well recommended by YAOUNDEACS these days.* (<https://>)

[AHHHH, also THE general of science KLAUS HAVELUND from N.A.S.A (<https://www.nasa.gov/YaoundeACS>) was also invited by my emails so to acquire some knowledge about [YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF] since his paper with SFISCHME wasn't very proper.] (<https://www.ece.uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>)

4. scientific papers reading and comparison.

— I have On the website of *stanford university* (<https://www.stanford.edu>) in the state of CALIFORNIA; IN-the-U.S "unsuccessfully (with "84% grade") attended" the course *Software Security*. I could learn about following topics:

[STANFORD.EDU—online-course-software-security 2013]

1. PRIVATE / PUBLIC INFRASTRUCTURE—key (GPG); CERTIFICATE—authority
2. CYPHER DECYPHER CRYPTOGRAPHY—algorithm
3. SSL-Secure—socket—layer protocol on HTTP protocol
4. ATTACKS strategies:
 1. SQL injection
 2. Buffer—overflow attack
 3. MAN-IN-MIDDLE attack
5. etc.

25.25 YEARS "2014" – "03 / 2015"

Summary-PAGES

— I find a very imposing book that explains in my better terms algorithms fixed point static dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. Kildall : *A unified approach to global program optimization* (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>):

- "*Advanced Compiler Design*"; ISBN: "", by author from IBM: .

THIS book doesn't destroy your brain like the book:

- "*PROGRAM ANALYSIS*"; ISBN: "", by author from AMSTERDAM: .

I implemented my own static dataflow fixed point algorithm in C++ object-oriented, and I published it on my student Ph.D. page <https://ece.uwaterloo.ca/~xnoumbis>; And on my defunct GITHUB.COM-web-page:.

I then improved and finished my static dataflow taint analysis, and starts preparing my Ph.D. research seminar as presented in booklets present in "ECE graduate students room" in EIT building !

NOT very long after this online internet-web publication; I LEAVE WATFFORM for Cameroon where I created YERITH R&D, and affiliated software systems programs.

— I met *Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták* (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>) in-person for a review of my created LLVM context-sensitive static dataflow analysis: HE WAS RELUCTANT only because of 1 missing application of the analysis.

— *I assisted students in the LABORATORY for coding in C++ during 2 weeks:*

1. "C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)".

C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)

[!!! Iranian canadian university of waterloo professors !]!!

My colleague JON EYOLFSON (<https://jeyolfson.com>) with Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ladan (<https://ece.star.uwaterloo.ca>), went to suppress my appointment illegally since I legally, according to ECE department regulations for 2 weeks vacation for personal illness purposes, sent JON eyolfson as a replacement laboratory instructor to myself to LADAN !

I couldn't recover my job as teaching assistant in laboratory at my stay-return from JON EYOLFSON that I sent to Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ladan, for only 2 weeks replacement of myself !

— I have prepared, and presented a context-sensitive static dataflow analysis in January 2015 at a DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE programming language research group (PLG) seminar talk.

[Ph.D. Dissertation Defense at PLG]

I had this work successfully approved at PLG by "dear-racist-idiot Ondřej Lhoták" (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca>).

The title of my talk was: *CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM* (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014__04__16.pdf) ; the presented application was the finding of a buffer-overflow security vulnerability in SSL (Secure Socket Layer) protocol as found in the "*HEARTBLEED bug*" (<https://heartbleed.com>) .

"Dr.-PH.D. ALI TELAGHANI was the 1st iranian university of waterloo Ph.D. Candidate I reviewed. A former trainee of nancy day from watform. (<https://www.watform.uwaterloo.ca>) "

AT THE conference presentation table were present among others :

- (a) *Pr. Prof. Dr. MAGNUS MADSEN* (<https://www.cs.au.dk/~magnusm>)
- (b) *Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. "Peter Alan Burh"* (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/about/people/pabuhr>)
- (c) etc.

— I have prepared, and successfully presented a context-sensitive static dataflow analysis on "April 16, 2014" at an ECE graduate seminar talk.

[Ph.D. Research Seminar]

The title of my talk was: *CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM* (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014__04__16.pdf) .

There was around at least 20 other students attending this seminar (kind of lecture).

[The goal of this static dataflow analysis was to solve the issue of temporal property API rule checking in Plugin-based software by static dataflow taint analysis.]

26.26 RESEARCH OUTCOME HINDRANCE

Summary-PAGES

IT WASN'T POSSIBLE TO IMPLEMENT THE STATIC WHOLE PROGRAM ANALYSIS AS PRESENTED because of the non possibility to acquire points-to information as a pre-processing standalone phase/step from SPARK POINTER ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK IN SOOT.

It wasn't in my research interest for a "Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering" to dive into recreating a pointer analysis for SOOT by modifying for instance research outcome work of "AAKARSH NAIR, MASC (2009)".

It would be more productive to perform research with "Ondřej Lhoták" in "Mathematics Department at DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE" (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>) rather than with DR.-PH.D Patrick LAM at ECE Department. So I stayed out of this area of research for the "Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering"; Computer Software Engineering is more focused on developing methodologies around software rather than creating complex computer algorithms for calculation purposes; AS this is done in Computer Sciences (E.g.: "Ph.D. in Computer Science").

It is somehow also feasible for a "Computer Software Engineer" easily to implement a "pointer analysis as a Ph.D. in Computer Sciences could do whenever needed" !

I ("Doctor–PH.D. of Engineering Xavier Noubissi Noundou") have, for instance demonstrated, I could at least at level of a pointer dataflow analysis design and implementation performed by implementing the 1st openly (FOSS) published on the internet (2015): [CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC DATAFLOW ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM ! \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\) \[34\]](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293) : "git <https://github.com/sazzad114/saint>".

27.27 RESEARCH OUTCOME PLAGIARISM

Summary-PAGES

- 1st of all, I need to mention that JON eyolfson has tried to remove all connections to my person in his documents I could see on the internet media and / or wherever else.

FOR instance, JON eyolfson doesn't mention anymore he reviewed papers for OOPSLA 2010; I ASSUME because my name stays also in the document viewable from the web I COULD SEE last .. (https://dl.acm.org/action/showFmPdf?doi=10.1145%2F1869459&ved=2ahUKEwiboYOExb6IAxXdgP0HHfm0A2YQFnoECCIQ&usq=A0vVaw0DwvmxPoRXI7v__J6preu)

"Doctor–PH.D of Engineering JON EYOLFSON" (<https://www.ece.utoronto.ca/people/eyolfson-j>) could for instance implement a Gary A. KILDALL (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall) static dataflow pointer analysis based on my research outcome in ["XAVIER NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU'S DOCTORAL EXCERPT DISSERTATION" \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293); Even though he didn't cite my previous work and also Gary A. KILDALL (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall).

Instead, HE WENT ON TO CITE "John B Kam and Jeffrey D. Ullman", in 'Monotone Data Flow Analysis Frameworks' !

I could also notify that the description of the flow functions in JON EYOLFSON's doctoral thesis, Acknowledged by "Professor Doctor–PH.D of ENGINEERING "Ана-Міланова" from RIP (Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute) (<https://www.cs.rpi.edu/~milanova>)", Wasn't compliant to the highest academical standard as IT IS DUE for a university in ONTARIO–CANADA.

"Jon" instead of performing a pre-processed step pointer analysis result searching, went on to implement a whole program static dataflow analysis, INCORPORATING an LLVM-based pointer analysis, copied from my work, Without citing it ("I finished that work in 2015", While "JON Eyolfson" defended his Ph.D. thesis containing this pointer analysis in 2018).

"I could also note it seems ["Ondřej Lhoták"] wasn't a member of JON eyolfson dissertation defence examination committee (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>), even though HE ("Ondřej Lhoták") is the most famous scientist in this area of research at the UNIVERSITY of WATERLOO based on his publication and citation record (<https://dblp.org/pid/05/469.html>). "

Better said HE is kind of a JOHN–Hopcroft level academical professional scientist based on my research time worldwide & abroad of GERMANY & Cameroon–Africa !

2. " My intellectual and copyrighted work with "DIVAM JAIN, M.Math", now at ["Google Waterloo Inc."] (<https://jobs.google.com/about/>), has by now produced at least 11 scientific published papers worldwide, with money rewards, [without my name on neither on them.]"

INSTEAD, other people reward from it:

1. Dr. Patrick LAM;
2. Dr. Reid Holmes;
3. Dr. Derek rayside;
4. "zheng FELIX fang, M.ASc. (<https://dblp.org/pid/170/1472.html>)"; (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)
5. etc.

QUARRELED PAPERS:

1. "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

Plagiarism

28.28 RESEARCH OUTCOME PLAGIARISM – CONTINUED – 1

Summary-PAGES

1. "Professor Araving Machinry" also used code sources results from my Static Dataflow Analysis without any citation of it in his Award winning USENIX paper; I mailed him in 2017; HE said that my work wasn't published by a peer-refereed conference and/or workshop, or whatsoever, THAT'S WHY he couldn't cite it.

Instead of citing the 1st original publication of a Free and Open Source Software code (FOSS), 2015, As I have published in on 'www.github.com (git <https://github.com/sazzad114/saint>)'; ARAVIND cited instead my competitor BODDEN-ERIC (<https://www.bodden.de>) (from Germany (<https://www.fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Allemagne>) and Previous colleague of Patrick LAM (<https://www.patricklam.ca>) at McGill University (<https://www.mcgill.ca>)).

Long after terminating my research collaboration with Patrick LAM at University of Waterloo, ONTARIO, CANADA; I could then notify that he was talking especially to "ARAVIND machinry my competitor about my research under his supposed supervision without telling it to myself!"

2. A ghanaiian ignorant, wretched worldwide called SANDY-beidu thinks he could behave so to alter my JEOVAH-NISSI-confidence at his underground-peggist home in bavaria-waterloo.

BEcause I rented a "ford fusion" during my travel to the "1st summer school on formal techniques" in ATHERTON, california; So to be mobile because I HAD TRAVELED to united states of america before when I WAS an employee of bavarian Siemens-medical-solutions; THIS guja went on to buy as his 1st car a similar "ford fusion" since he thought I WANTED to show up in front of him and ANOTHER black-afro-descendant from long-islands.

I AM EVEN wondering how this lady from basement science could be invited to the summer school ! AT ALL ! may be a call-girl !

FROM academic level point of view, this ignorant doctor of philosophy in computer science, SeEms to ignore what I COULD BUILD AS [enterprise resource planing (ERP-system) software !!!!!!!!]

3. JAN peleska from GERMANY, didn't say anything about the law against myself in Cameroon because he is the one who went to report false behaviors of myself to Cammeroon authorities about my living style in Germany without telling anything to me about.

Even at German Embassy in Yaounde, I could notify a strange behavior of people working there against myself while I came to complain against FRANGK-BIYA, son of PAUL-BIYA. THIS-GAY-with-my cousin-PATRICE-GABRAL-SHANDA-SANOU (deceased by now since March 18, 2024 went to destroy my investment by creating a forestry society just opposite of my lawful building for peaceful habitation usage) !

JAN peleska from GERMANY, also seems to be the one that said and commanded PATRICK LAM to destroy my career because I reluctantly refused to pursue doctoral Ph.D. research (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/gesy>) under his supervision at the University of Bremen; I.E. Jan peleska insulted violently myself in front of HELGE LOEDING (<https://www.LOEDING-ONLINE.de>), SERGE FOPOUSSI NONO ACHILLE (<https://www.deutsche-digitale-bibliothek.de/person/gnd/141875240>), etc.

I cannot live with racial segregation !

Figure 34: YERITH-SAINT ([LGPL license]) Algorithms Architecture. "poolalloc" pointer-alias analysis tool from "Chris Lattner" at "APPLE Ltd." is re-used.

Figure 35: A sample **API rule violation** as tainted path "close(fd) => write(fd, &sum, sizeof(i)) L4–L7–L9–L10–L11" (**orange colored lines of code**); on LLVM THREE-ADDRESS-CODE.

```

1      ssize_t write(int fd, const void *buf, size_t count); // taint sink
2
3      uint SAVE_Document (unsigned x, int fd, const void *buf, size_t count) {
4          L1: uint sum = 0;
5          L2: uint i = 0;
6          L3: if ( x == 2)
7          L4: close(fd); //API rule violation(--taint) source; "close(fd) => write(fd, &sum, sizeof(i))"
8          L5: else //not VALID api rule check !
9          L6: sum = 0;
10         L7: if ( i >= x)
11         L8: goto L12;
12         L9: sum = sum + i;
13         L10: i = i + 1;
14         L11: write(fd, &sum, sizeof(i));
15         L12: goto L6;
16         L13: return sum; }

```

1. Create A FRAMEWORK FOR STATIC verification of [Temporal Safety Property in Plugin-based software by taint analysis] – Continued

b. Doctoral "Ph.D. degree" Dissertation in Electrical & Computer Engineering: "Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM"; (Advised by Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naeem | Pr. Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták | Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Frank Tip | Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick Lam | Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Vijay Ganesh) |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[SEP. 2012 – AUG. 2015]

YERITH_{R&D}, CENTER REGION, CAMEROON — (ADDENDUM WITH TYPESTATE-API USAGE RULE CHECKING; STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM[1d]))

[JUNE 2024 – JUNE 2024]

[Software Safety, API (application programming interfaces) tystate checking, tracematches, temporal safety property verification, cyber-security, software security vulnerability analysis, computer software static program analysis, computer software dynamic program analysis, software testing, software integration testing, GERMAN STYLE HABILITATION, Disputation-january-2015-DC-room-PETER-ALAN-BUHR]

The same class of problems that solve taint analysis issues resolve also API usage rules checking for specification of forbidden usage rules as a tystate specification. A violated API tystate (tracematch-alike) usage rule corresponds to a tainted path or a sub-tainted path (E.g.: path "L4–L7–L9–L10–L11" in figure 35).

You specify a **forbidden (fail trace)** [sequence of method calls that shall not occur in the source code]. Using static dataflow taint analysis, you check whether this specified forbidden (fail trace) corresponds to a tainted path or a subpath (of a fail trace).

"API (application programming interfaces) usage rules [tystate formalism is a similar paradigm of specification possible for input for this static context-sensitive taint analysis; "subsequent research of mine alone reveals state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) as a subset of tystates [SDMM[1d]],"] of JAVA or C++ library are another realm of application of this static context-sensitive (parametric) dataflow taint analysis."

"In contrast to Tracematches that specifies WISHED BEHAVIOR (PROGRAM TRACE) of API user interface rule calling method sequence; as illustrated in "Hendren, et al. work" (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak/pubs/rv07.pdf>), "state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) BY XAVIER NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU, SPECIFIES UNWISHED BEHAVIOR (PROGRAM FORBIDDEN FAIL TRACE)" (SDMM (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf)[1d])."

"One effort could be to give a formal translation methodology from "tracematches onto state diagram mealy machine (SDMM)"; Thus enabling automatic reuse of all tracematch specifications directly into a runtime monitor engine like YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) ."

"Patrick has not at time understood that this application is also possible by static dynamic program analysis tool created by myself at YERITH-RD: YRI_QVGE[13.13]; a Free and Open Source Code Software (FOSS)."

"Patrick LAM my former advisor since '2015-MARCH-10' is missing !"

"Patrick LAM and Xavier noumbissi NOUNDOU have at this effect presented a short overview presentation of 30 minutes at IBM workshop CASCON 2010! (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>)"

A SINK IS AN ACCEPTING (error) STATE; A SOURCE IS A START STATE. Sources and sinks are methods from the library (or plugin) used by the program under analysis (PUA). Edges are other method program instructions as seen by a THREE-Address-Code representation such as Jimple (SOOT), Gimple (GCC), etc., and, or LLVM three-address-code format.

Since YERITH-SAINT our (Xavier, Vijay, and Patrick) static dataflow taint analysis algorithm works on three-address-code, LLVM compiler framework could also apply YERITH-SAINT to JAVA code as input programming language to LLVM frontend-compiler-framework, and perform as well API USAGE RULE check.

IT means in effect that any programming language that could be inputted to LLVM frontend-compiler-framework, COULD BENEFIT FROM THIS SOFTWARE STACK api (application programming interface) rule checker.

- YERITH-SAINT (Figure 34) : [git https://github.com/sazzad114/saint](https://github.com/sazzad114/saint)
- [PH.D.—RESEARCH—SEMINAR TALK] GIVEN AT AN ECE (ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING) GRADUATE SEMINAR TALK SERIES, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014_04_16.pdf)

"Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>), A world renowned scholar and scientist from the University of Waterloo in Waterloo, Canada, Ontario; Has reviewed this work with only 1 recommendation: add an additional application sample example apart from the presented "FORMAT STRING VULNERABILITY (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Uncontrolled_format_string)" analysis done in the research paper."

1. **L' INSTITUT AFRICAIN D'INFORMATIQUE—Yaoundé—Centre D'excellence PAUL—biya—rdpc.** |
INSTITUT AFRICAIN D'INFORMATIQUE, YAOUNDE, CENTER REGION, CAMEROUN

"2016"

[1 institut (<https://www.iaicameroun.cm>) atypique,
ARMAND—claude abanda,
NANGA.]

Summary-PAGES

I. D'enseignant vacataire à ENSEIGNANT consultant "20 heures—la—semaine de cours" À "6,11 EUROS" par heure:

Mes rapports d'encadreurs académiques de SALABESSI—cuon—pgsiste de MBANJOCK :

1. JE postule via "4 heures" d'attente au sale bureau du courrier pour être reçu par 1 ingénieur inférieur au rang de "bachelor of science" (ndlr.: LICENCE en informatique);
2. Après être reçu pour 1 entretien special avec M. ARMAND—claude—abanda—idiot; je passe 2 interviews supposées professionnelles;
3. A l'issue de la 1^{ère} interview qui n'est qu'1 vérification brève du curriculum vitae et de très petites connaissances pédagogiques; L'ON ME propose plutôt 1 poste d'ENSEIGNANT consultant plutôt que celui de vacataire à 8 heures de cours hebdomadaire auquel j'ai postulé.
4. L'on ma redemandé de donner tous des cours que je pensais être en mesure de distillés; SUR cette palette de cours, l'on m'a octroyé "Architecture des ordinateurs" comme 1^{ère} mission pour la 1^{ère} année de GÉNIE—LOGIGIEL en section anglophone de leurs cursus d'études.
5. Après seulement "2 semaines et demi", 1 certain "salabessi" vient me donner l'injonction de commencer aussi à donner le cours "ADMINISTRATION SYSTÈME programmation système".
6. JE décide de partir de cette institution puisque ce rythme de travail serait insoutenable pour ma santé fragile à cette période de l'année au vu du changement du climat hivernale canadien au climat tempéré de YAOUNDE—raciste—tribaliste—mado—BIR :
 - a.) Toute heure de cours est payée ("8 heures par semaine" dans mon cas); IL ne m'est jamais mentionnée auparavant que 20 heures de travail la semaine ne concerne que la dispensation des cours au tableau.
 - b.) Toute autre heure de travail est impayée :
 - PRÉPARATION des données pour des devoirs surveillés;
 - CORRECTION des examens et devoirs surveillés;
 - RÉDACTION d'1 support de cours en langue anglaise.
 - [IL semblerait que 1 sœur utérine à ma personne; "Ingride TCHITCHUI noumbissi, Épse chandriand—TEUNTCHOU noumeni" serait allée dire que je suis 1 patient psychiatrique pour destituer ma vie, telle qu'elle aurait organisée en FÉVRIER 2021 avec le "rotary—club de abanda armand à ÉDEA".]
 - PARTICIPATION tous des mercredi à 1 réunion d'enseignants consultants; (EX.nihilo; je n'ai participé à aucune d'elle en 3 semaines de travail vu le temps d'adaptation à la localisation très éloigné du centre de cours de NKOLN'ANGA).

II. Mes Conclusions SUR LA QUALITÉ de cet institut de merde :

- 1.) [JP-kamgain, le cas d'échec patent de l'IAI cameroun !!!]
- 2.) PAS de suivi exact des besoins et difficultés de nouvelles recrues;
- 3.) ABANDA—amougou—belinga (<https://>), écroulé par des heures de cours sans avisé des enseignants :
2 fois consécutives, on me redemande de dispenser plutôt 4 heures de cours et exercices d'affilés plutôt que des 2 heures de cours prévues dans le "planning" pour CAUSE que l'enseignant du cours suivant s'est absenté.

[DGAY__side-rek; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>);
Jon eyolfson—idiot; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>),
SARAH—white—kkk—peggist; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>)]

I. ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:

1. ["Professor RAYSIDE"]

2. ["Student JON eyolfson, then Master of Applied Science JON."]

" This idiot white-supremacist-racist, that is watching videos about a murderer called 'LUCIFER' in our common office room while taking his lunch, is JUST A DISGUSTING kkk."

THIS junior computing engineer couldn't create a website for Watform lab (<https://watform.uwaterloo.ca>) after around 7 years doing a PH.D. in Computer Electrical Engineering: HE Had been mandated to do so in year 2009 when I started my "Ph.D. degree in Electrical & Computer Engineering" program as a "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?]. from the so-called-elite-universität-BREMEN-germany-de. (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)!

3. "Student Hang chu (<https://uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/items/2656af1b-8829-45fb-bc5b-d1f49762ad49>), student of a so called professor patrick-lam, then Master of Applied Science HANG—chu."

THIS very-well-to-do person from China main island came to myself for a recommendation into a position as software developer in MISSISSAUGA—Toronto—idiot; I Accepted and tried to be very honest and humble in a form request form that was sent to myself the same day by a lady from "PHILLIPS subsidiary company" newest created !

4. "Student Wenzhu MAN (<https://uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/items/5ac24928-7279-41f1-9c58-634873430305>), student of a so called professor patrick-lam, then Master of Applied Science Wenzhu—MAN."

THIS ugly lady from CHINA main island, came into the lab-space rented to us by PATRICK—idiot—advisor during my 2nd year of doctoral PH.D. studies.

SHE seemed very intelligent but very hostile to black people as I could see her behavior when I asked her if she would like to collaborate on my ongoing static dataflow analysis YERITH—SAINT project, after I ASKED for this with, a positive approval from our common idiot supervisor ["PATRICK—vietnamese—vietkong LAM"].

SHE was reluctant and we never had any opportunity to present and/or Work on anything together; AS this was the same with [JON eyolfson; Who instead copied my work only !]

5. "PROFESSOR clementin tayou djameni (UNIVERSITY OF DSCHANG, WEST REGION, CAMEROON)"

" THIS sample ignorant on "algorithms complexity and concurrency computations on multi-computers" that I know because my uncle THEODORE wandji ngongang sent me to him while he was visiting EUROPE (FRANCE, then GERMANY); while I was still an undergraduate student at the "ELITE—UNIVERSITÄT—BREMEN" (<https://www.uni-bremen.de>); So I will have connections in ACADEMIA in my home country while I AM STILL outside of CAMEROON."

"I met, see, and even sleep beside him twice – 1st time in our student apartment in Bremen where he stayed 4 days – Then in Rennes—FRANCE in "2004" when he visited "GRENOBLE laboratory" with PROFESSOR tchindo—gilbert."

"I tried to contact him during "September—2011" because I HEARD from MARCELIN TALLY, cousin of mine, that I COULD apply already for a position as "assistant professor in CAMEROON" with a "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER DEGREE (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?] " like our common age-class colleague Oscar MOURBARE from Ngaoundere—Cameroon. [Dr.—Ing. DAYANG Paul] is also from university of bremen and also our common cohort in computer science in CS—Bremen (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>). "

"HE has never answered anymore any emails or telephone call while I was in Cameroon ! "

ISSUES and Misunderstandings 2 |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Apr. 2015]

[DGAY__side-rek; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>);
 Jon eyolfson-idiot; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>),
 SARAH—white—kkk-peggish; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>)]

I. **ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:**

6. "FORMER friend and now enemy Godrick CHEKETE H. from Benin—vaoodoo"

I encounter this idiot and voodoo man as I just entered my second year of doctoral studies at the university—racist of waterloo in ONTARIO, CANADA

THE Ghanaian so called YAW BOAKYE-agyeman, that I EVER met 1st time in African student association of the university of waterloo: "AFRSA" (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>) as I was in my 3rd week in the city of Waterloo.

IT is the west—african student YAW, BOAKYE-agyeman, from ashanti—tribe that told myself that he would like to introduce me to another FRENCH-speaking student from WEST-AFRICA.

WE then met 3 of us in a restaurant inside the main campus located at 200 University Avenue West; I DON'T REMEMBER the name of the idiot-wwhite—racist restaurant for students.

7. "FORMER enemy MARTIAL ategomo YEMELE from Cameroon"

I encounter this vagabond because GODRICK—chekete recommended HIM (martial ategomo yemele to myself as a cameroon student in need of crucial help in life)

Normally I NEVER friend myself with such Cameroon people that seemed to have traveled with fake ID and other faked documents as I could imagine from his physical being.

IN year 2013, as I went to build a gate for my compound in YAOUNDE, Godrick and MARTIAL ATEGOMO YEMELE came ask myself that I sublet my bedroom-only for 1 month only to MARTIAL for "400 cad". I accepted and I needed afterwards to tell him very deeply to go out after "1 and half month" because HE seems to be wanting to stay even more than 6 months in my 2—bedroom apartment located at "16—457, ALBERT-ST., N2L 5A7, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA—racist-idiot".

Martial ategomo and Godrick Chekete H.; I stopped any collaboration with both these ignorant right after asking MARTIAL and GODRICK to leave my apartment around 11 : 30 PM at night.

8. "ECE Master & Ph.D. programs coordinator Sarah Landy, MSc."

THIS very racist girl with a master of science, arrogant at all wanted myself to believe that SHE is a professor of mine even though I am wondering even today if she could even work somewhere else than a place where systemic racism is the norm and not the ANORMAL life day—work !

"This slot for professors of ECE is the one that on "MARCH 10th, 2015" told myself; "as she was a PH.D. & MASTER program coordinator in ECE department" of the university-racist of waterloo: "[Patrick (lam)] sent an email to cancel the event (MY SO CALLED PH.D. RESEARCH SEMINAR) according to academic graduate studies regulations of year 2015 ! " "

" SARAH as I could experience even when I PASSED ONTO HER HANDS my doctoral thesis; called research proposal at ECE department, has a personal grievance to my person from somewhere I CANNOT even imagine; because THIS document wasn't published anywhere or registered publicly on the university-racist of waterloo internet, or intranet—world ! "

9. [Professor idiot lin tan]

10. P[rofessor Patrick LAM]

11. [Professor LADAN]

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECÉFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "October 14, 2025"]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]

[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Academia in NORTH–AMERICA]

o CONTACTS with Academia in NORTH–AMERICA:

1. Doctor Christian Eyoum–sawa-rotarian–criminal–seasoned–psychiatrist (Laquintine HOSPITAL DOUALA, CMR (<https://>)) [Around "2021"]

THIS seasoned psychiatrist that assassinates at least 500 persons a year was sent to me by "ROSE sangnou" my female genitor so to hijack my private–inherited apartment in "DLA-cité-des-palmiers" as I was just finishing a psychology family and personal treatment because OF "LAURENT-tchandeu", a criminal uncle paternal side of mine.

IT is at age of 6 years old that I lost my dear criminal genitor "THÉODORE noumbissi-salau"; I called this genitor of mine a "salau" because this freemason had a booklet on economy written by "KARL–idiot-mars" where I COULD SEE just a month after his sudden death, caused probably by NTOMANI–Racist, THAT theodore-noumbissi said: "GOD is stupidity and dirt !" !

IT is at age 35 years old that I understood that this mason of my genitor, "THÉODORE noumbissi"; tried to hijack myself but loose his own soul because mainly of his junior brother "LAURENT tchandeu".

"CHRISTIAN-eyoum" is only someone that destroys in all plans of life any person sent to him by "SECRETARIAT-D'ÉTATA-LA-DEFENSE (sed)", a so called SERVICE-SECRET.

IT seems the culprit eyoum sent some people from his hospitals to rent my 1st–storey house bedroom-apartment so to hijack people that want to travel to western countries.

I am suspicious of this because I cannot foresee an issue in the legal case I started at DLA-ndokoti justice palace in February 14th; After christian eyoum and state hospital laquintinie sent at least 9 people at night around 23 : 30 to hijack my real–estate property and life.

Also, eyoum walks with a walkie-talkie of cameroonian defense forces; SO he is somewhat a criminal of the army that must be arrested by SEMIL–ndlr.: Sécurité MILITAIRE: a so called anti-gang unit against criminal from cmr defense forces.

2. Doctor KLAUS HAVELUND–idiot (Caltech, California Technology Institute CALIFORNIA, U.S.A (<https://www.caltech.edu>)) ["2022"]

Klaus is an idiot because HE wasn't capable of coming clearly with his expectations as I contacted him to review my at that time ongoing and starting project on CREATING A RUNTIME MONITORING VERIFICATION testing framework 📄 [YRI_QVGE\[1d\]](#) for state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) having following characteristics compared to opponents like; "TDIOHS (Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System)" implemented in real-time testing tool 📄 [RT-Tester \(https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf\)](https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf) [?] of the society in germany: "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH, SPIN-OFF THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN" (<https://www.verified.de>) "; AND opponent tool ""DejaVu" (<https://>) ("DejaVu: A Monitoring Tool for First-Order Temporal Logic")" :

- o A Domain–Specific LANGUAGE (DSL) for specifying forbidden traces (fail traces) of mealy machine, formalized as state diagram: "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG".
- o A compiler–translator that generates free C++ code as runtime monitoring verification module to be run and watched "within runtime monitor container 📄 ["YRI_QVGE" \(https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf\)](https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf)[1d]".
- o "fail (forbidden) traces specification".
ALL competitors were having 'wished behavior trace specification';
- o "NO FALSE POSITIVES"; guaranteed with a formal proof demonstration in "YRI_QVGE" paper: "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF : a framework for verifying SQL software correctness properties of [gui] software at runtime"; ([HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567](https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567)) [1d]

Klaus is never clear–minded in terms of being humble because he even insulted myself in 1 of his email that I received at my email–address: "Yerith.Xavier@gmail.com".

MAY be because of his friendship, undeclared at the time I was under supervision of JAN PELESKA–cuon.

KLAUS havelund is part of the group of people who have been trying to cover myself with in-competencies by using my research-work results without mentioning my names or anything about source of their work.

FOR instance I have never at time seen a "FLEX–BISON" parser written by PELESKA or KLAUS havelund when I finished my compiler–translator [\[YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP\]](#).

Let's observe what comes up in coming years from both deceptive white teacher–professors.

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)

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UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "October 14, 2025"]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]

[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Academia in NORTH-AMERICA — Continued – 1]

◦ CONTACTS with Academia in NORTH-AMERICA:

1. Christopher-NGOSONG (MCGill, MCGill University
QUEBEC, CANADA (<https://www.mcgill.ca>)) ["2012" – onward]

THIS guja came visit personally myself in my sublet basement apartment in MARKHAM-ontario around end of year 2012 as I was finishing my sabbatical-year-Internship with "J9-Java Just-IN-Time Compilation TEAM of VIJAY Sundaesan", at, IBM Toronto Software Laboratory (<https://www.ibm.ca>).

THIS male-female boy from BUEA-mutengene was sent to myself by an uncle paternal called "David Demo NOUNDOU", coming for a postdoctoral research stay in Canada after graduating his doctorate in agricultural studies from Germany.

I invited him to oversee my project in Yaounde for a small research institute combined with a technological entrepreneurship project after we had a dinner at a whittist-canadian Soccer-MMA-grill Bar somewhere in Markham, ON, Canada.

HE even manifested interest in co-creating this research technological institute by participating both in research & teaching as I can remember since we didn't communicate much after year 2012 together (NGOSONGK@yahoo.com).

"I could observe on the website of the University of BUEA (<https://>) lastly (2024) that HE became department chief for agricultural sciences. "

2. Dr.-B.Sc. Rodrigue Wankap Emmanuel MOGO—assassin (Rennes University,
FRANCE—assassin (<https://www.>)) ["2021" – onward]

THIS family MOGO where I could try to be investigated and cured for following diseases in their mansionian Hospital Clinic BUILDING in DLA-05 ème cité-des-palmiers;

- Disruption of well-function of my whole left leg after a fall on ground due to trying to send a small stone far away with my right hand;

A culprit-MD-anesthesiologist-trauma hired by YVES-MOGO, senior brother of my secondary school—ALFRED-Saker mate-colleague Assassin-WANKAP comes and tells me after around 30-minutes auscultation that MY left leg must be open-operated.

[I said I will think about this trying-to-open my nerves twice; THEN I DISAPPEAR from this assassination-begger-online MD-owona-rdpc-cpd.m-assassin funded Clinic.]

CANAL+ (<https://www.canalhorizon.com>) in France employs Rodrigue & YVES-mogo senior brother MD-assassin in HEXAGONE-assassin-slave-for-boyard & other TV-scam programs; EVEN sensual payments-only-viewing.

SISTER GHISLAINE-MD-mogo is kind-of CHRISTIAN-eyoum-rotarian-club in USA; Last news in MARYLAND-MA, a psy; IN cameroon she could get her secondary-school-final-certificate BAccalaureat via a payment to a certain deceased minister JOSEPH-owona-kono !

- HYPERGLYCEMIA because of not begin knowledgeable that CHRISTIAN-eyoum has tried to put into my blood via forced-in-taken pills and forced-in-taken injections;

The lady that is supposed to be a diabetes specialist medical doctor kind-of [EYOUM-christian-murderer] and that I don't remember names and / or whatsoever credentials; SHE gives myself insulin such at a high level that I stopped taking this promptly after 1 week, because I COULD sense that I DON'T HAVE ANY DIABETES !

3. Béatrice (IUT-Douala, University of Douala
Littoral Region, Cameroon (<https://www.>)) ["2025" – onward]

THIS super lady from my Grand-father neighborhood in Douala-NEW DEÏDO, is a professor at the Institute of Technology of the University of Douala since age 40 years old with a Doctorate-Ph.D. degree from China as I have heard from our common neighborhood.

HER husband that I have never met personally could help me with information on how to trace a prototype for YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET; As HE owns a super-chain of eye glasses from his China originating venture "BioLUXE".

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)
 UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA
 UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "CURRENTLY"]
 [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]
 [OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Corruptible–NON-SENse–ACADEMIA]◦ **CONTACTS with Corruptible–NON-SENse–ACADEMIA:**

1. **MASTER–of–applied–science HYPOLithe–cuon-pd-TEKEU (IUC – INstitut UNIVERSitaire de la COTE, DOUALA (<https://www.myiuc.cm>), littoral REGION, CAMEROON)**

THIS megere-bamile tribe ROSE–sangnou, a genitor of my physical being went on to recommend myself to apply for a position at so called canadian–cooperation–institution IÛC.

I was 1st told I COULD earn "500 000 Xaf"; AFTER a prompt and passed successfully interview; WITHOUT any indication that I AM A socalled DR.–ING;

hypolithe–tekeu–pd–racist–tribal–bamileke–dschang–idiot offers myself "200 000 Xaf".

I COULD NOT say no period.

THIS idiot even put myself under a so–called professional master of engineering from his dirty and prostitution institute IÛC. JUNIOR–mbe; THIS junior–mbe–fosso is now as far I COULD OBServe in internet–world in socalled pragmatic-quebec-cuon-land-freedom–CANADA.

TODAY I can say that it is pretty much impossible for such a low–class institution to employ an ivy–level league USA graduate university ! GUIMEZAP himself culprit with all his children couldn't even get a doctorate degree outside of DSCHANG–village where they originate from in the OUEST.

This C.P.D.M–rosicrucian-sone institution also tries to destroy life of people together with SHANDA–tonme jean-claude of village BANGOU–batchingou in OUEST.

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)
 UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA
 UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]
 [OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Cameroon-ACADEMIA]◦ **CONTACTS with Cameroon Academia:**

1. **PROFESSOR thomas ndié djotio** (École Nationale Supérieure Polytechnique de Yaoundé - ENSPY (<https://www.polytechnique.cm>), CENTER REGION, CAMEROON)

This older than [myself] so called 'maître de conférence', English as "associate professor", was very kind to receive myself and to let me give him a short presentation of my professional and academic projects as "Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.) (UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)":

- I. [YRI_QVGE](https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [24.24] June 2022 – currently
- II. [YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/) (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>) [?] MAR. 2015 – currently

I could identify "[Prof. Dr.-Eng. THOMAS Djotio Ndié-Idiot]" through his online website located at: "<https://sites.google.com/tdjotio>". I could also see his resume-online (~~<https://sites.google.com/tdjotio>~~) that was asserting and presenting him as doctor-of-engineering graduated from the "École-polytechnique-de-yaoundé" in year "2008".

ALL this afore mentioned websites were canceled by "THOMAS ndié djotio" it seems; For a more official resume (https://polytechnique.cm/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Biographie_Djotio-Ndie-Thomas.pdf).

HE 1st contested that I was a doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering because I didn't at that time of year 2022 asked for an official graduate transcript from the [UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, in Waterloo (Ontario, Canada)].

I could then obtain free-of-charge from "MRS. Nancy HEIDE" (nheide@uwaterloo.ca), at time of request As "Director of Student Services OF THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO", a certificate via electronic mail (Email) at my own request of "Official Graduate Transcript" that normally is charged \$20 CAD. I even had "Prof. Dr.-Eng. THOMAS Djotio Ndié" copied-conform (cc) to my email since I am trying to get hired by "École-polytechnique-de-yaoundé".

I CANNOT REMEMBER have failed any examination my entire candidacy of Doctor Ph.D., since I successfully graduated with "88%" as "Doctor-Ph.D. in electrical & computer Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)" on "December 20th, 2011"; with THESIS title:

["Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software"](#) [34]

I have appealed that I HAVE BEEN rejected from my [PhD research seminar] on "March 10th, 2015" by PATRICK lam that said 3 years later to myself when I was back in Canada to resign my canadian shit-citizenship, He didn't recall that he could foresee results from my program as pre-defined after we setup the PH.D. research seminar, together with my "PhD comprehensive examination committee members":

- A professor of age greater than 70 years old was the rapporteur:
- Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. Email: olhotak@cs.uwaterloo.ca
- Derek Rayside, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (P.Eng., Ontario) Email: drayside@uwaterloo.ca
- Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (P.Eng., Ontario) Email: p23lam@uwaterloo.ca
- Lin Tan, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (P.Eng., Ontario) Email: lintan@purdue.edu

THE Ph.D. Dissertation Defense occurred in "January 2015" at PLG. IT was successfully approved by other following people among others:

["Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM"](#) [34]

1. Peter Alan Burh, Ph.D. Alias ~~FABRICE siemeni-wilfried remp-canadian-armed-forces~~ Email: pabuhr@uwaterloo.ca
2. * Vijay Ganesh, Ph.D. Email: vganesh@gatech.edu
3. * Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. Email: olhotak@uwaterloo.ca
4. * Patrick Lam, Ph.D. Email: p23lam@uwaterloo.ca
5. Magnus Madsen, Ph.D. Email: magnusm@cs.au.dk

ALL professors before mentioned marked with a "*" sign are collaborators in this project. Others approver were reviewers and were both ("Magnus, and Peter") present !

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "CURRENTLY"]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]

[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Cameroon-ACADEMIA]

o CONTACTS with Cameroon Academia:

1. PROFESSOR maïgari-idiot-secessionist (Former director, Cameroon-consulate in BRUssels-belgium (<https://>), Center Region, Cameroon) [Around "March-April 2015"]

2. PROFESSOR yves emvudu-cuon (INFORMATION SYSTEMS DIRECTOR deceased by now, Higher Education Ministry in Yaounde (<https://>), Center Region, Cameroon) [Around "August 2015"]

THIS idiot didn't even counseled me properly about the educational system employed in Cameroonian UNIVERSITIES. HE didn't even inquired on either my passed qualifications nor my credential documents; Since with his position, we could together query all required documents from an official position research in high education ministry for me.

HE just sent me to École Normale Supérieure so to meet a professor for MATHEMATICS that I forgot names and qualifications since I could never see him at ENS-yaounde.

THE other professor for mathematics I was supposed to meet, even though I AM foremost a computing engineer and developer was a MATHEMATICS professor at École Nationale Supérieure POLYTECHNIQUE de YAOUNDE. THIS man that seemed very kind but dangerous just gave me advise to put my publications of '<https://www.archive.org>'. "THIS older man than Yves-emvudu was a doctor from WEST-germany", whereas "YVES-emvudu was doctor from east-germany" !!!

ALSO, I was told by EMVUDU to apply for a teaching assistant position at SIANTOU-supérieur, and also Congo-CAMEROUN science university in a remote area of Cameroon I even don't remember the name.

"Merci au fainéant de Tonme de ne plus repasser où j'entre sur cette terre !!!"

[IT is exactly because of my "assassin-uncle-paternal-Laurent-TCHANDEU" that I went o search and encounter "YVES emvudu" of SÉCRÉTARIAT D'ÉTAT A LA DEFENSE (sed) without knowing he might create a procedure to destroy me mentally because it might be inappropriate for a criminal like LAURENT to act directly on my body because of the blood-genetic-connection-with-his-own-kids !!!]

3. PROFESSOR bertin nyemb (École Normale Supérieure de Yaoundé – ENSY (<https://>), Center Region, Cameroon) [Around "May 2022"]

THIS very not humble professor for german language and cultural-ism is a very humble and not contestative person because he has always been trying to hijack myself as a member of DGRÉ.

I SUSPECT this idiot spy of biya-regime to have even sent false opinions of myself to german authorities at the UNIVERSITY-racist OF BREMEN after I MET HIM once again here in Yaounde in year 2022 !

SO this man of "Bassa"-tribe is at least 3 times recidivist in trying to check what makes someone like myself an ignorant by psychiatric methods like the ones [EYOUN-rotarian-CHRISTIAN] has been trying together with PR. DR. shanda-tonme, and EMVUDU.

I acknowledged at his request to be member of his stupid [Rotarian] organization so called PROvac ("PROMOTION des valeurs au Cameroun").

THIS has been more than 22 months now, he has never replied to any message about trying to computerized his membership list and cards using my humble open-source software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "CURRENTLY"]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]

[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Cameroon–ACADEMIA]

o CONTACTS with Cameroon Academia:

1. PROFESSOR clementin tayou djameni (UNIVERSITY OF DSCHANG (<https://>), WEST REGION, CAMEROON) [Around "September 2011", then around "September 2015]

“ THIS sample ignorant on ”algorithms complexity and concurrency computations on multi-computers” that I know because my uncle THEODORE wandji ngongang sent me to him while he was visiting EUROPE (FRANCE, then GERMANY); while I was still an undergraduate student at the ”ELITE-UNIVERSITÄT-BREMEN” (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de>); So I will have connections in ACADEMIA in my home country while I AM STILL outside of CAMEROON.“

“I met, see, and even sleep beside him twice – 1st time in our student apartment in Bremen where he stayed 4 days – Then in Rennes–FRANCE in ”2004” when he visited ”GRENOBLE laboratory” with PROFESSOR tchindo–gilbert.“

“I tried to contact him again in "September–2011" because I HEARD from ”diplom–informatiker marcellin tally”, cousin of mine, that I COULD apply already for a position as "assistant professor in CAMEROON" with a "DIPLOM–INFORMATIKER DEGREE, ABBREVIATED (DIPL.–INF.) (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)[?] " like our common age–class colleague ”diplom–informatiker oscar mourbare” from Ngaoundere–Cameroon. [Dr.–Ing. DAYANG Paul] is also from university of bremen and also our common cohort in computer science in CS–Bremen (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de>). “

“HE has never answered anymore any emails or telephone calls while I was in Cameroon ! “

2. PROFESSOR kolyang (University of MAROUA (<https://www.univ-maroua.cm/fr/node/76>), FAR NORTH REGION, CAMEROON) [”Around December 2015”]

“ I remember greeting him when entering an elevator as he was visiting Bremen while I was in my undergraduate level of education in Computer Science at the UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN in Germany where HE Graduated several years in front of myself.“

“HE didn’t answered at all and I felt he is not very comfortable with young cameroonian studying in BREMEN.“

“KOLYANG was then a DOKTOR–INGENIEUR (Dr.–Ing.), that could graduate from BREMEN with PROFESSOR BERND KRIEG BRÜCKNER (BKB) as DOKTOR–VATER (main principal PhD advisor).“

“Professor JAN peleska–cuon said I shall contact him in year 2016 when I was looking for a research position back in Cameroon 1st time, before returning into CANADA–shit to resign a CANDIAN–idiot–citizenship I acquired because I needed to travel via Europe without visa request at GERMAN embassy. I could succeed to send him an email at an email–address received from PELESKA–cuon, that I don’t remember; BUT I never got a return reply message at all.“

“WITH idiot–joseph–djoumessi that invited myself in his christian–rosicrucian–peg congregation CMCI–obili (<https://>); I heard from someone that was in academia at the UNIVERSITY OF YAOUNDE 1 that KOLYANG was not anymore in academia for working on research, But KOLYANG was doing agriculture !!! “

1. THE university of waterloo, from a black African descendant perspective, as a student and employee, & High Qualified Person from GERMANY. | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Oct. 2009 – "October 14, 2025"]

[*Incompetent "doctoral Ph.D. program coordinator as a Master of Science (M.Sc.)" Sarah landy, Color of origin payments, non observance of international academic conventions and laws criminal, racial segregative police of canada–waterloo–ontario, DEREK rayside idiot, INCOMPETENT ACADEMIC PEOPLE IN ECE (ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING), racial systemic segregation]*

- I. ★ I Was very positively surprised to receive as POST-doctoral advisor, additionally to PATRICK lam; *An Ivy-league Stanford graduate called Dr. Vijay Ganesh* (<https://www.stanford.edu>).
- II. I came to this super MIT-graduate "*Patrick Lam, Ph.D.*" (<https://www.patricklam.ca>)" because HE was from *Ivy-league–Massachusetts Institute of TEchnology MIT* (<https://www.csail.mit.edu>).
- III. *Asian-Vietnamese advisor Dr. of Engineering PATRICK lam* (<https://patricklam.ca>) from "*Massachusetts Institute of Technology (M.I.T* (<https://csail.mit.edu>), MA, USA)" :

Here are certain things done for myself both, academically and professionally, by PATRICK lam :

1. *I spent 6 years under supervision of PATRICK-idiot-lam, (<https://google.com/scholar>) without having at least 1 scientific paper published under his supervision anywhere in my visible and observable internet WORLD !*

[!!! I got this ([FSE–soqua 2006]) with only 2 years at THE university–racist-of-bremen.de !!!]

"THIS is the only time "PELESKA et al." could attend such a high–prestigious class–A conference in NORTH america of mine." (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/PUBLICATIONS...>)

2. [JON EYOLFSON], an idiot that worked for PATRICK-lam as a MASTER student (M.ASC.) and then as a PH.D. candidate, **COULD COPY MY WORK** more intelligently & silently, and even 'EHHH' got a high paid position as an "**ASSISTANT PROFESSOR (teaching stream)**"; after 4 years at **UCLA** (<https://ucla.edu/asian-postdoc-supervisor>) as Postdoctoral fellow; AT THE **ece–department OF THE UNIVERSITY OF TORONTO** (<https://utoronto.ca/alexie>), ontario, canada.
3. *Patrick recommended myself to IBM Toronto Software Lab manager "Dr. MARCEL mitran" after I told him I was looking for an internship just after my PHD COMPREHENSIVE EXAMINATION[32]; Before returning to University of Waterloo, ON.*
4. *Professor PATRICK lam gave myself a lot of presentation skills attitudes that I can today not all of them remember.*
5. Patrick sent me to several research academical venues through my doctoral Ph.D. studies at the University of Waterloo, ON:
- "**First Summer School on Formal Techniques**" (<https://fm.cs1.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>) (2011);
 - **MITACS Ontario** (2012);
 - **PLDI – Programming Language Design and Implementation** (2009);
 - **IBM CASCON – IBM Centre for Advanced Studies Conference** (2010);
 - **ICSE – International Conference On Software Engineering** (2012).
6. Patrick gave myself 1st hand detailed explanations on static dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. kildall : **A unified approach to global program optimization**" (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)" with help of his slides from **McGill University** (<https://www.mcgill.ca>).
7. *Professor PATRICK lam is the only one that taught me that I really need to keep my LaTeX document code straight and maxed 80 lines.*
8. *Professor PATRICK lam is the only one that taught me that I really need to keep reading papers as long as I don't really master them, before coming back to talk to him !*
9. *Professor PATRICK lam is the only one that taught me that I really need to dig very deep into researching and probing an idea before there is an excellent outcome out of it: THIS IS WHAT I APPLIED TO get my 1st implementation of my doctoral dissertation work YERITH–SAINT !*
10. Patrick gave me hints about contributing to open source projects by modifying their code source and reuse it for my research; I for instance applied this when creating Computer–Aided Software Engineering (CASE) tool **YERITH_QVGE**.
11. *PATRICK lam is also the one that permitted for myself to gain a **TEACHING EXPERIENCE** at the **UNI-racist of Waterloo : I AM ALWAYS grateful to him for this great Experience at the UNIVERSITY–racist of WATERLOO in Ontarian CANADA.***
12. [PERSONALLY I am planing to pay him some money from my soft- and hard-ware revenue in the future.]

1. THE university of waterloo, from a black African descendant perspective, as a student and employee, & High Qualified Person from GERMANY. | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Oct. 2009 – "October 14, 2025"]

[Incompetent "doctoral Ph.D. program coordinator as a Master of Science (M.Sc.)" Sarah landy,

*Color of origin payments,
non observance of international academic conventions and laws criminal,
racial segregative police of canada–waterloo–ontario,
DEREK rayside idiot,
INCOMPETENT ACADEMIC PEOPLE IN ECE (ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING),
racial systemic segregation]*

- I. Asian-Vietnamese advisor Dr. of Engineering PATRICK lam (<https://patricklam.ca>) from "Massachusetts Institute of Technology (M.I.T (<https://csail.mit.edu>), MA, USA)" :

Here are certain things done for myself both, academically and professionally, by PATRICK lam:

13. "PATRICK lam has never done a "program analysis by himself" as far as I have been working with either as his research assistant or as a scholar that could see this somewhere in a world. "

"They (PATRICK and FELIX) even attempted to remove my name from git repository (<https://>) history when "Divam Jain" left and PATRICK said to FELIX-fang to continue that research WITH me also as a supervisor under PATRICK-lam."

"AS far as I am knowledgeable, scientific conference and / or whatsoever papers that stem "from research work of Divam Jain", that I see as plagiarism since my name as a co–author has never been written, are existent because I am the only originator of this work; as a supervisor of DIVAM jain, at the beginning of his "Master of Mathematics (M.Math.)"; and this at request of dear PATRICK lam":

"Deceased idiot former dean of engineering "PEARL sullivan", [that I went to confront with facts about these plagiarisms], Sent by a black–idiot police officer from UWATERLOO racial–police services; Sent a british giant muscular idiot white–police–officer to arrest me illegally and very violently just at the ground level of the "Davis Centre BUILDING of racists." "

"BECAUSE i removed my clothes in front of surveillance digital cameras in a uw–office racial-police, Where the british–racist-police-from-scotland did tell me to sign papers that I DIDN'T EVEN had opportunity to read at all; THEY sent me in jail–custody to KITCHENER-waterloo criminal justice court. "

"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY" let all investigations done and concluded that I HAD NEVER ASSAULTED this idiot police white-british office that charged myself with 'ASSAULT TO POLICE OFFICER' ! "

"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY" told me she called "the office of THE president of the university of waterloo" to ask them to let myself defend my "Ph.D. degree dissertation"; BUT they told her with attorneys of law of the president of the university of waterloo: "What is a crown attorney doing in the office of president ?" "

"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY" then on another did tell me that someone from the office of the president-idiot–racist of the university of waterloo; said that they have certain attitudes that are based on their local culture!

Incompetent "doctoral Ph.D. program coordinator as a Master of Science (M.Sc.)" Sarah landy

went on to harass the university of waterloo police ; ESPECIALLY (ambinns@uwpolice.ca); to say Like a HE-girl–pom–pom–shit that: "THIS black gay guy is so huge that he must be destroyed mentally !!!

this kind of race–sarah–landy MUST never be admitted anywhere else in this black world other than her anus....zizi.

[THIS happened in year 2018 as I WENT TO DESTROY my so-called—white-oblivier canadian–CACA–shit—citizenship–pegg–kkk.]

"I AM THE one who told to MRS. cuon-idiot–racist–white–quebec–tabawec—"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY", that THIS IS CALLED discrimination !"

- a. "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

I. **Formal Training for occupying teaching positions** |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[**TEACHING ASSISTANT training;**
CUT-1 - Certificate in University Teaching 1]

[Summary-PAGES]

1. **Training in ECE Department (Electrical & Computer Engineering Department):**

Before starting my 1st formal appointment as a teaching assistant at the University of Waterloo, ON, CANADA; In year 2009, I received a group training for graduate students of the ECE (Electrical & Computer Engineering Department).

2. **Passed QUALIFICATION interview to teach OBJECT-ORIENTED PROGRAMMING WITH JAVA:**

I SUCCESSFULLY passed a presentation slides lecture for qualification interviews OF 30 minutes added with "Q&A - Questions & Answers" session; to teach Object-Oriented Java Programming to 1st year students at THE university of Waterloo in year 2012.

NEVERTHELESS, I was not chosen as THE committee said: I QUOTE THEM: "Xavier might no be able to manage this very young age students in a class of 100 or more." I WAS AGED MYSELF 29 years old in year 2012 when this happened ! THX TO PATRICK-IDIOT-LAM

PATRICK-IDIOT-LAM is only 4 years older than myself. (<https://www.patricklam.ca>)

IT seems PATRICK and lin-tan-AGED-exactly as myself were trying to avoid a so-called-negger at a high paid position at UNIVERSITY-OF-WATERLOO. "Lin tan" is born 1983 like Xavier noumbissi NOUNDOU ! (<https://cs.purdue.edu/lintan>)

THE class was given at the end to a seasoned professor named **SEBATIAN FISCHMEISTER** (<https://ece.uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>), that leads the **Embedded Research Group in ECE** (<https://ece.uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>).

3. **This was optional. CUT-1; Certificate in University Teaching – 1:**

"THE university of waterloo in ontario, Canada"; offers a formal training program in 4 certificates to qualify graduate students and / or whatsoever qualified persons for teaching at a UNIVERSITY.

I attended the level 1 certificate in 2010, but didn't pursue the last 3 levels because I felt I couldn't perform as fast as I wanted my doctoral research due to the high level of academic requirements due by researching in the "static code program analysis" area of research; At **WatForm (WATERLOO FORMAL METHODS group research)** (<https://watform.uwaterloo.ca>); led by "Prof. Dr. JOE atlee of the CS (Computer Science) Department" (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~jmatlee>).

AFTER my free registration, at my own request and without asking PATRICK-idiot-lam; and attendance of all 1st level courses at "DAVEN-PORT library on main (200 UNIVERSITY AVENUE WEST) campus" of the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, I notice IT would be impossible to myself to finish my research in due time without issues with my doctoral advisor !!!

WE were around 10 in a sumptuous and luxurious carpeted room at kind of 3rd level in the main building !

ESPECIALLY added to the fact I WAS EARNING SUCH A LOW 999-CAD, so I HAD to TA-teaching assisting PATRICK lam.

THAT'S why I resigned.

[I EVEN feared PATRICK lam was trying to make myself sick because of the amount of stipend I HAD, compared to other students like JON eyolfson who also add other stipend from NSREC-CANADA !!!]

"I was under supervision of my doctoral Ph.D advisor Dr.-Ph.D. of Engineering PATRICK lam".

I. Competencies Acquired and Learned as a TEACHER-PROFESSOR |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[*TEACHING ASSISTANT training*]

- o SUMMARY of given-co-taught courses: '2' undergraduate ("Bachelor") level courses.
- o Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)
 1. Creating a "JUnit 4-tutorial" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052444/>) [14] and got it reviewed by PATRICK LAM; THIS is not a task PATRICK as instructor asked me to perform; I did this in my free time and put it as sample training material for students. – *"(+) Professor task level"*
 2. GOING in class to teach JUnit for exercise session – *"(+) Professor task level"*
 3. Creating SAMPLE solutions to assignments – *"(+) Professor task level"*
 4. MARKING ASSIGNMENT à la patrick lam – *"(+) Professor task level"*
I felt very improved for my teaching software technical testing skills.
- o Programming for Performance (ECE 459)
 1. *TAKING some time in my time of research for my ["PH.D. in electrical & Computer ENGINEERING"] to receive students visit at my office; and teach them what they couldn't understand either in class, and / or for the course material ! – *"(+) Professor task level"**

" Since my PH.D.-advisor patrick was the Director of Software Engineering study programs, I Think he thought I could replace him as a lecturer and he wanted to test these skills."
 2. *"Really I didn't much like this course as taught by PATRICK because it was more a kind of programming course that wasn't very solid in mathematical and engineering foundations; Except for theories and histories on processor speed "MOORE-law" expansion and development ! "*

"THIS was more to gain money because I was only earning \$999 Cad as a "master of science, PH.D. candidate" under supervision PATRICK-lam; coming from a middle level-paid good money position."

I. Competencies Acquired and Learned as a TEACHER-PROFESSOR |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Jan. 2012 – 10 MARCH 2015]

[TEACHING ASSISTANT training]

◦ SUMMARY of given-co-taught courses: '3' undergraduate ("Bachelor") level courses; '2' graduate ("Master", "PhD", "Ph.D.") level courses.

◦ Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)

1. Because of my resignation act in front of all committee members of my doctoral Ph.D. comprehensive examination and DISSERTATION COMMITTEE members;
I resigned !

◦ Compilers (ECE 351)

1. I did during my time in BREMEN, a course called ("Übersetzer GENERIERUNG mit LEX und YACC") that could be translated in English-white: "Compiler / TRanslator GENERation with LEX & YACc".
2. Creating Python scripts to query, compile and build; and check results of computer programs as assigned for students in ECE 351 class of racist DEREK-GAYSIDE.

◦ * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – METHODS AND TOOLS FOR SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 650)

1. I went to classes like students to assist idiot-Igor-IVKOVIC that required this visitation of classes for me. – "(*) Professor task level"

"deceased NOVEMBER 2021 igor idiot-ivkovic wasn't not even capable of understanding what he taught in front of students professional himself. THAT'S why he required my presence in classes so I will help him better ! "

"IT Means IGOR-ivkovic shalln't have gain more "payment cheques" than myself because it seemed to me I would do more teaching than he did."

◦ Computer Networks (ECE 428)

1. "Creating Python scripts to query, compile and build; and check results of computer client-server programs as assigned for students class of racist-idiot Mahesh-Rayside."

◦ * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – FOUNDATIONS OF SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 651)

1. "Learned on the grasp theories and practices of software quality metrics and tools so to teach them to students. IGOR ivkovic, the deceased idiot-instructor wasn't even capable himself of anything." – "(*) Professor task level"

◦ [C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)]

1. Working with "iranian in north-america", as being a black-afro-descendant is not recommended at ALL !

"JON eyolfson is a burglar incompetent GUJA that is not even capable of respecting an agreement of 2-weeks replacement for his office mate."

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (TEACHING ASSISTANT — UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

- I. **Duties completed by Teaching Assistant [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou |**
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2012 – Apr. 2015]
- 1.) [SUMMARY of student research-teaching advisory work both "autonomously" and, from my PH.D-advisor PATRICK].
 - 2.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of INSTRUCTOR "MAHESH rayside-idiot":**
 - o **Computer Networks (ECE 428)** SPRING term (Jan.-Apr.) "2013"
 "THIS ignorant professor couldn't be even capable of clearly defining programming assignments, AS I had to tweak the Python code for automatically correct student code source from Gitlab-repositories created by a so called [PATRICK-lam]."
 [THIS ignorant didn't even know I was a perfect computer software developer since age 18 in Cameroon; as demonstrated by my professional record of employment in GERMANY that is at least trice more developed technologically than idiot CANADA.]
 - 3.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "Derek rayside-idiot":**
 - o **Compilers (ECE 351)** FALL term (Sep.-Dec.) "2012"
 "THIS idiot from massachusetts-gay institute of technology cannot even define what is mathematical relation WITHOUT saying: I quote him: 'a relation is like a table'... (<https://csail.mit.edu/sdg>)
 "I was kind of surprise that we MUST had to code source code to correct programmings assignments as "styles of programming for instance, comments, etc," MUST be also marked and more importantly advised, Especially from a performance confirmed seasoned software developer as myself: DR.-PH.D. of ENGINEERING XAVIER noumbissi noundou. (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) "
 "I was very surprised to see a [culprit called MATTHEW MA] that was Master of Applied Science of DEREK, COMING to myself with his mother and offer me "\$400 CAD so to code for his MASTER PROJECT in Computer Software Engineering from derek." "
 "Thinking that derek went to pay around \$30 000—CAD to MATHGENEALOGY.ORG, (<https://mathgenealogy.org>) so my free registration from "[PATRICK] AND rinard-martin; (<https://csail.mit.edu/~rinard>)" from 'PH.D.' onto 'ABD' be changed without any formal justification as specified [[here];] DEREK-GAYSIDE is only someone that hijacked to get a degree from renowned MIT." "
 - 4.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "LADAN":**
 - o **[C++ LABORATORY (ECE 250)]** FALL term (Sep.-Dec.) "2014"
 "THIS in german so called 'HURE'-prostitute (<https://Wikipedia.org>) Declares be a professor for software system.
 I cannot testify this as "her student MOHAMMAD HAMDAQA" was so ignorant and had a tremendous background in business but knew nothing on software system at all ! "
 "I spent hours talking to ladan via her idiot student from JORDAM-kingdom that seems to have even acquired a faculty position at so called "ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTREAL-qc-chien-tabawak-satan" (<https://www.polymtl.ca>) "
 - 5.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "deceased-Igor Ivkovic-idiot":**
 - o * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – METHODS AND TOOLS FOR SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 650) FALL term (Sep.-Dec.) "2013"
 1. I went to classes like students to assist idiot-Igor-IVKOVIC that required this visitation of classes for me. – "(*) Professor task level"
 "deceased NOVEMBER 2021 igor idiot-ivkovic wasn't not even capable of understanding what he taught in front of students professional himself. THAT'S why he required my presence in classes so I will help him better ! "
 "IT Means IGOR-ivkovic shalln't have gain more "payment cheques" than myself because it seemed to me I would do more teaching than he did."
 o * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – FOUNDATIONS OF SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 651) SPRING term (Jan.-Apr.) "2013"
 1. "Learned on the grasp theories and practices of software quality metrics and tools so to teach them to students. IGOR ivkovic, the deceased idiot-instructor wasn't even capable himself of anything." – "(*) Professor task level"
 - 6.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructors "Patrick LAM", and "LIN tan":**
 - o **Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)** SPRING term (Jan.-Apr.) "2015"
- II. **Duties completed by Teaching Assistant [Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou |**
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]
- 1.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "Patrick LAM":**
 - o **Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)** SPRING term (Jan.-Apr.) "2010"
 "I AM THE one that creates the only sample solution to midterms. PATRICK is not very good at kind of creating technical solutions based on graph-theoretical foundations as for instance when creating equivalence class based test sequences solutions." — 📄
 "Sample TESTING material I Created." (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052444/>) [14]
 - o **Programming for Performance (ECE 459)** SPRING term (Jan.-Apr.) "2011"
 I co-create with other teaching assistants such as [JON-eyolfson] solutions for assignments and / or midterms exams.
 I also receive students during predefined weekly time frame so to help them out with understanding of learning courses material.

1. CO-teach and CO-assign, & Co-mark Assignments for Graduate and Undergraduate Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [OCT. 2009 – APR. 2015]

[PROOF READING,
static code dataflow analysis,
SCALA,
JAVA, C++, *JUnit* testing,
research ideas talks and development,
computer programming teaching]

[Summary-PAGES]

I. Students from the University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA I helped during my stay at the University of Waterloo, ON:

1. ["Matthew Ming Ma, M.ASc., Mechatronics, Engineering":]

- o How to configure a "developer" JAVA virtual machine under Ubuntu LINUX;
- o "I gave him contextual help in writing JAVA code for his Master of Applied Science project, under supervision of Derek Rayside".
- o HE then got a so called, at "**APPLE INC. LTD.**" (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374bdca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) , **software in test developer** (<https://www.apple.com/jobs>) job;

That is why even a "**WIFI-connection**" to a laptop doesn't work with APPLE phones as I COULD experience myself in CAMEROON (a white phone paid for \$120 CAD).

2. ["DR. JON eyolfson, Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering":] (<https://www.jeyolfson.com>)

- o How to use efficiently and effectively double pointers in C++ function / method calling argument parameters;
- o "I gave him my full LaTeX doctoral Ph.D. thesis (ECE calls this a research proposal) document for helping him out with a template at his own request".

3. "Dr. Vajih MONTAGHAMI, Ph.D., Electrical & Computer Engineering":

- o Thorough discussions and talks about his research ideas and on computer programming related topics (mostly on the "Watform LAB white-board").

4. "Divam Jain, M.Math., Computer Science", from Ph.D.-advisor of mine Dr. of Engineering "Patrick LAM":

- o Gave "DIVAM" sample code of my sample projects in JAVA about static code dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. Kildall : A **unified approach to global program optimization** (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)"; As opposed for instance to static code dataflow analysis " à la **IFDS (Interprocedural, Finite, Distributive, Subset)** (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Inter-procedural-data-flow-analysis-with-IFDS-IDE-Bodden/a3f7557fe673ff0711e9049cf5ece8b02a51f7f1>)" from "**THOMAS-reps at the university of wisconsin-madison**" (<https://www.grammatech.com>) .

IBM provides WALA as library for working with IFDS framework. (<https://research.ibm.com/publications/program-analysis-using-wala>)

- o Introduction and supervision on how to use **SOOT** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) ;
- o Brief discussions and talks on using static dataflow analysis for JUNIT test case generation;
- o Declared "Master of Mathematics" title at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO: "**Detecting Test Clones with Static Analysis**" (<https://hdl.handle.net/10012/7943>).
- o **FOLLOWING** plagiary by [zheng FELIX fang] and [PATRICK lam] originate from this seminal initial work where I contributed partly in code source writing:

A) "**Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints**" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

5. "zheng FELIX fang, M.ASc., Electrical & Computer Engineering", from Ph.D.-advisor of mine Dr. of Engineering "Patrick LAM":

- o Overview of ["Divam Jain's"] previous work on SOOT and static dataflow analysis for generating JUNIT test cases.
- o Brief discussions and talks on using static dataflow analysis for generating JUNIT test cases.;
- o "Declared MASTER OF APPLIED SCIENCE title" at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO: "**Test Clone Detection via Assertion Fingerprints**" (<https://hdl.handle.net/10012/8831>);
- o FANG then got a position at MICROSOFT corporation in SEATTLE.
- o [1 scientific conference paper came out of this supervision-advising :]
 - a.) "**Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints**" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

1. HELPIng black–descendant students from the UNIVERSITY of waterloo–racist–on |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Oct. 2009 – apr. 2015]

I. Students from the University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA I helped during my stay at the University of Waterloo, ON:

1. "Amirhossein Vakili, Ph.D., Computer Science": (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~avakili>)
 - o How to use MAKE;
 - o static dataflow analysis explanation.
 - o "1st at all functional programming with SCALA introduction".
2. **STUDENTS in cameroon association rowac. (<https://rowac.ca>) "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"**
 - o **We at ROWAC (formerly CCAKW (Camerroonian Community Association in Kw)); Have invited ambassador-pd-idiot of Cameroon in OTTAWA (ontario) during summer 2014 if my thoughts are exact. THIS was during the soccer tournament we organized.**
 - o I presented and gave out certain documents I wrote about computer web software security vulnerabilities protection; AND measures to protect documents and computer–laptop during, after 1 general meeting evening around 06 : 00 PM.
 - o AFTER graduating, and came back into canada to resign an idiot-canadian citizenship acquired for travel-without-visa-purpose-only to EUROPE; I then discovered that several members of ROWAC were secret–servicess-agent of my assassin of paternal uncle LAURENT-tchandeu, PleniPOTENTIARY–minister:
 - Dr. (M.Sc.) Vincent Nanga
 - Dr. (M.Sc.) Innocent Tchigio
 - Dr.-PHARM. (M.Sc.) CHEONGWA wandzi-cheongwa@yahoo.com
3. "Godrick–chékété, Ph.D., French literature": "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"
 - o I MET "Godrick–chékété" via "YAW boakye-agyeman, ph.d. student in recreational studies at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON CANADA";
 - o Help in FINDING HIS way after his divorce from his spouse from BENIN (house searching, car fixing, etc.);
 - o HELP in looking for a financial loan at a Canadian bank.
4. "Eric Brefo–Mensah, Ph.D., Chemistry": "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"
 - o I MET Eric brefo-mensah via "CHIWANZA-kasanga";
 - o Help in proof reading his Master Thesis LaTeX document before his final submission in "year 2018".
5. Shirley Ddamba, "M.ASc. Civil Engineering": "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"
 - o I MET SHIRLEY at a bible study at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON CANADA;
 - o Help in learning hands–on car driving in Ontario.
6. Esther Lambert, "Ph.D., Geography, University of Toronto, 2017": "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"
 - o I MET ESTHER while she was cashier at ZEHRS–churchill–street.
 - o Help in proof reading her Master thesis for the department of geography;
 - o Help in learning hands–on car driving in Ontario;
 - o ESTHER then pursue 1 year internship at ONTARIO green–belt institute; SHE then was admitted at the University of Toronto for "doctoral Ph.D. in GEOGRAPHY".

RESEARCH AND TEACHING ('PROFESSIONAL' TEACHING ASSISTANT – CONTINUED [2] - THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. CO-teach and CO-assign, & Co-mark Assignments for Graduate and Undergraduate Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [OCT. 2009 – Apr. 2015]

I. *Professional Computer Engineers living in Germany I helped during my whole time at "UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, canada":*

1. "A paternal uncle Demo Noundou from Cameroon" (<https://www.ank-technologies.com>).

r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou" who at 1st was an illegal migrant worker idiot in GB–great britain, a junior brother of my late father and genitor "Théodore Nounbissi, B.Sc., Electrical & Computer Engineering"; was a student in Information Technology student at "TUHH — Technische Universität Hamburg–Harbug" (<https://www.tuhh.de>), and graduated from there with a "Bachelor of Sciences (B.Sc.)".

"Demo" then obtained a position as "PHP – JAVA Web Software Developer" at "Canon LTD.", based in Germany - Osnabrück !

AT least trice (3 times) a month, I will receive a phone call from Germany requesting software programming and / or database technical help from this GUJA.

Each time I could solve his issues until HE stopped calling around August 2014, when I became a CANADIAN citizen, and when himself *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* went for a marital union with *r-"Astride Patibé"*; a nurse from Cameroon – Baham – BAFANG tribe.

r-"CÉLESTIN puene" is another (Food–processing) engineer from Cameroon that came to myself sent by "his natal village Babouantou" friend paternal uncle *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* .

HE came saying he needed help in buying a mechanical truck from the USA for his brother in cameroon who possessed a road construction society in YDE. *r-"CÉLESTIN puene"* was first living in Frankfurt–GERMANY, before moving around 3 years after myself, into Canada [WASKAGANISH, qc; and "then Brampton, ON"].

" *r-"CÉLESTIN puene"* and *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* are now member of [** –"ROTARY CLUB INTERNATIONAL"–* **]; *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* was initiated by *r-"MBOUM, MD, Ph.D. (surgeon)"* from OSNABRÜCK–germany. I could say I do not want to be member when *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* asked for this in year 2014".

I. TRAIN young engineers & developers; CO-write software parts for YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM |

YERITH R&D, YAOUNDÉ, CMR

[2016 - 2017]

A. "ENGINEER-ENSPY job seeker-gay PAUL:"

THIS young scientist from ECOLE-NORMALE-SUPERIEURE-de-Yaounde came to myself via THE culprit named JOSEPH-djournessi during my attending of a biblical study at his home in BYEMASSI-yaounde-ACCACIA; IN year 2016.

"I started teaching C programming to this young gay electrical engineer from CMCI-communauté missionnaire internationale chrétienne OBILI-obédience (CMCI-obili); While he was looking for employment for almost 6 years after graduating as BSc.-electrical engineer from "École Nationale Supérieure Polytechnique de Yaoundé - ENSPY"."

HE stopped attending just 2 weeks after starting participating in group meeting with the 2 following scientist-educators.

HE said his financing person wanted him to focus only in applying for positions in industry such as "BRASSERIES DU CAMEROUN", etc.

B. "Scientist-educator-cuon KITIO:"

THIS young scientist from ECOLE-NORMALE-SUPERIEURE-de-Yaounde came to myself via THE culprit named JOSEPH-djournessi during my attending of a biblical study at his home in BYEMASSI-yaounde-ACCACIA; IN year 2016.

"I taught him how to use DEBIAN LINUX from the command line."

He could find a position as computer science teacher in a secondary school in west cameroon !

C. "Scientist-educator-cuon CHARLES-eteme; now working at Yaounde GENERAL hospital:"

THIS young scientist from ECOLE-NORMALE-SUPERIEURE-de-Yaounde came to myself via THE culprit named JOSEPH-djournessi during my attending of a biblical study at his home in BYEMASSI-yaounde-ACCACIA; IN year 2016.

"I taught him how to use DEBIAN LINUX from the command line."

HIS father could find him soon a position at "Yaounde GENERAL hospital" where he was earning "250 000 Xaf" to start his career as a staff web developer.

TODAY, as I have been living in Cameroon for more than 6 years now full time; I believed he was a "SED"-anti gang; IT means someone hijacking people from west-region so to make them wretched as a political argument for PAUL-biya-idiot-CPDM-president.

I. TRAIN young engineers & developers; CO-write software parts for [YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM](#) |

YERITH R&D, YAOUNDÉ, CMR

[Jan. 2021 – "October 14, 2025"]

A. "Engineer JEAN-PIERRE kamgain-idiot:"

This not professional computer science & computer engineering graduate, from "THE university of Yaounde 1", and from "IAI Cameroon"; was interested in various web-related tasks for searching employment within Douala.

1.) *plain code source "C" application programming interface development;*

A sample task was a development of a translator from "Qt 5 user interfaces (".ui" files)" onto "HTML5 pages";

2.) *JAVA servlet & apache tomcat server;*

A sample project using *APACHE-maven* (<https://>), for car maintenance & rental was developed both by myself and by JP-kamgain-culprit.

THIS sample exegete of "IAI Cameroon" wasn't capable of clearly write JAVA code as supposed with a "*bachelor of honours in Computer Software Engineering*" from both "IAI Cameroon"; And "University of Yaounde 1 (UY 1)".

3.) *PHP software development.*4.) *Training P.C.T.B-sarl employee on YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum:*

The culprit and school-mate NGADJEU-francis, refused to utilize JP because he went without asking advise from me recruit a so called call-girl-*IUC-cameroon* (<https://myiuc.com>).

5.) *Indicator for destruction of YVES-landry-galax-etoga in person:*

"JEAN-pierre kamgain has been trying to hijack my properties, both physically and emotionally because I COULD notify that HE was trying to spy my activities for "C.P.D.M party as NGADJEU-francis from P.C.T.B.-sarl did"“;

"Also JP-kamgain is the one that went to propose my ERP software system to BONTÉE sarl in AKWA-sud douala.“

6.) *[COPLATEC sarl is a psy-company for hijacking people at home:]*

OUR experience in Africa has been that at least "85% of societies" that are of type "SARL-ndlr-société à responsabilité limitée", 'GmbH (<https://WIKIPEDIAlinkDefinition.ORG>)-in-German-language';

"are companies for gay owned by soldiers FOR hijacking male and/or female consultants like myself that do not participate officially in lesbianism and homosexuality-zoophyte.“

ARLETTE-sibeuf seemed to be also member of SED.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (POSTDOCTORAL RESEARCHER AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. Create and Present, & Write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2012 – Apr. 2015]

[VIJAY-ganesh-chenapan, static dataflow taint analysis, dynamic binary program analysis, "INTEL-Pin", LLVM]

A. Duties completed by Researcher [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

 1. **SUCCESSFUL attendance of graduate level courses to improve my dissertation writing and research skills level of knowledge :** [Sep. 2012 – MAR. 2015]
 - a.) ["Program Analysis for Web Apps"] "Grade 88%";
 - b.) ["Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE)"] "Grade 88%".
 2. **SOLE and INDEPENDENT idea and research of development of static dataflow taint analysis with use of "compiler framework LLVM", for solving following complex software engineering problems:** [Sep. 2012 – MAR. 2015]
 - a.) "Application Programming Interface (API) usage temporal rules";
"QUANTAMP.COM (<https://www.quantstamp.com>) uses for instance part of this research outcome to solve the problem of checking the conformance of BITCOIN-related-software-automated-contracts."
 - b.) "Detecting software security vulnerabilities" that endanger normal workflow, PER user-requirement elicitation, OR per software usability engineering: "BUFFER-OVERFLOW problems"; "SQL-injection problems"; "FORMAT-STRING attacks problems"; "AUTOMATIC test case and test data generation solution classes";
 - c.) "VERY PRECISE AND DETAILED collaboration with Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. VIJAY-ganesh";

THIS research is more detailed in: [YERITH-SAINT \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293) [11].

1. Create and Present, & Write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2012 – 2014]

[Vijay-GANESH-from Ph.D.-at-stanford.edu (<https://research.gatech.edu/people/vijay-ganesh>),
RESEARCH outcome plagiarism,
RESEARCH outcome hindrance,
"JAN-peleska-crédible; best-ever-professor of mine",
"student advising-MISSING paper",
static dataflow taint analysis,
LLVM (<https://llvm.org/racist-apple>)]

- A. Duties completed by Assisting Professor [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (DR.-ING.-PH.D.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

[Summary-PAGES]

1. EXPERIMENTATION WITH IFDS-FRAMEWORK FROM "REPS ET AL."

[JAN. 2013 – JUNE 2013]

I discovered the "IFDS (Interprocedural, Finite, Distributive, Subset)" (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Inter-procedural-data-flow-analysis-with-IFDS-IDE-Bodden/a3f7557fe673ff0711e9049cf5ece8b02a51f7f1>) problems algorithm by THOMAS reps from UNIVERSITY-of-WISCONSIN-MADISON (<https://www.wisc.edu>), and from "Grammatech" (<https://www.grammatech.com>) ;

"I really enjoyed this graph-based software system interdependence algorithm; and accompanying free FOSS IBM-wala library (<https://research.ibm.com/publications/program-analysis-using-wala>) ".

NEVERTHELESS I tried a personal implementation of the IFDS-framework using SOOT (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) & Java-SCALA with no successful binaries; BECAUSE the ideology for using "IBM-wala" was quite strange to my understanding !!!

I then renounced & abandoned to pursue and implement "The KILDALL-style" ("Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)") using C++ and a book-Advanced Compiler Design-from ...IBM author... !:

 YERITH-SAINT (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) [34]

2. [Work on "Dynamic PROGRAM Analysis with FRANK-tip" in course CS846] & [Work on "Software System Security by Software VERIFICATION"]

3. [SUMMARY of student research-teaching advisory work both "autonomously" and, from my PH.D.-advisor PATRICK.]

[Sep. 2009 – Mar. 2015]

4. [Previous RESEARCH-development at AGBS—UNIVERSITY-OF-BREMEN.DE] :

"JAN peleska is my 1st best ever professor because I learned the best research skills from him while working in his research group in Germany-bremen-racist (E.g.: Unfortunately for myself; I couldn't get any professional-vocational student software developer position in a commercial company installed in Bremen.). (<https://informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp>) "

[FSE-soqua 2006]

"More importantly we had a paper at Foundations OF Software Engineering research conference in 2006 while I was working on my "Diplom-Informatiker degree [Dipl.-Inf.] (Master of Science equivalent)" in his research group at the University-of-bremen.de (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>): "Test Automation for Hybrid Systems" (www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf) — ("VERIFIED.DE" (<https://www.verified.de/products/model-based-testing>)) !!! "

5. Follow-up on research started by [DIVAM-jain] with following other fellow researchers at ECE:

- o DEREK-rayside
- o PATRICK-lam
- o REID-holmes
- o LIN-tan-idiot-gay-non-sense-girl
- o FELIX-fang
- o etc.

I started collaborating with DIVAM jain because PATRICK-lam sent DIVAM jain to me for learning about static dataflow code analysis using SOOT.

"WHEN divam-jain-racist left, I pursue this same research with FELIX fang, and then with researchers afore-mentioned in office of the director of software engineering program PATRICK-lam; Where we attended to group collaborative meetings."

THEN he was more about the problem itself; IN this occasion, how to automatically generate "JUnit test suites test cases" based on static code dataflow analysis of unit test code of the analyzed projects.

"A benchmark of "at least 100 open source JAVA libraries" was used to test these projects JUnit test code.

From this research came out at least 11 conference peer-reviewed papers and some journal articles, AND i wasn't mentioned as a co-author either:

- 1.) "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

1. Create and Present, & Write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2014 – 2018]

["sodomite-peggish-JULIA-rubin-AT-UNIVERSITY-of-british-columbia-CANADIAN-rate-gay-Israelite-ANTI-JESUS-OF-Nazareth",
dynamic binary program analysis,
"INTEL-Pin"]

A. Duties completed by Assisting Professor [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

4. **DEVELOPMENT of certain features of PHP-JAVA-judo-quebec web application for management of club members:**

[JUNE 2014 – NOV. 2014]

THE research paid-provision was around "1000 \$CAD" a month, which was very insignificant because of all the technologies working together such as: PHP, GWT (Google Web Toolkit), etc.

5. **PATRICK-idiot lam research idea**, and personal sole development of a dynamic binary program analysis for moving "PROGRAM-POINT" during runtime execution based on certain loop-condition; USING "INTEL-Pin" :

[SEP. 2014 – OCT. 2014]

PATRICK-idiot lam didn't allow myself to complete the program under his sole supervision.

I WASN'T really happy because he interrupted my main project on static taint dataflow analysis; HE didn't tell me anything about any outcome, and/or later done publication or whatsoever.

THIS research is more detailed in: [YERITH-SAINT \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293) [11].

6. **!!-sodomite-peggish-woman-attention-patrick-JULIA-rubin-ece-british columbia-faineant-chien-tabaweak-canaoe** said she will continue research with myself at UBC (<https://www.ece.ubc.ca/mjulia>) so I WILL GRADUATE as a "PH.D." !

[2018]

" IT was dereak-gayside that said I SHOULD TRY TO apply somewhere else than university-racist-of-waterloo since they-idiot-of-lam could call the police to arrest myself ILLEGALLY on waterloo dirty-racket-pd-cuon-tabaweak-quebec-salaud main campus !!! "

PLEASE FOLK that may think a white-racist Gives you a residence permit to allow yourself to fulfill your peace dreams; IT'S NOT THE CASE.

" THE WHITE-GAY-DAY-nancy-racist is only trying to reduce the speed of perfectionism and development of your country of origin by harassing you there with corrupt-gay authorities so you will try to go outside. "

" All these mansory-free-rotary-club-ETC.; CATHOLIC-gay-church is only a way to hijack your life in anti-christ-of-negger-jesus-of-nazareth like myself I HAVE BEEN experiencing for 7 years in ontarian-CANADA-shit-people-race. "

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (RESEARCH ASSISTANT – DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. CO-create and CO-present, & Co-write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[Algorithms dis-pension,
finite automaton theories,
"Year 2010 report",
"Year 2011 report",
"1st summer school on formal techniques",
[IDIOT-black-afro-descendant Sandy BEIDU from ghanaian land]]

I. Duties completed by Research Assistant [Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.; MSc)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

1. [SUMMARY of student research-teaching advisory work both "autonomously" and, from my advisor-PH.,D. PATRICK].
2. **SUCCESSFUL attendance of graduate level courses to improve my dissertation writing and research skills level of knowledge :** [SEP. 2009 – DEC 2011]
 - a.) ["First SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques"] "participated with certificate";
 - b.) ["Computer-Aided Verification-racist-nancy"] "Grade 90%";
 - c.) ["Advanced Compiler Design-cuon-plagiarism-of-jon"] "Grade 86%".

3. I went to **menlo-racist-college** (<https://fm.csl.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>) in California, USA, to the 1st summer school on formal techniques from "May 22, 2011" until "May 27, 2011"; under a recommendation-required (from professor doctor NANCY-idiot-day (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~nday>)).

I was accompanied by the GHANAIAN called SANDY-cuon-beidu supposed to be a very famous computer scientist originating from my home continent AFRICA.

[THIS hideous ignorant fellow, from a very poor material background arrived at the university of waterloo "WatForm-waterloo formal methods" in year 2010 if I have good memories; Saying to the world he is a JESUS-christian;]

This kind of black-afro-descendant is so disgusting that I believed that the racist **JO-atlee-his-research-advisor** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~jmatlee>) went to pick him so to dishonest myself in front of the extremely dominant ["iranian female population in ECE graduate student folks"] !

HE even thought that I RENTED my "ford fusion" to tell them (Sandy-idiot-day, and a lady from long-island-black-prostitute) that I AM A WELL-TO-DO-MAN in front of them.

[I JUST remembered my BUSINESS-trip while I WAS TRAVELING for SIEMENS-medical-solutions-erlangen IN concord-ca-usa; And I KNEW I NEEDED to be mobile; THAT's why I RENTED A luxurious "ford fusion" from my savings account from my HARD-job at SIEMENS.]

[SANDY-idiot-poor-man-in-all-system thought when the other ghanaian idiot-story-teller-Dr-PhD-ERIC-brefomensah brought me to his travesty-basement-slot in WATERLOO, in ontario, 2018; THAT i needed some drink from him !]

[PLEASE folk from basement places in GHANA; Cameroon don't need this kind of down-treatment as CAMEROON is way more advanced as demonstrated ONLY by me !!!!!!!]

4. I have worked on topic "temporal property verification in plugin-based software"; and created a computer-Libreoffice-Impress presentation slides for the **IBM workshop CASCON 2010-CDP-compiler-...** (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>); [IBM WORKSHOP-CDP CASCON 2010]

THIS research as "**Master Of Science**" (so called "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER DEGREE, ABBREVIATED (DIPL.-INF.) (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)[?]") led to my "**Doctoral Thesis / PhD comprehensive examination**" released research technical document : "**Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software**" (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>)

5. I have created sample program static code analyzes using the **SOOT framework** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) so to acquire skills in static code program analysis.

A very short introduction: " " (<https://>) to SOOT framework by

6. I HAVE IMPROVED my algorithm design skills by implementing popular algorithms using the Following ALGORITHM POPULAR BOOKS:

- A. **Computer Systems: A PROGRAMMER'S PERSPECTIVE, 2nd edition ("ISBN 13 : 978 - 0 - 13 - 610804 - 7")**; by "**BYANT**"-racist & "**O'HALLARON**"-racist-sexist;
- B. **Introduction to Algorithms-Isbn: " "**; by **THOMAS cormen** (https://www.amazon.com/Introduction-Algorithms-fourth-Thomas-Cormen/dp/026204630X/ref=sr_1_1?crd=2UBHH37C2Y2J3&dib=eyJ2IjojMSJ9.RxrAGDmePG_uPSHKskT1qe4eJp18_sU0zfGdVfEd1BzcV0qunH6HMFdUvjfBk5T7_hbHBgRqWVHVSmsYFd00P9qIyOhMwCdwVMeRQodxABi7cszQqi1XxeWBu8jZqpGALecudSCyPct_N4de9gw1drRqhl2Alh8huCTZ2PeIofPH8JLCoU0jaTq8vuQ-G7z1Jdit5yRk2hl627B7GRAFGV3fio1k8kSGbcuK5_JsFw6g.AobHaMGD2q1MBzQIcdziArWazLVBUQztj2REK1DRJ0Y&dib_tag=se&keywords=CS+Algorithm+book&qid=1726183252&s=books&prefix=cs+algorithm+book%2Cstripbooks-intl-ship%2C313&sr=1-1).

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (RESEARCH ASSISTANCE FROM FOLK-IDIOIT – DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. CO-create and CO-present, & Co-write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[**"JOHN HOPCROFT"**, **"samaneh navabpour-racist-extreme"**, **"1st Summer School on Formal Techniques"**, **LLVM, SOOT**]

I. **People from [the University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA] whom I got academic help:**

1. "AAKARSH nair, M.ASc., Computer ENGINEERING, 2009"

- "AAKARSH nair was the 1st student of DEAR-idiot PATRICK lam I have ever met.

HE is the 1st one to give me sample code on static dataflow analysis with "JAVA-SOOT framework (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>)" à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)" "

2. "NANCY day"

- "Professor DAY wrote a very good and tremendous recommendation that was used to admit myself to [**"First Summer School on Formal Techniques"**] (<https://fm.cs1.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>), by THE NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION, SRI International, Menlo College, Atherton, California, USA; in year 2011".

3. "Samaneh Navabpour, Ph.D., Electrical & Computer Engineering"

- SAM gave me 1st explanations about LLVM by using her previous work for a **paper-RITHM** (<https://>) she worked on in SEBASTIAN fischmeister embedded computer research group; She confessed not having exactly applied a static dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)";

BUT used only control flow graph related features to perform static dataflow analysis; this is NOT exactly **CLANG** (<https://>).

4. **Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naeem, Ph.D.** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~nanaeem>)

- NOMAIR was the 1st person apart from Patrick, my doctoral Ph.D. advisor that took so much time to help me understand and proof read my **doctoral Ph.D. Thesis** ([HTTPS://WWW.SEMANTICSCSCHOLAR.ORG/PAPER/TEMPORAL-PROPERTY-VERIFICATION-IN-PLUGIN-BASED-NOUNDOU/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33](https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/TEMPORAL-PROPERTY-VERIFICATION-IN-PLUGIN-BASED-NOUNDOU/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33)) [32];
- NOMAIR helped myself in understanding the intricacies of a context-sensitive static parametric analysis by explaining from his **research paper Multi-object ...** (<https://>).

5. **Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>)

- Professor Lhoták accepted to review my **YERITH-SAINT** algorithm thoroughly.
- Ondřej was very kind to help me with source code of 1 of his 1st LLVM dataflow analysis, before I started my own.

6. **Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. JOHN hopcroft-SEXIST, Ph.D.** (<https://www.cs.cornell.edu/jeh/>)

- Explanation, at my email request, and very promptly and generously about an algorithm in his compiler book.

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (GRADUATE INTERN AT INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS MACHINERY (IBM))

1. Perform duties assigned by big manager and PATRICK doyle in JAVA-J9 JUST-IN-TIME OPTIMIZATION team (, located in Markham-ONTARIO-canada); (advised by Prof. VIJAY sundaresan, M.Sc. (MCGILL, QC, CANADA) | Patrick Doyle, (M.ASc., UNIVERSITY OF TORONTO, Ontario, CANADA))) |
IBM TORONTO-IDIOT SOFTWARE LAB. [01/2012 – 08/2012]

[AS canadian-idiot permanent resident;

Automated Software TESTING with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIFY (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verify>),

Program OPTIMIZATION (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>), "Clark-salaud Verbrugge, Ph.D. (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump>)";

JVM – JAVA virtual machines, IBM – WEBSPPHERE, Managers are really understandable,

DOCTOR-ENGINEER,

Racism from restaurant in india-bangalore-IBM-gay]

[Summary Of D.ENG. [DR.-ING. in "French language"] (PH.D.) Review Research-PAGES]

I. Comfort excellent for work research at IBM:

1. I was working into a brown cubicle and had so much freedom in work that I WAS SOMETIMES afraid that I AM NOT PERFORMING well.

BUT when I STARTED working closely more with VIJAY I felt so busy that I WAS DREAMING of going home around 03 : 00PM in evening;

IN total, IBM in MARKHAM offers very good working and research conditions for his employees, *even better than my previous 1st full-time job as JUNIOR-SOFTWARE-DEVELOPER at SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS in Erlangen, BAVARIA, GERMANY !!!*

SIEMENS Medical solutions was really good in Erlangen; But i didn't like seeing "BOSS gerhard" watching his arm watch any 2 minutes to make sure we only had 45 minutes lunch-break; "Secretary "gudrun" is also really helpful and smiling ! "

II. ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:

1. **Prof. Vijay Sundaresan, MSc. – from Bangalore, INDIA**

THIS daemon of work was so kind that I ONLY FEEL I have satisfy him as much as he wanted and could !!!

HE is very attracted to good and fast male workers; because female workers would only try to hijack his time for a snack !!!

I am very proud of having work with such an amazing scientist at all !!!

ALSO the team managers, including the chinese woman, were very kind to myself as the only male afro-descendant from AFRICA !!!

2. **Patrick idiot Doyle, M.ASc. – from Ireland-CANADA**

THIS ignorant as a teacher and / or mentor couldn't even pick myself at time when I Was waiting for my hiring team for the internship to come at my encounter in the biggest room where we all intern were awaiting 1st day of internship.

III. Duties of Graduate INTERN [Doctor of Engineering] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

1. **FIX SOFTWARE TESTING FEATURE AUTOMATION USING BASH SCRIPTS**

I felt a lot better at this task because I could feel having a positive impact on the project team lead by manager that I don't remember names and academic titles.

ALSO vijay sundaresan wasn't very disgusting as people working in the restaurant, that always served myself BURNed food, especially pagan-an-food.

Vijay sundaresan is a very talented software lead and developer that I could ever see in my career; I VERY MUCH LIKED THE INTERACTIONS with him compared to PATRICK doyle.

TODAY I FEEL there are 2 factors that helped:

- A. **MCGILL university** (<https://www.mcgill.ca>) graduates in Computing Sciences are very much talented compared to other students from ONTARIO.
B. VIJAY-sundaresan was born also outside of Canada-racist-systemic like my recruiting manager that I forgot about names;

2. **MAINTAIN CERTAIN DAYS BUG DATABASE**

AT all not very difficult, since I WAS USED TO use CHARMNT in my previous full-time job at Siemens Medical Solutions in Erlangen, BAVARIA, germany.

3. **ATTEND TO COURSES AT IBM TORONTO-IDIOT LABORATORY GIVEN BY "pr. prof. dr.-ing. clark-salaud verbrugge" FROM MCGILL.ca** (<https://mcgill.ca>) "on Creating Optimizations for Compilers"

4. **SOLVE AS MANY AS BUGS IN COMPILER OPTIMIZATION CODE SOURCE IN C++**

Coming from a program analysis research team, that performed more static code analysis using framework like S00T, and LLVM; I WAS KIND OF not performing very well at this task at all because of the very applied and complicated data structures; Especially because PATRICK-indigeneous-iranian-irish-from-british-kingdom never even got me to a small talk for explaining me briefly what was the governing ideas leading the development team in MARKHAM.

INSTEAD, i only received so many documents that I had to read and detect understand myself.

Earning as much as 3 000 \$CAD monthly, I FELT SO BAD that I Went to complain to the manager; a very kind person; that allowed then myself to work with the team lead VIJAY sundaresan...

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' (WEB DEVELOPMENT INTERNSHIP AT BREMEN4U-GMBH-RACIST-PEGGIST)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN – HTML, CSS, PHP, JSP – CODE SOURCE FOR a Content Management System – as an EVENT MANAGEMENT SOFTWARE ONLINE racist (advised by MARTIN ...) |

BREMEN4U-GMBH-RACIST-PEGGIST, BREMEN, GERMANY-RACIST-PEGGIST

— March. 2004 —

[[WEB software development with PHP, CSS],

Peggist-racist colleague Martin...,

[JSP, HTML5,]

Samsung CONTACT Server on Redhat LINUX]

I. Duties of Web Development Intern [Vordiplom-B.Sc candidate (In Computer Science)] Xavier Noundou:

1. *Before attending and applying for this position; I attended courses workshops on Web development using MariaDB, HTML5, CSS, JSP, PHP during around 1 semester (4 months) at the Department of Computer Science ("FACHBEREICH 3) of the University of Bremen. (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)*
2. *Create configuration in Redhat LINUX for the Samsung Contact Server system.*
3. *Create HTML5, CSS, JSP, PHP combined code into a Content Management System for managing Event that are to be published on a specific date on the Bremen4u-Gmbh website.*
4. Martin was always having a very bad mouth-breath because of smoking cigarette all day together with drinking black dark coffee with no milk at all.
5. THIS was a very disgusting place to work as a new person living in Germany; also young girls from secondary school as internship workers; With almost no sense on respecting black african race at ALL !

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN C++ CODE SOURCE FOR THE SOFTWARE COMPONENT (which is protocol communication control) TXSUPERVISOR of Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist Software (advised by DARIO MERAUVIGLIA | GERHARD SENG) |

SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, BAVARIA, GERMANY

[NOV. 2007 – July 2009]

[C++,
Duties of Junior Software Developer (Software-Engineer),
Software Integration Testing [21],
UNDER german-traveler work-permit;
ROBOTER-linac,
Radiation Therapy Treatment,
IMRT beam treatment,
TXSUPERVISOR software component development]

1. Duties of Junior Software Developer (Software-Engineer) [Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

1. "MARVELOUS TRAVEL to Concord, CALIFORNIA, USA : my greatest and high paid experience of work since I was given birth in 1983 !!! — 5 000 EUROS

THANK you boss gerhard-idiot-SENG !!!!!!! "

2. "Participation in cancer treatment (IMRT) radiation therapy training, and all other software development related training for this position as JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER."
3. "C++ coding and defects fixing of DMIP control communication protocol as heart of Software component TXSUPERVISOR: around 110 000 Lines of code (SLOC)."

4. **Conception & Development of an automated software integration test infrastructure:**

- a. Cygwin bash-scripting
- b. Microsoft COM component as [CORBA] agent communication used

5. Software Integration testing using "IBM Purify Plus".

(COMPETITOR FROM "PR. PROF. DR-ING. Xavier noumbissi Noundou":
YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b]);
git <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif> ;

6. "DMIP Control Console" device as user control management for simulating radiation therapy linear accelerator "SIEMENS Linac Artiste" in our laboratory in Erlangen ground-base;
7. Focal entry point of all bugs of "Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist" software. INVESTIGATION, and then redistribution, according to defect type, to an appropriate sub-team VIA team-lead "Gehrrard Seng".
8. Support technical in writing software user manual with software testers.
9. Support technical with software testers in using "Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist" software.
10. Phone support technical in TROUBLESHOOTING "Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist" software.
11. Maintenance of communication development support from software developers from Siemens Concord in California, USA.
12. Maintaining using "MS office" of design documents of TXSUPERVISOR and "DMIP control communication protocol"; based on "FSM state machine theory": United States of America's FDA (U.S.A – Federal Drug and Administration), as well as CE (European Community) had to review the digitally signed documents; stored in "SAP-EDM (<https://www.sap.de>)".
13. Assisting "DARIO meraviglia" in selection of interns based on their qualification as reported on their CV – resume.
14. Advising of 2 software testing maintenance part-time employees:
 1. 1 from Germany, from The University of Bamberg (Bayern, Germany);
 2. 1 as an intern, from India.
15. "VMWare" (<https://www.vmware.com>) as debugging image creator development tool.
16. "MS Windows 2000", as well as, "MS Windows NT", as software development operating systems platforms.
17. "Visual Studio C++" as IDE;
18. "IBM Rational ClearCase" as Code BASE source management control software used;
19. "IBM CharmNT" as bug management platform used;
20. [LEGAL requirement summary experience with HANDLING of Design Documents Functional Specification for Medical Software according to "CE" ; "FDA".]

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN C++ CODE SOURCE FOR THE SOFTWARE COMPONENT (which is protocol communication control) TXSUPERVIROR of Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist Software (advised by DARIO MERAUVIGLIA | GERHARD SENG) |

SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, BAVARIA, GERMANY

[11/2007 – 07/2009]

[C++,

Duties of Junior Software Developer (Software-Engineer),

Software Integration Testing [21],

UNDER german-traveler work-permit;

ROBOTER-linac,

Radiation Therapy Treatment,

IMRT beam treatment,

TXSUPERVISOR software component development]

I. ISSUES – Problems with some colleagues:

1. Gerhard Seng and Dario Meraviglia told myself I should be promoted to the position of Dario as "technical lead of the software module component TXSUPERVISOR (only 1 developer)" if I could succeed in gaining a full-time permanent contract after an initial successful 6 months period of work under direct leadership of DARIO MERAUVIGLIA.

"AFTER SUCCEEDING the trial period of 6 months, I obtain a change of software developer contract from a full-time limited contract to a full-time permanent contract with "Siemens Medical Solutions"."

"HOWEVER after an additional 15 months of work, I am not anymore promoted to a higher level position of Technical Lead."

"This is why I decide to make the effort to go back to academia and pursue [a doctoral Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering (Computer Software)] at the University of Waterloo, in ONTARIO, CANADA; WITH [Dr.-PhD patrick lam as academic adviser] !! "

2. "Merlin Tonka from Cameroon" is calling me even before my first day at job in Erlangen to tell me he hopes I will be able to perform well and thus keep my job beyond the 1st 6 months period of try: He tells myself HE got my email from boss "Gehrrard Seng";

"From NORTH of GERMANY WHERE I STUDIED AND LIVED for almost 6 years before being recruited and before moving to Fürth-BAVARIA-Germany, this is not "SACK-ARBEIT": I.E. one shall not mixed private life affairs with business matters at all: THIS IS HOW I LEARNED IT in HAMBURG, and BREMEN ! "

3. "Merlin Tonka" one day follows myself in metro and bus so to tell me that HE shall be promoted as a team of a new testing and developers team, And that he shall be my manager.

" I was wondering silently (because very young in year 2008 with only 23.5) years old ("Merlin Tonka was at least 40 years old in front of my age"), that someone less qualified than myself and currently employed as only a software tester, which is a lower level required qualification; Put aside you are PhD-doctor-of-engineering; and that was recruited only 1 week before my personal recruitment, will become my manager by telling it to me only in streets ! "

"THE italian master of science-level engineer Dario Meraviglia is my technical lead, followed by Gerhard Seng, our common teal lead at Syngo-RTT-Therapist-SW-Realize team" !

4. After leaving "Siemens Medical Solutions" legally by resigning with a signed letter 3 months before leaving my IG-METAL-tariff-vertrag employment in year 2009; I sent a letter to thank "MERLIN TONKA" for the positive professional collaboration I had with him as a fellow cameroonian, despite a lot of troubles we had; I sent this letter only around 1 month after starting studying in Waterloo, Ontario, Canada.

"THE answer from "Merlin Tonka" is so negative minded and outspoken that I need to reply to tell him truth about not trying again to tell me he is superior to myself; I.e. Merlin tries in a letter to tell me I could not perform well in software developer job, that's why I resigned !!! "

"Only smelling the same dirty "grey-shirt" MERLIN was wearing almost every day was not comfortable because he was sitting just opposite side of my office-desk ! "

"I today in year 2024 can remark as a citizen living inside CAMEROON that killer from governmental agency [DGRE wear generally grey-shirts !]"

"UDM-université des montagnes (<https://WIKIPEDIA.ORG-racist>) later on in year 2009 invited DGRE-activist MERLIN tonka through THE KILLER OF MY GENITOR théodore noumbissi; So called [HUGUES NTOMANI tiako], which is sleeping with genitor ROSE sangnou so to perform crimes on my person even now in year 2024 ! "

"WHITE-blond supremacist slave-maker; PLEASE stop to hijack black afro-descendants that are talented. TILO. MÜCKE. DARIO. MERAUVIGLIA. MERLIN. TONKA ! "

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING – CONTINUED (1) (JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN C++ CODE SOURCE FOR THE SOFTWARE COMPONENT (which is protocol communication control) TXSUPERVIR of Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist Software (advised by DARIO MERAVIGLIA | GERHARD SENG) |
SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, BAVARIA, GERMANY [11/2007 – 07/2009]

III Students living in Germany I helped during my whole time at Siemens Medical Solutions:

1. **"paternal uncle Demo Noundou from Cameroon".**

Information Technology student in Bachelor of Sciences (BSc) at "TUHH — Technische Universität Hamburg–Harbug".

[Help in proof reading his Bachelor–Thesis.]

IV Students living in Canada I helped during vacation time by my uncle maternal "Théodore Wandji":

1. Co–roommate of Théodore Wandji at 5850 Rue Souart, #7, H3S 2E8, Quebec, Montreal, CANADA:

"Basser from Syria":

Electrical & Computer Engineering student in Master of Applied Sciences (M.ASc.) at "ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTREAL".

NON paid technical support in programming C++, with **"MS Windows 2000 as operating system (OS) platform"**.

2. **"Fabrice TCHOUMI from Cameroon":**

Electrical & Computer Engineering student in Bachelor of Applied Sciences (B.ASc.) at "ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTREAL".

NON paid technical support in programming C++, with **"MS Windows 2000 as operating system (OS) platform"**.

V Software Development Colleagues were:

1. Senior Software Developer "MAMIDI" from INDIA.
2. Senior Software Developer "Detlef Kendelbacker" (Contractor) from Bayern–Germany.
3. Team Lead "Gerhard seng" from Bayern–Germany.
4. Software Architect Balakrishnan; from India.
5. Software–Engineer [Diplom–Informatiker : [Dipl.–Inf.]] Xavier Noumbissi NOUNDOU; from Cameroon.
6. Technical Lead DESIREE görisen; from Bayern–Germany.
7. Technical Lead [Dr.] GANESH gopalakrishnan; from India.
8. Technical Lead [Diplom–Informatiker (FachHochschule) : [Dipl.–Inf. (FH)]] Johannes Bauer; from Bayern–Germany.
9. Technical Lead [Diplom–Informatiker (FachHochschule) : [Dipl.–Inf. (FH)]] Martin Maier; from Bayern–Germany.
10. Technical Lead [Ing., Polytechnico Di Milano] Dario Meraviglia; from Italy.

VI Software Testing Colleagues were:

1. Test Manager [Diplom–Informatiker : [Dipl.–Inf.]] "TILO mücke"; from Germany.
2. Software Tester "Merlin Tonka, M.Sc. (Computational Engineering, University of Erlangen–Nürnberg, Germany)" from Bagangte, Cameroon–French–Island
3. Software Tester "Suschma" from India
4. Software Tester "Swapnil, Bachelor (Mechanical Engineering)" from India
5. Software Tester "Dhananjay" from India

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (STUDENT SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT GEWETE GMBH)

1. CREATE SQL databases JAVA Servlet programs and C++ communication protocol software programs (advised by SVEN KAMRATH | JENS MÖLLER) | BERGMANN AUTOMATEN GMBH (NOW GEWETE GMBH), GERMANY [03/2005 – 04/2007]

[CE – EUROPEAN COMMUNITY (https://www.single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/ce-marking_en), UNDER german-traveler student part-time-work-permit, C++, MAKE, "JSWING", Hibernate, JAVA, Servlets, apache ANT, Eclipse IDE, XML (e.g: JAXP library), Qt, SQL, Vending machines, Communication protocol – [debugging at YERITH R&D Now !](#)]

I. APPLICATION FOR A STUDENT DEVELOPER POSITION AT "BERGMANN AUTOMATEN GMBH":

I stumble on this offered position while I WAS LOOKING FOR A NEW DEVELOPER position part-time when I KNEW MY PROJECT with "PROF. DR. RER. POL. KLAUS–racist bönkost" would not be renewed.

THE position was advertised on a website for student jobs of the TUHH (<https://www.tuhh.de>).

II. Duties of Student Software Developer [Vordiplom in Informatik] Xavier noumbissi Noundou:

1. "LaDIVA java servlet XML parsing project development, and its installer Graphical User Interface (GUI) program developed using "JSWING" (<https://>) JAVA library technology."
2. "MESO": "LaDIVA java servlet XML parsing follower project development."
The novelty in this follower project is that I INTRODUCED, based on my research skills, acquired in BREMEN, an object–relational database object mapper called "**Hibernate** (<https://www.hibernate.org>)"; THIS was to be capable of giving newer customers ORACLE 9i functionalities from "LaDIVA java servlet XML parsing project" !!!
3. "C++ coding of a "Sap-ABAP protocol communication interface" to put "Bergmann Automaten GmbH" vending machines in communication with vending machine of Hamburg public library that used "BIBLIOTHECA software library".
4. "C++ coding of *SIPv2 control communication protocol* (<https://>)."
5. Migration from "ORACLE 9i database tables" onto "MySQL database tables" for the MESO project (follower of LaDIVA software project); I used following technologies:
 - a. BASH–scripting
 - b. AWK scripting language.

III. Students living in Germany I helped during my whole time at "Bergmann Automaten GmbH, Rellingen, Hamburg":

1. "**paternal uncle Demo Noundou from Cameroon**".
Information Technology student in Bachelor of Sciences (BSc) at "TUHH — Technische Universität Hamburg–Harburg" (<https://www.tuhh.de>).
"Demo" then obtained by "Bergmann Automaten GmbH" a position as "Bachelor student working on its thesis, project–based":
 - a. I talked to "Mister Sven Kamrath of this request", by "Mister Demo Noundou", of a Bachelor Thesis Project.
 - b. HE ("DEMO") then refused a final offer as full–time "JAVA software developer" because he felt he couldn't perform well in a "JAVA plain object (JPO)" software development environment.
 - c. "[2008] Demo Noundou, B.Sc." then accepted a position at "Canon Ltd. as **PHP – JAVA Web Software Developer in Osnabrück; HE can–also wear title Dipl.–Ing. (FH).**".
 - d. " [2015] DEMO NOUNDOU is now at his own company in web development & training in HAMBURG. (<https://ank-technologies.com>) "
 - e. " [2024] DEMO is also a consultant in african universities curriculum development based in KENYA, and others. NO ONE CAN BE A PROPHET IN HIS HOME–YAOUNDE. (<https://SAINTEBIBLE.COM/jesusquoteTOCHECK>) "

"DEMO NOUNDOU, B.Sc." also had a "grade of (10.5/20)" which is not a very good grade to enter such position as the one I GOT LATER ON AT siemens medical solutions; A "GRADE OF 14.5/20" is required to apply for any entry level position at ["SIEMENS AG GERMANY–low–payer"].

IV. ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:

1. *Herr Sven Kamrath was very angry at myself 1 day during my stay in Rellingen to talk about an ongoing project 'LaDIVA XML Servlet Parser Server' !
"He found a subtle bug that I then fixed the same day."*

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (WEB-HTML-CSS DEVELOPER AT ZENTRUM FÜR MULTIMEDIA IN DER LEHRE (ZMML))

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN websites – www.s-hb.de (<https://www.s-hb.de>) mainly – for KLAUS-racist-extreme BÖNKOST (advised by PROF. DR. RER. POL. criminal Klaus Bönkost) |
 ZMML-UNIVERSITY-RACIST-SEXIST OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY [Feb. 2003 – Feb. 2005]

[UNDER german-traveler student work-permit;
 'dunklefarbige mitarbeiter xavier aus Afrika',
 HTML5,
 CSS,
 "photoshop",
 IMAGE-dateien,
 FADRI,
 SVEN schu]

I. Duties of WERKSTUDENT [candidate vordiplom in INFORMATIK] Xavier noumbissi Noundou:

1. "Reception, and implementation, of design documents (e.g.: "photoshop images", etc.) from FADRI-racist."
2. ["Programming of HTML5, CSS web pages."];

[Participated 1-month to a training internship at Bremen4u-GmbH.]

3. "Programming of RAD-server programs with Graphical User Interfaces (GUI); With programming support of Sven-schu-nazi."

"RAD-server programming language (<https://wikipedia.org> . . .) is a sample VISUAL BASIC dialect domain specific language. "

4. "Participation in weekly meeting on development of websites and test facilities for students in economia."

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES – UNI-RACIST BREMEN

1. CREATE A MODEL-BASED TESTING FRAMEWORK TO AUTOMATICALLY GENERATE STATECHART MODEL TEST CASES FOR REACTIVE SYSTEM SOFTWARE ([advised by Prof. Dr. rer. nat. habil. Jan Peleska]) |
UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY — "NOT fully described curriculum by myself" [09/2002 – 05/2007]
- a. "Diplom-Informatiker" : "MASTER 2" IN COMPUTER SCIENCE THESIS (DIPLOMARBEIT): "STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION FOR REACTIVE SYSTEMS (GRADE 18/20)"; as part work for the FSE-SOQUA (2006) Research Conference Proceedings full research paper: "Test Automation for Hybrid Systems" (VERIFIED.DE), AGBS-UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [12/2006 – 05/2007]
- [“V”-“WATER FALL”-MODEL of Software Development, reactive system, UML 2.0, HybridUML profile, [statechart](#), Theoretical Computer Science, TDIOHS (time discrete input output hybrid system), STCT (symbolic test case tree), uniformly distributed statistical test case generation, MBT-RT-Tester, YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF as of now a doctor (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) .]
- Algorithms developed by myself for this 'Master of Science research-based Thesis ("Diplomarbeit" in German)' (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/qualifikationsarbeiten/diplomarbeiten_e.html) [1a], based on 'Prof. Dr. Marie-Claude Gaudelle' research outcome, as a mathematician in France, are used in the RT-Tester tool of the verification and validation research and German society "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH, SPIN-OFF THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN" (<https://www.verified.de>) .
- b. C++ CODE GENERATION PLUGIN IMPLEMENTATION WITHIN CASE tool "Borland-Together", AGBS-UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [09/2006 – 02/2007]
- [reactive system, UML 2.0, [statechart](#), Theoretical Computer Science, TDIOHS (time discrete input output hybrid system), STCT (symbolic test case tree), C++ code generation, MBT-RT-Tester]
- Our algorithms are for the "TDIOHS: Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System" (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf) state diagram formalism, that could be visualized by [statecharts](#) for instance using a 'Verified Systems International GmbH plug-in' for 'Borland-Together 6' (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Micro_Focus_Together).
- c. "Research Master in Computer Science Software 2-Years PROJECT" : CogAG project : "Robot "Arni" usage in framework of creating mapping recognition algorithms and cartography.", Cognitive Systems Group (CoSy), "Christian Freksa as Project creator and lead", CoSy – University of Bremen, GERMANY [01/2005 – 03/2007]
- [Cognition, Cartography, RFID-tag technology, TEXT-TO-SPEECH (<https://>), Robot control, sensor, actuator, Debian Linux, C++, Qt, systemic racism]
- "My personal contributions were mostly in creating QT user interfaces code for controlling the virtual shop and the roboter "ARNI". I also was very much implicated in Software Engineering round-about code such as blackbox code for keeping a BB-blackboard software architecture between our software components and the MySQL database tables used to share some of the data between components of the software system."
- "I also worked on cognitive cartography algorithms using C/C++, together with "ALINA, Christian, Sasha, and SERDAR". I was moving the robot for scanning RFID sensors stapled onto our real test grocery store, and then trying to find a way for the robot-ARNI based on customer commands on the robot that were at entrance to help them find their way into the real test grocery store. I used text-to-speech technology to talk with robot-ARNI to customers. "
- I was also involved in:
1. HELPING in general project organization for instance:
 - A. Writing project meeting minutes.
 - B. Looking for places in train, buses for project week-end ("PROJEKT WOCHELENDE"). Etc.
 2. Searching for places ("Student sleep places – JUGENDHEBERGE") for project-week-end in groups for fasting our project development;
 3. Writing LaTeX documentation for project reports;
 4. Writing JUnit testing code for GUI code;
 5. Writing BASH-scripts for tackling connection problems between actuators and the Debian Linux Operating System (thanks to Christian).
- "Unfortunately I received a grade of only 2.7 (14/20) because I wasn't interested in cartography and cognition algorithms since this was the specialty of "Christian Freksa" and "CoSy Group of Research" (<https://cosy.informatik.uni-bremen.de>)."
- THIS IS THE REASON our project advisors "FRANK dylla", and "LUTZ frommberger" gave as justification to this baddest grade during my entire curriculum in ACADEMIA at all !
- I also need to mention that I was the only "SCHWARZNEGGER – black from africa" in this research group of mainly white-blond-racists like "MICHA", and "STEPHAN"...
- THESE 4 racists-idiot said some day I may not be very comfortable in group working with white-intellectual. I THINK "frommberger the female-male-gay-BORN-male was at origin of such systemic" sexist discrimination around myself; even during my research time under supervision of male-female-chevalie-boivert-PATRICK-lam !
- d. "A SEMANTIC COMPARISON BETWEEN BÜCHI AUTOMA AND TIMED AUTOMATA (Grade 20/20)", AGBS-UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [09/2004 – 12/2004]
- [Vordiplom in informatik – INDEPENDENT STUDY, Bachelor Independent Study, MATHEMATICS for Computer Science, Theoretical Computer Science, timed automata, büchi automata, timed csp, set algebra]
- I developed a set of transformations functions that take as input a büchi automaton and generates a timed automaton. This work was the 1st work under supervision of "Jan Peleska", at our request, because we had interest in working in avionics software development in his company "Verified Systems International GmbH" (<https://www.verified.de>)."
- It is my uncle maternal "Théodore Wandji Ngongang" who is the one that gave me this advise at that time of my life where I was around 20 years old in Germany; "Just at my 2nd year of University."
- "Finally a small offer a 200 Euros monthly came after I performed 100 % for this work unpaid [details at link 1b], t hat I used as Independent study. "
- e. "1st & 2nd Semester Software Development PROJECT (Grade 18/20)", ST-UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [09/2002 – 09/2003]
- [“V”-“WATER FALL”-MODEL of Software Development, Software Engineering, Project Requirements, "Gant Diagrams", UML 2.0, XML, PHP, MySQL, JAVA]
- "This 1st and 2nd semester project, divided in 2 parts consisted in creating a multi-user dungeon server (MUD-server) where a virtual world existed; 1st year was used to elicit user software program requirements, and establish "Requirement documents using UML 2.0".
 - "telnet (port 23)" protocol was used as client-server communication mechanism."
 - "I involved myself in a project where I contributed around 7 000 lines of plain JAVA code of program development."

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES – PSY-CARE – UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN

1. Psychological care | [10/2002 – 07/2007]
UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- A. "DIPL.-PSYCH. RALF ERIC STREIBL.", MATHEmatics and Computer Science Department, University of Bremen, Germany [10/2002 – 07/2007]
["Dipl.-Psych. Ralf ERIC Streibl".]
- "As a student of computer science in the "FB3" of the UNIVERSITY OF Bremen, In city Bremen, HANSEATISCHE-CITY, Germany, WE had a psychologist as 1 of our lecturer called "Dipl.-Psych RALF-idiot Eric Streibl". "
- RALF-idiot was kind of very reluctant to discriminative opportunities because I remember having visited courses on web creation based on PHP, and MariaDB, since I WAS having [a student-job (WERKSTUDENT) at "ZMML"].
- Eric RALF-idiot also gave myself a so called course titled "PROPÄDEUTIK" where we students learned on how to effectively, clearly present our projects or work; THIS was done in groups and individually !
- B. "AT-HOME-RACIST-IN-BREMEN PROGRAM", Foreigner office-"Sekretariat für AUSLÄNDISCHE studierende", University of Bremen, Germany [JULY 2005 – AUGUST 2017]
["RAÏNER schulze-smidt".]
- THIS program was exclusively addressed for foreign country students to gain access to german in-born families in order to accustom one to germany as a home country.
- "I joined this program because my maternal uncle "THÉODORE WANDJI" recommended it to myself because He was emigrating to CANADA-montreal, And would have been very far from me. "THÉODORE wandji ngongang" was the one person that welcomed and invited myself to study in BREMEN ! "
- AT this effect, each volunteer foreigner student would be connected to a single volunteering family of BREMEN. IN my specific case, I was assigned to the "ARISTOCRATIC"-bürgerliche family "SCHULZE-SMIDT", originating predominantly from HOLLAND into GERMANIA.
- MISTER "raïner-schulze-smidt", and his 2nd"SPOUSE GABRIELLE schulze-smidt" were really kind and nice to myself.
- "RAINER was "sole investor and proprietor-German-INHABER of an insurance company in Bremen, and in LONDON-great-britain", WHERE he did his apprenticeship as "INSURANCE-business-man". HIS 2nd spouse Gabrielle that I met in person; Was a part-time "physiotherapist" for the football team of Bremen city : "WERDERBREMEN (<https://>)". "
- Through them, I could know more about the origins of the autonomous-HANSE-STADT of Bremen, since "GOVERNOR SMIDT" as upper-upper grandfather of "MR. RAÏNER Schulze-Smidt", was governor of BREMEN for 50-years, and is the one person that acquire land from "HANNOVER-autonomous-STATE", to create a water-port-German-haven; "BREMERHAVEN", as a city and port for the autonomous city-federal-STATE of BREMEN.
- People and places I visit, and met, through organization of RAINER and GABI :
- 1.) HIS cousins from Brazil by talk-only & pictures (<https://>); that I DON'T remember family names;
 - 2.) HIS cousins from JOHANNESBURG by talk-only & pictures (<https://>); that I DON'T remember family names, but that are having a wool factory for exportation in the state of BREMEN-recist germania;
 - 3.) VISIT of "evangelic church" on King-JESUS birth day "December 25th";
 - 4.) VISIT of MUSEUM-"Fockemuseum";
 - 5.) VISIT of "musical-theater" in "BREMEN-DOMSHEIDE";
 - 6.) "Bernhadine", "Caspar", "Johann" & "senior sister JULIA" schulze-smidt.
 - 7.) Several friends of them in need of computer technical help in terms of Software installation, and support.
 - 8.) "DOROTHEE" and "her brother Dr. oec. Sebastian Dettmers (<https://>)";
 - 9.) "Kryenhop family" (<https://>) : a leader in industrial transfer And sale of asian food and products into GERMANY :
 - a.) Father "Rolf";
 - b.) Daughter "SVANTSKE";
 - c.) etc.
- "I quit this family relationship at request of "RAÏNER" and "his 2nd spouse GABRIELLE-gabi", because they thought I lied to them that I have got a position as a temporary "SOFTWARE DEVELOPER" employee earning "70 000 Euros" annually at "AMADEUS Germany GmbH", Via THE frankfurter human resource company """. "

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES – PSY-CARE – YERITH-RD-TEST

2. Psychological care |
 COLLÈGE INTEG –FROM-LAQUINTINIE-HOSPITAL-EYOUM-CHRISTIAN-IDIOT-CRIMINAL,
 DOUALA, CAMEROUN [01/2021 – 06/2021]
- A. "DR. (PH.D.) JEAN MOUBEB", Collège Integ –from-LAQUINTINIE-hospital-EYOUM-christian-idiot-criminal,
 Douala, Cameroun [01/2021 – 06/2021]
 ["DR. (Ph.D.) Jean MOUBEB".]

"ROSE sangnou-chienne-génitrice; a sanguinary mégère that is said to have caused a sudden death of her husband THÉODORE noumbissi-idiot; my biological genitor; ORGANIZES that I am brought by force to a psychiatric institute called Douala-laquintie-hospital because we had a talk at her mother's place where I WAS SAYING that I NEED my documents from my real-estate properties be given back to myself by her."

"AS I am currently writing this small report on NOVEMBER 20th, 2024; ALL my belongings weren't given back to me by VICTOR koliou noundou that detains this official documents that I MUST possess by inheritance right as summoned by a judge just after the death of my father and dear genitor THÉODORE noumbissi-idiot."

"INGRID-teuntchou-noumeni-chandriand, born-geboren Ingrid TCHITCHUI noumbissi is trying to take away all my real-estate properties, together with LAURENT-tchandeu free mason !!! "

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL SOCIETAL IMPROVEMENTS I

1. **2003 – 2005:** [ZMML – University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE ENHANCED LEARNING CAPABILITIES of economics students at the University of Bremen by DEVELOPING WEBSITES AND STUDENT SELF-LEARNING COMPUTER PROGRAMS, together with THE TEAM OF PROFESSOR KLAUS BÖNKOST.
2. **2006:** [FB 3; University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE created a website for the AFRICAN STUDENT ASSOCIATION "Nasgen e.V (New African Student Generation eingetragener Verein)" !
3. **2006:** [AGBS – University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE pleaded FORMER CAMEROON STUDENT serge achille fopoussi nono TO COME WITH MYSELF CONTRIBUTE at work research group of PROFESSOR JAN PELESKA.
4. **2006:** [GEWETE GmbH, Rellingen, Hamburg, Germany]: I HAVE completely alone, installed and deployed a networked installation of LaDIVA at a section of "KARLSRUHE city council !", SO TO ALLEVIATE DUTIES OF dear mentor DIPLOM-INGENIEUR (FH) SVEN KAMRATH !
5. **2006:** [GEWETE GmbH, Rellingen, Hamburg, Germany]: I HAVE SUCCESSFULLY pinpoint TU HAMBURG-HARBURG CAMEROON STUDENT david demo noundou TO MR. JENS MÖLLER of GEWETE GmbH ¹, FOR HIM TO HELP MR. DAVID DEMO NOUNDOU with access to FINAL SCHOOL YEAR WORK EXPERIENCE, AND BACHELOR OF SCIENCE THESIS-WORK.
6. **2006:** [University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I could successfully provide "MS WINDOWS SOFTWARE" INSTALLATION, TROUBLESHOOTING, and TRAINING to several GERMAN people because of "DEAR MR. RAINER SCHULZE-SMIDT" and HIS SPOUSE "MS. GABRIELE SCHULZE-SMIDT".
THESE EXPERIENCES WERE VERY POSITIVE FOR my finances !
7. **2005 – 2007:** [AGBS – University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE CONTRIBUTED TO TESTING EFFORTS BEFORE FIRST LAUNCH OF JET FLIGHT "AIRBUS A380" by my scientific AND engineering contributions in STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION within RT-TESTER software of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH; THANKS TO MERCIFUL PROFESSOR JAN PELESKA.
8. **2007 – 2009:** [SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, Erlangen, Bayern, Germany]: I HAVE SUCCESSFULLY MAINTAIN All Oncology Care Systems HOSPITALS customers, throughout the whole planet, ON FRONT-LINE OF problem/defect RESOLUTION WHENEVER technicians on CRITICAL problem phone resolution lines 1, 2, and 3 COULDN'T SOLVE SOFTWARE TECHNICAL ISSUES of linac.
9. **2009 – 2011:** [University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, Canada]: I HAVE socially, WITH COMPUTING TECHNOLOGY, helped following afro-descendants from CAMEROON:
 1. CÉLESTIN puene: helped him search on the internet, and call, because of his poor English language knowledge, U.S.A businesses for inquiring on buying trucks for his brother in Cameroon.
 2. FABRICE Kouam Kamdem: maintained and improved an on-line website for FREE for his cameroon oriented professional association.
 3. ALBERT HERVAIS Ngagom Piewe: taught Debian-Linux basic shell command usage, Java and C++ programming on phone and internet.
 4. I HAVE presented orally and given personal written material ON SOFTWARE SECURITY AND SAFETY to CAMEROON ASSOCIATION of migrants in KITCHENER-WATERLOO: "ROWAC".
10. **2012:** [IBM Toronto Software Laboratory, Markham, ON, Canada]: I HAVE INTRODUCED skilled migrant cameroon worker, as ACTUARY in TORONTO, "AUDREY Nguetie Tchamga, B.Sc (Université de Laval, Québec, CANADA)" to use and exploitation of FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE (FOSS) "Debian Linux".
11. **2012:** [IBM Toronto Software Laboratory, Markham, ON, Canada]: I HAVE advised, counseled, and even developed an on-line website for fellow CAMEROON expatriate YVES FRANCIS Kamga Mbiele, MBA (ÉCOLE SUPÉRIEURE DE GESTION, Paris) ON HIS ABANDONED PROJECT (WITH DAUGHTER OF FORMER ENERGY MINISTER of cameroon) FOR SOLAR ENERGY PRODUCTION in cameroon.

I WAS INTRODUCED to "YVES FRANCIS Kamga Mbiele, MBA (E.S.G, Paris)" BY MY AUNT-HUSBAND pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude.
12. **YEAR-2012:** I COULD SUCCESSFULLY buy and implement foundations of "IMMEUBLE YERITH_{r&d}" which WILL STEM as a "PREMIER COMPUTING RESEARCH AND "Software Testing & Validation"" center in CENTRAL AFRICA (yaounde, center region, cameroon) !

I BOUGHT THIS PLOT OF LAND FROM hon. THÉODORE DATOUO; vice-president of parliament in YAOUNDE, CENTER REGION IN CAMEROON !

Land title CERTIFICATE nr.: 560 792, in SIMBOK, mfoundi vi (6), vol. 265 !
13. **2014:** [University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, Canada]: I HAVE searched information, on how to WELCOME and ACCOMMODATE CAMEROON AMBASSADOR IN OTTAWA, for "ROWAC", a cameroonian ASSOCIATION of high skilled migrants (MOSTLY PROVENING FROM GERMANY) in KITCHENER-WATERLOO.

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL SOCIETAL IMPROVEMENTS II

14. **2021:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]: I HAVE built a partnership with Dr. PETER Akume Ngoe and his societal NGO so to provide his NGO with VERY CHEAP AND APPROPRIATE software solutions for a NGO financed foodstore.
15. **2022:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]: I HAVE SUCCESSFULLY trained Mr. NESTOR Kenfack in ONLY 3 days at basic usage of our ERP software system YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum for hardware shop selling. Mr. NESTOR Kenfack IS ONLY holder of a "B.E.P.C".
- USUALLY in Yaounde, a holder of a "B.E.P.C" couldn't be trained to use COMMONLY present ERP SOFTWARE SYSTEMS (e.g.: 'Sage Gescom i7', 'SAP Business One', etc.), BECAUSE THEY ARE MEANT for highly qualified users.
- Mr. NESTOR Kenfack HAD NEVER GOT exposure to an ERP system in the past.
16. **2023:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I have given software cyberspace security counsels to Santa Lucia AHALA by talking to a computer technician employee because I could see vulnerabilities at cashier while paying for my goods.
17. **2023:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I have counseled a business owner to start a bigger grocery shop and gave him ideas and ways on how to realize this using YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM, and, also, my unfinished two-storey building.
18. **2023:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I have started YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE), so to improve computing skills of fellow citizen, and also, of any other person that conforms to Cameroon laws !
20. **2024:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I try to have SANTA-LUCIA-AHALA AS 1 OF MY CLIENT THESE COMING YEARS so to have YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM there working instead of 'Odo'.
So they (SANTA-LUCIA-AHALA) will contribute in improving quality by thorough usage of this new platinum-platform.
21. **2024:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I am now working with ALT PLUS in YDE-AHALA so to have a working Supermarket in one, Instead "of a hardware-shop + a food-store separately, BUT JOINED physically".

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING RESEARCH ACHIEVEMENTS I

1. **YEAR-2005:** IMPLEMENTATION OF the JAVA servlet XML parsing and saving server "LaDIVA", AND ITS GUI (JAVA-SWING) configuration and installer program; for GEWETE GmbH !
2. **YEAR-2006:** IMPLEMENTATION OF "MESO"; the IMPROVED and revised version of the XML parsing and saving server "LaDIVA" for GEWETE GmbH !
3. **YEAR-2006:** IMPLEMENTATION OF the library computer systems communication protocol SIPv2 for GEWETE GmbH vending machines !
4. **YEAR-2005:** INVENTION OF A PROCEDURE TO systematically transform A BÜCHI AUTOMATON into A TIMED AUTOMATON ! TASK COORDINATED BY SHAREHOLDER PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA, of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH !
5. **YEAR-2006:** CREATION OF (with higher study part team CogAg of the University of Bremen [Cognitive Systems Group led by DEAR LATE PROFESSOR CHRISTIAN FREKSA]) ROBOT "arnie"; AND PROCEDURES TO automatically map a supermarket both geographically AND store item-wise with RFID technology by HELP OF A ROLLING ROBOT "arnie" !
6. **YEAR-2007** [FB 3! AGBS: Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)]: IMPLEMENTATION OF statistical uniformly distributed test cases generation for HAREL-statecharts ! COMMERCIALIZED BY VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH !
7. **YEAR-2007:** [FB 3! AGBS: University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE CONTRIBUTED TO TESTING EFFORTS BEFORE FIRST LAUNCH OF JET FLIGHT "AIRBUS A380" by my scientific AND engineering contributions in STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION within RT-TESTER software of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH; THANKS TO MERCIFUL PROFESSOR JAN PELESKA.
8. **YEAR-2008:** IMPLEMENTATION OF the communication and control protocol DIGITAL MEVATRON INTERFACE PROTOCOL (DMIP) version 13 for THE LINEAR ACCELERATOR "linac" of SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, Oncology Care Systems (OCS) !
9. **YEAR-2009:** Stopping my career; AFTER 21 MONTHS; as JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER at SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS (Oncology Care Systems) in ERLANGEN, BAYERN, GERMANY; with 0 defects / faults returning FROM CUSTOMERS because OF non achievement protocol repair ! Award saying from BOSS GERHARD SENG; MY TEAM LEAD !
10. **YEAR-2011** [ECE! Ph.D. in Computer Science]: I HAVE INVENTED AND INTRODUCED A PRACTICAL AND SIMPLE STATIC ANALYSIS BY ITERATIVE DATAFLOW ANALYSIS, to check temporal safety properties, expressed with tracematches, of JAVA programs !
THIS TECHNIQUE HAS BEEN USED in following:
 1. (* Similarly, but as a dynamic analysis technique) MASC thesis (2011; submitted at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA), OF ASSISTANT PROFESSOR JON Eyolfson of the UNIVERSITY OF TORONTO, ON, CANADA !
EVEN THOUGH JON Eyolfson MASC (COMPUTER ENGINEERING) SUBMISSION WAS EARLIER THAN MY Ph.D. in SOFTWARE ENGINEERING THESIS DEFENSE, because of finding an examiner (reporting) within ECE DEPARTMENT, I AM THE ONE THAT GAVE A PROTOTYPE DESIGN AND PROTOTYPE DOCUMENT FOR HIS SUBMISSION !
11. **YEAR-2012:** I COULD SUCCESSFULLY DEVELOP manual and automatic BASH (Bourne Again SHell) programs (scripts), THAT LEAD TO A 0.5% improvement of WEBSPHERE computing performance !
12. **YEAR-2013:** CREATION OF A RUNTIME dynamic taint analysis for the QUERCUS PHP INTERPRETER !
13. **YEAR-2015:** FIRST WORLD-WIDE OPEN-SOURCE (foss) RELEASE OF AN LLVM-BASED ON INTERMEDIATE REPRESENTATION (IR) static iterative KILDALL (gary kildall) DATAFLOW ANALYSIS named 'YERITH-SAINT' !
'YERITH-SAINT': <https://www.github.com/sazzad114/saint> !
14. **YEAR-2015:** CREATION OF A CONTEXT-SENSITIVE FLOW-SENSITIVE tainted paths generation algorithm by iterative dataflow analysis !
THIS TECHNIQUE HAS BEEN USED in following:
 1. (* EXACT same technique) PH.D. dissertation / thesis IN COMPUTER SCIENCE (2020; submitted at VIRGINIA TECH, VA, U.S.A), OF ASSISTANT PROFESSOR SAZZADUR Ahaman AT University of Arizona, Tucson, AZ, U.S.A !
 2. PH.D. dissertation / thesis IN COMPUTER SCIENCE (2020; submitted at the UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA, SANTA BARBARA, CA, U.S.A), OF ASSISTANT PROFESSOR ARAVIND Machiry AT Purdue University, IN, U.S.A !
15. **YEAR-2020:** FIRST OFFICIAL RETESTED RELEASE OF THE full featured OPEN SOURCE enterprise resource planing software "YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE"; FIRST OFFICIAL RELEASE OF THE OPEN SOURCE AUTOMATED BACKUP-SYSTEM AND ALERT ("yerith-erp-3.0"-system-daemon": <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0>) !

"YERITH-ERP-PGI-standalone, server, academic, client" ARE THE DIFFERENT VERSIONS OF THIS FOSS-ERP-PGI-FRENCH !

SERVER AND CLIENT are mainly meant for a supermarket having several cashiers offices, AND A SERVER directing MYSQL-commercial options in common for different client-cashier-OFFICES !

ACADEMIC is meant for use WITH an IN-MEMORY DATABASE like "SQLite" !
16. **YEAR-2021:** First stable release of YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE at PHARMACY FIANGO LYCÉE MAKÈPÈ !

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING RESEARCH ACHIEVEMENTS II

17. **YEAR-2022:** FIRST DELIVERY OF a compendium OF DOCUMENTS concerning OUR ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE !
<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>
18. **YEAR-2022:** CREATION OF AN OPEN SOURCE state transition diagram LIBRARY FOR RUNTIME DATAFLOW VERIFICATION (YR_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF) (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif))
20. **YEAR-2022:** MODIFICATION OF A Free Open Source Software (FOSS) "QVGE" (<https://showroom.qt.io/qvge-qt-visual-graph-editor>) TO DESIGN state diagram TEMPORAL SAFETY PROPERTIES ! "YR_QVGE" ! YR_QVGE is a commercial tool of mine priced at 3 000 EUROS a single executable copy.
21. **YEAR-2022:** CREATION OF AN OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE FRAMEWORK for runtime dataflow analysis (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF | YR_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF) (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif) | 🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif))!
22. **YEAR-2022:** I have added a runtime check verification view within FOSS-ERP ("YERITH-ERP-3.0-SERVER": 🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)) IN ORDER TO VIEW LOG MESSAGES SENT TO YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF !
23. **YEAR-2022:** CREATION of a systematic method, AND / OR PROCEDURE TO TEST AND / OR verify dataflow of thick-client (or web application), AGAINST A SAFETY TEMPORAL PROPERTY SPECIFICATION expressed as a STATE DIAGRAM (modified mealy machine) !
24. **YEAR-2022:** FIRST OFFICIAL REPORT in FRENCH LANGUAGE OF ACTIVITIES of YERITH R&D SINCE RELEASE OF FIRST STABLE VERSION OF YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum!
"REPORT in french: <https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051568/>" !
25. **YEAR-2023:** creation of a domain-specific language (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG) to describe *state diagram mealy machines* (📄 SDMM).
26. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION with flex and bison OF A DOMAIN-SPECIFIC LANGUAGE COMPILER to create source C++ code files for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)).
27. **YEAR-2023:** SUBMISSION OF A FULL TECHNICAL PAPER ("YR_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF: A FRAMEWORK FOR VERIFYING SQL CORRECTNESS PROPERTIES OF GUI SOFTWARE AT RUNTIME") TO SPLASH-ICTSS 2023 CONFERENCE in May 2023.
28. **YEAR-2023:** Implementation of more than 2-states *state diagram mealy machine* (📄 SDMM) in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)), and YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)).
29. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION of guarded condition expression specification within YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)), and automated code generation of guarded condition expression in YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)).
30. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF EMPLOYEE PAY GROUP within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum.
31. **YEAR-2023:** First release of our CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) drawing design tool "📄 [YRI_QVGE](#)" official commercial document.
32. **YEAR-2023:** online ENGLISH INTO FRENCH, and vice versa LANGUAGE TRANSLATION within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum.
33. **YEAR-2023:** CREATION of a viewing graphical user interface application for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF in JUNE.
34. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF FIRST RELEASE OF automatic EMPLOYEE PAY GROUP SALARY CALCULATION. Cumulated pay groups for a single employee salary calculation is included.
35. **YEAR-2023:** CREATION OF a user's guide for YERITH_QVGE.
36. **YEAR-2023:** STARTED IMPLEMENTATION OF a user sample project AUTOMATIC binary executable generation in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
37. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF MULTIPLE programs under analysis (PUA) monitoring within YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
38. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF MULTIPLE runtime monitors WITHIN A SINGLE EXECUTABLE for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
39. **YEAR-2023:** STARTED journal article (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8381187>) for STTT official journal release.
40. **YEAR-2023:** started a predicate logic for deriving SOFTWARE RECOVERY ACTIONS for sdmm ("state diagram mealy machine").
41. **YEAR-2023:** started writing YERITH R&D 2023 *annual report* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10515549>).
42. **YEAR-2024:** finished writing YERITH R&D 2023 *annual report*: THIS REPORT specifically says that CPDM ruling party has tried to destroy my life using *CHRISTIAN eyoum* (<https://scholar.google.fr/citations?user=eHvsI1UAAAAJ&hl=fr>).
43. **YEAR-2024:** started writing courses curricula and content for several courses of [YECEFOIQ](https://www.yecefoiq-sarl.cm) (<https://www.yecefoiq-sarl.cm>).
44. **YEAR-2024:** started creation of a web site application for teaching computer science center YECEFOIQ.
45. **YEAR-2024:** I have implemented case insensitive search for financial expenses list within YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
46. **YEAR-March 2024:** I have paused new features in YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM (I.E.: Human resource management, and Financial Accounting management) due to advancements required for their quality assurance, WITH 📄 [YRI_QVGE!](#)

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING RESEARCH ACHIEVEMENTS III

47. **YEAR–March 2024:** I could finally find 1 company commercial that rented my 1st 3–bedrooms apartment in DLA for "90 000 Xaf" monthly !
48. **YEAR–March 2024:** I have paid "50 000 Xaf" as starting advance funds for incorporating YERITH R&D SARL.
49. **YEAR–March 2024:** I am recruiting 1 commercial financial entrepreneur for ~~YECEFOHQ~~ (LOOKING for investment funds).
50. **YEAR–JUNE 25, 2024:** Returning client N.K hardware shop for YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 !
51. **YEAR–2024:** Refining automatic stock CSV data entry.
52. **YEAR–JULY 29, 2024:** Still training "Christelle Akamba" for just 1 000 Francs an hour.
THERE is no money outside in Yaounde; and my rental apartments are still not having renters due to LAURENT TCHANDEU that I know has been trying to disrupt my activities in the open source software (OSS) era.
53. **YEAR–September 08, 2024:** *I AM working on ground to perfection building YERITH.*
THERE is lack of funding even though I could have my judicial affair against CHRISTIAN-EYOUM and others to get sent back to NDOKOTI prosecutor.
UNFORTUNATELY attorney SYNCLAIRE-NJEUTCHA-TCHANA has been trying to disrupt my activities with some money-bribery he received from genitor–organizer of assassination of mine !!!
I now try to get ATTORNEY-tchonang-albertine on my side these days. C.P.D.M wolfgang owona idiot political party has been trying to take down all my activities so to destroy a non-gay citizen.
54. **YEAR–2024:** Incorporating unit of measure like gram, etc. for inventory stock entry creation and pricing.
55. **YEAR–2024:** Started incorporating Financial debt entries creation in YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
I am also specifying YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME for a new idea as good–physical stock exchange start–up marketplace idea.
56. **YEAR–NOVEMBER 2024:** I have re–introduced new color schemes for YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME, AND also started a document for SPECIFYING and DESCRIBING the already existing and ALREADY IMPLEMENTED: C++ runtime monitoring verification library SDMM (STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE) :
1. YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF : [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif) ;
 2. ITS usage as algorithmic trading stock exchange library and runtime monitoring engine with help of a FOSS *"STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE"* (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf) monitoring container for real–timing.
57. **YEAR–JANUARY 2025:** *I have incorporated "FR", "EN", USA–american flag and FRANCE-flag onto YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM so to hint users on Translation from English into FRENCH; And vice versa.*
58. **YEAR–JANUARY 2025:** *We are trying to render incorporating of sdmm[1d] as plug-gable dynamic libraries into YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.*
59. **YEAR–FebRUARY 2025:** *[I am also trying to check conformant thread calls from runtime QT-QTimer instances whenever a user tries to cancel his modification / insertion work; FOR instance a special case is whenever 'INSERT/UPDATE' button is pressed and then there is intermingling with the checking mechanism introduced for verifying whether a user cancels his work on the window frame or not !]*
60. **YEAR–March 2025:** *I am struggling with INGRID-own-sister that digest all time my genitor because of 6 children with less than 2 years separation birth time between them !*
61. **YEAR–April 2025:** *Currently doing major research & inspection work for a web shop by using partly our; At YERITH R&D, new invention WYSIWYG–Tool for web HTML pages (YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL) !*
62. **YEAR–April 2025:** *NO body originating from West Cameroon seems to be living peacefully in CMR with bulu tribe since event a ["president bulu of the republic"] is embezzling young researcher in science and / or engineering like myself so to perpetuate going to IMF-fucking-idiot to pertain African in under poverty world for ever-devilish !*
63. **YEAR–May 2025:** *[JUDGE yager] seems to think of taking my complaint more seriously these days since I was advised to meet another justice attorney working a kind of on my file; Directly this coming 20th week of year 2025 (May–12 up to May–16) !*
64. **YEAR–May 2025:** *Eyoum Christian sends even people as kind fo rental management agent into my house to act so to hijack myself again : "Soumbil" living here at Cité-des-Palmiers.*
65. **YEAR–May 2025:** *[I am also these days trying to incorporate a dynamic taint analysis within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum as an instance incarnation of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF and / or "SDMM" specification & accompanying source code.]*
66. **YEAR–May 2025:** *We are working on our 1st prototype complete product that automatically generates a webshop from QT-trolltech user–interface files again this month; We plan a travel abroad !*
67. **YEAR–May 2025:** *[Soumbil, a molester of myself via a so called paternal uncle–gay–hijacker seems to not understand that as a mature researcher professional, And born–again Christian; There is no need for myself to talk with non sense village–babouantou-born people like KOLIOU-gay-idiot VICTOR-noundou !]*
68. **YEAR–JUNE 5, 2025:** Currently refactoring YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum !

20.20 'VALKYRIE' upgrade to DEBIAN BULLSEYE (11.0); QT-5

VALGRIND USER INTERFACE: *valkyrie* (<https://www.valgrind.org/downloads/guis.html>)

July 2023

- Free open source code:
https://www.github.com/yerothd/valkyrie_NON_OFFICIAL

'VALKYRIE' is a dynamic analysis CASE tool for verifying memory errors, and using VALGRIND as backend program server for analysis.

21.21 CONTEXT SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM ("YERITH-SAINT")

October 2009 – March 2015

- Free open source code:
<https://www.github.com/sazzad114/saint>

'YERITH-SAINT' is a static taint analysis that computes tainted paths in C programs and that doesn't require any program annotations. 'YERITH-SAINT' is built upon the iterative dataflow framework and has been implemented using the LLVM compiler infrastructure. 'YERITH-SAINT' is interprocedural, flow-sensitive, and developers can choose to run it either with context-sensitivity or without. THE HEARTBLEED bug (april 2014; security breach in open ssl 1.0.1f) IS A POTENTIAL FINDING OF yerith-saint.

22.22 YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE

ERP SOFTWARE SYSTEM 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum'

Mars 2015 – Currently

- Free open source code:
🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)

'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE) ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING SOFTWARE !

23.23 YERITH-ERP-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON

'YERITH-ERP-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON': AUTOMATED ALERT, AND DB-BACKUP SYSTEM FOR 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum'

Mars 2015 – Currently

- Free open source code:
🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

'YERITH-ERP-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE) AUTOMATED ALERT, AND DATABASE BACKUP SYSTEM FOR FOSS-ERP YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE !

24.24 YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF

'YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF': C++ Library FOR RUNTIME MONITORING (Safety Temporal Properties) FOR State Diagram MONITORING !

June 2022 – Currently

- Free open source code:
🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)

'YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE) C++ library, THAT ENABLES TO IMPLEMENT STATE DIAGRAM SAFETY TEMPORAL PROPERTY RUNTIME CHECKING (and/or VERIFICATION).

25.25 YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF

'YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF': RUNTIME VERIFICATION OF TEMPORAL SAFETY PROPERTIES IN 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE'

June 2022 – Currently

- Free open source code:
🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)
- YERITH-ERP-9.0 DOCTORAL COMPENDIUM:
<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>

'YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE), AND REUSABLE DYNAMIC RUNTIME ANALYSIS AND TESTING INFRASTRUCTURE created for FOSS ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING SOFTWARE 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE' !

26.26 [YRI_QVGE](#)

'YRI_QVGE': Design and Creation of Runtime SAFETY TEMPORAL PROPERTIES FOR State diagram MONITORING C++ Library
'YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF' !

2,500 Euros a single executable copy FOR DEBIAN-LINUX
June 2022 - Currently

27.27 [YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE](#): an enterprise (management / financial) Resource Planing Software

ERP SOFTWARE SYSTEM 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE: an enterprise (management / financial) Resource Planing Software'

PRICE DEPENDS ON installations ! (STARTS AT 200,000 XAF per node-computer; ONLY AVAILABLE FOR DEBIAN-LINUX)
Mars 2015 - Currently

(GRADUATE) STUDENTS ADVISING / COUNSELING

- 1.) ["AMIRHOSSEIN VAKILI"], Ph.D. (www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~avakili) (COMPUTER SCIENCE, DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA)
- 2.) ["DAVID DEMO NOUNDOU"], BACHELOR OF SCIENCE, INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY, TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF HAMBURG-HARBURG, HAMBURG, GERMANY
- 3.) ["DIVAM JAIN"], M.MATH (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/handle/10012/7943>) (COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2013
- 4.) [Dr "ERIC BREFO-MENSAH"], M.SC (Waterloo) (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/handle/10012/13341>) (CHEMISTRY, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2018
- 5.) [Dr "ESTHER ELIZABETH LAMBERT"], M.SC (Waterloo) (<https://ca.linkedin.com/in/esther-lambert-5b869414>) (GEOGRAPHY, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2009
- 6.) ["Basser (from Syria)"], MAsc (ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING, ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTRÉAL, QC, CANADA) 2008
- 7.) ["FABRICE tchoumi"], MAsc (ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING (AVIONICS), ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTRÉAL, QC, CANADA) 2007 – 2008
- 8.) ["FELIX FANG"], MAsc (<https://www.uwaterloo.ca/electrical-computer-engineering/profile/p23lam/papers/15.pppj.af-analysis.pdf>) (SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2014
- 9.) Dr. rer. nat. "HASHIM CHUNPIR" (<https://www.igi-global.com/affiliate/hashim-chunpir/324991>) (MSC, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2005 – 2006
- 10.) DR.-ING. DIPL.-INF. "SERGE ACHILLE FOPOUSSI NONO", (DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 11.) "DERRICK FIEDLER (born YAPI YAPO)", (DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 12.) "INES NGAKOU TEMOU", (BACHELOR OF SCIENCE, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 13.) "DAVID KAMGA ADAMO", (DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 14.) C++ MATRIX programming : "Dr. MOHAMED RIDHA MAHFOUDHI", MBA, PhD (Financial Engineering, University of Laval, QC, Canada). 08 / 2009
- 15.) "MARCELLIN TAALY" (<https://www.assiwo.com>), (DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY)
- 16.) "MATTHIAS (from Germany)", DIPLOM-INGENIEUR (FH); INFORMATIK-INGENIEUR, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- 17.) "Virginie kamche", DIPLOM-INFORMATIKERIN; COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- 18.) "MAÏMOUNA BAMBA" (from COTE-D'IVOIRE), DIPLOM-INFORMATIKERIN; COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- 19.) ["Dr. Vajih MONTAGHAMI, Ph.D."] (Ph.D. (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/>)) (SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA)
- 20.) ["JON EYOLFSON", Ph.D.] (M.ASc. / Ph.D. (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/handle/10012/6206>)) (SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA)
- 21.) "THÉOPHILE TCHIENCHO", DIPLOM-INGENIEUR (FH), INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY, UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES, BREMEN, GERMANY

FAMILY THAT I DON'T KNOW WHEREABOUT - I

1. SHANDA family as a destructive life for BOTH noumbissi, and NGONGANG and whereabouts families

"SHANDA Ndjatie Dorothee, and her spouse official TONME-shanda-JEAN-claude" are the 1st persons that started destruction of my life by coming into my family with so called psychiatrist, via WOLFGANG-owona.

"OWONA wolfgang" seemed to getting married with ANGELA which is a cousin maternal of mine because HE WANTS to sell my soul to AMERICAN USA societies in the sense that HE put myself into troubles via GOVERNMENTS AGENCIES, all of them Are linked to secret services to which he belongs, as I HAVE HEARD from ANGELA myself.

Frequently, HE idiot wife says he traveled to USA, so he would talk to people that want my OPEN SOURCE entrepreneurial adventures to be stopped; GET money from them, Then organize hijacking with following agencies:

- 1.) Social Services; so I AM NO MORE independent in the state of biya-regime;
- 2.) HOSPITAL like "laquintinie", etc.

Dr.-wolfgang, which is born from MINISTER owona-joseph-deceased, And mother as daughter of MINISTER owona-Gregoire has tried to put Rosicrucian organization AMORC into my life via Angela who proposed to me to join a so called "lectorium-rosicrucae" based at external relations ministry Where WOLFGANG attends with her.

2. WAAH (anne), spouse Kemmegni, is a subject of BIYA SPOUSE !!!

This 'megere' of my grand mother mother's side; Tchuitchui-ELIZABETH;

Is obviously a devilish demon that possesses super-natural powers in dark kingdoms; Based of 3 sacred objects I have last seen in her house in Byemassi-YDE.

1. "Buffle" horns as a representation of Money-laundry-BAPHOMET-satan
2. 2 turtles carapaces in the back of the "Buffle" horns.
3. 2 portraits of girls invoking and respectively crying;

3. "SANGO, spouse Bernadette Noundou" IS SOMEWHAT a suspect at origin of this family tragedy !!!

This pseudo-suspect seems to want to acquire my place at KING.

Laurent tchandeu ministry plenipotentiary is a subject of itself at Batchieu-Babouantou kings places.

Obviously, every member of GRAND-FATHER noundou nuclear family is a subject to this GUJA.

FAMILY THAT I DON'T KNOW WHEREABOUT - II

4. "Victor Koliou NOUNDOU" IS A NOBODY into my life;

THIS idiot, junior brother of my deceased late father "Théodore Noubissi" is contacting people INCLUDING "derek rayside (drayside@uwaterloo.ca)" (Already talking with other ignorant paternal unwanted uncle "Jules NTETA noundou (julesnteta@gmail.com; julesnteta@yahoo.fr)" from Cameroon external research criminal agency (DGRE));

The idiot Victor presents itself as a chief of a family where I am supposed to belong with some faked official documents from uncle politician LAURENT tchandeu-IDIOT.

OFFICIAL registered document that "Victor KOLIOU NOUNDOU" refused to give a copy to myself when I asked him about, since I am the only, according to documents written by my late grand-father Michel NOUNDOU, Legitimate SUPERVISOR OF HIS left over to children and descendants, WEALTH AND MATERIAL POSSESSIONS !

"Afriland first-bank" and "Intelligentsia employee "Jean-PAUL-yamtche"; And CEO currently as of April 2024", A person that I really don't really know whereabouts in his genealogy or affiliation to my late grand-father; "Jean-PAUL-yamtche" owns a big storey house just opposite face of our main common house entrance in Babouantou idiot village !

"Afriland first-bank" and Intelligentsia MAIN CREATOR AND INSPIRATORY person; "Dr. PAUL fokam-kammogne", was, according to sayings of my genitor Rose Sangnou, 1 of an intimate friend of my late father and genitor "Théodore NOUMBISSI" !

"LAURENT tchandeu and Rose Sangnou" went to a place of "CCEI-bank (former company name and source of AFRILAND FIRST-BANK)", according to "Rose Sangnou" told myself in person when I reached age 32; That they ("LAURENT Tchandeu my paternal uncle" and "Rose SANGNOU" my genitor) gave money (BRIBED) to an employee of "CCEI-BANK" where "late Théodore NOUMBISSI" owed "4 000 000 XAF" at his death so that *MORTGAGE ("hypothèque" in French) on his property-land in BONABERI-DLA (700 m²)* would be erased everywhere in computers and documents of former 'CCEI-bank' !

"LAURENT tchandeu and Rose Sangnou" also told me, after I had an employment interview with "Dr. PAUL fokam-kammogne"; that my later genitor and father "Théodore NOUMBISSI" is the one, together with "HUGUES NTOMANI TIAKO", his business partner and soul-mate at that former ancient time, THAT computerized totally all enterprises businesses of "CCEI-bank (former company name and source of AFRILAND FIRST-BANK)" !

I remember seeing my late father only 1 time in a day, around 19 : 00 at diner time; this is before we moved to Yaounde in year 1990; After he quits "CA-CORP (Computer Associates Corporation)-DLA" to open and manage solely "CA-CORP (Computer Associates Corporation)-YDE" !

5. "LAURENT tchandeu (ltchandeu@yahoo.fr)" ASSASSINATES in an hospital "THEODORE noumbissi"; late father of mine on January 1992;

AS an orphan at age of 7.5 years old, I remember uncle paternal Laurent came into our biggest house in YDE-Essos to settle in the secondary apartment at the back of our house.

6. "LAURENT tchandeu" Tries with "Hugues Ntomani Tiako" "VIA judith ngaleu in Etobicoke (Toronto, Ontario, Canada)" to crash "my Toyota Corolla LE-2003" in December 2013

This sorcerer freemason ("Hugues Ntomani Tiako"), and Christian-so-called-ORTHODOX-catholic of Roma, acknowledges that IT SHALLN'T be that I gain cause in the court of justice process THAT I have against "LAQUINTINIE and SED", that sent 9 people, including "Christian Eyoum, MD, PsyD"; in February 2021 at night around 23 : 30, to hijack and attempts to kill myself.

SED sent myself 1 time in a CABANON Because they receive 15,000 FCFA from "Henri Bertrand Ngatchou and my genitor ROSE Sangnou", IN douala 2018.

"Galax Yves Landry Etoga" is personally, as a CPDM political party member, AND not as a SED authority implicated in trying to kill myself through psychiatry and / or any other means !

"Laurent Tchandeu (assassin of Ingrid's father and his elder brother in Babouantou-village)" is the one that connected "Ingrid TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI", born (geboren in German) TCHITCHUI NOUMBISSI; my uterine sister, to marry officially "THE IDIOT AND PSY-CHILD since age 12 CHANDRIAND TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI".

7. "LAURENT tchandeu" Deems and Dares OR-DONATES to squeeze my financial money income VIA genitor of mine "Rose SANGNOU" Since September 2023 until TODAY.

8. "***JULES NTETA NOUNDOU extremely dangerous person" is a consanguine brother (same father; another, still living mother, in same marriage) of "LAURENT tchandeu"; And his helper in almost everything dirty and / or clean here in CMR!

FAMILY THAT I DON'T KNOW WHEREABOUT - III

9. ("Derek Rayside drayside@uwaterloo.ca") pays money to MATHGENEALOGY.ORG project so that an equivalence to my "Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering degree from UWATERLOO", will be turned from PhD into the non-academic degree ABD; just 2 weeks after talking with "JULES NTETA NOUNDOU" at his dirty-office in "YDE-élig-essono"
10. "David demo noundou" tries to connect me to Laurent external security research agent "Jean-Daniel-tujilo-tchokote"; "VIA his natal village idiot babouantou friend Célestin puene (cpuene@cscmonavenir.ca)".
11. "David demo noundou" has written documents in Germany that I was mentally ill while staying 3 days in his rental apartment in September 2018.
12. "David demo noundou" is A student of myself at the TUHH; benjamin brother of my late father "THEODORE noumbissi"; since I could help him get an bachelor internship At "GEWETE GmbH", Where I was working while a student at Bremen University state.
13. "LAURENT tchandeu" was a "Minister Plenipotentiary of Cameroon Embassies in France, Belgium, etc. for around 30 years outside of Cameroon". Especially promoted sent outside Cameroon 1 year after assassinating his elder brother "THEODORE noumbissi".
14. "Henri Bertrand Ngatchou" tries to physically arrest and violates myself in front of at least 7 other people in his private residence of Bankepche-Bangou with no apparent reason other than humiliate myself.

"Henri Bertrand Ngatchou" vows a personal and individual cult to 'Shanda Owona Biya', especially as an appointed, not applied CPDM (RDPC) political party, vice-president in Bankepche-Bangou; with "Honorable Datouo Theodore" as his president.

15. "**RODRIGUE alain sienchié ngongang (sienchie@gmail.com)**", Ancient psychiatric patient in Düsseldorf-Germany Sends messages everywhere So I could again be hijacked into a Cabanon-cell FOR mad-ill-people; "Xavier Noumbissi Noundou" paid in total amount 2,000 Euros to help him get back "to his paternal family NGONGANG" in Deido-Dla-CMR !
16. "**Théodore Wandji Ngongang, And Aurélie Kamdoum Yano his spouse (takouengongang@yahoo.ca; ngongangtietie@yahoo.ca)**", ows myself around "1 500 EUROS" since year 2005 as he fled out from Germany to emigrates into "Montréal-Côtes-des-neiges" !
17. "**Idiot Angéla Tchamou Shanda Wolfgang Owona (krauserminrex@gmail.com)**", a maternal cousin of mine, tries to hijack myself in buses because She deems being a very important personality ("VIP") in front of myself.

"HER spouse Dr Wolfgang Junior Fernand Owona" was making her ("Angéla Tchamou Shanda Owona") come to myself and harassed me with: "Wolfgang wants to be president of the republic" !

This idiot of Wolfgang is the grandson mother side of "Grégoire Owona", who was implicated in the sudden death of his former colleague "Theodore Noumbissi (Late father of mine)".

"Grégoire Owona" is today inviting "my remaining genitor Rose SANGNOU" to his village houses in "Gomedzap-Center-Region-CMR"; so to think her How to destroy my life as a black and renowned scientist universally from the University of Waterloo; THIS in conjunction with former uni colleagues such as "Dr. PATRICK lam"; etc. "Grégoire Owona" -

For 2 days now (October 14, 2025.); my profile is down at MATHGENEALOGY.ORG project; And at same time I felt several people trying to hijack my person here in Cameroon because a certain "#PASTOR-landry ENTERS MY PERSONAL HOME WITH A WEAPON."

In cameroon, as I have heard from people in background, CRIMINAL-ASSASSIN FROM yves-galax-landry Wear name PASTOR.

Derek Rayside has put back a vietnamese idiot on my file at MATHGENEALOGY.ORG project so that I cannot be upwell in Cameroon.

My official university of waterloo graduate transcripts says:

"Program: Engineering Doctoral;

"PhD" Comprehensive Examination.

Status: Completed

Date Completed: 12/20/2011

In good english: "Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering ("PhD" in Electrical & Computer Engineering)".

In french language: Docteur-Ingénieur (Dr.-Ing.).

IT means I must also have *Ph.D.* exactly as My former room colleague Jon Eyolfson that is since 2022 an Assistant Professor in Teaching only at the University of Toronto, ON.

18. **"S2TBED main proprietor-ally A SO-called gangster-Simplice-KAMENI was seen 2 days ago here in a luxurious car by myself.**

"IMMEDIATELY, today, *"/Friday-Sep.-27th, & Saturday-Sep.-28th/*, both days in year 2024, I and neighborhood start again to experience energy supply disruption for more than 4 hours."

SIMPLICE KAMENI seems to be a cocaine dealer that works on laundering money through usage of wood processing & wood sale activities via intermediary White-racist-extremist—italian so-called "MARCO".

ALSO, I could experience certain "neggers" working there from far-north cameroun coming along my foot way to dance kind of like I am their aid.

KAMENI simplice is also implicated in financing together with my cousin culprit-theodore-MOISE-tebiwo-yamkam my properties entirely in Cameroon; Starting year 2013 when TEBIWO-yamkam-moise traveled to Canada.

BOTH moise-yamkam-tebiwo, and SIMPLICE-kameni-ebacka; are sleeping in so-called orgy-sexist-FRANCK-biya gay personal property estate here in YAOUNDE.

19. **"HONORÉ WUCHE, a genitor of mine Spouse; ", EVENTHOUGH her cousin uterin, as hijacker into my life.**

"THIS honore-wouche has been calling me on my phone cell while I was a doctor of Engineering working on my doctoral Ph.D. degree in year 2013; GIVEN TO HIM BY ROSE sangnou."

HONORÉ WUCHE has lost already at least two wives he got kids with them as a guja.

HIS uterine cousin "Rodrigue Alain NGONGANG SIENCHIE", that tried to break my neck last August 2024 while I was attending home for 4 weeks and visiting faked "church Chapelle De la GLOIRE-DE-CHRIST by FAKED-devilish-racist-bassa pastor-so-called MARK-DJENG-DJENG";

Said to myself in front of honore-wouche that: 'SEND "xavier-noundou-ph.d." Again to MAD-person cell at "laquintinie" AS you did twice at least; I didn't even knew who was this gay-honore-wouche with black tattooed wrist-arm-bracelet for gangster and riders.

IT seems this cousin of my mother-genitor; together with another man-lady-cousin-uterine so called NANA; are working on molesting myself in life here in Cameroon; HE-honore-wouche told me laughing that 1 of his daughter was working in south-cameroon in farming for PAUL-biya-family.

20. **"Bulu-Sud-East-Akan tribe AS stealer in CMR"**

- *Year 1983 was changed into year 1985-(~~ingrid-teuntchou-noumbissi~~ birth year) so to allow later on a hijack of my property via a marriage to a uterine sister; Called "INGRID-teuntchou-noumeni", Born-geboren "Ingrid-tchitchui-noumbissi";*

[TEUNTCHOU-isaac & JOSUE-nkwouano; & RICHARD-mfeugwang agreed on a dinner time of my passing away with all means via a psychiatric injection treatment by LAQUINTINIE-hospital;]

[LAURENT-tchandeu could then secure a prosperous career after the killing & hijacking of money of his blood-brother Théodore-noumbissi-rosicrucian-rotarian !]

- *"BULU-biya" tribe in CMR-c.p.d.m-r.d.pc are trying to hijack any wealth of Well-to-do rich cameroonian so to secure presidential leadership for ever.*
- *Bulu notary-justice attorney ["MENYE-Ondo Xavier-FRANCOIS"] & "LIMA-rose (at time in 2012, 2013 years)" change effectively & voluntarily year of birth of mine in my [LAND-title certificate of MFOUNDI-VI.]*

- *GENOCIDE of West originating people started in CMR*

"MARIE-commissary-of-DEA-05ème-arrondissement-od-City-DOUALA, in Littoral region, sent 8 burglars on street to arrest myself while I was relating to CMRnian that BIYA regime has tried to spoliolate all my belonging via TEUNTCHOU-isaac."

"INGRID-teuntchou couldn't say no to this fake-marriage only to destroy my life as a super engineer and scientist originating from WEST-cmr."

"[TEUNTCHOU-isaac] used since she was aged 15 years old while I went outside of CMR to study in GERMANY-racist-culprit; NGATCHOU-henri-bertrand, a maternal uncle of myself & Ingrid to beat her & accustomate her to perform only what was told to her via JOSUE-nkwouano, senior brother of NGATCHOU-henri ! "

- *2025, AVRIL --18--"DLA-ndokoti-palace seems to be for now out of service due to atrocities that I have related internationally via web-site "zenodo.org" ! " (<https://www.zenodo.org>)*

"ATANGA NJI idiot minister; Cannot prepare elections without asserting NON-Sence propaganda to Cameroon people."

- *Laurent-fainéant TCHANDEU, a paternal vernacular uncle of mine seems to be an ally of people in Zürich working in Avionics !*

TCHANDEU, TCHINGWA, KOLIOU, and HAKOUA seems to be working for whittle racist supremacists in other to destroy any afrique-intelligentsia out of a psychiatric cyclops and / or poverty; So no black intelligent person wouldn't gain his money out of independent intellectual work; & intellectual property.

TCHANDEU, the lead, a so called diplomat, Hires only personal people from his own blood family against scientists & engineers here in Cameroon in particular.

[Koliou, TEUNTCHOU have been associated together in their rosicrucian association de destroy my financial life as I COULD observed since February 2021 when TEUNTCHOU tried to kill me.]

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (1.)

28.28 HIJACK OF MY PRIVATELY OWNED PROPERTY BY laquintinie on FEBRUARY 2021

[r-DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM – tALKING AT *BBC-british-broadcast-corporation* (<https://>), AND *+--rotarian--+* club member in douala-sawa-tribe, chief of psy staff of LAQUINTINIE HOSPITAL IN DOUALA (LITTORAL REGION, CAMEROON)], has sent in FEB. 2021, without any official document, 7 people to break into my privately owned (closed with a steel gate) house in DOUALA, so to hijack myself and terrorize me. THIS HAPPENED AT NIGHT AROUND 11:00 PM, with BERTRAND, breaking my gate seals with a weapon of some sort (BERTRAND, was the lead thief of DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM).

THIS HIJACK OR ATTACK on my person happened just 1 day after I denounced to PRC.CM and SHANDY-SHANDY-CABINET.COM (biological father of my mother's side cousin ANGELA) a fake "BACCALAUÉAT"-DEGREE from 'ANGELA TCHAMOU SHANDA OWONA SPOUSE DR. WOLFGANG FERNAND JR. OWONA', because her sister-cousin CYNTHIA NKWOUANO told me about this: "ANGELA WENT TO CENTRAL AFRICAN REPUBLIC and received her diploma in a hotel".

I ALSO BECAME AN AGENT OF CAMEROONIAN DEFENSE AND SECURITY FORCES ON FEBRUARY 14, 2021.

DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM after this kidnapping, held me at LAQUINTINIE HOSPITAL for poisoning me 2 weeks, AND THEN RELEASED AN OFFICIAL DOCUMENT TO MY RELATIVE ROSE SANGNOU.

ROSE SANGNOU has since been using the fake document to go meet my clients to say that I AM A PSY PATIENT AND THAT THEY SHALL NOT DEAL ANYTHING WITH MYSELF. ROSE SANGNOU also went to meet all my privately-owned real estate properties' neighbors TO DO THE SAME.

I HAVE COMPLAINT BEFORE DOUALA-NDOKOTI JURISDICTIONAL TRIBUNAL in front of JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA SINCE FEB. 2021:

- 3 convocations have been sent by now to DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM; he hasn't come to respond to prosecutors.
- I am now awaiting for a "MANDAT D'EMMENER" AGAINST DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM, a form of order from judge that will bring DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM in front of prosecutors by police force.

29.29 Kidnapping on FEB. 2023 WHILE WALKING BACK IN MY YAOUNDÉ REAL ESTATE PROPERTY

1. DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI accepts to send 2 thugs-burglars on the road to kidnap myself, while I was walking on street to get back into my house, and to bring me in a cab at psychiatric hospital 'JAMOT' in YAOUNDÉ; this is requested by DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA, spouse pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude.

DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI is chief of psychiatry staff at psychiatric hospital 'JAMOT' in YAOUNDÉ.

DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI IS VERY WELL KNOWN IN YAOUNDÉ to say disturbing voices against BAMILEKE-TRIBE, an ethnic group of the west cameroon to which, I by birth, and not by spirit [I AM A BORN AGAIN CHRISTIAN], belong.

2. AFTER 2 WEEKS OF POISONING AND TRYING TO DESTROY MY BODY WITH DRUGS AND PILLS, a yellow clothed (level of BACHELOR OF SCIENCE) gate guard OF "HÔPITAL JAMOT" that I don't remember the name, tries to SNEAK INTO my private life by calling me on my private cell phone number [(+237) 6 52 39 69 50] every other day.

I SAID TO HIM THAT I DON'T ENTERTAIN RELATIONSHIPS WITH PEOPLE LIKE HIM.

PS: THIS GATE GUARD, yellow-clothed with an uniform, is of BETI-TRIBE like DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI!

3. S2TBED, a so-called forestry society here in Yaoundé seems to be a secret agency against black-owned societies here in Cameroon.

30.30 Attempt to give me a psy consultation by ROSE SANGNOU's sister DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM

AFTER RELEASED FROM 'JAMOT', i stop taking the drugs that i was forced to intake by drink.

Knowing that this is judicial information time, I accept to talk to DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM, which is DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA and ROSE SANGNOU sister, by my own request.

My goal is at time to collect as much information as possible.

She (DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM) tries to convince me that i should intake psy drugs in order to be more sociable !

31.31 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY ROSE SANGNOU IN JUNE 2023

In June 2023, in its 25th week, a relative, ROSE SANGNOU, living and based in Douala for more than 60 years, comes into Yaoundé, and settle for 1 week at DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA's house, at her (DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA) invite.

ROSE SANGNOU, whom was told, no more to persecute myself, during her interrogation time at prosecutors' office in Douala-Ndokoti, starts calling me increasingly and says she is in Yaoundé because her sister (DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA) son, PATRICE SHANDA SANOU CABRAL, is very ill and hospitalized at Yaoundé general hospital.

ROSE SANGNOU insists that we shall meet because she is my mother. I then accept, but refused to meet up her at my private owned property in Yaoundé-Ahala-Nsimbock. We then meet up first at DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA house, then at supermarket 'supermarché carrefour EKIE' in YAOUNDÉ-ÉKIE.

THIS PERIOD IS judicial information investigation time, that is mostly why I accepted to meet up with her.

I NOTICE with an impression THAT my mother ROSE SANGNOU COULD HAVE BEEN BRUTALIZED ON HER LEFT KNEE. SHE SAID SHE FELT DOWN IN THE BACK OF HER SISTER'S HOUSE (DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA) because the maid woman SPILLED water with amidon on the floor.

AFTER FINISHING our lunch, my mother ROSE SANGNOU says I SHOULD START AGAIN TO TAKE psychiatric drugs: I IMMEDIATELY STAND UP FROM LUNCH TABLE AND RETURNS TO MY PRIVATELY OWNED PROPERTY, 'immeuble yerith'.

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (2.)

32.32 MY SUSPICIONS about real activities of pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude and his wife

SEVERAL TIMES, pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude invited myself to hotel PARFAIT GARDEN in yaoundé so that I COULD SEE HIM ACTING as managing director of expatriate US CITIZEN ELECTRICAL ENERGY COMPANY.

so i suspect pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude receives money from some big giants NORTH-AMERICAN COMPANIES, so to disrupt my activities in the free open source software (FOSS) AREA.

33.33 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY Victor Koliou Noundou IN JULY 2023

PREVIOUSLY. HÔPITAL ADLUCÉM, a hospital in Douala-BONAMOISSADI, that I went with paternal uncle Victor Koliou Noundou to threat a hyperglycemia, established with him (uncle Victor Koliou Noundou) THAT I SHOULD BE BROUGHT USING AN AMBULANCE to 'LAQUINITIE-CABANON' because Dr. MVONDO felt that I am not well behaving !

Victor Koliou Noundou, a brother of my late father Théodore Noumbissi ASKED MYSELF, relentlessly, if I still take the psychiatric drugs.

I need to note here that, WITHOUT ANY APPARENT REASON, another brother of my late father Théodore Noumbissi, Laurent Tchandeu, former minister plenipotentiary, sent A TRUCK WITH 6 firefighters to take me by force from my privately rented apartment in yaoundé, in the year 2015, SO TO BRING ME TO A PSYCHIATRIST OF 'JAMOT': Dr. Kamga.

IN FRONT OF ME, Dr. Kamga SAYS TO Laurent Tchandeu AND ROSE SANGNOU THAT HE CAN'T KEEP ME THERE AT 'JAMOT' BECAUSE I AM NOT A PSYCHIATRIC DISEASED PERSON.

Dr. Kamga ALSO MENTIONS THAT IF I GO TO COURT AGAINST HIM, HE WOULD PUT ALL TROUBLES on ROSE SANGNOU since WHAT SHE SAID TO HIM SO THAT HE SENT A FIREFIGHTER TRUCK to take myself by force from my privately rented apartment is wrong.

Laurent Tchandeu IS TRYING SINCE Théodore Noumbissi, my deceased (JANUARY 9, 1992) father (and chief of the NOUNDOU family), passed away, to sack my POSITION AS CHIEF OF THE FAMILY NOUNDOU:

- IN MAY 2023, politician GRÉGOIRE OWONA, grand-father of MY COUSIN MOTHER SIDE "ANGELA TCHAMOU SHANDA OWONA SPOUSE DR. WOLFGANG FERNAND JR. OWONA", comes with Laurent Tchandeu (and spouse DR. HENRIETTE POLA) in my village BABOUANTOU to open a primary school as gift from political party R.D.P.C (C.P.D.M).

34.34 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY Laurent Tchandeu ON AUGUST 3rd, 2023

DR. Laurent Tchandeu, a paternal uncle of mine, tries to harass myself with taking psychiatric drugs.

HE DID THIS USING TELEPHONY APPLICATION "whatsapp".

35.35 WAITING FOR judge JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA

JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA SEEMS TO WANT TO destroy evidences against state hospital laquintinie since He (JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA) hasn't call by police force DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM to come answer allegations against him about TRYING TO KILL ME with psychiatric drugs at night after HIJACKING MY PRIVATE PROPERTY IN DOUALA-CITÉ-DES-PALMIERS !

36.36 ARMY GENDARMERIE COLONEL KÉMAJOU harasses ROSE sangnou my mother

ROSE SANGNOU, my mother, complained to myself that KÉMAJOU is calling her very frequently to tell her I (PROF. DR.-ING. DIPL.-INF. XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU) is not mentally sane since HE is doing a lot of christian cross-sign while walking on Yaoundé streets.

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (3.)

37.37 ARMY GENDARMERIE COLONEL KÉMAJOU destroying my life as a neighbor

A FORMER SED (SÉCRÉTARIAT D'ÉTAT À LA GENDARMERIE) retired colonel of cameroon gendarmerie, who has spying devices AT HOME TO HEAR PHONE, OR WHATSAPP conversations; MAKES CURRENT ELECTRICITY cut-off whenever I RECEIVE MONEY so I cannot cook and refrigerate my food properly.

THIS VERY POOR PERSON, both in spirit and financially; whose wife makes money out of cooking food for street workers, COULD SUCCESSFULLY intimidate people not to come attend work or anything else into my real estate properties.

COLONEL (retired) of Army Gendarmerie KÉMAJOU couldn't lie and convince people that I DON'T POSSESS A Ph.D in Computer Engineering; since his son "Jonas Kémajou" who he also in gendarmerie told me once: "Myself I also POSSESS A Ph.D QUALIFICATION WITH NO DEGREE AT HOME" !

I am wondering in Cameroon why army intermediates in civilian life and affairs; THIS DOESN'T HAPPEN usually in rich and developed countries like Germany.

This day of **Saturday November 18, 2023**; while I was talking to a computer technician neighbor named Gabriel Takoumbe, KÉMAJOU came along walking with an indigo "Garde Présidentielle (special unit of cameroon forces attached only for the President of The Republic.)" T-shirt.

COLONEL kemajou tells me HE WANTS MY PERSON NOT TO WRITE anymore on his forfeitures against myself; in front of at least 7 young men and women, saying He didn't call my genitor mother any day before.

COLONEL kemajou sect named JÉRUSALEM APOSTOLAT, sacks every public entry road to my real estate 2-storey building (unfinished yet).

Yves Landry Galax ETOGA, chief of secret services of Cameroon seems to like to try harassing competent professors of science and technology like myself. May be He works against CAMEROONIAN SKILLED ORPHANS like my humble person in JEOVAH-NISSI in heaven !

PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA and DR. PATRICK LAM have never said anything against what is happening to myself since 3 years ago; ALSO, Patrick is a member of Rotarian organization ROSICRUCIARY !

"29" November 2023: I HAVE RENOUNCED TO AN ATTORNEY since TCHANA NJEUTCHA Synclaire is clearly going against my personal interests !

"03" December 2023: KEMAJOU and its troops that call themselves Christians ARE HARASSING PEOPLE COMING HOME.

"04" December 2023: I cannot recognized Cameroon where someone high qualified by myself is permanently harassed physically by illegal neighbors like KEMAJOU gendarmerie colonel Criminal.

KEMAJOU gendarmerie colonel tries on the street to talk to myself while I am coming back from a hardware shop.

It seems to myself that illegal neighbors religious sect "Jerusalem Apostolat" is trying to make confusion about my humble person wherever I go in my life; Kemajou gendarmerie colonel has tried around my neighborhood, with help of SECTARIAN OF JERUSALEM APOSTOLAT; to make noise that XAVIER noumbissi noundou IS A PSYCHIATRIC PATIENT that doesn't want to take pills !

38.38 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY ROSE SANGNOU IN JANUARY 2024

ROSE SANGNOU, despite that JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA gave her prohibition to come to my home in Yaounde during year 2023, came by force with someone that I don't know whereabouts To my neighbor "CARINE LELE njougep tchana" To incriminate her about chairs she owns by now;

I destroyed chairs that were not in good shape last year from my humble home by throwing them away outside. It seems "CARINE LELE njougep tchana" put them in her personal home without asking myself since I just threw them away; which is normal since They don't belonged to me anymore !

"30" January 2024: It seems my genitor mother ROSE SANGNOU went to talk to gendarmerie people so they could harass myself to go for an illegal psychiatric treatment; because while I was talking to Justice "ME. ANDRÉ Mbet" today, I saw 1 gendarmerie man came into his personal office where he also, with his wife, Owns a financial transaction center.

I immediately told Justice "ME. ANDRE Mbet" about this attitude of gendarmerie people coming inside where I perform businesses to make some kind of visual and gesture signs to owners of businesses, So they wouldn't deal with myself anymore !

"24, 25" April 2024: 1 man wearing a talkie-walkie came across my personal road in Simbock YDE.

I went to talk to him since I was looking for a technician that didn't finish a work in my humble house. For 6 days now, this technician wasn't in my house anymore despite myself telling him to finish his work on my steel door.

I suspect again justice ("huissier") SHANDA-DJATIE and her spouse Pr. JEAN-CLAUDE shanda-tonme to harass my genitor and mother Rose SANGNOU to try to bring myself by force to a psychiatric destructive mind place.

JERUSALEM-APOSTOLAT rosicrucian sect tried to follow myself these last 2 days using the brigand 'Moise BATOMEN', and another person male, THAT i don't know whereabouts but that live behind "Carine Lele Njougep Tchana" house for at least 6 months from now backwards in time !

Just 1 month before, I was stopped from walking by to our main official road by a sectarian female of Jerusalem-APOSTOLAT. I now see that it was meant to bring myself to other roads were they don't have their own people on it, so they could hijack myself properly to bring by force to a psychiatric hospital so to try to deteriorate my physical and psy body.

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (4.)

39.39 SHANDA SANOU patrice cabral idiot son of Dorothée Shanda Owona passes away at age 33 (March 18, 2024)

"Dorothée Shanda Owona" who had tried to make myself sodomized "by Bertrand of Laquintinie" in Feb. 2021, illegally by police force.

SHE leaves now her son out of life after 3.5 years trying to destroy my life; Probably because she got some laundry money for this dirty task against A BORN-AGAIN-CHRISTIAN !

NONE of the people I have heard from coming back "from some kind of obituary ceremony" could even see any corpse of ATTORNEY OF LAW, deceased, Patrick Cabral SHANDA SANOU !

40.40 Dr. Annie Metiam, Spouse Eric-POKAM-WAM tries to say something illegally about my mental health publicly (May 23, 2024)

A sister of my mother and genitor ROSE SANGNOU, DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM, sends a RECORDED AUDIO MESSAGE via whatsapp-phone-android-application, without any request from "Rose Sangnou" and / or my person about a supposed mental health abilities report that She as GASTROENTEROLOGIST has wrote based on our investigation whatsapp call that was done in year 2023 during around the month of JUNE.

This retarded personage that was initially at "Alfred Saker School" oriented to perform Commerce AND Accounting, WITH A grade of 10.00/20 is an idiot; Not just because *she doesn't even have a "degree of Doctor of Medicine (Dr. med.)"*.

This happens unsolicited as I am having a talk together with "Rose Sangnou"; AND "PASTOR marco OF Pentecostal Christian CHURCH" ' 'chapelle de la gloire de christ" in DLA.

I AM SUSPICIOUS of this corrupt C.P.D.M aunt that has german citizenship to be from Central Intelligence Agency (CIA); hired specially to try to kill me by any means; even using sorcery.

41.41 YAGER MABOMA is an idiot of justice judge here in CMR

Since 2021, February that I have complaint for a group of harassers that came into my compound to brutalize myself in front of a so called judge of instruction from sawa tribal tribe, I STILL RECEIVE PEOPLE TRYING TO AGGRESS and Harass myself.

42.42 I-xavier-went on roads to shout That I required JUSTICE for my saved life by SYNCLAIRE NJEUTCHA TCHANA

- o **Wednesday 28th of JUNE 2024:** "Proverbs 1 : 18 – 21 (in Holy bible of JEOVAH-NISSI in Heaven)"

Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA was sodomized both physically and mentally to release myself as a client, So I will go in front of a judge without the initial attorney I have chosen myself.

I went to road "in AHALA-simbock" to shout at populace that I MUST HAVE JUSTICE DONE against people who broke my gate in the night of FEBRUARY 2023 to kill me with psy-drugs involuntarily.

Politics is going on thoroughly because the year 2025 must released a president of the republic of cameroon !

43.43 YAGER MABOMA has sent my documents to Attorney-prosecutor

- o **SATURDAY 31th of AUGUST 2024:**

I hope I can finish this matter without a judge that has been sodomized by "BIYA-clique".

"Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA" said to myself on my cell phone that I sent to him at least 2 other attorneys of law so to replace him; Which is FALSE.

"Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA" has received money from PAUL-biya.

"Tchonang albertine" is now the person I asked for, for assistance."

"I received this name and contact from my friend and customer "HAPPINESS POTENTIAL SARL" based in Akwa-douala ! "

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (5.)

44.44 Police of AHALA – 19ème arrondissement harassing myself because of SHANDA-tonmeo **Friday 6th of September 2024:**

"NESTOR kenfack tries to talk to my genitor and adversary ROSE-Sangnou without asking anything to myself."

"ROSE-idiot sangnou went to give certain objects to "NESTOR and VALÉRIE kenfack" that are supposed to be my sole customers and friends; Without any intermingled relationship with ROSE-sangnou since I told both of them THAT I am not interested into talking with someone who has tried to kill myself."

"I KNOW that it is C.P.D.M that went to give money to these burglars ("NESTOR" & "VALÉRIE") so they will try to intervene against my interests when court justice comes AS this has been the case with my personal attorney of law the culprit "SYNCLAIRE NJEUTCHA TCHANA"."

45.45 CLOVIS kemmegne as intelligence service gendarmerie agent against my privacy lifeo **Saturday 10th of November 2024:**

"A culprit called CLOVIS kemmegne, an intelligence secret service agent of GENDARMERIE NATIONALE of CAMEROON is tring to put troubles into my life via false divulged information around my new business relationships with a new tenant that I could gained via a so called "RENTAL PROPERTY MANAGER"-EMMANUEL-idiot."

"NOW that i have been staying in douala for more than 4-days in a row since my last hijack-attempt, in a so-called inherited property of noumbissi-vilain-idiot THÉODORE; I can see that clovis kemmgne changed the colours GREEN-Yellow-gendarmerie of his GAY-young-porn-female-clairvoyant-boy-jackdaniels; INTO a BLUE-presidential-GRAY-porn-DGRE colors."

"INSTEAD of doing is openly called business of electronics computer technician, and also, "GAY-handler-bar-JACKS.", THIS guja-gay is hiding himself behind my sister and my mother-side family to plan a so-called "CONSTAT-de-FAIT" for the idiot of justice judge HUGUES-alain-yager maboma-faineant."

"THE other gay-called napoa-maxime-eteme; a viagra-gay that seems to be a burglar to myself since BAMKOUÏ said to me he didn't worked at all for SEMIL; BUT is working for CMR-navy in DOUALA; came openly salute myself, together with another idiot called KAMGAIN jean-pierre;"

"i hope only "jean-loïc siewe and belvianne" that seemed to be young fellow cameroonian entrepreneurs are not intermeddle here."

"i can already see that siewe's mother is from the idiot-village-Babouantou !."

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (VI (6).)

CLOVIS kemmegne as intelligence service gendarmerie agent against my privacy lifeo **Wednesday 13th of November 2024:**

"SIEWE and BELVIANNE his collaborator of my new rental property seem to be not able to accommodate well due to destructive actions in water plumbery that seemed to be have done by a previous renter called; AND from R.D.P.C-C.P.D.M-south-bulu-tribe: GERMAIN Blaise ndzie and his wife called Geneviève Ndzie."

" ~~Dr. —NOMO siméon-replacement~~ by C.P.D.M.-eyoump-psy; A so-called MAXIME-napoa-eteme called someone I am not sure "Docteur" while I was crossing a street at DLA-cité-des-palmiers yesterday evening; THIS gay-female-psy-hijackist; THAT seemed to be an organizer of my killing via the hijack of my private property in DLA-FEBRURAY-2024 is the one that talked to my 1st before a same day at night I was hijacked. "

" ~~MAXIME-napoa-eteme~~ the gay-female-idiot is also from BETI-ekang-amougou-beling-TRAIBAL-tribe as a previous renter called NDZIE geneviève. "

o **SUNDAY 17th of November 2024:**

"IT seems there are no repression against criminals that come officially against my personal and / or familiar interests in CMR. "

"FOR INSTANCE, a family from "BATIÉ-ouest-cmr" that bake "beignets" and that used to transport "Pouse-Pousse" has built a 'bidon-ville-taudis' directly closed to my compound, Where my late father dear THEODORE-idiot noumbissi built a ground foundation, Without any rejection from SOUS-Préfecture that I contacted using my Attorney at law Mr. JUSTICE (Maître Synclaire NJEUTCHA tchana)."

"Some folk around this place in Béedi told me that:

1. "A beauty-gay hair-cut society wearing black and /or rosa T-SHIRTS, based on the opposite side of road to CLOVIS-telecom-Alias-kemmgne-gendarmerie-nationale-CMR";

"Sent a hijacker wearing finger-female-paint to say to people around where I was sitting reading my Bible-holy; That I AM SAID to be a mad-person; "

"BEFORE this physical attack even though I WASN'T talking to that gendarme that seems to act as a gay-female-hair treater; I COULD see a woman from CHRISTIAN-eyoum-tribal-tribe called Assassin. "

2. "Clovis telecom Alias clovis kemmegne" has repeatedly summon several people to harass me with no fear since he is well connected with ETOO-fils, a burglar called in CMR Soccer-player-female-male-born-again-gay-hijackist-Christian-eyoum "
3. "Maxime NAPOA-eteme is the one who told this very strange family since they don't do anything apparently to survive in Douala other than sneaking other people properties; WHERE enforced by "NAPOA ETEME, MAXIME" to Hijack myself even physically because I AM A NOBODY IN THIS COUNTRY called CAMEROON. "
4. "i suspect the current president of the republic of CMR called PAUL-biya to be behind this multi-attempt to destroy my life; Since for all my legal complaints nothing could be done for at least more than 12 years. "
5. "paul-biya-junior is mad; a culprit from mvomekaa. "

o **WEDNESDAY 27th of November 2024:**

"This new renter of mine a so-called-CALLPRIT jean-loïc siewe, And BELVIANNE meleu nossi seem not to even welcome very nicely their clients because they left so dirty the entrance step-feet of their rented apartment for 138 EUROS monthly. "

"ALSO this belvianne aged of 25th years old seem not to understand that I AM NOT CONFIDENT of renewing their rental agreement because of all inconsistencies I COULD notice since they entered this apartment inherited of mine:"

1. Her national identity card says she is "SCHOOL student of IUT-douala".

THERE was a so-called "gendarme-etoga-idiot" call Jonas-Kemajou-fainénat that scammed myself around 3 000 EUROS, And that was wearing a gendarme-green-attire, And that also has this "SCHOOL student of IUT-douala" instead of something professional-criminal-armed-robber-south-west-CMR.

SCIENTIFIC PRESENTATION TALKS 1

- 1.) *STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION FOR REACTIVE SYSTEMS, MASTER'S DEGREE THESIS DEFENSE TALK, DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS AND COMPUTER SCIENCE (FB 3), UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY* |★| *MAY "2007"*
- 2.) *STATICALLY VERIFYING API USAGE RULES USING TRACEMATCHES, 9th Workshop on Compiler-Driven Performance, CASCON 2010, Hilton Suites Toronto/Markham Conference Centre, MARKHAM, ONTARIO, CANADA (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>)* |★| *NOVEMBER "2010"*
- 3.) *TEMPORAL PROPERTY VERIFICATION IN PLUGIN-based SOFTWARE, PH.D. THESIS EXAMINATION COMPREHENSIVE !, DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>)* |★| *DECEMBER "2011"*
- 4.) *Course project small talk-presentation in front of PATRICK-lam-idiot & course ECE 750 students, 1 EIT room I don't remember code room number digits, DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA* *Spring "2013"*
- 5.) *(prepared based on result outcome of talk given during Spring 2013 for course project.); CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAIN T ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM, ECE GRAD TALK, DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA* *April "2014"*
- 6.) *CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAIN T ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM, PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES SEMINAR, DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA* *JANUARY "2015"*
- 7.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; sns cameroon ltd (Mr. DIVINE Njobati); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON* *JANUARY "2016"*
- 8.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; best car care & services (Mr. HENRI ngatchou); DOUALA; LITTORAL; CAMEROON* *JANUARY "2016"*
- 9.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; snob bazar outlet stores (Mr. LAVOISIER); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON* *MAY "2016"*
- 10.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; expert3dev s.a.r.l (Mr. Momo); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON* *JUNE "2016"*
- 11.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; bilingual entente bookshop (Mr. JACQUES); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON* *JANUARY "2017"*
- 12.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; BLACK & WHITE snack bars (Mr. TOM & Mr. AURÉLIEN iloga iloga (ecobank poste centrale yaoundé)); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON* *JUNE "2017"*
- 13.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for COMPUTER INFORMATICS ENGINEERING TRAINING; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; IUC [Institut Universitaire de la Côte] (Mr. HYPOLITHE Tekeu); DOUALA; LITTORAL; CAMEROON* *SEPTEMBER "2017"*
- 14.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS TALKS; Dr. SANDY beidu; Dr. ERIC brefo-mensah; WATERLOO; ON; CANADA* *JUNE "2018"*
- 15.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for CROWD FUNDING REQUEST PROPOSAL; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION (for "MS WINDOWS"); BAFIASOFT (Mr. CHRISTIAN rikong ngueyong); WATERLOO; ON; CANADA* *SEPTEMBER "2018"*
- 16.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; coplatec s.a.r.l (Mr. CONSTANT Kemmogne); DOUALA; LITTORAL; CAMEROON* *MAY "2020"*
- 17.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce and drugstore selling; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; pharmacy fiango lycée MAKÉPÉ (Dr. PETER Akume Ngoe); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON* *JANUARY "2021"*
- 20.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce and INDUSTRIAL logistics; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; bontée s.a.r.l (Ms. ARLETTE [Sibeufo-mpay-army-general-spouse-in-official]); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON* *FEBRUARY "2021"*
- 21.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce and PRODUCTION planing; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; CROQUE-MATIN (Mr. MOUSSA Saliou); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON* *MARCH "2021"*
- 22.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL ("MS WINDOWS 2000"); elektro maképé (Mr. ARMSTRONG); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON* *JUNE "2021"*
- 23.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; établissement kenfack (Mr. KENFACK); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON* *JULY "2021"*
- 24.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; clinique de l'espérance (Mr. YVES Mogo); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON* *SEPTEMBER "2021"*
- 25.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; pctb s.a.r.l (Dr. AIMÉE FRANCIS Ngadjou Tchana); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON* *OCTOBER "2021"*
- 26.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; quincaillerie la confiance (Mr. AIMÉE); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON* *NOVEMBER "2021"*

SCIENTIFIC PRESENTATION TALKS 2

- 27.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; quincaillerie n.k. (Mr. NESTOR Kenfack); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON **NOVEMBER "2021"**
- 28.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; happiness potential s.a.r.l (Mr. FABRICE Siemeni); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON **JANUARY "2022"**
- 29.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; pctb s.a.r.l (Dr. AIMÉE FRANCIS Ngadjou Tchana); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON **JANUARY "2022"**
- 30.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; AND networked installations; quincaillerie aimée (Mr. AIMÉE); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON **JUNE "2022"**
- 31.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; AND commercial financial accounting; poissonnerie plus (Mr. NESTOR Kenfack); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON **SEPTEMBER "2022"**
- 32.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0 BRIEF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL PRESENTATION; ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE YAOUNDÉ - ENSPY (PROF. DR.-ENG. THOMAS NDIÉ DJOTIO); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON* **May "2023"**
- 33.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-SERVER TRAINING; happiness potential sarl (DIPL.-ING. (FH) DR. FABRICE WILFRIED SIEMENI, M.Sc); Douala; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON **August "2023"**
- 34.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-SERVER financial accounting SHORT PRESENTATION VIEW DEMONSTRATION; quincaillerie aimée sarl (Ms. CHRISTELLE spouse NAMEKONG, B.SC.); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON **December "2023"**
- 35.) YERITH-ERP-9.0 VERY SHORT INFORMATION SESSION; happiness potential s.a.r.l (Mrs. Hecna Ngayam) ; Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON **May "2024"**
- 36.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-FOSS SHORT INFORMATION SESSION FOR COMMERCE; Mr. Hilaire Yimdjo, B.Sc. in Computer Science (entrepreneur in car care and management); Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON **May "2024"**
- 37.) YERITH-ERP-9.0 SHORT INFORMATION SESSION FOR COMMERCE; Mr. Nestor Kenfack (entrepreneur in hardware shop and grocery store); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON **June 12, "2024"**
- 38.) YERITH-ERP-9.0 Installation hardware checks; Mr. Nestor Kenfack (entrepreneur in grocery store); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON **June 13, "2024"**
- 39.) Aborted installation & training of family association "MA-sangnou-idiot-bangou"; Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON. **March "2025"**
- 40.) **Presentation & Questions & Answers (Q&A) with a young entrepreneur-woman-lady from Douala-sawa tribe; Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON.** **March, "2025"**
Based on our remarks to this lady of very low class revenue, we could find that we may add an option for "automatically recalculating cost-price of acquisition."
WE see here an opportunity to examine how to improve quality & revenue of this low-class entrepreneurial adventure !
THIS kind of entrepreneurial organization is very pro-eminent in Douala-sawa tribe as customers come into living-house to buy. !
- 41.) **YERITH-ERP-9.0 design introspective view talk accompanied with Q&A (Questions & Answers) by management consultant IRIS mbieukop; [M.-Iris-mbieukop] is an expert using MS-excel & PowerBI (BUSINESS intelligence).** **April, "2025"**
VERY impressive questions that could make our start-up "YERITH R&D" [improve YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum in terms of Ergonomics (color management)], and / or functionality; Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON
 ► **June 11, 2025 :**
[This guja seems to be an EYOUM because he was looking quite strange while I just great him yesterday night while entering DLA.] Kind-of son of a guja call PAUL-fokam-kemmogne—ifiot.
- 42.) **[YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum short introduction]; MBA-Claude BISSEG (bisseg@yahoo.fr); Very interesting introspective towards reconfiguring pricing options !**
Very similar to Microsoft Dynamics & Sales Forces software. MBA-Claude BISSEG seems to want trying this as a rental software monthly around "20, 000 Francs CFA monthly". **May 12, "2025"**
HIS father, M. BISSEG is a very well respected member of Lions-Club Douala, TOGETHER for instance with Dr.-criminal GWET-bell !
Attorney of JUSTICE-congolaise-brazzaville Vicent GOMEX & President-Congolaise Sassou are also members of Lions-Club-INTERNATIONL-criminal !
- 43.) **Presentation & Questions & Answers (Q&A) with a young entrepreneur named ROSTAND-moungam. Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON.** **June 2, "2025"**
ROSTAND is a startuper that uses Programming language "DART" and also website builder application "flutter flow" to give maximal power to its clients that are in need of a webshop !"
ROSTAND is at time skeptical in trying YERITH R&D product YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum because it seems to him not very simple to implement according to his web presence requirements !"

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— RESEARCHING GOALS IN "DISTRIBUTED & OPERATING COMPUTING SYSTEM" (CONSTRUCTION & ANALYSIS & VERIFICATION & VALIDATION) —

- Create technology for easing life in Africa • Make human-being life easier and cheaper •

Research KEYwords : Yerith-Xavier-NOUNDOU ✓ ([2025]-YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0); [2022]-SDMM; YRI_QVGE; YERITH-SAINT; [2006]-(Peleska. Yerith et al.); [2022]-KLAUS HAVELUND (LogSCOPE); [2017]-Frank-TIP-Koushik-SEN (EVENTRACECOMMANDER); [2007]-"Hendren, et al". (tracematches, S00T); THOMAS-reps (IFDS; IDE); [1977]-Gary-KILDALL ✓ (static code lattice-based "dataflow analysis"-seminal); [1977]-Patrick & Radia-COUSOT (Abstract INTERPRETATION);

Figure 36: 🇳🇬 "Portrait of YERITH-NISSI. now 42 years old."

DOCTOR-Ph.D. of Engineering (DR.-ING. / PH.D.) in Electrical & Computer Engineering; UNIVERSITY of waterloo-mutilative; '12/20/2011' !

★ — ★ DOCTOR-PH.D. of 🇳🇬 Engineering (DR.-ING. [21]) ★ — ★

Integrated Bachelor's & Master's degree ("B.Sc & M.Sc." / Dipl.-Inf.). UNIVERSITY-racist of BREMEN.; '05/25/2007'. — Diplom-INFORMATIKER 🇩🇪 (Dipl.-Inf. [?]) —

46.46 Professor-professional Computing Scientific Association Memberships

- Current: "acm: The Association for Computing Machinery"; "FME: Formal Methods Europe"; "ASQ: American Society for Quality".

47.47 Hardware Products

- ★ "Portable Computer for on-the-fly runtime verification monitoring" : YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>).

48.48 Software (System) Products ("Progiciels en langue Française")

- ★ "WYSIWYG Web Designer Generated Tool : YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL" ([HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORD/YRITOENTERLATERON](https://www.zenodo.org/record/YRITOENTERLATERON))[?].
- "Runtime MONITORING tester verifier" : YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b].
- "Computer-Aided Software Engineering (CASE) Design Tool for creating SDMM" : YRI_QVGE (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) [1d].
- "An Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) & Stock-live trading platform; ALL-in-one" : YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM (https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-9-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf).

49.49 Research Impact.

Table 13: Impact of 'Research & Technologies' [Created at YERITH R&D]

N°	RESULT	EXPERTISE DOMAIN	SINCE / YEAR	ORIGINALITY & PARTICULARITY	CERTIFICATION AND / OR REFERENCE
1.	ERP – PGI introduction because of creation & proof-tested YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.	Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) — Business Machinery	YEAR-2025	Insertion of a placebo ERP-PGI software system by R.D.P.C-C.PDM-biya-in-year-2025	N.A
2.	★ Secured Web-browser architecture only 2-tiers layers .	Web Apps Automatic Generation	YEAR-2025	1 st 2 layers web-browser based software architecture with security proof code backed and secure via model-checking runtime verification monitoring !	N.A
3.	★ Hardware YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET.	Dynamic Program Binary Analysis Verification	YEAR-2024	1 st open-sourced runtime verification on-the-fly; Also as Hot plug-in device embedded	CE
4.	★ Software YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL Software YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0	Web Apps Automatic Generation	YEAR-2024	"1.) WYSIWYG-Tool for HTML pages." 2.) HIGH-level view imperative Programming language for HTML pages dynamic; 3.) Automatic generation of safe & secure web sources files	N.A
5.	Software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM	Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) — Business Machinery	YEAR-2015	1 st Simpler to use ERP (Enterprise Resource Planing). Starting age 12 years old.	N.A and / or O.H.A.D.A (not required at all)
6.	🇳🇬 A C++ Functional Library for Specifying "SDMM" (State Diagram Mealy Machine).	Compiler Technology	YEAR-2022	1.) 1 st fully compliant to "David-harel statechart"-mealy machine" STATE DIAGRAM formalization for runtime monitoring verification & automatic model-based statchart-code-generation; 2.) Checks for forbidden trace specification across software system with no additional runtime overhead as demonstrated by concurrent event stream analysis technique	N.A

RESEARCH IMPACT — CONTINUED

Table 14: *Impact of 'Research & Technologies' [Created at YERITH R&D] — Continued.*

N°	RESULT	EXPERTISE DOMAIN	SINCE / YEAR	ORIGINALITY & PARTICULARITY	CERTIFICATION AND / OR REFERENCE
7.	Software YRI_QVGE	CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) Tool	YEAR-2022	1 st CASE-Tool for designing by drawing state diagram mealy machine (SDMM); 2.) 1 st model checker at runtime that encompasses Mealy-machine as opposed And not KRIPKE-structure !	N.A and / or CE (not required at all)
8.	Software YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	Dynamic Program Binary Analysis Verification	YEAR-2022	1 st open code sourced Runtime MONITOR container (generator) software for "SDMM"	N.A and / or CE (not required at all)
9.	Program YERITH-SAINT	Compiler Technology	YEAR-2013	1 st temporal property verification by (staged-alias analysis) static taint analysis framework-algorithm in LLVM	N.A
10.	Algorithms not published in any journal And / Or conference due to missing financial funding.	Theoretical Computer Science	YEAR-2015	Various algorithms for creating working User-QT software easily	N.A
11.	[UWATERLOO-SE 465-ECE 453] — Text-tutorial "JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL".	Unit Testing	YEAR-2009	Pragmatic Junit 4 Tutorial aided with "Cobertura Test Coverage Analyzer"	N.A
12.	Software "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (N.A).	Static Program Code Analysis Checking	YEAR-2013	Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints.	N.A
13.	Software YERITH-XRESIN-SOFTWARE.	Web Apps Program Analysis	YEAR-2013	A dynamic taint analysis software for Security for PHP in a JAVA PHP Interpreter.	N.A
14.	Taxonomy of Program-Software Verification & Analysis.	Software Verification	YEAR-2023	Unique positioning and specification of PROGRAM-software Verification & Analysis.	N.A
15.	MASTER thesis – Statistical test cases generation for reactive systems (N.A).	Test Cases / Test Data — Generation	YEAR-2007	Statistical uniform distribution generation of test cases for statechart diagrams.	N.A and / or A.R.I.N.C
16.	Vordiplom-B.Sc. Independent Study: A Semantic Comparison between Timed Automata and Büchi Automata (N.A).	Theoretical Computer Science	YEAR-2004	A set of transformations from Büchi automata to Timed Automata.	N.A

- Our commitment to create software tools & programs for insuring a better and safe software system quality as both open-sourced and priced products, Enables now young immature software developers and engineers in under-developed Africa to have better products and quality at a low cost price : ["Software Products at YERITH R&D"]. TABLE 13, TABLE 14 illustrate sample products, both potential-in-preparation hardware, and already available (accompanying) software.

THIS statement previously made is also available for medium sized companies in west developed countries where even not far as for in year 2000, and also years before; CRASHES of aircraft "Ariane 5 occurred and other airplanes from Airbus and BOEING, causing lost of several human being lives.

- YOUNG adults aged around \approx 12 years old can now start learning using a full-featured ERP-trading stock exchange software that uses a very simplified everyday language as testified by our previous report of "Start-Up YERITH R&D" for years 2022 – 2023 : "REPORT ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0 (YEAR 2023) (<https://zenodo.org/records/13949884>)".

This couldn't be possible years before starting 2015 when I started creating YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM; Our previous assertion is corroborated by deployment of YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum at at least 5 locations in Yaounde & Douala, in main cities of Cameroun, which is the leader of central africa economic zone C.E.M.A.C (<https://www.cemac.int>).

50.50 Tools & Programming Language Expertise

- **Operating Systems:** MS Windows (XP, 98, 2000, 7, 10, 11), DEBIAN LINUX (8, 9, 10, 11, 12)
- **SCM (Source Code Version Management Tools):** Git, Mercurial (hg), SVN, Rational ClearCase
- **Web Technologies:** MariaDB, HTML5, CSS, PHP, Quercus, Apache Tomcat, GWT (Google Web Toolkit), JSP
- **Scripting Languages:** Cygwin, Python, sed, AWK, Bash
- **Programming languages, Debugging, and Testing Analysis tools:** UML 2.0, SCALA, JAVA, C/C++, JUnit-5, DDD, Gcov, VALKYRIE YERITH[20.20], LTSA
- **Programming and Compiler Frameworks (including IDE):** DIFF, Patch, Txl, apache ANT, MAKE, Qt 5, SOOT, LLVM, flex, bison, Eclipse IDE, Codeblocks, CharmNT

51.51 Teaching for the University of Waterloo, Ontario, Canada–racist.

Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465) | Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650) | Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651) | Programming for Performance (ECE 459) | Computer Networks (ECE 428) | Compilers (ECE 351) | [C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)].

52.52 Summary of Professional Training in USA, Canada, & Germany

- "Professional international workshops and conferences". 2001 – 2015

53.53 Teaching / summary of competencies Acquired at THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA–RACIST.

- "Formal training at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO–racist". 2009 – 2011
- "Competencies acquired during courses teaching during doctoral studies at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO–racist". 2009 – 2011
- "Competencies acquired during courses teaching during post–doctoral studies at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO–racist". 2012 – 2015

54.54 Teaching ONLINE on the World Wide Web UNIVERSITY–level (graduate) Students.

I currently live in Africa, Cameroon where I cannot have a position at my level of knowledge and experience in a formal Cameroonian UNIVERSITY.

 "POUR les usagers de la langue FRANÇAISE : "Enseignant d'université"; ET NON Enseignant–employé d'université (d'État); EST 1 des définitions du mot professeur."

 Enseignant d'université signifie divulguer des enseignements académiques de rang doctoral et post–doctoraux aux apprenants des universités du monde. "LE titre et grade académique de *Ph.D. et / ou Docteur-de-3^{ème} cycle universitaire*" en est l'approbation universellement reconnue en ma connaissance.

Nonetheless I still teach via WWW books & tools, & programs that I deem at University level graduate courses level; Based on my "doctoral & post–doctoral Ph.D. studies In Computer Software Engineering" & work at the University–racist of Waterloo.

I am developing course material for online worldwide university level (graduate) students as depicted online on "zenodo.org" (<https://www.zenodo.org>) :

I.) Topic : SOFTWARE SYSTEM

- 1.) **FORMAL METHODS** using state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) for runtime monitoring and verification (via model checking) :
 - YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>)
 - A C++ Functional Library for Specifying "SDMM" (State Diagram Mealy Machine) – Book Preprint (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) ;
 - User's Guide for the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) ;
- 2.) **WWW (WORLD WIDE WEB) Design, Programming, & Deployment** : World Wide Web (WWW) Design & Programming using YERITH–WEB–DSL–9.0" : book in preparation, together with accompanying CDROM–USB–key dongle.
- 3.) **SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE** : SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH–ERP–3.0[??] : (https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf);
- 4.) **SOFTWARE VERIFICATION AND ANALYSIS** : Temporal Property Verification in Plugin–based Software by Program Analysis (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10990602>) ”.

II.) Topic : ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING (ERP) SOFTWARE & TOOLS

55.55 Research Expertise (PR. PROF. DR.-ING.)■ **Business Informatics** ⇒ *illustrative figure of business workflow of YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.*○ **Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) — Business Machinery**

- 1.) ERP-trading Stock Exchange Software: "YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0"[?]; <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0> C++; Qt 5; [03/2015 -]

■ **Software Engineering**○ **Web Apps Program Analysis**

- 2.) 3 A Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus; <https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis> JAVA; Firebug; [01/2013 - 04/2013]

○ **Web Apps Automatic Generation** ⇒ *illustrative table of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 (Section 27.27.5).*

- 3.) YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL[27.27]; <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9> flex, bison; [06/2024 -]

○ **Debugging Tool**

- 4.) 20.20 Open Source Contribution to "Valkyrie: Valgrind-GUI"; https://github.com/yerithrd/valkyrie_NON_OFFICIAL C++; Qt 5; [07/2023 -]

○ **CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) Tool**

- 5.) 1 "MBT-RT-TESTER PLUGIN" FOR "Borland-Together"[1b] C++; "Statechart-TDIOHS"; "Borland-Together"; "www.verified.de" [09/2006 - 02/2007]
6.) YRI_QVGE[1] C++; Qt 5; [06/2022 -]

○ **Compiler Technology**

- 7.) 34 Ph.D. dissertation: A Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM; <https://github.com/AmesianX/saint> LLVM; — 03/2015 —
8.) 1d A State Diagram Mealy Machine Description Language; https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang flex, bison; [04/2023 -]

■ **Software Engineering** ► **Software Verification** ⇒ *figure illustrating components of it (Section 13.13.1).*○ **Static Program Code Analysis** Checking à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)".

- 9.) 1(1)4 Conference Article : Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints JUnit; SOOT; JAVA; — 2013 —
10.) 32 Ph.D. thesis: Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software SOOT; JAVA; — 12/2011 —

○ **Dynamic Program Binary Runtime Analysis** Verification

- 11.) 1 YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime; <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif> C++; Qt-DBus; [06/2022 -]
12.) 1f A Runtime Monitoring Mealy Machine C++ library; https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif C++; Qt 5; [06/2022 -]

○ **Unit Testing**

- 13.) II Text-tutorial "JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL" JAVA; JUnit; "COBERTURA coverage analyzer" — 10/2009 —

○ **Test Cases / Test Data — Generation**

- 14.) 1a Statistical test cases generation for reactive systems C++; "Statechart-TDIOHS"; "Borland-Together"; "RT-Tester" — 05/2007 —

■ **Theoretical Computer Science**○ **Concurrent Systems, AUTOMATA theory**

- 15.) 1d Vordiplom-B.Sc. Independent Study: A Semantic Comparison between Timed Automata and Büchi Automata Set-Algebra; — 12/2004 —

56.56 Engineering Methodologies & Tools Expertise

- A.) **C++**; & **JAVA**; & **SQL – DBMS (Database Management System) MariaDB** with **DEBIAN LINUX & SVN** (E.g. : *(Part-Time) Student Software Developer Position* (<https://www.gewete.com>))
 SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
 a.) *Dipl.-Ing. JENS MÖLLER — Team Lead of myself at that time* 2005 – 2007
 b.) *Dipl.-Ing. (FH) SVEN KAMRATH — Technical Lead of myself at that time* 2005 – 2007
- B.) **C++** with **MS Windows (XP, 98,2000,7,10,11)** & **FSM (Finite State Machines)** & **Rational ClearCase** (E.g. : *Junior Software Developer position*) (<https://www.healthcare.siemens.com>)
 SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
 a.) *Dipl.-Inf. (FH) GERHARD SENG — Team Lead of myself at that time* 2007 – 2009
 b.) *Ing. (M.Sc.) DARIO MERAUIGLIA — Technical Lead of myself at that time* 2007 – 2009
- C.) **ERP System YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum** with **Javascript, XML, HTML5, CSS, PHP, MAKE, Qt 5, C++, MariaDB, flex & bison** (E.g. : *Inventor & Developer*)
 SUCCESSFULLY Used & Re-Tested.
 a.) *Annual reports : REPORTS ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/records/StillInDoing>) 2021 – 2023
 b.) *[Document local link !]*
- D.) **Software Testing (UNIT, Integration)** with **UML 2.0-HybridUML (Statechart by David-HAREL)** & **C++** (E.g. : *Statistical test cases generation for reactive systems at the UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN-racist-idiot, BREMEN-germany, Germany-racist*)
 SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
 a.) *Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska — MSc-advisor of myself at that time, Stakeholder of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH.* 2004 – 2007
 b.) *Prof. Dr. Rolf Drechsler — MSc-advisor of myself at that time* 2004 – 2007
 c.) *Diplomarbeit Kolloquium MASTER-thesis defence* May 25, "2007"
- E.) **JAVA** with **JUnit** (E.g. : *SE 465-ECE 453 — Text-tutorial "JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL"*)
 SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
 a.) *Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (ONTARIO) — Course Instructor.* SPRING term (Jan. – Apr.) – 2010
- F.) **Web Apps Automatic Generation** with **Javascript, XML, HTML5, CSS, PHP, MAKE, Qt 5, C++, MariaDB, flex & bison** (E.g. : *"WWW - World Wide Web (WWW) Design & Programming using YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0"* (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/YRITOENTERlaterOn>))
 a.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr. OWOLABI Legunsen, Ph.D., Cornell University, ITHACA, USA-*
 b.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Christian RIKONG Nguoyong, AS-degree in Computer Science, Santa monica-california, USA-*
 c.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr.-Ing. Thomas Djotio Ndie-*
 d.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr. Patrick-LAM-*
- G.) **Web Apps Program Analysis** with **Quercus & JAVA** (E.g. : *A Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus, CS846 at THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, Ontario-racist, Canada*) (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>)
 SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
 a.) *Prof. Dr. Frank Tip, Ph.D. – COURSE instructor* APRIL 30, "2013"
- H.) **Program Code Binary Analysis** with **SDMM & YERITH_QVGE** (E.g. : *Software Testing of YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum & Runtime Monitoring Verification.* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>))
 a.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr. OLAWABI, Ph.D., Cornell University, ITHACA, USA* December 20, "2025"
 b.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska — Stakeholder of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH.* October 7, "2025"
 c.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of KLAUS HAVELUND, Researcher at N.A.S.A., U.S.A.* July 11, "2025"
- I.) **Program Code Static Analysis** with **apache ANT, SOOT & JAVA** (E.g. : *Doctoral TheSis at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, Ontario-racist, Canada*) (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>)
 SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
 a.) *Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (ONTARIO) — PH.D.-advisor of myself at that time* December 20, "2011"
 b.) *Prof. Dr. Nomair Naeem, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (ONTARIO) — at my request before my PhD Comprehensive Examination* December "2011"
 c.) *PhD Comprehensive Examination – ECE-University of waterloo* December 20, "2011"
- J.) **Software Vulnerability Analysis** using **LLVM & C++** (E.g. : *Doctoral Dissertation in Computer Science at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, Ontario-racist, Canada*) (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>)
 SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
 a.) *Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. — at my request before my ECE graduate research seminar talk* "2014"
 b.) *ECE Graduate Seminar Talk Series at THE university of waterlloo-racist, ontario, canada* April, 16 "2014"
 c.) *PhD Dissertation Defence – CS-University of waterloo* January "2015"

[Research Expertise LINK internal to this document.]

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)

- 1.) A SEMANTIC COMPARISON BETWEEN BÜCHI AUTOMATA AND TIMED AUTOMATA, INDEPENDENT STUDY, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY, ADVISED BY PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA. JANUARY 2005
- 2.) STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION FOR REACTIVE SYSTEMS (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/qualifikationsarbeiten/diplomarbeiten_e.html), MASTER'S DEGREE IN COMPUTER SCIENCE THESIS, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, ADVISED BY PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA, AND PROF. DR. PHIL. NAT. ROLF DRECHSLER. MAY 25, 2007
- 3.) RESEARCH MASTER PROJECT REPORT cognitive agents, [Research Project Report Robotic-Cognition-Cartography], UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY, ADVISED BY DR.-ING. LUTZ Frommberger, DR.-ING. DIPL.-INF. Frank DYLLA, PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. Christian FRESKA. July 2006

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA (<https://www.uwaterloo.ca>)

- 1.) JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052444/>), UNDERGRADUATE COURSE LECTURES NOTES 'SOFTWARE TESTING, QUALITY ASSURANCE AND MAINTENANCE', UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA, ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM. OCTOBER 31, 2009
- 2.) TEMPORAL PROPERTY VERIFICATION IN PLUGIN-BASED SOFTWARE (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8ald09b015f29b33>), PHILOSOPHY DOCTOR (PH.D.) DISSERTATION, (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8ald09b015f29b33>) UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM. DECEMBER 20, 2011
- 3.) DYNAMIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR PHP IN QUERCUS (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>) ([git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis); [git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests)), PH.D. GRADUATE COURSE PROJECT 'program analysis of web apps', UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA ADVISED BY FULL PROFESSOR FRANK TIP. APRIL 30, 2013

**JAVA application server "Quercus" — JAVA-PHP-interpreter
PROGRAM analysis of web apps
SOFTWARE cyber-security**

- "[THIS course CS846 project led by Professor doctor Frank TIP], was about creating a security taint analysis program code in JAVA for the "Quercus JAVA PHP Interpreter", which is a web application server, COMPARABLE to Apache-Tomcat (<https://www.tomcat.org>); And that enables PHP developers to use existing JAVA libraries within their PHP code as well. "
- "I have implemented and tested a dynamic taint analysis using Firebug, and FirePHP. THIS taint analysis enables to warn developers about data and values that originate from outside the webserver, and / or also about values that emerge as results from operations that involve "tainted values"; MEANING values that are considered not safe because they originate from the outside world of the Quercus web application server. "
- "Taking particular care of unsafe outside world data and values (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) allows developers to avoid web cyber-software security vulnerabilities attacks such as SQL injection, BUFFER-OVERFLOW attacks, format string vulnerabilities, etc.."

► YEAR-2024

IN our project YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0, we will need to instrument binaries of a running JAVA virtual machine; Most probably "Debian-Linux OpenJDK Runtime Environment" (<https://docs.oracle.com>).

THIS binary instrumentation technology from INTEL-pin (<https://www.intel.com/missingfornow>) has an advantage over reinstrumenting and recompiling code sources each time any Qt-DBus message has been introduced and / or modified in tool YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>).

- 4.) CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>), POST-DOCTORAL PH.D. GRADUATE WORK, (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014_04_16.pdf) UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM. MARCH 10, 2015

**Heartbleed BUG security breach SSL-1.0.1-f (<https://heartbleed.com>)
Static PROGRAM code analysis of C programs
LLVM code; SOFTWARE cyber-security**
- 5.) CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM TOOL USER'S GUIDE (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051299>), POST-DOCTORAL PH.D. GRADUATE WORK artifact, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM. [OCTOBER 2015]

PUBLICATIONS – YERITH R&D (in English language) (II)

[REsearch Expertise LINK internal to this document.]

57.57 YERITH R&D – Algorithms Excerpt not published in conference papers due to resources.

1. [Created Algorithms Link].

58.58 YERITH R&D – Reports

2. YERITH R&D BUSINESS plan in FRENCH-cameroonian language (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/YRITOENTERlaterOn>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, October 16, 2024. October 16, 2024
3. REPORTS ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0 (<https://zenodo.org/records/StillInDoing>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, April 15, 2025. April 15, 2025
4. REPORT ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0 (YEAR 2023) (<https://zenodo.org/records/13949884>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, October 1, 2023. October 1, 2023

59.59 Business Informatics Management Knowledge

5. YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum SOFTWARE SYSTEM PRODUCT SHEET (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-product-sheet/yerith-erp-9-0-product-sheet.pdf>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, MARCH 2021. MARCH 2021
6. ADVANTAGES OF YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum COMPARED TO OTHER TOP ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEMS (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-document-comparison/yerith-erp-document-comparison.pdf>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, MARCH 2021. MARCH 2021
7. INFORMATION BROCHURE OF ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-brochure-english/yerith-erp-9-0-brochure-english.pdf>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, MARCH 2021. MARCH 2021
8. INSTALLATION GUIDE FOR ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum (<https://zenodo.org/record/8060182/>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, MARCH 2021. MARCH 2021

60.60 Associated Computer Devices

9. YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum RECOMMENDED POINT-OF-SALE HARDWARE (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-inventory-stock-recommended-hardware/yerith-erp-9-0-inventory-stock-recommended-hardware.pdf>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, MARCH 2021. MARCH 2021

61.61 Advanced Software Technology

10. "WWW - World Wide Web (WWW) Design & Programming using YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/YRITOENTERlaterOn>),
BOOK, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, March 2025. March 2025
11. Concepts around real-time trading for physical and / or virtual stocks with software system: YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME (<https://zenodo.org/records/14505133>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, DECEMBER 17, 2024. DECEMBER 17, 2024
12. A C++ Functional Library for Specifying "SDMM" (State Diagram Mealy Machine) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>),
Book in preparation, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, 2025. 2025
13. User's Guide for the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, 2023. 2023
14. YERITH-ERP-9.0 DOCTORAL COMPENDIUM (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>),
DOCTORAL COMPENDIUM, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, MAY 2022. MAY 2022
15. Runtime Verification Of SQL Correctness Properties with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>),
Journal article in preparation, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, August 2023. August 2023
16. Compendium of Documents About the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, June 2023. June 2023
17. SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH-ERP-9.0 (https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-9-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, JULY 2022. JULY 2022

10. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: a framework for verifying SQL software correctness properties of gui software at runtime** (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051303>), CONFERENCE article in submission, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, February 2023.

February 2023

PUBLICATIONS – YERITH R&D (en langue française) (III)

[LIEN interne à ce document sur mes Spécialités en recherche académique et / ou Professionnelle.]

62.62 YERITH R&D – Algorithmes scientifiques (En Anglais) – Non publiés dans 1 journal pour causes de ressources financières entre autres.

1. [Lien sur des algorithmes repertoriés et Créés par moi !]

63.63 YERITH R&D – Rapports

2. *RAPPORTS DE TRAVAUX SUR LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-3.0* (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/EntrainDetreCREEE>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, AVRIL 2025.
3. *RAPPORT DE TRAVAUX SUR LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-3.0 (années 2015-2022)* (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051568/>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, OCTOBRE 2022.

64.64 INFORMATIQUE de gestion — Connaissances Marketing

4. *BROCHURE DE GESTION COMMERCIALE* (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-brochure-gestion-commerciale-notions/yerith-erp-9-0-brochure-gestion-commerciale-notions.pdf>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, OCTOBRE 2021.

65.65 INFORMATIQUE de gestion — Management des données

5. *GUIDE DE L'UTILISATEUR 'MANAGER', PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/record/8058259/>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, JUIN 2018.
6. *YERITH-ERP-PGI-3.0: ESSAI DE PRODUCTIVITÉ ENTREPRENEURIALE* (<https://zenodo.org/records/10071437>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, MARS 2021.
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11. *AVANTAGES DE YERITH-PGI-9.0 COMPARATIVEMENT À SAGE GESCOM I7, ET À SAP BUSINESS ONE* (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-document-comparaisons/yerith-erp-9-0-document-comparaisons.pdf>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, MARS 2021.
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66.66 INFORMATIQUE de gestion — COMPTABILITÉ analytique

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67.67 INFORMATIQUE de gestion-PGI-Erp — Accessoires Recommandés

18. **MATÉRIEL INFORMATIQUE RECOMMANDÉ POUR LE POINT-DE-VENTE YERITH-PGI-9.0** (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-PDV-materiel-informatique-recommande/yerith-erp-9-0-PDV-materiel-informatique-recommande.pdf>), MARS 2021
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68.68 Ingénierie du Progiciel TRès Avancée

19. **YERITH-ERP-9.0 DOCTORAT / PH.D. COMPENDIUM** (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>), MAI 2022
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FORMER CIVIL ADDRESSES – CANADA

I HAVE LIVED AT ALL THE FOLLOWING ADDRESSES AS A CAMEROON CITIZEN, AND ADDITIONALLY as a permanent resident of canada (FROM YEAR 2005 - 2014) !

I acquired a canadian citizenship in August 2014 (because I couldn't fly freely into Europe without visa application as a Cameroon citizen.) !

I RENOUNCED solemnly THIS CANADIAN CITIZENSHIP, in front of judge at the "Waterloo Region Courthouse (85 Frederick St., Kitchener, ON N2H 0A7, Canada)" IN SEPTEMBER 2018 !

THE JUDGE SAID I COULD PAY FOR THE TRANSCRIPTS to be send to cameroon embassy in Ottawa; BUT I COULDN'T AFFORD for IT !

I THEN DEFINITELY and forever ABANDONED CANADA and ONTARIO for Cameroon in September 2018 !

1. LANDLORD !

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
C/O THÉODORE NGONGANG WANDJI
5850 RUE SOUART # 7
H3S 2E8 MONTREAL, QC

2. LANDLORD john guldemond, anna guldemond

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
391B CHURCHILL CRT
N2L 6B4 WATERLOO, ON

3. LANDLORD mike

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
186 CORRIE CRESCENT
N2L 5W4 WATERLOO, ON

4. LANDLORD Northview Fund

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
457 ALBERT STREET, APT 16
N2L 5A7 WATERLOO, ON

5. LANDLORD !

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
88 GLENBURN DRIVE
N2L 5K1 WATERLOO, ON

6. LANDLORD anna and spouse

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
310 HIAWATHA DRIVE
N2L 5H5 WATERLOO, ON

7. LANDLORD anna and spouse

AS canadian citizen; XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
310 HIAWATHA DRIVE
N2L 5H5 WATERLOO, ON

8. LANDLORD erick djeuyou pokem !

AS canadian citizen; XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
C/O erick djeuyou pokem
5738A rue Hochelega
H1N 1W3 Montreal, QC

FORMER CIVIL ADDRESSES – GERMANY

I HAVE LIVED AT ALL THE FOLLOWING ADDRESSES AS A CAMEROON CITIZEN, AND ADDITIONALLY as a STUDENT AT THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN (FROM YEAR 2001 - 2007).

I HAVE BEEN WORKING AS a "software entwickler (junior)" at SIEMENS HEALTHINEERS (OCS) until 2009 !

1. "UNIVERSITÄT BREMEN"

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
C/O THÉODORE NGONGANG WANDJI
LEOBENER STRASSE 4
28359 BREMEN

2. LANLORD "GEWOBA"

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
C/O TAALY MARCELLIN
GUSTAV-HEINEMANN-STRASSE 71
28359 BREMEN

3. LANLORD "GÜNTHER SPREEN"

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
ACHTERBERGSTR. 9
28219 BREMEN

4. LANLORD "ULA QUERFÜRTH"

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
MATHILDENSTR. 41
! NÜRNBERG

BANK ACCOUNTS

Cameroon

1. **EXPRESS UNION YAOUNDE-AHALA: Savings Only Account.:**
SHE (Ms. NGONO), that I couldn't close it: I have to leave it as a dormant closed bank account.
2. **AFRILAND-FIRST BANK HIPPODROME-YAOUNDE: Checking DORMANT Account.:**
I asked for this account to be totally closed in year 2017 with no apparent success; I don't know why.

Outside Cameroon: IN CANADA-Ontario

1. **HSBC UPTOWN WATERLOO; EURO Savings Account.:**
I couldn't close it because I was still inside Canada: So I still need it until I definitively and forever leave NORTH AMERICA !

So I would be glad they close it for myself, without any other mentions that is not in my favor in case I need again such an account elsewhere in the world, outside of Canada.

CANADA WAS A DISGUSTING PLACE TO LIVE FOR ME AS A BLACK AFRICAN.

REAL ESTATES POSSESSIONS

I OWN alone 2 LAND PROPERTIES with land title certificate IN CAMEROON (1 in douala, and 1 in yaoundé) !

1. DOUALA: **LAND TITLE CERTIFICATE nr. 14 000, volume 117, WOURI 5, béedi-kounghi located IN CITÉ-DES-PALMIERS_HAUTE-TENSION_BÉEDI !**
THERE ARE THREE 3-bedrooms APARTMENTS OF EACH around 135 m² of AREA.
I HAVE INHERITED (JANUARY 8, 1992) THIS LAND from late computer PROGRAMMER ANALYST THÉODORE noumbissi (born on APRIL 01, 1956 in OBALA, center-region), my birth-giver on planet earth !
2. YAOUNDÉ (named IMMEUBLE YERITH): **LAND TITLE CERTIFICATE nr. 560 792, volume 265, MFOUNDI VI (6), Nsimbock-AHALA located IN Nsimbock-AHALA_FACE_ENTREE-ETOA-DERRIERE-savonnerie_NOSA !**
THERE ARE 2 2-bedrooms APARTMENTS OF EACH around 105 m² of AREA.
THE GROUND LEVEL IS FINISHED; missing, because of funding, is 4 supplemental 2-BEDROOMS apartments as planned from UNDERGROUND LEVEL !
I HAVE BOUGHT THIS LAND, IN NOVEMBER 2012 (in front of asserted public notary ME. FRANCOIS-XAVIER MENYE ONDO), from cameroon national assembly parliament member; AND vice-president hon. THÉODORE datouo (FROM WEST-REGION; village BANGOU) !
ASSERTED PUBLIC NOTARY ME. FRANCOIS-XAVIER MENYE ONDO, has offices at "IMMEUBLE DU CRÉDIT FONCIER DU CAMEROUN (CFC)" !

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BRÈVE PRÉSENTATION
DU PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ (PGI)
YERITH-PGI-9.0

”Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]”

1 Progiciel de Gestion Intégré

Figure 1 – Une image de YERITH-PGI-9.0.

Figure 2 – Configuration TYPE de travail de YERITH-PGI-9.0.

YERITH-PGI-9.0 est un PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ (PGI)! La figure 1 illustre une image du PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0.

Un progiciel de gestion intégré est un **programme informatique** qui aide ses utilisateurs à réaliser des tâches suivantes :

1. enregistrer (répertoire), rechercher, etc. : des **FOURNISSEURS, CLIENTS, EMPLOYÉS, MEMBRES, etc..**
2. **enregistrer (répertoire), rechercher**, des stocks et / ou articles (OU IMMOBILISATIONS) dans un catalogue électronique
3. **VENDRE – TRANSFÉRER – SORTIR – ETC.**, des stocks et / ou articles (OU IMMOBILISATIONS) de leur catalogue électronique d'enregistrement
4. **créer des ALERTES** sur des **PÉRIODES DE TEMPS**, sur des **QUANTITÉS**, etc.
5. **VISUALISER DES STATISTIQUES** sur des ventes, des mouvements, etc. : de stocks, d'articles (OU IMMOBILISATIONS), etc.
6. **EN RÉSUMÉ**, permettre à une personne, un groupe d'individus (incluant une famille), une entreprise commerciale, ou une entreprise de services, etc. : de **suivre sa gestion sur le PLAN DU COMMERCE ET DE LA FINANCE à l'aide de l'informatique!**
7. **YERITH-PGI-9.0 PREND EN COMPTE DES LIGNES BUDGÉTAIRES!**

1.1 Droits D'accès

LES UTILISATEURS du progiciel de gestion intégré YERITH-PGI-9.0 n'ont pas les mêmes **droits de VISUALISATIONS, ET / OU DE MANIPULATIONS DES DONNÉES!**

Par exemple, 1 employé ne peut pas observer ou manipuler des données spécifiques à son patron.

1.2 Régionalisation

YERITH-PGI-9.0 est disponible dans des langues suivantes : ANGLAIS, et FRANÇAIS.

1.3 Périphériques D'utilisations

YERITH-PGI-9.0 doit / peut utiliser des appareils afficher à la suite :

1. **L'ordinateur** : CONTIENT YERITH-PGI-9.0 et des données (catalogues d'articles, catalogues de clients, statistiques, etc.)
2. **L'écran** : POUR VISUALISER CE QUE CONTIENT L'ordinateur

1. L'ordinateur (OBLIGATOIRE)

2. L'écran (OBLIGATOIRE)

3. Le tiroir de caisse (FACULTATIF)

4. L'imprimante de tickets PDV (thermique) (FACULTATIF)

5. Le lecteur de code barres (FACULTATIF)

6. 1 terminal (NC-300) à plusieurs utilisateurs (FACULTATIF)

3. **Le tiroir de caisse** : PERMET DE STOCKER DES BILLETS ET/OU PIÈCES D'ARGENT
4. **L'imprimante de tickets PDV (thermique)** : PEUT ÊTRE UTILISER POUR IMPRIMER DES REÇUS
5. **Le lecteur de code barres** : PERMET DE LIRE DES NUMÉROS UNIQUES INSCRIT SUR DES ARTICLES ET LES IDENTIFIANT.
6. **1 terminal (NC-300) à plusieurs utilisateurs** : appareil numérique permettant de ré-utiliser 1 seul ordinateur "desktop" pour plusieurs utilisateurs, de façon simultanée¹.

1. "<https://www.savingology.com>"

YERITH-PGI-9.0 Fiche de Données du Progiciel de Gestion Intégré (PGI)

YERITH-PGI-9.0 est un PGI (Progiciel de Gestion Intégré) qui a 6 types d'utilisateurs, et, rôles :

1. « Administrateur »
2. « Caissier »
3. « Gestionnaire de stock »
4. « Magasinier »
5. « Manager »
6. « Vendeur ».

YERITH-PGI-9.0 a les fonctions suivantes :

1. Vérification en Temps D'Exécution avec "yerith_qvge (<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri-db-runtime-verif>)"
2. administration des utilisateurs, et, des rôles
3. alertes sur les quantités en stocks, et sur les périodes de temps
4. gestion des RESSOURCES HUMAINES, clients (CRM), fournisseurs, lignes budgétaires, 'Business Analytics'.
5. gestion des stocks, DES IMMOBILISATIONS
6. gestion des ventes (locations, caisse, etc.)
7. recherche basée sur des modèles avec le caractère %
8. tableaux de bords.

YERITH-PGI-9.0 est :

1. léger, et très rapide
2. multi-sites
3. simple, et, intuitif.

Les tests d'utilisations de la mémoire sont réalisés avec l'outil **valgrind**. L'ASSURANCE QUALITÉ DU CODE SOURCE est réalisé avec L'ANALYSEUR DE CODE SOURCE **Cppcheck**.

La fenêtre d'accueil pour le « Manager »

Fonctionnement conceptuel de YERITH-PGI-9.0

OPÉRATIONS

Matériels Point-de-Vente

- ✓ Lecteur de code-barres, etc.

Systèmes-de-Gestion de Base-de-Données

- ✓ MySQL 10.5

Systèmes d'Exploitations

- ✓ Debian-Linux 11; 12.

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yerith-erp-9-0-document-comparaisons-4 _____ 4

Avantages D'utilisation de L'informatique Pour La Gestion De Stocks

YERITH-PGI-9.0 est un Progiciel de Gestion Intégré (PGI) avantageux par rapport aux autres méthodes de gestion de stocks à cause des raisons suivantes :

1. progiciel de gestion intégré, réseau compris
2. utilisation de MySQL comme moteur de base de données.

La fiche des stocks (SOLUTION INFORMATISÉE 'YERITH-PGI-9.0')

1 LARGE DIMENSION GÉOGRAPHIQUE

1 LARGE DIMENSION GÉOGRAPHIQUE DES BÂTIMENTS DE L'ENTREPRISE PEUT CAUSER DES PERTES DE TEMPS DANS LES DÉPLACEMENTS pour **comptabiliser des stocks**.

2 NOMBRES DE SUCCURSALES ÉLEVÉS

1 NOMBRE DE SUCCURSALES ÉLEVÉS DE L'ENTREPRISE PEUT ENTRAÎNER BEAUCOUP DE PERTES DE TEMPS pour **comptabiliser des stocks**.

3 QUANTITÉ TOTALE ÉLEVÉE D'ARTICLES À VENDRE, TRANSFÉRER

1 QUANTITÉ TOTALE ÉLEVÉE D'ARTICLES À VENDRE, ET À TRANSFÉRER PEUT ENTRAÎNER DES PERTES DE TEMPS **durant la comptabilisation des stocks**.

4 TRAVAIL SIMULTANÉ ET COORDONNÉ SUR LES DONNÉES

TRAVAILLER SIMULTANÉMENT EN GROUPE SUR LES DONNÉES DE STOCKS À VENDRE, OU À TRANSFÉRER, sans outils informatiques rend **la comptabilisation et l'affectation des états de stocks extrêmement difficile!**

Le tableau 1 illustre la complexité d'assumer efficacement des tâches de gestion de stocks **SANS OUTILS INFORMATIQUE**.

	SANS INFORMATIQUE	TABLEUR	YERITH-PGI-9.0
large dimension géographique de l'organisation	extrêmement difficile	extrêmement difficile	facile
nombre de succursales élevé	extrêmement difficile	extrêmement difficile	facile
quantité totale élevée d'articles à vendre, transférer	extrêmement difficile	très difficile	facile
travail simultané et coordonné sur les données	extrêmement difficile	très difficile	facile

Tableau 1 – Comparaison entre YERITH-PGI-9.0 et les autres solutions de gestion de stocks

CONCLUSION: PLUS L'ORGANISATION EST GRANDE EN ACTIVITÉS, ET EN SUPERFICIE, PLUS IL EST EXTRÊMEMENT IMPORTANT DE FAIRE USAGE D'1 PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ (PGI) POUR 1 RENTABILITÉ EFFICACE!

Avantages de YERITH–PGI–9.0 Comparativement à Sage Gescom i7, et à SAP Business One

YERITH–PGI–9.0 est un Progiciel de Gestion Intégré (PGI) facile d'utilisation à cause de ses caractéristiques suivantes :

1. vue du logiciel dépendante du rôle de l'utilisateur
2. formation complète en au moins 2 semaines
3. interface du logiciel très facile à utiliser
4. pas de connection internet requise
5. pas de formation commerciale requise
6. pas de formation comptable requise
7. pas de formation universitaire requise.

La fiche des stocks

Le tableau 1 illustre à merveille la simplicité et l'efficacité de YERITH–PGI–9.0, en comparaison avec les progiciels de gestion intégré "Sage Gescom i7", et "SAP Business One".

	YERITH–PGI–9.0	Sage Gescom i7	SAP Business One
vue du logiciel dépendante du rôle	OUI	OUI	OUI
formation complète	au moins 2 semaines	au moins 2 mois	au moins 3 mois
interface du logiciel	évidente	très compliquée	très compliquée
langage dans le logiciel	usuel de tous les jours	simple	technique
formation comptable	jamais	jamais	utile
formation en marketing	jamais	utile	utile
connection internet	optionel	optionel	obligatoire

Tableau 1 – Comparaison entre YERITH–PGI–9.0 et quelques autres progiciels de gestion intégré

OPÉRATIONS

<p>Matériels Point–de–Vente</p> <hr/> <p>✓ Lecteur de code–barres, etc.</p>		
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Avantages D'utilisation de L'informatique Pour La Gestion De Stocks

1 ENTRÉES, VISUALISATIONS, ET SORTIES des données

Le tableau 7 illustre la complexité d'assumer efficacement des tâches de gestion de stocks **SANS OUTILS INFORMATIQUE**.

1.1 RH Fournisseurs

Tableau 1 – INTERFACES GRAPHIQUES pour "RH Fournisseurs"

ENTRÉES	VISUALISATIONS	SORTIES*
RH Fournisseurs		

1.2 CRM Clients

Tableau 2 – INTERFACES GRAPHIQUES pour "CRM Clients"

ENTRÉES	VISUALISATIONS	SORTIES*
CRM Clients		

1.3 PAIEMENTS

Tableau 3 – INTERFACES GRAPHIQUES pour "PAIEMENTS"

ENTRÉES	VISUALISATIONS	SORTIES*
Check in		

1.4 CHARGES FINANCIÈRES

Tableau 4 – INTERFACES GRAPHIQUES pour "CHARGES FINANCIÈRES"

ENTRÉES	VISUALISATIONS	SORTIES*
Check in		

1.5 IMMOBILISATION / Stocks

Tableau 5 – INTERFACES GRAPHIQUES pour "IMMOBILISATION / Stocks"

ENTRÉES	VISUALISATIONS	SORTIES*
Check in		

1.6 Tableaux de Bords

Tableau 6 – INTERFACES GRAPHIQUES pour "Tableaux de Bords"

ENTRÉES	VISUALISATIONS	SORTIES*
Check in		

1.7 Entrer une immobilisation, un stocks, un service

Tableau 7 – INTERFACES GRAPHIQUES pour "Entrer une immobilisation, un stocks, un service"

ENTRÉES	VISUALISATIONS	SORTIES*
Check in		

2 CONCLUSION

PLUS L'ORGANISATION EST GRANDE EN ACTIVITÉS, ET EN SUPERFICIE, PLUS IL EST EXTRÊMEMENT IMPORTANT DE FAIRE USAGE D'UN LOGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ (PGI) POUR UNE RENTABILITÉ EFFICACE!

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YERITH-ERP-9.0 Point Of Sale Recommended Hardware

1 Barcode Scanner

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of barcode scanner: "Xfox FJ-5 USB Plug and Play Automatic Barcode Scanner" (approx. 17€).

Bar-code Scanner

2 Thermal Printer

ALL EPSON THERMAL PRINTERS !

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of thermal printer: "Epson TM T20ii Point of Sale Thermal Printer" (approx. 100€).

Thermal Printer

3 Cash Drawer

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of cash drawer: "HP QT457AT" (approx. 90€).

Cash Drawer

4 Touch Screen Monitor

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of touch screen monitor: "ASUS 15.6" LCD Monitor (VT168H)" (approx. 155€).

Touchscreen Monitor

5 Computer

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of desktop computer: "Lenovo Thinkcentre M720 Small Form Factor (SFF)" (approx. 450€).

Computer

6 Multi User Terminal Computer

We recommend, but not exclusively, the use of multi user terminal computer: "NC-300 Multi User Terminal Computer" (approx. 112€).

Multi User Terminal Computer

✓ **PECULIARITIES IN CERTAIN COUNTRIES AND/OR REGIONS** USAGE OF POINT-OF-SALE (THERMAL) PRINTERS REQUIRES ALSO ACQUISITION OF A GOVERNMENT-SOLD DEVICE FOR RECORDING AND CERTIFYING ALL FINANCIAL TRANSACTIONS BETWEEN THE THERMAL PRINTERS AND/OR YERITH-ERP-9.0 (e.g.: GERMANY, CANADA, etc.).

Table 2.1: Devices and hardware useful for YERITH-ERP-3.0.

Figure 2.1: Computer (MANDATORY)

Figure 2.2: Touchscreen Monitor (MANDATORY)

Figure 2.3: Cash Drawer (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.4: "Point of Sale Thermal Printer" (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.5: Bar-code Scanner (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.6: 1 Network Router (MANDATORY)

Figure 2.7: Numeric Tablet (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.8: "2 in 1 Computer" (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.9: Multi User Terminal Computer (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.10: Hardware components of Multi-User Terminal Computer NC-300 (at <https://www.savingology.com>): images are taken from SavingOlogy.com.

Figure 2.11: NC-300 PCI card

Figure 2.12: NC-300 terminals

YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0: BROCHURE DE GESTION COMMERCIALE

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]"

1 PARCOURS ACADÉMIQUE DE "XAVIER NOUBISSI NOUNDOU [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]"

Figure 1: Portrait de YERITH-nissi.

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]" EST CHRÉTIEN ÉVANGÉLIQUE 'BORN-AGAIN (né-de-nouveau)', CAMEROUNAIS, ET NÉ LE 16 Septembre 1983 À DOUALA DANS LA RÉGION DU LITTORAL AU CAMEROON.

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]" A 1 GRADE ACADÉMIQUE ET PROFESSIONNEL DE **"DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (DIPL.-INF.)"** PROVENANT DE **L'UNIVERSITÉ DE BRÊME EN ALLEMAGNE**, DEPUIS LE 25 MAI 2007.

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]" A 1 GRADE ACADÉMIQUE ET PROFESSIONNEL DE **PHILOSOPHIAE DOCTOR (PH.D.)** PROVENANT DE **L'UNIVERSITÉ DE WATERLOO (ON, CANADA)**, DEPUIS LE 20 DÉCEMBRE 2011.

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 - 2) document scientifique et / ou technique:
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2 INTRODUCTION

Figure 2: YERITH-PGI-9.0

YERITH-PGI-9.0 est 1 progiciel (système-logiciel) de gestion intégré.

Cette brochure apporte des notions élémentaires de 'marketing' nécessaires à l'utilisation de YERITH-PGI-9.0 (son menu principal est illustré dans la figure 2).

SON UTILISATION est intuitive si vous posséder toutes les informations utiles et complètes décrites dans cette brochure de gestion commerciale.

3 NOTIONS DE BASE

3.1 ORGANISATION ENTREPRENEURIALE

1 organisation entrepreneuriale est 1 entité d'1 ou de plusieurs personnes qui coordonnent leurs efforts physiques ou intellectuels afin de créer des biens matériels ou des services.

UNE ORGANISATION ENTREPRENEURIALE PEUT ÊTRE:

1. une organisation gouvernementale
2. une organisation non gouvernementale à but non lucratif (ONG)
3. une société commerciale.

UNE ORGANISATION ENTREPRENEURIALE EST COMPOSÉ DES ENTITÉS SUIVANTES:

1. boutique (ou encore bureau)
2. dépôt (ou encore magasin).

LA CRÉATION DES BIENS MATÉRIELS ET DES SERVICES NÉCESSITENT L'ACHAT, LA VENTE, L'UTILISATION, OU DES MODIFICATIONS DE MARCHANDISES.

EN GESTION COMMERCIALE, IL EXISTE:

1. une **personne morale**: c'est-à-dire 1 organisation entrepreneuriale
2. une **personne physique**: c'est-à-dire 1 individu.

3.2 SERVICE

Figure 3: La fenêtre pour entrer des services/stocks dans YERITH-PGI-9.0

1 SERVICE est 1 tâche exécutée par 1 organisation entrepreneuriale pour le bien être d'1 personne.

EXEMPLE de service: ouvrir son dossier chez 1 consultant en informatique.

3.3 MARCHANDISE

Figure 4: La fenêtre des marchandises dans YERITH-PGI-9.0

1 marchandise est défini par les éléments suivants:

1. le nom du produit d'ingénierie
2. son utilité pour l'organisation la possédant

EXEMPLE de marchandise: 1 marque de boisson gazeuse produite par 1 société commerciale, et revendue par 1 organisation entrepreneuriale.

3.4 STOCK DE MARCHANDISES

Figure 5: La fenêtre des stocks dans YERITH-PGI-9.0

1 **stock de marchandises** est composé de plusieurs services, ou de biens matériels, d'1 même nature, provenant d'1 même fournisseur, ayant les mêmes prix de ventes, et les mêmes prix d'achats.

1 stock de marchandises a, entre autres, les caractéristiques suivantes :

1. une désignation: le nom qui spécifie la marchandise
2. une date de péremption: la date à laquelle la marchandise est déclarée non utilisable
3. un prix d'achat: la valeur monétaire à laquelle s'est faite l'acquisition d'une unité du stock de marchandises
4. un prix de vente: la valeur monétaire à laquelle l'organisation entrepreneuriale vend une unité du stock de marchandises
5. un stock d'alerte (optionnel): quantité d'unités de marchandises pour laquelle l'organisation entrepreneuriale ré-alimentera son stock de marchandises.
6. une quantité: nombre d'unités de marchandises à la disposition de l'organisation entrepreneuriale.

EXEMPLE de stock marchandise: 1 organisation entrepreneuriale possède dans ses dépôts 18 bouteilles de la boisson gazeuse 'YERITH-FRESHNESS'.

3.5 TRANSFERTS ET / OU SORTIES DE IMMOBILISATIONS (ET / OU STOCKS)

Figure 6: La fenêtre des mouvements de stocks dans YERITH-PGI-9.0

1 **mouvement de stock** peut-être soit:

- a. 1 **transfert de stock** d'1 entité de l'organisation entrepreneuriale à 1 autre
- b. 1 **sortie de stock** d'1 entité de l'organisation entrepreneuriale : 1 client récupère son achat dans 1 entité de l'organisation entrepreneuriale autre que celle où il a effectué son achat.

EXEMPLE de transfert de stock: la société commerciale de recherche et développement YERITH_{r&d} envoie 20 copies sur DVD-disque de l'ERP-PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0 de son siège au rayon 'software' de son supermarché 'YERITH-SUPERMARCHÉ'.

EXEMPLE de sortie de stock: le client XAVIER YERITH de la société commerciale YERITH_{r&d} paie '150 000 FCFA' au siège de YERITH_{r&d} pour 1 copie de l'ERP-PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0; ensuite, il va retirer (sortir) 1 copie au supermarché 'YERITH-SUPERMARCHÉ'.

3.6 FOURNISSEUR

Figure 7: fenêtre des fournisseurs dans YERITH-PGI-9.0

1 **fournisseur** est 1 organisation entrepreneuriale qui vous donne par vente ou autres moyens des services ou des marchandises.

EXEMPLE de fournisseur: la société commerciale qui produit les boissons gazeuses que le supermarché 'YERITH-SUPERMARCHÉ' a en vente dans ses rayons.

3.7 CHARGES FINANCIÈRES

Figure 8: La fenêtre des charges financières dans YERITH-PGI-9.0

1 **charge financière** est une sortie de monnaie (d'argent) pour le compte de l'organisation entrepreneuriale (une organisation gouvernementale, une O.N.G., ou encore une société commerciale)!

EXEMPLE de charge financière: la facture mensuelle d'électricité.

3.8 ACHATS

Figure 9: La fenêtre des fiches des achats dans YERITH-PGI-9.0

CETTE FENÊTRE présente des achats enregistrés via la fenêtre des stocks (LORSQUE LE PRIX D'ACHAT D'1 ARTICLE D'1 STOCK est mentionné.

Ces achats sont soit des "IMMOBILISATIONS", soit des "STOCKS".

3.9 CLIENTÈLE

Figure 10: fenêtre de la clientèle dans YERITH-PGI-9.0

1 **clientèle** est l'ensemble des personnes qui constitue les utilisateurs ou acheteurs des marchandises ou services d'1 organisation entrepreneuriale.

EXEMPLE de clientèle: les personnes physiques ou morales qui achètent des boissons gazeuses au supermarché 'YERITH-SUPERMARCHÉ'.

3.10 POINT-DE-VENTE

Figure 11: point-de-vente dans YERITH-PGI-9.0

point-de-vente: lieu où s'effectue des achats de services ou de stocks de marchandises d'1 organisation entrepreneuriale.

EXEMPLE de point-de-vente: siège de la société commerciale YERITH_{r&d} où peut se faire l'achat d'1 copie de leur progiciel de gestion intégré YERITH-PGI-9.0.

3.11 VENTES

Figure 12: La fenêtre des ventes dans YERITH-PGI-9.0

1 vente est:

- 1 résultat monétaire (en argent) d'1 service effectué pour 1 client
- 1 résultat monétaire (en argent) de la passation d'1 stock de marchandises à 1 client

EXEMPLE de vente: 1 client verse '150 000 FCFA' pour l'achat d'1 copie du progiciel de gestion intégré (PGI) YERITH-PGI-9.0.

3.12 PAIEMENTS

Figure 13: La fenêtre des paiements dans YERITH-PGI-9.0

1 paiement est:

- 1 **crédit (provenant du verbe créditer):** action de déposer de la monnaie (ou argent) dans 1 compte bancaire d'1 organisation entrepreneuriale.
- 1 **débit (provenant du verbe débiter):** action de retirer de la monnaie (ou argent) d'1 compte bancaire d'1 organisation entrepreneuriale.

SYNONYMES DE 'CRÉDIT': entrée (argent), encaissement, versement.

SYNONYMES DE 'DÉBIT': sortie (argent), décaissement.

EXEMPLE d'encaissement (crédit): achat d'1 stock de marchandises par 1 personne physique.

EXEMPLE de décaissement (débit): achat d'1 stock de marchandises à 1 fournisseur.

3.13 TABLEAUX DE BORDS

Figure 14: La fenêtre des tableaux-de-bords dans YERITH-PGI-9.0

tableaux de bords: l'ensemble des présentations des données d'entrées et des sorties:

1. de monnaie (financières)
2. des services
3. des stocks de marchandises

qui permettent au directeur d'1 organisation entrepreneuriale de prendre des décisions pour de bons et meilleurs rendements (financier, fourniture de services, etc.) de son organisation entrepreneuriale.

EXEMPLE DE TABLEAU DE BORD: le diagramme en bandes représentant les 18 marchandises les plus vendues en terme de quantité.

3.14 CHARGES FINANCIÈRES

Figure 15: La fenêtre (non administrative) pour insérer 1 charge financière dans YERITH-PGI-9.0

1 CHARGE FINANCIÈRE est le coût d'1 produit ou service DONT L'ENTREPRISE À PAYER pour s'en approprier ou s'en servir.

1 LIGNE BUDGÉTAIRE est 1 compte financier duquel est extorqué des argents pour les acquisitions de l'organisation entrepreneuriale.

1 ligne budgétaire est généralement liée à 1 compte dans 1 institution bancaire.

LA CRÉATION D'1 CHARGE FINANCIÈRE DANS YERITH-PGI-9.0 demande au minimum les éléments suivants:

1. 1 **département de l'entreprise** (ce département peut être celui d'1 stock, etc.) qui a causé la charge financière

2. 1 **ligne budgétaire** de laquelle provient des fonds d'argents pour le paiement du produit et / ou service qui cause 1 charge financière
3. 1 **référence** : identification unique ALPHA-NUMÉRIQUE de cette dépense financière
4. 1 **désignation** (PEUT-ÊTRE À SOUHAIT LA MÊME désignation que la **référence sus-mentionnée**: identification unique ALPHA-NUMÉRIQUE de cette dépense financière
5. 1 **fournisseur** : PERSONNE PHYSIQUE OU MORALE, qui fournit le produit et / ou service objet de cette charge (dépense) financière
6. 1 **nombre de lots** : quantité totale de produits et / ou services de cette dépense financière
7. 1 **prix d'achat** : masse d'argent d'1 unité (1 lot) des produits et / ou services à acquérir pour cette dépense financière.

Figure 16: La fenêtre des charges financières dans YERITH-PGI-9.0

3.15 COMPTABILITÉ

Figure 17: La fenêtre de paramétrage de la comptabilité analytique dans YERITH–PGI–9.0

LA COMPTABILITÉ: REPRÉSENTE l'ensemble des processus et documents y afférents qui permettent de façon systématique de justifier les entrées et les sorties de monnaie (financières), des services, et des stocks de marchandises.

4 CONCLUSION

YERITH–PGI–9.0 permet le travail simultané et coordonné sur des données de gestion commerciale et / ou FINANCIÈRE par plusieurs utilisateurs d'une organisation entrepreneuriale.

Brochure D'information du progiciel de gestion intégré (PGI) YERITH-PGI-9.0

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]"

1 PARCOURS ACADÉMIQUE DE "Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]"

Figure 1: Portrait de YERITH-nissi.

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Table 1: YERITH-PGI-9.0 TÂCHES DES UTILISATEURS selon leur RÔLES !

Tâches	« Manager »	« Vendeur »	« Gestionnaire de stock »	« Magasinier »	« Caissier »
créer 1 rayon (département)	✓				
entrer 1 immobilisation / stock / service	✓	✓ (SERVICE)	✓ (immobilisation / STOCK)		
supprimer 1 immobilisation / stock	✓				
lister les immobilisations / stocks	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
modifier 1 immobilisation / stock	✓		✓		
transférer des immobilisations / stocks	✓		✓	✓	
sortir des immobilisations / stocks	✓		✓	✓	
modifier la stratégie de gestion des immobilisations / stocks (ex.: « FIFO », etc.)	✓	✓ (NON PERMANENT)	✓ (NON PERMANENT)		
vendre des marchandises	✓	✓			✓
accéder aux mouvements des immobilisations / stocks	✓		✓	✓	
gestion des achats	✓	✓	✓ (PARTIEL)		
gestion des FOURNISSEURS, RH	✓				
gestion des clients (CRM)	✓	✓ (PARTIEL)			
tableaux de bords	✓				
retour sur vente	✓				
accéder aux informations sur les ventes	✓	✓ (POUR SOI-MÊME)			

2 Introduction

yerith-pgi-3.0 est un Progiciel de Gestion Intégré (PGI).

Après son installation, yerith-pgi-3.0 est accessible à toute personne qui possède un compte d'utilisateur.

Les utilisateurs de yerith-pgi-3.0 ont les rôles ou niveaux d'accès suivants:

1. « Administrateur »
2. « Caissier »
3. « Gestionnaire de stock »
4. « Magasinier »
5. « Manager »
6. « Vendeur ».

yerith-pgi-3.0 permet de réaliser les tâches de gestion commerciales (Tableau 1, en fonction du rôle de l'utilisateur, comme suit:

1. créer 1 département (ex.: finance, immobilisations, stocks, etc.)
2. créer 1 rayon de vente
3. gérer des dépenses financières AVEC DES LIGNES BUDGÉTAIRES
4. manager des clients, et des fournisseurs, et des ressources humaines
5. manager des immobilisations (ex.: véhicules d'entreprise, etc.)
6. manager des stocks pour ventes
7. voir des tableaux de bords.

3 LES UTILISATIONS POTENTIELLES DE YERITH-PGI-9.0

1. BOURSE D'ÉCHANGE DE BIENS MOBILIERS OU IMMOBILIERS. Ceci puisse être utile pour des petites communautés sans DEVICES MOBILIÈRES
2. PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ POUR SUPER-MARCHÉS ET COMMERCES
3. BREF, TOUTE ORGANISATION ENTREPRENEURIALE.

4 Les atouts de yerith-pgi-3.0

1. 1 très grande stabilité de l'application
2. des utilisateurs avec des rôles bien spécifiés
3. 1 système d'alerte comportant des alertes paramétrées en fonction des quantités en stock ou des périodes de temps
4. la possibilité de générer des reçus au petit format pour des imprimantes thermiques, ou bien de générer des documents au format "A4"
5. Linux-Debian comme système d'exploitation, car très stable, performant, et moins vulnérable aux attaques des pirates informatiques en comparaison aux autres systèmes d'exploitation
6. 1 interface "ventes" qui permet au « Manager » d'avoir une vue d'ensemble des ventes (voir la Figure 2), et aussi d'effectuer des "retours sur ventes"
7. 1 interface "tableaux de bords" qui génère des rapports financiers, pour l'aide à la décision managériale du "business"

Figure 2: La fenêtre des ventes.

5 Le système d'alerte

Les utilisateurs aux rôles « Administrateur » ou « Manager » sont ceux capable de créer des alertes dans yerith-pgi-3.0. yerith-pgi-3.0 permet de créer des alertes pour:

1. 1 quantité d'articles restante en stock
2. 1 période de temps.

5.1 Alertes sur une quantité en stock

1 alerte sur la quantité en stock (X) d'1 produit est un message qui est généré lorsque la quantité en stock de ce produit atteint X.

Par exemple Xavier (« Manager ») crée une alerte sur le produit "mangue" qui se déclenche dès que sa quantité en stock atteint 100; 1 message est généré et envoyé à l'utilisateur Jean (« Magasinier »).

5.2 Alertes sur une période de temps

1 période de temps est définie par 1 date de début de période, et 1 date de fin de période.

1 alerte sur une période de temps pour un produit est un message qui est généré et qui reste existant dans yerith-pgi-3.0 durant toute la durée de cette période de temps.

Par exemple, un message d'alerte doit être envoyé à l'utilisateur Paul (« Caissier ») dès que la date du 05 Mai est atteinte afin que celui-ci applique un rabais de 20% sur chaque vente de yaourt 'trèsbon' durant une période de 2 semaines.

6 Le système de gestion de base-de-données

'MariaDB' est utilisé comme système de gestion de base de données. 'MariaDB' est très stable, très performant, et source-libre.

Des copies exécutables de 'MariaDB' peuvent être accessibles à très moindre coût (ex.: 0).

7 Conclusion

Figure 3: La fenêtre de visualisation de stocks.

La Figure 3 illustre la fenêtre de visualisation de stocks.

Figure 4: La fenêtre de vente.

La Figure 4 illustre la fenêtre pour faire les ventes d'articles.

yerith-pgi-3.0 est disponible dans les langues Anglais et Français.

YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 : ESSAI DE PRODUCTIVITÉ ENTREPRENEURIALE

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]"

CE LIVRET ESSAIE D'EXPLICITER COMMENT 1 ENTREPRISE DÉVELOPPE SES ACTIVITÉS DE FAÇON MAXIMALE AU PLAN D'1 PRODUCTIVITÉ EFFICACE GRÂCE AU PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0.

VERSION : 16 avril 2025

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Chapitre 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Motivations de ce LIVRET

CE LIVRET A POUR BUT D'EXPLIQUER COMMENT MAXIMISER LA PERFORMANCE D'1 ENTREPRISE GRÂCE AU PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0.

1.2 Structure De Ce LIVRET

Chapitre 2

PERFORMANCE D'UNE ENTREPRISE EN AFRIQUE

Ce chapitre vise à définir la performance d'une entreprise, apporter des éléments qui spécifient cette dernière, et montrer comment déterminer et évaluer rationnellement ces éléments de performance d'entreprise à l'aide DU PROGRAMME DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0.

2.1 Définition d'Entreprise Commerciale

Une entreprise commerciale est une entité organisationnelle qui vise à faire des gains financiers en échange de services et/ou de marchandises pour des individus ou pour d'autres entités organisationnelles.

Quelques exemples d'entreprises commerciales au Cameroun et au monde :

1. Mercedes-Benz (RFA ¹)
2. Walmart (États-Unis D'Amérique)
3. Cameroon Telecommunication (Camtel) (Cameroun)
4. Santa Lucia (Cameroun)
5. Supermarché DÔVV (Cameroun)
6. etc.

1. République Fédérale D'Allemagne.

2.2 Sécurité Au Sein De L'entreprise

NOS recherches et expériences sur le terrain nous démontre à suffisance que les éléments de sécurités externes et internes à l'entreprise entrepreneuriale sont des suivants par ordre d'importance :

- 1.) ***LA SAINTE BIBLE*** : en effet, l'entrepreneur et / ou chef d'entreprise se doit de posséder 1 sainte BIBLE avant toute chose Puisque des paroles de Bonnes œuvres et vies proviennent de ce livre sacré qui est aussi le livre le plus ancien sur cette terre et UNIVERS humain.

Nous recommandons 1 heure au minimum de lecture de versets bibliques par journée de vie; Et non de TRAVAIL. Personnellement je peux conseiller par exemple des versets suivants :

- o ["Esaïe 45"](#)
- o ["Sophonie 1"](#)
- o ["PSAUMES 140"](#)
- o ["PSAUMES 144 : 11 – 15"](#)
- o ["PSAUMES 23"](#)
- o ["HABACUC 3 : 15 – 19"](#)
- o etc.

2.3 Définition De Performance

La performance est une évaluation des activités d'une entreprise commerciale aux fins de justifier si cette dernière est rentable ou plus.

Une entreprise commerciale est rentable lorsqu'elle produit des bénéfices (ou encore des surplus d'argents par rapport au **Capital** investit).

CAPITAL: : matériels physiques (aussi appelés IMMOBILISATIONS), et / ou sommes financières investies pour faire fonctionner l'entreprise commerciale.

2.4 Paramètres de Concurrence

Des paramètres de concurrence sont des éléments qui influent sur l'attractivité d'1 entreprise commerciale :

1. 1 site internet (WWW : world wide web) AUX FINS DE DISTRIBUER SES INFORMATIONS COMMERCIALES ET DE SERVICES.
2. 1 accessibilité facile (ou encore dégagée)
3. 1 accessibilité propre
4. des plaques publicitaires bien visibles
5. des plaques publicitaires (ou encore rabats, ou promotions) bien visibles
6. des prémisses (ou encore infrastructures) dégagées
7. des prémisses (ou encore infrastructures) propres
8. des prémisses (ou encore infrastructures) aérées (ou encore ventilées, ou bien climatisées)
9. des prémisses (ou encore infrastructures) sentant bon
10. des prémisses (ou encore infrastructures) avec des passages et/ou allées dégagés (ou en encore non encombrés)
11. des prix clairement affichés
12. des prix à l'unité clairement affichés
13. 1 très bonne sécurité des biens, des immobilisations, et des personnes sur les prémisses (ou encore infrastructures)
14. 1 visibilité (ou encore publicité) sur le marché voulu

2.5 Paramètres de Performance

Figure 2.1 – Une image du PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ (ERP en anglais) YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0.

Des paramètres de performance sont des éléments qui, lorsque maximaux, démontrent 1 rentabilité positive d'1 entreprise commerciale :

1. 1 site internet (WWW : world wide web) AUX FINS DE DISTRIBUER SES INFORMATIONS COMMERCIALES ET DE SERVICES.
2. 1 **dissociation accrue et / ou élevée entre la famille de l'entrepreneur – investisseur, et ses affaires commerciales (Exception faites au niveau des actionnaires ou du TRÈS-HAUT management)**
3. 1 **visibilité maximale et informatisée sur des transactions commerciales de l'entreprise;**
4. 1 **Progiciel de gestion intégré simple et facile à ré-utiliser et / ou à entretenir, À TRÈS BAS COÛTS;**

Chapitre 3

Processus D'1 Entreprise En Afrique

Ce chapitre donne des canevas et / ou modèles (exemples) à partir desquels 1 organisation entrepreneuriale peut développer ses processus de fonctionnements (en anglais aussi nommés "**BUSINESS MODEL**").

3.1 Visions et Objectifs D'1 Organisation Entrepreneuriale

Il est primordial et très important de définir 1 vision (ou encore 1 objectif idéal; 1 but idéal à atteindre dans le monde physique et / ou matériel avant de prendre 1 décision pour la création d'1 organisation entrepreneuriale []) (ex. : S.A.R.L, START-UP; O.N.G., etc.).

Exemple de vision d'1 organisation entrepreneuriale :

- YERITH_{r&d} : vulgariser et simplifier l'utilisation de l'outil informatique dans la gestion des organisations entrepreneuriales du monde moderne.
- augmenter la consommation du chou vert vendu en boîte de conserve sans additifs chimiques nocifs à la santé.
- réduire les consommations de pétrole; au profit de l'énergie éolienne.

Le libellé d'1 vision et objectif entrepreneuriale devrait se limiter à 1 phrase au présent, à l'actif et non passif.

3.2 Ressources de Fonctionnements

3.2.1 Ressources Humaines

3.2.1.1 Acquisition des Ressources Humaines

3.2.1.2 Salaires et Émoluments

Figure 3.1 – Une image d'un fenêtrage illustrative des groupes d'employés d'un travailleur.

SALAIRE CUMULÉ D'UN EMPLOYÉ:

SALAIRE PAR GROUPE D'APPARTENANCE D'UN EMPLOYÉ:

GROUPES D'APPARTENANCE D'UN EMPLOYÉ:

GROUPE D'EMPLOYÉS:

GROUPE DE PAIE:

3.2.2 Ressources Informatiques et / ou Digitales

YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0

3.2.2.1 Acquisition des Ressources Informatiques et / ou Digitales

3.2.2.2 Réseau Informatique D'entreprise

1. L'ordinateur (**OBLIGATOIRE**)

2. L'écran (**OBLIGATOIRE**)

3. Le tiroir de caisse (**FACULTATIF**)

4. L'imprimante de tickets PDV (thermique) (**FACULTATIF**)

5. Le lecteur de code barres (**FACULTATIF**)

6. 1 routeur (**OBLIGATOIRE**)

7. La tablette numérique (**FACULTATIF**)

8. L'ordinateur 2 en 1 (**FACULTATIF**)

9. 1 terminal (NC-300) à plusieurs utilisateurs (**FACULTATIF**)

3.2.2.3 Maintenance Du Matériel Informatique et / ou Digital

3.2.3 Ressources Matérielles

3.2.3.1 Acquisition des Ressources Matérielles

3.3 Processus de Ventes Aux Clients

Chapitre 4

YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 AU CENTRE DE LA PERFORMANCE ENTREPRENEURIALE

Ce chapitre a pour but de prouver l'efficacité de YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 dans la maximisation des gains financiers d'une entreprise commerciale et / ou organisationnelle en Afrique.

Figure 4.1 – Yerith-Erp-9.0-platiNum PROCESSUS des affaires courantes.

Figure 4.2 – Yerith-Erp-9.0-platiNum PROCESSUS des composantes logicielles.

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Chapitre 6

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YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 :
NOTIONS DE COMPTABILITÉ ET DE
SYSTÈME O.H.A.D.A

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]"

VERSION : 16 avril 2025

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1.1 Motivations DE CE PAMPHLET

CE PAMPHLET A POUR BUT DE SIMPLIFIER LA REPRÉSENTATION ET COMPRÉHENSION DU SYSTÈME COMPTABLE O.H.A.D.A, UTILISÉ EN AFRIQUE FRANCO-PHONE!

1.2 Structure De Ce Pamphlet

Chapitre 2

CONCLUSION

GUIDE D'INSTALLATION POUR LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ (PGI) YERITH-PGI-9.0

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]"

VERSION : 16 avril 2025

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Chapitre 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Typographie

Toutes les commandes dans ce guide décrites de la manière suivante :

`commande`

sont à être exécutées en tant "super utilisateur" ("utilisateur root").

1.2 HARDWARE

1.2.1 RÉOLUTION DE L'ÉCRAN (desktop)

YERITH-PGI-9.0 est utilisé de meilleure résolution d'écran 22 pouces et plus!

1.2.2 Mémoire vive (RAM : random access memory)

YERITH-PGI-9.0 peut être utilisé par un ordinateur qui possède un minimum de 512 Mo de mémoire RAM (mémoire vive) sans aucun problème.

CEPENDANT, NOUS RECOMMANDONS L'UTILISATION D'ORDINATEURS AYANT UN MINIMUM DE 2 GO DE MÉMOIRE RAM.

1.3 Logiciels Prérequis

Tableau 1.1 – Logiciels requis pour l'installation de YERITH-PGI-9.0.

Logiciels	Versions
Debian	11.1 (bullseye)
gdebi	0.9.5.7 + nmu5
mariadb-server	10.5.12-0 + deb11u1
mariadb-client	10.5.12-0 + deb11u1
Qt	5.15.2
Texlive	2020.20210202-3

1.4 Fichiers Requis pour la Procédure D'installation

Tableau 1.2 – Fichiers requis pour l'installation de YERITH-PGI-9.0.

Fichiers
"yerith-erp-9-0-standalone.deb"
"yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data.deb"
"yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon.deb"

Le tableau 1.2 illustre les fichiers requis pour l'installation de YERITH-PGI-9.0.

Chapitre 2

INSTALLATION AUTOMATISÉE avec gdebi-gtk OU gdebi

Figure 2.1 – Interface graphique de Gdebi (Gdebi-gtk).

2.1 Installation De gdebi-gtk Et De gdebi

1. Ouvrir un terminal "bash"
2. Taper la commande suivante :

```
apt -y install gdebi-gtk gdebi
```

2.2 Installation Avec gdebi-gtk

1. Ouvrir un terminal "bash"
2. Taper la commande suivante :

```
gdebi-gtk yerith-erp-9-0-standalone.deb
```

3. cliquez sur le bouton "Install Package"
4. répétez la commande précédente avec les fichiers "**yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data.deb**" et "**yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon.deb**" respectivement.

2.3 Installation Avec gdebi

1. Ouvrir un terminal "bash"
2. Taper la commande suivante :

```
gdebi -n yerith-erp-9-0-standalone.deb
```
3. répétez la commande précédente avec les fichiers "**yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data.deb**" et "**yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon.deb**" respectivement.

Chapitre 3

PROCÉDURE D'INSTALLATION (manuelle) DE LA BASE-DE-DONNÉES SUR 1-DESKTOP-SERVEUR-RÉSEAU

3.1 Étapes D'installation De La Base-De-Données Sur 1-DESKTOP-SERVEUR-RÉSEAU

Il faut suivre les étapes suivantes pour obtenir une installation de la BASE-DE-DONNÉES du PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0 sur 1-DESKTOP-SERVEUR-RÉSEAU sans problèmes :

1. installer le logiciel `mariadb-server` sur (1-DESKTOP-SERVEUR-RÉSEAU)
2. configurer le logiciel `mariadb-server` sur (1-DESKTOP-SERVEUR-RÉSEAU)
modifier SI NÉCESSAIRE LE FICHIER `'/etc/mysql/mariadb.conf.d/50-server.cnf'` sur (1-DESKTOP-SERVEUR-RÉSEAU).

3.2 Installation de `mariadb-server` SUR 1-DESKTOP-SERVEUR-RÉSEAU

1. Ouvrir un terminal "bash"
2. Taper la commande suivante :

```
apt -y install mariadb-server mariadb-client
```

3.3 Modifier SI NÉCESSAIRE LE FICHIER '/etc/mysql/mariadb.conf.d/50-server.cnf'

S.V.P., BIEN VOULOIR EXÉCUTER LES CHANGEMENTS SUIVANTS SI VOUS SOUHAITER que votre base de données du pgi YERITH-PGI-9.0 SOIT ACCESSIBLE EN RÉSEAU-LAN-WAN.

1. changer, ceci (fichier '/etc/mysql/mariadb.conf.d/50-server.cnf') 'bind-address = 127.0.0.1' à 'bind-address = YE.YF.YG.YH' où 'YE.YF.YG.YH' est l'adresse locale IP du SERVEUR DE BASE DE DONNÉES À DISTANCE
2. enfin exécuter le commande suivante, AFIN DE REDÉMARRER les serveur de base de données 'mariadb-server' :

```
service mariadb restart
```

Chapitre 4

Procédure D'installation (manuelle) Du PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0

4.1 Étapes D'installation Du PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0

Il faut suivre les étapes suivante pour obtenir une installation de YERITH-PGI-9.0 qui fonctionne sans problèmes :

1. installer les logiciels gdebi et expect
2. installer enfin YERITH-PGI-9.0 (Qt et Texlive sont installé automatiquement)
3. **MODIFIER SI NÉCESSAIRE LE FICHER DE CONFIGURATION 'yerith-erp-3-0.properties' POUR AVOIR ACCÈS À LA BASE-DE-DONNÉES DU PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0**

4.2 Installation de gdebi et expect

1. Ouvrir un terminal "bash"
2. Taper la commande suivante :

```
apt -y install gdebi expect
```

4.3 Installation de Qt, Texlive, et de YERITH-PGI-9.0

1. Ouvrir un terminal "bash"

2. ensuite entrer y la commande suivante :

```
gdebi -n yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data.deb
```

3. puis :

```
gdebi -n yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon.deb
```

4. FINALEMENT, EXÉCUTER LA COMMANDE :

```
gdebi -n yerith-erp-9-0-standalone.deb
```

Cette commande installe automatiquement Qt et Texlive.

5. Entrer le mot de passe de l'utilisateur "root" du logiciel mariadb-server lorsque cela vous sera demandé;

Ceci est requis pour l'installation de la base de données "yerith_erp_3".

4.4 EXEMPLE de réseau de 2 ordinateurs

Figure 4.1 – Exemple de configuration réseau possédant 2 ordinateurs.

4.5 Exemple de configuration réseau multi-sites

Figure 4.2 – Exemple de configuration réseau multi-sites.

4.6 MODIFIER SI NÉCESSAIRE LE FICHIER DE CONFIGURATION 'yerith-erp-3-0.properties' POUR AVOIR ACCÈS À LA BASE-DE-DONNÉES DU PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0

S.V.P., BIEN VOULOIR EXÉCUTER LES CHANGEMENTS SUIVANTS SI VOUS SOUHAITER CONNECTER VOTRE INSTALLATION LOCALE DE YERITH-PGI-9.0 À 1-SERVEUR-EN-RÉSEAU :

1. Le fichier 'YERITH-ERP-3-0.PROPERTIES' est situé dans le disque dur de votre installation à l'URL : '/opt/yerith-erp-3-0-standalone-configurations-data'
2. modifiez la ligne du fichier 'YERITH-ERP-3-0.PROPERTIES' de 'db_ip_address=localhost' à 'db_ip_address=YE.YF.YG.YH' SELON QUE 'YE.YF.YG.YH' REPRÉSENTE l'adresse IP du serveur de base de données.

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Annexe A

L'utilisateur Standard (Administrateur) 'admin'

Après l'installation avec succès de [YERITH-PGI-9.0](#), l'application est accessible par l'utilisation d'un compte utilisateur standard avec le rôle d'administrateur en utilisant les données suivantes :

1. nom d'utilisateur : **admin**
2. mot de passe : **admin1**

Ce compte *administrateur* peut être modifié selon votre volonté.

Annexe B

COMMENT FAIRE FONCTIONNER 1 IMPRIMANTE THERMIQUE DANS 'YERITH-PGI-9.0'

Annexe C

DES FICHIERS DE PRÉFÉRENCES POUR 1 UTILISATEUR DE 'YERITH-PGI-9.0'

Annexe D

DES FICHIERS DE CONFIGURATIONS POUR LE PGI-ERP 'YERITH-PGI-9.0'

Annexe E

VARIABLES D'ENVIRONNEMENTS DE 'YERITH-PGI-9.0'

Annexe F

COMMENT DÉINSTALLER 'YERITH-PGI-9.0'

1. Ouvrir un terminal "bash"

2. taper la commande suivante :

```
apt -y --purge remove yerith-erp-9-0-standalone
```

3. ensuite la commande suivante :

```
apt -y --purge remove yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data
```


Annexe G

COMMENT DÉINSTALLER 'YERITH-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON'

1. Ouvrir un terminal "bash"
2. Taper la commande suivante :

```
apt -y --purge remove yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon
```

GUIDE PRATIQUE DU LOGICIEL DE GESTION COMMERCIALE ET FINANCIÈRE YERITH-PGI-9.0

"PROGRAMME ET CODE SOURCE OUVERT ET LIBRE"

"Xavier Noubbissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]"

LES CODES SOURCES, OUVERT ET LIBRE, ET CE,
DANS TOUS LES SENS DU TERME SONT
LOCALISÉS AUX ADRESSES INTERNET
SUIVANTES :

Ce LIVRE DE GESTION COMMERCIALE explique de manière simplistique le rôle de YERITH-PGI-9.0, et dorénavant, sera le guide pragmatique de son utilisateur.

VERSION : 16 avril 2025

1. YERITH-PGI-9.0, code source (non exécutable) :
<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0>
2. YERITH-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON, code source (non exécutable) :
<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon>

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Chapitre 1

Introduction

Cette introduction vise à fournir aux utilisateurs de mon PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ les prérequis nécessaires à son utilisation (**PARAMÉTRAGE, NAVIGATION, ET MANIPULATION DES LIENS DE L'APPLICATION YERITH-PGI-9.0 EN GÉNÉRAL!**)

1.1 MOTIVATIONS IDÉOLOGIQUES DE CE LIVRE

NOUS ÉDITONS CE LIVRE aux fins suivantes :

1. VULGARISER L'UTILISATION SIMPLISTIQUE D'1 ERP-PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0 [uNu22].

1.2 STRUCTURE DE CE LIVRE

ce livre est structuré comme suit :

1. chapitre 1 : INTRODUCTION AUX NOTIONS DE BASES, MOTIVATIONS IDÉOLOGIQUES DE CE LIVRE, éléments graphiques revues, paramétrages, et fonctions récurrentes dans YERITH-PGI-9.0.
2. chapitre 2 : TOUTE FONCTION UTILE ET RÉCURRENTE À TOUT UTILISATEUR EST TRAITÉE DANS CE CHAPITRE.
3. chapitre 3 : CE CHAPITRE DÉFINIT DES CAS USUELS D'UTILISATIONS D'1 ORGANISATION ENTREPRENEURIALE GÉNÉRIQUE. IL S'AGIT ENTRE AUTRES des créations des ressources entrepreneuriales, de leur transfert et/ou ventes, etc.
4. chapitre 4 : ce chapitre vise à démontrer que YERITH-PGI-9.0 peut être employé pour des organisations entrepreneuriales spécifiques! IL S'AGIT EN PARTICULIER D'ORGANISATIONS ENTREPRENEURIALES QUI POURVOIENT DES SERVICES!
5. chapitre 5 : "**TABLEAUX DE BORDS**" VISE À PRÉSENTER AU LECTEUR DES DIFFÉRENTES MÉTHODES POUR VISUALISER DES ACTIVITÉS COMMERCIALES (ventes, transferts, etc.) d'1 ORGANISATION ENTREPRENEURIALE DANS YERITH-PGI-9.0!
6. chapitre 6 : CONCLUSION!

1.3 NOTIONS DE BASE DE GESTION COMMERCIALE

PUISSE LE LECTEUR SE RÉFÉRER au document 'YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 : BROCHURE DE GESTION COMMERCIALE' [uNu21b] pour avoir accès à **toutes les connaissances théoriques et pratiques des sciences de gestion et/ou marketing** utiles et/ou nécessaires à une bonne compréhension de ce livre pratique et UTILE DU pgi (progiciel de gestion intégré) YERITH-PGI-9.0 [uNu18, uNu22]!

1.4 NOTIONS DE BASE D'INFORMATIQUE DE GESTION COMMERCIALE

PUISSE LE LECTEUR SE RÉFÉRER aux documents suivants pour avoir accès à **des connaissances de bases et pratiques en informatique de gestion commerciale** :

- 1) YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 : DOCUMENT COMBINANT LES PRÉSENTATIONS DE YERITH-PGI-9.0 [uNu21c]
- 2) GUIDE D'INSTALLATION POUR LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-9.0 [uNu21a].

1.5 NOTIONS DE BASE DE COMPTABILITÉ ET SYSTÈME OHADA

1.6 PHILOSOPHIE DES FENÊTRES PAR FONCTIONNALITÉS

1.7 ÉLÉMENTS GRAPHIQUES

YERITH-PGI-9.0 a été implémenté avec l'aide de la bibliothèque graphique Qt [Ltd22]!

1.7.1 GÉNÉRALITÉS

Figure 1.1 – Des différents éléments graphiques d'une fenêtre conventionnelle de YERITH-PGI-9.0.

Chaque fenêtre de gestion commerciale peut contenir des éléments suivants :

1. 1 barre de menu
2. 1 barre d'outils
3. des boutons de navigations (boutons de couleur noire) et des boutons d'actions (boutons de couleur AUTRE QUE noire)
4. 1 tableau des éléments à manipuler
5. des éléments graphiques pour filtrer des résultats du tableau
6. des éléments graphiques aux fins de navigation des résultats du tableau
7. des champs textuels non modifiables aux fins d'afficher des données du tableau.

1.7.2 CONTEXTES DES TABLEAUX

Figure 1.2 – La fenêtre de visualisation des paiements pour clients et/ou fournisseurs.

	Nom Entreprise	Montant payé	Compte client (après)	Type de paiement	Désignation	Référenc
1	DR-ING	-201,00	0,00	décaissement (retour achat)	test_yeroth_1	:
2	DR.-ING. XAVIER	-1 206,00	0,00	décaissement (retour achat)	test_yeroth_1	:
3	DR.-ING. XAVIER	-402,00	0,00	décaissement (retour achat)	test_yeroth_1	:
4	DR.-ING. XAVIER	-603,00	0,00	décaissement (retour achat)	test_yeroth_1	:
5	DR.-ING. XAVIER	-402,00	0,00	décaissement (retour achat)	test_yeroth_1	:
6	DR-ING	-603,00	0,00	décaissement (retour achat)	test_yeroth_2	1
7	DR.-ING. XAVIER	-402,00	0,00	décaissement (retour achat)	test_yeroth_1	:

Summary statistics from the screenshot:

- # lignes: 59
- 1 / 1
- # paiements: 11
- # clients: 3
- décaissé (débité): -5 151,00 FCFA
- encaissé (crédité): 0,00 FCFA
- Type d'entreprise: client
- réinitialiser

L'INTITULÉ DES COLONNES D'1 TABLEAU dans YERITH-PGI-9.0 est dépendante du contexte du titre de la fenêtre :

- 1) PAR EXEMPLE; dans la fenêtre de visualisation des paiements pour clients et/ou fournisseurs présentée dans la figure 1.2, la colonne "Désignation" veut signifier 1 désignation DU PRODUIT VENDU ET RETOURNER!
- 2) PAR EXEMPLE; dans la fenêtre de visualisation de charges financières présentée dans la figure 1.3, la colonne "Désignation" veut signifier 1 désignation d'1 charge financière!

Figure 1.3 – La fenêtre de visualisation de CHARGES FINANCIÈRES.

1.8 Connexion à 1 autre localisation (succursale du réseau CONNECTÉ) dans YERITH-PGI-9.0

1.9 PARAMÉTRAGES DANS YERITH-PGI-9.0

1.9.1 INTRODUCTION

Tableau 1.1 – Types de paramètres de l'application PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0 et du système d'alertes et de sauvegardes automatisées.

TYPES DE PARAMÈTRES	UTILISATEURS MODIFICATEURS
paramètres locaux	<i>Administrateur, Manager</i>
paramètres serveurs	<i>Manager</i>

Tous les paramètres du PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0 sont centralisés dans la section "ADMINISTRATION".

Il existe des **paramètres locaux** (enregistrés sur le disque dur de l'ordinateur de l'utilisateur), et des **paramètres serveurs** (enregistrés dans la base de données du PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0) :

1. Des **paramètres locaux** influencent uniquement des instances du PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0 dans l'ordinateur de l'utilisateur, et sont modifiables par 1 **Administrateur** ou 1 **Manager**.
2. Des **paramètres serveurs** influencent TOUTES LES INSTANCES DU PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0 QUI SONT RATTACHÉES AU SERVEUR DE BASE DE DONNÉES EN QUESTION!
Des paramètres serveurs sont modifiables UNIQUEMENT par 1 **Manager**.

Tous les types de paramètres et les utilisateurs responsables de leurs modifications sont illustrés dans le TABLEAU 1.1.

TOUS PARAMÈTRE LOCAL OU SERVEUR EST SOIT :

1. 1 **paramètre de l'application erp (pgi)** (SECTION 1.9.2)
2. 1 **paramètre du système d'alertes et de sauvegardes automatisées** (SECTION 1.9.3).

1.9.2 PARAMÈTRES DE L'APPLICATION ERP (PGI)

Figure 1.4 – La fenêtre de paramétrage du PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0.

1 paramètre de l'application erp (pgi) YERITH-PGI-9.0 est 1 valeur qui influence ses comportements du PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0 lors de son exécution : **le format des reçus ("petit ", "A4 ", ou "A5 ") en est 1 exemple!**

1.9.3 PARAMÈTRES DU SYSTÈME D'ALERTES ET DE SAUVEGARDE AUTOMATISÉE DE LA BASE DE DONNÉES

Figure 1.5 – La fenêtre de paramétrage du système d'alertes, et du système de sauvegarde automatisée.

1 paramètre du système d'alertes, et du système de sauvegarde automatisée YERITH-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON est 1 valeur qui influence ses comportements lors de son exécution : **le répertoire de sauvegarde des bases de données MySQL de YERITH-PGI-9.0 EN EST 1 EXEMPLE!**

Chapitre 2

Fonctions Récurrentes de L'UTILISATEUR DE YERITH-PGI-9.0

Ce Chapitre présente des utilités génériques d'utilisations pour 1 utilisateur dans YERITH-PGI-9.0.

2.1 Localisation dans YERITH-PGI-9.0

Figure 2.1 – La fenêtre de visualisation de stocks.

	Désignation	Catégorie	Prix vente (TTC)	Qté totale	Date péremption
1	test_yeroth_1	test_yeroth_categorie_1	201,00	12	01.07.2023
2	test_yeroth_1	test_yeroth_categorie_1	201,00	12	01.12.2022
3	test_yeroth_2	test_yeroth_categorie_2	222,00	6	06.06.2023

VOUS POUVEZ TOUJOURS CONNAÎTRE DANS QUELLE FENÊTRE DE NAVIGATION VOUS VOUS TROUVEZ EN 1 MOMENT PRÉCIS GRÂCE À LA LECTURE DU TITRE DE CETTE FENÊTRE!

Prenez pour exemple **la fenêtre de visualisation de IMMOBILISATIONS/stocks (Figure 2.1), DONT LE TITRE EST : "Yerith-pgi-3.0 – FICHE DES Stocks – FIFO"!**

2.2 Créer 1 Compte Utilisateur (**)

Figure 2.2 – La fenêtre d'accueil de L'ADMINISTRATION YERITH-PGI-9.0.

✓ Procédure pour créer un compte utilisateur

1. À partir de la fenêtre d'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 2.2), on clique sur "l'onglet" intitulé **opérations**
2. Choisir '**créer**' dans le 'combo box' "opérations"
3. Choisir '**un compte utilisateur**' dans le 'combo box' "objets".
Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 2.3
4. Saisissez les informations requises dans les champs de textes
5. Cliquer sur le 'bouton' "Enregistrer" pour valider votre travail.

Figure 2.3 – La fenêtre "créer un compte utilisateur".

Yeroth-pgi-3.0 ~ administration ~ créer

Actions Outils Aide

Menu principal

Créer Lister Administration Modifier Supprimer

Alerte Bon de commande Catégorie Compte bancaire Compte utilisateur Départements de produits Local

Données personnelles de l'utilisateur

prénoms [* champ de texte obligatoire]

noms [* champ de texte obligatoire]

titre

lieu de naissance

date de naissance 16/06/2022

ville

province / état

pays

boîte postale

email @

numéro de téléphone 1

numéro de téléphone 2

données de connexion

nom d'utilisateur [* champ de texte obligatoire]

mot de passe [* champ de texte obligatoire]

vérification du mot de passe [* champ de texte obligatoire]

rôle

localisation YEROTH_RD_TEST

Annuler Enregistrer

2.3 Supprimer 1 Compte Utilisateur (**)

Figure 2.4 – La fenêtre "lister les comptes utilisateurs".

✓ Procédure pour supprimer un compte utilisateur

1. À partir de la fenêtre d'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 2.2), on clique sur 'l'onglet' intitulé "opérations"
2. Choisir '**supprimer**' dans le 'combo box' "opérations"
3. Choisir '**un compte utilisateur**' dans le 'combo box' "objets".
Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 2.4
4. Sélectionner le compte utilisateur à supprimer dans la liste des comptes utilisateurs affichée
5. Cliquer sur le 'bouton' "Supprimer".
La question est ensuite posée si vous confirmer votre choix (figure 2.5)!
Cliquer sur le 'bouton' "OK" pour confirmer votre choix!

Figure 2.5 – La fenêtre "supprimer un compte utilisateur".

2.4 SÉLECTIONNER DES COLONNES VISIBLES D'1 TABLEAU

Figure 2.6 – La fenêtre "Sélectionner des colonnes visibles d'1 tableau".

✓ Procédure pour sélectionner des colonnes visibles d'1 tableau

1. À partir de la fenêtre du tableau, cliquez sur l'icône ¹ () avec 1 signe **PLUS (+)** dans son intérieur
2. Ensuite, sélectionner des colonnes d'1 tableau en cochant sur des 'check box' correspondants tel que illustrée à la figure 2.6!

✓ **INFLUENCES AUX PRÉFÉRENCES PERSONNELLES DE L'UTILISATEUR:** LA POSITION DE CHAQUE COLONNE SÉLECTIONNÉE, AINSI QUE SA PRÉSENCE EST AUTOMATIQUEMENT ENREGISTRÉE COMME DANS LES PRÉFÉRENCES personnelles de l'utilisateur courant, par YERITH-PGI-9.0.

AINSI, CHAQUE NOUVELLE MODIFICATION, soit de la position, ou encore de la sélection d'1 colonne est automatiquement remarquée par le pgi YERITH-PGI-9.0 **sans aucune intervention mécanique** de l'utilisateur!

1. copiée du site web <https://www.iconshock.com>

2.5 IMPRIMER EN VERTICALE (portrait)

Figure 2.7 – La fenêtre "Impression de document – verticale (portrait)".

✓ Procédure pour imprimer 1 document en verticale

1. À partir de la fenêtre du tableau, cliquez sur l'icône ² ()
2. Ensuite, cliquez sur le 'bouton de radio' "VERTICALE (portrait)" tel que illustrée dans la figure 2.7!

✓ **INFLUENCES AUX PRÉFÉRENCES PERSONNELLES DE L'UTILISATEUR :** LA POSITION D'IMPRESSION SÉLECTIONNÉE : "VERTICALE", pour la fenêtre en cours d'utilisation EST AUTOMATIQUEMENT ENREGISTRÉE COMME DANS LES PRÉFÉRENCES personnelles de l'utilisateur courant, par YERITH-PGI-9.0.

AINSI, CHAQUE NOUVELLE MODIFICATION, soit de la POSITION D'IMPRESSION, OU ENCORE DES COLONNES DU TABLEAU SÉLECTIONNÉES, est automatiquement remarquée par le pgi YERITH-PGI-9.0 **sans aucune intervention mécanique** de l'utilisateur!

2. copiée du site web <https://www.iconshock.com>

2.6 IMPRIMER EN HORIZONTALE (paysage)

Figure 2.8 – La fenêtre "Impression de document – horizontale (paysage)".

✓ Procédure pour imprimer 1 document en horizontale

1. À partir de la fenêtre du tableau, cliquez sur l'icône ()
2. Ensuite, cliquez sur le 'bouton de radio' "HORIZONTALE (paysage)" tel que illustrée dans la figure 2.8!

✓ **INFLUENCES AUX PRÉFÉRENCES PERSONNELLES DE L'UTILISATEUR :** LA POSITION D'IMPRESSION SÉLECTIONNÉE : "HORIZONTALE", pour la fenêtre en cours d'utilisation EST AUTOMATIQUÉMENT ENREGISTRÉE COMME DANS LES PRÉFÉRENCES personnelles de l'utilisateur courant, par YERITH-PGI-9.0.

AINSI, CHAQUE NOUVELLE MODIFICATION, soit de la POSITION D'IMPRESSION, OU ENCORE DES COLONNES DU TABLEAU SÉLECTIONNÉES, est automatiquement remarquée par le pgi YERITH-PGI-9.0 **sans aucune intervention mécanique** de l'utilisateur!

2.7 ACCÉDER À L'HISTORIQUE D'1 IMMOBILISATION / Stock

Figure 2.9 – L'historique d'1 stock.

	Date	Heure	Type d'opération	ID de l'opération	Qté initiale en stock	Qté en mouvement	Qté restante en stock
1	02.06.2022	06:41:50	ENTRÉE	1	0,00	(+)1,00	1,00
2	06.06.2022	12:07:47	RÉ-APPROVISIONNEMENT	1	1,00	(+)11,00	12,00

L'historique d'1 immobilisation / stock est 1 journal qui regroupe de façon chronologique des éléments suivants :

1. données d'insertion
2. données de locations
3. données de réapprovisionnement
4. données de sorties
5. données de transferts
6. données de ventes.

✓ **AGRANDISSEMENT DE L'HISTORIQUE D'1 IMMOBILISATION / Stock :** DANS YERITH-PGI-9.0, SI L'HISTORIQUE D'1 IMMOBILISATION/Stock n'est pas désactivée, **cet historique n'est plus agrandi si sa limite accordée dans la base de données de YERITH-PGI-9.0 EST ATTEINTE (6.500 CARACTÈRES DE TYPE "varchar")!**

Figure 2.10 – La fenêtre de visualisation de stocks.

The screenshot shows the 'FICHE DES STOCKS - FIFO' window. At the top, there are menu items 'Actions', 'Outils', and 'Aide'. Below that is a toolbar with various icons. The main area contains several buttons: 'Achats STOCKS OU IMMOBILISATIONS', 'Afficher', 'Menu', 'Entrer une immobilisation, un stock, un service', and 'Marchandises / SERVICES'. A search bar is present with the text 'terme à rechercher (description de l'article (ou service))' and a dropdown menu set to 'FIFO'. The table below has the following data:

	Désignation	Catégorie	Prix vente (TTC)	Qté totale	Date péremption
1	test_yeroth_1	test_yeroth_categorie_1	201,00	12	01.07.2023
2	test_yeroth_1	test_yeroth_categorie_1	201,00	12	01.12.2022
3	test_yeroth_2	test_yeroth_categorie_2	222,00	6	06.06.2023

At the bottom, there are summary statistics and filters:

- # lignes: 59
- 1 / 1
- #stocks: 3
- Début: 01/01/2022
- Fin: 19/06/2022
- filtres:
- Montant TVA: <
- réinitialiser filtre
- filtrer
- Catégorie
- valeur à rechercher
- réinitialiser
- # d'articles: 30
- Valeur d'inv.: 3 600,00 FCFA
- type de inventaire: STOCKS
- réinitialiser

✓ Procédure pour accéder à l'historique d'1 immobilisation / stock

1. À partir de la fenêtre "FICHE DES STOCKS OU IMMOBILISATIONS" (figure 2.10), sélectionnez l'IMMOBILISATION/stock dont vous souhaitez consulter l'historique

2. Ensuite, cliquez sur l'icône ³ ()!

3. copiée du site web <https://www.iconshock.com>

2.8 DÉSACTIVER L'HISTORIQUE D'1 IMMOBILISATION / Stock

2.8.1 À L'Insertion D'1 IMMOBILISATION / Stock

Figure 2.11 – La fenêtre pour désactiver 1 stock et / ou IMMOBILISATION (DURANT L'INSERTION).

Yeroth-pgi-3.0 - entrer 1 IMMOBILISATION, OU 1 stock, ou 1 service

Actions Outils Aide

Annuler INSÉRER Menu Immobilisations / Stocks Sortir ou Transférer DES Immobilisations / STOCKS

Caractéristiques d'un(e) immobilisation / stock / service

Choix

- insérer 1 immobilisation
- insérer 1 stock
- insérer 1 charge financière
- vente d'1 service à un client

département produit

catégorie

référence

désignation [* champ de texte obligatoire]

fournisseur

nombre de lots 1,00 quantité [* champ d...]

quantité totale achat

prix d'achat [* champ de texte obligatoire]

Description

prix de vente (TTC) 0.00 %

prix de vente en gros (TTC) %

AJOUTER TVA 7.25 % historique désac

péréemption (date) 08/06/2022

localisation STOCK

stock d'alerte

référence reçu d'achat

Image de l'immobilisation / stock / service

supprimer l'image sélectionner une image

Durant l'insertion d'1 immobilisation / stock, il suffit de décocher le 'checkbox' "historique désac.". pour qu'aucun journal d'historique ne soit créé pour l'immobilisation / stock!

2.8.2 À La Modification D'1 IMMOBILISATION / Stock

Figure 2.12 – La fenêtre pour désactiver 1 stock et / ou IMMOBILISATION (DURANT LA MODIFICATION).

Yeroth-pgi-3.0 - modifier (ré-approvisionner) un(e) stock / immobilisation

Actions Outils Aide

Entrer une immobilisation, un stock, un service

Actualiser Menu Annuler Supprimer

Caractéristiques de l'immobilisation OU du stock (service)

ré-approvisio.

reference	123456789	localisation du stock	
désignation	test_yeroth_1	date de péremption	01/07/2023
fournisseur		stock d'alerte	0.00
département du produit	yeroth departement 1	référence reçu d'achat	
catégorie	test_yeroth_categorie_1	historique désactiver	<input type="checkbox"/>

quantité restante 12.00 achat

prix d'achat 150.00

prix de vente	201.00	34.00%
prix de vente en gros	201.00	34.00%

TVA 7.25 %

Description

Image du stock (service)

supprimer l'image sélectionner une image

Si l'immobilisation / stock est déjà créer, il suffit de se rendre à la fenêtre "MODIFIER CE STOCK" et d'y décocher le 'checkbox' "historique désactiver" aux fins de supprimer de nouvelles insertions dans journal le d'historique de l'immobilisation / stock!

Chapitre 3

CAS D'UTILISATIONS D'1 ORGANISATION ENTREPRENEURIALE GÉNÉRIQUE

Ce chapitre a pour objectifs de démontrer la pertinence de mon PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ dans 1 environnement organisationnellement structuré!

3.1 RESSOURCES HUMAINES & FOURNISSEURS

3.1.1 Créer 1 Compte Travailleur (ou Fournisseur)

3.1.2 Supprimer 1 Compte Travailleur (ou Fournisseur)

3.2 CLIENTÈLE

- 3.2.1 Créer 1 Programme De Fidélité De Clients**
- 3.2.2 Créer 1 Catégorie De Client**
- 3.2.3 Créer 1 Compte Client**
- 3.2.4 Supprimer 1 Programme De Fidélité De Clients**
- 3.2.5 Supprimer 1 Catégorie De Client**
- 3.2.6 Supprimer 1 Compte Client**

3.3 IMMOBILISATIONS

3.3.1 Définition

3.3.2 Insérer 1 Immobilisation

3.3.3 Consulter L'historique D'1 Immobilisation

3.4 STOCKS et / ou MARCHANDISES

3.4.1 Insérer 1 Stock de Marchandises

3.4.2 Consulter L'historique D'1 Stock

3.4.3 Consulter La Liste Des Marchandises NON Achevées

3.4.4 Consulter La Liste Des Marchandises Achevées

3.5 MOUVEMENTS (SORTIES ET TRANSFERTS) DE IMMOBILISATIONS et / ou STOCKS

- 3.5.1 Sortir 1 Immobilisation / Stock**
- 3.5.2 Transférer 1 Immobilisation / Stock**
- 3.5.3 Consulter La Liste Des Sorties De Immobilisations**
- 3.5.4 Consulter La Liste Des Transferts Des Immobilisations**
- 3.5.5 Consulter La Liste Des Sorties De Stocks**
- 3.5.6 Consulter La Liste Des Transferts Des Stocks**

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3.6.1 TYPES DE PAIEMENTS

3.6.1.1 TYPES DE PAIEMENTS DE FOURNISSEURS

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3.6.3 Consulter Des paiements (DE CLIENTS)

3.6.4 Consulter Des paiements (AVEC FILTRES)

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3.8 FINANCES

3.8.1 Insérer 1 COMPTE BANCAIRE (*)

3.8.2 Insérer 1 CHARGE FINANCIÈRE

3.8.3 Consulter Des Payements

3.8.4 Consulter Des Transactions Financières (AVEC 1 FOURNISSEUR)

3.8.5 Consulter Des Transactions Financières (AVEC 1 CLIENT)

Chapitre 4

CAS D'UTILISATIONS D'ORGANISATIONS ENTREPRENEURIALES SPÉCIFIQUES

Ce chapitre a pour objectifs de démontrer la pertinence de mon PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ dans 1 environnement organisationnellement structuré!

4.1 1 service d'immigration / 1 CABINET D'AVOCATS / 1 Entreprise de LOGISTIQUE, ETC.

4.1.1 Insérer 1 CHARGE FINANCIÈRE SUR 1 LIGNE BUDGÉTAIRE

Figure 4.1 – La fenêtre pour entrer 1 charge financière sur 1 ligne budgétaire.

The screenshot shows a software window titled "YEROTH-ERP-3.0 - check in 1 ASSET, OR 1 inventory STOCK, or 1 service". The interface includes a menu bar with "Functions", "Tools", and "Help". Below the menu bar are several buttons: "Cancel", "insert", "Menu", "ASSET / Stocks", and "ASSETS / Stocks TRANSFER or CHECK OUT". The main area is titled "ASSET, stock or service characteristics" and contains a "Choice" dropdown menu with options: "insert 1 ASSET", "Check in STOCK", "create 1 financial expense", and "a client service sale". To the right of the dropdown is a "purchase price" field marked as "[* mandatory field]". Below these are several input fields: "article department", "budget line", "reference", "designation" (marked as "[* mandatory field]"), "supplier", and "batch qty" (with a value of "0,00"). At the bottom, the "purchase total amount" is displayed as "0.00 FCFA".

4.1.2 Créer 1 Dossier Clientèle

4.1.3 Générer 1 FICHE SOMMAIRE D'1 Client

4.1.4 Modifier Des Détails D'1 Client

4.2 1 COTISATION

4.2.1 Créer 1 Cotisation Mensuelle

4.2.2 Créer 1 Compte De Membre

4.2.2.1 Générer 1 Carte De Membre

4.2.3 Payer 1 Cotisation De Membre

4.3 1 ASSURANCE D'ENTREPRISES

4.3.1 Créer 1 Police D'assurance

4.3.2 Créer 1 Compte De Membre

4.3.2.1 Générer 1 Carte De Membre

4.3.3 Payer 1 Police D'assurance

4.4 1 HÔTEL

4.4.1 Une Réservation De Chambre

4.4.2 Une Location De Chambre

4.4.3 Une Sortie De Chambre

Chapitre 5

TABLEAUX DE BORDS

Ce chapitre présente des outils scientifiques et/ou statistiques nécessaires et utiles pour COMPRENDRE SES FONCTIONNEMENTS organisationnels, et représentés dans YERITH-PGI-9.0!

5.1 TYPES DE DIAGRAMMES REPRÉSENTATIFS DES DONNÉES DANS YERITH-PGI-9.0

5.1.1 DIAGRAMME À BANDE

Figure 5.1 – EXEMPLE DE DIAGRAMME À BANDE.

1 DIAGRAMME À BANDE REPRÉSENTE DES VALEURS NUMÉRIQUES SOUS FORME D'1 SUITE DE SURFACES RECTANGULAIRES DE MÊME LARGEUR ET DE LONGUEURS PLUS OU MOINS DIFFÉRENTES.

LA LONGUEUR D'1 BANDE DE SURFACE RECTANGULAIRE EST PROPORTIONNELLE À LA VALEUR NUMÉRIQUE QU'ELLE REPRÉSENTE!

✓ **Exemple de représentation de valeurs numériques par 1 diagramme à bande** La figure 5.1 représente 2 pourcentages :

1. "61,538" par 1 bande rectangulaire de couleur VERTE;
2. "38,462" par 1 bande rectangulaire de de couleur ROUGE.

5.1.2 DIAGRAMME CIRCULAIRE

Figure 5.2 – EXEMPLE DE DIAGRAMME CIRCULAIRE.

1 DIAGRAMME CIRCULAIRE REPRÉSENTE DES VALEURS NUMÉRIQUES SOUS FORME D'1 SUITE D'AIRES CIRCULAIRES PLUS OU MOINS DIFFÉRENTES.

CHAQUE VALEUR NUMÉRIQUE REPRÉSENTÉE A 1 AIRE CIRCULAIRE, et 1 angle PROPOR-TIONNEL À LA GRANDEUR DE LA VALEUR NUMÉRIQUE REPRÉSENTÉE!

✓ **Exemple de représentation de valeurs numériques par 1 diagramme circulaire** La fi-gure 5.2 représente 2 pourcentages :

1. "61,538" par 1 aire circulaire de couleur VERTE;
2. "38,462" par 1 aire circulaire de couleur ROUGE.

5.2 Générer 1 bilan comptable ANALYTIQUE

5.3 Générer 1 CHIFFRE D'AFFAIRE

5.4 Générer 1 PALMARÈS DE CHIFFRES D'AFFAIRES

Chapitre 6

Conclusion

CETTE CONCLUSION PERMETTRA DE CONCLURE SUR LES PERTINENCES ET CAS D'UTILISATIONS LES MIEUX APPROPRIÉS DE MON PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ "YERITH-PGI-9.0".

Chapitre 7

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Annexe A

PHILOSOPHIE DU DESIGN-INDUSTRIEL DE YERITH-PGI-9.0

Figure A.1 – La fenêtre de visualisation de stocks.

J'AI CONSTRUIS ET IMPLÉMENTÉ YERITH-PGI-9.0 AVEC LES OBJECTIFS SUIVANTS :

1. **Les champs de textes destinés à la recherche textuelle arbore dans leur espace d'écriture, des indications sur la fiabilité et la pertinence des résultats.**
cf. l'image de la fenêtre A.1 de visualisation des stocks de YERITH-PGI-9.0; le champs textuel juste au-dessous du 'bouton' "menu" mentionne que toute recherche effectuée en son sein, se fera uniquement dans la COLONNE 'DESCRIPTION DE L'ARTICLE, OU DU SERVICE' du tableau de stocks.
2. **YERITH-PGI-9.0 est privé en presque tout point de la MAXIMISATION DES FENÊTRES : CECI DANS LE SOUCIS DE POUVOIR UTILISER YERITH-PGI-9.0, sans autre formes de manipulation du code (C++), sur des ordinateurs (tablettes numériques) avec pour SYSTÈME D'EXPLOITATION ANDROID.**
3. **YERITH-PGI-9.0 est portable :**

1. **sur toutes les plateformes possible ayant juste 1 compilateur C++ (MAC-OS, ETC.)**
2. **(ANDROID-GOOGLE) grâce à l'outil Qt-creator.**
4. **L'utilisateur a accès de tout endroit du logiciel à 1 autre endroit en exécutant au GRAND MAXIMUM 3 actions : RÈGLE DE 3 CLICS.**

Annexe B

DROITS D'UTILISATION DE MON LOGICIEL DE GESTION COMMERCIALE ET FINANCIÈRE YERITH-PGI-9.0

NOTRE SYSTÈME LOGICIEL YERITH-PGI-9.0-STANDALONE EST GRATUIT DANS TOUS LES SENS DU TERME! (la version 'open-source' ne contient pas de comptabilité)

LE LOGICIEL 'YERITH-PGI-9.0-STANDALONE' VIENT À L'ÉTAT. IL NE COMPORTE AUCUNE GARANTIE, DE QUELQUE FORME QUE CE SOIT.
MERCIIII

TOUTEFOIS NOUS INTERDISONS SON UTILISATION POUR 1 QUELCONQUE ACTIVITÉ POUVANT FAIRE PRÉVALOIR L'INJUSTICE DANS TOUS LES SENS DU TERME, **et contrevenant aux lois et règlements en vigueur du lieu où l'utilisateur se retrouve!**

**DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (UNIVERSITÄT BREMEN).
VIELEN DANK FÜR MEINE EXZELLENTAUSBILDUNG.**

TOUTEFOIS, SI VOUS RECOUREZ AUX SERVICES D'1 TIERCE PERSONNE, CE TECHNICIEN OU INGÉNIEUR, OU PROFESSEUR PEUT VOUS DEMANDER DE L'ARGENT POUR RÉMUNÉRER SON TEMPS DE TRAVAIL, et non pour l'achat du logiciel (en soit) :

1. YERITH-PGI-9.0, code source (non exécutable) :
<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0>
2. YERITH-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON, code source (non exécutable) :
<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon>

Logiciel de Gestion des Stocks et de Gestion des Ventes

(yerith-erp-3.0)

Manuel de l'Utilisateur

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À propos de l'auteur

Figure 1 – Portrait de YERITH-NISSI.

Chapitre 1

Introduction

yerith-erp-3.0 est un logiciel de gestion des ressources d'une entreprise commerciale (**ERP – 'Enterprise Resource Planning'**).

yerith-erp-3.0 permet entre autres d'exécuter les tâches de l'entreprise commerciale suivantes :

- 1) **la gestion des achats d'articles**
- 2) **la gestion d'un portefeuille clients**
- 3) **la gestion des stocks**
 - (i) **les sorties des stocks** : sortie des stocks d'une succursale pour réception par un client
 - (ii) **les transferts des stocks** : mouvement des stocks d'une succursale vers une autre succursale
 - (iii) les ventes des stocks.

Figure 1.1 – La fenêtre d'accueil sans aucun utilisateur enregistré.

1.1 Accès au guide de l'utilisateur

La figure 1.1 illustre la fenêtre d'accueil de yerith-erp-3.0 sans aucun utilisateur enregistré.

Il est requis qu'un utilisateur soit enregistré dans yerith-erp-3.0 afin d'avoir accès au manuel de l'utilisateur.

L'utilisateur de yerith-erp-3.0 doit accomplir les opérations suivantes afin d'avoir accès au manuel de l'utilisateur :

- 1) à partir de la fenêtre d'accueil (voir figure 1.1), cliquez sur le menu déroulant '**Aide**'
- 2) ensuite cliquez sur le lien '**Guide de l'utilisateur (PDF)**'.

1.2 Structure du guide de l'utilisateur

Ce manuel de l'utilisateur de yerith-erp-3.0 est structuré comme suit :

- ✓ le chapitre 2 décrit les utilisateurs de yerith-erp-3.0 et leurs rôles
- ✓ le chapitre 3 explicite les fonctionnalités de gestion des stocks
- ✓ le chapitre ?? parle de la gestion des clients
- ✓ le chapitre ?? parle de la gestion des achats
- ✓ le chapitre 4 présente le système d'alertes sur les stocks
- ✓ le chapitre 5 décrit le point de vente
- ✓ le chapitre 6 décrit comment procéder à des mouvements de stocks
- ✓ le chapitre 7 explicite la gestion des ventes
- ✓ le chapitre 8 explicite la gestion des mouvements de stocks
- ✓ le chapitre 9 discute de la recherche et de la génération des rapports commerciaux de l'entreprise
- ✓ le chapitre 10 explique comment avoir accès aux détails de l'utilisateur enregistré, aux informations commerciales de l'entreprise, et enfin à la version de yerith-erp-3.0 que l'on utilise
- ✓ le chapitre 11 traite de l'administration du logiciel
- ✓ le chapitre 12 discute des problèmes connues de yerith-erp-3.0
- ✓ enfin, le chapitre 13 conclut ce manuel d'utilisation.

Chapitre 2

Les Rôles et Les Utilisateurs

Rôles ayant accès à la fonctionnalité : Administrateur 2.2, Caissier 2.7, GestionnaireDeStocks 2.5, Magasinier 2.6, Manager 2.3, Vendeur 2.4.

Ce chapitre décrit les différents types d'utilisateurs de yerith-erp-3.0 : Administrateur, Caissier, Magasinier, Manager, et Vendeur.

2.1 Introduction

yerith-erp-3.0 maintient les données suivantes pour chaque utilisateur :

- 1) l'email
- 2) la boîte postale
- 3) le date de naissance
- 4) le lieu de naissance
- 5) la localisation (le site de l'entreprise où l'employé est en fonction). Cette valeur ne peut être éditée.
- 6) le mot de passe **[obligatoire]**
- 7) les noms **[obligatoire]**
- 8) le nom d'utilisateur **[obligatoire]**
- 9) le numéro de téléphone 1
- 10) le numéro de téléphone 2
- 11) le pays
- 12) les prénoms **[obligatoire]**
- 13) la province ou l'état
- 14) le rôle dans yerith-erp-3.0 (Administrateur, Caissier, Magasinier, Manager, ou Vendeur) **[obligatoire]**
- 15) le titre (Dr., Me., Mlle, Mme, Mr, Pr., Prof.) **[obligatoire]**
- 16) la ville

2.2 Le Rôle "Administrateur"

La figure 2.1 illustre la fenêtre d'accueil d'un utilisateur avec le rôle *Administrateur*, après qu'il se soit enregistré dans yerith-erp-3.0.

Figure 2.1 – La fenêtre d'accueil d'un *Administrateur*.

Un utilisateur avec le rôle *Administrateur* a accès aux fonctionnalités suivantes :

- 1) arrêter le système d'alerte
- 2) connecter [YERITH-PGI-9.0](#) à une autre localisation
- 3) démarrer le système d'alerte
- 4) modifier les paramètres de l'application
- 5) modifier les paramètres du système d'alerte.

Un utilisateur avec le rôle *Administrateur* assume les tâches de créer et de maintenir les objets suivants :

- 1) les alertes (sur une période de temps, ou sur une quantité en stock)
- 2) les catégories d'articles
- 3) les clients
- 4) les comptes utilisateurs
- 5) les fournisseurs
- 6) les localisations (une localisation est un site de l'entreprise où se trouve un ou plusieurs stocks).

2.3 Le Rôle "Manager"

La figure 2.2 illustre la fenêtre d'accueil d'un utilisateur avec le rôle *Manager*, après qu'il se soit enregistré dans yerith-erp-3.0.

Figure 2.2 – La fenêtre d'accueil d'un *Manager*

Un utilisateur de yerith-erp-3.0 avec le rôle *Manager* a accès aux fonctionnalités suivantes :

- 1) administration (voir chapitre 11)
- 2) gestion des achats (voir chapitre ??)
- 3) gestion des clients (voir chapitre ??)
- 4) gestion des stocks (voir chapitre 3)
- 5) gestion des ventes (voir chapitre 7)
- 6) mouvements de stocks (voir chapitre 8)
- 7) point de vente (voir chapitre 5)
- 8) système d'alertes (voir chapitre 4)
- 9) tableaux de bords (voir chapitre 9).

2.4 Le Rôle "Vendeur"

La figure 2.3 illustre la fenêtre d'accueil d'un utilisateur avec le rôle *Vendeur*, après qu'il se soit enregistré dans yerith-erp-3.0.

Figure 2.3 – La fenêtre d'accueil d'un *Vendeur*

Un utilisateur de yerith-erp-3.0 avec le rôle *Vendeur* a accès aux fonctionnalités suivantes :

- 1) gestion des achats (voir chapitre ??)
- 2) gestion des clients (voir chapitre ??)
- 3) gestion des stocks (voir chapitre 3)
- 4) gestion des ventes (voir chapitre 7)
- 5) point de vente (voir chapitre 5)
- 6) système d'alertes (voir chapitre 4).

2.5 Le Rôle "GestionnaireDeStocks"

La figure 2.4 illustre la fenêtre d'accueil d'un utilisateur avec le rôle *GestionnaireDeStocks*, après qu'il se soit enregistré dans yerith-erp-3.0.

Figure 2.4 – La fenêtre d'accueil d'un *GestionnaireDeStocks*

Un utilisateur de yerith-erp-3.0 avec le rôle *GestionnaireDeStocks* a accès aux fonctionnalités suivantes :

- 1) gestion des achats (voir chapitre ??)
- 2) gestion des stocks (voir chapitre 3)
- 3) mouvements de stocks (voir chapitre 8)
- 4) système d'alertes (voir chapitre 4).

2.6 Le Rôle "Magasinier"

La figure 2.5 illustre la fenêtre d'accueil d'un utilisateur avec le rôle *Magasinier*, après qu'il se soit enregistré dans yerith-erp-3.0.

Figure 2.5 – La fenêtre d'accueil d'un *Magasinier*.

Un utilisateur de yerith-erp-3.0 avec le rôle *Magasinier* a accès aux fonctionnalités suivantes :

- 1) gestion des stocks (voir chapitre 3)
- 2) mouvements de stocks (voir chapitre 8)
- 3) système d'alertes (voir chapitre 4).

2.7 Le Rôle "Caissier"

La figure 2.6 illustre la fenêtre d'accueil d'un utilisateur avec le rôle *Caissier*, après qu'il se soit enregistré dans yerith-erp-3.0.

Figure 2.6 – La fenêtre d'accueil d'un *Caissier*.

Un utilisateur de yerith-erp-3.0 avec le rôle *Caissier* a accès aux fonctionnalités suivantes :

- 1) point de vente (voir chapitre 5)
- 2) système d'alertes (voir chapitre 4).

Chapitre 3

La Gestion des Stocks

Rôles ayant accès à la fonctionnalité : *Magasinier 2.6.*

Ce chapitre décrit comment avoir accès aux fonctionnalités de gestion des stocks et comment les utiliser.

3.1 Introduction

Les tâches de gestion des stocks sont illustrées dans le Tableau 3.1, en fonction du rôle de l'utilisateur.

Tâches	Manager	Vendeur	GestionnaireDeStocks	Magasinier	Caissier
entrer un stock	✓		✓		
supprimer un stock	✓				
lister les marchandises	✓	✓	✓		
lister les stocks	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
modifier un stock	✓		✓		
transférer des stocks	✓		✓	✓	
sortir des stocks	✓		✓	✓	
modifier la stratégie de gestion des stocks (ex. : FIFO , etc.)	✓	partiel	partiel		
vendre des marchandises	✓	✓			✓
accéder aux mouvements des stocks	✓		✓	✓	

Table 3.1 – Tableau des tâches et des rôles associés à la gestion des stocks

3.2 Les stratégies de gestion des stocks

yerith-erp-3.0 implémente 4 stratégies pour gérer les stocks à vendre ou à sortir :

- 1) **CMUP** : Cours Moyen, Unité Pondérée.
La stratégie **CMUP** affiche tous les stocks de façon (Cours Moyen, Unité Pondérée).
- 2) **DEF_DEO** : Date of Expiration First, Date of Expiration Out.
La stratégie **DEF_DEO** affiche les stocks à vendre ou à sortir selon le principe : les stocks avec des dates de péremption les plus proches sont les premiers à sortir.
- 3) **FIFO** : First In, First Out.
La stratégie **FIFO** affiche les stocks à vendre ou à sortir selon le principe "**First In, First Out**" : Les stocks avec des dates d'entrée en stock plus anciennes sont les premiers à sortir.
- 4) **LIFO** : Last In, First Out.
La stratégie **LIFO** affiche les stocks à vendre ou à sortir selon le principe "**Last In, First Out**" : Les stocks avec des dates d'entrée en stock plus récentes sont les premiers à sortir.

La stratégie de gestion des stocks se modifie comme suit :

- ✓ de façon permanente dans la section 'administration' de [YERITH-PGI-9.0](#).
- ✓ de façon temporaire (à des fins de visualisation de l'ordre des sorties de stocks) dans la fenêtre 'fiche des stocks' de [YERITH-PGI-9.0](#).

3.3 Entrer un stock

Yerith-erp-3.0 entretient les données suivantes pour chaque stock :

- 1) la catégorie **[obligatoire]**
- 2) la désignation **[obligatoire]**
- 3) la date de péremption du stock
- 4) le fournisseur
- 5) la localisation du stock
- 6) le montant de la TVA d'un article
- 7) le prix de vente d'un article **[obligatoire]**
- 8) la quantité initiale (nombre de lots, et quantité par lot) **[obligatoire]**
- 9) la référence
- 10) la référence du reçu d'achat
- 11) le stock minimum : si cette quantité est atteinte, alors le nombre de la colonne 'Qté totale' du stock est affiché en rouge.

Il existe deux méthodes pour entrer un stock dans Yerith-erp-3.0 :

- 1) la 1^{ère} **méthode** est utilisée pour entrer un stock d'articles à partir d'un formulaire vide
- 2) la 2^{ème} **méthode** permet à l'utilisateur de réutiliser la **catégorie**, la **désignation**, le **prix d'achat**, le **prix de vente**, la **TVA** si existante, et la **référence** d'un stock de même nature déjà existant.

Les deux méthodes sont les suivantes :

✓ 1^{ère} méthode

À partir de la fenêtre d'accueil intitulée '**Yerith-pgi-3.0 – fenêtre de l'utilisateur**' (voir figure 2.2), cliquez sur le bouton "**Entrer un stock**" pour obtenir un formulaire vide afin d'entrer en stock. Le formulaire obtenu est illustré dans la figure 3.1.

Si vous entrez la référence d'un article qui existe déjà dans le stock, les informations suivantes sont automatiquement remplies :

- 1) la **désignation**
- 2) la **catégorie**

Yeroth-erp-3.0 - entrer un stock

Actions Outils Aide

Alertes

Enregistrer Marchandises Menu Stocks Sortir ou Transférer

Caractéristiques du stock

référence

désignation

fournisseur

catégorie

nombre de lots quantité

quantité total

prix d'achat

prix de vente

TVA

péremption (date)

localisation du stock

stock minimum

référence reçu d'achat

Image de l'article

Description

annuler sélectionner une image

Figure 3.1 – Le formulaire vide pour entrer un stock.

✓ 2^{ème} méthode

- 1) À partir de la fenêtre d'accueil (voir figure 2.2), cliquez sur le bouton "Stocks"
- 2) ensuite, sélectionnez un stock en cliquant dessus une fois
- 3) enfin, cliquez sur le bouton "Entrer un stock".

Là vous obtenez un formulaire partiellement rempli avec les données réutilisables du stock sélectionné. Le formulaire que vous obtenez est celui de la figure 3.2.

The screenshot shows a software window titled "Yeroth-erp-3.0 - entrer un stock". At the top, there is a menu bar with "Actions", "Outils", and "Aide". Below it is a toolbar with icons for navigation and a section labeled "Alertes". The main interface features a navigation bar with five buttons: "Enregistrer" (black), "Marchandises" (red), "Menu" (black), "Stocks" (orange), and "Sortir ou Transférer" (yellow). The central area is a form titled "Caractéristiques du stock" with the following fields:

- référence: 35678975
- désignation: Supermont
- fournisseur: (empty)
- catégorie: Eau minérale
- nombre de lots: 1 (with a spinner) / quantité: (empty)
- quantité total: (empty)
- prix d'achat: 100
- prix de vente: 139.43
- TVA: 7.25 %
- péremption (date): 07/01/2020
- localisation du stock: (empty)
- stock minimum: (empty)
- référence reçu d'achat: (empty)

Below the form is a "Description" field (empty) and an "Image de l'article" section with a large empty box and two buttons: "annuler" and "sélectionner une image".

Figure 3.2 – Le formulaire partiellement rempli pour entrer un nouveau stock.

3.4 Lister des stocks

La figure 3.3 illustre la fenêtre d'accueil de yerith-erp-3.0 pour lister les stocks.

Le titre de cette fenêtre explicite la stratégie de gestion des stocks utilisée pour vendre ou sortir des articles : CMUP.

Figure 3.3 – La fenêtre pour lister les stocks.

À partir d'une fenêtre quelconque qui y donne accès, l'accès à la fonctionnalité, 'Lister des stocks' se fait avec au moins l'une des méthodes suivantes :

- ✓ **1^{ère} méthode**
cliquez sur le lien "**Lister des stocks**" dans le menu déroulant **Actions**
- ✓ **2^{ème} méthode**
cliquez sur le bouton "**Stocks**".

3.4.1 Les stocks listés en rouge

Les stocks listés en **rouge** dans la colonne "Qté totale" sont ceux dont la quantité minimale en stock a été atteinte.

Les stocks listés en **rouge** dans la colonne "Date péremption" sont ceux dont la date de péremption a été atteinte.

3.4.2 Les stocks listés en vert

Les stocks listés en **vert** dans la colonne "Date péremption" sont ceux qui ont été sélectionnés pour la vente par l'algorithme correspondant : **DEF_DEO**.

Les stocks listés en vert dans la colonne "Date entrée" sont ceux qui ont été sélectionnés pour la vente par l'un des algorithmes suivants : **FIFO**, **LIFO**.

3.5 Imprimer la fiche des stocks au format PDF

Il existe deux méthodes pour imprimer la liste des stocks qui apparaît dans la fenêtre intitulée 'Yerith-erp-3.0 - Lister des stocks'.

✓ **1^{ère} méthode**

Cliquez sur le lien 'Imprimer la fiche des stocks' qui se trouve dans le menu déroulant 'Outils'

✓ **2^{ème} méthode**

Cliquez sur l'icône blanche représentant une 'imprimante'

✓ **3^{ème} méthode**

Pressez simultanément les boutons "CTRL" et "P" de votre clavier.

Un fichier au format PDF ayant la liste des stocks affichée est alors généré.

3.6 Rechercher un article ou un stock

Il existe deux méthodes pour rechercher un article / stock :

✓ **1^{ère} méthode**

- 1) cliquez sur le bouton "rechercher"
- 2) ou bien cliquez sur le lien 'Rechercher un article' dans le menu déroulant **Outils**.

L'utilisateur est alors conduit vers une petite fenêtre de dialogue où il peut introduire les mots clés de sa recherche, ainsi que les paramètres optionnels suivants : la **catégorie du stock**, la **désignation du stock** et le **fournisseur du stock**. Ceci est illustré dans la figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4 – La fenêtre pour rechercher un stock (ou un article).

Pour une recherche efficace, les mots clés doivent être des mots ou parcelle de mots qui apparaissent dans les endroits suivant :

- 1) la catégorie du stock
- 2) la désignation du fournisseur
- 3) la désignation du stock
- 4) les mots qui ont été introduits dans le champs de texte 'Description' qui apparaît lorsque l'on entre un nouveau stock (voir par exemple la figure 3.2).

✓ 2^{ème} méthode

L'utilisateur peut aussi entrer la référence du stock recherché dans le champs de recherche situé juste en dessous des boutons suivants : "Afficher", "Entrer un nouveau stock", "Menu", "Modifier", et "Sortir".

Figure 3.5 – Le champs de texte pour rechercher les stocks (ou articles) en utilisant seulement leur référence.

Ceci est illustré dans la figure 3.5 où les stocks ayant la référence '123456789' ont été recherchés.

Lorsqu'une recherche de stocks (ou d'articles) est active, le mot 'rechercher' du bouton "rechercher" et le lien 'Rechercher un article' dans le menu déroulant 'Outils' sont soulignés.

Le bouton "réinitialiser" ou le lien 'Réinitialiser la recherche' dans le menu déroulant 'Outils' permettent de désactiver la recherche et ainsi d'afficher tous les stocks à nouveau.

3.7 Afficher les détails d'un stock

La figure 3.6 illustre les détails du stock 'Supermont'.

Figure 3.6 – Une fenêtre qui présente les détails d'un stock.

Il existe trois méthodes pour afficher les détails d'un stock :

✓ **1^{ère} méthode**

- 1) sélectionnez le stock dont vous souhaitez afficher les détails en cliquant une fois sur lui à partir de la fenêtre '**fiche des stocks**'
- 2) cliquez ensuite sur le bouton "**Afficher**".

✓ **2^{ème} méthode**

- 1) sélectionner le stock dont vous souhaitez afficher les détails en cliquant une fois sur lui à partir de la fenêtre '**fiche des stocks**'
- 2) cliquer ensuite sur le lien '**Afficher les détails de ce stock**' du menu déroulant **Actions**.

✓ **3^{ème} méthode**

- 1) sélectionner le stock dont vous souhaitez afficher les détails en cliquant une fois sur lui à partir de la fenêtre '**fiche des stocks**'
- 2) maintenir l'indexeur de la souris sur le stock sélectionné et ensuite cliquer sur le bouton droit de la souris
- 3) un menu déroulant s'affiche, cliquer sur le lien '**Afficher les détails de ce stock**' du menu déroulant qui s'est affiché.

3.8 Consulter l'historique d'un stock

La figure 3.7 illustre l'historique d'un stock.

	Date	Temps	Type d'opération	Qté initiale en stock	Qté retirée	Qté restante en stock
1	13.12.2019	21:28:11	ENTREE	36.00	0.00	36.00
2	13.12.2019	21:28:50	VENTE	36.00	3.00	33.00
3	14.12.2019	11:55:24	VENTE	33,00	1,00	32,00
4	15.12.2019	13:07:34	VENTE	32.00	1.00	31.00
5	28.12.2019	10:14:30	VENTE	29,00	1,00	28,00
6	28.12.2019	10:21:10	TRANSFERT	28,00	1,00	27,00

Figure 3.7 – L'historique d'un stock.

✓ **1^{ère} méthode**

- 1) sélectionner le stock dont vous souhaitez consulter l'historique en cliquant sur lui avec le bouton gauche de la souris à partir de la fenêtre '**fiche des stocks**'
- 2) cliquer ensuite sur le lien '**Afficher l'historique de ce stock**' du menu déroulant **Actions**.

✓ **2^{ème} méthode**

- 1) sélectionner le stock dont vous souhaitez consulter l'historique en cliquant sur lui avec le bouton droit de la souris à partir de la fenêtre '**fiche des stocks**'
- 2) cliquer ensuite sur le lien '**Afficher l'historique de ce stock**' du menu contextuel qui s'est affiché.

L'historique du stock peut être imprimé au format PDF en cliquant sur l'icône représentant une imprimante.

3.9 Modifier les détails d'un stock

La figure 3.8 illustre la fenêtre pour modifier les détails du stock 'Cola'.

Figure 3.8 – Une fenêtre qui permet la modification des détails d'un stock.

Seul les informations suivantes d'un stock peuvent être modifiées :

- 1) la date de péremption des articles du stock
- 2) la quantité minimale en stock
- 3) le prix de vente d'un article du stock.

Il existe trois méthodes pour modifier les détails d'un stock :

✓ **1^{ère} méthode**

- 1) sélectionner le stock dont vous souhaitez modifier les détails en cliquant une fois sur lui à partir de la fenêtre '**fiche des stocks**'
- 2) cliquer ensuite sur le bouton "**Modifier**".

✓ **2^{ème} méthode**

- 1) sélectionner le stock dont vous souhaitez modifier les détails en cliquant une fois sur lui à partir de la fenêtre '**fiche des stocks**'
- 2) cliquer ensuite sur le lien '**Modifier ce stock**' du menu déroulant **Actions**.

✓ **3^{ème} méthode**

- 1) sélectionner le stock dont vous souhaitez modifier les détails en cliquant une fois sur lui à partir de la fenêtre '**fiche des stocks**'

- 2) maintenir l'indexeur de la souris sur le stock sélectionné et ensuite cliquer sur le bouton droit de la souris
- 3) un menu déroulant s'affiche, cliquer sur le lien '**Modifier ce stock**' du menu déroulant qui s'est affiché.

3.10 Visualiser les articles / stocks périmés

La figure 3.9 illustre que la date de péremption du stock 'Cola' (22 Février 2017) est dépassée.

ID	Référence	Désignation	Catégorie	Prix unitaire	Montant TVA	Prix vente	Qté totale	
1	5	123456789	Supermont	Eau minérale	110,00	7,97	117,97	3

Figure 3.9 – Le stock 'Cola' est périmé.

On visualise les stocks périmés en allant à la fenêtre 'fiche des stocks'.

Tous les stocks dont la colonne 'Date de péremption' est affichée en rouge sont périmés.

3.11 Visualiser les stocks dont la quantité minimale en stock est atteinte

L'utilisateur de yerith-erp-3.0 peut définir une quantité minimale pour un stock : c'est le nombre d'articles du stock en dessous duquel l'entreprise ne devrait pas se retrouver.

La figure 3.10 illustre que la quantité minimale de 50 articles du stock 'Cola' est atteinte.

	ID	Référence	Désignation	Catégorie	Prix unitaire	Montant TVA	Prix vente	Qté totale
1	3	129876543	Curcuma-gins.	Tea	1 600,00	116,00	1 716,00	65
2	4	123456789	Supermont	Eau minérale	110,00	7,97	117,97	31
3	5	123456789	Supermont	Eau minérale	110,00	7,97	117,97	3

Figure 3.10 – La quantité minimale du stock 'Cola' est atteinte.

On visualise les stocks dont la quantité minimale en stock est atteinte en allant à la fenêtre 'fiche des stocks'.

Tous les stocks dont la colonne 'Quantité en stock' est affichée en rouge ont leur quantité minimale en stock déjà atteinte.

3.12 Supprimer un stock

Il existe deux méthodes pour supprimer un stock :

✓ 1^{ère} méthode

- 1) sélectionner le stock à supprimer partir de la fenêtre 'fiche des stocks'
- 2) cliquer ensuite sur le lien 'Supprimer ce stock' dans le menu déroulant **Actions**.

✓ 2^{ème} méthode

- 1) sélectionner le stock à supprimer partir de la fenêtre 'fiche des stocks'
- 2) maintenir l'indexeur de la souris sur le stock sélectionné et ensuite cliquer sur le bouton droit de la souris
- 3) un menu déroulant s'affiche, cliquer sur le lien 'Supprimer ce stock' du menu déroulant qui s'est affiché.

Le stock supprimé n'est plus affiché.

Chapitre 4

Le Système d'Alertes sur les Stocks

Rôles ayant accès à la fonctionnalité : Administrateur 2.2, Caissier 2.7, Magasinier 2.6, Manager 2.3.

Ce chapitre décrit comment créer, lister, modifier, et supprimer les alertes sur les stocks.

4.1 Introduction

Le programme qui implémente le système d'alertes de yerith-erp-3.0 s'appelle "yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon". yerith-erp-alert-3.0 est configuré pour démarrer en tant que "processus en arrière plan" lors du démarrage de l'ordinateur.

La figure 4.1 présente l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour créer une alerte.

The screenshot shows a window titled "Yeroth-erp-3.0 ~ administration ~ créer". The interface includes a menu bar with "Actions", "Outils", and "Aide". Below the menu is a "Menu principal" with icons for navigation. The main area contains five buttons: "Créer", "Lister", "Administration", "Modifier", and "Supprimer". A tabbed interface is visible with tabs for "Alerte", "Bon de commande", "Catégorie", "Client", "Compte utilisateur", "Fournisseur", "Localisation", and "Remise". The "Alerte" tab is active, showing a form with the following fields:

- Données de l'alerte:
 - désignation de l'article
 - désignation de l'alerte
 - ID du destinataire
 - quantité en stock
 - stock minimum
 - date de péremption
 - nom du destinataire
- condition (radio button)
- quantité
- période de temps:
 - début (28/12/2019)
 - fin (28/12/2019)
- message de l'alerte (text area)

At the bottom, there are two buttons: "Annuler" and "Enregistrer".

Figure 4.1 – La fenêtre principale pour la création d'une alerte.

le système d'alertes sur les stocks permet aux utilisateurs de contrôler les dates de péremption des stocks, ainsi que les quantités d'articles en stock.

yerith-erp-3.0 définit deux types d'alertes sur les stocks :

- 1) **les alertes sur une quantité en stock**
- 2) **les alertes sur une période de temps.**

L'interface de yerith-erp-3.0 pour créer des alertes a deux *boutons de radio*¹ :

- 1) le bouton de radio 'quantité en stock'
- 2) le bouton de radio 'période de temps'.

1. les boutons de radio permettent de faire des choix exclusifs

4.2 Créer une alerte sur une quantité en stock

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**créer**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**une alerte**' dans le '*combo box sujets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée sur la figure 4.1.
- 4) Il est préférable pour de d'abord choisir le stock pour lequel une alerte doit être créer. Pour cela il faut choisir sa désignation dans le champs de texte '**désignation de l'article**', qui possède un menu auto-déroulant.

Les informations des champs de textes situées à droite du champs de texte '**désignation de l'article**' sont non modifiables et affichent des valeurs en fonction du stock de l'article sélectionné :

1) quantité en stock

2) quantité minimale (stock)

3) date de péremption.

Ces informations aident à paramétrer l'alerte.

- 5) Donner une désignation à l'alerte en remplissant le champs de texte '**désignation de l'alerte**'.
- 6) Choisir un destinataire qui recevra le message de l'alerte lorsque celle-ci sera déclenchée. Ceci se fait dans le champs de texte '**ID du destinataire**', qui possède un menu auto-déroulant.

Le nom complet du destinataire est affiché automatiquement dans le champs de texte '**nom du destinataire**', qui est situé juste à droite du champs de texte '**ID du destinataire**'.

- 7) Choisir le type d'alerte : **quantité en stock** en cliquant sur la bouton radio '**condition**' et en *saisissant un nombre dans le champs de texte 'quantité'*.
- 8) Remplir le champs de texte '**Message de l'alerte**'. C'est ce message qui sera envoyé au destinataire de l'alerte lorsque celle-ci sera déclenchée.
- 9) Achever la procédure en cliquant sur le bouton "**Valider**".

4.3 Créer une alerte sur une période de temps

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**créer**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**une alerte**' dans le '*combo box sujets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée sur la figure 4.1.
- 4) Il est préférable pour de d'abord choisir le stock pour lequel une alerte doit être créer. Pour cela il faut choisir sa désignation dans le champs de texte '**désignation de l'article**', qui possède un menu auto-déroulant.

Les informations des champs de textes situées à droite du champs de texte '**désignation de l'article**' sont non modifiables et affichent des valeurs en fonction du stock de l'article sélectionné :

- 1) quantité en stock
- 2) quantité minimale (stock)
- 3) date de péremption.

Ces informations aident à paramétrer l'alerte.

- 5) Donner une désignation à l'alerte en remplissant le champs de texte '**désignation de l'alerte**'.
- 6) Choisir un destinataire qui recevra le message de l'alerte lorsque celle-ci sera déclenchée. Ceci se fait dans le champs de texte '**ID du destinataire**', qui possède un menu auto-déroulant.

Le nom complet du destinataire est affiché automatiquement dans le champs de texte '**nom du destinataire**', qui est situé juste à droite du champs de texte '**ID du destinataire**'.

- 7) Choisir le type d'alerte : **période de temps** en cliquant sur la bouton radio '**début**' et en choisissant *les dates de début et de fin de la période de temps pendant laquelle l'alerte sera active*.
- 8) Remplir le champs de texte '**Message de l'alerte**'. C'est ce message qui sera envoyé au destinataire de l'alerte lorsque celle-ci sera déclenchée.
- 9) Achever la procédure en cliquant sur le bouton "**Valider**".

4.4 Voir toutes les alertes qu'un utilisateur a reçu *

* : Cette fonctionnalité est exclusivement réservée aux utilisateurs *Manager*.

Pour voir toutes les alertes qui lui sont destinées, l'utilisateur doit accomplir les actions suivantes à partir de toutes fenêtre ayant le lien '**Alertes**' dans sa barre de menu :

- 1) cliquer sur le lien '**Alertes**' qui est situé dans la barre de menu. Ce lien se retrouve dans toutes les fenêtres concernant la gestion des stocks
- 2) un utilisateur a aussi accès aux alertes qui lui sont destinées en cliquant sur le lien '**Alertes**' que l'on retrouve dans le menu déroulant **Outils**.

4.5 Voir les détails d'une alerte

L'utilisateur doit accomplir les actions suivantes à partir de toutes fenêtre ayant le lien '**Alertes**' dans sa barre de menu :

- 1) cliquer sur le lien '**Alertes**' qui est situé dans la barre de menu. Ce lien se retrouve dans toutes les fenêtres concernant la gestion des stocks
- 2) ensuite, sélectionner dans l'onglet '**Alertes**' l'alerte dont vous souhaitez voir les détails
- 3) enfin, cliquer 2 fois consécutives sur cette alerte.

4.6 Marquer une alerte comme résolue *

* : Cette fonctionnalité est exclusivement réservée aux utilisateurs *Manager*.

L'utilisateur doit accomplir les actions suivantes à partir de toutes fenêtre ayant le lien '**Alertes**' dans sa barre de menu :

- 1) cliquer sur le lien '**Alertes**' qui est situé dans la barre de menu. Ce lien se retrouve dans toutes les fenêtres concernant la gestion des stocks
- 2) ensuite, sélectionner dans l'onglet '**Alertes**' l'alerte dont vous souhaitez voir les détails
- 3) enfin, cliquez sur le bouton "**Marquer résolue**".

4.7 Supprimer une alerte *

* : Cette fonctionnalité est exclusivement réservée aux utilisateurs *Manager*.

L'utilisateur doit accomplir les actions suivantes à partir de toutes fenêtre ayant le lien '**Alertes**' dans sa barre de menu :

- 1) cliquer sur le lien '**Alertes**' qui est situé dans la barre de menu. Ce lien se retrouve dans toutes les fenêtres concernant la gestion des stocks
- 2) ensuite, sélectionner dans l'onglet '**Alertes**' l'alerte dont vous souhaitez voir les détails
- 3) enfin, cliquez sur le bouton "**Supprimer une alerte**".

Chapitre 5

Point De Vente (La Vente d'Articles)

Rôles ayant accès à la fonctionnalité : Caissier 2.7, Manager 2.3.

Ce chapitre décrit comment vendre des articles, appliquer des rabais, et appliquer la TVA sur un article ou la retirer.

5.1 Introduction

La figure 5.1 illustre l'interface graphique pour procéder à la vente d'articles.

Figure 5.1 – La fenêtre pour vendre les articles.

Le tableau où sont affichés les articles à vendre a les colonnes suivantes :

- 1) Référence
- 2) Désignation
- 3) P.U. (Prix Unitaire)

- 4) Qté (**Quantité**)
- 5) Qté restante en stock (**Quantité restante en stock**)
- 6) Total TTC (**Total Toute Taxes Comprise**)
- 7) TVA (**Taxe sur la Valeur Ajouté**).

5.1.1 La stratégie de vente utilisée

Le titre de la fenêtre affiche la stratégie de vente des stocks utilisée. Dans la figure 5.1 par exemple, la stratégie de vente utilisée est **CMUP**.

5.2 Sélectionner des articles à vendre

Il existe 2 méthodes pour sélectionner des articles à vendre :

✓ **1^{ère} méthode**

Sélectionner les stocks des articles à vendre en entrant leur code bar dans le premier champs de texte de l'interface (voir figure 5.2)

Yeroth-erp-3.0 - point de vente - CMUP [factures pdf au format: 'petit']

Actions Outils Aide

Menu principal Alertes Lister les stocks

Articles Article au détail **117,97 FCFA**

référence [focus avec F11] désignation [focus avec F12]

	Référence	Désignation	Catégorie	Qté	Qté en stock	Prix unitaire	TVA	Total TTC
1	123456789	Supermont	Eau minérale	1	31.00	110.00	7.97	117.97

Caissier: **Xavier NOUMBISSI-NOUNDOU**

Imprimante: **epson TM-T20ii**

Nom du client:

À rembourser: **0,00 FCFA**

Quantité à vendre: **1**

Total HT: **110,00 FCFA**

TVA (7.25 %): **7,97 FCFA**

Total TTC: **117,97 FCFA**

annuler vendre

Figure 5.2 – Le champs de texte pour ajouter les articles en utilisant leur code bar.

✓ 2^{ème} méthode

Sélectionner les stocks des articles à vendre en entrant leur désignation dans le deuxième champs de texte de l'interface (voir figure 5.3).

Yeroth-erp-3.0 - point de vente - CMUP [factures pdf au format: 'petit']

Actions Outils Aide

Menu principal Alertes Lister les stocks

Articles Article au détail **1 716,00 FCFA**

référence [focus avec F11] Curcuma-ginseng tea

Référence	Désignation	Catégorie	Qté	Qté en stock	Prix unitaire	TVA	Total TTC
1 129876543	Curcuma-ginseng tea	Tea	1	65.00	1600.00	116.00	1716.00

Caissier	Xavier NOUMBISSI-NOUNDOU	Quantité à vendre	1
Imprimante	epson TM-T20ii	Total HT	1 600,00 FCFA
Nom du client		TVA (7.25 %)	116,00 FCFA
À rembourser	0,00 FCFA	Total TTC	1 716,00 FCFA

annuler vendre

Figure 5.3 – Le champs de texte pour ajouter les articles en utilisant leur désignation.

5.3 Afficher les détails d'un article / stock sélectionné pour la vente

La figure 5.5 illustre les détails du stock 'Saouda'.

Il existe deux méthodes pour voir les détails d'un stock sélectionné pour la vente :

✓ **1^{ère} méthode**

Il suffit de cliquer deux fois sur n'importe quelle partie autre que '**Qté**' de la ligne du stock sélectionné.

✓ **2^{ème} méthode**

Il suffit de cliquer sur l'onglet '**Article au détail**' après la sélection du stock.

5.4 Changer la quantité à vendre d'un article / stock

Il existe deux méthodes pour changer la quantité d'articles d'un stock :

✓ 1^{ère} méthode

il faut cliquer sur l'élément 'Qté' avec le bouton gauche de la souris, et ensuite changer la quantité à vendre (voir figure 5.4)

The screenshot shows the 'Yeroth-erp-3.0 - point de vente - CMUP' interface. At the top right, the total amount is displayed as '8 580,00 FCFA'. Below this, there are tabs for 'Articles' and 'Article au détail'. A search bar contains 'référence [focus avec F11]' and 'désignation [focus avec F12]'. A table lists the product details:

Référence	Désignation	Catégorie	Qté	Qté en stock	Prix unitaire	TVA	Total TTC
1 129876543	Curcuma-ginseng tea	Tea	5	65.00	1600.00	580.00	8580.00

At the bottom, a summary section shows the cashier 'Xavier NOUMBISSI-NOUNDOU', the printer 'epson TM-T20ii', and the amount to be refunded '0,00 FCFA'. To the right, the 'Quantité à vendre' is set to '5', and the total amounts are: Total HT (8 000,00 FCFA), TVA (7.25 %) (580,00 FCFA), and Total TTC (8 580,00 FCFA). Buttons for 'annuler' and 'vendre' are visible at the bottom right.

Figure 5.4 – L'élément 'Qté' sélectionné pour changer la quantité d'articles 'Cola' à vendre.

✓ 2^{ème} méthode

il faut cliquer deux fois sur n'importe quel autre partie de la ligne du stock sélectionné, autre que 'Qté' pour avoir accès à une vue détaillée de ce stock.

La vue de détails du stock permet de changer la quantité à vendre dans le champ de texte 'quantité à vendre' (voir figure 5.5).

The screenshot shows a web application window titled "Yeroth-erp-3.0 - point de vente - CMUP [factures pdf au format: 'petit']". The interface includes a menu bar with "Actions", "Outils", and "Aide". Below the menu, there are navigation links: "Menu principal", "Alertes", and "Lister les stocks". The main content area is divided into two tabs: "Articles" and "Article au détail". The "Article au détail" tab is active, displaying the following information:

référence de l'article	129876543	nom du client	nom du client
désignation de l'article	Curcuma-ginseng tea	nom du caissier	Xavier NOUMBISSI-NOUNDOU
fournisseur	Carrefour		
catégorie	Tea		
prix unitaire	1 600,00 FCFA		
quantité en stock	65		
quantité à vendre	5		
remise (FCFA)	0.00		
remise (%)	0.00		
TVA (7.25 %)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	580.00	
date de péremption	04/12/2020		
localisation	Yaoundé		

On the right side of the interface, there is a large green button labeled "Retour". Below the article details, there is a section titled "Image de l'article" which is currently empty.

Figure 5.5 – Le champs de texte 'quantité à vendre' permet de changer la quantité à vendre d'un article.

5.5 Appliquer une remise sur un article / stock à vendre

Voici la démarche à suivre pour appliquer une remise sur le prix unitaire d'un article à vendre :

- 1) Sélectionner l'article à vendre (voir section 5.2)
- 2) ouvrir la vue de détails de l'article auquel vous souhaitez appliquer une remise
- 3) appliquer la remise en FCFA ou en pourcentage, en choisissant respectivement les bouton de radio "**remise (FCFA)**" ou "**remise (%)**", et en entrant le montant ou le pourcentage de remise à appliquer. (voir figure 5.5)
- 4) vous pouvez ensuite conclure la vente (voir section 5.11).

5.6 Modifier la TVA sur un article à vendre

Voici la démarche à suivre pour retirer ou ajouter la TVA sur un article à vendre :

- 1) Sélectionner l'article à vendre (voir section 5.2)
- 2) ouvrir la vue de détails de l'article auquel vous souhaitez appliquer une remise
- 3) retirer ou ajouter la TVA en cochant le 'check box' TVA (voir figure 5.5).
- 4) vous pouvez ensuite conclure la vente (voir section 5.11).

5.7 Supprimer un article de la liste des articles à vendre

Yeroth-erp-3.0 - point de vente - CMUP [factures pdf au format: 'petit']

Actions Outils Aide

Menu principal Alertes Lister les stocks

Articles Article au détail **8 697,97 FCFA**

référence [focus avec F11] désignation [focus avec F12]

	Référence	Désignation	Catégorie	Qté	Qté en stock	Prix unitaire	TVA	Total TTC
1	129876543	Curcuma-ginseng tea	Tea	5	65	1600.00	580.00	8580.00
2	123456789	Supermont	Eau minérale	1	31.00	110.00	7.97	117.97

Caissier **Xavier NOUMBISSI-NOUNDOU**

Imprimante **epson TM-T20ii**

Nom du client

À rembourser **0,00 FCFA**

Quantité à vendre **6**

Total HT **8 110,00 FCFA**

TVA (7.25 %) **587,97 FCFA**

Total TTC **8 697,97 FCFA**

annuler vendre

Figure 5.6 – Le bouton rouge sert à supprimer un article de la liste des articles à vendre.

Il suffit de sélectionner la ligne de l'article à vendre, et ensuite cliquer sur le petit bouton rouge qui se trouve juste après le champs de texte 'Caissier'.

Ce bouton rouge est illustré dans la figure 5.6, juste après le champs de texte 'Caissier'.

5.8 Vendre à un client divers

Il suffit de laisser le champs de texte 'Nom du client' vide lors de la vente.

5.9 Vendre à un client nommé

Il suffit de saisir le nom du client dans le champs de texte 'Nom du client'.

Figure 5.7 – La fenêtre de la création d'un nouveau compte client à partir de l'interface de vente.

Si le nom du client n'apparaît pas dans la liste suggérée, l'utilisateur doit sélectionner le texte '**nouveau client (*)**' (dans la liste suggérée). L'utilisateur sera alors conduit à la fenêtre pour créer un nouveau compte client (figure 5.7).

5.10 Annuler une vente en cours

Il suffit de cliquer sur le bouton "Annuler" pour annuler une vente en cours.

5.11 Conclure une vente

Voici la démarche à suivre pour conclure une vente :

- 1) sélectionner les articles à vendre (voir section 5.2)
- 2) entrer les quantités à vendre (voir section 5.4)
- 3) s'il y'a lieu, appliquer des remises ou modifier la TVA (voir section 5.5)
- 4) enfin, retourner à la fenêtre titrée '**Yerith-erp-3.0 - Fenêtre de la vente**' et presser sur le bouton "**Vendre**" (voir figure 5.6).

5.12 Imprimer la facture à la suite d'une vente

YEROTH
Computer Systems R&D Start-Up
Email : yerotherp30@gmail.com
Tél. : +237 6 80 59 65 72
B.P. : 626262 Yaoundé

Numéro de contribuable : 123456789
Numéro de compte bancaire : 123456789,
UBC Plc

Yaoundé, le samedi 28 décembre 2019

Client "DIVERS"
Représentant :
B.P. :
Email :
Tél. :

Facture Nr. : 16 (comptant)

Heure de vente : 10 :14 :31
Boutique de vente : Douala
Vendeur : Xavier NOUMBISSI-NOUNDOU

Référence	Désignation	Catégorie	Qté	Prix unitaire	TVA	Total TTC
129876543	Curcuma-gin.	Tea	1	1600.00	116.00	1716.00
123456789	Supermont	Eau minérale	1	110.00	7.97	117.97
TOTAUX			2		123,97	1 833,97 FCFA

Arrêté la présente facture au montant total TTC de **1 833,97 FCFA**.

Figure 5.8 – Une facture générée à la suite d'une vente.

Une facture au format PDF est automatiquement générée, juste après qu'une vente soit effectuée. La figure 5.8 illustre un exemple de facture.

5.13 Imprimer un exemple de facture au format PDF avant de conclure une vente

YEROTH
Computer Systems R&D Start-Up
Email : yerotherp30@gmail.com
Tél. : +237 6 80 59 65 72
B.P. : 626262 Yaoundé

Numéro de contribuable : 123456789
Numéro de compte bancaire : 123456789,
UBC Plc

Yaoundé, le samedi 28 décembre 2019

Client "DIVERS"
Représentant :
B.P. :
Email :
Tél. :

Facture Nr. : EXEMPLE (*NON VALIDE*) (comptant)

Heure de vente : 10 :11 :05
Boutique de vente : Douala
Vendeur : Xavier NOUMBISSI-NOUNDOU

Référence	Désignation	Catégorie	Qté	Prix unitaire	TVA	Total TTC
129876543	Curcuma-gin.	Tea	1	1600.00	116.00	1716.00
TOTAUX			1		116,00	1 716,00 FCFA

Arrêté la présente facture au montant total TTC de 1 716,00 FCFA.

Figure 5.9 – Une facture proforma générée avant de conclure une vente.

Il existe deux méthodes pour imprimer une facture proforma avant de conclure la vente éventuelle des articles présents dans le tableau qui apparaît dans la fenêtre intitulée '**Yerith-erp-3.0 - Fenêtre de la vente**'.

✓ **1^{ère} méthode**

Cliquer sur le lien '**Imprimer la facture (proforma)**' qui se trouve dans le menu déroulant '**Outils**'

✓ **2^{ème} méthode**

Presser simultanément les boutons "**CTRL**" et "**P**" de votre clavier.

Une facture proforma au format PDF est alors générée. Un exemple de facture proforma est illustré dans la figure 5.9.

Chapitre 6

La Sortie d'Articles

Rôles ayant accès à la fonctionnalité : Magasinier 2.6, Manager 2.3.

Ce chapitre décrit comment procéder à la sortie ou au transfert d'articles.

6.1 Introduction

Figure 6.1 – La fenêtre pour sortir des articles en stock.

La figure 6.1 illustre l'interface graphique pour procéder aux sorties, ou aux transferts d'articles.

La fenêtre avec pour titre "sortir ou transférer des stocks" permet d'effectuer les opérations suivantes :

- 1) **une sortie de stocks**;
- 2) **un transfert de stocks**.

Une **sortie de stocks** est le retrait d'articles par un client auprès d'une boutique (ou d'un dépôt) de votre entreprise après que le paiement se soit effectué dans une autre unité de l'entreprise.

Un **transfert de stocks** est un mouvement de stocks d'une boutique (ou d'un dépôt) de votre entreprise vers une autre unité de l'entreprise.

6.1.1 La stratégie de sortie des articles / stocks utilisée

Le titre de la fenêtre affiche la stratégie de sortie des stocks utilisée. La stratégie affichée dans la figure 6.1 est : "**CMUP**" (en effet : **Cours Moyen Unité Pondéré**).

6.2 Effectuer une sortie d'articles

La démarche pour effectuer une sortie d'articles en stock est la suivante :

- 1) sélectionner les articles à faire sortir (appliquer l'une des méthodes décrites dans la section 5.2 du chapitre 5 sur la vente d'article)
- 2) le cas échéant, choisissez le nom de l'entreprise cliente dans le menu déroulant du champs de texte '**Client**'
- 3) saisissez dans le champs de texte '**Récepteur**' le nom de la personne qui réceptionne les articles
- 4) si vous avez des notes spécifiques à cette sortie d'articles, écrire les dans le champs de texte '**notes**'
- 5) cliquer sur le bouton "**Sortir**" pour conclure la sortie de stocks.

6.3 Effectuer un transfert d'articles

La démarche pour effectuer un transfert d'articles en stock est la suivante :

- 1) sélectionner les articles à transférer (appliquer l'une des méthodes décrites dans la section 5.2 du chapitre 5 sur la vente d'article)
- 2) saisissez dans le champs de texte '**Récepteur**' le nom de la personne qui réceptionne les articles
- 3) saisissez ensuite dans le champs de texte '**Transfert**' le nom de la boutique ou du dépôt qui recevra les articles à transférer
- 4) si vous avez des notes spécifiques à ce transfert d'articles, écrire les dans le champs de texte '**notes**'
- 5) cliquez sur bouton "**Sortir**" pour conclure le transfert d'articles.

6.4 Autres opérations de sortie d'articles / de stocks

Pour toutes autres opérations de sortie des stocks, appliquer la méthode similaire décrite dans le chapitre 5 qui porte sur la vente d'articles (ex. : annuler la sortie d'articles, imprimer une proforma du bon de sortie, etc.).

Chapitre 7

Les Ventes (les états des ventes d'articles)

Rôles ayant accès à la fonctionnalité : Caissier 2.7, Manager 2.3.

Ce chapitre décrit comment consulter les chiffres d'affaires (les recettes). Le chapitre explique aussi comment paramétrer cette consultation afin d'obtenir des résultats plus précis (ex : le chiffre d'affaire réalisé sur un article).

7.1 Introduction

The screenshot shows the 'Yeroth-erp-3.0 - ventes' application window. It features a menu bar with 'Actions', 'Outils', and 'Aide'. Below the menu is a toolbar with icons for home, back, help, and print, along with 'Menu principal' and 'Alertes' buttons. The main content area has two tabs: 'Ventes' (selected) and 'Détails d'une vente'. A search bar labeled 'référence' is positioned above a table of sales records. The table has columns for 'Nr. Fac.', 'Date vente', 'Heure vente', 'Référence', 'Catégorie', 'Désignation', 'Prix unitaire', and 'Qté'. Below the table is a summary section with various filters and statistics.

	Nr. Fac.	Date vente	Heure vente	Référence	Catégorie	Désignation	Prix unitaire	Qté
1	12	28.12.2019	09:53:40	129876543	Tea	Curcuma-gins.	1 600,00	2,00
2	13	28.12.2019	09:54:01	129876543	Tea	Curcuma-gins.	1 600,00	1,00
3	14	28.12.2019	10:07:24	129876543	Tea	Curcuma-gins.	1 600,00	1,00
4	14	28.12.2019	10:07:24	123456789	Eau minérale	Supermont	110,00	1,00
5	15	28.12.2019	10:09:24	129876543	Tea	Curcuma-gins.	1 600,00	1,00
6	15	28.12.2019	10:09:24	123456789	Eau minérale	Supermont	110,00	1,00
7	16	28.12.2019	10:14:30	129876543	Tea	Curcuma-gins.	1 600,00	1,00
8	16	28.12.2019	10:14:30	123456789	Eau minérale	Supermont	110,00	1,00

Début	28/12/2019	désignation	Quantité vendue	9,00
Fin	28/12/2019	nom de la catégorie d'articles	TVA (FCFA)	719,91 FCFA
nom du caissier (caissière)		nom de l'entreprise cliente	Remise totale	0,00 FCFA
nom de l'entreprise fournisseur		numéro de facture	Total vente	10 649,91 FCFA
Total vente	>=			
réinitialiser filtre		filtrer		réinitialiser

Figure 7.1 – La fenêtre du module caisse (les états de ventes)

Le module 'Caisse' de yerith-erp-3.0 donne une vue d'ensemble sur toutes les ventes effectuées. La figure 7.1 illustre l'interface graphique du module 'Caisse'.

7.2 Voir le journal des ventes sur une période de temps

Un utilisateur **avec le rôle Manager** définit les dates de début et de fin de la période sur laquelle il souhaite voir les ventes. Il peut aussi ajouter les paramètres suivants à sa requête :

- 1) le nom d'un caissier (champs de texte '**Caissier**')
- 2) la désignation d'un l'article (champs de texte '**Désignation**')
- 3) une catégorie d'articles (champs de texte '**Catégorie**')
- 4) le nom d'un client (champs de texte '**Client**')
- 5) le numéro d'une facture. (champs de texte '**Facture N.**').

Lorsque plus d'un paramètre est utilisé pour la requête, yerith-erp-3.0 emploi l'opérateur logique '**AND**' pour générer la requête.

NB : les utilisateurs **avec le rôle Caissier** ont seulement accès à leur journal des ventes du jour. Ils ont aussi accès au paramétrage des éléments suivants :

- 1) la désignation d'un l'article (champs de texte '**Désignation**')
- 2) une catégorie d'articles (champs de texte '**Catégorie**')
- 3) le numéro d'une facture. (champs de texte '**Facture N.**').

7.3 Voir les détails d'une vente

Il suffit de cliquer deux fois sur la vente sélectionnée.

7.4 Voir le journal des ventes d'un caissier

Il suffit de paramétrer la requête avec le nom de ce caissier dans le champs de texte '**Caissier**' (Voir la figure 7.1).

7.5 Voir le journal des ventes d'un article

Il suffit de paramétrer la requête avec la désignation de cet article. Ceci se fait dans le champs de texte '**Désignation**' (Voir la figure 7.1).

7.6 Voir le journal des ventes d'une catégorie d'articles

Il suffit de paramétrer la requête avec le nom de la catégorie de cet article. Ceci se fait dans le champs de texte '**Catégorie**' (Voir la figure 7.1).

7.7 Voir le journal des achats d'un client nommé

Il suffit de paramétrer la requête avec le nom du client concerné. Ceci se fait dans le champs de texte '**Client**' (Voir la figure 7.1).

7.8 Voir le journal des ventes d'une facture

Il suffit de paramétrer la requête avec le numéro de facture correspondant. Ceci se fait dans le champs de texte '**Facture N.**' (Voir la figure 7.1).

7.9 Imprimer le journal des ventes au format PDF

Il existe deux méthodes pour imprimer 'le journal des ventes' de la liste des ventes qui apparaît à la fenêtre titré '**Yerith-erp-3.0 - Caisse**'.

✓ 1^{ère} méthode

Cliquer sur le lien '**Imprimer le journal des ventes**' qui se trouve dans le menu déroulant '**Outils**'

✓ 2^{ème} méthode

Presser simultanément les boutons "**CTRL**" et "**P**" de votre clavier.

Chapitre 8

Les Mouvements de Stocks

Rôles ayant accès à la fonctionnalité : Magasinier 2.6, Manager 2.3.

Ce chapitre explique la différence entre une sortie et un transfert de stocks. Il décrit aussi comment consulter les transferts et les sorties des stocks effectués.

8.1 Introduction

Figure 8.1 – La fenêtre pour visualiser les sorties et les transferts d’articles.

La figure 8.1 illustre l’interface de yerith–erp–3.0 pour visualiser les sorties et les transferts d’articles.

Dans yerith–erp–3.0, une transaction est :

- 1) une **sortie de stocks**,
- 2) ou bien un **transfert de stocks**.

Une **sortie de stocks** est le retrait d’articles par un client auprès d’une boutique ou d’un dépôt de l’entreprise qui utilise yerith–erp–3.0.

Un **transfert de stocks** est un mouvement de stocks d’une boutique ou d’un dépôt de l’entreprise vers une boutique ou dépôt de votre entreprise.

8.2 Voir les transactions sur une période de temps

- 1) Sélectionnez les dates de début et de fin respectivement dans les champs de dates ‘Début’ et ‘Fin’.

Les transferts de stocks s'affichent automatiquement dans le 1^{er} premier onglet, pendant que les sorties de stocks s'affichent automatiquement dans le 2^{ème} onglet.

L'utilisateur peut aussi ajouter les paramètres suivants à sa requête :

- 1) le nom d'un magasinier (champs de texte '**Magasinier**')
- 2) la désignation d'un l'article (champs de texte '**Désignation**')
- 3) la catégorie d'un l'article (champs de texte '**Catégorie**')
- 4) le numéro d'un bon de sortie (champs de texte '**Numéro du bon de sortie**')
- 5) le nom d'un récepteur (champs de texte '**Nom du récepteur**').

Lorsque plus d'un paramètre est utilisé pour la requête, yerith-erp-3.0 emploi l'opérateur logique '**AND**' entre les différents paramètres pour générer le résultat de la requête.

8.3 Voir les transactions d'un magasinier

- 1) Sélectionnez dans le champs de texte '**Magasinier**' le nom du magasinier dont vous souhaitez observer les transactions effectuées .
- 2) Les transactions du magasinier choisi s'affichent automatiquement.

8.4 Voir les transactions d'un article

- 1) Sélectionnez dans le champs de texte '**Désignation**' la désignation de l'article dont vous souhaitez visualiser les transactions effectuées .
- 2) Les transactions de l'article choisi s'affichent automatiquement.

8.5 Voir les transactions d'une catégorie d'articles

- 1) Sélectionnez dans le champs de texte '**Catégorie**' le nom de la catégorie d'articles dont vous souhaitez visualiser les transactions effectuées.
- 2) Les transactions de la catégorie d'articles choisie s'affichent automatiquement.

8.6 Voir les transactions d'un bon de sortie

- 1) Sélectionnez dans le champs de texte '**Numéro du bon de sortie**' le numéro du bon de sortie dont vous souhaitez visualiser les transactions effectuées.
- 2) Les transactions du bon de sortie choisi s'affichent automatiquement.

8.7 Voir les transactions d'un récepteur d'articles

- 1) Sélectionnez dans le champs de texte '**Nom du récepteur**' le nom de la personne dont vous souhaitez visualiser les transactions effectuées, dont il a été le récepteur.
- 2) Les transactions de la personne choisi s'affichent automatiquement.

8.8 Imprimer le journal des transactions au format PDF

Il existe deux méthodes pour imprimer 'le journal des transactions' qui apparaît dans la fenêtre titrée '**Yerith-erp-3.0 - transactions**'.

✓ 1^{ère} méthode

Cliquez sur le lien '**Imprimer le journal des sorties/transferts**' qui se trouve dans le menu déroulant '**Outils**'.

✓ 2^{ème} méthode

Pressez simultanément les boutons "**CTRL**" et "**P**" de votre clavier.

Un fichier au format PDF est alors généré et affiché.

La figure 8.2 illustre un exemple de journal de sorties des stocks au format PDF.

YEROTH
Computer Systems R&D Start-Up
Email: yerotherp30@gmail.com
Tél.: +237 6 80 59 65 72
B.P.: 626262, Douala

Numéro de contribuable: 123456789
Numéro de compte bancaire: 123456789,
UBC Plc

Douala, le samedi 28 décembre 2019

Journal des transferts d'articles du 28.12.2019 au 28.12.2019

Imprimé par: Xavier NOUMBISSI-NOUNDOU
Heure d'impression: 10:27:08
Filtres: ""

id	Date sortie	Heure sortie	Référence	Désignation	Catégorie	Qté sortie	Local. sortie	Local. entrée	Nom magasinier
1	28.12.2019	10:27:01	5678	Thé	Tea	3,00	Bassa	Bonapriso - .	Xavier NOUMB.
						3,00			

Figure 8.2 – Un journal de sorties des stocks.

Chapitre 9

Les Tableaux de Bords

Rôles ayant accès à la fonctionnalité : Manager 2.3.

Ce chapitre décrit comment consulter les tableaux de bord. En effet, bon nombre de décisions des Manager proviennent de la visualisation des rapports financiers, et commerciaux.

9.1 Introduction

Figure 9.1 – La fenêtre principale pour générer les tableaux de bords.

La figure ?? illustre l'interface de yerith-erp-3.0 pour paramétrer et générer l'évolution du chiffre d'affaire (au format PDF) sur une période de temps.

L'interface graphique 'comparaison des chiffres d'affaires' (figure ??) permet à l'utilisateur de comparer les chiffres d'affaire d'objets allant de 2 à 9 unités.

Les objets de comparaisons sont les suivants :

- 1) le chiffre d'affaire des articles vendus
- 2) le chiffre d'affaire des catégories d'articles vendues
- 3) le chiffre d'affaire des clients nommés de l'entreprise
- 4) le chiffre d'affaire des caissiers de l'entreprise.

L'utilisateur a le choix entre les diagrammes comparatifs suivants :

- 1) le diagramme en bande
- 2) le diagramme circulaire.

La figure 9.3 et 9.4 illustrent des exemples de diagramme comparatif en 'diagramme en bande' et en 'diagramme circulaire' respectivement.

9.2 Générer l'évolution du chiffre d'affaire

Il faut effectuer les actions suivantes dans l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 illustrée dans la figure ?? :

- 1) choisir la date de 'début (mois)'
- 2) choisir la date de 'fin (mois)'
- 3) choisir l'année souhaitée
- 4) conclure en cliquant sur le bouton "**générer le fichier PDF**".

9.3 Générer les chiffres d'affaires de plusieurs articles de façon comparative

La figure ?? illustre comment générer un diagramme en bande, comparatif des quatre articles avec les chiffres d'affaires les plus élevés.

Figure 9.2 – Une figure comparative des chiffres d'affaires de quatre articles de la fenêtre des rapports commerciaux.

La figure 9.3 illustre le fichier PDF généré avec pour option 'diagramme en bandes'.

La figure 9.4 illustre le fichier PDF généré avec pour option 'diagramme circulaire'.

YEROTH
Computer Systems R&D Start-Up
Émail: yerotherp30@gmail.com
Tél.: +237 6 80 59 65 72
B.P.: 626262 Douala

Numéro de contribuable: 123456789
Numéro de compte bancaire: 123456789,
UBC Plc

Douala, le samedi 28 décembre 2019

Diagramme en bandes représentant "articles avec les chiffres d'affaires les plus élevés" (en pourcentage %).

Générer par: Xavier NOUMBISSI-NOUNDOU
Heure de génération: 10:29:49
Période: 01.01.2019 – 28.12.2019

Figure 1: articles avec les chiffres d'affaires les plus élevés.

Détails en FCFA:

- 1) "Curcuma-ginseng tea": 20 600,00 FCFA
- 2) "Supermont": 1 039,70 FCFA

YEROTH
Computer Systems R&D Start-Up
Émail: yerotherp30@gmail.com
Tél.: +237 6 80 59 65 72
B.P.: 626262 Douala

Numéro de contribuable: 123456789
Numéro de compte bancaire: 123456789,
UBC Plc

Douala, le samedi 28 décembre 2019

Diagramme circulaire représentant "articles avec les chiffres d'affaires les plus élevés" (en pourcentage %).

Générer par: Xavier NOUMBISSI-NOUNDOU
Heure de génération: 10:33:29
Période: 01.01.2019 – 28.12.2019

Figure 1: articles avec les chiffres d'affaires les plus élevés.

Détails en FCFA:

- 1) "Curcuma-ginseng tea": 20 600,00 FCFA
- 2) "Supermont": 1 039,70 FCFA

9.4 Générer les chiffres d'affaires de plusieurs catégories articles de façon comparative

Il faut procéder comme à la section 9.3, juste en changeant le combo box 'sujets' d'articles à 'catégories' et le combo box 'qualité'.

9.5 Générer les chiffres d'affaires de plusieurs clients de façon comparative

Il faut procéder comme à la section 9.3, juste en changeant le combo box 'sujets' d'articles à 'clients' et le combo box 'qualité'.

9.6 Générer les chiffres d'affaires de plusieurs caissiers de façon comparative

Il faut procéder comme à la section 9.3, juste en changeant le combo box 'sujets' d'articles à 'caissiers' et le combo box 'qualité'.

Chapitre 10

Les Informations Générales

Rôles ayant accès à la fonctionnalité : Administrateur 2.2, Caissier 2.7, Magasinier 2.6, Manager 2.3.

Ce chapitre décrit comment avoir accès aux informations publiques de l'entreprise et de yerith-erp-3.0 (ex. : le siège social de l'entreprise, la version de yerith-erp-3.0 utilisée, etc).

10.1 Voir les détails de l'utilisateur avec lequel on s'est enregistré

Figure 10.1 – Un exemple de la fonctionnalité 'Qui suis je?'.

La figure 10.1 illustre un exemple de la fonctionnalité '**Qui suis je?**'.

À partir de n'importe quelle fenêtre de yerith-erp-3.0, cliquez sur le lien '**Qui suis je?**' dans le menu déroulant '**Outils**' pour obtenir les informations suivantes de l'utilisateur avec lequel on s'est enregistré :

- 1) l'email
- 2) l'identification de l'utilisateur
- 3) la localisation
- 4) les noms
- 5) le numéro de téléphone 1
- 6) le numéro de téléphone 2
- 7) les prénoms
- 8) le rôle
- 9) le titre.

10.2 Voir les informations générales de l'entreprise

À partir de n'importe quelle fenêtre de yerith-erp-3.0 (excepté les fenêtres de l'administration), cliquez sur le lien '**Informations sur l'entreprise**' dans le menu déroulant '**Aide**' pour obtenir les informations suivantes de l'entreprise où yerith-erp-3.0 est ainsi déployé :

- 1) l'email
- 2) l'adresse
- 3) la boîte postale
- 4) la dénomination de l'entreprise
- 5) la localisation
- 6) le numéro de contribuable
- 7) le pays
- 8) les secteurs d'activités
- 9) le siège social
- 10) le téléphone
- 11) la ville.

La figure 10.2 illustre un exemple de la fonctionnalité '**Informations sur l'entreprise**'.

Figure 10.2 – Un exemple de la fonctionnalité '**Informations sur l'entreprise**'.

10.3 Voir le manuel de l'utilisateur au format PDF

Il suffit de cliquer sur le lien '**Manuel de l'utilisateur (PDF)**' qui se trouve dans le menu '**Aide**' de la fenêtre principale de chaque type d'utilisateur de yerith-erp-3.0 :

- 1) *Administrateur* (voir figure 2.1)
- 2) *Caissier* (voir figure 2.6)
- 3) *Magasinier* (voir figure 2.5)
- 4) *Manager* (voir figure 2.2).

10.4 Voir la version de yerith-erp-3.0 que vous utilis

Il suffit de cliquer sur le lien '** propos**' qui se trouve dans le menu '**Aide**' de n'importe quelle fenetre de yerith-erp-3.0.

La figure 10.3 illustre un exemple de la fonctionnalit '** propos**'.

Figure 10.3 – Un exemple de la fonctionnalit '** propos**'.

Chapitre 11

L'Administration de yerith-erp-3.0

Rôles ayant accès à la fonctionnalité : Administrateur 2.2, Manager 2.3.

Ce chapitre décrit comment effectuer les tâches d'administration (ex : créer un nouveau compte pour un utilisateur, etc.).

11.1 Introduction

Figure 11.1 – La fenêtre de l'administrateur.

La figure 11.1 illustre la fenêtre d'accueil de l'administration de yerith-erp-3.0.

On y arrive automatiquement lorsqu'on s'enregistre à yerith-erp-3.0 avec un utilisateur du rôle *Administrateur*.

Avec un utilisateur du rôle *Manager*, on clique sur le bouton "**Administration**" à partir de l'interface d'accueil des utilisateurs du rôle *Manager* (voir figure 2.2).

11.2 La connection à d'autres localisations

La figure 11.2 illustre l'interface graphique de connection à la base de données d'une autre localisation; cette interface graphique est le 1^{er} onglet de la fenêtr de l'administration.

Figure 11.2 – l'interface graphique de connection de yerith-erp-3.0 à d'autres localisations.

Voici la procédure par laquelle l'utilisateur peut connecter son installation de yerith-erp-3.0 à la base de données d'autres localisations :

- 1) choisir dans le champs de texte '**localisation**' le nom de localisation à laquelle on souhaite se connecter. Lorsque cela est fait, l'adresse IP de la localisation choisie est automatiquement affichée dans le champs de texte '**adresse IP**'
- 2) cliquer sur le bouton "**connecter**".

Si la connection est réussie, le mot '**ONLINE**' est affiché en couleur verte au dessus du bouton "**connecter**".

11.3 Les paramètres généraux

La figure 11.3 illustre l'interface graphique des paramètres généraux de yerith-erp-3.0; cette interface graphique est le 4^{ème} onglet de la fenêtr de l'administration de yerith-erp-3.0.

Les paramètres généraux qui peuvent être modifiés sont les suivants :

- 1) le lecteur des fichiers PDF
- 2) le compilateur des fichiers '.tex'
- 3) le répertoire des fichiers temporaires
- 4) la taxe sur la valeur ajouté
- 5) la stratégie de vente/sortie des stocks (**CMUP**, **DEF_DEO**, **FIFO**, **LIFO**)
 - 1) la sélection de **CMUP** présente tous les stocks présents dans la base de données
 - 2) la sélection **DEF_DEO** présente tous les stocks selon la stratégie "**Date of Preemption, First Date of Preemption Out**"
 - 3) la sélection de **FIFO** présente tous les stocks selon la stratégie "**First In, First Out**"
 - 4) la sélection de **LIFO** présente tous les stocks selon la stratégie "**Last In, First Out**"
- 6) le format des fichiers de facturations
- 7) l'année de départ des rapports lors de la génération des chiffres d'affaire.

Les stratégies de gestion des stocks sont décrites dans la section 3.2.

Figure 11.3 – l'interface graphique de paramétrage général de yerith-erp-3.0.

11.4 Les paramètres du système d'alertes

La figure 11.4 illustre l'interface graphique des paramètres du système d'alertes de yerith-erp-3.0; cette interface graphique est le 5^{ème} onglet de la fenêtre de l'administration de yerith-erp-3.0.

Figure 11.4 – l'interface graphique de paramétrage du système d'alertes yerith-erp-3.0.

Le système d'alertes est démarré par défaut lors du démarrage de l'ordinateur.

Il faut démarrer l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 en tant qu'administrateur du système d'exploitation afin de pouvoir stopper le système d'alertes lorsqu'il a été démarré lors du démarrage de l'ordinateur.

Les paramètres du système d'alertes qui peuvent être modifiés sont les suivants :

- 1) **alertes sur la période (s)** : définit l'intervalle de temps (en secondes) après lequel yerith-erp-3.0 visite la base de données pour voir s'il y'a de nouvelles alertes sur les périodes de temps
- 2) **alertes sur la quantité (s)** : définit l'intervalle de temps (en secondes) après lequel yerith-erp-3.0 visite la base de données pour voir s'il y'a de nouvelles alertes sur les quantités en stocks.

Cette interface graphique permet aussi :

- 1) de **démarrer le système d'alertes** en pressant sur le bouton "**démarrer**". Lorsque le système d'alertes est en marche, le mot anglais '**ON**' est affiché en vert au dessus du bouton "**démarrer**".
- 2) **d'arrêter le système d'alertes** en pressant sur le bouton "**arrêter**". Lorsque le système d'alertes n'est pas en marche, le mot anglais '**OFF**' est affiché en couleur rouge au dessus du bouton "**arrêter**".
Cette action nécessite que l'utilisateur est démarré yerith-erp-3.0 en tant qu'administrateur du système d'exploitation.
- 3) **d'actualiser le statut** dans lequel se trouve le système d'alertes en pressant sur le bouton "**rafraîchir le statut**".

11.5 Les Alertes

11.5.1 Afficher les détails d'une alerte

La figure 11.5 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 qui affiche les détails d'une alerte.

Figure 11.5 – Une interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 qui affiche les détails d'une alerte.

✓ Procédure pour afficher les détails d'une alerte

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**une alerte**' dans le '*combo box sujets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.7.
- 4) Sélectionner l'alerte dont vous souhaitez afficher les détails dans la liste des alertes affichée.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Afficher**". Les détails sur le stock sont affichés dans une nouvelle fenêtre.

11.5.2 Créer une alerte

La figure 11.6 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour créer une alerte.

Données de l'alerte	
désignation de l'article	Curcuma-ginseng tea
désignation de l'alerte	curcuma_alerte_3
ID du destinataire	ycassiere1
quantité en stock	57
stock minimum	66
date de péremption	04.12.2020
nom du destinataire	Caissière YEROTH YEROTH
condition	<=
quantité	50
début	28/12/2019
fin	28/12/2019
message de l'alerte	Renouveler le stock !

Figure 11.6 – L'interface graphique pour créer des alertes.

✓ **Procédure pour créer une alerte** Consulter les sections 4.2 et 4.3 pour savoir comment créer respectivement des alertes sur la quantité en stock et des alertes sur la période de temps.

11.5.3 Lister les alertes

La figure 11.7 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 qui liste les alertes.

Figure 11.7 – L'interface graphique qui liste les alertes.

✓ Procédure pour lister les alertes

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir la figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**une alerte**' dans le '*combo box sujets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre qui liste les alertes (voir la figure 11.7).

11.5.4 Modifier les détails d'une alerte

La figure 11.8 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour modifier les détails d'une alerte.

Figure 11.8 – L'interface graphique pour modifier les d'étails d'une alerte.

✓ Procédure pour modifier les détails d'une alerte

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le 'combo box opérations'.
- 3) Choisir '**une alerte**' dans le 'combo box sujets'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.7.
- 4) Sélectionner l'alerte dont vous souhaitez modifier les détails dans la liste des alertes affichée.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Modifier**". Les détails sur le stock sont affichés dans une nouvelle fenêtre.
- 6) Faites les modifications que vous souhaitez. Pour les alertes, seul le message d'alerte peut être modifié.
- 7) Cliquer sur le bouton "**valider**" pour valider les modifications faites.

11.5.5 Supprimer une alerte

La figure 11.9 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour supprimer une alerte.

Figure 11.9 – L'interface graphique pour supprimer des alertes.

✓ Procédure pour supprimer une alerte

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**supprimer**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**une alerte**' dans le '*combo box sujets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.7.
- 4) Sélectionner l'alerte à supprimer dans la liste des alertes affichée.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Supprimer**". La question est ensuite posée si vous confirmer votre choix. Cliquer sur le "**OK**" pour confirmer votre choix.

11.6 Les Catégories d'Articles

11.6.1 Afficher les détails d'une catégorie d'articles

Figure 11.10 – L'interface graphique pour afficher les détails d'une catégorie d'articles.

La figure 11.10 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 qui affiche les détails d'une catégorie d'articles.

✓ Procédure pour afficher les détails d'une catégorie d'articles

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**une catégorie d'articles**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.12.
- 4) Sélectionner la catégorie d'articles dont vous souhaitez afficher les détails.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Afficher**". Les détails sur la catégorie d'articles sont affichés dans une nouvelle fenêtre.

11.6.2 Créer une catégorie d'articles

Figure 11.11 – L'interface graphique pour créer une catégorie d'articles.

La figure 11.11 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour créer une nouvelle catégorie d'articles.

✓ Procédure pour créer une catégorie d'articles

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**créer**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**une catégorie d'articles**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.11.
- 4) Saisissez la désignation de la nouvelle catégorie d'articles à créer dans le champs de texte '**désignation**'.
- 5) Si vous le souhaitez, saisissez un texte qui décrit cette nouvelle catégorie d'articles dans le champs de texte '**description de la catégorie**'.
- 6) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Valider**" pour valider votre travail.

11.6.3 Lister les catégories d'articles

Figure 11.12 – L'interface graphique qui liste les catégories d'articles.

La figure 11.12 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 qui liste les catégories d'articles.

✓ Procédure pour lister les catégories d'articles

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**une catégorie d'articles**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre qui liste les catégories d'articles (figure 11.12).

11.6.4 Modifier les détails d'une catégorie d'articles

Figure 11.13 – L'interface graphique pour modifier les d'étails d'une catégorie d'articles.

La figure 11.13 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour modifier les détails d'une catégorie d'articles.

✓ Procédure pour modifier les détails d'une catégorie d'articles

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**catégorie d'articles**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.12.
- 4) Sélectionner l'alerte dont vous souhaitez modifier les détails dans la liste des désignations des catégories d'articles affichée.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Modifier**". Les détails sur le stock sont affichés dans une nouvelle fenêtre.
- 6) Faites les modifications que vous souhaitez. Pour les alertes, seul le message d'alerte peut être modifié.
- 7) Cliquer sur le bouton "**valider**" pour valider les modifications faites.

11.6.5 Supprimer une catégorie d'article

Figure 11.14 – L'interface graphique pour supprimer une catégorie d'articles.

La figure 11.14 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour supprimer une catégorie d'articles.

✓ Procédure pour supprimer une catégorie d'articles

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**supprimer**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**une catégorie d'articles**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.12.
- 4) Sélectionner l'alerte à supprimer dans la liste des désignations des catégories d'articles affichée.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Supprimer**". La question est ensuite posée si vous confirmer votre choix. Cliquer sur le "**OK**" pour confirmer votre choix.

11.7 Les Comptes Clients

11.7.1 Afficher les détails d'un compte client

Figure 11.15 – L'interface graphique pour afficher les détails d'un compte client.

La figure 11.15 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 qui affiche les détails d'un compte client.

✓ Procédure pour afficher les détails d'un compte client

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**un compte client**' dans le '*combo box sujets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.17.
- 4) Sélectionner le compte client dont vous souhaitez afficher les détails dans la liste des comptes clients affichée.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Afficher**". Les détails du compte client sont affichés dans une nouvelle fenêtre.

11.7.2 Créer un compte client

The screenshot shows a web application window titled "Yeren - administration - créer". The interface includes a menu bar with "Actions", "Outils", and "Aide". Below the menu is a "Menu principal" section with buttons for "Créer", "Lister", "Administration", "Modifier", and "Supprimer". A secondary menu contains tabs for "Alerte", "Bon de commande", "Catégorie", "Client", "Compte utilisateur", "Fournisseur", and "Localisation". The main content area is titled "Données du client" and contains a form with the following fields: "nom de l'entreprise", "nom du représentant", "quartier", "ville", "pays", "siège social", "email @", "numéro de téléphone 1", "numéro de téléphone 2", and "numéro de contribuable". A large text area for "description du client" is also present. At the bottom right of the form are "Annuler" and "Valider" buttons.

Figure 11.16 – L'interface graphique pour créer un compte client.

La figure 11.16 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour créer un nouveau compte client.

✓ Procédure pour créer un compte client

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**créer**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**un compte client**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.16.
- 4) Saisissez les informations requises dans les champs de texte suivants :
 - 1) nom de l'entreprise **[obligatoire]**
 - 2) nom du représentant **[obligatoire]**
 - 3) quartier
 - 4) ville
 - 5) pays
 - 6) siège social
 - 7) email@
 - 8) numéro de téléphone 1
 - 9) numéro de téléphone 2
 - 10) numéro de contribuable
 - 11) description du client.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Valider**" pour valider votre travail.

11.7.3 Lister les comptes clients

Figure 11.17 – L'interface graphique qui liste les comptes clients.

La figure 11.17 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 qui liste les comptes clients.

✓ Procédure pour lister les comptes clients

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**un compte client**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre qui liste les comptes clients (figure 11.17).

11.7.4 Modifier les détails d'un compte client

Figure 11.18 – L'interface graphique pour modifier les détails d'un compte client.

La figure 11.18 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour modifier les détails d'un compte client.

✓ Procédure pour modifier les détails d'un compte client

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**un compte client**' dans le '*combo box sujets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.17.
- 4) Sélectionner le compte client dont vous souhaitez modifier les détails dans la liste des comptes clients affichée.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Modifier**". Les détails du compte client sont affichés dans une nouvelle fenêtre.
- 6) Faites les modifications que vous souhaitez.
- 7) Cliquer sur le bouton "**valider**" pour valider les modifications faites.

11.7.5 Supprimer un compte client

Figure 11.19 – L'interface graphique pour supprimer un compte client.

La figure 11.19 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour supprimer un compte client.

✓ Procédure pour supprimer un compte client

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**supprimer**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**un compte client**' dans le '*combo box sujets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.17.
- 4) Sélectionner le compte client à supprimer dans la liste des comptes clients affichée.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Supprimer**". La question est ensuite posée si vous confirmer votre choix. Cliquer sur le "**OK**" pour confirmer votre choix.

11.8 Les Comptes Fournisseurs

11.8.1 Afficher les détails d'un compte fournisseur

Figure 11.20 – L'interface graphique pour afficher les détails d'un compte fournisseur.

La figure 11.20 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 qui affiche les détails d'un compte fournisseur.

✓ Procédure pour afficher les détails d'un compte fournisseur

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**un compte fournisseur**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.22.
- 4) Sélectionner le compte fournisseur dont vous souhaitez afficher les détails dans la liste des comptes fournisseurs affichée.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Afficher**". Les détails sur le compte fournisseur sont affichés dans une nouvelle.

11.8.2 Créer un compte fournisseur

The screenshot shows a web application window titled "Yeren - administration - créer". At the top, there is a menu with "Actions", "Outils", and "Aide". Below this is a "Menu principal" with several icons. The main content area has a row of buttons: "Créer", "Lister", "Administration", "Modifier", and "Supprimer". Below these buttons is a horizontal tab bar with "Alerte", "Bon de commande", "Catégorie", "Client", "Compte utilisateur", "Fournisseur", and "Localisation". The "Fournisseur" tab is selected. The main form area is titled "Données du fournisseur" and contains two columns of input fields. The left column has fields for: "nom de l'entreprise", "nom du représentant", "quartier", "ville", "pays", "siège social", "email @", "numéro de téléphone 1", "numéro de téléphone 2", and "numéro de contribuable". The right column has a large text area for "description du fournisseur". At the bottom right of the form are two buttons: "Annuler" and "Valider".

Figure 11.21 – L'interface graphique pour créer un nouveau compte fournisseur.

La figure 11.21 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour créer un nouveau compte fournisseur.

✓ Procédure pour créer un compte fournisseur

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**créer**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**un compte fournisseur**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.21.
- 4) Saisissez les informations requises dans les champs de texte suivants :
 - 1) nom de l'entreprise **[obligatoire]**
 - 2) nom du représentant
 - 3) quartier
 - 4) ville
 - 5) pays
 - 6) siège social
 - 7) email@
 - 8) numéro de téléphone 1
 - 9) numéro de téléphone 2
 - 10) numéro de contribuable
 - 11) description du fournisseur.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Valider**" pour valider votre travail.

11.8.3 Lister les fournisseurs

Figure 11.22 – L'interface graphique pour lister les comptes fournisseurs.

La figure 11.22 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 qui liste les comptes fournisseurs.

✓ Procédure pour lister les comptes fournisseurs

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**un compte fournisseur**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre qui liste les comptes fournisseurs (figure 11.22).

11.8.4 Modifier les détails d'un fournisseur

Figure 11.23 – L'interface graphique pour modifier les détails d'un compte fournisseur.

La figure 11.23 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour modifier les détails d'un compte fournisseur.

✓ Procédure pour modifier les détails d'un compte fournisseur

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**un compte fournisseur**' dans le '*combo box sujets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.22.
- 4) Sélectionner le compte fournisseur dont vous souhaitez modifier les détails dans la liste des comptes fournisseurs affichée.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Modifier**". Les détails du compte fournisseur sont affichés dans une nouvelle fenêtre.
- 6) Faites les modifications que vous souhaitez.
- 7) Cliquer sur le bouton "**valider**" pour valider les modifications faites.

11.8.5 Supprimer un compte fournisseur

Figure 11.24 – L'interface graphique pour supprimer un fournisseur.

La figure 11.24 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour supprimer un compte fournisseur.

✓ Procédure pour supprimer un compte fournisseur

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**supprimer**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**un compte fournisseur**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.22.
- 4) Sélectionner le compte fournisseur à supprimer dans la liste des comptes fournisseurs affichée.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Supprimer**". La question est ensuite posée si vous confirmer votre choix. Cliquer sur le "**OK**" pour confirmer votre choix.

11.9 Les Comptes Utilisateurs

11.9.1 Afficher les détails d'un compte utilisateur

The screenshot shows a web application window titled "Yeren - administration - détail". The interface has a dark theme. At the top, there are menu items: "Actions", "Outils", and "Aide". Below this is a "Menu principal" with icons for home, back, and help. A row of buttons includes "Lister", "Créer", "Administration", "Modifier", and "Supprimer". Below these are tabs for "Alerte", "Bon de commande", "Catégorie", "Client", "Compte utilisateur", "Fournisseur", and "Localisation". The "Compte utilisateur" tab is active, displaying "Données personnelles de l'utilisateur" and "données de connexion".

Données personnelles de l'utilisateur	
prénom	Xavier
nom	NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU
titre	Pr.
lieu de naissance	Douala
date de naissance	01/01/1993
email @	xn@gmail.com
numéro de téléphone 1	
numéro de téléphone 2	

données de connexion	
id	xavierp
mot de passe	****
rôle	LePatron
localisation	Golf

Retour

Figure 11.25 – L'interface graphique pour afficher les détails d'un compte utilisateur.

La figure 11.25 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 qui affiche les détails d'un compte utilisateur.

✓ Procédure pour afficher les détails d'un compte utilisateur

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le 'combo box opérations'.
- 3) Choisir '**un compte utilisateur**' dans le 'combo box objets'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.27.
- 4) Sélectionner le compte utilisateur dont vous souhaitez afficher les détails dans la liste des comptes utilisateurs affichée.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Afficher**". Les détails sur le compte utilisateur sont affichés dans une nouvelle fenêtre.

11.9.2 Créer un compte utilisateur

The screenshot shows a web application window titled "Yeren - administration - créer". The interface has a dark theme. At the top, there is a menu bar with "Actions", "Outils", and "Aide". Below it is a "Menu principal" with icons for home, back, and help. A row of buttons includes "Créer", "Lister", "Administration", "Modifier", and "Supprimer". A secondary row of tabs includes "Alerte", "Bon de commande", "Catégorie", "Client", "Compte utilisateur", "Fournisseur", and "Localisation". The main content area is titled "Données personnelles de l'utilisateur" and contains two columns of form fields. The left column includes: "prénoms", "noms", "titre", "lieu de naissance", "date de naissance" (with a date picker showing "11/05/2017"), "émail @", "numéro de téléphone 1", and "numéro de téléphone 2". The right column is titled "données de connexion" and includes: "id", "mot de passe (1)", "mot de passe (2)", "rôle", and "localisation" (with a dropdown menu showing "Golf"). At the bottom right, there are "Annuler" and "Valider" buttons.

Figure 11.26 – L'interface graphique pour créer un compte utilisateur.

La figure 11.26 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour créer un nouveau compte utilisateur.

✓ Procédure pour créer un compte utilisateur

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**créer**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**un compte utilisateur**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.26.
- 4) Saisissez les informations requises dans les champs de texte suivants :
 - 1) prénoms **[obligatoire]**
 - 2) noms **[obligatoire]**
 - 3) titre **[obligatoire]**
 - 4) lieu de naissance
 - 5) date de naissance
 - 6) ville
 - 7) province / état
 - 8) pays
 - 9) boîte postale
 - 10) email
 - 11) numéro de téléphone 1
 - 12) numéro de téléphone 2
 - 13) nom d'utilisateur **[obligatoire]**
 - 14) mot de passe **[obligatoire]**
 - 15) vérification du mot de passe **[obligatoire]**
 - 16) rôle **[obligatoire]**.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Valider**" pour valider votre travail.

11.9.3 Lister les comptes utilisateurs

Figure 11.27 – L'interface graphique pour lister les comptes utilisateurs.

La figure 11.27 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 qui liste les comptes utilisateurs.

✓ Procédure pour lister les comptes utilisateurs

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**un compte utilisateur**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre qui liste les comptes clients (figure 11.27).

11.9.4 Modifier les détails d'un compte utilisateur

The screenshot shows a web application window titled "Yeren - administration - modifier". The interface includes a menu bar with "Actions", "Outils", and "Aide". Below the menu is a "Menu principal" section with buttons for "Créer", "Lister", "Administration", "Modifier", and "Supprimer". A secondary menu contains "Alerte", "Bon de commande", "Catégorie", "Client", "Compte utilisateur", "Fournisseur", and "Localisation". The main content area is titled "Données personnelles de l'utilisateur" and is divided into two columns. The left column contains fields for "prénom" (Xavier), "nom" (NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU), "titre" (Pr.), "lieu de naissance" (Douala), "date de naissance" (01/01/1993), "email @" (xn@gmail.com), "numéro de téléphone 1", and "numéro de téléphone 2". The right column is titled "données de connexion" and contains fields for "id" (xavierp), "mot de passe" (masked with asterisks), "rôle" (LePatron), and "localisation" (Golf). At the bottom of the form are "Annuler" and "Valider" buttons.

Figure 11.28 – L'interface graphique pour modifier les détails d'un compte utilisateur.

La figure 11.28 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour modifier les détails d'un compte utilisateur.

✓ Procédure pour modifier les détails d'un compte utilisateur

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**un compte utilisateur**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.27.
- 4) Sélectionner le compte utilisateur dont vous souhaitez modifier les détails dans la liste des comptes utilisateurs affichée.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Modifier**". Les détails du compte utilisateur sont affichés dans une nouvelle fenêtre.
- 6) Faites les modifications que vous souhaitez.
- 7) Cliquer sur le bouton "**valider**" pour valider les modifications faites.

11.9.5 Supprimer un compte utilisateur

Figure 11.29 – L'interface graphique pour supprimer un compte utilisateur.

La figure 11.29 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour supprimer un compte utilisateur.

✓ Procédure pour supprimer un compte utilisateur

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**supprimer**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**un compte utilisateur**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.27.
- 4) Sélectionner le compte utilisateur à supprimer dans la liste des comptes utilisateurs affichée.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Supprimer**". La question est ensuite posée si vous confirmer votre choix. Cliquer sur le "**OK**" pour confirmer votre choix.

11.10 Les Localisations

Une localisation représente une boutique ou un dépôt de l'entreprise utilisant yerith-erp-3.0.

Les informations sur une localisation permettent de se connecter à la base de données de la boutique ou du dépôt qu'elle représente.

11.10.1 Afficher les détails d'une localisation

La figure 11.30 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 qui affiche les détails d'une localisation.

Figure 11.30 – L'interface graphique pour afficher les détails d'une localisation.

✓ Procédure pour afficher les détails d'une localisation

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**une localisation**' dans le '*combo box sujets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.32.
- 4) Sélectionner la localisation dont vous souhaitez afficher les détails dans la liste des localisations affichée.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Afficher**". Les détails sur la localisation choisie sont affichés dans une nouvelle fenêtre.

11.10.2 Créer une localisation

La figure 11.31 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour créer une localisation.

✓ Procédure pour créer une localisation

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**créer**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**une localisation**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.31.
- 4) Saisissez les informations requises dans les champs de texte suivants :
 - 1) adresse IP

Figure 11.31 – L'interface graphique pour créer une localisation.

- 2) nom **[obligatoire]**
- 3) numéro unique
- 4) quartier
- 5) ville
- 6) province / état
- 7) pays
- 8) boîte postale
- 9) date d'ouverture
- 10) email@
- 11) numéro de téléphone 1
- 12) numéro de téléphone 2
- 13) base de données
- 14) description du lieu.

Si vous avez entré une adresse IP pour cette localisation, vous devez choisir le type de base de données utilisé dans cette localisation. Pour l'instant, yerith-erp-3.0 ne fonctionne qu'avec **MySQL**.

La section C.2 dans l'annexe C (L'Environnement Logiciel) contient plus d'information aux sujets des bases de données dans yerith-erp-3.0.

- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Valider**" pour valider votre travail.

11.10.3 Lister les localisations

La figure 11.32 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 qui liste les localisations.

Figure 11.32 – L'interface graphique pour créer une localisation.

✓ Procédure pour lister les localisations

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**une localisation**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre qui liste localisations (figure 11.32).

11.10.4 Modifier les détails d'une localisation

La figure 11.33 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour modifier les détails d'une localisation.

Figure 11.33 – L'interface graphique pour modifier les détails d'une localisation.

✓ Procédure pour modifier les détails d'une localisation

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**lister**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**une localisation**' dans le '*combo box objets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.32.
- 4) Sélectionner la localisation dont vous souhaitez modifier les détails dans la liste des localisations affichée.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Modifier**". Les détails de la localisation sont affichés dans une nouvelle fenêtre.
- 6) Faites les modifications que vous souhaitez.
- 7) Cliquer sur le bouton "**valider**" pour valider les modifications faites.

11.10.5 Supprimer une localisation

La figure 11.34 illustre l'interface graphique de yerith-erp-3.0 pour supprimer une localisation.

✓ Procédure pour supprimer une localisation

- 1) À partir de l'interface graphique de l'accueil de l'administration (voir figure 11.1), on clique sur l'onglet intitulé **opérations**.
- 2) Choisir '**supprimer**' dans le '*combo box opérations*'.
- 3) Choisir '**une localisation**' dans le '*combo box sujets*'. Vous êtes automatiquement conduit à la fenêtre illustrée par la figure 11.32.
- 4) Sélectionner la localisation à supprimer dans la liste des localisations affichée.
- 5) Cliquer sur le bouton "**Supprimer**". La question est ensuite posée si vous confirmer votre choix. Cliquer sur le "**OK**" pour confirmer votre choix.

Figure 11.34 – L'interface graphique pour supprimer une localisation.

Chapitre 12

Les Problèmes Connues et leurs Solutions

Ce chapitre décrit quelques problèmes qui peuvent survenir lors de l'utilisation de yerith-erp-3.0 et comment les résoudre.

12.1 Démarrage du Système d'Alerte

Lorsque l'on démarre le système d'alerte, le bouton **ON** n'est pas aussitôt affiché.

Il est nécessaire de quitter la fenêtre et d'y revenir pour voir le bouton **ON** affiché.

Chapitre 13

Conclusion

Nous avons décrit yerith-erp-3.0 dans ce document. yerith-erp-3.0 est un logiciel de gestion des stocks et de gestion des ventes.

yerith-erp-3.0 cible toutes les entreprises qui ont besoin d'une solution de gestion des stocks et de gestion des ventes efficaces et facile à utiliser.

yerith-erp-3.0 est concis, efficace, et solutionne les problèmes de gestion des stocks et de gestion des ventes d'une façon pragmatique.

L'apprentissage de yerith-erp-3.0 nécessite selon nos investigations environ 2 jours de formation de 4 heures chacun.

Merci pour votre confiance et vos appréciations.

"XAVIER NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]"

Ce chapitre présente les raccourcis usuels de yerith-erp-3.0, sous forme de tableau, pour accéder à certaines fonctions.

Raccourcis	Résumé de la fonction
Ctrl + H	Appelle l'aide, résumée pour l'utilisateur
Ctrl + P	Imprimer au format PDF
Ctrl + F	Lancer l'interface de recherche
Ctrl + I	Réinitialiser la recherche
Ctrl + W	Observer avec quel utilisateur je me suis enregistré (Qui suis je?)

Table A.1 – Tableau des raccourcis

L'environnement Hardware

Ce chapitre discute des composantes matérielles nécessaires pour le bon fonctionnement de yerith-erp-3.0.

B.1 La mémoire RAM

yerith-erp-3.0 peut être utilisé sur un ordinateur qui possède un minimum de 512 Mo de mémoire RAM (mémoire vive) sans aucun problème.

Cependant, nous recommandons l'utilisation d'ordinateurs ayant un minimum de 2 Go de mémoire RAM.

B.2 Le disque dur

L'utilisateur de yerith-erp-3.0 doit se prémunir d'un disque dur en fonction de la quantité de données qu'il prévoit stocker dans la base de données.

yerith-erp-3.0 n'a pas de requis quant à la capacité des disques durs du client. C'est le système d'exploitation et le système de gestion de base de données (SGBD) utilisé qui conditionnent la capacité des disques durs à utiliser.

B.3 Le Matériel Informatique Recommandé

YERITH-PGI-9.0 Matériel Informatique Recommandé Pour Le Point De Vente

1 Le Lecteur de Code barres

Nous recommandons l'utilisation du lecteur de code barres " USB Plug and Play Automatic Barcode Scanner " (approx. 17€).

Le lecteur de code barres

2 L'imprimante de Tickets PDV (thermique)

TOUTES LES IMPRIMANTES DE TICKETS EPSON.

Nous recommandons l'utilisation de l'imprimante de tickets PDV (thermique) " Epson TM T20ii Point of Sale Thermal Printer " (approx. 100€).

L'imprimante de tickets PDV (thermique)

3 Le Tiroir de Caisse

Nous recommandons l'utilisation du tiroir de caisse " HP QT457AT " (approx. 90€).

Le tiroir de caisse

4 Le Moniteur

Nous recommandons l'utilisation du moniteur d'ordinateur " ASUS 15.6" LCD Monitor (VT168H) " (approx. 155€).

L'écran tactile

5 L'ordinateur

Nous recommandons l'utilisation de l'ordinateur " Lenovo Thinkcentre M720 Small Form Factor (SFF) " (approx. 450€).

L'ordinateur

6 TERMINAL À PLUSIEURS UTILISATEURS

Nous recommandons l'utilisation du terminal à plusieurs utilisateurs (3) NC-300 de "<http://www.savingology.com>" (approx. 112€).

Terminal à Plusieurs Utilisateurs

✓ **PARTICULARITÉS DANS CERTAINS PAYS ET/OU RÉGIONS DU MONDE** L'USAGE DES IMPRIMANTES DE TICKETS PDV, REQUIERT L'ACHAT ET L'UTILISATION D'1 APPAREIL POUR ENREGISTRER ET CERTIFIER TOUTES LES TRANSACTIONS FINANCIÈRES ENTRE L'IMPRIMANTE PDV ET LE PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0 (exemple : RFA, CANADA, etc.).

L'environnement Logiciel

Ce chapitre discute des logiciels requis (ou recommandés) pour le bon fonctionnement de yerith-erp-3.0.

C.1 Le système d'exploitation

yerith-erp-3.0 fonctionne exclusivement avec **Debian Linux** comme système d'exploitation. yerith-erp-3.0 a été développé avec la **version 9.4.0 (stretch)** de Debian Linux.

C.2 Le système de gestion des bases de données

yerith-erp-3.0 utilise de façon standard **MySQL** comme système de gestion des bases de données.

Le progiciel de gestion intégré yerith-erp-3.0 a été développé et testé avec la version 5.5 de MySQL.

Ce chapitre décrit les différentes configurations de yerith-erp-3.0.

D.1 Les configurations de yerith-erp-3.0

yerith-erp-3.0 a les configurations suivantes :

- 1) la configuration **standalone**
- 2) la configuration **académique**
- 3) la configuration **client**
- 4) la configuration **serveur**.

D.2 La configuration *standalone* de yerith-erp-3.0

La configuration **standalone** de yerith-erp-3.0 comprend toutes les fonctionnalités. Elle est utilisée pour une boutique ou pour un dépôt qui a besoin d'une seule installation de yerith-erp-3.0.

D.3 La configuration *client* de yerith-erp-3.0

La configuration *client* fonctionne uniquement en combinaison avec la configuration *serveur* de yerith-erp-3.0.

La configuration **client** de yerith-erp-3.0 ne donne pas accès à la section **Administration** du logiciel. Aussi, elle ne permet pas l'accès aux stocks des autres localisations.

D.4 La configuration *serveur* de yerith-erp-3.0

La configuration **serveur** fonctionne uniquement en combinaison avec la configuration **client** de yerith-erp-3.0.

La configuration **serveur** de yerith-erp-3.0 comprend toutes les fonctionnalités et est utilisée dans le cadre d'une installation avec plusieurs **clients**.

Lorsqu'une configuration dans la section **paramètres de l'application** est modifiée, le serveur envoie un signal à chacun des **clients** afin qu'ils actualisent leurs paramètres de configuration, en les récupérant de la base de données.

REPORT ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0 (YEAR 2023)

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]"

YERITH_{r&d}
"Immeuble YERITH"
barrière-Simbock
Yaoundé VI, Cameroon
Email: YERITH.xavier@gmail.com

Yerith R&D

Yerith-erp-pgi platiNum business Workflow

Figure 1: YERITH-ERP-9.0 BUSINESS Workflow

Figure 2: YERITH-ERP-9.0 COMPONENTS Workflow

Yerith R&D

Yerith-erp-pgi platiNum COMPONENTS Workflow

Figure 3: YERITH-ERP-9.0 manager main window frame

Abstract

This annual report summarizes efforts of Computer Systems R&D Start-up YERITH_{r&d} on its Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) software product YERITH-ERP-9.0 in this year 2023.

YERITH-ERP-9.0 was invented in October 2015 in Yaoundé, Center region of Cameroon: it is an integrated Enterprise Resource Planing software for small, medium, and large entrepreneurial organizations. An entrepreneurial organization is here recognized as either a non governmental organization (N.G.O), a governmental agency, or a commercial society.

"**Financial expense management**" and "**Human resource management**" software modules sections were improved and incorporated respectively this year. Also, several improvements on financial accounting reporting were made.

A new software product: YERITH_QVGE (<https://zenodo.org/records/10070127>), was created as YERITH-ERP-9.0's runtime monitoring analysis verification module. YERITH_QVGE can run as a stand-alone product, or as a system service for YERITH-ERP-9.0 **on the Debian Linux operating system platform.**

YERITH_QVGE (<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) is a state-of-the-art **program analysis generator** that compares with bleeding edge technology software products used at The NASA (<https://www.nasa.gov>), such as "LogScope" [Hav22] and "DejaVu" [HPU18] by Dr. KLAUS HAVELUND (<https://www.havelund.com>).

Other comparable bleeding edge technology libraries and / or tools include "libfsmtest" (<https://bitbucket.org/JanPeleska/libfsmtest/src/master>) by Prof. Dr. rer. nat. habil. JAN PELESKA (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp>); "EventRaceCommander" [AMK⁺17] and "Purify" [HJ91] at IBM (<https://research.ibm.com/labs/watson>); and "Valkyrie / Valgrind" (<https://valgrind.org>).

YERITH_QVGE's (<https://zenodo.org/records/10070127>) drawing tool is priced at 2, 500 EUROS.

PEOPLE LISTED HERE, in alphabetical order, have financed and / or supported YERITH_{r&d} in the last 5 years (2023 backward):

1. Ing. Célestin Puene, MSc
2. Christian Ngueyong, AS degree in Computer Science
3. Collins Akosa, MASc (Waterloo, 2012), PhD (KAUST, 2016)
4. Dr. Emmanuel Rodrigue Wankap
5. Henri Bertrand Ngatchou (Ets Best Car Care & Services)
6. Dipl.-Inf. (FH) Jean-Daniel Tujilo
7. Joachim Nsofini , PhD (Waterloo, 2017)
8. Dr.-Pharm., B.Sc. (Nigeria), PETER AKUME ("Pharmacy FIANGO LYCÉE DE MAKÈPÈ")
9. Dr. (M.Sc.) Vincent Nanga (Geography, Germany)
10. Dr. (M.Sc.) Innocent Tchigio (Geography, University of Göttingen, Germany)
11. Dr.-PHARM. (Waterloo), M.Sc. (Belgium), CHEONGWA wandzi.

*"I have been hijacked by state hospital LAQUINTINIE in February 2021 ("**Organizer : Maxime NAPOA-eteme**") AND, in February 2023, by LAURE MENGUENE mvindi of JAMOT HOSPITAL. ALL THESE ATROCITIES AGAINST MY humble self and person, were commanded personally by PAUL BIYA; the President of the Republic of Cameroon, and also the PRESIDENT OF C.P.D.M (R.D.P.C) political ruling party. MY MOTHER-rose-Sangnou-NOUMBISSI and almost all my BLOOD-family members belong to this "C.P.D.M."; As well As any cameroonian that seems to leave freely here in CMR. "*

"ALL materials and furniture of YERITH_{r&d} located just opposite side of main entrance of BIYA's regime forestry society **"S2TBED"** were robbed illegally by "TEUNTCHOU Isaac" while I was in Douala for 3 weeks; in January 2025."

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WHO Is "Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.–Ing.]"

Figure 4: Portrait of YERITH–nissi.

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.–Ing.]" is a CHRISTIAN BY FAITH, Cameroonian, born on September 16 1983 in DOUALA (LITTORAL region, CAMEROON). Xavier has a "*Diplom–Informatiker (Dipl.–Inf.)*" qualification from the **University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY** (May 25, 2007). Xavier N. Noundou IS A "*Dr.–Ing. : Doctor of Engineering (Ph.D. equivalent – Computer Software Verification & Analysis)*" from **THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO (ON, CANADA); DECEMBER 20, 2011!**

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.–Ing.]" now, as CEO of YERITH_{r&d}, consults entrepreneurial organizations for their business informatics financial accounting needs.

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.–Ing.]" , also implements and configures program analysis and verification needs for his customers.

Xavier has worked together with **Prof. Dr. rer. nat. habil. Jan Peleska**, at AGBS–University of Bremen, GERMANY; and 2 years later at WatForm–University of Waterloo, ON, Canada, with **DR PATRICK LAM**.

Just after terminating his supervision with **DR PATRICK LAM**, Xavier had a great honour to pursue his studies with **Dr. Vijay Ganesh**, as a post–doctoral research supervisor!

Dr. Vijay Ganesh, a great software creator for computer security by super–algorithm, was before The UNIVERSITY of WATERLOO, ON; A Ph.D. in computer Science graduate of THEORY GROUP at Stanford University.

Xavier could successfully work with **Dr. Frank Tip** at The University of Waterloo (Waterloo, ON, Canada) on his first JAVA dynamic program analysis. Previously to being Professor at the University of Waterloo, David R. Cheriton School of Computer Science, **Dr. Frank Tip** was a research manager at **IBM TJ Watson Research Center from 1995 to 2012** (<https://research.ibm.com/labs/yorktown-heights>)!

Xavier also had the great opportunity through **Dr. Marcel Mitran** and **Dr. Patrick Lam**; to work as a graduate intern in Markham (Toronto, ON, CANADA) at IBM TORONTO SOFTWARE LABORATORY; in the JAVA-J9 Just-In-Time Compiler Optimization Team, together with **Patrick Doyle, MSc (University Of Toronto, ON, Canada)**, and **Vijay Sundaresan, MSc (McGill University, QC, Canada)**.

Xavier has following academic and professional engineering research contributions:

- 1) 'Statistical test case generation for reactive systems' at RTT-MBT at VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH (<https://www.verified.de>).
- 2) 'Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis For C using LLVM'
 1. source code in C++:
<https://www.github.com/sazzad114/saint>
 2. technical report article:
<https://zenodo.org/record/8051293>
- 3) 'YERITH-ERP-9.0':
 1. source code in C++:
 - a. YERITH-ERP-9.0:
<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0>
 - b. YERITH-ERP-9.0 SYSTEM DAEMON:
<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon>
 2. technical report article (ongoing publication):
<https://zenodo.org/record/8052724>
- 4) 'YERITH_QVGE'
 1. source code in C++:
 - https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang
 - https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif
 - <https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri-db-runtime-verif>
 - https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS
 2. technical report article (ongoing publication):
<https://zenodo.org/records/10070127>

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

This chapter explains what is the Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) software YERITH-ERP-9.0; what kind of entrepreneurial organization could make use of it; And what will be the development perspectives for the coming years.

1.1 YERITH-ERP-9.0: An Efficient And Simple To Use Enterprise Resource Planing Software

Figure 1.1: Financial Expense Creation Window in Administration Section

The screenshot shows the 'YERITH-ERP-3.0 - administration ~ create ~ FINANCIAL EXPENSES' window. It features a menu bar with 'Functions', 'Tools', and 'Help'. Below the menu is a 'Main menu' with icons for navigation and help. The main area contains four buttons: 'Create', 'List', 'Administration', and 'Modify'. A tabbed interface is visible with tabs for 'Stock alert', 'FINANCIAL EXPENSE*', 'Category', 'budget line', 'Bank account', 'User account', 'Department', and 'Site'. The 'FINANCIAL EXPENSE*' tab is active, displaying a form for 'financial expense data'. The form includes fields for 'department', 'budget line', 'reference' (marked as a mandatory field), 'designation' (marked as a mandatory field), 'supplier', 'quantity' (set to 1,00), 'unit purchase price' (marked as a mandatory field), 'Tax (%)', and 'total purchase price'. To the right, there is a section for 'REPETITION AND COMMAND DATA' with a 'REACTIVATE repetitions' checkbox and a 'repeat every' field set to 1.00 day(s). At the bottom, there is a 'FINANCIAL EXPENSE DESCRIPTION' text area and 'Cancel' and 'Save' buttons.

1.1.1 Motivation

YERITH-ERP-9.0 [Nou23f,Nou23b,Nou23c] is an **Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP)** software system that aims 'effectiveness' and 'simplicity', compared to other high ranked ERP software systems (e.g.: SAP Business One, 'Sage Gescom i7', 'Odoo Exp', etc.).

YERITH-ERP-9.0 is implemented by me with THE USER INTERFACE LIBRARY QT [Ltd22]. Our goal when designing and implementing this ERP software system is more folds:

- 1) Render enterprise resource planing (erp) software system usage and manipulation as easy as reading a leisure or recreational book so to reduce user strain size.
- 2) Contribute to reduce poverty by improving software system technology for enterprise resource planing (erp):
 1. Best and accurate technology SHALL REDUCE management effort and produce more reliable and cost-minimized business financial accounting information that enables to anticipate and reduce time of decision making.
 2. Best and accurate technology reduces time execution of commercial business transactions, and thus, associated costs.
 3. So entrepreneurial commercial organizations could reduce a selling price without reducing its profit.

YERITH_{r&d} would be grateful for governments that are not able to provide sufficient funds for commercial versions of YERITH-ERP-9.0, to ask me for free of charge commercial versions.

1.1.2 Uses Of YERITH-ERP-9.0

An ERP (Enterprise Resource Planing) software is a program, and / or software system that enables its users to:

1. **Classify, Save, Search, Sort**, inventory stock article, commercial services, and assets in an electronic directorate;
2. **Sell – Check-out – Transfer – ETC.**, inventory stock article, commercial services, and assets from their electronic directorate;
3. **Create alert based on timing periods, inventory stock articles, commercial services, and / or assets quantities, etc.**
4. Save, Search, etc., **Suppliers, Employees, Clients (or Customers), Members, etc..**
5. In summary, an ERP enables an individual, a group of people (including families), an commercial entrepreneurial organization, etc.: to overview its entrepreneurial management from a COMMERCIAL AND FINANCE viewpoint with the help of informatics (and / or computers).
6. YERITH-ERP-9.0 handles financial budget lines !

1.1.3 YERITH-ERP-9.0 Current Software Metrics

Table 1.1: YERITH-ERP-9.0 RELEVANT SOFTWARE SYSTEM METRICS.

Software Metric	Value
User Interface (windows, dialog) number	60
MariaDB SQL table number	40
MariaDB SQL table column number	320
Latex template for PDF printing	80
Source lines of code (SLOC)	350,000

1.1.4 YERITH-ERP-9.0 Current Software System Components

- ERP software itself: [YERITH-ERP-9.0](#).
FOSS code location <https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0>
- Component 1: *yerith-erp-9-0-configurations-data*: Configuration data for [YERITH-ERP-9.0](#).
This software component entails:
 - A configuration property file "yerith-erp-9-0.properties" that contains MariaDB database connection parameters data.
 - A configuration property file "yerith-erp-9-0-system-local-configuration-ENGLISH.properties" that contains local computer device and storage configuration parameters data.
 - A folder "yerith-erp-9-0-sql-backup-restore" where [YERITH-ERP-9.0](#) database backups will be stored.
- Component 2: *YRI_QVGE*: Runtime Monitoring Analysis Verification System.
FOSS code location 1 https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang
FOSS code location 2 https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif
FOSS code location 3 <https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri-db-runtime-verif>
FOSS code location 4 https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS
- Component 3: *yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon*: Service daemon for alerts over inventory stocks, assets, and financial expenses.
FOSS code location <https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon>

1.2 YERITH-ERP-9.0 Activity Sector Usage Report

Table 1.2: Societies used for Testing and Validation of YERITH-ERP-9.0 (2015-2023).

INDUSTRIAL SECTOR	LANGUAGES	Companies (network: # computers)	# users (accessories: quantity)	Integration difficulty (increasing 1 – 5)
1. GROCERY SHOP	FRENCH	POISSONNERIE PLUS	3	5
2. GROCERY SHOP	ENGLISH	NGO-PHARMACY FIANGO LYCÉE DE MAKÉPÈ (✓: 2)	5	3
3. BOOKSHOP	FRENCH	BILINGUAL entente bookshop	2	5
4. HEALTHCARE	ENGLISH	PHARMACY FIANGO LYCÉE DE MAKÉPÈ (✓: 4)	5 (✓: 1)	5
5. HEALTHCARE	FRENCH	P.C.T.B s.a.r.l (✓: 5)	20	5
6. HEALTHCARE	FRENCH	HAPPINESS POTENTIAL s.a.r.l	3	3
7. LOGISTICS	FRENCH, & ENGLISH	BONTÉE s.a.r.l (✓: 4)	6 (✓: 1)	3
8. HARDWARE SHOP	FRENCH	HARDWARE SHOP N.K	5	2
9. HARDWARE SHOP	FRENCH	HARDWARE SHOP la confiance	6	5
# Sectors	# LANGUAGES	# Companies	# Users #accessories	CUMULATED DIFFICULTY (MEAN)
5	2	9	55 2	4

Figure 1.2: 2 pie charts on customers till year 2023.

Figure 1.3: Represented customer sector till 2023, in percentages (%).

Figure 1.4: Percentage (%) of users per customer sector.

YERITH-ERP-9.0 is aimed at being simpler in usage and manipulation than older top ranked ERP software systems (e.g.: SAP Business One, 'Sage Gescom i7', 'Odoo Erp', etc.). A detailed comparison is to find in paper [Nou23b].

YERITH-ERP-9.0 could be used by any entrepreneurial organization, WHETHER governmental, OR NON GOVERNMENTAL (N.G.O) ! Applications are for instance:

1. engineering offices;
2. insurance companies;
3. JUSTICE ministries services in AFRICA;
4. etc.

1.3 Features To Develop for the coming Years

1.3.1 ADDENDUM : Laurent-tchandeu for his boss PAUL-biya mvondo

THIS report is still in finalization in "FEBRUARY 11, 2025" because of BIYA-rdpc-cpdm regime that has destroyed my financial income through my genitor and my ambassador-uncle (LAUrent ntchandeu)¹ because PAUL biya's regime is trying to again violate cameroon elections to come supposed this year 2025 :

- *I have for instance indexed publicly on road that if a political ruling party for more than 60 years couldn't pay his employees for governmental action since Cameroon supposed independence in "1960"; By means of computerized mechanisms; IT IS NOT MANAGING for CAMEROON ELECTION WITH more than at least 4000 other persons that They (government of BIYA's regime) could managed.*
- *I directly heard that since JANUARY 2025 they have finally introduced "Aigle" (<https://www.scam.prc.cm>) as a new computerized payment system for civil government employees.*
- *ALSO this new year 2025, "Immeuble YERITH" was destroyed of almost all its equipments by RDPC-teuntchou-isaac.*

1.3.2 Features – next

From this year onwards, YERITH-ERP-9.0 versions will not be Free and Open Source Software (FOSS).

YERITH_{r&d} would be grateful for governments that are not able to provide sufficient funds for commercial versions of YERITH-ERP-9.0, to ask me for free of charge commercial versions.

ESPECIALLY CAMEROON GOVERNMENT that is trying to implement a human resource module for SAP Waldorf since the year 1994 : "SIGIPES-2" almost 30 years at it (YEAR 2023)!

1. Execute Information flow policy control by usage of YRI_QVGE to Reduce Over Usage of government financial budget lines .
2. PROVIDE A SAMPLE template, for francophone central Africa states, **financial accounting plan o.h.a.d.a.**

This financial accounting plan will enable registered companies and societies, to use YERITH-ERP-9.0 for official tax income declaration.

3. Create a new "Expert Comptable (Chartered Accountant)" application profile user type.
4. Create a module that enables users of YERITH-ERP-9.0 to provide web applications on the World Wide Web (WWW) by just pressing a button.

Qt WebEngine Widgets C++ Classes seem to be what to use to provide this feature to YERITH-ERP-9.0 users.

5. Improve database connection information security of YERITH-ERP-9.0 because of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF fail state (error accepting state) recovery SQL mechanism feature.

I.e.: security of information and execution must guarantee that no intruders malware program, or code snippet, executes a malware SQL query statement.

¹*"THIS guja says on internet media he is looking for funds with a registered Cameroon NGO : HIS own Doctor nephew doesn't even have any funding because LAURENT harasses him as reported in JUDICIAL information (CV of Xavier NOUNDOU noumbissi attached to this document ! ")*

6. Improve fail state (error accepting state) recovery SQL mechanism of YERITH-ERP-9.0 in non SQL query statements; i.e.; create another efficient Qt-DBus recovery mechanism, in form of a Remote Procedure Call (RPC). Drawback here is the cumbersome configuration mechanism of Qt-DBus interface for RPC.
7. Implement offline dynamic analysis module within YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: I.e., produce analysis results based on program trace (event log).
8. Design and implement a mechanism to template solutions to class of use cases monitoring analysis verification within YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
I.e: define a mechanism to generate runtime monitors for several database tables column SQL query temporal safety property just using one template model.
9. Design and create a Computer Device integrated with YERITH-ERP-9.0, so to improve information security and robustness of the application.

1.4 YERITH-ERP-9.0 Literature

This section summarizes all documents (26 in total at time of writing) created for explaining concepts, ideas, and technologies implemented to create YERITH-ERP-9.0.

1.4.1 Required Marketing Knowledge

In French Language

- 1) **BROCHURE DE GESTION COMMERCIALE** (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-brochure-gestion-commerciale-notions/yerith-erp-9-0-brochure-gestion-commerciale-notions.pdf>),
RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **OCTOBRE 2021**.

1.4.2 Business Informatics Management Knowledge

In English Language

1. **YERITH-ERP-9.0 SOFTWARE SYSTEM PRODUCT SHEET** (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-product-sheet/yerith-erp-9-0-product-sheet.pdf>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, **MARCH 2021**.
2. **ADVANTAGES OF YERITH-ERP-9.0 COMPARED TO OTHER TOP ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEMS** (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-document-comparison/yerith-erp-document-comparison.pdf>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, **MARCH 2021**.
3. **INFORMATION BROCHURE OF ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH-ERP-9.0** (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-brochure-english/yerith-erp-9-0-brochure-english.pdf>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, **MARCH 2021**.
4. **INSTALLATION GUIDE FOR ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH-ERP-9.0** (<https://zenodo.org/record/8060182/>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, **MARCH 2021**.

In French Language

- 1) **GUIDE DE L'UTILISATEUR 'MANAGER', PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-9.0** (<https://zenodo.org/record/8058259/>),
RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **JUIN 2018**.
- 2) **YERITH-ERP-PGI-3.0: ESSAI DE PRODUCTIVITÉ ENTREPRENEURIALE** (<https://zenodo.org/records/10071437>),
RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **MARS 2021**.
- 3) **GUIDE PRATIQUE DU LOGICIEL DE GESTION COMMERCIALE ET FINANCIÈRE YERITH-PGI-9.0** (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-software-system-uses/yerith-erp-9-0-software-system-uses.pdf>),
RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **MARS 2021**.
- 4) **DOCUMENT COMBINANT LES PRÉSENTATIONS DE YERITH-PGI-9.0** (https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-info-francais_20230615/yerith-erp-9-0-info-francais.pdf),
RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **MARS 2021**.

- 5) **FICHE DE DONNÉES DU PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-9.0** (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-fiche-de-donnees/yerith-erp-9-0-fiche-de-donnees.pdf>),
RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **MARS** 2021.
- 6) **BROCHURE D'INFORMATION DU PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-9.0** (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-brochure/yerith-erp-9-0-brochure.pdf>),
RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **MARS** 2021.
- 7) **AVANTAGES DE YERITH-PGI-9.0 COMPARATIVEMENT À SAGE GESCOM I7, ET À SAP BUSINESS ONE** (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-document-comparaisons/yerith-erp-9-0-document-comparaisons.pdf>),
RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **MARS** 2021.
- 8) **AVANTAGES D'UTILISATION DE L'INFORMATIQUE POUR LA GESTION DE STOCKS** (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-document-comparaisons-1/yerith-erp-9-0-document-comparaisons-1.pdf>),
RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **AVRIL** 2021.
- 9) **BRÈVE PRÉSENTATION DU PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ (PGI) YERITH-PGI-3.0** (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-presentation-pour-novices/yerith-presentation-pour-novices.pdf>),
RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **SEPTEMBRE** 2022.
- 10) **GUIDE D'INSTALLATION POUR LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-9.0** (<https://zenodo.org/record/8060217>),
RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **MARS** 2021.
- 11) **RAPPORT DE TRAVAUX SUR LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-3.0 (années 2015-2022)** (<https://zenodo.org/record/8051568>),
RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **OCTOBRE** 2022.
- 12) **YERITH-ERP-PGI-3.0 : Configuration MULTI-SITES (SUCCURSALES)** (https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-multi-sites-base-de-donnees/YERITH-ERP_multi_sites_base_de_donnees.pdf),
Configuration MULTI-SITES (SUCCURSALES), YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **mars** 2023.

1.4.3 Financial Accounting Knowledge

In French Language

- 1) **YERITH-ERP-PGI-3.0: NOTIONS DE COMPTABILITÉ ET DE SYSTÈME O.H.A.D.A** (<https://zenodo.org/records/10071458>),
RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **MARS** 2021.

1.4.4 Associated Computer Devices

In English Language

1. **YERITH-ERP-9.0 RECOMMENDED POINT-OF-SALE HARDWARE** (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-inventory-stock-recommended-hardware/yerith-erp-9-0-inventory-stock-recommended-hardware.pdf>), TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, **MARCH** 2021.

In French Language

- 1) **MATÉRIEL INFORMATIQUE RECOMMANDÉ POUR LE POINT-DE-VENTE YERITH-PGI-9.0** (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-PDV-materiel-informatique-recommande/yerith-erp-9-0-PDV-materiel-informatique-recommande.pdf>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **MARS** 2021.

1.4.5 Advanced Software Technology

In English Language

1. **YERITH-ERP-9.0 DOCTORAL COMPENDIUM** (<https://zenodo.org/record/8052724>), DOCTORAL COMPENDIUM, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **MAY** 2022.
2. **Runtime Verification Of SQL Correctness Properties with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** (<https://zenodo.org/records/10070127>), journal article in preparation, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, **August** 2023.
3. **Compendium of Documents About the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE)** (<https://zenodo.org/record/8387240>), RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, **June** 2023.
4. **SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH-ERP-9.0** (https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-9-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf), TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, **JULY** 2022.
5. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: a framework for verifying SQL software correctness properties of gui software at runtime** (<https://zenodo.org/record/8051303>), CONFERENCE article in submission, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, **February** 2023.

In French Language

- 1) **YERITH-ERP-9.0 DOCTORAT / PH.D. COMPENDIUM** (<https://zenodo.org/record/8052724>), DOCTORAT COMPENDIUM, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **MAI** 2022.

Chapter 2

REPORT ON CUSTOMER EXPERIENCES AND FINDINGS

This chapter talks about customer experiences that were gained this year 2023. We could successfully have two customers this year.

2.1 Associated Computer Devices for YERITH-ERP-9.0

Table 2.1: Devices and hardware useful for YERITH-ERP-9.0.

Figure 2.1: (MANDATORY)

Computer

Figure 2.2: Touchscreen Monitor (MANDATORY)

Figure 2.3: Cash Drawer (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.4: "Point of Sale Thermal Printer" (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.5: Bar-code Scanner (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.6: 1 Network Router (MANDATORY)

Figure 2.7: Numeric Tablet (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.8: "2 in 1 Computer" (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.9: Multi User Terminal Computer (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.10: Hardware components of Multi-User Terminal Computer NC-300 (at <https://www.savingology.com>): images are taken from SavingOlogy.com.

Figure 2.11: NC-300 PCI card

Figure 2.12: NC-300 terminals

We have tried to search for very cheap devices because of the low income of small and medium companies here in Cameroon.

Table 2.1 illustrates sample computer devices and associated hardware for operating YERITH-ERP-9.0.

YERITH-ERP-9.0, in its current level of software development implementation, may not be appropriate at time for very large companies, with more than 100 employees: "Runtime monitoring", as well as "Financial expense management", and "Human resource management" modules software may solve this retard in the coming years.

2.1.1 Printing Devices And Counseling

We counsel our customer to use HP printing device solutions because drivers are available for Debian Linux operating system (LOGO:).

Also, it is advisable to print documents from their PDF format. Customers had for examples issues trying to perform correct printing from "LIBREOFFICE-WRITER", because of a complicated configuration system.

2.1.2 Computer Networking Devices

YERITH_{r&d} now counsels new customers or clients, to use Multi-User Terminal Computer NC-300 (Figure 2.10) for saving on computer hardware costs.

1 set devices of Multi-User Terminal Computer NC-300 enables up to 3 users to share a same desktop computer without the use of a computer network router (illustrated in Figure 2.6).

So their access to a LAN (Local Area Network) or Internet, occurs through the network interface of the shared desktop computer.

2.2 Software Ergonomics within YERITH-ERP-9.0

- Each text input field has an associated text inside the field for specifying what to search for, and where in database table column.
- Each icon or menu item is set not to be visible whenever it is not required or needed. For instance, whenever an inventory stock table is empty, icons and menu items for PDF printing (ICON:) disappear from a user interface.

MOTO: what is not needed is not visible. ¹

- Each window is accessible within 3 window GUI actions.
- Each function within a window GUI is accessible only in:
 - THROUGH A BUTTON just in front of a user on the Window.
 - THROUGH the context menu accessible using a click on the 2nd mice button.
 - THROUGH search for it in the window menu bar items.
- The settings configuration window panel has 2 types of settings:
 - computer local settings (LOCAL PARAMETERS)
 - remote server settings (SERVER PARAMETERS): only business information such as e.g.: VAT (Value Added Taxes), currency, etc.

2.3 Employee Training

We found that employee training is best done based on an employee skill set, and should be divided into 6 parts:

1. A visual demonstrating overview of YERITH-ERP-9.0
2. Questions based on knowledge and information acquired during visual demonstration of YERITH-ERP-9.0
3. Explanations about the key business concepts, business ideas, and software ergonomics implemented within [YERITH-ERP-9.0](#)
4. Executions of example use cases by employees
5. Questions and answers part conclusion
6. "**PLANING of general computing technology training for employees, based on observed missing knowledge during this training session**".

¹ARLETTE sibeuf, Financial and Accounting Director at "Bontée SARL in Akwa-Douala"

Chapter 3

NEW SOFTWARE FUNCTIONAL FEATURES

This chapter reports about all new ERP software functionalities introduced in this year 2023 in YERITH-ERP-9.0.

3.1 English to French And Vice-Versa Online Direct Translation

Users of YERITH-ERP-9.0 could now direct translate, online, without restarting application, translate YERITH-ERP-9.0 content from English into French, and Vice-Versa.

This occurs in the "Help" menu:

- in the main window
- in the administration section main window
- etc.

3.1.1 English Section

"Help" → "FR"

3.1.2 French Section

"Aide" → "EN"

3.2 Financial Expense Management

Figure 3.1: 2 pictures of financial expense management module.

Figure 3.2: Create a financial expense window.

Figure 3.3: View financial expenses window.

Figure 3.1 reports 2 pictures of the "Financial expense management" module we implemented this year within YERITH-ERP-9.0.

The "Financial expense management" module enables following actions:

1. File of any expense of an entrepreneurial organization; may it be an inventory stock purchase; a company physical asset; a company logical financial asset.

Each financial expense is reported within a financial budget line, that is linked to a physical bank account, registered only in YERITH-ERP-9.0.

2. Execute a financial expense ordering at a repetitive pre-determined time period frame.

3.2.1 Financial Accounting BUDGET LINES (COMMERCIAL ONLY)

Figure 3.4: Financial Accounting Budgets lines listing window tab (non administrative section).

ID	BUDGET LINE title	BUDGET LINE AMOUNT	Bank account title
0	665 - débit caisse	130,000.00	YR-DEBIT-CAISSE
1	664 - crédit caisse	0.00	YR-CREDIT-CAISSE

Commercial Operation Type

A COMMERCIAL OPERATION TYPE IS: ...

Commercial Operation Type Account

A COMMERCIAL OPERATION TYPE ACCOUNT IS: ...

Financial Budget Line

A FINANCIAL BUDGET LINE IS: ...

3.2.2 Financial Accounting Booking (COMMERCIAL ONLY)

Figure 3.5: Budgets lines – Financial Account Type Association window tab.

Yeroth-erp-3.0 - financial accounting - commercial operations types

Functions Tools Help

Main menu

Budget Line - financial operation type accounts association between financial operation type - financial operations account

financial operation type financial operation type account

ASSOCIATE

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN financial operation type - financial operations account

	ID	TYPE OF COMMERCIAL OPERATION	entrance OR going out (money)	Budget line title
1	0	sale	credit (money entry)	664 - crédit caisse
2	1	FINANCIAL EXPENSE	debit (money outgoing)	665 - débit caisse
3	2	merchandise purchase	debit (money outgoing)	665 - débit caisse

3.2.3 Financial Accounting Report Improvements (COMMERCIAL ONLY)

Figure 3.6: YERITH-ERP-9.0 Business Dashboard window.

Following new usability has been added to a financial accounting summary analytic report:

1. progress bars for Report PDF printing
2. reporting of budget lines balance sheet

3.3 Human Resource Management

Figure 3.7: 2 pictures of human resource management module.

Figure 3.8: Employee listing viewing window.

Figure 3.9: An employee belonging groups window.

Figure 3.7 reports 2 pictures of the "Human resource management" module we implemented this year within YERITH-ERP-9.0.

YERITH-ERP-9.0 views an employee as a supplier of services. The "Human resource management" module enables following actions:

1. File an employee or a company supplier.
2. Create a pay group; each employee associated to this pay group earns a same amount of money.

A pay group may be linked to a particular specific company location, Or may be a company wide unspecified location pay group.

A tax percentage amount is associated with each pay group; it could have 0% value.
3. Create an employee group associated with a pay group.
4. View, Remove, and Assign an employee to an employee group; an employee may belong to several pay group, and earns accordingly a cumulated salary per pay group.
5. View, modify time period an employee shall belong to a pay group.

At the end of a belonging time period, an employee is Not automatically removed from a pay group. But his salary from this pay group remains calculated to 0, in any currency defined in the administrative section "Application settings".
6. View pre-calculated monthly and annual, cumulated by pay group, salary of an employee in an employee details section window ("supplier details").

3.3.1 Payment Registration as a Financial Expense (Commercial version only)

Figure 3.10: A payment references page within YERITH-ERP-9.0 Anew.

	Payment date	Company name	Reference (article or service)	Paid amount	Supplier account (after)
1	31.03.2025	Xavier noundou	31.03.2025-SALAIRE-Xavier noundou	-261,900.00	-261,900.00
2	02.04.2025	Xavier noundou	02.04.2025-SALAIRE-Xavier noundou	-145,500.00	-407,400.00

Summary statistics from the interface:

- # rows: 59
- # payments: 2
- # suppliers: 1
- paid-out (debited): -407,400.00 F
- paid-in (credited): 0.00 F
- Company type: supplier

All employees payments registrations, as a financial expense in module "PAYMENTS", are available only in YERITH-ERP-9.0 commercial version.

WE PLAN a USB-dongle key version starting beginning year 2026.

3.4 Runtime Verification Monitoring Analysis Module: YERITH_QVGE System

Figure 3.11: YERITH-ERP-9.0 monitoring interface window tab.

Figure 3.11 illustrates summary (AN EXPLANATION OF THE SQL QUERY, and not the exact syntax) SQL query sent to YERITH-ERP-9.0 database, with complementary information (e.g.: timestamp, etc.).

Information that appears in YERITH-ERP-9.0 monitoring interface is received by a dynamic program analyzer: "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF "; that runs as a service background process on the same computer device. **"YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF " versions that allows for OFFLINE dynamic analysis will not be open source (FOSS).**

Each runtime monitor specification violated by an YERITH-ERP-9.0 execution is displayed in Figure 3.12. Details of each violated runtime monitor specification could be analyzed by a developer using YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (a component of YERITH_QVGE design and testing system) window interface, as shown in Figure 3.12.

Figure 3.12 illustrates a sample SQL event sequence mismatch) as specified by runtime monitor "YERITH_QVGE_sample_SAFETY_PROPERTY_one_Recovery_SAMPLE".

Chapter 4 explains the Design And Testing System YERITH_QVGE [Nou23a, Nou23d] with full authority.

Figure 3.12: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF error reporting window tab.

YR-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF _ console (FOSS version enabled)

Actions Tools HELP

Enter "source" or "SQL event" for filtering Reset Filter

SQL Error Event Reporting Logging SQL Event Logging

	time stamp	sql event log	source	target	changed qty	runtime monitor ID
1	05:40:09:959	'SELECT_stocks'	yeroth-erp-pgi-3.0	YR-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	1	7
2	05:40:10:017	'SELECT_stocks'	yeroth-erp-pgi-3.0	YR-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	1	0

runtime monitor name YEROTH_QVGE_sample_SAFETY_PROPERTY_one_Recovery_SAMPLE

TIME STAMP	SQL recovered executed query	Result
1 05:40:09:959	'INSERT INTO categories (id, nom_categorie, nom_departement_produit) values (yr_id, 'YR_ASSET_cat', 'YR_ASSET')	

source file	line number
1 src/windows/stocks/yeroth-erp-stocks-window.cpp	2149

(before) pre-condition on source state		(after) post-condition on target state	
1	not_in_before(YR_ASSET_cat, categories.nom_categorie)	1	in_after(YR_ASSET_cat, stocks.categorie)

evaluated guarded condition expression	value	previous state	accepting state	is error state
1 in_sql_event_log ('DELETE.categories.YR_ASSET_cat', STATE(YR))	True	YR	E	True

YR-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: this console is registered to the system d-bus as service: 'yr.db-runtime.verif'.

Chapter 4

NEW SCIENTIFIC AND ENGINEERING INNOVATION (IN SOFTWARE QUALITY ASSURANCE)

This chapter reports about YERITH_QVGE Design and Testing System by Dynamic Program Analysis. YERITH_QVGE, a compounded software stack, has a Free And Open Source (FOSS) part, and a commercial paying part. Governments not able to pay for commercial versions of YRI_QVGE, and YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, could ask me for a free of charge version.

4.1 Motivations

Figure 4.1: A State Diagram Mealy Machine Design Model within YERITH_QVGE.

Figure 4.2: YRI_QVGE workflow.

Software correctness properties are essential to maintain quality by continuous and regressive integration testing, as well as runtime monitoring the program after customer deployment.

To this intent, I have developed a stack software package of 4 complementary libraries, and / or programs named YERITH_QVGE [Nou23a, Nou23d] a test and design system by dynamic program analysis. Details of YERITH_QVGE are explained in Section 4.2.

Figure 4.1 illustrates the commercial drawing tool that is part of YERITH_QVGE. Figure 4.2 illustrates a workflow of design and testing system YERITH_QVGE.

In summary, YERITH_QVGE (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF) allows specification of a SQL temporal safety property by means of a state diagram mealy machine [NOU23g, Wik22]. In YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, a specification characterizes effects of program events (via SQL statements) on database table columns by means of set interface operations (\in , \notin), and, enable to check these characteristics hold or not at runtime. Integration testing is achieved for instance by expressing a state diagram that encompasses both Graphical User Interface (GUI) states and MySQL [Mar22] databases queries that glue them.

For example, a simple specification would encompass states between 'Department administration' and 'Stock listing' GUI interfaces, and transitions between them by means of MySQL databases operations. YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF doesn't generate false warnings; YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF specifications are *not desirable (forbidden) specifications (fail traces)*.

4.2 YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) Test And Design System by Dynamic Program Analysis

Table 4.1: YRI_QVGE Design and Testing System Dependencies

PROJECT	Required Library
1) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG	
2) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP	1)
3) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS	1)
4) YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	2)

Figure 4.3: YRI_QVGE software library dependencies.

YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) is a CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) design tool to generate "domain-specific language (DSL) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG ¹" files, to be inputted into the "compiler YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP ", so to generate C++ files for the "runtime verifier tester YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF ²" that allows for manual verification of SQL correctness properties of Graphical User Interface (GUI) software.

Figure 4.3 show a diagram of the afore described process; The step of the unit tests is colored in gray because it is only for developers of YRI_QVGE intended; accordingly, Table 4.1 illustrates the same process as a software library dependency table.

Figure 4.2 illustrates a workflow diagrammatically of the afore described process.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF inputs SQL correctness properties expressed using the formalism "state diagram mealy machine (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG)". Figure 4.7 illustrates a software system architecture of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, together with the monitored program under analysis. The Free Open Source Code Software (FOSS) tool-chain of development testing is located as follows for free, EXCEPT for "YRI_QVGE " that is a Closed Source Code Software (CSCS):

- COMPILER (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP):
https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang

¹https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif

²<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri-db-runtime-verif>

- RUNTIME VERIFIER TESTER (i.e.: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF):
<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri-db-runtime-verif>
- state diagram mealy machine UNIT TESTS CODE (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS):
https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS
- state diagram mealy machine (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG):
https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif

4.2.1 SDMM: "State Diagram Mealy Machine"

Figure 4.4: A motivating example, as previous bug found in YERITH-ERP-9.0.

$Q_0 := \text{NOT_IN_BEFORE}(\text{YRI_ASSET}, \text{department.department_name}).$

$Q_1 := \text{IN_AFTER}(\text{YRI_ASSET}, \text{stocks.department_name}).$

Figure 4.5: A SAMPLE state diagram mealy machine file.

```

1. yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec yri_missing_department_NO_DELETE
2. {
3.   START_STATE(d) : NOT_IN_BEFORE(YRI_ASSET, department.department_name)
4.   -> [in_sql_event_log('DELETE.department.YRI_ASSET', STATE(d))] / 'SELECT.department' ->
5.     ERROR_STATE(e) : IN_AFTER(YRI_ASSET, stocks.department_name).
6. }
  
```

Journal article in preparation [Nou23d] introduces a simple finite state machine formalism called State Diagram Mealy Machine ("SDMM"). Compiler YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP [Nou23a, Nou23d] inputs a specification as a "SDMM" and outputs a C++ program as a runtime monitor code specification for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF dynamic program analyzer.

Figure 4.4 illustrates a simple automaton defining a "SDMM" specification. Its equivalent specification using Domain-Specific Language YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG is illustrated in Figure 4.5.

YERITH_{r&d} develops and sells YRI_QVGE: a graphical drawing tool for generating YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG [Nou23a, Nou23d] textual specification, as the one illustrated in Figure 4.5. Figure 4.1 illustrates a sample screenshot of YRI_QVGE.

4.2.2 Dynamic Program Analyzer Generator "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF" (OFFLINE analysis in commercial version)

Figure 4.6: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF error reporting window tab.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF is a dynamic program analysis generator that inputs a text specification of a mealy automaton, and that uses state diagram mealy machine ("SDMM") library YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG to generate a runtime monitor binary executable that allows to:

- **Visualize** a graph representation, generated by the DOT-Graphviz [gra22] library program, of a runtime monitor specification.
- **Visualize, export, print**, system under test (SUT) (or also called program under analysis [PUA]) SQL events emitted to its database: for this, the library user must have instrumented (added additional source code) in its program sources, so to notify YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF of a query (E.G.: SELECT, etc.) to its application database.
- **Visualize, export, print**, SQL error events, as specified by the inputted "SDMM", that occur while the SUT is running (or not; using SUT SQL log event file).
- **Visualize** only SUT (system under test) SQL error events at the command line of execution as it prints out.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF versions that will allow for OFFLINE (from a trace event log file) dynamic analysis will not be Free and Open Source Software (FOSS).

Figure 4.6 illustrates a sample SQL error event log of Graphical User Interface (GUI) of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

4.2.3 "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF" Software Architecture

Figure 4.7: SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

Figure 4.7 illustrates a software architecture of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF:

1. Any software layer of a software system architecture can be checked against a temporal safety property, as long as, it is instrumented and emits necessary Qt-Ddbus [dqj22] events to YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF layer.

Chapter 5

CONCLUSION

This chapter concludes this annual report on effort work on YERITH_{r&d} business main software product YERITH-ERP-9.0.

5.1 Endeavor

YERITH_{r&d} advocates for usage of a simple and efficient ERP (Enterprise Resource Planing) business software here in Africa because of a low level of formal education, and of income.

YERITH-ERP-9.0 was designed to be useful starting for people having at least 11 years of formal education at primary and collegial level here in Cameroon. ERP systems created, and, in usage in western developed countries, require advanced knowledge as detailed in [Nou23b].

5.2 MAJOR CONTRIBUTION IN COMPUTER ENGINEERING SCIENCE

Table 5.1: COMPARISON TABLE BETWEEN C⁺⁺ [MS01], JAVASCRIPT [Fla20], AND JAVA [AGH00]. JAVASCRIPT and JAVA only have virtual machines that are in FACT REACTIVE SYSTEMS ! (WYSIWYG: What You See Is What You Get; VM: Virtual Machine)

FEATURES	C ⁺⁺	Javascript	Java
1. PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE PHILOSOPHY	object-oriented	object-oriented	object-oriented
2. MACROS	✓	✓	
3. MULTIPLE INHERITANCE	✓		
4. support INTERFACES	✓	✓	✓
5. STATIC COMPILATION	✓		
6. RUNTIME MONITORING & VERIFICATION	✓ (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)	✓ (VM INTERPRETATION AND MANAGEMENT)	✓ (VM INTERPRETATION AND MANAGEMENT)
7. UNIT TESTING FRAMEWORK	✓	✓	✓
8. NETWORK CAPABLE	✓	✓	✓
9. CROSS PLATFORM PORTABLE	✓	✓	✓
10. include FILE LIBRARY CAPABILITY	✓		
11. MULTI THREADING	✓		✓
12. WYSIWYG GUI DESIGN TOOL	✓		✓
13. VIRTUAL MACHINE IS A REACTIVE SYSTEM		✓	✓

Table 5.1 encompasses a detailed scientific comparison between most at time of writing popular programming languages: C⁺⁺, JAVASCRIPT, JAVA.

We found following reasons for introduction of virtual machines in the programming languages JAVASCRIPT, and JAVA:

- JAVA and JAVASCRIPT overcome runtime monitoring requirements by introducing language interpretation via virtual machine implementation and execution of programs.
- C++ doesn't have a mainstream equivalent to date; due to its compiled nature.
I advocate YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF as the component through which any programming language may have for free by runtime execution, runtime monitoring capability.

5.3 Societal Outcome Improvement

Following points would be major improvements in society if usage of YERITH_{r&d}'s computer systems products would be promoted:

- Africa has very bad institutions in terms of following-up clients files such as for example in JUSTICE palaces ministries.

YERITH_{r&d} would love to supply governments in southern francophone Africa with affordable and useful software systems at low cost so to improve politics governance management and ACCOUNTABILITY.

- Affordability and accessibility of low priced and simple to use ERP systems may boost economy because the lack of business acumen knowledge of very young entrepreneurs would be compensate by implemented knowledge in ERP YERITH_{r&d}'s YERITH-ERP-9.0.

Let us for instance remember that at least 75% of Cameroon population is aged under 18 years old. Research investigations of YERITH_{r&d}, as reported last year (2022) in [NN23], shows an introduction of YERITH-ERP-9.0 usage teaching starting at the 09th year (class of "5^{ème} francophone", etc.)¹ of formal education in Cameroon would be very beneficial for young adult people when later on creating start-ups.

Especially, more than 90% of this under 18 years old young people stop schooling before reaching the 1st year of university education because of lack of funding, here in Cameroon of CPDM (RDPC) political ruling party.

- Advanced Software Technology [NOU23g, Nou23e, Nou23a, Nou23d] developed for YERITH-ERP-9.0, both as Free and Open Source Software (FOSS), and as commercial priced product; would boost and improve software system quality in Africa.

¹Last year report said 10th year.

Chapter 6

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RAPPORT DE TRAVAUX SUR LE
PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ
YERITH-PGI-9.0
(années 2015 – 2022)

"Pr. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou"

Résumé

Ce document rapporte notre ACTIVITÉ DE L'ANNÉE 2015 JUSQU'À CE JOUR sur le progiciel de gestion intégré (PGI (erp)) YERITH-PGI-9.0.

YERITH-PGI-9.0 est 1 PGI crée depuis le 1 Octobre 2015.

YERITH-PGI-9.0 est 1 SYSTÈME D'INFORMATION qui permet à 1 personne, 1 groupe d'individus (incluant 1 famille), 1 entreprise commerciale, 1 entreprise de services, OU BIEN ENCORE 1 service ÉTATIQUE, etc.; de **suivre sa gestion sur le PLAN DU COMMERCE ET DE LA FINANCE à l'aide de l'informatique.**

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Chapitre 1

Présentation de "Pr. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou"

Figure 1.1 – Portrait de yerith-nissi.

"Pr. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou" EST CHRÉTIEN ÉVANGÉLIQUE 'BORN-AGAIN (né-de-nouveau)', CAMEROUNAIS, ET NÉ LE 16 Septembre 1983 À DOUALA DANS LA RÉGION DU LITTORAL AU CAMEROUN.

"Pr. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou" A 1 GRADE ACADÉMIQUE ET PROFESSIONNEL DE "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (DIPL.-INF.)" PROVENANT DE **L'UNIVERSITÉ DE BRÊME EN ALLEMAGNE**, DEPUIS LE 25 MAI 2007.

"Pr. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou" A 1 GRADE ACADÉMIQUE ET PROFESSIONNEL DE PHILOSOPHIAE DOCTOR (PH.D.) PROVENANT DE **L'UNIVERSITÉ DE WATERLOO (ON, CANADA)**, DEPUIS LE 20 DÉCEMBRE 2011.

"Pr. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou" A DES CONTRIBUTIONS EN RECHERCHES ET DÉVELOPPEMENTS, ACADÉMIQUES ET EN INGÉNIERIE PROFESSIONNELLE COMME SUIT :

1. 'Statistical test case generation for reactive systems' RTT-MBT¹; pour la start-up VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH ("<https://www.verified.de>") de l'Université de Brême en Allemagne fédérale.

1. <https://www.verified.de/products/model-based-testing>

2. 'Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis For C using LLVM'

1) code source en C++ :

YERITH-SAINT

<https://www.github.com/sazzad114/saint>

2) document scientifique et / ou technique :

<https://zenodo.org/record/8051293>

3. 'YERITH-ERP-3.0' :

1) code source en C++ :

YERITH-ERP-9.0

<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0>

YERITH-ERP-9.0 SYSTEM DAEMON

<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon>

2) publications en continue : <https://zenodo.org/record/8205911>

4. 'YERITH_QVGE'

1) code source en C++ :

YR_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP

https://www.github.com/yerithd/yr_sd_runtime_verif_lang

YR_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG

https://www.github.com/yerithd/yr_sd_runtime_verif

YR-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF

<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yr-db-runtime-verif>

YR_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS

https://www.github.com/yerithd/yr_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS

2) document scientifique et / ou technique :

<https://zenodo.org/record/8381187>

Chapitre 2

Progiciel de Gestion Intégré AU CAMEROUN

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Figure 2.1 – 2 IMAGES représentatives de YERITH-PGI-9.0 (YERITH-ERP-9.0 en ANGLAIS).

Figure 2.2 – Une image de YERITH-PGI-9.0.

Figure 2.3 – DES CHARGES financières (lignes budgétaires incluses)!

The screenshot displays the 'FINANCIAL EXPENSE listing' window in YEROTH-ERP-3.0. It includes a search bar for product names and a table with the following data:

	Product name	Supplier name	Department	budget line	Purchase price	Order date
1	T	CASINO_YR	YR_ASSET	YR_01_140000	-300.00	20.01.2023
2	Z	HP_YR	YR_ASSET	YR_01_140000	-200.00	20.01.2023
3	A	HP_YR	YR_ASSET	YR_02_140000	-3,000.00	20.01.2023
4	ZZ	MINTAP_yerothie	yeroth departement 1 65 - CHARGES FINANCIÈRES		-750.00	20.01.2023

At the bottom, there is a summary row: # rows 59, 1 / 1, # purchases 4, Total (debited) -4,250.00 FCFA. The interface also includes a 'reset' button and filter options for 'Begin' (01/01/2022) and 'End' (20/01/2023).

YERITH-PGI-9.0 est un PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ (PGI)! La figure 2.1 illustre 2 images du PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0.

Un progiciel (PRODUIT + LOGICIEL) de gestion intégré est un **programme informatique** qui aide ses utilisateurs à réaliser des tâches suivantes :

1. **enregistrer (répertorier), rechercher**, des stocks et / ou articles (OU IMMOBILISATIONS) dans un catalogue électronique
2. **VENDRE – TRANSFÉRER – SORTIR – ETC.**, des stocks et / ou articles (OU IMMOBILISATIONS) de leur catalogue électronique d'enregistrement

3. créer des **ALERTES** sur des **PÉRIODES DE TEMPS**, sur des **QUANTITÉS**, etc.
4. **VISUALISER DES STATISTIQUES** sur des ventes, des mouvements, etc. : de stocks, d'articles (OU IMMOBILISATIONS), etc.
5. enregistrer (répertorier), rechercher, etc. : des **FOURNISSEURS, CLIENTS, EMPLOYÉS, MEMBRES, etc..**
6. **EN RÉSUMÉ**, permettre à une personne, un groupe d'individus (incluant une famille), une entreprise commerciale, ou une entreprise de services, etc. : de **suivre sa gestion sur le PLAN DU COMMERCE ET DE LA FINANCE à l'aide de l'informatique!**
7. YERITH-PGI-9.0 PREND EN COMPTE DES LIGNES BUDGÉTAIRES!

2.1.1 DOMAINES D'APPLICATIONS

YERITH-PGI-9.0 (YERITH-ERP-9.0 EN ANGLAIS) peut être ré-utilisé par N'IMPORTE QU'ELLE ORGANISATION NON gouvernementale (ONG), OU GOUVERNEMENTALE!

YERITH-PGI-9.0 A POUR OBJECTIF premier D'ÊTRE TRÈS facile d'utilisation POUR DES personnels ou UTILISATEURS sous éduqués!

LES PGI (erp en anglais) les plus propagés au CAMEROUN : Sage Gescom i7, SAP Business One, ou encore Odoo, SONT BÂTIS pour des licenciés!

1 COMPARAISON DÉTAILLÉE SE FAIT DANS LES DOCUMENTS [[uNu21c](#), [uNu21a](#)]!

En RÉSUMÉ, YERITH-PGI-9.0 a les **fonctions suivantes** :

1. administration des utilisateurs, et, des rôles
2. alertes sur les quantités en stocks, et sur les périodes de temps
3. gestion des RESSOURCES HUMAINES, clients (CRM), fournisseurs, LIGNES BUDGÉTAIRES
4. gestion des stocks, DES IMMOBILISATIONS
5. gestion des ventes (locations, caisse, etc.)
6. recherche basée sur des modèles avec le caractère %
7. tableaux de bords.

LE GUIDE et/ou MANUEL DE L'UTILISATEUR [[uNu22a](#)] DE YERITH-ERP-9.0 re-précise des domaines d'applications, ainsi QUE DES CAS D'UTILISATIONS pratiques!

QUELQUES DOMAINES D'UTILISATIONS SONT PAR EXEMPLE :

1. bureaux d'études et de conception en ingénierie;
2. cabinets d'avocats;
3. sociétés d'assurances;
4. etc.

2.1.2 Droits D'accès

LES UTILISATEURS du progiciel de gestion intégré YERITH-PGI-9.0 n'ont pas les mêmes **droits de VISUALISATIONS, ET / OU DE MANIPULATIONS DES DONNÉES!**

Par exemple, un employé ne peut pas observer ou manipuler des données spécifiques à son patron.

2.1.3 Régionalisation

YERITH-PGI-9.0 est disponible dans des langues suivantes : ANGLAIS, et FRANÇAIS.

2.2 AVANCEMENT PÉDAGOGIQUE ET/OU TECHNOLOGIQUE avec YERITH-PGI-9.0

Table 2.1 – Comparaison entre YERITH-PGI-9.0 et quelques autres progiciels de gestion intégrés

CRITÈRES	YERITH-PGI-9.0	Sage Gescom i7	SAP Business One
vue du logiciel dépendante du rôle	OUI	OUI	OUI
formation complète	au moins 2 semaines	au moins 2 mois	au moins 3 mois
interface du logiciel	évidente	très compliquée	très compliquée
langage dans le logiciel	usuel de tous les jours	simple	technique
formation comptable	jamais	jamais	utile
formation en marketing	jamais	utile	utile
connection internet	optionnel	optionnel	obligatoire

Nos travaux depuis OCTOBRE 2015 au CAMEROUN (yaoundé et douala), et au CANADA (waterloo (ontario)), NOUS ONT AMENÉ À ÉTABLIR le tableau 2.1, comparatif des 3 progiciels de gestion intégrés les plus appropriés POUR LA PLUPART DES entreprises!

AVANCEMENT technologique

Le tableau 2.1 illustre à merveille la simplicité et l'efficacité de YERITH-PGI-9.0, en comparaison avec les progiciels de gestion intégrés "Sage Gescom i7", et "SAP Business One".

EXPÉRIENCE PÉDAGOGIQUE avec "NESTOR KENFACK"

EN PARTICULIER, NOTRE EXPÉRIENCE D'INTÉGRATION dans des structures du promoteur investisseur "NESTOR KENFACK" :

1. QUINCAILLERIE N.K (sis AHALA-barrière)
2. POISSONNERIE PLUS (sis AHALA-barrière)

nous ont permis de RÉALISER que nous pouvions, **AVEC SUCCÈS DE RÉSULTATS OPÉRATIONNELS EFFECTIFS** :

1. FORMER 1 TITULAIRE DU b.e.p.c AU NIVEAU ACADÉMIQUE en 3 JOURS SEULEMENT!
B.E.P.C : brevet d'études DU PREMIER CYCLE (ENVIRON 12 ans d'études primaires et d'études du premier cycle d'enseignement secondaire francophone!).
2. EN DEHORS DE YERITH-PGI-9.0, IL EST IMPOSSIBLE À 92% DE FORMER effectivement le titulaire d'1 niveau académique inférieur à la licence¹, **À L'UTILISATION EFFECTIVE D'1 PGI (erp), avec des résultats opérationnels effectifs!**

1. Environ 3 ans universitaires après l'obtention du BACCALAURÉAT.

AVANCEMENT pédagogique

Il ressort de nos expériences en entreprises commerciales et/ou organisations non gouvernementales; Sage Gescom i7, SAP Business One, Odoo, etc., sont SIMPLEMENT TRÈS difficile à intégrer dans 1 environnement de TRAVAIL où le personnel opérationnel et/ou logistique à 1 niveau éducatif INFÉRIEUR À 1 LICENCE!

2.3 AVANTAGES DE L'UTILISATION DES PGI (erp en ANGLAIS)

L'utilisation des PGI (erp an anglais) aurait des avantages très imposants pour des pouvoirs publics en ce qui concerne des points suivants :

1. **FACILITATION DE L'ÉCONOMIE;** des petits commerçants ne maîtrisant plus des techniques de gestion commerciale MODERNE, ne souffrirait PLUS DU problème de manque de savoir!

EN EFFET, tout les savoirs de techniques modernes en gestion commerciale et comptable SERAIENT IMPLÉMENTÉ dans YERITH-PGI-9.0!

2. **FACILITATION DE LA COLLECTE DES IMPÔTS (fisc) :** en effet, le calcul des recettes et des montants imposables par des administrations fiscales aux commerçants et industriels POURRAIENT ÊTRE fait directement sur la base DE LEUR (**PROPRE DÉCLARATION EN LIGNE sur le média INTERNET**)!

EN EFFET, CECI EST MONNAIE COURANTE dans des grands pays industriels occidentaux TELS QUE LA RÉPUBLIQUE FÉDÉRALE D'ALLEMAGNE (RFA), LE CANADA, ETC.!

3. **FACILITATION DE L'IMPLÉMENTATION des nouvelles politiques économiques ET FISCALES du cameroun!**

En effet, chaque année budgétaire, des FORMULES DE CALCULS seraient automatiquement ré-actualisées dans YERITH-PGI-9.0 (YERITH-ERP-9.0 en ANGLAIS), au fin de faciliter l'implémentation des politiques financières et économiques du CAMEROUN!

2.4 Recommandations EFFECTIVES AU GOUVERNEMENT

2.4.1 Coûts TECHNOLOGIQUES

Table 2.2 – Comparaison de réutilisation au plan financier (**APPROXIMATIF**) entre YERITH-PGI-9.0 et quelques autres progiciels de gestion intégré

CRITÈRES	YERITH-PGI-9.0	Sage Gescom i7	SAP Business One
SYSTÈME D'EXPLOITATION	Debian Linux	MS Windows	Debian Linux
Coût D'ACQUISITION	30 \$USA	200 \$USA	30 \$USA
Coût De La Formation POUR 1 TECHNICIEN	300 \$USA	VARIABLE	VARIABLE
Coût De La Formation POUR 1 USAGER	500 \$USA	VARIABLE	VARIABLE
Coût De La Maintenance (mensuel) POUR 1 ORDINATEUR	30 \$USA	VARIABLE	VARIABLE
Coût De L'acquisition du PGI (ERP en ANGLAIS)	VARIABLE	VARIABLE	VARIABLE

LE TABLEAU 2.2 COMPARATIF DES RESSOURCES FINANCIÈRES RELATIVES À L'ACQUISITION ET À L'ENTRETIEN DES PROGICIELS DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ AU CAMEROUN ressort que :

1. LE SYSTÈME D'EXPLOITATION Debian Linux EST LE MEILLEUR.

2.4.2 Conclusions

L'UTILISATION DES PGI (ERP en Anglais) devrait être PROMUE PAR DES MESURES TELLES QUE :

1. **LA RÉDUCTION DE CERTAINES TAXES entrepreneuriales AUX FINS DE PROMOUVOIR L'ACHAT ET / OU LA maintenance des progiciels de gestion intégré**
2. **LA SUBVENTION financière et/ou économique de l'entrepreneur–investisseur**

EN EFFET, la ré–utilisation des pgi (ERP en anglais) AUGMENTERAIT LA PRODUCTIVITÉ DES entreprises à 1 haut niveau, DIMINUANT ainsi la faillite et la baisse de productivité!

Chapitre 3

PERSPECTIVES D'AVENIRS

3.1 PLAN COMMERCIAL ET INDUSTRIEL

Figure 3.1 – Une image d'1 ordinateur portable 2 – 1 (2 en 1).

JE RECOMMANDE LE financement de LA START-UP TECHNOLOGIQUE YERITH_{r&d} POUR LA MISE EN ŒUVRE DES "ordinateurs portables 2 – 1 (2 en 1)" MUNIS de YERITH-PGI-9.0 (EN ANGLAIS YERITH-ERP-9.0)!

En particulier, des "ordinateurs portables 2 – 1 (2 en 1)" sont très ré-utilisables dans des structures et/ou secteurs industriels et/ou tertiaires avec des caractéristiques suivantes :

1. OPÉRATIONS DE GESTION AUX endroits sans tables et / ou espaces de dépôts (ex : À L'ENTRÉE D'1 SCIERIE industrielle, etc.)
2. MANQUE D'ESPACE pour le dépôt d'ordinateurs "DESKTOP" (e.g. : 1 comptoir ambulancier de vente MTN¹).

1. ENTREPRISE SUD-AFRICAINE OPÉRANT DANS LA TÉLÉPHONIE MOBILE AU CAMEROUN.

3.2 PLAN ÉDUCATIF

3.2.1 Définitions de Gestion Commerciale et Comptable

AU PLAN ÉDUCATIF, nous avons ré-écrit certaines définitions de gestion commerciale [uNu22a, uNu22b, uNu21b] AUX FINS de les rendre plus compréhensibles POUR DES JEUNES en formation au PGI (erp en ANGLAIS) YERITH-PGI-9.0 (en ANGLAIS YERITH-ERP-9.0)!

Nous avons approché des promoteurs d'établissements scolaires et universitaires professionnels AUX FINS de partager des informations et DE PRÉPARER des jeunes élèves et étudiants à l'utilisation des PGI (erp en ANGLAIS) :

1. COLLÈGE intec DOUALA (m. JEAN PIERRE moubeb, EN PERSONNE);
2. Institut Universitaire de la Côte DOUALA (M. Hypolithe Tekeu, EN PERSONNE);
3. Startup Academy 237 YAOUNDÉ (Dr. CLAUDEL noubissie, via EMAIL, WHATSAPP).

Ces 3 échanges ont été sans suite favorables pour cause de défaut de plan OHADA dans YERITH-PGI-9.0.

L'INTÉGRATION DU SYSTÈME COMPTABLE OHADA suis son cours en ce moment!

3.2.2 Intégration au Programme Officiel d'Enseignement Secondaire

Nous préconisons des points suivants aux fins de permettre aux jeunes, même ceux arrêtant des études au bas âge d'être en mesure d'utiliser efficacement 1 pgi (erp en anglais) :

1. INSTRUCTION DE YERITH-PGI-9.0 (YERITH-ERP-9.0 EN ANGLAIS) dès des classes de 4ème AU PREMIER CYCLE D'ENSEIGNEMENT SECONDAIRE FRANCOPHONE; et anglophone ÉQUIVALENT!

LE RESPECT DE CES MESURES PERMETTRA aux FUTURS gouvernements DU CAMEROUN de ne plus avoir à investir beaucoup de moyens financiers et autres; AUX FINS DE PROFESSIONNALISER des jeunes!

EN EFFET, pour ceux des jeunes qui n'iront pas bien loin dans des études, ils seront néanmoins en mesure d'exercer des professions libérales ou pas à l'aide de l'outil informatique DE BASE!

3.3 PLAN DE LA recherche appliquée et/ou fondamentale EN GÉNIE INFORMATIQUE

AU PLAN DE LA RECHERCHE scientifique appliquée et/ou fondamentale, YERITH-PGI-9.0 (en ANGLAIS YERITH-ERP-9.0), NOUS A PERMIS DE DÉVELOPPER DES OUTILS ET MÉTHODES DE test, vérification, et validation de progiciels [Nou23].

NOUS AVONS APPROCHÉ DES STRUCTURES DE HAUTES TECHNOLOGIES :

1. HIMORE-MEDICAL s.a.r.l (PROMOTEUR ingénieur informaticien arthur zang)

AUX FINS DE leur proposer DES COOPÉRATIONS DE VÉRIFICATION ET DE TESTS AUTOMATISÉS DE LEUR PROGICIELS dans le domaine médical cardio-vasculaire!

NOUS SOMMES SANS SUITE DE RÉPONSE JUSQU'À CE JOUR!

Chapitre 4

CONCLUSION

L'UTILISATION DES progiciels de gestion intégré (EN ANGLAIS "enterprise resource planing software") DEVRAIT ÊTRE PROMUE PAR DES MESURES TELLES QUE :

- **LA RÉDUCTION DE CERTAINES TAXES entrepreneuriales AUX FINS DE PROMOUVOIR L'ACHAT ET LA maintenance des progiciels de gestion intégré**
- **LA SUBVENTION financière et/ou économique de l'entrepreneur-investisseur**

EN EFFET, la ré-utilisation des pgi (ERP en anglais) AUGMENTERAIT LA PRODUCTIVITÉ DES entreprises à 1 haut niveau, DIMINUANT ainsi la faillite et la baisse de productivité!

Chapitre 5

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YERITH-CONSULTING : Description De La Structure

YERITH-CONSULTING est un cabinet de développement et de consulting du PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ (PGI; ERP en anglais) "YERITH-PGI-9.0" situé :

1. juste à l'entrée de la ville de "YAOUNDÉ";
2. aux alentours de "BARRIÈRE";
3. face de l'entrée du quartier "etoa";
4. À L'IMMEUBLE YERITH!

YERITH-CONSULTING a le personnel suivant :

1. PRÉSIDENT DIRECTEUR GÉNÉRAL ("Xavier Noubissi Noundou (Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.)")
2. 2 développeurs d'applications C++, MySQL, Qt5.15
3. 2 développeurs de tests unitaires C++, MySQL, Qt5.15
4. 1 testeur manuel d'application Qt5
5. 1 rédacteur technique LaTeX, LibreOffice.

YERITH-CONSULTING est aussi 1 incubateur de tech-entrepreneurs.

FINANCEMENTS POUR LA MISE EN PLACE DU GROUPE YERITH_{r&d} :

1. "Xavier Noubissi Noundou (Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.)" .

La fenêtre d'accueil de YERITH-PGI-9.0

La fenêtre des marchandises

OPÉRATIONS

Matériels Point-de-Vente

- ✓ Lecteur de code-barres, etc.

Systèmes-de-Gestion de Base-de-Données

- ✓ MySQL

Systèmes d'Exploitations

- ✓ Debian-Linux

YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE : Description Du Projet De Centre de formation en Informatique

YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE est un institut de formation qualifiante en informatique situé :

1. juste à l'entrée de la ville de "YAOOUNDÉ";
2. aux alentours de "BARRIÈRE";
3. face de l'entrée du quartier "etoa";
4. À L'IMMEUBLE YERITH!

YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE comportera dans 1 premier temps d'1 salle de formation de 27 m² de superficie. Elle sera comme suit :

Table 1 – MATÉRIELS INFORMATIQUES RE-PROPOSÉS

QUANTITÉS	MATÉRIELS
1) 1	climatiseur portatif
2) 1	table ovale de conférence
3) 1	tableau blanc avec marqueurs indélébiles
4) 2	vidéoprojecteurs
5) 8	chaises en fer
6) 1	routeur Wifi MARQUE NXP-300
7) 2	MULTI-USER Terminal NC-300 de " http://www.savingology.com "
8) 2	ordinateurs-PC
9) 6	écrans plats d'ordinateurs
10) 6	souries d'ordinateurs PS / 2
11) 6	claviers d'ordinateurs PS / 2

YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE a le personnel suivant :

1. P.D.-G. ("Xavier Noubissi Noundou (Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.)"),
2. gardien et / ou agent d'entretien.

Vue d'ensemble face immeuble YERITH.

Vue de la salle de 27 m².

Chantier de construction

Vue intérieure du 2ème portail manquant.

Vue intérieure de l'entrée secondaire de la salle 1 de 27 m².

Vue intérieure du portillon de l'entrée.

YERITH–SUPÉRETTE : Description du Projet De Supérette

YERITH–SUPÉRETTE est une supérette située :

1. juste à l'entrée de la ville de "YAOUNDÉ";
2. aux alentours de "BARRIÈRE";
3. face de l'entrée du quartier "etoa";
4. À L'IMMEUBLE YERITH!

YERITH–SUPÉRETTE est une supérette de 30 m² de superficie. Elle sera équipée des aliments et des articles comme suit :

1. produits agro-alimentaires (exemple : yaourts, jus de fruits, etc.)
2. petit coin cosmétique,
3. petit coin électronique (et informatique),
4. petit coin quincaillerie.

YERITH–SUPÉRETTE a le personnel suivant :

1. directeur général : "Xavier Noubissi Noundou (Pr. Prof. Dr.–Ing.)"
2. caissier
3. gardien et / ou agent d'entretien.

YERITH–SUPÉRETTE utilise le progiciel de gestion intégré [YERITH–PGI–9.0](#) pour ses opérations de gestion commerciale!

La fenêtre d'accueil pour le « Cais- sier »

La fenêtre des marchandises

OPÉRATIONS

Matériels Point-de-Vente

- ✓ Lecteur de code-barres, etc.

Systèmes-de-Gestion de Base-de-Données

- ✓ MySQL

Systèmes d'Exploitations

- ✓ Debian-Linux

YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE : Description Du Projet De Centre de formation en Informatique

YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE est un institut de formation qualifiante en informatique situé :

1. juste à l'entrée de la ville de "YAOOUNDÉ";
2. aux alentours de "BARRIÈRE";
3. face de l'entrée du quartier "etoa";
4. À L'IMMEUBLE YERITH!

YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE comportera dans 1 premier temps d'1 salle de formation de 27 m² de superficie. Elle sera comme suit :

Table 1 – MATÉRIELS INFORMATIQUES RE-PROPOSÉS

QUANTITÉS	MATÉRIELS
1) 1	climatiseur portatif
2) 1	table ovale de conférence
3) 1	tableau blanc avec marqueurs indélébiles
4) 2	vidéoprojecteurs
5) 8	chaises en fer
6) 1	routeur Wifi MARQUE NXP-300
7) 2	MULTI-USER Terminal NC-300 de " http://www.savingology.com "
8) 2	ordinateurs-PC
9) 6	écrans plats d'ordinateurs
10) 6	souries d'ordinateurs PS / 2
11) 6	claviers d'ordinateurs PS / 2

YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE a le personnel suivant :

1. P.D.-G. ("Xavier Noubissi Noundou (Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.)"),
2. gardien et / ou agent d'entretien.

Vue d'ensemble face immeuble YERITH.

Vue de la salle de 27 m².

Chantier de construction

Vue intérieure du 2ème portail manquant.

Vue intérieure de l'entrée secondaire de la salle de 27 m².

Vue intérieure du portillon de l'entrée.

1 Description du Centre de Formation

Ce centre de formation en Informatique est la propriété de la start-up entrepreneuriale de Génie des Systèmes de Gestion Informatisés YERITH_{r&d}.

Le fondateur et directeur général de YERITH_{r&d} est **Prof. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou**.

YERITH_{r&d} est 1 start-up entrepreneuriale à vocation confessionnelle évangélique, Et non laïque!

Des principes laïques sont **non compatibles** avec la foi chrétienne de **JEOVAH-NISSI** (ou encore **JÉSUS-DE-NAZARETH**), telle que proclamée dans la Sainte Bible évangélique chrétienne; Par opposition à la Bible Tobie catholique orthodoxe :

- **Mariage homosexuel ("Lévitique 20 verset 13, version Louis Segond de 1910" ¹)!**

Les cours de centre de formation ont pour cibles les personnes suivantes :

1. Travailleurs qualifiés en Informatique.
2. Travailleurs qualifiés en Sciences et en Génie.
3. Élèves et écoliers des établissements confessionnelles évangéliques.
4. Étudiants dans les universités publiques confessionnelles évangéliques.
5. Étudiants dans les universités du monde moderne (incluant des catholiques orthodoxes).

2 SITUATION GÉOGRAPHIQUE

"Immeuble YERITH" est situé à Yaoundé, face 2^{ème} entrée de l'entreprise industrielle forestière **S2TBED**, au quartier Ahala - Barrière ("derrière savonnerie NOSA").

3 CONTACTS

1. EMAIL : YERITH.XAVIER@gmail.com
2. TÉLÉPHONE (Réseau MTN) : 6 52 39 69 50 – Xavier.

4 HORAIRES DE COURS ET D'OUVERTURES (DÈS LE 09 JANVIER 2024)

Lundi à Vendredi

1. Matin : 08 : 00 – 12 : 00.
2. Après-Midi : 14 : 00 – 17 : 30.

Week-end

1. Samedi : 08 : 00 – 12 : 00.
2. Dimanche : FERMÉ.

5 CANDIDATS AUX COURS PROPOSÉS

Les tarifs des cours sont présentés en Section 7.

LES COURS (Section 8) SERONT RÉ-AMÉNAGÉS en fonction du niveau des candidats.

TOUS LES COURS, excepté le cours [COURS-4] ("Initiation à l'informatique ..."), REQUIERT AU MINIMUM LE NIVEAU D'ÉDUCATION DE LA CLASSE DE 3^{ème} DE L'ENSEIGNEMENT SECONDAIRE FRANCOPHONE AU CAMEROUN.

1 niveau excellent au 1^{er} cours suivis : ([COURS-4]), peut permettre l'accès aux autres cours, graduellement; SANS nécessiter le retour à la classe de 3^{ème} DE L'ENSEIGNEMENT SECONDAIRE FRANCOPHONE AU CAMEROUN.

LES COURS [COURS-20] ("STUDIO PROJET ...") ET [COURS-24] ("... DÉVELOPPEMENT D'APPLICATIONS WEB ...") REQUIÈRENT 1 NIVEAU DE BACCALAURÉAT SCIENTIFIQUE ET / OU TECHNIQUE.

LES AUTRES COURS de [COURS-12] À [COURS-26] REQUIÈRENT LE NIVEAU DE LICENCE EN INFORMATIQUE AU MINIMUM EN ÉQUIVALENCE, et sont dispensés de préférence en Anglais.

6 INSCRIPTION

LES FRAIS D'INSCRIPTION AU CENTRE DE FORMATION sont de l'ordre de **30 MILLES FRANCS**, et sont **NON REMBOURSABLES**: 1 REÇU EST ÉMIS APRÈS PAYEMENT DES FRAIS OU D'1 PARTIE DES FRAIS.

Les documents suivants sont requis pour 1 inscription aux cours de ce centre de formation en Informatique qualifiante :

1. <https://sainte bible.com/leviticus/20-13.htm>

- 1 carte d'identité nationale (CNI) valide, ou 1 récépissé en cours de validité.

1 CERTIFICAT DE RÉUSSITE DE FORMATION SERA DÉLIVRÉE À L'ISSUE D'1 FORMATION ACCOMPLIE À 1 COURS SUIVIS AVEC SUCCÈS.

7 TARIFS TABULAIRES

1 heure (1h) de cours représente 45 minutes de délibérés et 15 minutes de pause.

Tableau 1 – TARIFS TABULAIRES DES COURS PROPOSÉS (Section 8)

COURS PROPOSÉS	NOMBRE D'HEURES DE COURS ET DE TD	TARIFS (DISCUTABLES)
INSCRIPTION	N/A	30 MILLES
[COURS-3]; MATHÉMATIQUES POUR L'INFORMATIQUE	21 heures [1.5h x 2 x 7-semaines]	84 MILLES
[COURS-4]; INITIATION À L'INFORMATIQUE	06 heures [1h x 3 x 2-semaines]	21 MILLES
[COURS-5]; INSTALLER LE SYSTÈME D'EXPLOITATION Debian Linux	06 heures [1h x 3 x 2-semaines]	30 MILLES
[COURS-6]; INITIATION À L'INFORMATIQUE DE GESTION, AVEC YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0	32 heures [1.5h x 4 x 6-semaines]	108 MILLES
[COURS-7]; SITES WEB STATIQUES AVEC GOOGLE-SITES	36 heures [2h x 3 x 6-semaines]	126 MILLES
[COURS-9]; INITIATION ÉQUIVALENT MS-OFFICE-WORD-EXCEL-ETC., LIBREOFFICE	18 heures [1.5h x 4 x 3-semaines]	36 MILLES
[COURS-10]; MANIPULATION D'IMAGES	09 heures [1.5h x 2 x 3-semaines]	27 MILLES
[COURS-11]; RÉDIGER DES DOCUMENTS SCIENTIFIQUES AVEC LATEX	27 heures [1.5h x 3 x 6-semaines]	93 MILLES
[COURS-15]; INTRODUCTION A LA PROGRAMMATION IMPERATIVE, C, C++	36 heures [2h x 3 x 6-semaines]	180 MILLES
[COURS-18] INTRODUCTION AU TEST ET À LA VÉRIFICATION DE PROGRAMMES INFORMATIQUES	29 heures [2h x 2 x 7-semaines]	140 MILLES
[COURS-20]; STUDIO PROJET PROGICIEL C++, Java, UML 2.0	42 heures [2h x 3 x 7-semaines]	250 MILLES
[COURS-24]; INTRODUCTION AU DÉVELOPPEMENT D'APPLICATIONS WEB (AVEC PROJET)	42 heures [3h x 2 x 7-semaines]	105 MILLES
[COURS-25]; ADMINISTRATION SYSTÈME AVEC Debian Linux	18 heures [1.5h x 4 x 3-semaines]	90 MILLES
[COURS-26]; TRAVAIL DE RECHERCHE INDÉPENDANT SUPERVISÉ	42 heures [1.5h x 4 x 7-semaines]	200 MILLES
[COURS-27]; COURS DE DOCTRINE PENTECÔTISTE CHRÉTIENNE	2 heures [1h x 2 x 1-semaine]	20 MILLES
[COURS-28]; COURS DE SOFT-SKILLS	2 heures [1.5h x 2 x 1-semaine]	18 MILLES
AUTRES COURS EN FONCTION DU NIVEAU DU CANDIDAT ET À LA DEMANDE	XX heures	XXX MILLES

7.2 Auto-Emploi : Entrepreneuriat

Les technologies et applications LIBRES ET GRATUITES ("FOSS" en Anglais; pour "Free And Open Source Software") sont privilégiées dans l'apprentissage aux fins de permettre l'auto-emploi de l'apprenant beaucoup plus simple, et moins coûteux.

En effet, l'utilisation des technologies et / ou applications propriétaires peuvent être très onéreuses.

À la demande des apprenants, les promoteurs du centre de formation peuvent accompagner idéologiquement, et / ou matériellement les candidats qualifiés et compétents dans leur projet d'entrepreneuriat technologique de l'information et de la communication (TIC).

7.1 Technologies et Applications LIBRES ET GRATUITES ("FOSS")

Ce centre de formation met l'accent sur des cours en Informatique pratique et en Informatique appliquée.

Les technologies et applications LIBRES ET GRATUITES ("FOSS" en Anglais; pour "Free And Open Source Software") sont privilégiées dans l'apprentissage aux fins de réduire des coûts de formation et permettre à l'apprenant d'exercer ses compétences à moindre coût, au vue du retard technologique et économique du continent Africain.

1 accent particulier est mis sur la méthodologie, et non seulement l'application de la technologies; ceci facilite l'utilisation des compétences acquises dans différents projets avec des technologies et / ou applications différentes de celles utilisées dans ce centre de formation.

Par exemple : la transition du SGBD (Système de Gestion de Base de Données) "FOSS" **MySQL** au SGBD commercial **Oracle** ne serait pas 1 problème important.

8 COURS PROPOSÉS

1. [COURS-1] ; Anglais pour l'informatique.
2. [COURS-2] ; Allemand pour l'informatique.
3. [COURS-3] ; Mathématiques (algèbre linéaire, logique) pour l'informatique.
4. [COURS-4] ; Initiation à l'informatique avec le système d'exploitation "**LIBRE ET GRATUIT (FOSS)**" Debian Linux ([HTTPS://DEBIAN.ORG](https://DEBIAN.ORG)) (avec DES NOTIONS DE SÉCURITÉ DE L'INFORMATION, COURRIEL (email), YOUTUBE.COM, LICENCES et droits d'auteurs, ETC.).
5. [COURS-5] ; Installer le système d'exploitation Debian Linux.
6. [COURS-6] ; Informatique de Gestion; Installer et réutiliser le progiciel de gestion intégré (ERP en Anglais) YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 ([HTTPS://ZENODO.ORG/RECORD/8060217](https://ZENODO.ORG/RECORD/8060217)), PHPMYADMIN.
7. [COURS-7] ; Initiation à la programmation de sites web statiques grâce à GOOGLE SITES ([HTTPS://SITES.GOOGLE.COM](https://SITES.GOOGLE.COM)).
8. [COURS-8] ; Initiation à la réutilisation au système de gestion de base de données "**LIBRE ET GRATUIT (FOSS)**" MySQL ([HTTPS://MARIADB.COM](https://MARIADB.COM)) sous Debian Linux (Exemples avec PHPMYADMIN).
9. [COURS-9] ; Initiation à la rédaction de documents avec 1 équivalent de MS-OFFICE-WORD-POWERPOINT-EXCEL : LibreOffice ([HTTPS://WWW.LIBREOFFICE.ORG](https://WWW.LIBREOFFICE.ORG)) sous Debian Linux.
10. [COURS-10] ; Initiation à la manipulation et la réutilisation d'images prises par caméra sous Debian Linux; ENTRE AUTRES AVEC ImageMagick ([HTTPS://IMAGEMAGICK.ORG/](https://IMAGEMAGICK.ORG/)), et / ou Xfig.
11. [COURS-11] ; Initiation à la rédaction de documents (scientifiques) grâce à LaTeX ([HTTPS://WWW.LATEX-PROJECT.ORG](https://WWW.LATEX-PROJECT.ORG)) sous Debian Linux.
12. [COURS-12] ; CRÉER DES RÉSEAUX LAN avec Wifi .
13. [COURS-13] ; INTRODUCTION À L'ARCHITECTURE DES ORDINATEURS ("VON NEUMANN"; CISC; RISC).
14. [COURS-14] ; INTRODUCTION À LA PROGRAMMATION DES SCRIPTS (exemples avec sed², AWK³, Bash⁴).
15. [COURS-15] ; INTRODUCTION À LA PROGRAMMATION IMPÉRATIVE avec C / C++⁵ (exemples avec Valkyrie (VALGRIND)⁶, GDB⁷, Bash, Make⁸, et Git⁹).
16. [COURS-16] ; INTRODUCTION À LA PROGRAMMATION ORIENTÉE OBJET (exemples avec Git, Make, Findbugs, Ant¹⁰, JUnit¹¹, C++, et JAVA¹²).
17. [COURS-17] ; INTRODUCTION À LA PROGRAMMATION DES INTERFACES GRAPHIQUES AVEC Qt 5¹³.
18. [COURS-18] ; INTRODUCTION AU TEST ET À LA VÉRIFICATION DE PROGRAMMES INFORMATIQUES (exemples avec Ant, Findbugs, JUnit, Cobertura¹⁴, GDB, Gcov¹⁵, lcov¹⁶, Valkyrie (VALGRIND), YERITH_QVGE¹⁷).
20. [COURS-20] ; STUDIO PROJET DE DÉVELOPPEMENT SYSTÈME-LOGICIEL ORIENTÉ OBJET avec C++ ET / OU JAVA, UML 2.0.
21. [COURS-21] ; INTRODUCTION À LA CRÉATION DE COMPILATEURS * (FLEX, BISON).
22. [COURS-22] ; STRUCTURES DE DONNÉES (exemples : GRAPHES, AUTOMATES, MAP, ETC.).
23. [COURS-23] ; SOFTWARE VERIFICATION WITH PROGRAM ANALYSIS * (exemples : YERITH_QVGE, ETC.).
24. [COURS-24] ; INTRODUCTION AU DÉVELOPPEMENT D'APPLICATIONS WEB; cours comportant 1 projet (exemples : Ant, Selenium, HTML, CSS (Cascading Style Sheets), JSON, PHP (Personal Home Pages), MySQL, PHPMYADMIN, JSP (Java Server Pages)¹⁸, Apache Tomcat, GWT (Google Web Toolkit), ETC.).

2. <https://www.gnu.org/software/sed/>

3. <https://www.gnu.org/software/gawk/>

4. <https://www.gnu.org/software/bash/>

5. <https://www.en.wikipedia.org/wiki/C++>

6. https://www.github.com/yerithd/valkyrie_NON_OFFICIAL

7. <https://www.sourceware.org/gdb/>

8. <https://www.gnu.org/software/make/>

9. <https://www.git-scm.com>

10. <https://www.ant.apache.org>

11. <https://www.junit.org/junit5>

12. <https://www.ibm.com/topics/java>

13. <https://www.doc.qt.io/qt-5/index.html>

14. <https://cobertura.github.io/cobertura>

15. <https://>

16. <https://>

17. <https://www.github.com/yerithd/yr-db-runtime-verif>

18. <https://www>.

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25. [COURS-25] ; ADMINISTRATION SYSTÈME avec Debian Linux (exemples : SED, AWK, BASH, UFW, ETC.).
 26. [COURS-26] ; TRAVAIL DE RECHERCHE INDÉPENDANT SUPERVISÉ.
 27. [COURS-27] ; COURS DE DOCTRINE PENTECÔTISTE CHRÉTIENNE DE JEOVAH-NISSI (aussi dit JÉSUS-DE-NAZARETH).
 28. [COURS-28] ; COURS DE soft-skills (Rédiger son résumé. Comment faire 1 présentation 'SLIDES', etc.).

Tableau 2 – COURS ASSOCIÉS (en Section 8)

MÉTIER	COURS ASSOCIÉS	TOTAL
Développeur Web dynamique	[COURS-1], [COURS-4], [COURS-5], [COURS-7], [COURS-8], [COURS-12], [COURS-14], [COURS-15], [COURS-24], [COURS-25]	10
Administrateur De Base de données SQL	[COURS-1], [COURS-4], [COURS-5], [COURS-7], [COURS-8], [COURS-12], [COURS-14], [COURS-24], [COURS-25]	09
Administrateur Système	[COURS-1], [COURS-4], [COURS-5], [COURS-7], [COURS-8], [COURS-9], [COURS-10], [COURS-12], [COURS-14], [COURS-15], [COURS-24], [COURS-25]	12
Consultant en Progiciels de Gestion Intégré	[COURS-1], [COURS-3], [COURS-4], [COURS-5], [COURS-6], [COURS-8], [COURS-9], [COURS-11], [COURS-12], [COURS-14], [COURS-15], [COURS-24], [COURS-25]	13
Développeur D'applications Web	[COURS-1], [COURS-3], [COURS-4], [COURS-5], [COURS-7], [COURS-8], [COURS-9], [COURS-10], [COURS-12], [COURS-13], [COURS-14], [COURS-15], [COURS-16], [COURS-18], [COURS-22], [COURS-24], [COURS-25]	17
Développeur Progiciels, Rédacteur Technique (Latex)	[COURS-1], [COURS-3], [COURS-4], [COURS-5], [COURS-7], [COURS-8], [COURS-9], [COURS-10], [COURS-11], [COURS-12], [COURS-13], [COURS-14], [COURS-15], [COURS-16], [COURS-17], [COURS-18], [COURS-20], [COURS-22], [COURS-23], [COURS-24], [COURS-25]	21
Développeur – Chercheur (MASTER) en Ingénierie Informatique	[COURS-1], [COURS-3], [COURS-4], [COURS-5], [COURS-7], [COURS-8], [COURS-9], [COURS-10], [COURS-11], [COURS-12], [COURS-13], [COURS-14], [COURS-15], [COURS-16], [COURS-17], [COURS-18], [COURS-20], [COURS-22], [COURS-23], [COURS-24], [COURS-25], [COURS-26], [COURS-27]	23
Développeur – Chercheur (DOCTEUR) en Ingénierie Informatique	[COURS-1], [COURS-3], [COURS-4], [COURS-5], [COURS-7], [COURS-8], [COURS-9], [COURS-10], [COURS-11], [COURS-12], [COURS-13], [COURS-14], [COURS-15], [COURS-16], [COURS-17], [COURS-18], [COURS-20], [COURS-21], [COURS-22], [COURS-23], [COURS-24], [COURS-25], [COURS-26], [COURS-27]	24

Le Tableau 2 illustre pour chaque métier listé à la section 9 des cours qui permettraient 1 APPROFONDISSEMENT ou 1 accès plus facile à des formations et / ou qualifications académiques et / ou professionnelles.

POSSIBLES EMPLOIS et MÉTIERS

■ **Développeur Web dynamique :**

1. Sociétés commerciales et / ou administrations publiques pour créer, tester, installer, et / ou maintenir des sites web en réseau local pour la comptabilité matière.
2. Magasin de ventes en ligne pour entretenir le site web.

■ **Administrateur De Base de données SQL :**

1. Employé dans 1 start-up et /ou PME pour assurer 1 maintenance du réseau informatique local; créer 1 ou des sites web; exécuter des tâches sur des bases de données SQL, avec pour commanditaire des développeurs d'applications web; etc.

■ **Administrateur Système :**

1. Employé dans 1 start-up et /ou PME, sous la direction d'1 ingénieur de travaux de grade au minimum en équivalence; Pour sélectionner, tester, installer, maintenir des applications en réseau local et / ou réseau WAN ("Wide Area Network").

■ **Consultant en Progiciels de Gestion Intégré :**

1. Sociétés commerciales et / ou administrations publiques pour sélectionner, installer, maintenir des applications de gestion managériale.
2. Entreprendre dans des solutions de gestion commerciale spécialisées pour start-up, et / ou Petites et Moyennes Entreprises (PME).

■ **Développeur D'applications Web :**

1. Sociétés commerciales et / ou administrations publiques pour créer, tester, installer, et / ou maintenir des applications web en réseau local pour la comptabilité matière.

2. Magasin de ventes en ligne pour entretenir le site web.

■ **Développeur Progiciels, aussi Rédacteur Technique (Latex) :**

1. Sociétés commerciales et / ou administrations publiques pour créer, tester, installer, et / ou maintenir des applications web, et /ou lourdes graphiques, en réseau local; Sous la supervision d'1 informaticien d'1 grade minimum de "MASTER of Science" EN équivalence académique.
2. Toute organisation entrepreneuriale peut bénéficier de ses compétences pour rédiger des documents scientifiques et / ou technique : EXEMPLE : guide de l'utilisateur, etc..

■ **Développeur – Chercheur (MASTER) en Ingénierie Informatique :**

1. Sociétés commerciales et / ou administrations publiques pour créer, tester, installer, et / ou maintenir des applications web, et /ou lourdes graphiques.

■ **Développeur – Chercheur (DOCTEUR) en Ingénierie Informatique :**

1. Sociétés commerciales et / ou administrations publiques pour : Former des jeunes informaticiens, créer des applications nouvelles et innovantes aussi bien dans l'application que dans les technologies ré-utilisées.
2. Entreprendre dans des solutions spécialisées nouvelles et innovantes aussi bien dans l'application que dans les technologies ré-utilisées .

9 QUALIFICATIONS MÉTIERS

9.1 QUALIFICATIONS MÉTIERS et COURS ASSOCIÉS DU CENTRE DE FORMATION

Les cours proposés (Section 8) par ce centre de formations qualifiantes en Informatique permettraient 1 **APPROFONDISSEMENT** ou 1 **accès plus facile aux formations pour des professions suivantes** :

1. Développeur Web dynamique (HTML, CSS (Cascading Style Sheets), PHP, MySQL, JavaScript, JSON)
2. Administrateur De Base de données SQL
3. Administrateur Système (Debian Linux, MS-WINDOWS, Apple)
4. Consultant en Progiciels de Gestion Intégré (PGI; ERP en Anglais)
5. Développeur D'applications Web (HTML, CSS (Cascading Style Sheets), PHP, Apache Tomcat, Java Servlets (JSP inclus), Google Web Toolkit (GWT))
6. Développeur Progiciels (Qt, C++, Java, C#); Rédacteur Technique
7. Développeur – Chercheur (MASTER) en Informatique
8. Développeur – Chercheur (DOCTEUR) en Informatique.

BIOGRAPHIE DU PROMOTEUR ET ENSEIGNANT PRINCIPAL

Promoteur et Enseignant "Xavier Noubissi Noundou (Prof. Dr.)"

Figure 1 – Portrait de "Xavier Noubissi Noundou (Prof. Dr.)".

Prof. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou est chrétien évangélique "Born-Again (né-de-nouveau)", camerounais, et né le 16 septembre 1983 à Douala dans la région du littoral au Cameroun.

Prof. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou a 1 grade académique et professionnel de "**Diplom-Informatiker**" provenant de l'**université de Brême en République Fédérale d'Allemagne (RFA)**, depuis le 25 Mai 2007.

Prof. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou a 1 grade académique et professionnel de "**Docteur en Ingénierie**" : "**Doctor of Engineering (Ph.D.)**", provenant de l'**Université de Waterloo (Waterloo, Ontario, Canada)**, depuis le 20 Décembre 2011!

Sa dissertation est : "**Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software**".

Prof. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou a des contributions en recherches et développements, académiques et en ingénierie professionnelle comme suit :

1. 'Statistical test case generation for reactive systems' **RTT-MBT**; pour la start-up **VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTER-**

NATIONAL GmbH (<https://www.verified.de>) de l'Université de Brême en Allemagne fédérale.

2. Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) Software System 'YERITH-ERP-3.0' :

- 1) code source en C++ :
 - a. YERITH-ERP-9.0 : <https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0>
 - b. YERITH-ERP-9.0 SYSTEM DAEMON : <https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon>

- 2) publications en continue : <https://zenodo.org/record/8205911>

3. Dynamic Program Analysis Generator 'YERITH_QVGE'

- 1) code source en C++ :
 - https://www.github.com/yerithd/yr_db_runtime_verif
 - https://www.github.com/yerithd/yr_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS
 - https://www.github.com/yerithd/yr_db_runtime_verif_lang
 - <https://www.github.com/yerithd/yr-db-runtime-verif>

- 2) document scientifique et / ou technique : <https://zenodo.org/record/8381187>

EXPERTISES :

Prof. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou possède des expertises et compétences suivantes :

- Gestion des projets et des Start-up technologiques.
- Édition d'ouvrages techniques et scientifiques.
- Informatique de Gestion
 1. Gestion de la Stratégie de L'information (flux des données, et matériels informatique)
 2. Implémentation du Progiciel de Gestion Intégré **YERITH-PGI-9.0**.
- Conception de Progiciels
 - Assurance Qualité du Progiciel (JUnit, FINDBUGS, CPPCHECK, ETC.)
 - Construction du Progiciel (Qt 5, C++, MySQL, ETC.)

1 Introduction

Figure 1 – ILLUSTRATION d'1 "routeur" internet

Le monde est essentiellement digital dans ces temps modernes. La digitalisation permet la facilitation des conditions de vies.

La présentation des données et informations au grand public par voie digitale la mieux appropriée par ces temps modernes est, et reste à ce moment, 1 site internet (WWW-WEB).

Ce cours vise à former des étudiants et / ou élèves à la conception, organisation, implémentation, mise en place et maintenance de sites et applications internet-Web; et ceci avec les toutes dernières technologies stables et viables pour 1 usage concurrentiel et long.

2 Enseignant

- Prof. Dr. Xavier Noundou.

3 Documentation Privilégiée Du Cours

1. **CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM**,¹, par moi : Résumé, chapitre 1, chapitre 2, et chapitre 3.
2. **DYNAMIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR PHP IN QUERCUS**², par moi : chapitre 1, 2, 5, and Appendix A2.
3. **SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH-ERP-3.0**³, by ME : Tableau 1.1 en 'Sous-section 1.1.2'; chapitre 2 (2 pages); chapitre 4 (2 pages).
4. **PHP.NET** (<https://www.php.net>)
5. **TOMCAT.APACHE.ORG** (<https://tomcat.apache.org>)

4 Coût Du Cours

- **105 MILLES FRANCS**; à raison de 2 500 francs l'heure de cours distillé.

5 Durée et Organisation Du Cours

1 heure (1h) de cours représente 45 minutes de délibérés et 15 minutes de pause.

5.1 Durée du Cours

- 42 heures [3h x 2 x 7-semaines] :

42 heures réparties en 3 heures 2 fois la semaine, et ce pendant 7 semaines.

5.2 Organisation des cours

Chaque semaine de cours :

- 30 minutes théoriques la semaine
- 05 heures et 30 minutes au laboratoire d'exercices pratiques.

Des détails sur les examens pratiques et exercices sont encore à venir.

6 Contenu Du Cours

1. **Bref historique de l'internet.**
2. **Couches du protocole de communication Internet (OSI, pas exhaustif), outils et technologies pare-feux ('firewall' en Anglais), 'PING', 'WHOIS', etc.**
3. **Architecture d'1 site web, architecture d'1 application web (n-tiers).**
4. **Outils d'interactions avec 1 application-site-web;** technologies 'navigateur', 'CACHE du navigateur', 'URL (Universal Resource Locator)', 'HTML', 'DTD (Document Type Definition)', 'CSS', 'javascript', etc.
5. **'GIMP', 'IMAGEMAGICK', Git⁴, Ant, Maven, etc.**
6. **LE LANGAGE DE PROGRAMMATION pour scripts PHP (Personal Home Pages), etc.**
7. **LE LANGAGE DE PROGRAMMATION interprété JAVA, la technologie JAVA-servlet, des pages JSP (Java Server Pages), serveur d'applications Apache-Tomcat, etc.**
8. **FICHIERS DE CONFIGURATIONS, 'json files', '.properties files', 'GWT (Google Web Toolkit)', etc.**
9. **Hébergements de sites et d'applications web, 'SSH (SSL-Secure Socket Layer)'.**
10. **Outils de débogage d'1 application-site-web;** technologies incluses dans 1 navigateur, 'SELENIUM', fichiers 'log' dans 'Apache Tomcat', Java debugger (JDB), etc.
11. Pour le projet, des notions minimalistes suivantes seront abordées : SÉCURITÉ DES APPLICATIONS WEB, GESTION DES BASES DE DONNÉES **MYSQL**.

1. <https://zenodo.org/record/8051293>
2. <https://zenodo.org/record/8051621>
3. <https://zenodo.org/records/10086413>
4. <https://git-scm.com>